

**TEMPERATURE OF A
“TEMPERATE” ALPINE
GLACIER: GLACIER DE
TSANFLEURON,
SWITZERLAND.**

Owain David Russell Bayley

PhD Thesis
Aberystwyth University

September 2007

Summary of thesis

Candidate's surname: BAYLEY
Candidate's forenames: OWAIN DAVID RUSSELL
Candidate for the Degree of: PhD
Institute at which study pursued: ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY

Full title of thesis: TEMPERATURE OF A “TEMPERATE” ALPINE GLACIER:
GLACIER DE TSANFLEURON, SWITZERLAND.

SUMMARY

Snow pack and ice temperatures in boreholes to the glacier bed were measured using thermistors (accuracy of ± 0.04 °C), at three sites on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland, a small temperate glacier, with an extensively karstified limestone bed. Additionally, automated weather stations were used to record continually basic meteorological variables (including snow depth). These were periodically supplemented by eddy correlation measurements of turbulent fluxes, recorded to characterize the glacier surface energy budget. Data collection occurred over a $\sim 2\frac{3}{4}$ year period between April 2004 and January 2007.

Snow had an insulating effect on the underlying ice surface, reducing heat loss from the ice. Maximum snow depth and distribution was spatially uniform, with temperatures ranging from ~ -19 to 0 °C. Depths of penetration of the winter cold wave into near-surface ice varied between 13.2 and 15.1 m, and the coldest recorded ice temperatures were winter ice surface minima of ~ -4.5 °C. The winter cold wave was eliminated during the ablation season at two of the three sites, with temperatures mostly reaching melting point. However, cold ice was widespread to depth at one site and failed to be eliminated. Thus, Tsanfleuron violates the definitions of a temperate glacier and is technically polythermal, at least englacially.

Crevasses are identified as heat sources near the ice surface and sinks at depth, while water and air flow (“cave breathing”) between the glacier bed and the subglacial karst system are identified as two of the main basal heat fluxes. Differential ablation rates measured at similar altitudes are controlled by ice surface morphology, specifically crevassing, and slush flows.

Numerical modelling allowed reconstruction of missing data and non measured meteorological parameters. These data, in conjunction with derived snow and glacier ice density, thermal conductivity and diffusivity, were used to drive a one-dimensional point surface energy balance model, predicting surface lowering, and snow and ice temperatures. The impacts on glacier temperature and mass balance of air temperature and precipitation changes under global warming scenarios are assessed.

KEY WORDS: Temperate ice, Temperature, Borehole, Snow pack, Surface energy balance, Ablation, Crevasse, Subglacial karst

Table of contents

Summary	i
Table of contents	ii
List of figures	vii
List of tables	xvii
List of symbols	xix
Acknowledgements	xxv
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LIERATURE REVIEW	1
1.1 Introduction	1
Why study the temperatures of a temperate alpine glacier?	1
Why Glacier de Tsanfleuron?	3
Thesis aims	4
Key work to be conducted in this thesis and why?	5
1.2 Temperate glacier ice	7
1.3 Importance of a detailed characterisation of temperate glacier temperatures	9
1.4 Applications of temperate ice temperature research	15
1.5 Temperate glacier temperature profiles	15
1.5.1 Previous studies of temperate glacier temperatures	18
1.5.2 Melting point temperature of temperate ice	20
1.6 Physical properties of snow and ice	22
1.6.1 Density	22
1.6.2 Thermal conductivity	22
1.6.3 Thermal diffusivity	24
1.7 Processes controlling snow and ice temperature profiles	24
1.7.1 Heat transfer between the glacier surface and the atmosphere	24
1.7.2 Heat transfer processes through the snow	24
1.7.3 Heat transfer processes through ice	25
1.8 Surface heat fluxes	25
1.8.1 Net radiation	27
1.8.2 Turbulent heat fluxes	35
1.8.3 Latent heat from refreezing of melt water	44
1.8.4 Precipitation heat supply	46
1.8.5 Conductive heat flux into the ice	47
1.9 Englacial heat fluxes	48
1.9.1 Firn compaction	48
1.9.2 Crevasses as heat sources and sinks	48
1.9.3 Deformation driven strain heating	49
1.10 Basal heat fluxes	52
1.10.1 Water flow and refreezing at the grain scale at boundaries between the crystals and at the macro scale within the ice and at the bed.....	52
1.10.2 Geothermal heat flux	53
1.10.3 Friction at the bed due to sliding	54
1.10.4 Air flow at the glacier bed	55
1.11 Modelling glacier surface energy balance and melt	55
1.11.1 Degree day methods	55

1.11.2	Surface energy balance methods	56
1.12	Theoretical modelling of ice temperatures in the vertical dimension	57
1.12.1	Historical overview and measured temperate ice profiles	57
1.12.2	Analytical solution to the glacier ice temperature equation (Robin 1955)	60
1.12.3	Extensions to the simple Robin (1955) analytical solution	63
1.13	Subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity	65
1.13.1	Water pressure	65
1.13.2	Electrical Conductivity	66
1.14	Research objectives	67
1.15	Thesis outline... ..	68
CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS		70
2.1	Glacier de Tsanfleuron	70
2.2	Meteorology and snow pack measurements	75
2.2.1	Automated weather stations (AWS) on the glacier surface	75
2.2.2	Field meteorological observations	86
2.2.3	Snow pack measurements.....	86
2.3	Borehole measurements	89
2.3.1	Hot water drilling	89
2.3.2	Borehole classification	93
2.3.3	Borehole instrumentation	94
	Temperature.....	94
	Water pressure	116
	Electrical conductivity	118
2.3.4	Differential GPS	121
2.3.5	Inclinometry	122
2.3.6	Ice thickness and ablation measurements	123
2.4	Laboratory measurements of ice core density	123
CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I: BOUNDARY LAYER METEOROLOGY AND SNOW PACK CONDITIONS		126
3.1	Introduction	126
3.2	Meteorology and glacier surface energy balance	126
3.2.1	Basic meteorological time series data	126
	Summary	142
3.2.2	Eddy correlation and four component radiation measurements.....	142
3.2.3	Surface energy balance	149
	Summary	151
3.3	Snow pack	151
3.3.1	Snow depth	151
	Summary	158
3.3.2	Snow density and stratigraphy	159
	Summary	166
3.3.3	Snow pack temperatures	166
	Temperature time series	167
	Summary	179
	Temperature profiles	180
	Summary	186

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II: ENGLACIAL AND BASAL CONDITIONS	190
4.1 Glacier ice	190
4.1.1 Ice thickness	190
4.1.2 Ice temperature	194
Temperature time series	195
Summary	209
Temperature profiles	211
Summary	233
4.1.3 Ice core density	233
4.1.4 Repeat borehole inclinometry (ice deformation)	235
4.2 Subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity (to aid interpretation of temperature data)	236
4.2.1 Water pressure time series	236
4.2.2 Electrical conductivity time series	239
Summary	241
 CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I: METEOROLOGY, SNOW PACK AND NEAR-SURFACE ICE TEMPERATURES	 243
5.1 Introduction	243
5.2 Meteorology and surface energy balance	243
5.2.1 Meteorology	244
5.2.3 Surface energy balance	251
Summary	252
5.3 Snow pack temperatures	253
5.3.1 Near-surface snow temperatures	254
5.3.2 Snow temperatures at depth within the snow pack	256
5.3.3 Temperature changes and snow pack processes as the snow pack becomes isothermal	258
Summary	262
5.4 Near-surface ice temperatures	263
5.4.1 Ice temperatures	263
Summary	272
5.5 The influence of the snow cover over near-surface ice temperatures	274
5.5.1 Seasonal “winter” snow pack effects	274
5.5.2 Transient “summer” snowfall effects	275
5.5.3 Thermal conductivity of snow	276
5.5.4 Internal snow pack energy	283
Summary	286
5.6 The influence of fractures and crevasses on ice temperatures	287
5.6.1 Crevasse temperatures and heat transfer processes	288
5.6.2 Crevasses as heat sinks	290
5.6.3 Crevasses as heat sources	291
Summary	293
5.7 Differential across-glacier ice surface ablation	294
5.7.1 Across glacier ice surface ablation variation	295
5.7.2 Controlling processes	296
5.7.3 Glacier surface morphological control	298
5.7.4 Slush flows	299

	Summary	303
5.8	Chapter summary	303

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II: GLACIER THERMAL PROPERTIES, ENGLACIAL AND BASAL HEAT SOURCES, SINKS AND ENERGY FLUXES.....

		306
6.1	Introduction	306
6.2	Winter cold wave	306
	6.2.1 Thermal conductivity of glacier ice	307
	6.2.2 Conductive heat flux through the surface glacier ice	308
	6.2.3 Initiation of the winter cold wave	312
	6.2.4 Elimination of the winter cold wave	313
	6.2.5 Depths of penetration of the winter cold wave	317
	Summary	318
6.3	Englacial temperatures, cold ice, heat sources and sinks	319
	6.3.1 Englacial ice temperatures	319
	Englacial cold ice	323
	6.3.2 Englacial heat sources	326
	Deformation-induced strain heating	326
	Englacial water flow and latent heat release on refreezing ...	327
	6.3.3 Englacial heat sinks	328
	Wedges of advected cold ice	328
	Summary	330
6.4	Basal temperatures, heat sources and sinks	330
	6.4.1 Basal ice temperatures	331
	6.4.2 Basal heat sources	335
	Geothermal heat flux	335
	Frictional heat flux at the bed due to sliding	335
	Water flow at the bed	335
	Air flow at the bed between the subglacial karst and the subglacial hydrological system	338
	6.4.3 Basal heat sinks	342
	Summary	343
6.5	Chapter summary	344

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING: ENERGY BALANCE AND GLACIER TEMPERATURES

		347
7.1	Introduction	347
7.2	Quality control and infilling of missing data in recorded meteorological time series	349
7.3	Derivation of non recorded variables	351
	7.3.1 Reconstruction of solid precipitation from snow depth Measurements	351
	7.3.2 Reconstruction of short wave incoming radiation (SW↓)	354
	7.3.3 Reconstruction of long wave incoming radiation (LW ↓)	357
7.4	Characterisation of the full surface energy balance for the two year meteorological study period	359
	7.4.1 Turbulent heat flux determination	359
	7.4.2 Modelling long wave radiation emission (LW ↑)	361

7.4.3	Modelling short wave radiation emission (SW ↑)	362
7.4.4	Results	362
7.4.5	Glacier surface energy balance discussion	367
	Summary	369
7.5	Modelling snow pack evolution and temperatures	370
7.5.1	Model description	370
7.5.2	Results	371
	Summary	375
7.6	Modelling ice surface ablation and glacier ice temperatures	376
7.6.1	Model description	376
7.6.2	Results	381
7.6.3	Discussion	386
7.6.4	Investigation of the effects of slush flows over ice surface ablation	388
	Summary	389
7.7	Modelling snow and ice temperature change under global warming best estimates	390
7.7.1	Increasing air temperature scenarios	391
7.7.2	Increasing solid (winter) precipitation scenarios	393
7.7.3	Simultaneous increasing air temperature and solid (winter) precipitation scenarios	395
	Summary	397
7.8	Chapter summary	398
CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS		400
8.1	Introduction	400
	What did this thesis set out to achieve?	400
	How well were the thesis objectives met?	401
8.2	Key thesis findings and implications	405
	Implications	408
	The wider significance of this work	410
8.3	Evaluation of methods of investigation	414
8.3.1	Temperature measurement in hot water drilled boreholes and the snow pack	414
8.3.2	Snow pack investigations	415
8.3.3	AWS data collection over the glacier surface	416
8.3.4	Water pressure and electrical conductivity	417
8.3.5	Energy balance and glacier temperature modelling	417
8.4	Recommendations for further work	418
8.4.1	Temperature measurement	418
8.4.2	Snow pack investigations	419
8.4.3	AWS data collection over the glacier surface	419
8.4.4	Water pressure and electrical conductivity	420
8.4.5	Numerical modelling	420
APPENDIX		422
REFERENCES		428

List of Figures

CHAPTER 1		Page
1.1	Variation of flow law parameter, A , with temperature, plotted from the data presented by Paterson (1994 p97).	11
1.2	Calculated seasonal variations in firn temperature in central Greenland. (Paterson, 1994, p208).	17
1.3	Temperature profile from the Athabasca glacier, Canada. (Paterson, 1971).	19
1.4	Schematic diagram of energy exchanges at the glacier surface. Re-drawn and modified from Van der Veen (1999).	27
1.5	Heat produced by strain induced ice deformation and the heat required to maintain ice at pressure melting point at the Athabasca Glacier. (Paterson, 1971).	52
CHAPTER 2		
2.1	Map of Glacier de Tsanfleuron and inset location in Switzerland.	71
2.2	Borehole and meteorological station locations.	71
2.3	Easterly component of the surface velocity field during (a) summer 2002 and (b) winter 2003 reproduced from Chandler (2005).	74
2.4	Basic meteorological sensors (a) RM Young 05103 wind monitor. (b) NR Lite net radiometer. (c) SR50 sonic ranging sensor. (d) MP100A temperature and relative humidity probe (in radiation shield). (e) HPF01 heat flux plate.	79
2.5	Schematic diagram of basic meteorological station as deployed on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, February 2005.	81
2.6	Eddy correlation and four component radiation sensors (a) CSAT 3 sonic anemometer (front) and KH20 krypton hygrometer (background). (b) CNR1 net radiometer.	84
2.7	Schematic diagram of eddy correlation and four component radiation meteorological station.	85
2.8	Snow depth measurements via the probe technique.	87
2.9	Snow pack analysis via snow pits (a) ~ 4 m snow pit with access steps, April 2006. (b) Collecting snow samples for density measurement at the meteorological station site, January 2006. (c) Weighing of snow density cutter and snow sample allowing density determination. (d) Temperature measurement with stainless steel thermometer in snow pit wall.	89

2.10	Hot water drilling (a) HDS1000BE drilling setup, April 2004. (b) Hydrological engineering a water supply to be pumped to the supply reservoir, August 2006.	92
2.11	Relationship between resistance and temperature for Fenwal UNICURVE 192 – 502 LET – A01 thermistors, plotted from figures produced by Fenwal Inc.	98
2.12	Fenwal UNICURVE thermistor probe deployed in this study.	100
2.13	Thermistor string deployment on Tsanfleuron (a) Wooden pole used to anchor the thermistor string at the top of a borehole. (b) Installation of crevasse thermistor string.	104
2.14	Thermistor wiring to CR-10(X) loggers and AM16X32 Multiplexers (a) Wiring diagram. (b) Field deployment in Campbell Scientific data logger enclosure.	106
2.15	Temperature measured during snow calibration for three thermistors, indicating the magnitude of the errors associated with the data logger resistance measurement and data storage resolutions.	109
2.16	Diagrammatical representation of error as a result of the resolution of the data logger resistance measurements used to measure temperature.	109
2.17	Mounting of snow pack thermistors, position of data logger mounting pole relative to the borehole, and position of excess thermistor cable at the end of the summer (North site).	112
2.18	Snow pack calibration temperatures during stable period before adjustment to applied mean.	114
2.19	Snow pack calibration temperatures during stable period after adjustment to mean applied.	114
2.20	Temperature recorded by thermistor 16.0a plotted against that recorded by thermistor 16.0c, located at the same depth in BH04-01 over a one year period.	116
2.21	Water pressure sensors (a) Honeywell 24PCG data logger controlled sensor. (b) TRAFAG self-logging sensor.	118
2.22	Electrical conductivity probe manufactured from 230 V light fitting deployed at Tsanfleuron.	120
2.23	Cable following reaming tip used to re-drill closed boreholes.	123
2.24	Ice core density measurements (a) Squaring off ice core ends. (b) Length measurements. (c) Diameter measurements. (d) Mass determination.	125

CHAPTER 3

- 3.1 Daily mean (a) air temperature and (b) relative humidity recorded at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007 at a heights of ~3 m and ~ 0.4 m above the glacier surface. 129
- 3.2 Daily mean (a) wind speed at a height of ~3 m and ~0.4 m above the surface (b) and net radiation recorded at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007 at a height of ~ 2 m above the glacier surface. 131
- 3.3 Wind rose direction plot for data recorded at a height of ~3 m above the surface between February 2005 and February 2007 (plot radius scaled to the modal wind direction, to which the other directional segments are relatively represented). 132
- 3.4 Heat flux from the base of the snow pack into the glacier ice surface (positive values indicate energy flow into the ice) recorded between January 2006 and July 2006. 133
- 3.5 Monthly maxima, mean and minima (a) air temperature, (b) relative humidity, (c) wind speed and (d) net radiation. 134
- 3.6 Two hour resolution air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period in the winter snow accumulation period between JD 334 (30th November) and JD 359 (25th December) 2005. 138
- 3.7 Two hour resolution air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period in the spring – early summer snow ablation period between JD 174 (23rd June) and JD199 (18th July) 2005. 139
- 3.8 Two hour resolution air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and distance from SR50 to glacier surface during a 25 day period in the summer ice ablation period between JD 237 (25th August) and JD262 (20th September) 2005 (the horizontal dashed line on distance to surface plot, denotes the position of the glacier surface at beginning of illustrated period). 140
- 3.9 Two hour resolution air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period including a summer snow fall period between JD 209 (28th July) and JD234 (22nd August) 2006. 141
- 3.10 Four components of radiation and net radiation during a 14 day period between day 220 and day 34 (2006) recorded individually using the two CM3 pyranometers and the two CG3 pyrgeometers on the CNR1 Net Radiometer. 145
- 3.11 Four components of radiation and net radiation during a 12 day period between day 30 and day 42 (2007) recorded individually using the two

	CM3 pyranometers and the two CG3 pyrgeometers on the CNR1 Net Radiometer.	
3.12	Sensible heat flux measured over the glacier surface using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments between (a) day 220 to 234 (2006) and (b) day 30 to 42 (2007).	147
3.13	Latent heat flux measured over the glacier surface using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments between (a) day 220 to 234 (2006) and (b) day 30 to 42 (2007).	148
3.14	Energy balance at the glacier surface over a 24 hour period on (a) day 230 (2006) and (b) day 35 (2007) derived from the four individual radiation components (recorded by the CNR1 net radiometer) and measurements of sensible and latent heat flux (recorded using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments).	150
3.15	(a) Snow depth recorded automatically by the SR50 (with periodic manually measured snow depths in red) and (b) daily mean snow surface elevation change at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007.	154
3.16	Route of the January 2005 and January 2006 snow depth transects, at ~30 m separation in undisturbed snow to the side of glacier pistes and passing through BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 at 10 m separation.	157
3.17	Histograms of (a) January 2006 and (b) January 2007 snow depths recorded on the ~30 and 10 m transects.	158
3.18	Snow density profiles measured using samples extracted from the North facing wall of snow pits dug at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007 (and April 2005 at BH04-01).	162
3.19	Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 in (a) the 2004 / 05 winter between November and May and (b) the 2005 / 06 winter between November and May.	172
3.20	Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-06 in (a) the 2004 / 05 winter between November and January and (b) the 2005 / 06 winter between November and June.	173
3.21	Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH05-07 in the 2005 / 06 winter between November and February.	175

3.22	Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 in the accumulation period of the 2004 / 05 winter between November and February.	176
3.23	Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 during April and May in the ablation period of the 2004 / 05 winter and the (b) 2005 / 06 winter.	178
3.24	Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-06 between April and June in the ablation period of the 2005 / 06 winter.	180
3.25	Bi-monthly average snow pack temperature profiles derived from thermistor data collected during the 2004 / 05 winter at (a) BH04-01 and (b) BH04-06.	182
3.26	Bi-monthly average snow pack temperature profiles derived from thermistor data collected during the 2005 / 06 winter at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06, (c) BH05-07 and (d) BH05-07 re-plotted with suspect thermistors removed.	184
3.27	Snow pack temperature profiles over 5 day periods during the “ripening” of the snow pack, at the end of the 2004 / 05 winter at (a) BH04-01 and at the end of the 2005 / 06 winter at (b) BH04-01 and (c) BH040-06.	187
3.28	Temperature profiles recorded manually using a stem thermometer in the North facing wall of snow pits dug at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007.	189

CHAPTER 4

4.1	Processed 50 MHz radar transect across glacier de Tsanfleuron conducted in April 2004 presented as instantaneous frequency, (with boreholes 04-01, 05-07 and 04-06 superimposed at their respective locations).	191
4.2	Ice and snow surface elevation above the glacier bed for the duration of the study period between May 2004 and January 2007 at (a) BH04-01 and (b) BH04-06, determined from borehole drilling to the bed, melt-out of thermistor strings and data logger mounting poles and SR50 snow depth measurements, validated with periodic manual snow depth and ice surface location measurements.	193
4.3	Ice and snow surface elevation above the glacier bed for the duration of the study period between May 2004 and January 2007 at BH05-07, determined from borehole drilling to the bed, melt-out of thermistor strings and data logger mounting poles and SR50 snow depth measurements, validated with periodic manual snow depth and ice surface location measurements.	194
4.4	Temperature time series for thermistor 14.0a (a) as recorded by the data logger and (b) with transient effects due to the borehole BH04-01 being	196

	open and the thermistor recording an air rather than ice temperature removed.	
4.5	Temperature time series recorded by near-surface, englacial and basal thermistors at the North site in BH04-01 and BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01) from September 2004 to October 2006.	200
4.6	Temperature time series recorded by near-surface and basal thermistors at the South site in BH04-06 from August 2004 to January 2007.	201
4.7	Temperature time series recorded by near-surface, englacial and basal thermistors at the Central site in BH05-07 from August 2005 to January 2007.	202
4.8	Thermistor time series during the period of initial winter cooling of the near-surface ice, between the end of November 2004 and beginning of February 2005 from (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06).	204
4.9	Thermistor time series during the period of elimination of the winter cold wave in spring and summer of the near-surface ice, (a) at the North site during April and May 2005 in BH04-01 and (b) at the South site between April and October 2006 in BH04-06.	206
4.10	Temperature time series of thermistors at all heights above the bed at the South site in BH04-06 between mid May and late July 2006 during the occurrence of a large thermal disturbance originating at the glacier bed and propagating up the borehole.	208
4.11	Temperature time series recorded by thermistors in a crevasse directly adjacent to BH05-07 at the Central site from August 2005 to January 2007.	210
4.12	Ice melting temperatures modelled from basic theory (Paterson, 1994) using both ice thickness and three solute concentrations from ice cores recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron assigned to different ice layers in ice flow modelling (Hubbard <i>et al.</i> , 2003) and average solute concentrations.	212
4.13	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2004 and August 2005 at BH04-01 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near- surface ice and snow pack thermistors.	215
4.14	Monthly average borehole temperatures between September 2005 and August 2006 at BH04-01 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors.	216
4.15	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2004 and February 2005 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors.	219

4.16	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2005 and August 2006 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors.	220
4.17	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2006 and February 2007 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice thermistors.	221
4.18	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2005 and February 2006 at BH05-07 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface snow and ice thermistors.	223
4.19	Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2006 and January 2007 at BH05-07 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice thermistors.	224
4.20	Monthly average crevasse temperature profiles between (a) August 2005 and February 2006 and (b) August 2006 and January 2007.	226
4.21	Penetration of the 2004 / 05 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the winter cooling period at (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06).	228
4.22	Penetration of the 2005 / 06 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the winter cooling period at (a) the North site (BH04-01), (b) the South site BH04-06 and (c) the Central site BH05-07.	229
4.23	Elimination of the 2004 / 05 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the spring warming period at the North site (BH04-01).	231
4.24	Elimination of the 2005 / 06 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the spring warming period at (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06).	232
4.25	Schematic representation of how the longest two Tsanfleuron cores, core 97-1 recovered from the accumulation area near the present location of BH04-01 and core 96-5 recovered from the glacier snout can be combined to provide a core sequence from the glacier surface to the bed, for use in laboratory characterisation of ice density.	234
4.26	Ice density profiles for (a) core 97-1 and (b) 96-5.	235
4.27	Borehole deformation induced strain rate variation with height above the glacier bed in a down glacier and an across glacier direction derived from repeat inclinometry at the South site, near the location of BH04-06.	236
4.28	Water pressure time series in (a) BH05-13 (~ 50 m down glacier from	238

	BH05-07) and (b) at the Central site (BH05-07) from August 2005 to August 2006 and January 2007 respectively.	
4.29	Water pressure time series at the South site in BH05-12 (adjacent to BH04-06) from October 2005 to July 2006, adjusted for atmospheric pressure and sensor location in the borehole.	239
4.30	Electrical conductivity time series in (a) BH05-06 at the North site (adjacent to BH04-01) from September 2005 to September 2006 and (b) BH05-10 at the South site (adjacent to BH04-06) from October 2005 to January 2007.	241
4.31	Electrical conductivity time series at the Central site in BH05-07 from August 2005 to January 2007.	242
CHAPTER 5		
5.1	Plot of wind speed against wind direction for the 30 minute averages recorded at Tsanfleuron.	247
5.2	Hemispherical photograph captured using a 180 ° “fish eye” lens indicating sky view as seen by radiometers at the meteorological station deployed on Tsanfleuron in August 2006.	248
5.3	Contour plots of daily snow temperatures, bounded by snow depth at all three borehole locations over the period of data collection February 2004 to February 2007.	254
5.4	Maximum winter thermal disturbance due to cooling, experienced by near-surface thermistors at each depth below the ice surface in BH04-01 and BH04-06.	266
5.5	Thermistor time series showing diurnal temperature cycles under snow free conditions at 1.05 and 5.05 m below the ice surface in BH04-06 in September 2005, also displayed air temperature and net radiation for the same period.	272
5.6	Diagrammatical representation of the phase lag and amplitude attenuation methods of thermal conductivity determination from recorded temperature cycles.	278
5.7	Tsanfleuron snow pack thermal conductivity profile determined from attenuation of diurnal anthropogenically derived temperature cycles at BH04-01 and BH04-06, presented with Sturm <i>et al.</i> (1997)’s published snow thermal conductivity range.	282
5.8	Contour plot of daily mean temperature variation with depth below the ice surface in the crevasse adjacent to BH05-07 over the period of data collection, August 2005 to February 2007.	289
5.9	Contour plot of horizontal daily mean temperature gradient between the	290

crevasse and the thermistor string deployed in the adjacent BH05-07 over the period of data collection August 2005 to February 2007.

- 5.10 Time series plot of horizontal ice temperature gradient at 1 m below the surface between the crevasse and the adjacent BH05-07 and 2 m air temperature. 292
- 5.11 Time lapse images (in the order (a)-(f)) of a small slush flow (~ 70 m long) over a ~30 second period at approximately 1300 on day 221 (2005) in the topographic concavity in which the South site is situated. 302

CHAPTER 6

- 6.1 Bi-monthly mean bulk conductive energy flux into the ice surface in the seasonally active thermal layer at the North and South sites during the period of winter cooling and penetration of the winter cold wave in (a) the 2004-05 winter and (b) the 2005-06 winter. 310
- 6.2 Contour plot of temperature with height above the glacier bed in borehole BH04-01 combined with the adjacent BH05-16 over the period of data collection August 2004 to October 2006. 321
- 6.3 Contour plot of temperature with height above the glacier bed in borehole BH04-06 over the period of data collection, August 2004 to February 2007. 322
- 6.4 Contour plot of temperature variation with height above the glacier bed in borehole BH05-07 over the period of data collection, August 2005 to February 2007. 323
- 6.5 Processed 50 MHz radar transect across Glacier de Tsanfleuron conducted in April 2004, presented using a constant gain, (with boreholes 04-01 and 05-16, 05-07 and 04-06 superimposed at their respective locations). 325
- 6.6 Deformation-induced strain heating variation with height above the glacier bed, derived for the South site from repeat inclinometry determination of borehole deformation and strain rate calculation in a borehole adjacent to BH04-06. 327
- 6.7 Temperature time series of BH04-06 deep thermistors at the South site between mid August and early December 2004 during the occurrence of basal heat supply events. 333
- 6.8 Normalized power spectra periodogram for the temperature time series of thermistor 70.0b at the base of BH04-06 at the South site between day 236 and day 337 (2004). 334
- 6.9 Examples of sinkholes developed in the bottom of glacially formed cavities in exposed limestone formerly at the glacier bed in the forefield of Tsanfleuron, exposed striated bedrock with water pools in former subglacial depressions formed by over deepening in the lee of bed rock bumps and diagrammatical representation of the “Cave breathing” heat flux at the glacier bed. 341

CHAPTER 7

7.1	Flow diagram of the various stages involved in modelling of snow and ice temperatures.	349
7.2	Gap filled wind speed data between day 60 and day 150 (2006), depicting the period when the RM Young wind monitor cables detached from the data logger terminals (between day 87 and day 115).	351
7.3	Gap filled and smoothed snow depth and reconstructed snowfall between February 2005 and February 2007.	354
7.4	Daily maximum and mean reconstructed SW↓ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	357
7.5	Daily maximum and minimum reconstructed LW↓ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	359
7.6	Reconstructed sensible heat flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	363
7.7	Reconstructed latent heat flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	364
7.8	Daily maximum and minimum reconstructed LW↑ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	365
7.9	Daily maximum and mean reconstructed SW↑ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	366
7.10	Reconstructed time series of the four individual radiation components (smoothed with a 10 day moving average).	367
7.11	Modelled monthly average energy fluxes for each surface energy source over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection.	368
7.12	Modelled daily mean energy flux at the glacier surface available for surface temperature change or melt over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection.	369
7.13	Comparison of modelled and measured snow depth over the two year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	372
7.14	Comparison of modelled and measured snow temperature time series.	373
7.15	Comparison of selected modelled and measured snow temperature profiles.	375
7.16	Comparison of modelled and measured ice ablation over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	382

7.17	Comparison of modelled and measured ice temperature time series over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.	384
7.18	Comparison of selected modelled and measured ice temperature profiles (with the top 20 m ice temperatures expanded as an inset in each plot).	386
7.19	Modelled glacier surface temperature for the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2006.	387
7.20	Modelled and measured ice surface heat flux for the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2006.	388
7.21	Modelled snow depth and ice surface elevation under slush flow snow pack removal scenarios.	389
7.22	Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various air temperature warming scenarios.	393
7.23	Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various increasing solid precipitation scenarios.	395
7.24	Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various increasing air temperature and solid precipitation scenarios.	396

List of Tables

CHAPTER 1		Page
1.1	Thermal properties of snow, ice, water and air, compiled from Oke (1987) and Paterson (1994).	22
CHAPTER 2		
2.1	Basic meteorological station sensor specifications.	78
2.2	Eddy correlation and four component radiation sensor specifications.	84
2.3	Borehole drilling log and details of borehole instrumentation.	93
2.4	Thermocouple temperature sensors and their stated accuracy used in several previous studies.	95
2.5	Thermistor temperature sensors and their stated accuracy deployed in this and several previous studies.	96
2.6	Thermistors deployed in this study.	103

CHAPTER 3

- 3.1 Summary of basic meteorological variables recorded at 30 minute resolution by the basic meteorological station over a two year period between February 2005 and February 2007. 133
- 3.2 Summary of basic meteorological variables at 30 minute resolution from the basic meteorological station over a four month period between April 2005 and July 2005, recorded simultaneously at two heights, ~3 m and ~0.4 m above the glacier surface respectively. 135
- 3.3 Summary of snow pit data collected at three locations BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 in April 2005, January and April 2006 and January / February 2007. 153
- 3.4 Summary of the January 2006 and January 2007 snow depth transect data. 157
- 3.5 BH04-01 snow pack stratigraphy determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007. 163
- 3.6 BH04-06 snow pack stratigraphy determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007. 164
- 3.7 BH05-07 snow pack stratigraphy determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and February 2007. 165
- 3.8 Burial and melt-out dates for snow pack thermistors located at (a) BH04-01 (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 during the 2004 / 05 and 2005 / 06 winters. 168

CHAPTER 5

- 5.1 Bulk snow pack temperature gradients determined monthly for each of the three thermistor sites. 257
- 5.2 Temperature gradient, conductive heat flux and internal energy of Tsanfleuron snow packs at the times of snow pit analysis in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007. 285

CHAPTER 6

- 6.1 Depths of penetration of the winter cold wave at the North, South and Central sites in the 2004-05 and the 2005-06 winters. 317
- 6.2 Summary of warm and cold ice thermal stratification at each of the instrumented borehole sites in the 2004-05, 2005-06 and 2006-07 glacier years. 325

CHAPTER 7

- 7.1 Tsanfleuron snow and ice properties used in the “tsanf” glacier model (Essery, unpublished) with published values for comparison. 370

APPENDIX

A1	Calibration constant, B , for use in Blatter (1989) temperature calculation, determined from distilled water and distilled water ice cube calibration.	422
A2	Correction factor, A , for correction of intermediate calibrated temperature, determined empirically from snow calibration of thermistors.	423
A3	Glacier surface annual ablation at borehole locations during the summers of 2004, 2005 and 2006.	424
A4	Borehole thermistor deployment dates, locations within the boreholes and melt out dates of near-surface thermistors in holes (a) BH04-01, (b) BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01) and (c) BH04-06.	425
A5	Borehole and crevasse thermistor deployment dates, locations within the borehole and crevasse and melt out dates of near-surface thermistors in (a) a crevasse adjacent to BH05-07, (b) BH05-07.	426
A6	Periods of data from which non ice temperature transient effects were removed from the near-surface thermistors of all three boreholes prior to presentation of ice temperatures and supporting evidence for removal.	427

List of Symbols

SI units are given for all quantities, although units may vary as stated within the text

$a =$	Extinction coefficient (dependent upon wavelength and the nature of the transmitting medium)
$A =$	Temperature dependent constant in Glen's flow law
$A^* =$	Correction factor determined using snow calibration
$A' =$	Calibration constant
$a_o =$	Radiation absorbed by ozone (W m^{-2})
$a_w =$	Radiation absorbed by water vapour (W m^{-2})
$B =$	Temperature dependent ice viscosity (N s m^{-2})
$B^* =$	Empirical calibration parameter
$B' =$	Calibration constant
$\dot{c} =$	Cloud amount (as a proportion of the sky)
$C =$	Heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$c =$	Specific heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$C' =$	Calibration constant
$C_a =$	Heat capacity of air (J K^{-1})
$C_h =$	Bulk exchange coefficient
$c_p =$	Specific heat of air ($1005 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$c_{pi} =$	Specific heat capacity of ice ($2009 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$C_w =$	Specific heat of liquid water ($418 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$d =$	Day of year
$d_s =$	Modelled snow depth (m)

$D_0 =$	Initial ice crystal size (mm)
$D_H =$	Bulk transfer coefficient for heat in air
$d_r =$	Day of the summer solstice
$dT/dz =$	Temperature gradient (K m^{-1})
$dU/dt =$	Rate of change of internal (stored) energy per unit area of snow cover / ice mass (J s^{-1})
$D_w =$	Bulk transfer coefficient for water vapour in air
$d_y =$	Average number of days in a year
$e =$	Vapour pressure (Pa)
$e_s =$	Saturation vapour pressure (Pa)
$F =$	Melt fraction (the fraction of the annual firn layer, by weight, that is formed by refreezing of melt water),
$f_m =$	Temperature index melt factor
$g =$	Acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2})
$G =$	Conductance (S)
$G_s =$	Heat flux at the ice surface (W m^{-2})
$h =$	Elevation of the surface (m)
$H =$	Ice thickness (m)
$h_d =$	Hour of the day
$H' =$	Hour angle measured from solar noon
$H_S =$	Strain heating (W m^{-3})
$I_o =$	Solar constant (1.37 kW / m^2)
$I_t =$	Extra – terrestrial radiation on a horizontal surface (W m^{-2})
$k_V =$	Von Karman constant (0.40)
$\kappa_c =$	Calibration parameter
$\kappa =$	Thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
$K =$	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
$K' =$	Momentum transfer (eddy diffusivity)
$k' =$	Von Karmann's constant (0.41)
$K_0 =$	Crystal growth rate ($\text{mm}^2 \text{ a}^{-1}$)
$K_c =$	Cell constant
$K_{eff} =$	Effective thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
$L =$	Obukov scale length (m)
$L_f =$	Latent heat of fusion (0.333 MJkg^{-1})
$L_f' =$	Specific heat of fusion (J kg^{-1})
$L_v =$	Latent heat of vaporization ($2.50 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$)
$L_s =$	Latent heat of sublimation (2845 kJ Kg^{-1})
$LW\uparrow =$	Long wave radiation emission from the glacier surface (W m^{-2})
$LW\downarrow =$	Long wave sky radiation emission (W m^{-2})
$LWn =$	Net long wave radiation (W m^{-2})
$M =$	Melt rate / accumulation rate ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
$M_E =$	Melt (mm W.E.)
$m =$	Optical air mass (the ratio of the distance the sun's rays travel through the atmosphere to the depth of the atmosphere along the zenith path)
$M_b =$	Basal melt rate (m s^{-1})
$M_{bi} =$	Bulk ionic concentration (mol kg^{-1})
$M_f =$	Mass water refreezing per unit time and volume ($\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$)
$M_i =$	Ice melt (m^{-3}),
$m_s =$	Solute molality (Mol L^{-1})
$n =$	Exponent in Glen's flow law

n'	Impurity concentration (mol kg^{-1})
p	Mean transmissivity of the atmosphere along the zenith path
P	Pressure (Pa)
p'	Absolute pressure (kPa)
P_0	Triple point pressure (Pa)
P_r	Precipitation rate (mm s^{-1})
P_S	Surface air pressure (Pa)
P_σ	Hydrostatic stress (Pa)
q	Specific humidity
Q	Heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q'	Activation energy (kJ mol^{-1})
Q_0	Conductive heat flux from the surface energy balance (W m^{-2})
Q_I	Conductive heat flux out of the top ice layer to the layer below (W m^{-2})
Q_a	Specific humidity at the height of the air temperature measurement (kg kg^{-1})
Q_D	Deformation driven strain heat flux (W m^{-3})
Q_F	Heat generated by friction at the bed (W m^{-2})
Q_{FC}	Firm compaction heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_G	Geothermal heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_{Sur}	Energy flux available for warming the surface (W m^{-2})
Q_H	Sensible heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_I	Conductive heat flux at the snow / ice interface (W m^{-2})
Q_L	Heat generated by freezing of melt water in snow and firn (J),
Q_{LE}	Latent heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_{LW}	Net long wave radiation flux at the snow – air, ice – air, interface (W m^{-2})
Q_M	Energy flux available for surface melt (W m^{-2})
Q_n	Conductive heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_N	Conductive heat flux from the glacier bed (W m^{-2})
Q_n	Conductive heat flux out of the n^{th} ice layer to the layer below (W m^{-2})
Q_{N-1}	Conductive heat flux from the layer above the bottom layer (W m^{-2})
Q_{n-1}	Conductive heat flux into the n^{th} ice layer from the layer above (W m^{-2})
Q_P	Precipitation heat flux (W m^{-2})
Q_R	Net radiation (W m^{-2})
Q_s	Saturation specific humidity at the surface temperature (kg kg^{-1})
Q_{SW}	Net shortwave radiation flux (W m^{-2})
r	Radius vector of the earth's orbit
R	Universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)
$R(T'_0)$	Resistance at reference temperature T_0 (Ω)
$R(T_{\text{par}})$	Resistance at temperature T_{par} (resistance recorded by the logger) (Ω)
R_a	Thermistor resistance at lowest temperature to be measured (Ω)
R_b	Thermistor resistance at middle temperature to be measured (Ω)
R_c	Thermistor resistance at highest temperature to be measured (Ω)
R_{EC}	Resistance of EC sensor (Ω)
R_f	Resistance of fixed resistor (Ω)
RH	Relative humidity (%)
RH_{700}	Relative humidity at 700 mb level of the atmosphere (%)
R_{ref}	Optimum value for linearising resistor (Ω)
R_s	Resistance of temperature sensor (Ω)
S^*	Irradiance of the solar beam striking the top of the atmosphere (“Solar constant”) (W m^{-2})
S_f	Water equivalent fresh snow fall (mm W.E.)

$SW\uparrow$	Shortwave outgoing radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$)
$SW\downarrow$	Short wave incoming radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$)
$SW\downarrow_z$	Shortwave incident at depth (z) ($W\ m^{-2}$)
SW_d	Diffuse fraction of solar radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$)
SWE	Snow water equivalent (mm W.E.)
SWE^n	Modelled snow water equivalent at time step n (mm W.E.)
SWE^{n-1}	Modelled snow water equivalent at time step n-1 (mm W.E.)
SW_n	Net short wave radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$)
T	Temperature (K)
t	Time (s)
$T(0,t)$	Surface temperature at time t ($^{\circ}C$)
$T(z,t)$	Temperature at depth z at time t ($^{\circ}C$)
T'_0	Reference temperature (K)
T_0	Triple point temperature (K)
$T_{(1)}$	Temperature of the top ice layer (K)
T_2	Air temperature at 2 m above surface (K)
$T_{(2)}$	Temperature of the second ice layer below surface (K)
T_{700}	Air temperature at 700 mb level of the atmosphere ($^{\circ}C$)
T_a	Air temperature (K)
T_b	Basal temperature (K)
T_{cal}	Calibrated temperature (K)
T_{cor}	Final calibrated temperature (C)
T_N	Temperature of the basal ice layer (K)
T_n	Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer (K)
$T_n^{(i)}$	Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer at time step i (K)
$T_n^{(i+1)}$	Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer at time step i + 1 (K)
T_{n+1}	Temperature of the ice layer below the n^{th} ice layer (K)
T_{N-1}	Temperature of the ice layer above that at the bed (K)
T_{n-1}	Temperature of the ice layer above the n^{th} ice layer (K)
T_p	Temperature of the precipitation (K)
T_{par}	Temperature at which resistance is $R(T_{par})$
$T_{par}(C)$	Parameterized temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
T_S	Glacier surface temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
T_v	Amplitude of temperature variation (K)
T_z	Temperature at a given depth (z) (K)
Tz	Temperature at height (z) above the surface (K)
t_{ρ}	Densification time constant
u	Wind speed ($m\ s^{-1}$)
u^*	Friction velocity ($m\ s^{-1}$)
u_b	Sliding velocity ($m\ s^{-1}$)
v	Velocity ($m\ s^{-1}$)
V_2	Wind speed at 2 m above surface ($m\ s^{-1}$)
W	Energy release by phase changes (J)
W_v	Bulk vein water concentration
w	Vertical velocity ($m\ s^{-1}$)
W'	Fractional water content by weight
X	Result stored in data logger final storage
X_s	Elevation dependant coefficient
Y_s	Elevation dependant coefficient

$Z =$	Solar zenith angle ($^{\circ}$)
$Z_i =$	Total ice depth (m)
$z =$	Depth (m)
$z_L =$	Elevation of the land surface (m)
$z' =$	Sensor height (m)
$z_0 =$	Surface roughness length (m)
$z_{0U} =$	Surface roughness for wind speed
$z_s =$	Sun's zenith distance (m)
$Z_s =$	Elevation dependant coefficient
$z_t =$	Air temperature measurement height (m)
$z_u =$	Wind speed measurement height (m)
$z_z =$	Maximum depth (z) to which melt water penetrates (m)
$\alpha =$	Albedo
$\alpha_i =$	Ice surface albedo
$\alpha_s =$	Snow surface albedo
$\beta =$	Bowen ratio
$\beta^* =$	Rate of change of melting point with pressure ($7.42 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}(\text{kPa})^{-1}$)
$B^{\wedge} =$	Rate of change of melting point with pressure ($9.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}(\text{kPa})^{-1}$ or $8.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K m}^{-1}$)
$\beta' =$	Rate of change of melting point with pressure (K Pa^{-1})
$\delta =$	Solar declination angle ($^{\circ}$)
$\delta =$	Solar declination angle ($^{\circ}$)
$\Delta SR50 =$	Depth increase in smoothed SR50 snow depth (m)
$\Delta t =$	Length of time step (s)
$\Delta T_0 =$	Amplitude of temperature variation ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
$\Delta T_1 =$	Temperature change of the top ice layer (K),
$\Delta T_N =$	Temperature change of the bottom (N^{th}) ice layer (K),
$\Delta T_n =$	Temperature change of the n^{th} ice layer (K).
$\Delta z_n =$	Ice layer thickness (m)
$\Delta e_2 =$	Saturation vapour pressure at the glacier surface (Pa)
$\Delta T_a =$	Amplitude of the yearly variation in air temperature (K)
$\varepsilon =$	Surface emissivity
$\varepsilon_a =$	Atmospheric emissivity
$\varepsilon^* =$	Effective emissivity of the sky
$\varepsilon_0 =$	Emissivity of clear sky
$\theta =$	Surface slope ($^{\circ}$)
$\theta_t =$	Temperature depression of the ice below its pressure melting point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
$\theta' =$	Potential temperature (K)
$\rho =$	Density (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_1 =$	Density in the uppermost grid element of the model (surface)
$\rho_a =$	Air density (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_i =$	Density of ice (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_m =$	Maximum snow density (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_s =$	Density of surface snow (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_0 =$	Fresh snow density (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_w =$	Density of liquid water (kg m^{-3})
$\rho_z =$	Density at depth (z) (kg m^{-3})
$\sigma =$	Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$)
$\sigma^* =$	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)
$\sigma_s^* =$	Conductivity of solution ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)

σ'	=	Uniaxial stress (kPa)
σ_c	=	Cloud fraction
τ	=	Effective shear stress (kPa)
τ	=	Hour angle measured from solar noon (°)
τ_b	=	Basal shear stress (kPa)
T_{dx}	=	Driving stress (Pa)
φ	=	Latitude (°)
φ_T	=	Latitude of the tropic of Cancer (°)
Ψ_{diff}	=	Diffuse net sky transmissivity
Ψ_{dir}	=	Direct net sky transmissivity
ω	=	Frequency of variation
$\omega/2\pi$	=	Frequency of temperature variation
ω'	=	Angular frequency
$\partial T/\partial t$	=	Rate of temperature change over time (K s ⁻¹)
$\partial T_n/\partial t$	=	Rate of change in temperature of the n th ice layer (K s ⁻¹)
$\frac{\partial Q_t}{\partial z}$	=	Absorption of energy coming from the atmosphere (J m ⁻¹)
$\dot{\varepsilon}$	=	Uniaxial Strain rate (s ⁻¹)
$\vec{v}(x, y)$	=	Velocity vector (m s ⁻¹)
$(X S)$	=	Angle of incidence of the sun's rays on the slope (X is a unit normal vector pointing away from the surface and S is a unit vector expressing the sun's position)

Acknowledgements

I should sincerely like to thank my supervisors Bryn Hubbard and Richard Essery for all their assistance, perseverance and guidance throughout all stages of this work. I would also specifically like to thank Dave Chandler for all his assistance pertaining to help in the field with data loggers, borehole drilling, inclinometry and DGPS and in the office with numerical modelling, sharing his Tsanfleuron data and frequently explaining mathematical problems. Similarly Nick Rutter for his assistance in the field with the met stations, eddy correlation instruments and digging numerous snow pits, Dave Kelly for sensor building, repair, calibration and procurement of components, Tommy Ridgeway for potting the thermistors in resin, Glacier 3000 for logistical support on Tsanfleuron especially Florence Labarre for her insatiable interest in our work on the glacier, arranging transport assistance and sending people with skidoos to rescue us on numerous occasions when the Tsanfleuron weather was at its worst and Dave Webb for proof reading the final manuscript. I would also like to extend a big thank you to the following people for their assistance in the field: Dan Bewley, Cat Butcher, Dave Chandler, Samyn Denis, Richard Essery, Helen Freeman, Chris Hann, Alyn Hubbard, Bryn Hubbard, Bernd Kulesa, Shona Mackie, Armin Mewes, Tavi Murray, Dave Rippin, Nick Rutter, Tom Sudbury and Jemma Wadham. Finally and in no way least I should like to thank my fiancée Katie for her unwavering support.

This research was funded via a studentship from the Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, University of Wales, Aberystwyth. Additional field work expenses were met through collaboration on NERC Grant (NER/A/S/2002/00607) awarded to Dr B. Hubbard and a grant from the University of Wales, Aberystwyth, Research Fund awarded to Dr R.Essery, to which I am greatly indebted.

Chapter 1

Introduction and literature review.

1.1 Introduction

Why study the temperatures of a temperate alpine glacier?

Many studies of glacier ice temperatures have been conducted, predominantly on polythermal and cold ice masses. Only a handful of studies have been conducted on temperate glaciers, with very few investigations in recent decades (e.g. Sharp, 1951; Miller, 1954; Paterson, 1968; 1972; Harrison, 1975; Binschadler *et al.*, 1976; Cohen *et al.*, 2000) and a dearth of studies of temperate glacier temperatures in the European Alps (e.g. Suter *et al.*, 2001). Many of the processes studied in temperate alpine locations are applicable to other ice masses at larger scales and with different thermal regimes.

“Glaciers and ice caps are key indicators and unique demonstration objects of global climate change” (Haeberli *et al.*, 2007). Glaciers and ice caps (excluding Greenland and Antarctica) have the potential, if fully ablated, to cause significant sea level rise, with estimates ranging between 0.15 m SLE (Sea Level Equivalent) (Ohmura, 2004) and 0.37 m SLE (Dyurgerov and Meier, 2005). To date mass losses from glaciers and small ice caps are estimated to have contributed to observed sea level rise by $0.50 \pm 0.18 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$ between 1961 and 2004 and by $0.77 \pm 0.22 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$ between 1991 and 2004, as a consequence of global warming (IPCC, 2007). In light of these observations one of the key objectives of future glaciological research must be to predict how ice masses will respond under future climate change scenarios.

Temperate glaciers in the European Alps appear to be highly sensitive to climate warming, exhibiting a dramatic acceleration in mass loss over recent decades, 30 to 40 % of the glacierized area and ~ 50 % of ice volume was lost between 1850 and 1970 (Haeberli and Holzle, 1995), with a further 25 % of the remaining volume estimated to have been lost since (Haeberli, 2005). Specific examples include, the exceptional mass losses observed over nine alpine glaciers during 2003, when an average ice loss of $2500 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, ~ 60 % higher than the previous maximum annual ablation rate of $1600 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ was recorded, as a consequence of extraordinarily high air temperatures coupled with low precipitation and an albedo feedback (caused by deposition of Sahara dust on glacier surfaces) (Zemp *et al.*, 2005).

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The cryospheric impacts of climate change are not limited to temperate alpine valley glaciers. Global warming has led to changes in the temperature distribution of polythermal glaciers, e.g. at Storgläciaren, where between 1989 and 2001, 8.3 m of the cold surface layer warmed to melting point, as a consequence of warmer winter temperatures and a longer melt season (Pettersson *et al.*, 2003). Significant alterations in the total mass and flow dynamics of cold and polythermal ice comprising the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets have also been recorded. Accelerated ice flow velocities have been reported for many marginal glaciers in Greenland (e.g. Thomas *et al.*, 2003; Joughin *et al.*, 2004; Howat *et al.*, 2005; Rignot and Kanagaratnam, 2006) and Antarctica (e.g. Scambos *et al.*, 2004; Shepherd *et al.*, 2004; Thomas *et al.*, 2004; Rignot *et al.*, 2004; 2005; Zwally *et al.*, 2006), with potential consequences for the stability of the adjacent parts of the ice sheets. The Greenland ice sheet has recently experienced mass loss due to these observed increasing ice flow velocities and more rapid near-coastal melting, with Antarctic loss increases being partly attributed to similar changes in ice flow (IPCC, 2007). The dynamics of slow moving ice sheet (cold) ice and that of ice shelves are well understood and can be adequately modelled, however, key deficiencies exist in the parameterisation of fast flowing (warmer) outlet glacier and ice stream ice (IPCC, 2007). Unfortunately until recently “shortcomings in forcing, physics and resolution in comprehensive ice flow models have prevented them from fully capturing the ice flow changes” IPCC (2007).

Early ice sheet models (e.g. Huybrechts *et al.*, 1996) included both ice flow and ice temperature evolution, but the two parameterisations evolved independently. Attempts to address the deficiencies in ice flow modelling of the major ice sheets have been conducted through the development of state of the art thermo-mechanical ice sheet models under the European Ice Sheet Modelling Initiative (EISMINT) (Payne *et al.*, 2000). Such time dependent models of polythermal ice sheet evolution are based on complexly and non linearly linked prognostic equations for the evolution of ice thickness and ice temperature evolution (Payne and Baldwin, 2000). The importance of coupling ice temperature and flow is highlighted with the identification of ice flow instability (Payne and Dongelmans, 1997; Payne *et al.*, 2000) (previously termed creep instability by Clarke *et al.*, 1977, where positive feedbacks exist with the potential to generate explosive increases in ice velocity, with small perturbations in flow triggering enhanced warming).

Modelling studies require field data to calibrate ice flow in response to climate change. Much of the fast flowing ice, radiating outwards from idealised modelled ice sheets under the EISMINT program (Payne *et al.*, 2000) is replicated at the margins of the Greenland ice sheet (and in the Antarctic ice streams). Such glaciers are large (10s to 100s of km in length), often inaccessible

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

and located in inhospitable environments. Temperate alpine glaciers however, provide logistically accessible and manageable analogues for such glaciers; whilst an improved understanding of the thermal structure and flow dynamics of temperate alpine glaciers is of intrinsic scientific importance in its own right, given their climatic sensitivity, proximity to human settlement and use for water resources and hydro electric power generation in mountain regions.

Why Glacier de Tsanfleuron?

This thesis focuses on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland, building on previous studies conducted on the glacier, specifically the collection and crystallographic analysis of ice cores (Tison and Hubbard, 2000; Hubbard *et al.*, 2000a), surface (Chandler, 2005) and subglacial dynamics (Hubbard, 2002a) and recent advances in temperate glacier flow modelling (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003). Glacier flow is controlled by two key processes; basal sliding and internal deformation (Paterson, 1994). Basal sliding has been measured in subglacial cavities at the snout of Tsanfleuron (Hubbard, 2002a) and incorporated into flow models, while Monte Carlo simulations of Tsanfleuron ice velocity suggest internal ice deformation accounts for ~14 to 55% of the observed flow (Chandler *et al.*, 2006).

Ice temperature controls ice softness and thus deformation in response to an applied stress, influencing local ice flow dynamics and the response of a glacier to climate change. Warm ice at melting point deforms more quickly than cold ice (Paterson, 1994). Temperate glaciers such as Tsanfleuron are by definition composed of warm ice, with a seasonally active thermal layer at their surface, in which cold ice develops. Near surface cold ice forms as temperatures annually fall below melting point, due to the penetration of the “winter cold wave” (Benn and Evans, 1998). Measurements of the penetration depth of this cold wave suggest it to be of the order of 10 - 20 m (Paterson, 1994; Suter *et al.*, 2001; Engelhardt, 2004; Zagorodnov *et al.*, 2006); this depth is generally accepted as applicable to most temperate glaciers (Paterson, 1994). To date most reports of temperate ice temperatures below ~ 20 m, indicate a linear temperature decrease with depth following melting point depression with increasing pressure below the ice surface (Paterson, 1971; 1972; Harrison, 1972; 1975). The exact ice temperature distribution within Glacier de Tsanfleuron is at present not known. In the absence of glacier specific temperature profiles, Hubbard *et al.*, (2003) in ice flow modelling investigations were forced to assume a linear temperature variation with depth at Tsanfleuron and that ice temperatures were spatially uniform, varying only with surface altitude. However, regions of colder ice located at depth within other so called ‘temperate’ glaciers have been identified (e.g. Mathews, 1964). The

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

existence, location and temperature of ice below its melting point has implications for the parameterisation of ice deformation in glacier flow models which utilise Glen (1955)'s non linear temperature dependent Flow law parameter, A . To accurately represent ice deformation and spatially variable temperate ice rheology in glacier flow models a characterisation of ice temperature is thus required. Consequently it is important to investigate the temperature variation of Glacier de Tsanfleuron, controlled by energy fluxes into and out of the glacier at the surface/atmosphere and the sole/bed interfaces, to determine whether the 'temperate' glacier is at melting point throughout, and if not, what is the spatial variability of cold ice? The question remains; what is the temperature of a 'temperate' alpine glacier?

Ground penetrating radar transects forming part of a NERC funded research program being conducted on Tsanfleuron (Murray *et al.*, 2006) also require accurate snow and ice temperature profile measurements for calculation of the ice liquid water content. Initial data from these radar transects will be used to search for and identify regions of possible colder ice, assisting in the location of drill sites for thermistor borehole instrumentation, in return for temperature data for radar processing. The requirement for accurate Tsanfleuron temperature profile measurements for radar interpretation and glacier flow modelling, justifies collaboration with grant researchers, facilitating financial and logistical support for this investigation.

Thesis aims

This study will closely support a NERC funded multidisciplinary research program (Grant no. NER/A/S/2002/00607), assessing the current lack of knowledge concerning the structure of temperate valley glaciers, focussed on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. Specifically this thesis aims to; develop a detailed understanding of the temperature of a 'temperate' glacier, accurately measuring snow and ice temperatures in the field, generating temperature profiles for integration (elsewhere) into the spatially distributed Tsanfleuron alpine glacier flow model (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003), to improve current deficiencies in the parameterisation of ice deformation. Quantification of the energy fluxes to and from the glacier at all depths, from the atmospheric interactions at the glacier surface to the subglacial environment will be sought, to evaluate the recorded temperature profiles. Additionally temperature data from this study will be combined with derivations of glacier specific snow pack and ice physical and thermal properties to provide driving data for use in the development and testing a one dimensional glacier energy flux model to be derived for Tsanfleuron, predicting snow and ice temperatures, accumulation and ablation.

Key work to be conducted in this thesis and why?

Snow pack temperature measurements, though not of direct relevance to glacier flow investigations, are critical to energy exchange processes in the near surface ice, as the snow mediates energy transfer to and from the ice for as much as 75% of the glacier year. Snow temperature data (combined with thermal properties) will allow calculation of energy fluxes through the snow, elucidating snowpack energy transfer processes and the thermal influence of the snowpack to the glacier ice (currently not fully understood).

As outlined above measurements of the spatial and temporal variability of ice temperatures at high accuracy, will seek to determine the temperature of a temperate alpine glacier and evaluate the 'temperate' classification of the thermal regime of Glacier de Tsanfleuron. These temperature data will be used by others for incorporation into valley glacier flow models allowing a parameterisation of spatially variable temperate ice rheology and for use in the calculation of ice water content from radar data. Ice temperature data will additionally in this thesis be used to investigate a number of thermal phenomena and processes suggested to influence the thermal regime of temperate glaciers, answering a number of key questions, specifically:

- What is the depth of penetration of the Tsanfleuron winter cold wave? And is this within the range 10 – 20 m (Paterson, 1994), in keeping with that commonly accepted for temperate glaciers?
- What is the spatial variability of ice temperatures at Tsanfleuron?
- Does perennial cold ice exist within Glacier de Tsanfleuron, if so, at what temperature and why?
- What are the magnitude and spatial and temporal variations of englacial energy fluxes?
- Do fractures and crevasses exert a thermal influence over ice temperatures near the glacier surface, if so how? (Currently such features are ambiguously suggested to be both heat sources (Suter *et al.*, 2001) and sinks (Harrison *et al.*, 1998) to the surrounding ice).
- What are the thermal influences, if any, of the subglacial karst system underlying Tsanfleuron? (Thermal interactions of this type may be inferred from Ford *et al.*, 1976 and Vivian, 1980 but to date have not been specifically reported. Subglacial electrical conductivity and water pressure measurements will be used in conjunction with temperature data to evaluate these glacier/karst interactions).

Specific physical and thermal properties to be determined as part of this study include, snow and ice depths, snow pack stratigraphy, snow and ice densities, thermal conductivities and thermal diffusivities. Determination of snow depth, seasonal variation and spatial heterogeneity thereof,

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

across the glacier surface is important in assessing the thermal influence of the snow pack over the ice surface and as driving and validation data for the glacier energy and mass balance model, while snow stratigraphic analysis will assist in process interpretation and inferences regarding retardation of water percolation through the snowpack by impermeable ice layers. Accurate determination of ice depth is vital for tracking the location depth of near surface thermistors which will, in summer get closer to the surface due to ice ablation, also ice depth is required for the calculation of overburden pressures and thus the melting point depression with depth below the ice surface (currently assumed in temperate ice temperature literature to be the most significant control on ice temperature). Accurate measurements of ice depth at different locations across the glacier, in conjunction with detailed meteorological, energy flux and temperature data, will it is hoped, help explain differences in ice ablation rates previously reported between multiple sites the same altitude on other glaciers (e.g. Konya *et al.*, 2004, Fountain and Vecchia, 1999 and Tangborn *et al.*, 1997). Snow and ice density measurements are required for ablation calculations in the energy balance model and are used in the determination of snow and ice thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity values. Determination of Tsanfleuron specific values of the key thermal parameters of conductivity and diffusivity is vital to physically realistic parameterisation in the glacier energy and mass balance model and are to be used in conjunction with temperature gradient data to determine energy flows within the snow and ice using Fourier's law.

To explain observed temporal snow and ice temperature variations, determinations of the energy fluxes into, through and out of the glacier surface via energy balance modelling and measurement of the fluxes via both basic meteorological instrumentation and full characterisation of the energy fluxes using eddy correlation and four component radiation sensing instruments are required. Basic glaciometeorological data will also provide the driving data for the glacier energy balance model. A one dimensional numerical model is to be developed to link the various snow and ice heat sources and sinks, to accurately predict snow pack and glacier ice temperatures, energy fluxes, glacier accumulation and ablation. The development and operation of such a model will aid process understanding and it is hoped, allow identification of any non parameterised processes in need of further investigation. It is intended that the integrated alpine glacier energy flux model, once fully developed, may be applicable to other glaciers in similar alpine settings and process understanding gained through its development, may benefit ice mass modelling at a range of spatial scales.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Glacier surface energy balances have previously been extensively studied (e.g. Konzmann and Braithwaite, 1995; Oerlemans and Knap, 1998; Willis *et al.*, 2002; Hock and Holmgren, 2005), englacial and subglacial energy fluxes have similarly been considered (e.g. Paterson, 1971), snow and temperate ice temperatures have been recorded (e.g. Paterson, 1968; 1971; 1972; Harrison, 1975; Pfeffer and Humphrey, 1996; Taras *et al.*, 2002; Mihalcea *et al.*, 2006) and investigations of snow pack and glacier ice physical and thermal properties have been conducted (e.g. Shumskiy, 1960; Lange, 1985; Sturm *et al.*, 1997). However, to date these investigations have generally occurred independently of each other. Snow pack and near surface ice temperatures are complexly interlinked with the controlling processes not easily separated, thus neither the snow pack, or the near surface temperate ice temperatures and energy fluxes can easily be considered in isolation from the other. Similar natural complexity exists at the glacier bed in terms of the energy transfers between the basal ice and the subglacial hydrological system. For the first time, this study seeks to use an integrated approach to the study of energy fluxes and temperatures throughout the entire glacier depth.

In this chapter temperate glacier ice is defined (Section 1.2), consideration is given to the importance of detailed characterisation of temperate glacier temperatures (Section 1.3) and the applications thereof (Section 1.4). Previous investigations of temperate glacier ice temperatures are outlined (Section 1.5), as are the physical properties of snow and ice (Section 1.6), processes controlling snow and ice temperature profiles (Section 1.7), glacier surface heat fluxes (Section 1.8), englacial heat fluxes (Section 1.9) and basal heat fluxes (Section 1.10). Section 1.11 details energy balance and melt modelling, Section 1.12 outlines methods of modelling ice temperatures in the vertical dimension, while the theory of subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity variation are discussed in Section 1.12. Research objectives and a thesis outline are given in Sections 1.14 and 1.15 respectively.

1.2 Temperate glacier ice

Temperate glacier ice is widely and, incorrectly considered to have a uniform temperature of 0 °C. This popular misconception likely stems from confusion caused by the multiplicity and over-simplification of the definitions of temperate ice. “Temperate ice is a complex material consisting of ice, water, air, salts and carbon dioxide” (Paterson, 1994, p.211). Some of the more common temperate ice definitions include:

- “ice at its melting point” (Lliboutry, 1971)
- “A glacier containing liquid inclusions in which the concentration of salts is not too high” (Lliboutry, 1971)

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

- “ice that is in thermal equilibrium with a liquid phase” (Lliboutry, 1971)
- “ice that contains within it a liquid phase (whether the liquid inclusions communicate or not) and which is in local equilibrium with it” (Lliboutry, 1971)
- “ice at a depth below that influenced by seasonal temperature fluctuations is at pressure melting point.” (Ahlmann, 1935)
- “ice is at the melting point throughout, except for a surface layer, some 10 m thick, in which the temperature is below 0 °C for part of the year” (Paterson, 1994, p12.)

A more accurate definition is that: temperate glacier ice, despite winter cooling, reaches melting point for some period of the glacier year. Temperate ice may exist in polythermal glaciers along with cold ice, however, for a glacier to be classed as temperate, the ice must reach melting point throughout, for some part of the year. For ice to be classified as temperate, ice cooled by low surface air temperatures and heat loss during the previous winter, must either be warmed by the heat fluxes into the ice or be ablated, such that the remaining ice at the end of the ablation season is at the melting temperature. The precise melting temperature is dictated by numerous factors, including:

- overburden pressure,
- solute content and
- bubble content of the ice mass.

Glaciers composed of temperate ice in general tend to be located in mid latitude locations with moderate climates. That is not to say, however, that all glaciers located in the mid latitudes have a temperate thermal regime. For instance, some high altitude glaciers in the European Alps exhibit ice temperatures in their accumulation areas characteristic of a cold thermal regime (Haeberli, 1976). For example, englacial temperatures at the Colle Gnifetti core drilling site (Monte Rosa, Swiss Alps) were reported as low as -14.4 °C (Oeschger *et al.*, 1978) and -14.1 °C (Haeberli and Funk, 1991) at depths of 15 m and 12 m respectively. Mathews (1964) similarly reported sub freezing temperatures on South Leduc Glacier, Canada, which had previously been considered temperate, while 10 m temperature measurements in the Athabasca glacier showed that the ice was temperate in the accumulation area but not in the ablation area (Paterson, 1972). In fact Blatter and Haeberli (1984) suggested that the majority of the world’s mountain glaciers may be partially cold, and that the occurrence of glaciers that are completely temperate in the traditional sense of the definition may be restricted to locations with greater than 2000 mm a⁻¹ precipitation. Temperate glaciers can also be present in low altitude polar regions, often in maritime regions where glaciers experience a large mass throughput resulting from heavy winter snowfalls and intense summer ablation.

1.3 Importance of a detailed characterisation of temperate glacier temperatures

“Glaciers and ice sheets are sensitive indicators of climatic variations. Their volume varies in response to temporal variation in accumulation and ablation and to temporal variations in ice temperature, which causes changes in ice mechanical properties” (Greuell and Smeets, 2001). In the light of the IPCC climate change predictions of continued anthropogenic warming, one of the current key focuses for glaciological research is the prediction of how temperate valley glaciers are likely to respond to climate change and contribute to sea level rise (Gregory and Oerlemans, 1998). Ice flow and mass balance models form the basis for modelling ice mass response. These models are commonly 3D and spatially distributed, enabling the spatial variability of ice response to applied stress to be calculated. The physical properties controlling this response include: ice temperature, ice crystallography, liquid water, air bubble, debris and solute content of the ice.

Glen’s flow law

Flow properties of ice occur as a consequence of processes operating at three different scales: lattice scale processes (flow properties of mono crystals), crystal scale processes (flow properties of crystal aggregates e.g. dislocation glide and boundary diffusion) and glacier scale processes (flow variations as ice flows over bedrock irregularities) (Budd and Radok, 1971). At the glacier scale, ice deforms via creep as a result of gravity-induced stresses. The processes resisting glacier flow, however, are spatially and temporally variable, resulting in non-uniform glacier flow (Harper *et al.*, 2001). Hydrostatic pressure and shear stress drive glacier ice deformation via the weight of overlying ice and the glacier surface slope. Ice deformation experiments suggest a simple power law relationship between stress and strain rate (e.g. Glen, 1955; Steinemann, 1954; Landauer, 1957; Weertman, 1957; Butkovich and Landauer, 1958; Glen, 1958 and Rist and Murrell, 1994).

The flow of ice under a constant stress as studied by Glen (1955) demonstrates that strain rate is highly dependent on shear stress when represented as a flow law in the form:

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = A \tau^n \quad (1.3.1)$$

where:

- $\dot{\varepsilon}$ = Uniaxial Strain rate (s^{-1})
- A = Temperature dependent constant
- τ = Effective shear stress (kPa)
- n = Exponent (mean value = 3)

A value of ~ 3 for the exponent n is reported by (Nye, 1953; Glen, 1958; Hansen and Landauer, 1958; Steinemann, 1958a; Gow, 1963; Mellor and Smith, 1967; Barnes *et al.*, 1971; Paterson,

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1977; Russell-Head and Budd, 1979; Martin and Sanderson, 1980; Hooke, 1981 and Song, 2005). Kuon and Jonas (1973) report a stress exponent of 5.7, while Hooke (1981) notes that field data often suggest values of n between 4 and 6 as natural ice appears to be weaker (softer) than laboratory ice.

Relationships between temperature and ice physical properties

Temperature influences ice physical properties, however, the physical properties in turn influence the temperature, these relationships are investigated below for certain key properties:

1. Temperature

Glen (1955); Rist and Murrell (1994) and Gagnon and Gammon (1995) have described the temperature dependence of ice rheology, proposing the following Arrhenius relationship:

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = A \exp(-Q'/RT) \sigma'^n \quad (1.3.2)$$

where:

$\dot{\varepsilon}$ = Uniaxial strain rate (s^{-1})

A = Flow law parameter ($s^{-1} kPa^{-3}$)

Q' = Activation energy for creep (139 $kJ mol^{-1}$ for temperatures above $-10^\circ C$ (Weertman, 1973))

R = Universal gas constant ($8.314 J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$)

T = Temperature (K)

σ' = Uniaxial stress (kPa)

n = Exponent

The flow law parameter (A) varies with temperature as indicated in Figure 1.1 (Paterson, 1994).

Figure 1.1: Variation of flow law parameter, A, with temperature, plotted from data presented by Paterson (1994, p97).

Colbeck and Evans (1973) observed an accelerating viscosity decrease with increasing stress as ice melting temperature was approached, concluding that a linear viscous mechanism dominates ice deformation at low stresses and that intercrystalline glide dominates at high stresses. Mellor and Testa (1969) reported that viscosity of ice decreases more rapidly than in Glen's exponential relationship (with deformation rate increasing by factors of 3 to 4 as temperature was increased from -10 °C to -2 °C). Barnes and Tabor (1966) observed ice hardness to change more rapidly above -1.2 °C than below -1.2 °C, suggesting that the flow of ice at melting point may not be predictable from Glen's Arrhenius relation of temperature dependence. Steinemann (1958b), however, agreed that rheological properties of melting ice could be determined by extrapolation of results to experiments at sub freezing temperatures (-0.02 °C) as conducted by Glen (1955).

2. Crystallography

Duval (1973) found that transient creep rate increased with crystal size over a certain size range and was influenced by crystal orientation. Duval and LeGac (1980) argued that minimum creep rates were independent of crystal size. A preferred crystal orientation fabric and a tertiary equilibrium crystal size develop in ice undergoing creep deformation to high strains (Hooke, 1981; Jacka and Li, 1994). Borehole closure rates via plastic flow in a shear environment are closely related to the c – axis fabric of the ice (Thwaites *et al.*, 1984). Thorsteinsson *et al.*,

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

(1999) showed that, despite the main features of deformation at Dye 3, Greenland, being explained by anisotropy and temperature, the residual enhancement correlated well with dust and soluble ion concentration divided by crystal size. Crystal size has been reported to increase with depth from 1 to 2 mm diameter near the surface to as large as 3 – 10 cm near the bed (Vallon *et al.*, 1976).

The rate of crystal growth depends upon the surface meteorology; under high accumulation rates, high crystal deformation rates occur and dynamic recrystallisation due to seasonal temperature fluctuations, takes over from normal crystal growth (Li and Jacka, 1999). For crystals formed under stress in firn layers, the crystal growth rate is controlled by temperature, while the mean crystal size depends on initial crystal size, growth time and temperature. In the absence of stress, crystal grain growth has been considered to increase as a function of temperature and time by Gow (1969) and by Jacka and Li (1994) in the form:

$$D^2 = D_0^2 + K_0 t f(T) \quad (1.3.3)$$

where:

D_0 = Initial crystal size (mm)

K_0 = Growth rate (determined empirically to be $1.86 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ a}^{-1}$ at $-17 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

t = Time (a)

$f(T)$ = The Arrhenius relation (Glen, 1955) in the form:

$$f(T) \propto \exp\left(\frac{-Q'}{RT}\right) \quad (1.3.4)$$

where:

Q' = Activation energy for crystal growth (observed to be similar to the activation energy for creep by Weertman (1973), which he reported to be 139 kJ mol^{-1} for temperatures above $-10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

R = Universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)

When stress is applied to the ice, an equilibrium crystal size is achieved which is a function of the temperature and strain deformation. Budd and Jacka (1989) suggested crystal size should be regarded as a consequence of the deformation rate rather than a cause thereof. Large crystals form in the ablation zones of temperate glaciers in response to a move from high to low stress zones as a consequence of surface ablation (Higashi, 1967). Hooke and Hudleston (1980) reported a change in ice fabric and crystal size across the boundary between ice of different ages, accounting for much rheological contrast (Gao *et al.*, 1988).

3. Liquid water content

Liquid water in temperate polycrystalline ice is located within grains, inside bubbles with larger inclusions and in an interconnected system of veins that lie along the lines where three or more grains meet (Mader, 1992a; 1992b). Mader (1992 b) reported a strong temperature dependence of the effective diffusivity of polycrystalline ice through changes in geometry of the water vein system at grain boundaries as a direct result of the latent heat required for melting or freezing at the vein walls during temperature change. This water has an important effect on the rate of ice flow, particularly in temperate glaciers (Lliboutry, 1976). The strain rate of ice is increased at higher water contents through the facilitation of adjustment of grains with different initial orientations to a preferred direction of orientation for greater deformation (Paterson, 1994) as liquid water inclusions enhance melting and refreezing associated with recrystallisation (Lliboutry and Duval, 1985). Cohen (2000) suggested the presence of water between sediment layers and clean ice layers in basal ice causes a significant weakening. Duval (1977) presented the control of water content over ice viscosity, by means of a linear relationship between the factor A_0 in Glen's flow law and water content in the water volume to ice volume range 0.01 to 0.8 %. A 1 % rise in water content is reported by Benjumea *et al.* (2003) to result in a factor 3 increase in the effective strain rate. Measurements of liquid water content of temperate ice have yielded values of 0.32 to 1.31 % (Vallon *et al.*, 1976), 0.6 to 0.95 % (Lliboutry, 1983), 1 to 1.7 % (Lliboutry, 1971; Raymond and Harrison, 1975), 1.04 to 1.24 % (Dupy, 1970 (in Lliboutry, 2002), 1 to 2 % (Cohen, 1999), 0.09 to 4.1 % (Murray *et al.*, 2000) and 0.4 to 3.2 % (Benjumea *et al.*, 2003). Murray *et al.* (2000) concluded that a substantial amount of water is stored within temperate glaciers with significant implications for ice rheology.

The spatial variability of liquid water content in alpine Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland was considered by Hubbard *et al.* (2003) to vary systematically throughout the depth of ice. Three distinctive internal zones were identified, with relative bulk water concentrations and ice softness varying by an order of magnitude between the zones, based on an assumption of a uniform temperature profile. The rheological role of liquid water content was investigated in the three separate glacier ice zones, using values of water content and the ice softness value in Glen's flow law scaled to a value of 1.0 for englacial upper zone ice. This yielded values of 1.80 and 10.74 for basal clear lower zone and basal diffused basal zone ice respectively.

4. Impurities (dissolved and solid)

The influence of dissolved impurities on ice strength depends on the ionic species and the concentrations involved (Nakamura and Jones, 1973). Renaud (1949) reported that impurities

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

tend to be concentrated at grain boundaries. More recently scanning electron microscopy techniques (Mulvaney *et al.*, 1988; Wolff and Mulvaney, 1988 and Potts *et al.*, 1992) and Raman scattering measurements (Fukazawa *et al.*, 1998) allowed direct observation of these impurities. These dissolved impurities are generally considered to soften ice and increase deformation (e.g. Raraty and Tabor, 1958; Jones and Glen, 1968; 1969; Nakamura and Jones, 1970; 1973; Glen, 1974; 1975; Dahl – Jensen and Gundestrup, 1987; Shoji and Langway, 1987; Paterson, 1994 and Thorsteinsson *et al.* 1999). Two possible mechanisms have been identified: (a) the substitution of soluble impurities within the ice lattice, creating defects that speed diffusional relaxation and (b) impurities creating point defects in the form of liquid zones or disordered zones at grain boundaries, which subsequently speed diffusional processes allowing faster deformation (Thorsteinsson *et al.*, 1999). The presence of dissolved impurities may also lower the melting point in high stress zones around solid impurity inclusions, which may enhance flow (Budd and Jacka, 1989).

Low concentrations of solid mineral inclusions (e.g. dust, silt, sand and volcanic ash) increase ice softness, it is believed due to the existence of a microscopic water layer around particles (e.g. Swinzow, 1962; Baker and Gerberich, 1979; Fisher and Koerner, 1986; Etchelmeyer and Zhongxiang, 1987; Thorsteinsson *et al.*, 1999 and Cohen, 2000). Silt sized particles have been reported to decrease ice strength (e.g. Holdsworth and Bull, 1970; Baker and Gerberich, 1979; Shoji and Langway, 1985; Song *et al.*, 2004, 2005a and b). However, Budd and Jacka (1989) and Jacka *et al.*, (2003) concluded that solid impurities have little effect on creep deformation, while Nayar *et al.* (1971) and Hooke *et al.*, (1972) found decreasing creep rates with increasing solid impurity content, and ice containing low concentrations of ultra fine amorphous silica particles shows a strength increase with increasing particle content (Nayar *et al.*, 1971, Lange and Ahrens, 1983).

Until recently models of valley glacier flow represented temperate ice as being of a uniform softness. However, Hubbard *et al.* (2003) identified three distinct rheological layers in temperate ice cores recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron and for the first time incorporated a layered ice softness profile into a numerical temperate ice flow model (as had previously been pioneered in models of polythermal glaciers (Payne *et al.*, 2000)). Results suggested a glacier modelled as a homogeneous ice body, to be as much as 65 % larger than that predicted using the multi layered rheology technique, under a glacier retreat scenario in response to a 75 m rise in equilibrium line altitude imposed on the current glacier profile (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003). However, Hubbard *et al.* (2003), in the absence of temperature data from Glacier de Tsanfleuron, were forced to assume a

spatially uniform temperature distribution based on temperature records for Blue Glacier, U.S.A. (Harrison, 1975).

To the author's knowledge no detailed incorporation of a temperate glacier ice temperature profile into a flow model has been attempted to date. Thus, as a first step towards addressing this situation, an accurate, high precision characterization of temperate ice temperature is required.

1.4 Applications of temperate ice temperature research

In addition to the application of temperate ice temperature profiles to ice flow modelling through the direct influence of temperature over ice deformation rate (and to a lesser extent though its influence over crystal growth rates and thus crystallography) the temperature of temperate ice influences the coefficient of friction governing ice sliding (Bowden and Hughes, 1939) and the presence of liquid water in inclusions at grain boundaries within the ice (Mader, 1992 b). Thus, temperate ice temperature investigations are applicable also to studies of glacier sliding and ice liquid water content.

Ice temperature measurements near the glacier surface are of specific application in characterizing the glacier surface energy balance, allowing quantitative assessment of the heat flux away from the surface into the ice during the spring and summer and out of the ice during autumn and winter in response to the annual cycle of surface energy receipt. Similarly, on a diurnal scale, energy transfer into the glacier from short wave solar radiation and energy loss from the glacier surface via nocturnal long wave radiation emission are closely linked to surface ice temperature.

1.5 Temperate glacier temperature profiles

Temperatures are neither spatially nor temporally uniform throughout any ice mass. In the vertical dimension, ice temperature profiles vary systematically at both annual and diurnal timescales. Seasonal variation is driven by climatic characteristics of the glacier location over an annual period, generating a thermally active layer to a depth of 10 – 20 m (Paterson, 1994; Suter *et al.*, 2001; Engelhardt, 2004; Zagorodnov *et al.*, 2006) resulting from the propagation and subsequent degradation of the “winter cold wave” (Paterson, 1994) (Figure 1.2). Diurnal variations are observed to much shallower depths (~ 1 m) mainly in response to radiation variation and synoptic meteorological influences. Below 15 – 20 m depth glacier temperature is dependent on long term surface conditions.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In general the temperature variation experienced over a given time period is large at the surface, decreasing with depth, increasing again near the bed, in response to changes in heat sources and sinks. During winter, sub-freezing air temperatures in contact with the glacier surface cause near surface ice cooling that can influence temperatures in the top 20 m of the glacier. The depth and amplitude of the cold wave propagation varies with location on the glacier as a result of surface ice and snow properties and processes. The heat flux variation over a given period and the subsequent temperature profile below the glacier surface has been predicted using heat transfer theory according to Fourier's law (Paterson, 1994) formulated as:

$$Q = -K \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) \quad (1.5.1)$$

where:

Q = Heat flux,

K = Thermal conductivity (see section 1.6.2),

T = Temperature,

z = Depth.

(The minus sign indicates heat flows from regions of high to low temperature)

Paterson (1994 p206) stated that the temperature profile at any time in the annual cycle of temperatures, can be determined from the following parameterization:

$$T(z,t) = T_v \exp(-z\sqrt{\omega/2\kappa}) \sin(\omega t - z\sqrt{\omega/2\kappa}) \quad (1.5.2)$$

where:

$T(z,t)$ = Temperature at depth z at time t ,

T_v = Amplitude of temperature variation,

$\omega/2\pi$ = Frequency of variation,

z = Depth,

κ = Thermal diffusivity.

It is evident that low frequency, high amplitude thermal disturbances (the annual temperature cycle) penetrate to a greater depth than high frequency low amplitude, diurnal cycles. Sanderson (1978) calculated diurnal temperature variations were reduced to 5 % of their surface amplitude by 0.5 m depth while the annual cycle penetrated to a depth of 10 m before being attenuated to 5 %.

Reported temperature profiles often follow a curved lineation down through the ice (e.g. Sverdrup, 1935). Profiles generated solely from conductive heat exchange (due to a lack of melting and subsequent latent heat release on refreezing) on the Greenland ice sheet, displaying the penetration and degradation of the winter cold wave, are shown in Figure 1.2. Winter profiles display temperatures at depth which are warmer than those at the surface, due to the time lag

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

associated with the penetration of the winter cold wave. Temperatures at depth are indicative of the heat supplied to the ice during the previous summer. Contrary to continental scale cold ice sheet scenarios, temperate glaciers (as outlined below) experience ice surface melting, percolation and refreezing of melt at depth within the ice contributing to substantial heating near the surface, causing more rapid degradation of the winter cold wave following the onset of melt.

Anomalous to this one dimensional theory however is the temperature profile recovered from a borehole in Grenzgletscher, Switzerland (Suter *et al.*, 2001). Grenzgletscher displays a heat-flow inversion, with a temperature minima at ~ 100 m below the surface, caused by cold ice advection to this depth from higher regions of the accumulation area, with temperatures increasing towards both the surface and the bed.

Figure 1.2: Calculated seasonal variations in firn temperature in central Greenland.
Source: Paterson (1994, p208).

At the glacier surface spatial temperature variation occurs due to glacier surface topography and the altitudinal range through which the ice flows. Air temperature exerts a control over the temperature of the ice surface directly in contact with it, with warmer mean annual air temperatures in the lower altitude ablation zone, decreasing according to the lapse rate from the snout to the head of the glacier. An example of such altitude controlled ice temperature was observed in the 10 m ice temperatures on the Athabasca glacier, which were reported to decrease with altitude at a rate of 0.3 °C per 100 m rise in elevation (Paterson, 1972).

1.5.1 Previous studies of temperate glacier temperatures

Paterson (1971 and 1972) and Harrison (1972 and 1975) measured the temperature distribution of temperate ice using borehole investigations. Ice temperature distribution near the surface is directly related to surface air temperature and energy transfers, mediated by snow pack and ice physical properties, particularly thermal conductivity. The temperature profile is controlled by heat exchange with the atmosphere by means of convection, conduction (allowing direct energy transfer between air and ice) and advection by melt water percolating through snow and firn layers to the ice surface and subsequent latent heat release on refreezing.

Savage and Paterson (1963) report the temperature of the upper 100 m in Athabasca glacier, Canada, to be somewhat below melting point. Paterson (1971) measured temperatures at depths down to 257 m in boreholes in the Athabasca glacier, by means of thermistor strings and reported an average temperature of -0.5°C at a depth of 10 m in the ablation area. Temperatures above 70 m depth were significantly below the pressure melting point (however the mean difference was only 0.01°C) with temperatures below 70 m being insignificantly different to the pressure melting temperature. In the lower half of two boreholes, heat generation attributed to internal deformation was sufficient to maintain the ice temperature slightly below that of the pressure melting point, while freezing of water within the ice was postulated to provide heat for this purpose elsewhere in the glacier. Paterson (1971) also noted the effects water-filled boreholes would have on the temperature field in the ice surrounding the hole and based on the formulation of Bullard ((1947) in Paterson, 1971) concluded; if water stood in the hole for three months it would subsequently require five months of cooling for the disturbance to reduce to 5 % of its initial value. The glacier was shown to be temperate in its accumulation area but not in the ablation area (Paterson, 1971) and differences between the pressure melting point and the observed temperature below 17 m were attributed to either impurities in the ice or due to Bader's (1950) melting around bubbles mechanism at bubble pressure rather than hydrostatic pressure, (Figure 1.3).

Paterson (1972) also concluded the Athabasca glacier was temperate in the accumulation area but not in the ablation area, as insufficient heat was conducted into the ice surface to return it to melting point following the previous winter's cooling. Percolation of melt-water and subsequent latent heat release following refreezing and penetration of solar radiation were both considered negligible heat sources in the ablation area as the calculated rate of water penetration was less than the ablation rate. Ablation was thus the main factor prominent in eliminating the winter cold

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

wave at Athabasca. It was noted that the glacier was not strictly temperate (see Section 1.2 for definitions of temperate ice).

Figure 1.3: Temperature profile from the Athabasca glacier, Canada. The solid line represents the pressure melting point, deviations from this line are suggested to be the consequence of impurities in the ice and/or the presence of bubbles. Source: Paterson (1971).

Harrison (1972) in a study of Blue Glacier, USA, observed temperatures ranging from $-0.03\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ near the surface to $-0.13\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a depth of 105 m to an accuracy of ± 0.02 or $0.03\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Water filled boreholes freeze closed via conduction of heat into the surrounding ice; this process was used in conjunction with the energy supplied to drill boreholes to calculate ice temperatures. The temperature was on average $\sim 0.05\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ colder than pressure melting point, as a consequence of small amounts of soluble impurities (both air and salts of atmospheric origin) lowering the melting point.

Further observations of englacial temperatures in Blue Glacier were conducted by means of strings of glass encapsulated thermistors (Harrison, 1975). Temperatures were measured to depths of 192 and 72 m with an accuracy of ± 0.002 to $0.005\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperatures were found not to be in agreement with simple models of temperate glacier temperature profile. Temperatures varied linearly with depth (from $-0.02\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5.6 m to $-0.16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 192 m below the surface) except near the surface (which may have been attributed to firm permeability) and were colder than predicted at all depths (Harrison, 1975). Paterson (1972) suggested the existence of a near

surface layer in the ablation area of temperate glaciers which was “considerably colder than 0 °C”, while Harrison (1975) stated that “it is doubtful that such a layer exists at all”, if it did, it was less than 5 m thick on Blue Glacier, (Harrison, 1975).

1.5.2 Melting point temperature of temperate ice

The melting point for pure ice at atmospheric pressure at sea level is 0 °C. The melting temperature of glacier ice, however, is lower than that of pure ice, the temperature of which is determined primarily by the hydrostatic pressure, dissolved impurity composition and bubble content of the ice. The depressed melting point varies systematically with the controlling properties throughout the glacier. Ice melting temperature is unrelated to the grain size or the structure of the ice.

Hydrostatic pressure depression

Ice melting temperature is a function of hydrostatic pressure (Fish and Zaretshy, 1997); ice overburden pressure facilitates melting at the pressure melting point with a temperature below 0 °C. The pressure melting temperature was calculated by Paterson (1971) for the Athabasca glacier using a gradient of 0.00742 deg bar⁻¹, equivalent to 6.62 x 10⁻⁴ °C m⁻¹ of ice. The depression of the melting point by overburden pressure with air saturated water (accounting for ice containing bubbles) has been parameterized by Paterson (1994, p.212) in the form:

$$T = T_0 - \beta' P \quad (1.5.3)$$

where:

T = Temperature,

T_0 = Triple point temperature (0.01 °C),

β' = Rate of change of melting point with pressure (9.8 x 10⁻⁵ K (kPa)⁻¹),

P = Pressure.

Bubble content depression

Bader (1950) and Raymond (1976) have considered the thermal effects of bubbles in temperate ice from Malaspina Glacier, Alaska and Blue Glacier, Washington, USA respectively. Bader (1950) suggested a mechanism whereby as ice rises toward the surface in the ablation zone due to surface melting. Air pressure in the bubbles in the ice become out of equilibrium with the hydrostatic pressure, subsequently equilibrium is re-established via melting around the bubbles. This theory is supported by observations made by Raymond (1976) in which bubbles were observed to be partially filled with liquid, isolated from veins between crystals, however, it is suggested that most of the liquid observed by Bader (1950) originates from the conduction of heat from external sources into the ice as it neared the glacier surface. Paterson (1971) argued

that similar to Bader (1950) differences between the predicted pressure melting temperature of temperate ice in the Athabasca Glacier and the observed temperatures may partially be due to heat supplied by pressure melting of ice around air bubbles and suggested that the ice was at the melting point corresponding to the bubble pressure and not the hydrostatic pressure. Raymond (1976) concluded that “in a zone where ice is being unloaded by ablation or vertical strain rate and bubbles have a pressure in excess of the ice mean stress, the bubbles will force the ice temperature to be lower than the “pressure melting curve.”

Solute content depression

Further melting point depression below that due to pressure has been attributed to the curvature of the solid – liquid interfaces of ice crystals and the presence of impurities (Mader, 1992b). On Blue Glacier, Washington, U.S.A. an impurity content (salt plus carbon dioxide) of 5.5 mol m^{-3} in the liquid contained at the intersections at triple grain boundaries, (assuming the impurity molecules are dissociated) resulted in an ice temperature lowering of about $0.020 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Harrison and Raymond, 1976). On the Athabasca Glacier solute concentrations of 1 part in 10^6 with liquid water contents of 1 % were suggested to decrease the melting point by $0.005 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Paterson, 1971). Solute content driven melting point depression is expressed by Paterson (1994, p.212) in the form:

$$T = T_0 - \beta' P - \frac{An'}{W'} \quad (1.5.4)$$

where:

T = Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$),

T_0 = Triple point temperature ($0.01 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$),

β' = Rate of change of melting point with pressure ($9.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K (kPa)}^{-1}$),

P = Pressure (Pa),

A = $1.86 \text{ (K kg mol}^{-1}\text{)}$,

n' = Impurity concentration (mol kg^{-1}),

W' = Fractional water content by weight.

In laboratory experiments ice temperatures closely follow pressure melting point during compression, however, during rapid decompression and ice expansion, temperature initially only returns 75 % of the way to pressure melting temperature, then is warmed by thermal conduction (Goodman *et al.*, 1979). A consequence of these findings is that in the ablation area near the surface, temperatures may be below the pressure melting temperature following ice unloading as ablation occurs.

1.6 Physical properties of snow and ice

In order to interpret and model temperature profiles through temperate ice, knowledge of the physical and thermal properties of the ice is required, typical values for snow, ice, liquid water and air are given in Table 1.1.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Comments</i>	<i>Density (kg m⁻³)</i>	<i>Heat capacity (J m⁻³ K⁻¹ x 10⁶)</i>	<i>Specific heat (J kg⁻³ K⁻¹ x10³)</i>	<i>Thermal conductivity (W m⁻¹ K⁻¹)</i>	<i>Thermal diffusivity (m² s⁻¹ x10⁻⁶)</i>
Snow	Fresh	50 - 200	0.21	2.09	0.08	0.10
	Old	200 - 500	0.84	2.09	0.42	0.40
Ice	(0 °C)	830 - 917	1.93	2.097	2.10	1.09
Water	Still (4 °C)	1000	4.18	4.18	0.57	0.14
Air	Still (10 °C)	1.2	0.0012	1.01	0.025	20.50

Table 1.1: Thermal properties of snow, ice, water and air, compiled from Oke (1987) and Paterson (1994).

1.6.1 Density

In the accumulation area the density of firn and ice increases with depth as a result of compaction, caused by the weight of overlying ice. Air is forced out of the firn as pore spaces close and transition to ice occurs, subsequently bubbles compress at depth in the ice allowing ice densities of ~ 830 to ~ 910 kg m⁻³ once bubbles have formed. In the ablation area, surface ablation causes an unloading of the ice which partially expands, becoming less dense, thus ice density is depth dependent and changes under the influence of the temperature variation experienced within the glacier (Shumskiy, 1960). Density variation resulting from the compression or expansion of ice with air inclusions, lags the driving load change due to differences between the external pressure and the pressure within the ice and as a consequence of the time required for plastic-viscous flow to occur (Shumskiy, 1960). An empirical density – depth formula is given by Schytt (1958) in the form:

$$\rho_z = \rho_i - (\rho_i - \rho_s) \exp(-Cz) \quad (1.6.1)$$

where:

ρ_z = Density at depth z ,

ρ_i = Density of ice (917 kg m⁻³),

ρ_s = Density of surface snow,

z = Depth,

C = Constant for a given site, a first estimate of C is $1.9 / z_i$ where z_i is the depth of the firn ice transition.

For pure ice at 0 °C the density is assumed to be 917 kg m⁻³ (Paterson, 1994).

1.6.2 Thermal conductivity

“Thermal conductivity is defined as the proportionality constant between the heat transport and the temperature gradient” (Sturm *et al.*, 1997). The defining Fourier equation states:

$$Q = -K \frac{dT}{dz} \quad (1.6.2)$$

where:

Q = Heat flux,
 K = Thermal conductivity,
 dT/dz = Temperature gradient.

The thermal conductivity of pure ice at 0 °C is 2.10 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Paterson, 1994 p.205) but in reality the value varies with temperature and density. Snow is an excellent thermal insulator, quantified via its low thermal conductivity (Sturm *et al.*, 1997) (Table 1.1). Snow thermal conductivity is widely expressed in terms of its density (Van Dusen, 1929; Yen, 1965; Ostin and Anderson, 1991) however grain size, grain type and bonding differences result in an order of magnitude thermal conductivity variation for a given density (Sturm *et al.*, 1997). Thermal conductivity has been parameterized in terms of density via the Van Dusen (1929) equation applicable to snow, firn and ice, to give a lower limit (Paterson, 1994, p205):

$$K = 2.1 \times 10^{-2} + (4.2 \times 10^{-4})\rho + (2.2 \times 10^{-9})\rho^3 \quad (1.6.3)$$

where:

K = Thermal conductivity (W m⁻¹ K⁻¹),
 ρ = Density (kg m⁻³).

While the Schwerdtfeger (1963) formula gives the upper limit (Paterson, 1994, p205):

$$K = \frac{2K_i \rho}{(3\rho_i - \rho)} \quad (1.6.4)$$

where:

K = Thermal conductivity (W m⁻¹ K⁻¹),
 ρ = Density (kg m⁻³) and suffix i denotes the value for ice.

Thermal conductivity of ice varies inversely with temperature by ~ 0.17 % °C⁻¹, the same may be expected for snow (Langham, 1981). Mean reported snow thermal conductivities for a number of observations in different studies, range from 0.012 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Ostin and Andersson, 1991) to 1.220 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Lange, 1985), while Sturm *et al.* (1997), in possibly the most detailed analysis of snow thermal conductivity, report values in the range 0.021 to 0.654 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ for dry snow types ranging from fresh snow though to very hard wind slabs. For further details see Section 5.5.3 for snow thermal conductivity and Section 6.2.1 for ice thermal conductivity.

1.6.3 Thermal diffusivity

The thermal diffusivity of ice is temperature dependent, however the temperature dependence is usually neglected because the effect is relatively small (Hooke, 1998). Thermal diffusivity is calculated from thermal conductivity in the form (Paterson, 1994, p.206):

$$k = \frac{K}{\rho c} \quad (1.6.5)$$

where:

- k = Thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$),
- K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
- ρ = Density (kg m^{-3}),
- c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$).

1.7 Processes controlling snow and ice temperature profiles

1.7.1 Heat transfer between the glacier surface and the atmosphere

Energy transfer between the glacier surface and the atmosphere occurs primarily via the processes of radiation exchange (both long and short wave), convection (sensible and latent heat) and a limited amount of conduction to the boundary layer air in direct contact with the ice. Glacier surface temperatures represent the balance between atmospheric heat fluxes and the conductive heat transfer into the glacier, which in turn depends on the history of previous heat exchanges and surface temperatures (Luce and Tarboton, 2001).

1.7.2 Heat transfer processes through the snow

Snow consists of three phases; air, water vapour and ice, resulting in more complex heat transfer than in solid glacier ice (see below), with five energy transfer processes (Sturm *et al.*, 1997):

- 1 Conduction through the ice lattice (55 – 60 % of heat transfer (De Quervain, 1956)),
- 2 Conduction through air in the pore spaces,
- 3 Latent heat transport across pore spaces due to vapour sublimation and condensation (30 – 40 % of heat transfer (Colbeck, 1993)),
- 4 Radiation (reported to be several orders of magnitude smaller than other mechanisms, Sturm *et al.*, (1997)),
- 5 Convection.

Conduction through the ice matrix, convection and radiation penetration dominate processes in dry snow packs. Wet snow cannot sustain the temperature gradients necessary for conduction in the same way, thus it cannot conduct significant amounts of heat (Langham, 1981). Heat transfer in wet snow is consequently dominated by percolation and refreezing of liquid water. Within the non saturated snow pack energy fluxes caused by convection, transporting both sensible and

latent heat as air moves through the pack, in part driven by wind pumping mechanisms (Clarke *et al.*, 1987), are small in comparison with those from molecular conduction process. However, convective transfer is of importance in controlling snow crystal metamorphosis, with vapour transport playing a key role in post depositional crystallographic changes (see Section 1.3 for crystallographic influence over ice flow) (Albert, 2002). The presence of ice lenses formed via the burial of previously melting surfaces or wind crusts act to limit convection (and water percolation) in temperate snow and as such convective heat transfer can often be considered negligible compared to conductive transfer. Heat transfer mechanisms within the temperate glacier snow pack thus vary with water content and consequently time of year, dominated by conduction during dry periods, with a small amount of radiation penetration, changing to advective transfer via water percolation and latent heat release on freezing as the snow pack becomes isothermal and begins to melt in late spring.

1.7.3 Heat transfer processes through ice

The dominant heat transfer mechanism in glacial ice is conduction based on Fourier theory, in the form:

$$Q = -K\nabla T \quad (1.7.1)$$

where:

Q = Heat flow,
 K = Thermal conductivity,
 T = Temperature.

Additional smaller heat transfers occur via radiation penetration (to shallow depths in the absence of snow cover), liquid water percolation and latent heat release following refreezing deeper within the glacier.

1.8 Surface heat fluxes

It is generally accepted that for mid latitude alpine glaciers the main sources of melt energy during summer are absorption of radiation and turbulent heat fluxes in a ratios of approximately 3:1 or greater, with maritime locations giving a ratio closer to 1:1 respectively as a consequence of different synoptic climate conditions, with anticyclones dominating continental areas and cyclones dominating maritime regions (Willis *et al.*, 2002). Radiation: turbulent energy supply ratios of greater than 3:1 are reported by De la Cassiniere (1974); Rothlisberger and Lang (1987); Mattson and Gardner (1989); Calanaca and Heuberger (1990); Van de Wal *et al.* (1992); Pluss and Mazzoni (1994) and Willis *et al.* (2002), ratios of 3:1 by La Chapelle (1959); Ambach (1963); Ambach and Hoinkes (1963); Zhongyuan and Xinzhi (1985); Rothlisberger and Lang (1987); Marks and Dozier (1992); Konzelmann and Braithwaite (1995); Cline (1997) and

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Oerlemans and Knap (1998). Ratios of 2:1 are given in studies by Braithwaite and Olesen (1990); Braithwaite (1995a); Hock and Holmgren (1996 and 2005), while ratios of 1:1 are reported by Streten and Wendler (1968); Wendler and Streten (1969); Fohn (1973); Martin (1975); Poggi (1977); Hogg *et al.* (1982); Harding (1986) and Hay and Fitzharris (1988a). Untersteiner (1961) and De la Casiniere (1974) presented extreme cases where sensible and latent heat fluxes cancelled, thus all energy for melt was derived from net radiation in, contrast to Prowse and Owens (1982) and Moore and Owens (1984) which report exceptional cases where turbulent fluxes were the dominant heat sources for snow melt.

Prevailing air masses, altitude and terrain features influence the relative importance of turbulent and radiative heat fluxes (Male and Granger, 1981). Surface energy exchange also exhibits distinct seasonal differences driven by changes in air temperature, wind speed and radiation and glacier surface characteristics (Albert and Hawley, 2000). Unfortunately many of the energy balance studies conducted on glaciers are limited to a short time period during summer months (e.g. Ambach, 1979; Kuhn, 1981 and Munro, 1989).

The energy flux at the glacier surface (fluxes towards the surface are considered positive) is the sum of the net short wave radiation, net long wave radiation, sensible heat, latent heat and heat flux from precipitation (Figure 1.4). The energy flux available for melt (Q_M) has been parameterized by Male and Gray (1981) in the following way:

$$Q_M = Q_{SW} + Q_{LW} + Q_H + Q_{LE} + Q_I + Q_P - dU/dt \quad (1.8.1)$$

where:

Q_M = Energy available for surface melt,

Q_{SW} = Net shortwave radiation flux,

Q_{LW} = Net long wave radiation flux at the snow – air, ice – air, interface,

Q_H = Sensible heat flux from the air at the snow / ice - air interface,

Q_{LE} = Flux of latent heat (evaporation, sublimation, condensation) at the snow
air, ice – air, interface,

Q_I = Conductive heat flux at the snow / ice interface,

Q_P = Precipitation heat flux,

dU/dt = Rate of change of internal (stored) energy per unit area of snow cover / ice mass.

Figure 1.4: Schematic diagram of energy exchanges at the glacier surface. Re-drawn and modified from Van der Veen (1999).

When the surface energy balance is positive, at temperatures below 0 °C, energy is used to warm the snow pack and / or glacier ice. Once the glacier surface is raised to 0 °C positive excess energy in the energy balance generates melt. The energy used in melt is related to the depth of ice ablated following Hay and Fitzharris (1988b) in the form:

$$M_i = \frac{Q_M}{L_f \rho_i} \quad (1.8.2)$$

where:

- M_i = Ice melt (m^{-3}),
- Q_M = Energy available for melt (J),
- L_f = Latent heat of fusion (0.333 MJkg^{-1}),
- ρ_i = Density of ice.

Refer to Section 1.11 for details of studies pertaining to glacier surface energy balance modelling.

1.8.1 Net radiation (Q_R)

Net radiation is the main energy source for melting in many alpine glacial environments. Complex models have been derived for net radiation in snow covered mountainous terrain (Dozier, 1980) however, these are hungry in terms of input data and their use is limited to clear sky conditions (Hock and Holmgren, (2005). Net radiation or radiation heat flow is the balance of incoming and out going shortwave radiation in the wavelength range 0.3 to 2.2 μm and incoming and outgoing long wave radiation falling within the range 6.8 to 100 μm (between 2.2

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

and 6.8 μm radiation levels are low (less than 5% of the total)) (Geiger, 1966), from Braithwaite *et al.* (1998) net radiation is expressed as:

$$Q_R = (SW \downarrow + SW_d)(1 - \alpha) + (LW \downarrow - LW \uparrow) \quad (1.8.3)$$

where:

Q_R = Net radiation,

$SW \downarrow$ = Direct beam solar radiation,

SW_d = Diffuse fraction of solar radiation,

α = Albedo,

$LW \downarrow$ = Long wave sky radiation emission,

$LW \uparrow$ = Long wave radiation emission from the glacier surface.

Short wave radiation

Short wave radiation incident upon the surface is composed of two solar components (McClung and Schaerer, 1993), the direct beam component ($SW \downarrow$) and the diffuse component (SW_d) scattered toward and away from the surface within the atmosphere. Incoming short wave is partly reflected at the glacier surface, that which is not reflected penetrates into the surface. The amount of reflectance is governed by the surface albedo (α), which is dependent upon numerous factors (see below) including radiation wavelength, grain size and impurity content of the surface (Bohren and Barkstrom, 1972 and Brun *et al.*, 1989) and snow density (Bergen, 1970).

Direct beam component ($SW \downarrow$)

The amount of solar radiation, transmitted through the atmosphere, reaching the glacier surface is dependent upon time of day, topography, cloud cover and atmospheric turbidity. In addition short wave direct beam solar radiation is a function of latitude, longitude and time, through the sun's azimuth and zenith angles, consequently variations exist in the solar radiation reaching the top of the atmosphere (Greuell and Konzelmann, 1994). Diurnal variation results in maximum short wave radiation receipt at the local solar noon. The direct beam component is attenuated through the atmosphere via absorption by ozone, water vapour, oxygen, carbon dioxide and methane. Additionally Rayleigh scattering occurs as a consequence of atmospheric molecules and aerosols. Direct short wave radiation incident upon a glacier surface can be transmitted, reflected or absorbed (Oke, 1987). Reflection is controlled by the surface albedo (see below) while penetration into the glacier is controlled by Beer's law (see below). During snow cover conditions in mountainous regions the shortwave incoming radiation receipt is further complicated by reflection from surrounding snow covered slopes (Male and Granger, 1981).

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Garnier and Ohmura (1970) express the direct clear day radiation component, SW_{\downarrow} , falling upon a slope as:

$$SW_{\downarrow} = \left(\frac{I_o}{r^2} \right) \int_0^m p \cos(XAS) dH' \quad (1.8.4)$$

where:

I_o = Solar constant (1.37 kW / m²),

r = Radius vector of the earth's orbit,

p = Mean transmissivity of the atmosphere along the zenith path,

m = Optical air mass (which is the ratio of the distance the sun's rays travel through the atmosphere to the depth of the atmosphere along the zenith path),

(XAS) = Angle of incidence of the sun's rays on the slope (X is a unit normal vector pointing away from the surface and S is a unit vector expressing the sun's position),

H' = Hour angle measured from solar noon.

Values for I_o , r and m are calculated from planetary orbits and are available from standard meteorological tables, for further details refer to Garnier and Ohmura (1970).

Diffuse component (SW_d)

Diffuse short wave radiation refers to radiation which is redirected towards the surface through Rayleigh and Mie scattering mainly by aerosols and water droplets in the atmosphere. The magnitude of the diffuse short wave radiation varies through the day with maxima early in the morning and late in the evening due to the longer path taken through the atmosphere by the radiation (Oke, 1987). List (1968) reports a simple expression for calculation of the diffuse shortwave radiation component under conditions of cloudless sky in the form:

$$SW_d = 0.5[(1 - a_w - a_o)I_t - SW_{\downarrow}] \quad (1.8.5)$$

where:

a_w = Radiation absorbed by water vapour,

a_o = Radiation absorbed by ozone,

I_t = Extra – terrestrial radiation on a horizontal surface = $(I_o / r^2) \int \cos z_s dH$ (tabulated by List (1968)),

r = Radius vector of the earth's orbit,

z_s = Sun's zenith distance,

SW_{\downarrow} = Direct radiation reaching a horizontal surface of the Earth.

The factor 0.5 represents the assumption that half of the incident radiation is scattered in the direction of the surface whilst the other half is scattered away.

Albedo (α)

Of the radiation reaching the glacier surface a fraction is reflected away by the surface and the remaining radiation is absorbed. The magnitude of the reflected fraction is determined by the surface albedo (the reflected radiation divided by the total radiation). Surface albedo is defined as “the broadband hemispherically averaged reflectance in approximately the spectral range 0.3 – 2.8 μm , which controls the net shortwave radiation flux at a glacier surface” Brock *et al.*, (2000b).

Albedo is defined from the following:

$$Q_{SW} = (1 - \alpha) (SW\downarrow + SW_d) \quad (1.8.6)$$

where:

Q_{SW} = Net short wave radiation absorbed by a snow surface,

α = Albedo,

$(SW\downarrow + SW_d)$ = Incident short wave radiation (both direct beam and diffuse).

Snow albedo is generally controlled by grain size (Warren and Wiscombe, 1980 and Wiscombe and Warren, 1980), concentration of light absorbing impurities (Brock *et al.*, 2000b), liquid water content (Colbeck, 1979) and with variation due to different sun angles, expected to be less than 5 % (Gerland *et al.*, 1999). Freshly fallen snow (with a density of ~ 100 to $\sim 150 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) has an albedo of 0.82, when subject to purely aging and compaction processes it reaches a minimum albedo of 0.5 after 50 days (Cherry *et al.*, 2005). Light dustings of snow (principally onto ice or debris covered ice) at all times of year, though especially in summer consequently dramatically increase the glacier albedo, with dramatic effects in terms of ablation reduction (Hoinkes, 1968).

Ice albedo is dependent upon age, crystal structure, surface morphology, dust and soot concentrations, moranic debris inclusions (Bøggild *et al.*, 1996 and Cutler and Munro, 1996), the presence of liquid water in intercrystalline veins and at the surface (Brock *et al.*, 2000b), bubbles and cracks in the ice surface (Mellor, 1977) solar elevation, slope and aspect, cloudiness (Konzelmann and Braithwaite, 1995 and Oerlemans, Unpublished) and shows a spectral dependency (Warren, 1982). Albedo for glacier surfaces vary from >0.9 for fresh dry snow, ~ 0.4 for clean ice and > 0.1 for debris covered ice (Paterson, 1994).

Pure ice and snow are weakly absorptive, where as dust particles are strongly absorptive at visible wavelengths, thus a small dust covering can greatly increase absorption, reducing albedo (Warren and Wiscombe, 1980). Snow albedo with a thin dust layer increases over time up to a limit as a result of aggregation of the dust particles (Adhkiary *et al.*, 1996 and 1997). However for an ice

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

surface a similar albedo increase is limited by the “diffusion loss” of particles with melt water (Adhkiary *et al.*, 2000 and 2002) or the removal of fines by intense rainfall events, especially following periods of surface melt dominated by turbulent fluxes where a smooth ice surface is produced with highly mobile fine debris (Brock, 2004).

Albedo also shows variability over diurnal time scales, with higher values in the early morning and evening due to direct reflection during these periods, resulting from patterns of solar altitude change (Hubley, 1957; Streten and Wendler, 1968) and physical changes in the surface properties due to melting and re-freezing (Oke, 1987, p.98). Cloud cover is the major atmospheric influence over albedo, albedo increases with increasing cloud cover and decreases as cloud height increases (Male and Granger, 1981). Greuell and Konzelmann (1994) used an albedo difference of 0.05 between cloudy and clear sky conditions to account for the cloud cover control over albedo, inferred from Ohmura (1980). Under high albedo conditions an increase in cloudiness resulted in higher values of net radiation whilst under low albedo conditions net radiation decreased under increased cloud cover (Serreze and Bradley, 1987).

Greuell and Konzelmann (1994) present a representation for the albedo, α , in terms of density of the snow or ice at the surface and the cloud cover such that:

$$\alpha = \alpha_i + (\rho_i - \rho_s) \frac{(\alpha_s - \alpha_i)}{(\rho_s - \rho_i)} + 0.05(\dot{c} - 0.5) \quad (1.8.7)$$

where:

α = Albedo,

ρ = Density,

\dot{c} = Cloud amount,

Subscript i denotes ice and subscript s denotes fresh snow.

ρ_i = Density in the uppermost grid element of the model (surface),

α_s = Snow surface albedo,

α_i = Ice surface albedo.

Spatial and temporal variation in surface albedo on Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland, has been studied by Klok *et al.*, (2003). Spatially heterogeneous banding in albedo was reported, these bands were believed to be caused by high debris concentration in certain areas of the glacier tongue. Mean albedo was very high in March and April (> 0.90) but decreased into the summer as the snow pack ablated reaching a minimum of 0.25 in late August. Spatial and temporal albedo variations associated with the decay of the winter snow pack on a temperate glacier (Haut Glacier d’Arolla) were also examined by Brock *et al.* (2000a) using a semi-distributed surface

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

energy balance model (Arnold *et al.*, 1996) and were found to exert a strong control over the magnitude of surface energy fluxes under high energy weather conditions but exerted a lesser control under low energy conditions. Towards the end of the ablation period the albedo for the remaining snow was close to that for ice and tended to increase with elevation (however, ice albedo decreased down glacier due to increasing debris content in accordance with Oerlemans (1992, 1993)).

Penetration into snow and ice

Incident short wave radiation that is not reflected penetrates the surface. Penetration of radiation is low and shows a strong spectral dependence (Perovich, 2007) and is assumed to follow Fick's second law of diffusion (Giddings and La Chapelle, 1961). The wavelength of the incident radiation, grain size, free water content and the formation of sequential layering with different optical properties in the snow pack control the penetration into snow. The decay of the incident shortwave radiation penetration into the ice or snow follows an exponential decrease parameterized by Beer's Law (Oke, 1987) suggesting penetration depths as deep as 1 m in snow and up to 10 m in ice. Beer's law takes the form:

$$SW \downarrow_z = SW \downarrow e^{-az} \quad (1.8.8)$$

where:

$SW \downarrow_z$ = Shortwave incident at depth z ,

a = Extinction coefficient (dependent upon wavelength and the nature of the transmitting medium),

$SW \downarrow$ = Direct beam solar radiation.

Any radiation which penetrates into the snow in the top tens of centimetres is scattered repeatedly and eventually re-emerges at the surface (Brandt and Warren, 1993).

Significant amounts of short wave radiation may penetrate patches of bubble free ice (Paterson, 1972). In bubbly ice however, radiation is scattered by the bubbles embedded in the ice reducing the depth of penetration (Bohren and Barkstrom, 1972). Lliboutry (1964 in Paterson, 1972) gives a radiation extinction coefficient at the glacier surface of 0.028 mm^{-1} decreasing to 0.0018 mm^{-1} at depths below 0.2 m implying 99% of radiation is absorbed in the first 1.85 m of ice, however Weller (1968) concluded radiation was an important means of heat transfer even at a depth of 4 m.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Physically based modelling to simulate the penetration of radiation into snow, taking account of the spectrally dependant interactions between radiation and snow grains has shown that snow before the onset of melt attenuates radiation more than coarse grained snow which has been subject to melting, while impurities within the snow reduce the transparency to radiation (Gerland *et al.*, 2000).

Fohn, (1973) reported 20 % of daily snow melt was generated internally within the snow pack as a result of penetration of solar radiation, consistent with Brandt and Warren's (1993) report that the bulk of solar heating was concentrated in the top few millimetres of the snow pack. Carrol (1982) and Ohmura (1984) however observed no subsurface temperature maxima caused by radiation penetration into snow and concluded the bulk of absorbed radiation must occur at the surface. The penetration of short wave radiation into surface ice may result in diurnal temperature variations in the ablation area during summer. Paterson (1972) however concluded that influences of penetration of incident solar radiation were small and could be neglected in the modelling of the temperature of the Athabasca glacier.

Long wave

Long wave radiation is emitted by all objects with a temperature greater than absolute zero (-273.15 °C (0 K)), the magnitude of which is proportional to the fourth power of the object temperature, while the wavelength of the emitter radiation is proportional to the reciprocal of the temperature. Net long wave radiation is the sum of the long wave incoming radiation minus the long wave emitted radiation.

Incoming radiation (LW↓)

Water vapour, carbon dioxide and ozone in the atmosphere emit long wave radiation in all directions in proportions of ~81%, ~17% and ~2% respectively, a component of which is received at the glacier surface. In the lower atmosphere, water vapour is the main long wave radiation source. Thus the presence of all cloud types increases long wave incoming radiation, especially low dense cloud, fog and clouds associated with snowfall (Serreze and Bradley, 1987). The magnitude of the emitted flux is dependent upon the temperature of the atmosphere from which it is being emitted, such that warmer temperatures result in greater long wave radiation emission.

Incoming long wave radiation can be determined from (Braithwaite and Olesen, 1990):

$$LW \downarrow = \varepsilon^* (\sigma T_a^4) \quad (1.8.9)$$

where:

$LW \downarrow$ = Long wave incoming radiation,
 ε^* = Effective emissivity of the sky,
 σ = Stefan Boltzmann constant,
 T_a = Air temperature.

ε^* is expressed as the emissivity of clear sky and cloud cover :

$$\varepsilon^* = (1 + k' \dot{c}) \varepsilon_0 \quad (1.8.10)$$

where:

k' = Constant depending on cloud type (assumed to be 0.26),
 \dot{c} = Cloud cover (as a proportion of the sky),
 ε_0 = Emissivity of clear sky.

According to Ohmura (1981) clear sky emissivity is:

$$\varepsilon_0 = 8.733 \times 10^{-3} T_a^{0.788} \quad (1.8.11)$$

The effect of cloud attenuation varies throughout the year, for equal cloudiness attenuation is greatest in August and September and smallest in April and May, due to systematic seasonal variation in cloud type (Greuell and Oerlemans, 1986).

Emitted radiation (LW \uparrow)

The amount of long wave radiation emitted from a surface is controlled by the temperature of the emitting surface by means of Stefan-Boltzmann's law. The emission coefficients of snow and ice at long wave radiation wave lengths are close to 1.0 (Kuhn, 1984 in Greuell and Konzelmann, 1994), thus the long wave radiation emission can be calculated with confidence from the surface temperature (Greuell and Konzelmann, 1994):

$$LW \uparrow = \varepsilon \sigma T_s^4 \quad (1.8.12)$$

where:

$LW \uparrow$ = Long wave emitted radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 ε = Surface emissivity (assumed to be 1.00),
 σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} W m^{-2} K^{-4}$),
 T_s = Surface temperature (K).

Surface emissivity is assumed to reflect that of an ideal black body radiator with a value of 1.00, measurements of snow surface emissivity by Kondo and Yamazawa (1986) support this assumption, reporting an estimated emissivity of 0.970 ± 0.008 . Surface temperature is often not measured thus under non snow conditions the surface temperature is assumed to be 0 °C while

under snow cover conditions the surface temperature of the snow can be derived from the mean daily air temperature using the following formulation from Motoyama *et al.* (1986):

$$T_s = T_a - 3.0 \quad (1.8.13)$$

where:

T_s = Surface temperature (K),

T_a = Air temperature (K).

As the temperature of the glacier surface cannot exceed 0°C the maximum possible value of emitted long wave radiation from the glacier surface is 315.6 Wm⁻².

1.8.2 Turbulent heat fluxes

Turbulent heat fluxes represent the second largest energy transfer after radiation exchanges within the atmospheric boundary layer, defined as the lower part of the atmosphere which is directly influenced by the glacier surface. Contributions of 20 – 40% of the total energy balance have been reported for turbulent fluxes (Kuhn, 1970; Van den Broeke, 1996; Oelemans *et al.*, 1999 and Denby and Greuell, 2000). The transfer of energy from the free atmosphere to the surface is dependent upon the stability of the atmospheric boundary layer, controlled by vertical wind speed and temperature profiles (Kuhn, 1987). Turbulent fluxes in the form of sensible and latent heat transfer occur at the microclimatological scale via both free convection as a result of a parcel of air being less dense than the surrounding air and forced convection where air near the surface is forced into motion when it flows over obstacles, the magnitude of which is controlled by the surface roughness and the speed of horizontal flow (Oke, 1987). At the meso-climatological scale synoptic air mass movements influence the magnitude of turbulent heat fluxes by affecting wind speed, air temperature and moisture content of the atmosphere (Cline, 1997).

Cold dry periods are characterized by evaporation at the glacier surface and negative sensible heat transfer, warm dry periods however, exhibit evaporation and positive sensible heat transfer, while warm wet periods exhibit condensation at the surface with positive sensible heat input (Sverdrup, 1936). When air temperatures are above freezing the sensible heat flux is always toward the surface, whilst the latent heat flux can be in either direction (dependent upon the humidity of the air) (Oerlemans, Unpublished). Under conditions of low humidity, energy is lost from the surface via evaporation, under high humidity conditions, heat is supplied to the surface via condensation. In early summer during the final stages of the snow cover, snow free patches

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

develop, these discontinuities are of importance to profiles of near surface wind, air temperature and humidity (Semadeni – Davies *et al.*, 2004). Previous studies have shown sensible heat to be an order of magnitude greater than latent heat over alpine glaciers (La Chapelle, 1959 and Ambach and Hoinkes, 1963).

Sensible heat (Q_H)

Sensible heat fluxes transfer energy via conduction and convection in response to two driving forces, the temperature gradient between the glacier surface and the atmosphere above and the rate of mixing of air molecules within the boundary layer, controlled by the wind speed, surface roughness and the atmospheric stability. The larger the temperature gradient the larger the sensible heat flux. Within the atmospheric boundary layer, increasing wind speed and shear stress results in increased turbulent mixing and thus a greater sensible heat exchange, toward the glacier surface when air temperatures increase with height into the atmosphere (stable) and away from the surface when temperatures decrease with height (unstable). Increasing stability reduces the sensible heat flux to the glacier and introduces a non linear relationship between heat flux and air temperature (Braithwaite, 1995a). As sensible heat transfer is related to the temperature difference at the snow air interface, large heat transfers operate when marked atmospheric advection occurs such as during föhn in alpine valleys (Hastenrath, 1978). Sensible heat fluxes have been reported during the spring to contribute up to 60 % of the total heat supply to a melting snow pack (Prowse and Owens, 1982).

Latent heat (Q_{LE})

Surface latent heat fluxes transfer energy as a result of a reversible isobaric – isothermal change of phase (evaporation, condensation, melting, fusion or sublimation) (Oke, 1987), in response to the specific humidity gradient between the glacier surface and the atmosphere above enhanced by the rate of mixing of air molecules within the boundary layer, controlled by the wind speed, surface roughness and the atmospheric stability. The changes of state controlling sensible heat transfer include sublimation (ice to vapour transfer); melting (ice to liquid transfer); condensation (vapour to liquid transfer) and freezing (liquid water to ice transfer). Energy is lost when moisture evaporates away from the surface and is added during condensation (Paterson, 1994). When the air in contact with the surface is drier than the surface as a result of vapour pressure decrease with height, the latent heat flux is from the glacier toward the atmosphere as energy is sourced from within the snow pack / near surface ice to drive evaporation and sublimation, however, if the converse were true and vapour pressure increases with height causing the air to be

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

supersaturated with respect to the surface, energy is transferred to the glacier as condensation occurs.

Rapid latent heat transfer is usually prominent during periods with warm moist air masses, developing a strong vapour pressure gradient decreasing towards the glacier surface, under one such storm condition latent heat fluxes reportedly contributed in excess of 20 % to the surface heat balance over a melting snow pack (Prowse and Owens, 1982). The contribution of latent heat transfer via evaporation to ablation is greater in the spring when it accounts for up to 100 % of mass loss before the snow pack becomes isothermal and begins to melt, the importance then decreases through the summer (Wendler and Weller, 1974).

Turbulent heat flux determination

Three methods are available for the determination of turbulent heat fluxes (Denby and Greuell, 2000)

- 1) Direct measurement via eddy correlation methods,
- 2) Calculations based on the aerodynamic profile method,
- 3) Calculations based on the bulk transfer method (residual method).

Eddy correlation measurements

Eddy correlation measurements are the only direct method of turbulent heat flux determination, by means of measuring momentum, heat and water vapour transfers in the atmospheric boundary layer simultaneously using CSAT3 sonic anemometers and KH20 Krypton hygrometers, with fast response times (10 or 20 Hz) from which sensible and latent heat fluxes can be determined. Unfortunately such instruments cannot be left running unattended on an AWS through the winter due to the fragility of the sensors, susceptibility to malfunction during bad weather and the large data volumes generated by the 10 or 20 Hz scan interval, thus these detailed measurements are only made over short study periods when the instruments can be checked and data downloaded daily. Consequently methods are required to reconstruct turbulent heat fluxes from meteorological variables measured by simple AWSs which can be validated against eddy correlation derived flux measurements during field visits.

Various attempts at direct measurement of turbulent fluxes using sonic anemometers over snow and glacier surfaces have been made (e.g. Hicks and Martin, 1972; Munro, 1989; Yen, 1995; Smeets *et al.*, 1998; Harding and Lloyd, 1998; Van der Avoird and Duynkerke, 1999 and Lloyd

et al., 2001) however such studies tend to have only been for short periods of time during manned field campaigns.

Aerodynamic Profile methods

Aerodynamic profile (or flux gradient) methods provide a means of determining turbulent heat fluxes from measurements of wind speed, relative humidity and air temperature made simultaneously at two or more heights using basic meteorological instrumentation in the absence of normally unmeasured values of surface temperature and roughness lengths (e.g. Streten and Wendler, 1968; Wendler and Weller, 1974; Price and Dunne, 1976; Ambach, 1986; Braithwaite and Olesen, 1990; Konzelmann and Braithwaite, 1995; Arnold *et al.*, 1996; Hock and Holmgren, 1996; Cline, 1997; Braithwaite *et al.*, 1998; Williams *et al.*, 1999; Denby and Greuell, 2000 and Hock and Holmgren, 2005). Sensible and latent heat fluxes are determined by calculating differences in these parameters with height and making use of the similarity hypothesis. The similarity hypothesis simply assumes that for an atmospheric boundary layer of a defined depth, transfer rates anywhere within the depth of the layer are the same as at the surface (Williams, 2006). The momentum transfer between the two instrument heights is a function of shear velocity and height as follows (Williams, 2006):

$$K' = \kappa' u^* z' \tag{1.8.14}$$

where:

- K' = Momentum transfer (eddy diffusivity)
- κ' = Von Karman's constant
- u^* = Friction velocity
- z' = Sensor height

Ambach (1986) suggested simple approximations based on experiments over the Greenland ice sheet relating sensible and latent heat fluxes to air temperature and vapour pressure, based on the following assumptions

- 1 A melting glacier surface (temperature equal to 0 °C and vapour pressure equal to the saturation vapour pressure at 0 °C).
- 2 Adiabatic stratification in a Pradtl-type boundary layer with different aerodynamic roughness parameters for ice and snow.

The approximations are as follows:

$$Q_H = K_S \cdot P \cdot T_2 \cdot V_2 \tag{1.8.15}$$

$$Q_{LE} = K_L \cdot \Delta e_2 \cdot V_2 \tag{1.8.16}$$

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

where:

Q_H = Sensible heat flux (W m^{-2}),

Q_{LE} = Latent heat flux (W m^{-2}),

K_S = Coefficient (6.34×10^{-6} mm water d^{-1} for ice and 4.42×10^{-6} mm water d^{-1} for snow),

K_L = Coefficient (for condensation on ice 9.83×10^{-3} mm water d^{-1} , for condensation on snow 6.86×10^{-3} mm water d^{-1} , for evaporation from ice 11.14×10^{-3} mm water d^{-1} and for evaporation from snow 7.77×10^{-3} mm water d^{-1}),

P = Atmospheric pressure (Pa),

T_2 = Air temperature at 2 m above surface ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),

V_2 = Wind speed at 2 m above surface (m s^{-1}),

Δe_2 = Saturation vapour pressure at the glacier surface (Pa).

The flux gradient approach assumes some form of similarity such that the coefficients of turbulent diffusivity and eddy viscosity can be determined from vertical wind profiles above the surface (Braithwaite, 1995a); three wind profiles have been suggested by Grainger and Lister (1966) for glaciological applications:

1. Logarithmic wind profile

The simplest profile of wind is that of speed increasing as the natural logarithm of the height above the surface based on the assumption that heat and momentum fluxes are constant with height within the surface boundary layer; however this is only strictly true for neutral and very stable atmospheric conditions (Grainger and Lister, 1966, Braithwaite, 1995a). While lapse conditions are very unusual over glacier surfaces, aerodynamic stable stratification is common over melting glacier surfaces in summer as the air temperature generally increases in the first few meters above the surface and buoyant forces inhibit turbulence (Grainger and Lister, 1966) air near the surface is cooled, increases in density and remains in position when disturbed, retarding the turbulent exchange (Price and Dunne, 1976). The derivation of sensible heat flux for a logarithmic wind profile neglects the effects of stability and as such the flux may be overestimated at low wind speeds (Braithwaite, 1995a) this needs to be accounted for in turbulent flux calculations (Hock and Holmgren, 1996).

Under stratified conditions stability corrections must be applied in the form of either the complex Monin – Obukov (MO) similarity theory (e.g. Profansky and Dutton, 1984; Munro, 1989 and Garrat, 1992) or the simpler linear bulk Richardson number (Ri) (e.g. Webb, 1965 and Hay and Fitzharris, 1988a). Over a considerable range the two correction factors are essentially identical (Price and Dune, 1976). The Richardson number relates the relative effects of buoyancy to mechanical forces (Oke, 1978) and is used by Braithwaite (1995a) over a melting surface in the form:

$$Ri = (gTz)/(Tu^2) \quad (1.8.17)$$

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

where:

- Ri = Richardson number (positive in a stable atmosphere),
- g = Acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2}),
- T_z = Temperature at height (z) above the surface ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
- T = Air temperature (K),
- u = Wind speed (at 2 m above the surface) (m s^{-1}).

$Ri = 0.01$ represents the boundary between neutral and stable conditions (Oke, 1978)

2. Power Law wind profile

A profile relating wind velocity to a fractional power of the distance from the surface, can be used throughout the whole range of stabilities via modification of the power parameter and has been used by Wallen (1948) over glacier surfaces and Sverdrup (1936) over snow surfaces, however the need to change the parameters have led to difficulties applying laws of this form (Grainger and Lister, 1966).

3. Log-linear wind profile

The log-linear profile approach based on the work of Monin-Obukov, incorporates a function to account for stability into the logarithmic law and has been used over glaciers by Grainger and Lister (1966); De la Casiniere (1974); Munro and Davies (1977); Munro (1989 and 1990) and Duykerke and van den Broeke (1994). The wind at height z is given by (Braithwaite, 1995a):

$$u = (u^* / k') [\ln(z' / z_{0U}) + \alpha(z' / L)] \quad (1.8.18)$$

where:

- u = Wind speed,
- u^* = Friction velocity,
- k' = Von Karman's constant (0.41),
- z' = Sensor height,
- z_{0U} = Surface roughness for wind speed,
- α = Empirical parameter (assumed to be 5 for both wind and temperature (Munro, 1989)),
- L = Obukov scale length.

MO similarity theory assumes a constant turbulent flux layer where fluxes change in the vertical by less than 10 %. A limitation of the MO theory is that determination the Obukov length in the form:

$$L = \frac{\rho c_p u^*{}^3 T}{k' g Q_H} \quad (1.8.19)$$

where:

- L = Obukov scale length,
- ρ = Air density (kg m^{-3}),
- c_p = Specific heat of air, constant pressure ($1005 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$),

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

u^* = Friction velocity (m s^{-1}),
 T = Air temperature (K),
 k' = von Karman's constant (0.41),
 g = Gravitational acceleration (m s^{-2}),
 Q_H = Sensible heat flux (W m^{-2}).

is required to calculate the sensible heat flux however, an a priori knowledge of the sensible heat flux is needed to calculate L . Munro (1989) solved this problem by means of an iterative procedure, found to converge within five iterations. Over glacier surfaces however the application of MO theory is problematic due to the stable atmospheric conditions and the large surface roughness invalidating the assumption of a constant flux layer, to the extent that an undesirable situation arises where the fluxes determined using MO theory become dependent upon the instrument reference height (Munro, 1989). Denby (1999) describes in detail the structure of the turbulent boundary layer over sloping terrain stating that the assumptions of MO theory are often violated.

Under neutral conditions in the lower atmosphere, sensible and latent heat fluxes are then determined as a function of either temperature difference or specific humidity difference between the two instrument heights respectively and wind speed difference as follows (Williams, 2006):

$$Q_H = \rho_a C_a \left[\frac{k'(T_2 - T_1)}{\ln(z_2 / z_1)} \right] \left[\frac{k'(u_2 - u_1)}{\ln(z_2 / z_1)} \right] \quad (1.8.20)$$

where:

Q_H = Sensible heat flux (W m^{-2}),
 ρ_a = Air density (kg m^{-3}),
 C_a = Heat capacity of air (J K^{-1}),
 k' = Von Karmann's constant (0.41),
 T = Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 u = Wind speed (m s^{-1}),
 z = Height above snow surface (m).

$$Q_{LE} = \rho_a C_a \left[\frac{k'(q_2 - q_1)}{\ln(z_2 / z_1)} \right] \left[\frac{k'(u_2 - u_1)}{\ln(z_2 / z_1)} \right] \quad (1.8.21)$$

where:

Q_{LE} = Latent heat flux (W m^{-2}),
 ρ_a = Air density (kg m^{-3}),
 C_a = Heat capacity of air (J K^{-1}),
 k' = Von Karmann's constant (0.41),
 q = Specific humidity (dimensionless),
 u = Wind speed (m s^{-1}),
 z = Height above snow surface (m).

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Denby and Greuell (2000) report profile methods severely underestimate turbulent fluxes when a wind speed maxima is present due to reduced shear and increasing temperature gradients as the maxima is approached and thus the bulk transfer method (outlined below) with its minimal overestimation is considered more appropriate over sloping ice surfaces under the influence of katabatic winds.

Assumptions of the aerodynamic approach include (Hay and Fitzharris, 1988a):

- 1 Log, power or log linear profiles for temperature, humidity and wind speed,
- 2 Equality of scale heights for temperature humidity and wind speed,
- 3 Similarity of exchange coefficients,
- 4 Steady state conditions apply,
- 5 No heat exchange with the underlying ice,
- 6 The glacier surface is melting,
- 7 No mass exchange due to wind action.

Bulk Transfer methods

Due to problems of measuring wind speed, temperature and relative humidity continuously at two heights, (mainly through snow fall varying the instrument height and at times burying lower sensors), the bulk transfer method (essentially an integrated form of the aerodynamic profile method (Denby and Greuelle (2000) and as such, less sensitive to gradient variations as a consequence of the presence of wind speed maxima) has been devised to allow slightly lower precision measurements from robust sensors stationed at only one height above the surface to be used in turbulent heat flux determination in conjunction with assumptions about conditions at the glacier surface. The use of lower precision measurements allows the use of meteorological data from AWS left unattended for long periods, dramatically increasing the data availability. All other components of the energy and mass balances are measured, the remaining unaccounted melt is then explained by means of the turbulent heat fluxes (Denby and Greuell, 2000). During ablation conditions, the surface is justifiably assumed to be at 0 °C, have a relative humidity of 100 % and zero wind speed, heat fluxes and vapour fluxes are defined as follows (Williams, 2006):

$$Heat(H) = \rho_a c_p D_H (\theta'_z - \theta'_0) \quad (1.8.22)$$

$$WaterVapor (E) = \rho_a L_v D_w (q_z - q_0) \quad (1.8.23)$$

where:

ρ_a = Air density (kg m⁻³),

θ' = Potential temperature (K),

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

q = Specific humidity (dimensionless),
 c_p = Specific heat of air ($1.005 \times 10^3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$),
 L_v = Latent heat of vaporization ($2.50 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$),
 D_H = Bulk transfer coefficient for heat in air,
 D_w = Bulk transfer coefficient for water vapour in air.

The bulk transfer method of turbulent flux determination results in a mathematical simplification of the fluxes termed the Bowen Ratio, the ratio of sensible to latent heat flux in the form:

$$\beta = \frac{H}{LE} = \frac{\rho_a C_a D_H (T_a - T_s)}{\rho_a L_v D_w (q_a - q_s)} \quad (1.8.24)$$

where:

β = Bowen ratio,
 ρ_a = Air density (kg m^{-3}),
 C_a = Heat capacity of air (J K^{-1}),
 D_H = Bulk transfer coefficient for heat,
 T = Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 L_v = Latent heat of vaporization ($2.50 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$),
 D_w = Bulk transfer coefficient for water vapour in air,
 q = Specific humidity (dimensionless).

Assuming D_H and D_w are the same and cancelling ρ_a simplifies the Bowen ratio (Equation 1.8.24) to:

$$\beta = \frac{C_a (T_a - T_s)}{L_v (q_a - q_s)} \quad (1.8.25)$$

By assuming the surface has a temperature of 0°C and a relative humidity of 100 % and zero wind speed under melting conditions it is possible to determine the Bowen ratio from measurements at one measurement height. Knowing the other components of the surface energy balance and the Bowen ratio it is possible to solve to the energy balance equation and determine the sensible and latent heat fluxes. Examples of the use of this technique include; Greuell and Konzelmann (1994); Hay and Fitzharris (1988a); Hock and Noetzli (1997); Brock *et al.*, (2000a); Mittaz *et al.* (2000); Willis *et al.* (2002); Konya *et al.* (2004) and Semadeni – Davies *et al.*, (2004).

Two problems remain with the bulk transfer method:

- 1) The determination of surface temperature under non melting conditions,
- 2) The determination of surface roughness lengths for momentum, temperature and water vapour.

The bulk method can only be applied if the surface temperature and roughness lengths are known (Greuell and Smeets (2001). Reported roughness lengths for snow and ice vary by an order of

magnitude. Surface roughness lengths are highly dependent upon measurement height and have been determined from surface micro topography yielding values of 2.46 mm for ice and 5.5 mm for snow (Munro, 1989).

Yen (1995) outlines problems associated with modelling turbulent fluxes over snow surfaces, complicated by variations of turbulent flux with height resulting from temperature profile anomalies, attributed to radiation heating above the surface. Air temperature measurements by De la Casiniere (1974) and Halberstam and Schieldge (1981) support this observation, with temperature maxima at 20 to 50 cm above the snow surface. Wager and Jamieson (1977) report that under the influence of gravity winds flowing down hill, there is no satisfactory method of calculating energy exchange between the glacier and the atmosphere and outline an alternative method to energy exchange quantification based on measurement of the energy content of the glacier directly by means of accurate measurement of temperature and density at the surface. They report an accuracy with this method of 10 % for long term energy changes within a glacier.

1.8.3 Latent heat from refreezing of melt water

Latent heat transfer occurs as a result of percolation and subsequent freezing of water at depths below the surface in snow packs and cracks and crevasses in glacier ice. Latent heat release on refreezing has a decisive impact on thermal patterns within glaciers in the Swiss Alps (Suter *et al.*, 2001). When liquid water is present in the snow pack, water flows under gravity at temperatures as low as - 3 to - 4 °C. Percolation rates through snow have been shown to be highly heterogeneous in the range of 0.13 to 0.49 mhr⁻¹ (Campbell *et al.*, 2006). Ice layers or other less permeable snow strata delay percolation, causing ponding and significant lateral flow when encountered (especially under a sloping snow pack conditions) (Hughes and Seligman, 1939; Sharp, 1952; Gerdel, 1954; Langham, 1974a and 1974b). Downward movement of water occurs through ice lenses in limited areas, via flow fingers of ~1 cm diameter. Changes in injected dye return curves indicate increasing transmission efficiency throughout the melt season as near surface ice layers are destroyed by early season ablation (Campbell *et al.*, 2006). Ice layers have been reported to disintegrate quickly, within a few hours when subject to large melt fluxes (Male, 1980). On reaching the ice surface, lower layers of the snow become saturated (forming what is often called a firn aquifer) and water moves down slope and drains into the nearest crevasse (Fountain, 1996).

Once the snow surface has thawed, isothermal conditions are reached at depth in the snow pack primarily through the refreezing of percolating melt-water (Sverdrup, 1935 and Hughes and

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Seligman, 1939). Latent heat is released on freezing, when water contacts snow (or ice) at sub zero temperatures at the wetting front (Lang *et al.*, 1979; Oerter *et al.*, 1981; Oerter and Moser, 1982; Fountain, 1989 Conway and Benedict, 1994 and Schneider, 1999). The warming influence of refreezing water in a snow pack is significant due to the ratio of the latent heat released to the specific heat capacity, resulting in a 1 °C temperature rise for 160 g of snow following the refreezing of 1 g of liquid water (Paterson, 1994). Percolating liquid and subsequent re-freezing, regarded as the primary mechanism of snow pack warming (Marsh and Woo, 1984; Conway and Benedict, 1994 and Suter *et al.*, 2001) is a more efficient method of energy transfer to the ice surface than conduction through the snow pack ice lattice and is of principal importance at the beginning of the melt period (Wendler and Weller, 1974). Previous snow pack studies have assessed water movement through the snow pack by means of measuring the heat flux generated by the percolating water using thermistors (Conway and Raymond, 1993; Sturm and Holmgren, 1993 and Conway and Benedict, 1994). The rate of latent heat release in snow and firn is expressed in terms of physical processes within the snow and firn (Paterson, 1994, p226):

$$Q_L = L_f v_s \rho_s \frac{F}{z_z} \quad (1.8.26)$$

where:

Q_L = Heat generated by freezing of melt water in snow and firn (J),

L_f = Specific heat of fusion (J kg⁻¹),

F = Melt fraction (the fraction of the annual firn layer, by weight, that is formed by refreezing of melt water),

z_z = Maximum depth to which melt water penetrates (m),

ρ = Density (kg m⁻³),

v = Velocity component (m s⁻¹).

subscript s denotes surface values.

Latent heat release following freezing of water within glacier ice occurs at two scales; the macro scale where water is contained in crevasses, englacial stream channels, moulins and isolated cavities and the micro scale in the voids at grain boundaries. At the micro scale Nye and Frank (1973) suggest polycrystalline ice at its melting point is permeable to water, as water is able to flow between the grains driven by a pressure gradient. An important source of micro scale heating may consequently be the release of latent heat from the refreezing of percolating melt water at depth in the ice. In addition to the percolation of surface derived water through the ice, other water sources within the ice at the micro scale may include; melting due to strain heating, melting induced by changes in hydrostatic pressure, water trapped in small pockets when the ice formed and by the bubble melting mechanism suggested by Bader (1950) (Paterson, 1971).

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Latent heat release from macro scale sources can potentially provide large amounts of localized heating whereas freezing at the micro scale provides heat throughout the glacier. Melt advection and latent heat release has the capacity to operate at all depths where liquid water is available to freeze. Permeability of temperate glacier ice at the macro scale is very small, orders of magnitude smaller than through the snow pack (19 cm a⁻¹ in fine grained ice, 0.8 cm a⁻¹ in coarse grained blue ice and 0.05 cm a⁻¹ in coarse grained white ice (Raymond and Harrison, 1975) and 2 – 4 cm a⁻¹ Berner *et al.* (1977)). Rates are somewhat larger where ice is bubble free and with very small grains or where internal melt-water generation is large (Lliboutry, 1996). In contrast to the large volumes of water percolating through the snow pack, (with the exception of where cracks and crevasses prevail) only limited amounts of water enter the glacier ice at any given point on the ice surface, thus the vast majority of latent heat release is at the ice surface (at the bottom of the snow-pack in spring), resulting in superimposed ice formation.

Spatial variability in latent heat release across the glacier occurs as a result of surface morphology and variations in ice permeability. Latent heat release upon refreezing is a much less dominant heat source in the ablation area than in the accumulation area as ice in the ablation area is “at best only slightly permeable to water” Paterson (1972). Ice may be warmer in the accumulation area than the ablation area due to differences in permeability where percolating melt has a large influence in the near surface energy balance, to the extent that some glaciers may be temperate only in the accumulation area (e.g. Loewe, 1966 and Schytt, 1968). Paterson (1972) concludes that since the rate of water percolation into the Athabasca glacier is less than the ablation rate, refreezing of melt water is not an important heat source for this glacier.

1.8.4 Precipitation heat supply (Q_p)

In addition to surface melting, precipitation at air temperatures > 1.5 °C (Rohrer, 1989) provides liquid water to percolate into and refreeze in snow packs and on ice surfaces. Precipitation falling on to the glacier surface contributes heat via advection. The amount of heat supplied to the glacier by precipitation is generally episodic in nature and small relative to the other heat fluxes in the surface energy balance and thus is often neglected by many authors. Liquid precipitation on to a snow pack is generally more important in terms of its effect over the development of preferential water movement pathways through the snow and retention within the snow pack than the addition of heat.

Two separate cases exist for heat supply to the glacier surface from precipitation:

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Precipitation on to a melting snow pack where the rain does not freeze.

In this situation the advected energy supplied to the glacier via non freezing precipitation can be quantified as follows:

$$Q_p = C_w \rho_w P_r (T_p - T_s) \quad (1.8.27)$$

where:

Q_p = Heat flux supplied to the glacier surface via liquid precipitation,

C_w = Specific heat of liquid water ($418 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),

ρ_w = Density of liquid water,

P_r = Precipitation rate,

T_p = Temperature of the precipitation (assumed to be equal to the air temperature),

T_s = Temperature of the glacier surface.

The amount of energy supplied to the glacier surface under non freezing conditions is negligible in comparison with other components of the surface energy balance. For example if 4 mm of rain fell at a temperature of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (assuming a melting surface at $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) an energy flux of 0.38 W m^{-2} is added at the surface, two orders of magnitude smaller than that for commonly reported net radiation values and as such this flux is often neglected. However cases do exist where this precipitation heat flux is significant, Fitzharris *et al.* (1980) report the precipitation heat flux contributed up to 20 % of total heat input during a rain on snow event for a particularly intense event when 250 mm of precipitation at a temperature of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ fell during a 25 hour period, though such events are uncommon.

2. Precipitation on to a cold snow pack with freezing.

When freezing of liquid precipitation occurs at the glacier surface, energy is released via the latent heat of fusion. As the latent heat of fusion of ice (330 kJ kg^{-1}) is considerably larger than the specific heat of ice ($2.0 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) the energy released can be significant in terms of energy supply for melting. However liquid precipitation events onto a cold snow pack are very rare over glaciers in the continental interior and as such are often only considered significant for maritime glaciers.

1.8.5 Conductive heat flux into the ice (Q_i)

The conductive heat flux into (or out of) the ice surface is generated as a consequence of temperature differences between the base of the snow pack in winter and the atmospheric boundary layer in summer and the near surface ice layers due to changes in the surface energy balance, the flux is proportional to the temperature gradient (Patterson, 1994, p206) in the form:

$$Q_I = -K \left(\frac{\delta T}{\delta z} \right) \quad (1.8.28)$$

where:

Q_I = Conductive heat flux into the ice,

K = Thermal conductivity,

T = Temperature,

z = Depth below the ice surface (see Section 6.2.5 for depths of penetration of the “winter cold wave”).

1.9 Englacial heat fluxes

1.9.1 Firn compaction (Q_{FC})

Heat generation via compaction of snow and firn arises due to a vertical movement of firn driven by hydrostatic pressure, the proportional change in air space in the firn is linearly related to change in stress due to the weight of overlying snow (Robin, 1958). In addition to the natural processes of densification over time, on areas of Tsanfleuron artificial snow compaction occurs as a result of piste grooming, Keller *et al.*, (2004) report significantly higher snow densities (700 kg m^{-3} compared to an undisturbed density of 400 kg m^{-3}), snow hardness and thermal conductivity ($0.53 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ compared to $0.14 \text{ W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ off piste) following compaction by grooming traffic in a similar Swiss ski resort. Paterson (1994, p.225) parameterize heat generation via snow and firn compaction in the form:

$$Q_{FC} = \frac{\omega P_\sigma}{\rho} \left(\frac{d\rho}{dz} \right) \quad (1.9.1)$$

where:

Q_{FC} = Firn compaction heat flux,

ω = Vertical velocity component,

P_σ = Hydrostatic stress component,

ρ = Density,

z = Depth.

Sharp (1951) concluded that heating via compaction was so small it could be ignored.

1.9.2 Crevasses as heat sources and sinks

Further complication of the three-dimensional ice temperatures is caused by the presence of crevasses, moulins, supra-and englacial streams, acting as heat sources and sinks influencing ice in their vicinity. Crevasses are initiated in zones of extending flow along cracks in the ice surface caused by thermal expansion, when tensile stresses are large enough to fracture ice, especially where thermal stresses are dominant in the top ~ 3 m of the glacier ice (Sanderson, 1978). Following initiation crevasses inhibit supraglacial runoff and facilitate transfer of large volumes

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

of melt-water to depth within the ice (see Section 1.8.3 for detail of latent heat fluxes when freezing of such water occurs).

Crevasses have been observed to act as both heat sources and heat sinks, influencing the microclimatology of the ice mass in their proximity. Heat supply to adjacent ice in summer occurs via conduction from air (warmer than the adjacent ice) within crevasses, temperature gradients within the vicinity of such crevasses have been observed to continue smoothly from air filled crevasses through the crevasse wall into the ice (Pings, 1963). Warming to anomalously large depths as a consequence of crevassing has been measured in boreholes drilled in Jungfraufirn in the Bernese Alps (Suter *et al.*, 2001). Crevasses act as preferred melt-water drainage channels temporarily storing melt-water at their base, providing a large input of latent heat (Suter *et al.*, 2001). Clarke and Jarvis (1974) report an anomalously warm ice layer attributed to refreezing of water in crevasses opened by a surge on Steele Glacier, Yukon, and advective heat transfer or large displacements along shear planes. The penetration of water from water filled crevasses during surging was again highlighted as a cause of anomalously warm ice temperatures in cold glaciers by Clarke and Jarvis (1976).

Crevasse temperatures tend to vary erratically, probably due to air convection, with low temperatures where the crevasses are open at the surface during winter due to ponding of cold winter air (Harrison *et al.*, 1998). Thus crevasses that remain free from water and snow bridging in winter allow intense cooling at depths below the surface due to the cold winter air coming into contact with crevasse walls at depth.

1.9.3 Deformation driven strain heating (Q_D)

Down slope movement of temperate glaciers is controlled by two heat generating processes, internal plastic deformation of the ice and sliding at the bed (Gudmundsson *et al.*, 1999). Sliding at the bed (see Section 1.10.3) (including deformation in any basal sediment layers) accounted for 60 to 90 % of the observed surface motion at Storglaciaren (Hooke *et al.*, 1992), 77 to 84 % at the Athabasca glacier (Raymond, 1971) and 60 to 70 % at Haut Glacier d' Arolla (Willis *et al.*, 2003) with the remaining velocity attributed to ice deformation. Heat is generated via deformation, driven by ice flow within a glacier in response to stress applied by the force of gravity (Copland *et al.*, 1997c). Strain heating can be derived from field evidence collected using repeat measurements of the axial curvature of the borehole driven by ice deformation integrated over the period between inclinometry surveys. Previous repeat inclinometry studies have been focussed mainly on cased boreholes (e.g. Perutz, 1950; Sharp, 1953; Paterson and Savage, 1963; Savage

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

and Paterson, 1963 and 1965; Shreve and Sharp, 1970; Hooke, 1973; Hooke and Hanson, 1986 and Hooke *et al.*, 1987 and 1992), Russell – Head and Budd (1979) used a fluid filled hole, while Raymond, (1971); Copland *et al.* (1997c); Harper *et al.* (2001) and Willis *et al.* (2003) used cable following techniques in un-cased boreholes. At Worthington Glacier, Alaska (a temperate glacier) 30 – 40 % of the glacier surface motion was attributed to deformation, measured via repeat inclinometry in non-cased boreholes and the sliding rate at the bed was observed to change without influencing the rate of internal deformation in the ice above (Harper *et al.*, 1998).

The process of strain heating represents a positive feedback loop through which ice deformation generates heat. Ice viscosity is a function of temperature, thus as ice is warmed by deformation generated heat its viscosity further decreases and it deforms faster, causing an explosive increase in ice velocity, consequently generating more heat (Clarke *et al.*, 1977), a process termed “creep instability”. Creep instability is only constrained by the onset of pressure melting (Payne, 1999). This positive feedback has been suggested as a possible contributory cause of the rapid disintegration of ice masses and glacier surges (Robin, 1955 and 1969 and Yuen *et al.*, 1986). Lateral advection of colder ice from up glacier may provide a mechanism to reverse this feedback, as may the latent heat required for melting in the vicinity of the bed, associated with heat generated by sliding when melting point is reached (Pohjola and Hedfors, 2003). A fraction of the heat generated by strain heating may be stored within the ice in the form of latent energy which is subsequently liberated during recrystallisation (Steinmann, 1958).

Theoretical consideration of strain heating by Paterson (1994) provides the following derivation of heat generation (Q_D):

For an element with sides of length Δx , Δy , Δz . A stress σ_z is applied which results in the lengthening of side Δz by $\delta z = \varepsilon_z \Delta z$ where ε_z is the strain. The work done straining is $(\sigma_z \Delta x \Delta y) \delta z = \varepsilon_z \sigma_z \Delta x \Delta y \Delta z$ thus the rate of heat production per unit volume, which is equal to the work done per unit volume per unit time, is $\varepsilon_z \sigma_z$ where ε is the strain rate in the z direction. The total rate of heat production is:

$$Q_D = \dot{\varepsilon}_x \sigma_x + \dot{\varepsilon}_y \sigma_y + \dot{\varepsilon}_z \sigma_z + 2(\dot{\varepsilon}_{yz} \tau_{yz} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{xz} \tau_{xz} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{xy} \tau_{xy}) \quad (1.9.2)$$

where:

τ = Shear stress components.

An alternative formulation for the deformation driven strain heat flux is given by Pohjola and Hedfors (2003) (based on Hooke, 1981) as the work done on the ice in the form:

$$Q_D = \dot{\varepsilon} \tau \quad (1.9.3)$$

where:

Q_D = Deformation driven strain heat flux,

$\dot{\varepsilon}$ = Strain rate (following Glen's Flow law for ice).

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = (\tau / B)^n \quad (1.9.4)$$

where:

$$n = 3,$$

and

τ = Stress (parameterized as).

$$\tau = \rho_i g H \sin \theta \quad (1.9.5)$$

where:

ρ_i = Ice density,

g = Acceleration due to gravity (9.82 ms^{-2}),

H = Ice thickness,

θ = Slope angle,

B = Temperature dependent ice viscosity (parameterized as).

$$B = B_0 \exp(T_0 / T) \quad (1.9.6)$$

where:

$$B_0 = 1.928 \text{ Pa a}^{1/3},$$

$$T_0 = 3155 \text{ K},$$

T = Temperature.

Paterson (1971) has shown from calculations based on borehole measurements made in the Athabasca glacier that strain heating increases almost exponentially from the surface towards the bed but provides enough heat to maintain the ice at the pressure melting temperature, counteracting surface heat loss, only in the lower half of the ice thickness. Above this depth, heat must be supplied by freezing of water in the ice and the associated latent heat release (Figure 1.5). Where excess heat above that required to warm ice to the pressure melting point is generated by internal deformation, melting occurs. This amount of melting has been quantified for boreholes on the Athabasca Glacier to be sufficient to melt only ~1.5 % of the ice per 100 years (Paterson, 1971).

Figure 1.5: Heat produced by strain induced ice deformation (solid lines) and the heat required to maintain ice at pressure melting point, as hydrostatic pressure is reduced by ice flow towards the surface (dashed lines) in two boreholes at Athabasca Glacier. Source: Paterson (1971).

1.10 Basal heat fluxes

1.10.1 Water flow and refreezing at the grain scale boundaries between the crystals and at the macro scale within the ice and at the bed

Nye and Frank (1973) concluded glacier ice was permeable. However, at the grain scale air bubbles block, and deformation and recrystallisation close off inter granular channels seriously reducing the mobility of water within the ice (Vallon *et al.*, 1976), thus ice is permeable at any one time, over a scale of a number of grains, but over the whole glacier permeability is negligible (Lliboutry, 1971). This ice water content originating from a number of sources including; percolation from the surface, melt generated by strain heating, melt generated by pressure changes, being trapped in small pockets during firnification and ice melt around bubbles in response to hydrostatic pressure change as suggested by Bader (1950) (Paterson, 1971), has been reported to exhibit a strong linear relationship with effective strain rate (Duval, 1977). Water flow at the micro scale in the intergranular vein system provides a heat transfer, as water flows between regions of ice at different temperatures i.e. from warm ice regions at pressure melting point where water is generated to colder regions where refreezing of the water releases latent heat.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

At the macro scale nearly all liquid precipitation and melt enters the glacier via crevasses and moulins. Crevasses are the most dominant entry mechanism due to their high frequency of occurrence over many glaciers, moulins tend to develop at the bottom of crevasses following small fractures, efficiently routing water and heat deep into the glacier and to the bed (Fountain and Walder, 1998). Many englacial conduits, passages and fractures within temperate ice have been reported, often intersected during borehole drilling (e.g. Engelhardt, 1978; Hantz and Lliboutry, 1983; Hooke *et al.*, 1988 and Fountain, 1994.). Hock and Hooke (1993) used tracers injected into boreholes to support the existence of englacial conduits, while borehole video camera studies have visually shown englacial connections (Pohjola, 1994; Harper and Humphrey, 1995; Copland *et al.*, 1997a and b; Fountain *et al.*, 2005a and b). These englacial water flow passageways influence ice temperatures in their vicinity via heat advection, but not the thermal regime of large areas of ice (Paterson, 1971).

Water flow transports heat from the surface to the bed and across the glacier bed, generally towards the snout as water flows through the subglacial drainage system. Boulton (1972) highlighted basal conditions where water produced via melting at one location under a temperate glacier moves to another basal location with a different thermal regime where it refreezes, in order for this refreezing to occur energy is lost from the water as heat is conducted upwards away from the glacier bed into the ice.

1.10.2 Geothermal heat flux

Geothermal heat is heat supplied to the glacier at its bed by conduction from the mantle, the decay of radioactive isotopes in the underlying bedrock, and shallow magma bodies act as local heat sources. The amount of heat supplied is dependent upon the age of the rocks and the presence of any recent or current tectonic activity, radioactive heat producing elements such as U, Th and K, however, distort the relationship between tectonic age and heat supply (Sclatter *et al.*, 1980). Geothermal heating is not influenced by the type and speed of glacier, it thus represents a larger heat flux to the glacier sole at slower or stationary glaciers. Once pressure melting point has been reached at the glacier bed geothermal heat is no longer conducted in to the ice but melts the basal ice. Mountain topography results in spatially variable, non vertical heat fluxes from the bedrock to the glacier sole (Luthi and Funk, 2001). Temperature measurements in boreholes drilled in to the bedrock below Glacier d Argentiere showed temperatures of +1.7 °C at 5 m and 2.7 °C at 40 m (Vivian, 1980). During the last glacial maximum (18 Ka BP) Switzerland was situated entirely within a zone of continuous permafrost which blocked the karst drainage of the limestone regions and exerted profound cooling of surface temperatures in the uppermost

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

kilometres of the crust. These Quaternary temperatures have lowered today's temperatures in the upper crust by 5 – 6 °C equating to a reduction in the geothermal heat flux of 20-30 % of the observed values (Haebereli *et al.*, 1984). Ford *et al.*, (1976) in studies under the Columbia Icefield suggest that geothermal heat flow may be reduced to as little as 10 to 40 % of its undisturbed value in the presence of macro porous karst bedrock drainage features.

Measured heat fluxes vary from 46 mW m⁻² for rocks older than 1700 Ma to 77 mW m⁻² for rocks younger than 250 Ma, while in Europe, over rock of age 0 – 250 Ma the average heat flux is reported to be 80 mW m⁻² (Scatter *et al.*, 1980). Paterson (1994) suggests that the global average geothermal heat flux of 0.0599 W m⁻² (or 59.9 mW m⁻²) is sufficient to melt a 6 mm thickness of ice at its pressure melting point each year. Hooke *et al.* (1980) report geothermal fluxes for Baffin Island in the range 0.5 to 0.8 heat flux units (HFU), equivalent to 20.9 to 33.5 mWm⁻². Rao and Jessop (1975) report a geothermal flux of 0.6 ± 1.3 HFU (25.1 ± 54.34 mW m⁻²) for the Canadian Shield, while Sass *et al.* (1972) report a value of 1.0 ± 0.1 HFU (41.8 ± 4.2 mW m⁻²) for South Greenland.

1.10.3 Friction at the bed due to sliding (Q_F)

Friction between the sole of the glacier and its bed as the ice flows downhill under the influence of gravity generates a heat flux into the ice. The magnitude of the frictional heat flux is equal to “the rate of loss of potential energy of a column of ice of unit cross section as it moves down slope” (Paterson, 1994), thus frictional heat generation is greatest under fast moving glaciers. Barnes *et al.* (1971) show that friction at the glacier bed varied with temperature in addition to the velocity of sliding. The amount of frictional heat released at the bed is considered proportional to the product of the velocity and the basal shear stress. Mathematically, in temperature modelling, this frictional heat is simply added to the geothermal heat resulting in a higher temperature gradient at the bed (Hooke, 1977). Sliding induced friction is parameterized as:

$$Q_F = (\rho_i g H)(u_b \theta) = u_b \tau_b \quad (1.10.1)$$

where:

Q_F = Heat generated by friction at the bed,

ρ_i = Ice density,

g = Acceleration due to gravity,

H = Ice thickness,

u_b = Basal sliding velocity,

θ = Surface slope,

τ_b = Basal shear stress.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Heat generated at the bed via friction is partitioned between the bed and the ice depending on their relative thermal conductivity and heat capacity. Melt water, acting as a lubricant is generated when sufficient heat is conducted into the ice to overcome the latent heat of fusion and raise the temperature to the melting point of ice (Marmo *et al.*, 2005). Paterson (1994 p.112) gives a typical value of 6 mm a^{-1} for the basal melt rate due to frictional heating and suggest that heat supplied via basal friction is generally of the same order of magnitude as the geothermal heat flux.

1.10.4 Air flow at the glacier bed

Though to the author's knowledge no reference has been made in glaciological literature to air flow at the glacier bed, it is postulated however, that air flows between the ice and the macro porous karst limestone underlying Glacier de Tsanfleuron (Section 6.4.2) in response to temperature gradient changes and air flow patterns within the karst system, providing an additional heat flux at the bed.

1.11 Modelling glacier surface energy balance and melt

Two methods for modelling glacier energy and mass balance exist; positive degree day (Temperature index) models and surface energy balance models:

1.11.1 Degree day methods

The degree day method “assumes the melting of snow or ice to be proportional to the sum of all temperatures above melting point” Braithwaite (1995a). Simple, non input hungry temperature index models e.g. Schytt (1964); Braithwaite (1981); Braithwaite and Olesen (1989); Woo and Fitzharris (1992); Johannesson *et al.* (1993); Laumann and Reeh (1993); Braithwaite (1995b); Takeuchi *et al.*, (1996); Vincent and Vallon (1997); Braithwaite *et al.*(1998); Hock (1999); Braithwaite and Zhang (2000) and Hock (2003) use meteorological variables as indices of physical processes. Johannesson *et al.* (1995) outline three main advantages of the degree day approach, these include:

- 1) Climatic scenarios are typically given in terms of temperature and precipitation.
- 2) Energy balance models are problematic in terms of extrapolation of inputs over large areal extents.
- 3) Degree day coefficients are stable over time and a wide range of climatic regimes.

The simplicity of the degree day models however, result in a number of complications and limitations, for example ablation on steep slopes which, accelerated through a lack of winter

snow cover and increased gravitational wind speed, is poorly modelled (Boggild *et al.* 1994). In more uniform surroundings if the average temperature on a given day is zero no positive degree days will be allocated to this day, however, it may be possible that for periods of the day the melting point may have been exceeded producing unaccounted for melt (Reeh, 1991). The stability of the degree day factors as championed by Johannesson *et al.* (1995) is brought into question by both Braithwaite and Olesen (1990) where different ice degree day factors are reported for different seasons on Qamanarssup Sermia and by Boggild *et al.* (1994) who suggest that on Storstrommem Glacier, different degree day factors were experienced in consecutive years (1989 and 1990) as a result of more cloudy conditions during the 1989 field season. One of the most obvious limitations of the degree day method is the lack of accounting for the storage and freezing of melt water and rainfall in the porous snow pack early in the melt season, Janssens and Huybrechts (2000) suggest the incorporation of a refreezing factor into degree day models to improve the accuracy of the representation of the physical processes. Despite limitations of the degree day approach considerable valuable mass balance data can be gathered through its use, typical degree day factor values are 0.003 for snow and 0.007 for ice (Reeh, 1991).

1.11.2 Surface energy balance methods

Energy balance models, based on net radiation provide the most accurate predictions of glacier mass balance, however such models are energy intensive, complex and time consuming. Physically based distributed models are based on solutions to the heat balance equations for snow and ice e.g. Escher – Vetter (1985); Arnold *et al.* (1996); Bosch *et al.*, (1991); Brock *et al.* (2000a); Escher – Vetter (2000); Willis *et al.* (2002); Klok and Oerlemans (2002); Konya *et al.* (2004) and Hock and Holmgren (2005).

Physically based energy balance models have been grouped by Arnold *et al.* (1996) into three distinct categories:

- 1) Non dimensional studies to compare energy balance calculations with melt measurements at individual locations (e.g. Hay and Fitzharris, 1988a; Braithwaite and Olesen, 1990; Munro, 1990; Jordan, 1991 and Van de Wal *et al.*, 1992).
- 2) One dimensional studies to model glacier mass balance gradients along glacier flow lines (e.g. Munro, 1991; Oerlemans, 1992; Oerlemans and Fortuin, 1992 and Oerlemans, 1993).
- 3) Two dimensional studies that attempt to model spatial variations in energy balance components across the glacier (e.g. Munro and Young, 1982; Escher – Vetter, 1985 and Arnold *et al.*, 1996).

Examples of physically based energy balance models include; SNTHERM (Jordan 1991), a physically based point snow cover energy balance model which models surface temperature, transport of liquid water and water vapour, snow accumulation and ablation, densification, metamorphism and the effect on the thermal and optical properties of the snow pack (Cline, 1997). CROCUS (Brun *et al.*, 1989), a numerical model developed to simulate energy and mass evolution within a snow pack as a function of precipitation, air temperature, humidity, wind velocity, incoming short wave and long wave radiation (Brun *et al.*, 1989), DAISY (Bader and Weilenmann, 1992) used by (Morris *et al.*, 1997) to model temperature variations in polar snow and GEOTOP (Bertoldi *et al.*, 2004) a rainfall runoff model to which a snow accumulation and melt module has been added (Zanotti *et al.*, 2004).

1.12 Theoretical modelling of ice temperatures in the vertical dimension

1.12.1 Historical overview and measured temperate ice profiles

Numerous studies have attempted to quantify the energy flows to and from glacier and ice sheet ice and subsequently developed both one and two dimensional models of ice temperature distribution. In order to model ice temperatures a number of assumptions in several models of varying complexity have been made by different authors.

In static equilibrium the temperature of temperate ice is given by Cohen *et al.* (2000) as:

$$T = T_0 - K_p (P - P_0) - K_m m_s \quad (1.12.1)$$

where:

T = Ice temperature,

T_0 = Triple point temperature,

$K_p = 0.074 \text{ K MPa}^{-1}$ for air free ice and 0.098 MPa^{-1} for air saturated ice,

P = Pressure,

P_0 = Triple point pressure,

$K_m = 1.86 \text{ K kg mol}^{-1}$,

m_s = Solute molality.

In this formulation, an increase in pressure or solute concentration causes a temperature reduction (Cohen *et al.*, 2000).

Basic early parameterizations of the temperature distribution in a glacier were described by means of the equation of heat conduction (Hooke, 1976) in the form:

$$\frac{DT}{Dt} = k\nabla^2 T + \frac{Q_D}{\rho_i C} \quad (1.12.2)$$

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

where:

- T = Temperature,
- Q_D = Heat generation via ice deformation,
- ρ_i = Ice density,
- C = Heat capacity,

With boundary conditions imposed at the glacier surface and bed and Q_D being the only englacial heat source considered.

Van Ommen *et al.*, (1999) and Dahl-Jensen *et al.*, (2003) both present similar simple one dimensional time dependent energy balance models, calculating temperature profiles as a function of surface climate and geothermal heat flux at the glacier bed in the form (Dahl-Jensen *et al.*, 2003):

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} - \rho c \omega' \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \quad (1.12.3)$$

where:

- $T(z,t)$ = Temperature as a function of depth at a given time,
- t = Time,
- z = Depth,
- K = Thermal conductivity,
- ρ = Density,
- c = Specific heat capacity,
- ω' = Vertical velocity in the ice.

Suter *et al.*, (2001) modelled glacier ice temperature using another simple parameterization of the one dimensional Fourier equation with sinusoidal surface temperature variation, not including the effects of the energy exchange with the atmosphere under the assumptions that:

- 1 Heat transfer is limited to vertical conduction (vertical advection due to accumulation is not considered),
- 2 Latent heat, convective heat (via air and liquid water), sensible heat, radiation, strain heating, lateral firn and ice advection and ground heat fluxes are neglected,
- 3 Firn density is assumed to be constant with depth,
- 4 Air temperature at the surface is equal to the snow surface temperature,

Temperature was parameterized as (Suter *et al.*, 2001):

$$T(z,t) = T_a + z \left(\frac{dT}{dz} \right) + \Delta T_a e^{-z\sqrt{\omega'/sk}} \sin \left(\omega' t - z \sqrt{\frac{\omega'}{2k}} - \phi \right) \quad (1.12.4)$$

where:

- T = Temperature,

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

- z = Depth,
- t = Time,
- T_a = Mean annual air temperature,
- ΔT_a = Amplitude of the yearly variation in air temperature,
- ω' = Angular frequency ($2\pi / P$) where P is the period,
- k = Thermal diffusivity,
- ϕ = Adjustment determined individually for each englacial temperature profile to shift the air temperature maximum of the sin curve to the summer.

Large discrepancies between the modelled and measured ice temperatures were accounted for in terms of penetrating and refreezing melt-water.

Greuell and Oerlemans (1986) modelled glacier temperatures with a two component model, accounting for energy fluxes between the atmosphere and the glacier, with mass transfer processes and phase changes within the glacier. Ice temperature parameterizations included percolating and refreezing liquid water and densification of firn by metamorphosis, however the following were neglected:

- 1 Penetration of radiation,
- 2 Strain heating.

Ice temperatures were modelled following the energy conservation law (Greuell and Oerlemans, 1986):

$$\rho c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + W \quad (1.12.5)$$

where:

- ρ = Density,
- c_p = Specific heat capacity,
- T = Temperature,
- w = Velocity normal to the surface,
- z = Depth,
- K = Thermal conductivity,
- W = Energy release by phase changes.

Greuell and Konzelmann (1994) presented a similar two component model for glacier ice temperature, again accounting for energy fluxes between the atmosphere and the glacier and processes within the glacier, by solving the following thermodynamic equation:

$$\rho c_{pi} \frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial Q_t}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (ML_M) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (FL_M) \quad (1.12.6)$$

where:

- ρ = Density,
- c_{pi} = Specific heat capacity of ice ($2009 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$),

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

T = Temperature,

t = Time,

K_{eff} = Effective thermal conductivity,

z = Depth,

$\frac{\partial Q_t}{\partial z}$ = Absorption of energy coming from the atmosphere,

M = Melt rate ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$),

L_M = Latent heat of fusion ($0.334 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$),

F = Freezing rate ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

The effective conductivity is used to account for the processes of convection, radiation and vapour diffusion (Mellor, 1977). Horizontal advection, horizontal conduction and strain heating are neglected.

Blatter and Haeberli (1984) presented a two dimensional steady state solution for temperature distribution in alpine glaciers, based on the following differential equation, in a moving medium fixed geometry, with constant thermal diffusivity and boundary conditions, in the form (Blatter and Haeberli, 1984):

$$K \cdot \Delta T(x, y) - \vec{v}(x, y) \cdot \Delta T(x, y) = 0 \quad (1.12.7)$$

where:

K = Thermal diffusivity,

T = Temperature,

$\vec{v}(x, y)$ = Velocity vector.

This model was reported to produce slightly higher temperatures than those observed in the field, attributed to historical changes in glacier geometry, ice flow and surface boundary conditions. It was also reported that advection of cold ice could occur over long distances even within zones of temperate surface ice, strongly influencing the temperature distribution (Blatter and Haeberli, 1984).

1.12.2 Analytical solution to the glacier ice temperature equation (Robin, 1955)

Deriving an equation for the three dimensional temperature distributions within an idealized ice mass from first principles (the first law of thermodynamics) Van der Veen (1999) reported the full thermodynamic or temperature equation in the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = & -u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} - w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \\
 & + k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \\
 & + \frac{1}{\rho C_p} \left(\dot{\varepsilon}_{xx} \sigma_{xx} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{yy} \sigma_{yy} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{zz} \sigma_{zz} \right) + \\
 & + \frac{1}{\rho C_p} \left(2 \dot{\varepsilon}_{xy} \sigma_{xy} + 2 \dot{\varepsilon}_{xz} \sigma_{xz} + 2 \dot{\varepsilon}_{yz} \sigma_{yz} \right) + \\
 & \frac{L_f M_f}{\rho C_p}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.12.8}$$

where:

T = Temperature,

t = Time,

u, v, w = Velocity components in three dimensions respectively,

x, y, z = Three dimensional co-ordinates,

k = Thermal diffusivity,

ρ = Density,

C_p = Specific heat capacity,

$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ = Strain rate,

σ_{ij} = Stress,

L_f = Specific heat of fusion,

M_f = Amount of water refreezing per unit time and volume.

Robin (1955) produced the most prominent analytical solution for the temperature of ice, upon which most subsequent glacier temperature modelling has been based. In order to solve the temperature equation (Equation 1.12.8), Robin (1955) considered a stable ice sheet of constant size with a temperature distribution which did not change in time, the two dimensional form of the ice sheet was considered and the following assumptions were made:

- 1 The basal temperature is below melting point,
- 2 Horizontal diffusion is neglected,
- 3 Horizontal advection is neglected,
- 4 Heat generation from internal deformation is included in the geothermal heat flux.

Under these conditions the full thermodynamic equation (Equation 1.12.8) for ice reduces to:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} - w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \tag{1.12.9}$$

This equation is solvable analytically if two more assumptions are made:

- 5 A steady thermal state exists ($\partial T / \partial t = 0$),

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

- 6 A steady state ice sheet profile exists; that is to say vertical (downwards) velocity at the surface is equal to the accumulation rate.

Van der Veen (1999) (in a review of Robin, 1955's solution) suggested the steady state ice sheet profile had to satisfy the condition:

$$w(z) = -\frac{Mz}{H} \quad (1.12.10)$$

where:

- $w(z)$ = Vertical velocity vector,
 M = Accumulation rate,
 H = Ice thickness.

The steady state temperature could then be determined by solving the simplified heat equation, taking Van der Veen, (1999)'s simplification of Robin (1955)'s equation in the form:

$$K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \frac{Mz}{H} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (1.12.11)$$

Van der Veen (1999)'s interpretation of the Robin (1955) solution used two boundary conditions namely:

1 Surface temperature is prescribed to be the 10 m temperature (shown to be very close to the mean atmospheric temperature (Hooke, 1998)). Hooke (1998) however, noted three situations where this boundary condition is not representative of glacier temperatures:

- a. When ablation zone temperatures are warmer than the mean air temperatures as a result of winter snow insulation and percolating melt water.
- b. Where zones of ice several degrees warmer than mean annual air temperatures at depth exist high on the glacier, above the equilibrium line, resulting from latent heat release on freezing of percolating melt water in the firm,
- c. Where ice colder than the mean annual air temperature at high altitudes and latitudes occurs due to more efficient radiative cooling during the winter nights than the summer daytime warming.

2 The vertical temperature gradient at the glacier bed is equal to the geothermal heat flux. The basal temperature gradient (when basal temperatures are below pressure melting point) is described by Van der Veen (1999) as:

$$\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)_b = -\frac{Q_G}{K} \quad (1.12.12)$$

where:

Q_G = Geothermal heat flux,
 K = Thermal conductivity.

The steady state temperature profile can now be determined by integrating the simplified heat equation (Equation 1.2.11) twice with respect to z . For positive mass balance, the analytical solution for the temperature profile can be written as:

$$T_z = T_s - \frac{Q_G \sqrt{\pi}}{2Kq} [\text{erf}(zq) - \text{erf}(Hq)] \quad (1.12.13)$$

where:

T_z = Temperature at a given depth,
 z = Depth below surface,
 Q_G = Geothermal heat flux,
 K = Thermal conductivity,
 H = Ice thickness,
 T_s = Surface temperature.

and

$\text{erf}(z)$ represents the error function defined as:

$$\text{erf}(z) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^z \exp(-\bar{z}^2) d\bar{z} \quad (1.12.14)$$

and

$$\bar{z} = zq \quad (1.12.15)$$

$$q = \sqrt{\left(\frac{M}{2kH}\right)} \quad (1.12.16)$$

where:

k = Thermal diffusivity,
 M = Accumulation rate.

Temperature profiles for negative surface accumulation (ablation) can be achieved by numerically integrating the reduced form of the temperature equation (Equation 1.12.9). Surface accumulation results in considerable glacier cooling and surface ablation results in considerable glacier warming, expressed in the role of vertical velocity in the model (Van der Veen, 1999).

1.12.3 Extensions to the simple Robin (1955) analytical solution

The temperature profiles generated by the simple Robin (1955) solution to the temperature equation are simplifications and in many cases unrealistic, thus a number of theoretical extensions have been suggested by various authors.

Basal temperature

Weertman (1961) suggested an extension of the Robin (1955) analytical solution to allow the basal temperature to be at the melting point. The basal melt rate (M_b) was added to the equation for vertical velocity at depth to give:

$$w(z) = -\frac{Mz}{H} - M_b \quad (1.12.17)$$

In order to derive the temperature profile, the basal temperature gradient has to be modified to include the latent heat lost during melt, in the form:

$$\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}\right)_b = -\frac{Q_G}{k} + \frac{L_f M_b}{K} \quad (1.12.18)$$

where:

- Q_G = Geothermal heat flux,
- K = Thermal conductivity,
- k = Thermal diffusivity,
- L_f = Specific latent heat of fusion,
- M_b = Basal melt rate.

The gradient can be found from two values, the surface temperature (T_s) and the basal temperature (T_b) as suggested by Van der Veen (1999) in the form:

$$\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}\right)_b = -\frac{2q(T_b - T_s)}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left[\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{MH}{2k}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^{-1} \quad (1.12.19)$$

where:

- $q = \sqrt{(M/2KH)}$,
- T_b = Basal temperature,
- T_s = Surface temperature,
- M = Accumulation rate,
- H = Ice thickness,
- k = Thermal diffusivity.

Strain heating

Van der Veen (1999) shows how the requirement that strain heating be incorporated into the geothermal heat flux can be relaxed and how strain heating can be considered explicitly using laminar flow theory. In doing so the shear stress is considered to increase linearly from the surface with the maximum equal to the driving stress at the bed. Strain heating, which only affects temperature in the lower layers, is then described by:

$$Q_D(z) = \frac{2A}{\rho C_p} \left(\frac{h-z}{H} \right)^4 \tau_{dx}^4 \quad (1.12.20)$$

where:

$Q_D(z)$ = Heat generated by strain heating,
 A = Flow law parameter (temperature dependent),
 ρ = Density,
 C_p = Specific heat capacity,
 h = Elevation of the surface,
 z = Depth,
 H = Ice thickness,
 τ_{dx} = Driving stress.

1.13 Subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity

Direct measurements of subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity were made at Tsanfleuron at the same locations as the thermistor strings to assist interpretation of basal temperature measurements by means of providing additional information to aid process elucidation at the glacier bed.

1.13.1 Water pressure

Subglacial water pressure (WP) influences ice sliding velocity, glacier stability and sediment dynamics (Benn and Evans, 1998) and is used in this study as a means of assisting interpretation of basal thermistor temperature data in terms of resolving subglacial processes. Many studies have measured subglacial water pressure (e.g. Iken, 1972; Hodge, 1976; Engelhardt, 1978; Hantz and Lliboutry, 1983; Kamb *et al.*, 1985; Iken and Bindschadler, 1986; Kamb and Engelhardt, 1987; Hooke *et al.*, 1989; Engelhardt *et al.*, 1990b; Fountain, 1994; Hubbard *et al.*, 1995; Iverson *et al.*, 1995; Jansson, 1995; Murray and Clarke, 1995; Smart, 1996; Smart and Ketterling, 1997 and Gordon *et al.*, 2001). Drainage configurations are divided into two forms, discrete, arborescent channelized systems and distributed, non arborescent systems. Discrete arborescent systems are hydraulically efficient with a large melt water carrying capacity in Nye (Nye, 1973) and Rothlisberger channels (Rothlisberger, 1972). Distributed systems however are less efficient with lower flow rates characterized by processes of water flow through melt water films (Weertman, 1957 and 1972), linked cavities (Kamb, 1987), permeation through subglacial sediments (Boulton, 1974) and through the formation of canals within or on top of unconsolidated sediments (Walder and Fowler, 1994). Each configuration is characterized by individual drainage and water pressure signatures allowing assistance with interpretation of basal thermistor data. Subglacial drainage systems beneath temperate glaciers may evolve and decay

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

seasonally in terms of spatial extent of channelized and non channelized systems in response to variation in melt water supply (Hock and Hooke, 1993 and Hubbard *et al.*, 1995).

Where glaciers flow over alpine karst, the glacier may be drained karstically through the underlying bedrock, often resulting in decreased ice velocities and erosion rates (Smart, 1983). Hydraulic continuity between subglacial melt-water and karstic ground water has been inferred in several cases (Ford, 1971; Marie, 1977; Wildberger, 1981, Smart, 1983 and Benn and Evans, 1998) and observed by Smart and Ford (1983) in the form of subglacial streams sinking into shafts beneath the ice.

1.13.2 Electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity (EC) is a measure of a solution's ability to conduct an electrical current, via the mobile dissolved ions in solution. EC measurements of glacial melt-water act as a surrogate for the total concentration of dissolved solids present in the waters (Fenn, 1987). The amount of solute acquisition is dependent upon, the initial chemistry of the waters, the duration of contact between the waters and rock material, the grain size, shape and mineralogical properties of the rock material and the ratio between the surface area of the rock debris and the water volume (Sharp, 1991). High solute concentrations represent contact with reactive sediments at the glacier bed possibly for a long period of time (Brown *et al.*, 1994), allowing dissolution and solute acquisition to occur in hydraulically inefficient drainage pathways characteristic of a distributed drainage system. Low solute contents however suggest waters have had very short sediment contact times and thus are likely to have originated supra or englacially, routed through the subglacial drainage system via hydraulically efficient pathways. EC can thus be used to infer residence times of subglacial waters (Stone and Clarke, 1996). Carbonation reactions are the most important mechanism controlling the composition of subglacial waters in contact with bedrock (Souchez and Lemmens, 1987). Melt waters draining glaciers are typically ionically enriched (relative to their concentration as input precipitation) with Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} and Si ions.

Collins (1979) distinguished between supraglacial melt and waters of subglacial origin in the discharge waters of alpine glaciers using EC measurements. Collins (1981 and 1983) used EC measurements to provide estimates of solute load. Gordon *et al.* (2001) defined four different borehole drainage types based on the provenance of waters flowing in and out of glacier boreholes at Haut Glacier d' Arolla, a differentiation was made between low EC englacial or supraglacial waters ($0 - 10 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and more concentrated subglacial waters ($11 - 40 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$).

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Stone *et al.*, (1993) report steadily increasing EC time series values in the range $\sim 15 - 75 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ from Trapridge glacier, representing the gradual solute acquisition of basal waters in contact with the glacier bed, sharp decreases in EC are attributed to an infusion of low solute surface water. Engelhardt *et al.* (1990a) measured EC under Ice Stream B, Antarctica, as part of a salt injection study. Tranter *et al.* (1997) used a portable EC meter as a means of borehole water level detection and measured bulk EC values of $16 - 43 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ in subglacial waters at Haut Glacier d'Arolla, three water types were identified with conductivity modes of $0 - 10$, $11 - 30$ and $46 - 55 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ representing supraglacial runoff, bulk glacial runoff from the channel marginal zone and concentrated waters during periods of recession flow from the distributed drainage system respectively.

Temperature exerts a strong positive control over EC, as a result reported EC values are corrected to standard temperatures, often $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Collins (1977) made the recommendation that temperature corrections should not be applied to glaciological EC studies while Calles and Calles (1990) and Smart (1992) favour correction to $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (adopted as a reference temperature in this study).

1.14 Research objectives

The aim of this study (as stated above) is to measure ice and snow pack temperatures and related physical and thermal properties and to investigate the influence of these characteristics on the glacier energy balance. Measurements will be obtained from the glacier surface to the bed at various spatial and temporal scales. The following objectives are identified.

1. Conduct accurate temperature measurements continuously within the snow pack and ice boreholes to the glacier bed, over a number of annual cycles at several locations in an across-glacier transect at a continuous temporal resolution of two hours or better. Spatial resolution of temperature measurements must be sufficiently high to characterise internal snow pack processes as well as near-surface and deeper englacial temperature fluctuations.
2. Measure temperature profiles throughout the ice depth and compare the profiles with theoretical pressure melting point temperatures currently used to characterise ice temperature in temperate glacier flow models.
3. Measure electrical conductivity and water pressure near to temperature measurements at the glacier bed to assist in the interpretation of basal temperature records.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

4. Determine the spatial variability of snow depth over the ice surface and the physical and thermal properties of the snow pack, using repeat snow depth surveying techniques and snow pit analysis.
5. Determine glacier ice density and thermal conductivity using temperature measurements and ice cores recovered from Tsanfleuron by Tison and Hubbard (2000).
6. Deploy basic automated meteorological instrumentation at one or more locations on the glacier surface to collect continual meteorological data throughout two annual cycles. Develop and apply a snow and ice temperature model predicting surface energy balance, snow pack growth and decay, ice ablation and snow and ice temperature profiles. Compare predicted and measured snow depths, ablation rates and temperature profiles and further run the model to assess glacier response to future climate change scenarios.
7. Deploy eddy correlation and four-component radiation sensors for short attended periods to measure at high frequency the turbulent heat fluxes and all four components of the radiation balance over snow and ice surfaces. Compare measured turbulent heat fluxes with those determined using the bulk aerodynamic methods applied to basic meteorological data.

1.15 Thesis outline

A background review of the processes controlling snow pack and temperate ice temperatures along with a summary of previous investigations and numerical modelling studies have been presented. The objectives outlined above were addressed using a number of fieldwork techniques and automated instruments deployed on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, detailed in Chapter 2. Meteorological data and components of the glacier surface energy balance are presented and summarized (Section 3.2), snow temperatures, snow pack seasonal evolution and physical properties are presented and explained (Section 3.3). Glacier ice thickness, ablation, temperatures and laboratory ice core analysis derived density measurements are reviewed (Section 4.1), while subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity are presented in Section 4.2.

Glacier surface meteorology and surface energy balance, snow pack temperatures and near surface ice temperatures are discussed in Sections 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 respectively. The influences of the snow cover over the near surface ice temperatures are outlined in Section 5.5 along with a

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

determination of the thermal conductivity of the snow. The influences of fractures and crevasses over ice temperatures are assessed in Section 5.6, while a discussion of the differential across glacier ablation measurements is presented in Section 5.7. Chapter 6 addresses englacial and basal ice properties, temperatures, heat sources and sinks. Consideration is given to the initiation and elimination of the winter cold wave, along with the penetration depths thereof and a determination of the glacier ice thermal conductivity in Section 6.2. Englacial ice temperatures and the presence of cold ice are outlined in Section 6.3, while basal ice temperatures and heat sources are discussed in Section 6.4.

Non measured components of the surface energy balance are derived from basic recorded meteorological variables, the measured and derived datasets are then used to drive an energy balance model to predict snow pack and ice temperature profiles, snow pack growth and decay and ice ablation. The differences between modelled and observed temperature profiles and ablation rates are discussed and the model re-run using the IPCC climate change scenarios to assess the impact of global warming over Tsanfleuron temperatures and ablation rates (Chapter 7). Finally the main conclusions of this study are summarized (Section 8.2), the wider implications of a better understanding of temperate ice temperatures are discussed and recommendations for future investigation are presented (Section 8.4).

Chapter 2

Field site and methods

2.1 Glacier de Tsanfleuron

Site description

Glacier de Tsanfleuron is a small relatively flat, ‘temperate glacier’ with a short steep tongue (Figure 2.1). The glacier has surface area of $\sim 3.4 \text{ km}^2$, flowing over hard bedded macro-porous Mesozoic, Cretaceous (Urgonian) and Tertiary limestone through an altitudinal range of ~ 2960 to ~ 2420 m a.s.l., located to the Northwest of Sion, in the canton of Valais and to the Northeast of Les Diablerets, in the canton of Vaud, Switzerland at $46^\circ 20' \text{ N}$ and $07^\circ 15' \text{ E}$ (Figure 2.1 inset). The glacier is bounded by the Oldenhorn (3122 m) to the North and an ice divide to Glacier des Diablerets at le Dôme (3005 m) and Quille du Diable (2908 m) to the West. To the South and Southeast is an extensive (~ 1500 m wide) proglacial area of glacially eroded limestone bedrock and to the East there exists a small valley, trending West - East, into which the glacier tongue flows towards Col du Sanetsch. The glacier is ~ 3.2 km long at present though it has experienced considerable retreat since the Little Ice Age, retreating ~ 1500 m in the last 100 years through a geological syncline (Swiss Glacier Monitoring Network). The accumulation zone occupies only a limited area at the top of the glacier which has been developed commercially for both winter and summer cross country skiing. This skiing region will become increasingly important in the local economy under present climate change scenarios (Koenig and Abegg, 1997). Associated with this recreational development is a cable-car station near the summit of Sex Rouge (2970 m) used to access the glacier. The ablation area covers much of the glacier and is highly crevassed with a zone of transverse crevasses (orientated predominantly North – South) extending from the foot of the Oldenhorn (at ~ 2810 m a.s.l. down glacier of Col de Tsanfleuron) to the glacier terminus.

Figure 2.1: Map of Glacier de Tsanfleuron and inset location in Switzerland.

Figure 2.2: Borehole and meteorological station locations.

Previous work conducted on Glacier de Tsanfleuron and the limestone fore-field

Previous studies have investigated the glacier's internal ice composition and crystallography from ice cores (Tison and Hubbard, 2000; Hubbard *et al.*, 2000a), spatial variability in water content and rheology (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003), basal ice layers (Hallet *et al.*, 1978; Lemmens *et al.*, 1983; Souchez and Lemmens, 1985; Tison and Lorrain, 1987; Hubbard and Sharp, 1995; Hubbard *et al.*, 2000a), surface dynamics (Grust, 2004; Chandler, 2005), subglacial dynamics (Hubbard, 2002), hydrology (Grust, 2004) and hydrochemistry (Fairchild *et al.*, 1993, 1994, 1999a, b). The exposed proglacial bedrock shows examples of striations, chatter marks, Nye channels, roche moutonnées and carbonate precipitate crusts and has been studied in detail in terms of the geomorphology and the sub glacially deposited carbonate crusts (Sharp *et al.*, 1989, 1990; Fairchild *et al.*, 1993; Hubbard and Hubbard, 1998; Hubbard *et al.*, 2000b).

Ice crystallographic measurements made on ice cores recovered from the glacier (Tison and Hubbard, 2000) suggest the presence of four distinct crystallographic units:

- Unit 1: Composed of homogeneous fine grained ice with a uniform fabric, located within 20 m of the ice surface.
- Unit 2: Characterised by an increased range of crystal sizes, marking the start of the dynamic recrystallisation process.
- Unit 3: Characterised by an abrupt increase in crystal size at a depth of ~ 33 m below the surface.
- Unit 4: Composed of large jagged interlocking crystals with a strong multi modal fabric within 10 m of the bed.

Hubbard and Sharp (1995) studied basal ice exposed at the glacier margins and in sub glacial cavities, identifying three main ice facies present at Tsanfleuron termed (a) *englacial*, (b) *clear* and (c) *dispersed*. “Dispersed” facies ice was formed by “open system refreezing of basal melt waters, requiring a spatially extensive meltwater supply and heat sink” (Hubbard *et al.* 2000a). Hubbard *et al.*, (2000a) also identified a highly metamorphosed, bubble-poor basal ice layer ~ 10 m thick, which corresponded to the “clear” facies ice, postulated to have formed via deformation driven metamorphism of bubbly englacial ice. Metamorphism in the form of gas removal occurred as a consequence of meltwater generated by deformation related grain boundary melting and refreezing. Studies from eight ice cores (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003) revealed three distinctive internal ice zones; an upper zone, a lower zone and a basal zone - corresponding to the *englacial* ice facies, *clear* facies and *dispersed* facies respectively. Bulk ionic chemistry of the cores suggested relative bulk water content and ice softness varied by over an order of

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

magnitude between zones: relative to the upper zone (upper zone = 1) the lower zone indicated a value of 1.8 and the basal zone a value of 10.74 for water content and ice softness.

Measurements of surface velocity from an array of 23 surveyed stakes made by Chandler (2005) suggest mean surface velocities for Glacier de Tsanfleuron in the range 1.0 to 12.7 cm d⁻¹ (3.7 to 46.4 m yr⁻¹) with no significant change between two consecutive years. Ice flow is predominantly from West to East, with the highest velocities on the North side of the glacier, increasing down glacier towards the snout (Figure 2.3). Hubbard (2002) measured basal sliding in a subglacial cavity using multi-turn potentiometers attached to CR-10X data loggers. Results from this study indicated that velocity increased quasi-linearly away from the glacier bed, the extrapolation of which suggested ~ 10.55 mm d⁻¹ could be attributed to slip at the ice bedrock interface, further supported by evidence from the exposed bedrock with its carbonate precipitates and striations.

Sliding velocities and basal shear stresses calculated for Glacier de Tsanfleuron using a numerical ice flow model and Monte Carlo simulations suggest basal sliding contributes between 45 and 84% of the observed surface velocity with the remainder accounted for by ice deformation (Chandler *et al.*, 2006).

Dye trace experiments (Grust, 2004) suggest most liquid water reaching the bed is preferentially drained through sink holes and cracks into the underlying macro-porous limestone, recharging the subglacial karst aquifer, rather than being routed at the ice bedrock interface. This conclusion is supported by the absence of surface drainage from the glacier over the exposed karstic limestone plateau flanking the Southeast side of the glacier, with subterranean flows through the epikarst, surfacing a few kilometres to the south near the town of Saviessse (Pers. Comm.. N.Golscheider)¹.

Between 1850 and 1973 the surface area of Glacier de Tsanfleuron decreased by ~ 3.37 km², equating to an area loss of 47 % (Koenig and Abegg, 1997). Based on the 1973 areal extent, and the IPCC (1990) Scenario A (“Business as usual”) climate change predictions for a temperature rise of + 0.3 °C per decade the areal extent of the glacier was predicted to have decreased by 1.95 km² by 2010, a relative area loss of 51 % from the 1973 position and a 74 % reduction from 1850 (Koenig and Abegg, 1997). In 1973 all ski lifts were located on the ice, in 2004 the Quille du Diable and Tsanfleuron lifts both terminated on bedrock approximately 400 m from the glacier edge (Figure 2.1).

¹ Dr Nico Golscheider, Centre of Hydrogeology, University of Neuchatel, Switzerland.

Figure 2.3: Easterly component of the surface velocity field during (a) summer 2002 and (b) winter 2003, Outline marks the margin or assumed flow divide. Contours at 50 m intervals. Co-ordinates are in Swiss Grid. Reproduced from Chandler (2005) with permission of the author.

Work conducted in association with the present project funded by NERC Grant (NER/A/S/2002/00607)

The research carried out for this PhD was associated with a broader NERC funded research program entitled “Effect of spatial variability of physical parameters on the rheology of temperate glaciers and their modelled response to climate change”. This research programme aims to address the current lack of knowledge of the 3D structure of temperate valley glacier ice masses. Specific reference is made to rheologically important variables in spatially-distributed numerical glacier flow models used to predict glacier response to climate change. Developments have included the incorporation of spatially variable ice rheology into an existing valley glacier motion model by means of an enhancement factor and basal sliding (Hubbard *et al.* 2006).

Glaciological techniques being applied in addition to those outlined in this study include:

- Multi-frequency (50 MHz, 100 MHz and 200 MHz) surface radar (multiple offset, common offset and common midpoint surveys) to investigate the glacier geometry and ice liquid water content and spatial distribution there of (under the assumption of a lack of sediment in the ice). Techniques rely on the inverse relationship between liquid water content and the propagation, velocity and attenuation of radar waves in ice, in conjunction with laboratory ice core measurements and theoretical modelling (Murray *et al.*, 2006).
- Borehole radar surveys (vertical radar profiles, zero offset and multiple offset).
- Borehole and snow pack seismic and electro-seismic investigations (Kulesa *et al.*, 2006).
- Borehole self potential profiling.
- Laboratory based Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) analysis of ice cores allowing determination of the dielectric constant of ice and hence the water content (specifically at the grain boundaries), using modified press on techniques applied to a range of ice facies taken from ice core samples (West *et al.* in press).

2.2 Meteorology and snow pack measurements

In order to quantify accurately the energy balance at the glacier / snow surface, an automated weather station (AWS) was established on Glacier de Tsanfleuron in February 2005. Basic meteorological parameters were recorded continually from that time through to early 2007. These are described below.

2.2.1 Automated weather stations (AWSs) on the glacier surface

Automated weather stations have been deployed on a number of glacier surfaces for the purposes of determination of glacier climate and surface energy balance for example: Arnold *et al.* (1996);

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Steffen *et al.* (1996); Hock and Holmgren (1996); Greuell *et al.* (1997); Oerlemans *et al.* (1999); Reijmer *et al.* (1999); Albert and Hawley (2000); Oerlemans (2000); Box and Steffen (2001); Steffen and Box (2001); Oerlemans and Grisogno (2002); Oerlemans and Klok (2002); Reijmer and Oerlemans (2002); Favier *et al.* (2004); Oerlemans and Klok (2004); Strasser *et al.* (2004); Klok *et al.* (2005), Pellicciotti *et al.* (2005) and Van den Broeke *et al.* (2005).

Basic AWS

Parameters measured in this study included wind speed and direction, air temperature and relative humidity, net all wave radiation, snow depth and ice ablation. Basic one-height measurements were supplemented with additional readings at a lower height for periods during the late accumulation and ablation season of 2005 and intermittently higher temporal resolution, four component radiation measurements and eddy correlation instrumentation.

Sensors

Specifications of the basic meteorological sensors are outlined below and summarized in Table 2.1.

MP100A Temperature and relative humidity sensor

The MP100A is a solid state hygrometer produced commercially by Rotronic. The Temperature and relative humidity probe was housed in a naturally ventilated radiation shield (Figure 2.4.d.), naturally ventilated shields were chosen in preference to forced ventilation types because of the high wind velocity characteristics over Tsanfleuron. The MP100A has a temperature accuracy of ± 0.5 °C for the range - 40 °C to + 60 °C and a humidity accuracy at 23 ± 2 °C of $\pm 1\%$ for humidities in the range 5 – 95 % RH, and ± 2 % for humidities less than 5 % and greater than 95 % RH (Campbell Scientific Inc., 1995). The possibility exists for artificially augmented temperature measurements under strong radiation conditions, despite the MP100A sensor being housed in a radiation shield, such errors are reported by Brock *et al.* (2000b) to be < 0.5 °C. For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (1995).

NR – LITE net radiometer

Net radiation was monitored using a NR-LITE net radiometer produced by Kipp and Zonen (Figure 2.4.b). The sensor is composed of one upward looking and one downward looking black sensor surface allowing measurement of incoming and outgoing shortwave and long wave radiation components (Campbell Scientific Inc., 1998a). The NR-Lite net radiometer is specifically sensitive to wind speed variations resulting in reduced measurement accuracy, this

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

wind speed sensitivity is eliminated using a correction based on wind speed measurements made using by the RM Young 05103 wind speed and direction sensor. The spectral range of the sensor is 0.2 to 100 μm with sensor asymmetry typically $\pm 5\%$ ($\pm 10\%$ worst case) (Campbell Scientific Inc., 1998a). For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (1998a). The main limitations experienced in the recording of net radiation data were snow fall and / or rime formation disturbing radiation measurements during unattended periods, by covering the upper face of the NR Lite sensor while the lower sensor face remained free, most of these instances were easily identified (often in conjunction with the SR50 time series) and the data corrected accordingly.

RM Young 05103 Wind speed and direction sensor

The 05103 wind speed and direction sensor (Figure 2.4.a.) is a rugged, corrosion resistant, lightweight propeller vein type sensor produced by R M Young Co. Measurements of horizontal wind speed are made as rotations of the helicoid shape propeller (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2002a). Wind direction is determined through detection of the position of the vane using a potentiometer. The 05103 has a wind speed accuracy of $\pm 0.3 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ for wind speeds in range 1 to 60 ms^{-1} and $\pm 1.0 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ for wind speeds in range 60 to 100 ms^{-1} , wind direction accuracy was $\pm 3^\circ$ (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2002a). For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002a).

SR50 sonic ranging sensor

Information on winter snow fall and summer ice ablation was provided by an SR50 sonic ranging sensor (Figure 2.4.c.) manufactured by Campbell Scientific, based on a 50 kHz (ultrasonic) electrostatic transducer (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2003a). Distance from the sensor to the surface is determined by means of measurement of the time for transmissions to travel to the surface, be reflected and return to the sensor, referenced to the metal mesh at the base of the transducer. However, as the speed of sound in air varies as a function of temperature, the SR50 takes a measurement of the air temperature from the MP100A for use in a temperature correction. In addition to snow fall and melting, the SR50-determined distance is affected by the passage of sastrugi (small snow surface waves moved by the wind) and blowing snow (Albert and Hawley, 2000). Blowing snow events tend to be easily identified and corrected for on the basis of their characteristic high frequency oscillations over small time periods signature. The passage of sastrugi are identified by small amplitude oscillations about a mean depth over a time scale of a few days to weeks (Albert and Hawley, 2000). The SR50 has an accuracy of $\pm 1 \text{ cm}$ (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2003a) and did not experience any tilting (as often reported over glacier surfaces) following August 2005, as the supporting mast was drilled sufficiently deep into the ice ($> 4 \text{ m}$)

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

such that surface ablation did not cause the mast to tilt. For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (2003a).

HPF01 Heat flux plate

The heat flux at the base of the snow pack between the snow and ice was determined using a HPF01 heat flux plate manufactured by Hukseflux (Figure 2.4.e.) (assuming the flux is perpendicular to the sensor). The HPF01 is a thermopile sensor with an accuracy of $\pm 20\%$ (Campbell Scientific Inc., 1998b). The HPF01 has a low ohmic value (resulting in little pick up of electromagnetic disturbances) and gives zero output for zero input. For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (1998b).

<i>Meteorological variable</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Serial number</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>
Air temperature	Rotronic MP100A	25290034 &	-40 to +60 °C	± 0.5 °C
Relative humidity		26407003	5 to 95 %	± 1 %
Wind speed	RM Young 05103 wind	41206 &	0 to 60 ms ⁻¹	± 0.3 ms ⁻¹
Wind direction	monitor	54862	0 to 360 °	± 3 °
Net radiation	NR Lite (Kipp and Zonen)	000508	-2000 to + 2000 W m ⁻²	± 30 W m ⁻²
Snow depth / ice ablation	Campbell Scientific SR50	C3005	0.5 to 10 m	± 1 cm
Snow – ice heat flux	Hukseflux HFP01	001493	-2000 to 2000 W m ⁻²	± 20 %

Table 2.1: Basic meteorological station sensor specifications.

Figure 2.4: Basic meteorological sensors (a) RM Young 05103 wind monitor. (b) NR Lite net radiometer. (c) SR50 sonic ranging sensor. (d) MP100A temperature and relative humidity probe (in radiation shield). (e) HPF01 heat flux plate.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Field deployment and instrument mounting

The AWS was deployed on the glacier on February 27th, 2005 and was visited with data collection and maintenance tasks being conducted on 22nd April 2005, 28th July 2005 (when the AWS was righted and drilled into the ice following it toppling over on 25th July (deduced from meteorological data)), 27th September 2005, 22nd January 2006, 28th April 2006 and various times in August 2006 and January 2007. The station was located ~ 400 m South of the foot of the Oldenhorn at the glacier's northern margin on a relatively featureless part of the glacier with a surface slope of ~ 5 °, at an altitude of 2760 m (see Figure 2.2).

The AWS deployed on Tsanfleuron had the above mentioned sensors mounted on a sectioned aluminium mounting pole of max length ~ 6.7 m and 36 mm diameter supported by a sliding tripod when deployed in February 2005 and subsequently drilled into the ice in August 2005 (Figure 2.5). The pole was inserted vertically down through the snow pack until the point of the steel spike (attached to the base to facilitate easy insertion through the snow) was resting on the ice surface, this was confirmed by measurement of the snow depth and comparison with the snow depth in an adjacent snow pit to the ice surface. A collar was attached ~ 200 mm below the top of the mounting pole, into which three equally-spaced holes at 120 ° separation were drilled and attached to tensionable 3 mm steel rope guy lines anchored to the ice surface by means of ice screws at bearings of 0 °, 120 ° and 240 ° from the centre of the vertical mast.

Prior to deployment on Glacier de Tsanfleuron the calibrations of the NR-Lite radiometer and the RM-Young 05103 Wind Monitor were checked in the laboratory using the procedure outlined by Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002a). The calibration of the SR50 sonic ranging sensor was tested by manual measurement of the distance between the steel mesh at the bottom of the sensor and a solid surface directly below it, while the MP100A was validated against air temperature data collected from thermistors deployed above the glacier surface.

Figure 2.5: Schematic diagram of basic meteorological station as deployed on Glacier de Tsanfleuron, February 2005.

The RM Young 05103 wind monitor was mounted directly to the top of a custom made 34 mm attachment bolted to the top of the ASW mounting pole at a height of ~ 3.5 m above the February snow surface and fastened in place by means of a hose clamp (“jubilee clip”). The wind vane alignment was determined by setting the data logger to record wind direction, sighting along the

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

centre line of the wind vane toward a point on the horizon due south at an azimuth of 180° , adjusting the position of the vane mounting bracket until the reading for wind direction on the logger was correct, the hose clamp was then tightened. An additional grounding wire was run from the SPARE terminal inside the junction box of the RM Young 05103 to the metal AWS mounting pole in an attempt to try and prevent the build up of static charge which can discharge through the transducers causing erroneous signals and transducer failure (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2002a). Directly below the RM Young 05103 was mounted the radiation shielded MP100A temperature and relative humidity probe. The probe was fixed to the pole at an azimuth of 0° and a height of 3.42 m by means of two U bolts around the vertical pole. The net radiometer was mounted at a height of 2.38 m, well above the minimum 1.5 m operating height suggested by Campbell Scientific Inc. (1998a), on the South facing side of the pole at an azimuth of 180° such that no shadow is cast over it at any time of the day. Mounting was via four U bolts and galvanised mounting plate, to allow adjustment in two planes for the purposes of levelling the instrument. The SR50 sonic ranging sensor was mounted on a guyed horizontal boom also made from 36 mm diameter aluminium tubing. The sensor was located 0.74 m from the vertical pole at a height of 1.92 m above the snow surface.

The data logger enclosure was mounted on the mast at a height of 1.28 m at an azimuth of 295° by means of two U bolts (9 mm diameter, 50 mm gape) through holes in the exterior of the enclosure. During subsequent field visits, mounting poles were shortened and lengthened and sensor positions adjusted, in response to the changing position of the glacier surface. In August 2005 a scaffolding pole was drilled into the ice surface to a depth of ~ 4.8 m to which the aluminium pole was vertically bolted, eliminating the need for guy lines and a tripod.

Data logger control

Data logger control was provided by a Campbell Scientific CR-10X with 1 MB of extended memory with auxiliary power provided by a 12 V solar panel (Maplin model number 685-SP150-12V, maximum power output of 2.88 W and a nominal current of 150 mA), attached to two 12 V, 7.2 Ah batteries connected in parallel. The solar panel was mounted vertically on the mast facing South to maximise insolation receipt. A vertical mounting position was chosen as it was more robust than a tilted mounting and was most effective for shedding snow and ice. The CR-10X was used to log air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, net radiation and snow depth, every 20 seconds and average data was output to final storage every 30 minutes.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Eddy correlation and four component radiation AWS

In order to accurately measure the turbulent heat fluxes and quantify the individual radiation fluxes a CSAT3 three dimensional sonic anemometer, a KH2O krypton hygrometer and a CNR1 net radiometer were deployed on the glacier during the summer 2005, summer 2006 and January 2007 field seasons.

Sensors

Specifications of the eddy correlation and four component radiation sensors are outlined here and summarized in Table 2.2.

CSAT3 three dimensional sonic anemometer

The CSAT3 is a 3D sonic anemometer (Figure 2.6.a) capable of measuring “wind speed and the speed of sound in the air, on three non-orthogonal axes” (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2002b). From these measurements orthogonal wind speed components, referenced to the anemometer head and sonic temperature, are derived. Thus the CSAT3 allows measurement of the turbulent fluctuations of vertical and horizontal wind speed, allowing determination of the momentum flux. The anemometer is orientated such that it is pointing into the prevailing wind in order to minimise disruption caused by the anemometer’s arms and the mounting paraphernalia. For further details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002b).

KH20 krypton hygrometer

The KH20 hygrometer (Figure 2.6.a) is a precision UV absorption hygrometer capable of measuring fluctuations about the mean vapour pressure (Campbell Scientific Inc., 1989). As such, it cannot be used for the measurement of absolute vapour pressure. When deployed the KH20 is levelled, insulated from the metal support structure, exposed with a fetch to height ratio of at least 100:1, deployed close enough to the CSAT3 (~20 cm) so that both sensors are sampling the same eddy field and the source and detector windows are kept clear. For more details refer to Campbell Scientific Inc. (1989).

CNR1 net radiometer

The CNR1 net radiometer (Figure 2.6.b) is composed of two CM3 pyranometers, one measuring incoming solar radiation and the other measuring reflected solar radiation and two CG3 pyrgeometers, one measuring far infrared radiation from the sky and the other from the surface. These fluxes generate voltage signals proportional to the radiation intensity. Both the upwards facing and the downwards facing sensors measure radiation received in a whole 180° hemispheric

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

field of view. In four Separate Components Mode (4SCM), two solar radiation signals and two far infra red signals are measured and recorded separately and snow / ice surface albedo can also be determined from the ratio of reflected and incoming radiation. The spectral range of the CM3 pyranometers measuring the solar radiation is 305 – 2800 nm, while the spectral range of the CG3 pyrgeometers measuring the far infrared is 5-50 μm . The expected accuracy for daily totals is $\pm 10\%$ for both sensor types (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2003b).

Figure 2.6: Eddy correlation and four component radiation sensors (a) CSAT 3 sonic anemometer (front) and KH20 krypton hygrometer (background). (b) CNR1 net radiometer.

<i>Meteorological variable</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Serial numbers</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>
Turbulent fluxes of horizontal and vertical wind speed	CSAT 3 Sonic Anemometer	0708 & 0413 (control box 0708-1) & (control box 0413-1)	0 to 65.535 ms^{-1}	$\pm 2 \text{ mms}^{-1}$
Vapor pressure	KH20 Krypton Hygrometer	1487 & 1489 & 1470		
SW Incoming radiation	CNR1 Net Radiometer	010343 & 061106	0.3 to 3 μm	$\pm 25 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$
SW outgoing radiation			and	
LW Incoming radiation			5 to 42 μm	
LW outgoing radiation				
Liquid precipitation	ARG100 Rain Gauge	030255 & 030257	N/A	$\pm 0.20 \text{ mm}$
Data logger	CR-5000	1415 & 1450	N/A	N/A

Table 2.2: Eddy correlation and four component radiation sensor specifications.

Field deployment

Eddy correlation instruments were deployed on a commercially available Campbell Scientific $\sim 2.5 \text{ m}$ high galvanized steel meteorological tripod, free standing on the ice surface as indicated in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Schematic diagram of eddy correlation and four component radiation meteorological station as deployed in August 2005, 2006 and January 2007.

Eddy correlation instruments were deployed in August 2005 with 12 V, 7.2 Ah batteries attached to a tripod mounted 12 V, 2.88 W solar panel. Notwithstanding exhaustive field trials in the UK prior to deployment on the ice, this power supply combination proved to be, under the poor meteorological conditions experienced, insufficient resulting in periods of power loss (despite changing the battery in the field for a 12 V 50 Ah car battery). Successful power supply improvements were made for the August 2006 and January 2007 deployment which involved the use of 12 V, 90 Ah batteries attached to 'A' frame mounted Uni-Solar 64 W (3.88 A max current) solar panels via Morning star SunSaver-6 solar shunt regulators. Problems occurred with CSAT3 sonic anemometer not working during wet conditions similar to Yen (1995).

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Data logger control

Data logger control for the eddy correlation system was provided by a Campbell Scientific CR-5000 logger which recorded four radiation components, from which albedo was calculated; three individual wind speed components; average wind speed; relative humidity and vapour pressure. These variables were logged at a frequency of 10 Hz during August 2005 and at 20 Hz during August 2006 and January 2007, and averaged to provide 30 minute averages of net radiation (W m^{-2}), sensible heat (W m^{-2}) and latent heat (W m^{-2}).

2.2.2 Field meteorological observations

During field visits, synoptic weather conditions, wind direction, cloud type and cloud cover estimates were made according to World Meteorological Organisation codes (WMO) at 0900, 1200, 1500 and 1800. To minimize systematic variability in estimation and interpretation of cloud amount and type, observations were made by the same observer.

2.2.3 Snow pack measurements

Snow pits were dug during field visits at each of the borehole locations (see Figure 2.2) as a means of accurately determining snow depth and to measure profiles of temperature, density and stratigraphy. Snow pit analysis was conducted following the protocol of Elder *et al.*, (1991).

Snow depth

Snow pit depth

Snow pit depth was measured by digging pits to the ice surface and measured using a folding plastic ruler in shallow holes and a tape measure in deeper snow (Figure 2.9.a), these manual measurements were used to validate the SR50 time series data.

Depth transects

Transects across the glacier were made, conducting probing surveys using a graduated avalanche probe to attempt to quantify the spatial variability of snow depth (Figure 2.8.b). Sample points were located by GPS and at each site an average of three depth readings was taken. Specific emphasis was placed on depth data collection in the vicinity of instrumented boreholes, collecting many more readings in these areas (Figure 2.8.a). Under deep snow conditions extendable snow depth probes were used, but identifying the ice surface was difficult in snow deeper than ~ 3 m because of the presence of thick ice lenses at depth (see Tables 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7).

Figure 2.8: Snow depth measurements via the probe technique (a) At the North site on return to the glacier, January 2006. (b) Snow depth transect, January 2006.

Snow temperature

Temperature measurements were made at 10 cm intervals in the pit wall, starting at the surface with a 10 cm long dial stem thermometer pre-calibrated in a deionized ice water-bath at 0 °C. The thermometer was always in the shade during measurements; on the pit wall this was achieved by sampling the North facing wall and for the snow surface temperature reading, shade was efficiently provided using a snow shovel (Figure 2.9.d).

Snow density

A 1000 cm³ stainless steel triangular cross-section snow density cutter with detachable lid was used to collect snow samples (Figure 2.9.b) for weighing on an electronic scale (± 1 g) (Figure 2.9.c). Prior to samples being collected the cutter and lid were inserted into one of the snow pit walls (not being analysed) to cool and equilibrate to the snow temperature. When collecting a sample it was necessary to ensure the cutter was perpendicular to the snow face in order to collect a uniform sample and to avoid under sampling. It was also necessary to ensure the cutter was not pushed too far into the snow face which would compact the snow causing an over-weight sample to be collected, in hard compact snow at the base of the pit a rubber mallet was used to aid cutter insertion. Two side-by-side samples were recovered at each height down through the snow pack, weights were compared, and if they differed by more than 5 % (due to spatial heterogeneity in the

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

snowpack and over or under sampling) a third sample (and if necessary a fourth) was taken; those that seemed anomalous were rejected.

Snow stratification and crystallography

A log of the snow pack layers was made in each pit to provide additional information to improve our understanding of snow processes. Visual inspection was assisted through the use of a paint scraper to cut vertically down through the snow pit wall, feeling changes in the stratigraphy and allowing detection of ice lenses and crusts not clearly visible to the naked eye. An alternative, and often complementary, approach, employed occasionally in this study involved the use of a paint brush to brush away loose snow crystals in the pit wall leaving ice lenses and crusts exposed. A semi quantitative assessment of snow layer hardness was made using the fist, finger, pencil and knife technique. Snow crystallography was analyzed following La Chapelle (1992). Crystal sizes (longest visible dimension) were determined using a millimetre graduated rule and hand lens.

Figure 2.9: Snow pack analysis via snow pits (a) ~ 4 m snowpit with access steps, April 2006. (b) Collecting snow samples for density measurement at the meteorological station site, January 2006. (c) Weighing of snow density cutter and snow sample allowing density determination. (d) Temperature measurement with stainless steel thermometer in snow pit wall.

2.3 Borehole measurements

2.3.1 Hot water drilling

Borehole drilling at Glacier de Tsanfleuron

Borehole drilling has been used in numerous studies of cold, temperate and polythermal glaciers as a means of accessing englacial ice and the glacier bed. Gillet (1975) outlines the three main borehole drilling types as; steam drilling, hot water drilling and electrical drilling. Manual hot water drilling was used in this study. This method is relatively cheap to operate and efficient in ice depths up to ~ 200 m. However, this method does involve heat loss across the glacier surface and down the borehole, a loss of “touch” when boreholes drain and produces a conical hole shape.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Borehole drilling at Glacier de Tsanfleuron was conducted during the spring of 2004, summer of 2005 and again in the summer of 2006 using the Aberystwyth Centre for Glaciology hot water ice drills: modified carwashes produced commercially by Kärcher, models HDS1000BE and HDS100DE. The HDS1000BE drill consists of a petrol driven three piston water pump used to generate the high water pressures required for drilling while the HDS100DE water pump is diesel driven. Pressurised cold water passes through a diesel burner to supply the necessary heat prior to exiting the drill. The drills weigh ~ 200 kg when full of fuel, stand ~ 0.8 m high, ~ 0.9 m wide and 1.2 m long and are built around a tubular steel frame onto which the electrical control box is bolted. On the glacier, the drills were mounted on sledges to facilitate easy transport between drill sites, the sledge also served a second purpose of preventing the drill from melting itself into the snow pack as it warmed up during use. Water was fed to the drill from a 200 L storage reservoir, itself fed under gravity when water flows freely across the glacier surface (Figure 2.10). At an outflow pressure of 90 bar the drill used approximately 800 L of water per hour (Hubbard and Glasser, 2005). Drilling fuel consumption was ~ 2 L of petrol and 4 L of diesel per hour for the HDS1000BE (Hubbard and Glasser, 2005) and 7 L of diesel per hour for the HDS100DE. Drilling was hampered by a number of maintenance problems, typical problems included leaking piston seals, split hydraulic hoses, blown fuses, ice plugs, a snapped throttle cable, soot coated heater coils and a seized engine, all of which were repaired in the field from spare parts carried with the drill or the flushing of the drill at night with anti freeze, though at considerable expense to drilling time.

The sources of water for drilling differed depending on the glacier surface conditions at the time of drilling. During snow-covered conditions toward the end of the winter it was hoped that sufficient water would be available at the base of the snow pack sourced from percolation of surface melt, to supply drilling water. However this source was not available due to the difficulty of reaching the base of the ~ 4 m snow pack and on the one occasion the ice surface was accessed to begin a hole, no melt water was present, thus snow was melted by recirculating hot water into the supply butt – which was intermittently topped up with snow to provide drilling water. During summer drilling on the ablating ice surface, water was siphoned under gravity or pumped from supraglacial streams or pools up glacier from the drill site and transported via long hoses (typically ≥ 100 m) to the reservoir butt (Figure 2.10.b). During drilling water could be recirculated from the borehole to the reservoir. Recirculation involved pumping melt water generated during drilling back to the water butt from a collecting pool at the side of the borehole melted prior to the commencement of the drilling, the collecting pool was fed from the borehole naturally as water flows back up the hole during drilling. At Tsanfleuron recirculation was

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

achieved using a two-stroke petrol pump manufactured by Koshin, model SEN-25L type BAB – 0, with 25 mm / 1 inch connections, a maximum capacity of 115 L min⁻¹ and a power output of 1.05 kW. Re-circulation ceased to function when hydraulic connections were made and englacial borehole drainage occurs; in these situations the borehole was often abandoned.

In order to drill a borehole, the hot pressurised water exiting the drill flowed through high pressure Conti Asymflex 3TE 12 Din rubber hose with steel mesh reinforced walls to the drill stem. Hoses varied in length but were typically ~ 100 m at Tsanfleuron. Markings were placed on the hose at 5 m intervals with coloured insulating tape to allow the driller to determine the depth of the drill tip during drilling. The drill stem (~ 1.5 m in length) was attached at one end to the high pressure hose and at the other to a slim drilling tip, which housed the drilling nozzle. Nozzles were interchangeable and had a small aperture ranging in diameter from 1.0 to 1.5 mm through which the water flowed as a “pencil jet”. Pencil jet nozzles of 1.4 mm diameter were used in the drilling of the Tsanfleuron boreholes. Following drilling, prior to inclinometry and installation of sensors, holes were reamed out using an alternative drill stem, tip and nozzle configuration. Reaming (and cable following for re-inclinometry) involved a shorter drill stem, ~ 0.7 m long, a “cable following” drill tip (Figure 2.23.), the use of nozzles producing a cone shaped spray of water and a higher water flow rate leaving the drill to enlarge the diameter of the borehole. With drilling pressures of 90 – 135 bar and water temperatures of approximately 120 – 150 °C drilling rates in clean temperate ice are typically ~ 2 m min⁻¹ near the ice surface, decreasing to 0.5 m min⁻¹ at depth and near the bed (Hubbard and Glasser, 2005). A decrease in drilling speed was attributed to cooling en route to the drill stem as the hose rested on the glacier surface and the development of a layer of silty clasts at the bottom of the borehole as they were melted out of debris rich basal ice. Drilling rate could be increased by increasing the water temperature and pressure, though only within a certain range of values, and by insulating the hose with foam pipe lagging sections over the glacier surface. Drilling was conducted with an over-the-shoulder technique, whereby the driller fed the high pressure hose over their shoulder and down the borehole. Skill was required to ensure the drill tip was kept just above the base of the borehole in order to achieve the optimum drilling efficiency and verticality. Using the over-the-shoulder technique allowed the driller to feel what the drill stem was doing. For example, sudden free fall of the drill stem occurred when englacial voids were intersected, accompanied by a decrease in water level and an associated sudden increase in the weight of the drilling hose (when the borehole was water filled the hose was largely buoyant but when drainage occurred the pressure in the borehole was atmospheric pressure and the driller thus had to support the entire and occasional considerable weight of the water filled hose).

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Drilling was halted when the drill reached the glacier bed or an obstacle (large englacial boulder) preventing further advance of the drill stem, or the borehole drained englacially. The bed was assumed to have been reached when no further drill tip advance occurred despite the stem being kept at its maximum depth for a number of minutes. Ice depth determined solely from the length of boreholes may have been misleading if the drill stem encountered a steeply sloping bed and slid along it rather than terminating perpendicular to it (Lliboutry, 2002). Fortunately, particularly with shallow holes in temperate ice, a combination of factors came together to indicate that the bed has been reached. For example at Tsanfleuron bed detection was aided by data on ice depth generated by ground penetrating radar (GPR) surveys of the glacier at the drill sites. In at least one borehole drilled during spring 2004 (BH04-06) a sudden drop of the drill stem was experienced followed by an impact with what appeared to be a solid object and an associated water pressure drop within 5 m of where the GPR data suggested the bed was. No subglacial substrate was found on the drill stem at the time of drilling, on the inclinometer or on recovered basal water-pressure probes, supporting evidence of a hard bed and a subglacial cavity. Upon termination of drilling the hose was removed from the borehole by walking the hose away from the hole over the shoulder of the driller and drilling assistant. Once drilled (in summer) boreholes were isolated from supraglacial water inflow via channel diversion to prevent moulin formation.

Figure 2.10: Hot water drilling (a) HDS1000BE drilling setup, April 2004. (b) Hydrological engineering a water supply to be pumped to the supply reservoir, August 2006.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

2.3.2 Borehole classification

Each borehole drilled was given a specific code indicating its year of drilling and the order in which the holes were drilled in each year. For example, BH04-02 was the second hole drilled in 2004, while BH05-07 was the seventh hole drilled in 2005. During drilling any sudden increase in the rate of drill advance or a drop in borehole water level at height above the bed was interpreted as a connection to an englacial void or drainage channel; These two interpretations were distinguished on the basis of whether or not the water level in the hole recovered; if so the connection was with a void of finite volume rather than an active linked englacial channel. Details of the holes drilled, their locations, drilling dates (and subsequent dates of reaming), depth, any englacial connections, the type (if any) of bed connection, water level fluctuations and instruments and sensors installed there in were recorded in a drilling log (Table 2.3) Figure 2.2 gives borehole locations on the glacier surface.

<i>Hole</i>	<i>Date drilled (cumulative day beginning 2004)</i>	<i>Depth (m)</i>	<i>Bed contact?</i>	<i>Northing</i>	<i>Easting</i>	<i>Instrumentation</i>	<i>Notes (cumulative day beginning 2004)</i>
BH04-01	27/04/04 (118)	94.0	No	46°19'28.80	7°13'42.50	Thermistors	Drilled to 25 m (118), Drilled to 59 m (121), Drilled to 77 m (123) ice plug at 10 m, Drilled to 94 m and reamed (128)
BH04-06	12/05/04 (133)	64.0	Yes	46°19'5.57	7°13'47.80	Thermistors	Drilled to 64 m and reamed (133), Cavity at 64 m and hard bed contact, drained
BH05-07	12/08/05 (590)	98.5	Yes	46°19'18.641	7°13'42.667	Thermistors, Electrical conductivity & Water pressure	Drilled to 90 m* (587), Partially drained (589), Partially drained (597)
BH05-10	04/08/05 (582)	56.0	Yes	46°19'5.774	7°13'48.007	Electrical conductivity	Large cavity at 23 – 24 m*, Partially drained (582), Reamed (586), Partially drained (587) to 22 m*, Partially drained (588) to 15 m*, Water full (597)
BH05-12	05/08/05 (583)	58.0	Yes	46°19'5.567	7°13'47.799	Water pressure	Water full (587) bubbles at surface, Water full (597)
BH05-13	10/08/05 (588)	59.0	Yes	46°19'14.808	7°13'52.697	Water pressure (self logging)	Partially drained (590)
BH05-16	20/08/05 (598)	128.5	Yes	46°19'28.799	7°13'42.498	Thermistors & Electrical conductivity	Small cavity at 50 m*, Crack at 85 m*, Partially drained (602) to 25.5 m*
BH05-17	24/08/05 (602)	132.0	Yes	46°19'28.505	7°13'42.727	Water pressure (self logging)	Partially drained (603)

* All depths measured from the surface down

Table 2.3: Borehole drilling log and details of borehole instrumentation.

2.3.3 Borehole instrumentation

Temperature

Hot water borehole drilling creates a thermal disturbance in the ice. The best option to limit the thermal disturbance is to drill the hole as quickly as possible using high flow rates with high temperature drilling water (Makinson, 2003). Due to the heat supplied in borehole generation, when temperature sensing instruments are deployed soon after drilling they are not registering a true ice temperature but the decay of temperature with time back toward the undisturbed temperature (Humphrey, 1991). The duration of the thermal disturbance is prolonged by liquid water remaining in the hole following drilling (Suter *et al.*, 2001). To counteract this disturbance, it is necessary to either allow sufficient time for borehole closure via ice creep (Paterson, 1977) and thermal equilibration with its surrounding ice, or apply correction factors to measured temperatures to account for the thermal disturbance and possible convective flows in the liquid water in the borehole. A technique to determine the undisturbed ice temperature from that of a thermally disturbed borehole was outlined by Humphrey (1991). Rather than the simple technique of comparing temperature decay with an inverse time model, Humphrey (1991) derived a numerical model to predict the heat flow to a refreezing borehole when the temperature record for the borehole is shorter than the stabilization time required to return to the undisturbed temperature.

Previous methods for temperature sensing in glacier ice

A number of techniques have been used to determine the temperature of glacier ice via borehole investigations. The most common and successful of these are outlined below, along with an indication of the level of accuracy obtained.

Borehole closure method

Harrison (1972), in a study of Blue Glacier, Washington, U.S.A., used a simple indirect method of temperature measurement based on the rate of closure of the boreholes. The closure of water filled boreholes by freezing indicated a heat flux away from the wall of the borehole, the rate of which was interpreted in terms of the temperature of the ice at the time the hole was drilled. The rate of closure was calculated from the electrical power supplied to a conical thermal drill and its rate of progress when reaming and re-reaming holes at week long intervals. At a depth of 105 m an estimated uncertainty in temperature of 0.02 or 0.03 °C is reported.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Thermocouples

Echelmeyer *et al.* (1992) monitored ice temperatures near the surface of Jakobshavns Isbræ, West Greenland by means of thermocouples and thermistors installed to depths of 14 m with a reported accuracy for the thermocouples of ± 0.3 K. Thermistor accuracy was reported to be “about an order of magnitude better” than that for thermocouples (Echelmeyer *et al.*, 1992). Thermocouple accuracy reported in various other studies is of the order of tenths of a degree as summarized in Table 2.4.

<i>Glacier</i>	<i>Glacier type</i>	<i>Years of study</i>	<i>Maximum deployment depth</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Variegated Glacier, Alaska	Temperate.	1973	20 m	$\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$	Bindschadler <i>et al.</i> (1976)
Urumqi Glacier No.1, China	Polythermal	1984	15 – 20 cm (into subglacial tunnel walls)	$\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$	Echelmeyer and Zhongxiang (1987)
Jakobshavns Isbrae, Greenland	Cold	1984 - 1986	14 m	$\pm 0.3^{\circ}\text{C}$	Echelmeyer <i>et al.</i> (1992)
McCall Glacier, Alaska	Polythermal	1972 and 1975	15 m	$\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$	Rabus and Echelmeyer (2002)

Table 2.4: Thermocouple temperature sensors and their stated accuracy used in several previous studies.

Thermistors

Early sub-surface ice temperature measurements were made in 1939 using specifically designed resistance thermometers constructed from copper resistance coils wound around brass tubes, deployed within the Ross Ice Shelf, Antarctica with an accuracy of “better than 0.1°C ” (Alton Wade, 1947). Paterson (1971) on the Athabasca glacier, Alberta Canada, used pairs of thermistors attached to the multi core power cable of electrically powered thermal drills. Temperatures were measured to a standard error of 0.02 to 0.03°C . Paterson (1972), in a follow up study, used thermistors on the same glacier in holes drilled 10 m down into the ice, with an accuracy of 0.04°C . Harrison (1975), however, in the measurement of borehole temperatures on Blue Glacier, Washington USA, achieved an order of magnitude better accuracy (an accuracy of between 0.002 to 0.005°C) using glass encapsulated thermistors with a nominal resistance of $3000\ \Omega$ at 0°C . Each thermistor assembly was calibrated in the laboratory in ice baths prepared using distilled water and (distilled water) ice and the whole assembly was again calibrated in the field at the time of deployment in water filled boreholes at a depth of 1.5 m. Recent studies by

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Pettersson and Blatter (Pers.comm)² in Storgläciaren, Sweden, have seen thermistor strings achieve a temperature measurement accuracy of ± 0.04 °C. The best precision achieved using thermistors was reported by Clow *et al.* (1996) for the high precision temperature logging system used at GISP2, Greenland and at Taylor Dome, Antarctica. Temperatures were measured using negative temperature coefficient (NTC) thermistors manufactured by Fenwall Electronics whose resistances were measured with a commercially available digital multi-meter housed in a stable environment, resulting in reported precisions of 0.00011 – 0.00032 °C. Thermistor accuracy reported in various other studies is of the order of a few hundredths of a degree, as summarized in Table 2.5. In addition to glaciological studies, thermistors are also the mainstay temperature measurement technique for other geophysical disciplines in non ice boreholes e.g. in permafrost boreholes with accuracies in the range ± 0.05 to ± 0.1 °C (Sass *et al.*, 1979, Isaksen *et al.*, 2000, Smith and Burgess, 2002 and Harris *et al.*, 2001, 2003) and for measurement of ground temperatures with accuracies in the range ± 0.02 to ± 0.1 °C (Blackwell and Spafford, 1987, Beck and Balling, 1988, Blackwell and Steele, 1989, Prenskey, 1992, Philips *et al.*, 2002).

Glacier	Thermal regime	Years of study	Maximum deployment depth	Accuracy	Reference
Seward Glacier, Yukon	Temperate	1948 and 1949	62.2 m	± 0.1 °C	Sharp (1951)
Taku Glacier, Alaska	Temperate	1950-1953	170 ft	± 0.01 to 0.03 °C	Miller (1954)
Wilkes Station, Antarctica	Cold	1957 - 1959	16 m	± 0.05 °C	Cameron and Bull (1962)
Meighen Ice cap, Canada	Cold	1965 - 1967	121 m	± 0.05 °C	Paterson (1968)
Athabasca Glacier, Canada	Temperate	1967 - 1969	257 m	± 0.02 to 0.03 °C	Paterson (1971)
Athabasca Glacier, Canada	Temperate	1967 - 1970	10 m	0.04 °C	Paterson (1972)
Trapridge Glacier, Yukon	Cold	1972 - 1973	87 m	± 0.02 °C	Jarvis and Clarke (1975)
Steele Glacier, Yukon	Cold	1972	114 m	Not stated	Jarvis and Clarke (1975)
Blue Glacier, Washington	Temperate	1971 and 1972	192 m	± 0.002 to 0.005 °C	Harrison (1975)
Steele Glacier, Yukon	Cold	1972 - 1974	114 m	± 0.075 °C	Clarke and Jarvis (1976)
White Glacier, Axel Heiberg Island	Cold	1956 - 1962	280 m	± 0.2 °C	Muller (1976)
Barnes Ice cap, Canada	Polythermal	1975	200 m	± 0.1 °C	Classen (1977)
Barnes Ice cap, Canada and Sukkertoppen Iskappe, Greenland	Cold	1974 - 1977	8.6 m (Barnes Ice cap) and 23 m (Sukkertoppen Iskappe)	± 0.05 °C	Hooke (1978)
Barnes Ice cap, Canada	Polythermal	1974 - 1978	276 m	± 0.05 °C	Hooke <i>et al.</i>

² Dr Rickard Pettersson, Department of Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, Sweden. Dr Heinz Blatter, Institute for Atmospheric and Climate Science, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich, Switzerland.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

James Ross Island Ice cap, Antarctica	Cold	1976 - 1981	14 m	± 0.1 °C	(1980) Aristarain <i>et al.</i> (1987)
White Glacier, Axel Heiberg Island	Polythermal	1974 - 1981	380 m	± 0.2 °C	Blatter (1987)
Urumqi Glacier No.1, China	Polythermal	1984	15 – 20 cm (into subglacial tunnel walls)	± 0.04 °C	Echelmeyer and Zhongxiang (1987)
Vestfonna Ice cap, Svalbard	Polythermal	1956 - 58	12.1 m	Not stated	Palosuo (1987)
Colle Gnifetti, Monte Rosa, (Grenzgletscher) Switzerland	Cold	1977 - 1985	124 m	Few hundredths of a degree	Haerberli and Funk (1991)
Jakobshavns Isbrae, Greenland	Cold	1984 - 1986	12 m	± 0.03 °C	Echelmeyer <i>et al.</i> (1992)
Jakobshavns Isbrae, Greenland	Cold	1988 - 1989	1550 m	± 0.05 °C	Iken <i>et al.</i> (1993)
GISP2, Greenland and Taylor Dome, Antarctica	Cold	1994 and 1995(GISP2) 1994 and 1995 (Taylor Dome)	3000 m (GISP2) 554 m (Taylor Dome)	± 0.00011 to 0.00032 °C	Clow <i>et al.</i> (1996)
Amitsuloq, West Greenland	Cold	1992	1.75 m (snowpack)	± 0.2 °C	Pfeffer and Humphrey, (1996)
Ice Stream B, Antarctica	Cold	1993 - 1994	500 m	± 0.05 to 0.1 °C	Harrison <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Hans Tausen Ice Cap, Greenland	Cold	1993 - 1994	10 m	Not stated	Braithwaite <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Law Dome, East Antarctica	Cold	1996	1200 m	± 0.02 °C	Van Ommen <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Engabreen, Norway	Temperate	Several days in 1996 and 1997	210 m (bed accessed via tunnel not borehole)	± 0.02 °C	Cohen <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Colle Gnifetti, Monte Rosa, (Grenzgletscher) Switzerland	Cold	1996 - 1997	101 m	± 0.05 °C	Luthi and Funk, (2001)
Breithorn plateau and Grenzgletscher, Switzerland	Temperate and Cold	1991, 1992 and 1994	120 m	± 0.1 °C	Suter <i>et al.</i> (2001)
South Pole, Antarctica	Cold	2001	2345 m	± 0.11 to 0.24 °C	Price <i>et al.</i> (2002)
McCall Glacier, Alaska	Polythermal	1972	75 m	± 0.1 °C	Rabus and Echelmeyer (2002)
Kuparuk basin, Alaska	Snow pack	1994 -1995	Base of snow pack	± 0.3 °C	Taras <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Lomonosovfonna Ice cap, Svalbard	Cold	1997	120 m	± 0.05 °C	Van de Wal <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Siple Dome, West Antarctica	Cold	1997 - 1998	1004 m	± 0.02 °C	Engelhardt, (2004)
Baltoro Glacier, Pakistan	Unknown	2004	Ice surface and surface debris layer	± 0.25 to 0.4 °C	Mihalcea <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland	Temperate	2004 - 2007	128.5 m	± 0.04 °C	This study

Table 2.5: Thermistor temperature sensors and their stated accuracy deployed in this and several previous studies.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

On the basis of these studies and the cost and robustness of thermistors in comparison to thermocouples, thermistors were chosen for snow and ice temperature measurements in this study. Thermistor strings attached to CR-10 and CR-10X data loggers recorded temperatures from the time of first deployment in the spring of 2004 until January 2007.

Thermistor theory

Thermistors are metal oxide semiconductors the resistance of which varies as a function of temperature. Negative temperature coefficient (NTC) thermistors are characterized by decreasing resistance with increasing temperature (Figure 2.11). One of the key features of thermistors, making them sensitive indicators of temperature change, is the fact that they display a large change in resistance for a small change in temperature.

Figure 2.11: Relationship between resistance and temperature for Fenwal UNICURVE 192 – 502 LET – A01 thermistors, plotted from figures produced by Fenwal Inc.

A number of empirically based formulations of the relationship between resistance measured by a thermistor and temperature have been presented (Thermometrics Inc., 2004). Initially, resistance temperature characteristics were plotted with the log of resistance as a function of the reciprocal of absolute temperature. More recently, resistance temperature characteristics have been represented by considering the log of resistance to be a polynomial in the reciprocal of absolute temperature (Thermometrics Inc., 2004). The most widely used polynomial form is that proposed by Steinhart and Hart (1968), which requires calibration of resistance at three temperatures, and is represented as:

$$\frac{1}{T} = A' + B'(\ln R_s) + C'(\ln R_s)^3 \quad (2.3.1)$$

where:

T = Temperature (Kelvin),

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

R_s = Resistance of temperature sensor,
 A', B' and C' = Calibration constants,

It has been shown that, over a restricted range of temperature, accuracies of ± 0.005 °C can be achieved using this formulation (Sostmann and Metz, 1992 and Thermometrics Inc., 2004).

Probe design and construction

Thermistors were chosen in preference to thermocouples as they have greater accuracy, are more stable and provide greater sensitivity to small-scale temperature fluctuations while being less complex and less expensive (Thermometrics Inc., 2004). Fenwal UNICURVE 192 – 502 LET-A01 (hereafter “FU-A01”) interchangeable thermistors, with a nominal resistance of $5\text{ K } \Omega$ at 25 °C were selected for temperature probe construction as they are high quality, inexpensive and had previously been used successfully in borehole temperature logging studies on Storgläciaren, Sweden (Pettersson, Pers.comm)³. The FU-A01 thermistors are small, epoxy coated, highly stable and reliable thermistors with a manufacturer’s stated tolerance of ± 0.2 °C (Honeywell, 1998). In house sensor manufacture took the following procedure:

- (a) The tinned copper alloy legs of the thermistors were cut to a length of ~ 15 mm.
- (b) Heat shrink tubing ~ 25 mm in length was slid over the exposed ends of twin core multi strand plain annealed copper wire (7/0.20 mm) (speaker cable).
- (c) The legs were soldered to the PVC insulated multi strand speaker cable.
- (d) The heat-shrink was slid back down the wire and shrunk in place over the thermistor legs to prevent short circuiting between the thermistor legs.
- (e) Each thermistor bead and its (heat-shrink-covered) legs was placed in the bulb of disposable plastic pipettes and potted in resin (Araldite) specifically designed for potting of electrical connections (Figure 2.12).

The process of potting in resin not only water-proofs the electrical connections and protects the thermistor from the high englacial pressures anticipated, but it also helps prevent changes in the oxidization state of the metal oxide thermistors, relieves strain where wires attach to the ceramic bodies of the thermistors and, by increasing the thermal capacity and increasing the thermal inertia of the sensor, attenuates the response to rapid temperature fluctuations.

³ Dr Rickard Pettersson, Department of Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, Sweden.

Figure 2.12: Fenwal UNICURVE thermistor probe deployed in this study.

Cables were cut from 100 m and 500 m rolls in the following lengths: 10.0, 10.2, 10.4, 10.6, 10.8, 11.0, 11.2, 11.4, 11.6, 11.8, 12.0, 13.0, 14.0, 15.0, 16.0, 18.0, 22.0, 26.0, 30.0, 50.0, 70.0, 90.0, 100.0 130.0 and 150.0 m. Sets of sensor strings were assembled incorporating each of these lengths, sufficient to instrument three boreholes. If joins in the cable were necessary they were double heat shrunk, once over the individual soldered joint and secondly to hold the contacts a distance of at least 30 cm apart along the length of the cable. This task was achieved by looping the cable back on its self to limit the chance of shorting between the joints in the two cables should water ingress under the heat shrunk tubing (Figure 2.12), the joint was also sealed with self amalgamating rubber tape.

Nine individual thermistor strings were produced for deployment in three holes. Three strings were prepared for each hole: a short snow pack string, a medium length upper ice string and a longer deep ice string. Each sensor assembly was given an individual code based on the length of the wire attached to it and a letter corresponding to which borehole it belonged to (named A, B and C), for instance 10.0A was a 10.0 m long sensor assembly to be deployed in hole A (the first borehole). A further colour coding system was used to distinguish which string the sensors were to be incorporated into, red tape was used to indicate the snow pack strings, blue depicted the upper ice strings while white was used for the longer lower ice strings. Refer to Tables 3.8, 4.2 and 4.3 for details of the deployment locations of thermistors in the snow pack, ice and crevasse respectively.

Probe calibration

FU-A01 thermistors are high precision but have a relatively low manufacture's stated accuracy of ± 0.2 °C, however, higher accuracy was achieved by conducting additional calibrations of the temperature probes, these followed the procedures of Pettersson (pers.com)⁴ and Blatter (1998) who achieved an accuracy of ± 0.04 °C. A numeric calibration of the thermistor probes using the results of laboratory calibration experiments was conducted to calculate the calibrated ice temperature, T_{cal} , using the method for calibrating Fenwal thermistors as developed by Blatter (1998) on the basis of relationships presented by Fenwal. The numerical calibration was further improved by an empirically derived adjustment factor, A^* , from further calibration in a water soaked snow pack in the field. Initially parameterized ice temperature, T_{par} , was determined from the resistance recorded by the CR10-X logger ($R(T_{par})$) during a laboratory calibration procedure at 0.000 °C using the following equation from Fenwal, presented by Blatter (1998):

$$T_{par} = \frac{T'_0 B^*}{\left[T'_0 \log \left[\frac{R(T_{par})}{R(T'_0)} \right] \right] + B^*} \quad (2.3.2)$$

where:

- T_{par} = Temperature at which resistance is $R(T_{par})$ (K) (set to ice point (0.000°C) during laboratory calibration) ,
- T'_0 = Reference temperature (298.15 K),
- $R(T_{par})$ = Resistance at temperature T_{par} (resistance recorded by the logger) (Ω),
- $R(T'_0)$ = Resistance at reference temperature T_0 (5000 Ω),
- B^* = Calibration parameter determined empirically from the calibration of the sensors in a mixture of distilled water and distilled water ice cubes (values for each sensor given in Table A1 (see appendix)).

The resistance ($R(T_{par})$) was determined during laboratory experiments at 0.000 °C. Thermistors were calibrated in a mixture of distilled water and distilled water ice cubes, used to produce a temperature of 0.000 °C. Temperatures were recorded using the same data logging techniques as in the field, every 2 minutes for a period of greater than 2 hours. Distilled water was chosen as a method of calibration due to the ease of formation of the ice point at precisely 0.000 °C (at STP). Harrison (1975) successfully conducted calibrations of thermistors in water baths prepared with distilled water and distilled water ice. The distilled water ice cubes were produced in ice cube bags and handled using gloves to minimise the possibility of contamination. Glassware used during the calibration procedure was sterilized and triple rinsed with distilled water prior to use. The thermistors were fixed in 3 bunches each containing 36 sensors, wired to AM16/32

⁴ Dr Rickard Pettersson, Department of Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, Sweden.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

multiplexers, attached to the CR-10X data loggers and then suspended from a retort stand into three 3 L glass beakers (sufficiently large to allow the heat capacity of the water bath to be considerably larger than the temperature sensors, so that the temperature of the water bath is negligibly altered when they are immersed). The beakers were placed on top of magnetic stirring plates with a magnetic stirrer placed in the bottom of each beaker such that thermal gradients in the liquid bath were minimized and the beakers were placed in a refrigerator to provide a stable environment similar to that which the sensors would be exposed to in the field. Two separate calibrations were conducted, one with just distilled water ice cubes, which were allowed to melt during the calibration and secondly using a mixture of distilled water ice cubes and distilled water from the beginning of the calibration. The distilled water ice cubes were placed in the beakers, completely covering the bunched thermistors with the magnetic stirrers continually operating, the beakers were also manually stirred periodically while the temperatures were logged.

A correction was required to the parameterized temperature (T_{par}) determined from Equation 2.3.2 to account for the difference between the parameterized temperature and the actual temperature. This difference arose from the fact that Equation 2.3.2 is an approximation of the resistance temperature relationship for Fenwal thermistors, not an exact formulation of the relationship, the corrected calibrated temperature (T_{cal}) is determined from the following equation (Blatter, 1998):

$$T_{cal} = m(T_{par}(C))^2 + (1 - 10m)T_{par}(C) \quad (2.3.3)$$

where:

T_{cal} = Calibrated temperature (K),

$m = 0.00058333$ (applicable to all Fenwal thermistors),

$T_{par}(C)$ = Parameterized temperature in Celsius.

The final calibrated temperature was determined by adjusting T_{cal} using a sensor specific correction factor, A^* , determined empirically from the snow calibration. Sensor assemblies, cables and data logger enclosures were buried under at least 1 m of water-soaked snow. The data loggers were set to record temperature at 5 minute intervals and were left logging for a period in excess of 48 hours. At the end of the calibration period the sensors were dug up, results used to derive the correction factor, A^* , and assembled into their respective strings ready for installation into the boreholes. The correction was applied in a similar way to Harrison (1975), in the form:

$$T_{cor} = T_{cal} + A^* \quad (2.3.4)$$

where

T_{cor} = Final calibrated temperature,

T_{cal} = Intermediate calibrated temperature,

A^* = Correction factor determined using snow calibration (given in Table A2 (see appendix)).

The calibration was validated by deployment of two thermistors at the same height in BH04-01, (Figure 2.20).

Field deployment of thermistors

Ice

Thermistor strings were assembled only after borehole drilling had been completed, allowing each string to be tailored to the depth of each hole. Thermistors were not equally spaced down through the ice but were arranged such that there was higher resolution spatial coverage in the top 20 m of the ice and in the bottom few meters near the bed, with widely spaced thermistors at mid depth in the ice where the ice temperatures were expected to be stable. Strings were held taught in the boreholes by means of short sections (~ 60 mm) of thick walled steel pipe attached to their bottom to facilitate borehole insertion, lowered down the boreholes and anchored at the ice surface to wooden poles across the top of the boreholes (Figure 2.13.a). Thermistors were deployed as outlined in Table 2.6.

	<i>BH04-01</i>	<i>BH04-06</i>	<i>BH05-07</i>	<i>BH05-16</i>
Ice thickness (at time of drilling) (m)	130.8	59.9	98.5	128.5
Depth of lowest thermistor (m)	89.6	59.9	98.5	127.5
Date of thermistor string deployment	13/05/2004	13/05/2004	13/08/2005	24/08/2005
Number of thermistors in borehole	12	8	19	6

Table 2.6: Thermistors deployed in this study (BH05-16 was drilled to the bed adjacent to BH04-01 and had the deep ice thermistor string assembled for BH04-01 deployed in it).

Snow pack

Thermistor strings were attached to 34 mm diameter vertical wooden poles rather than directly to the metal data logger mounting poles (see below) to limit errors caused by heat conduction along the mounting pole. During summer field visits, sensors were attached at 20 cm intervals upwards from the ice surface and secured by means of plastic cable ties slotted into notches cut in the pole. This allowed the thermistors supported in the air to record air temperatures before burial (and after melt out) and the snow temperature profile to be recorded throughout the snow pack build-up and the decay the following spring.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Crevasse

A thermistor string was deployed in a small crevasse ~ 1.75 m up glacier of BH05-07 (Figure 2.13.b) in an attempt to investigate quantitatively the hypothesis that crevasses act as heat sinks near the glacier surface through ponding of cold air (Section 1.9.2). The string was weighted and installed vertically down the crevasse to a depth of 6 m and supported by a length of Dexian spanning the crevasse attached to a wooden pole drilled ~ 2.2 m into the ice, (Figure 2.13.b).

Figure 2.13: Thermistor string deployment on Tsanfleuron (a) Wooden pole used to anchor the thermistor string at the top of a borehole. (b) Installation of crevasse thermistor string. Note also the mounting of the data logger and solar panel in the background.

Data-logger mounting

Data loggers and solar panels were mounted using ‘U’ bolts to scaffolding poles drilled ~ 4.8 m vertically into the ice surface. Loggers were initially mounted ~ 1 m above the ice surface on the up glacier side of the pole, but were raised further above the ice surface via additional 1.6 m sections of scaffolding pole added intermittently as the snow pack thickness increased. Solar panels were similarly raised and lowered in response to the fluctuating snow surface. Power connections to the data logger were maintained through the use of in-house manufactured solar panel extension cables. The wooden thermistor mounting poles were attached to the vertical scaffolding poles with cable ties rather than metal brackets to minimise conduction.

Data logger control, data collection and processing

Campbell Scientific CR-10 and CR-10X data loggers and AM16X32 multiplexers were used in this study to control and log various sensors.

Data logger and multiplexer wiring for thermistor control

Two CR-10X data loggers (SN XE5207 and X6305) and one CR-10 (SN 12360) were used in the monitoring of the 3 instrumented boreholes. One of the data loggers had an extended 2 MB memory (SN XE5207) while the storage capacity of the standard memory data loggers was augmented with a SM 716 storage module and a CSM1 card reader storage module (SN E3119). Campbell Scientific AM16X32 multiplexers (SN5028, 5029, 5277 and E1414) were used to increase the number of sensors that could be measured by the data loggers. The AM16X32 allowed sequential multiplexing of up to 48 thermistors through two data logger COM terminals. Thermistors were wired to the multiplexers as shown in Figure 2.14.a. Three thermistors were wired to each of the SETs on the multiplexer allowing a maximum capacity of 48 thermistors to be measured during one program iteration. Completion fixed resistors forming part of the half bridge were located between the data logger and the multiplexer (Figure 2.14.a). The technique used for determination of the optimum value for the fixed resistors is outlined below.

Data logger malfunction causing corruption and loss of stored data frequently occurred. This was believed to be associated with static charge build up near the logger. Attempts to minimize the charge build up were only partially successful as the logger could not properly be grounded when located on the glacier. The use of CSM1 card reader storage modules, where available, proved a more robust storage medium, being less susceptible to corruption than the logger internal memory. Hardware shortages prevented storage cards being attached to all loggers, CSM1 modules were attached to CR-10 loggers rather than the CR-10Xs to ensure data storage if power loss occurred (only a problem with CR-10 loggers).

Figure 2.14: Thermistor wiring to CR-10(X) loggers and AM16X32 Multiplexers (a) Wiring diagram. (b) Field deployment in Campbell Scientific data logger enclosure, note the need for labelling of each thermistor wire.

Calculation of optimum value of fixed resistance for bridge measurements

The thermistor was configured in a half bridge with a fixed resistor, the value of which was selected such that the relationship between the voltage output and the resistance over the expected temperature range is almost linear. The value of the linearising resistor was determined from the following equation, after Burke (1981):

$$R_{ref} = \frac{R_b(R_a + R_c) - 2R_aR_c}{R_a + R_c - 2R_b} \tag{2.3.5}$$

where:

- R_{ref} = Optimum value for linearising resistor,
- R_a = Thermistor resistance at lowest temperature to be measured (48535Ω @ -20 °C),
- R_b = Thermistor resistance at middle temperature to be measured (27667Ω @ -10 °C),
- R_c = Thermistor resistance at highest temperature to be measured (16325Ω @ 0 °C).

The optimum size for the fixed resistor was determined to be 22.1 k Ω, rounded up to the nearest available size. This selection was confirmed as appropriate by the same resistor value being selected using the alternative inflection point and equal slope methods suggested by Thermometrics Inc. (2004).

Logging temperature using Campbell Scientific Instruction 5

Ice temperature measurements were made through the use of CR-10X data logger Instruction 5. Instruction 5 applies an excitation voltage to a half bridge wiring located between the logger and multiplexer, makes a single ended voltage measurement, reverses the excitation voltage, and makes another measurement. The difference between the two measurements is used to calculate the result to be stored in the final storage memory of the logger (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2000). The stored result is the radiometric (which eliminates voltage reference errors, (Campbell Scientific Inc., 2001)) ratio of the measurement to the excitation voltage, expressed in the form:

$$X = \frac{R_s}{R_s + R_f} \quad (2.3.6)$$

where:

X = Result stored in data logger final storage,

R_s = Resistance of temperature sensor (Ω),

R_f = Resistance of fixed resistor (Ω).

Equation 2.3.6 is rearranged to determine the resistance of the thermistor from the result stored in the data logger, resulting in the form of the equation:

$$R_s = \frac{XR_f}{(1 - X)} \quad (2.3.7)$$

Data collection

Field data collection was conducted using PConnectCE software on a HP Jornada palmtop running Windows Mobile Pocket PC 2003 Second Edition and backed up on compact flash cards. Data downloaded using PConnectCE was stored in the .bdf file format and transferred to computer by Active sync, automatically converting data format to a .dat or .xls format.

Error analysis for thermistor measurements

Outlined below is an analysis of the sources and magnitude of errors encountered making temperature measurements with the FU – A01 thermistors. Errors arise from both the data loggers and the sensors. Data logger errors are outlined and quantified, as are a list of error sources affecting the thermistors. A purely numerical determination of thermistor error was not possible due to there being no way of determining variation between thermistors due to the manufacture procedure. Thus, an empirical determination for sensor uncertainty is presented. Sensor and data logger uncertainties are combined to calculate the total error in temperature measurements, following which an assessment of thermistor calibration drift over time is presented.

Data logger errors

Campbell Scientific CR-10 and CR-10X data loggers have two resolution data formats for final storage: a low resolution (4 – character, 2 byte) and a high resolution (5 – character, 4 byte) format. The high resolution format was used for all temperature data storage in this study. In this format the small-scale oscillation clearly visible between day 125.4 and day 126.4 for thermistor 10.6c in Figure 2.15 equates to the data storage resolution, i.e. the smallest decimal place to which the result is stored in the logger, ~ 0.001 °C.

The AC half bridge instruction makes resistance measurements using a dual polarity 0.75 ms excitation pulse for ionic depolarisation with signal integration over the last 0.25 ms. Thus the excitation voltage is applied across the thermistor for exactly the same amount of time for each polarity to prevent sensors polarising with repetitive measurements (Campbell Scientific Inc, 2000). As a result of the analogue to digital conversion performed by the logger a second much larger resolution oscillation is clearly visible between day 125.0 and day 125.4 for thermistor 10.6c in Figure 2.15. This results from the resolution of the logger resistance measurement (Instruction 5) stated to be 0.67 mV, which can be seen empirically to equate to ~ 0.01 °C. The error in temperature measurement is half this, ~ 0.005 °C, given in Figure 2.16 by the shaded area for readings recorded as - 0.03 °C. This error can be illustrated by considering the hypothetical examples of point A, which is just under - 0.025 °C, which would be recorded by the logger as point A', while point B, just over - 0.025 °C, would be recorded as B' as a result of rounding. A third source of data logger uncertainty results from the accuracy of the data logger, stated to be 0.02 % of full scale input range used which in terms of error in temperature is equal to ~ 0.001 °C.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Figure 2.15: Temperature measured during snow calibration for three thermistors, indicating the magnitude of the errors associated with the data logger resistance measurement and data storage resolutions.

Figure 2.16: Diagrammatical representation of error as a result of the resolution of the data logger resistance measurements (see text for explanation).

Experimental design to minimise and quantify non data logger related sources of error in temperature measurements

Thermistor accuracy

FU- A01 thermistors are resistance temperature matched and interchangeable (pre calibrated). They have a nominal resistance of $5\text{ K } \Omega$ at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a manufacturer's stated tolerance of $\pm 0.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However further calibration has been shown to improve this accuracy to $\pm 0.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ when combined with data logger errors (Pettersson, Pers.comm)⁵.

Accuracy of fixed resistors in bridge

The temperature coefficient for the $22.1\text{ k}\Omega$ resistors used in this study is $15\text{ ppm }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$. From the internal data logger temperature recorded throughout the year the maximum temperature range to which the logger (and therefore the attached resistors) was exposed was 25 to $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thus the maximum resistance change resulting from a $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature variation is $16.6\text{ } \Omega$ which is less than 0.07% of the resistance of the fixed resistor.

Cable resistance

Long cable lengths have the effect of adding to the thermistor resistance (Clow *et al.*, 1996), the longer the length of the sensor cable the greater this additional resistance, thus wire with as low a capacitance as possible was used in sensor construction. In this study the uncertainty associated with longer cable lengths was calibrated out of the system: all thermistor assemblies were calibrated with the full cable lengths attached, no cables were lengthened or shortened in the field (where shortening was necessary, cutting the cable was avoided by looping excess cable along the thermistor string).

Selection of the excitation voltage to minimize effect of self-heating errors

The temperature of the thermistors increases above the ambient temperature as heat is dissipated as a result of the power generated when an excitation voltage is supplied and current flows through the sensor to make the resistance measurement. For an accurate measurement of temperature it is therefore necessary to design a circuit that minimises the temperature rise associated with self heating (Sostmann and Metz, 1992). The rate of temperature increase is given by the thermistor dissipation constant, making it possible to determine excitation voltage combinations that result in acceptable heating-induced errors. With the manufacturer's stated dissipation constant of $0.75\text{ mW }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ and a desirable level of error due to self heating of

⁵ Dr Rickard Pettersson, Department of Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, Sweden.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

± 0.001 °C (such that it can be considered negligible), the maximum power which could be supplied to the thermistor was 0.00075 mW, consequently the voltage across the thermistor must not exceed 190 mV for temperature measurements at -20 °C or 110 mV for measurements at 0 °C. These equate to maximum supply voltages of 277 mV and 260 mV respectively. An excitation voltage an order of magnitude smaller, (25 mV) was used in the AC half bridge measurements; hence self-heating errors were limited to negligible levels.

Errors resulting from cable capacitance and settling effects

Twin core cables composed of a pair of conductors separated by an insulator act as a capacitor when a voltage is applied across them - electrons are gradually stored until an opportunity for discharge occurs. Cable capacitance affects the signal level and is frequency dependent. The scale of the problem of wire capacitance is dependent on precise cable characteristics, length and the voltage across the conductors. Cable capacitance is almost impossible to quantify. However, the associated errors are minimised through the use of low excitation voltages, and where possible, cable with a low capacitance and are included in the empirical error calculation (below).

Errors associated with the thermal response of the sensor equilibration

Potential errors associated with slow thermal response of the monitoring instrument are not applicable as the thermistor beads are frozen into the ice and not inserted each time a measurement is made. Thus they are already in thermal equilibrium with their surroundings at the time of the measurement and do not experience rapid high frequency temperature fluctuations.

Errors associated with heat transfer along thermistor cables and mounting poles

Heat transfer along the mounting poles and thermistor cables is only likely to be problematic in the snow pack and the near surface ice, where temperature gradients are larger than at depth in the ice. The greatest problem is likely to be heat conduction into the ice in summer. Sensor cables would ideally be installed diagonally through the snow pack and ice rather than vertically, as such a setup would minimise heat conduction along the wires, which is greatest when cables pass perpendicularly through the thermal gradient. However, such a setup is not realistic for snow pack field deployment and is even more difficult in the ice. To minimise undesirable heat transfer along sensor cables, the diameter of the lead wires were kept as small as possible (following Sostmann and Metz, 1992). The potential for heat conduction along the steel mounting poles, drilled into the ice surface was several of orders of magnitude greater than that of the thermistor strings. Any heat flux into the ice as a result of conduction along mounting

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

poles and cables was masked by dissipation of much larger heat components of the energy balance at the surface. The thermistors deployed in the summer on the mounting pole to measure winter snow pack temperatures were not attached directly to the steel pole, rather they were cable tied to wooden poles fixed to the mounting poles with an air gap between (Figure 2.17). The insulating properties of the wood minimised heat conduction from the steel pole to the thermistors and vertically between the adjacent thermistors along the mounting poles, thereby limiting the errors in the snow or air measurement resulting from heat conduction. The problem of thermistors in the top few metres of the ice registering heat conduction into the ice from the mounting pole was minimised by ensuring that the mounting pole was installed > 1.5 m away from the borehole into which the sensors were deployed, allowing any heat conducted by the pole to be dissipated into the ice in its immediate proximity with minimal disturbance of ice surrounding the thermistors.

Figure 2.17: Mounting of snow pack thermistors, position of data logger mounting pole relative to the borehole, and position of excess thermistor cable at the end of the summer at the North site).

Errors associated with radiative heating of thermistors recording air temperatures and shallow near surface snow pack temperatures

The uncertainty associated with differential heating caused by incident solar radiation on thermistors or shading controlled cooling was minimised by installing all thermistors and cables together on the North side of the mounting pole preventing the thermistors receiving direct

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

sunlight and ensuring an equal shading effect on all thermistors (Figure 2.17). Excess thermistor cable (as mentioned above) was coiled up and placed in a plastic bag on the ice surface to allow burial by snow as early as possible to limit any errors associated with heating of the wire coils (Figure 2.17).

Errors associated with pressure variation

Experiments by Harrison (1975) over a depth range greater than that at Tsanfleuron suggest no significant effect of pressure on thermistor sensitivity.

Variability between thermistors as a result of the manufacture process

It was not possible to quantify the variability between thermistors as a result of variability in the manufacture process. Hence an accurate quantification of the temperature errors via the propagation of errors method was impossible, invoking the need for an empirical determination.

Empirically determined sensor uncertainty

All thermistors were calibrated at 0.000 °C in a distilled water / ice solution and further adjusted via a snow pack calibration. Basic ice point calibration allowed sensor calibration to an accuracy better than the manufacturer's stated accuracy of ± 0.2 °C (Figure 2.18). A further improvement in the accuracy was made by adjustment of all thermistors to their mean temperature (averaged over 40 readings) during their stable period in the snow pack (Figure 2.19). The mean standard deviation of the magnitude of the differences between the mean snow pack temperature of the thermistors used for adjustment and the individual non adjusted snow pack thermistor temperatures during the full stable period of > 150 readings indicates a sensor – performance – related error of ≤ 0.04 °C.

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Figure 2.18: Snow pack calibration temperature records before adjustment.

Figure 2.19: Snow pack calibration temperature records after adjustment.

Calculation of the total error in thermistor temperature measurements

Total error can be calculated from the individual components noted above. These include:

- Precision of data logger resistance measurement = ± 0.005 °C
- Resolution of data logger storage = ± 0.001 °C
- Data logger accuracy = ± 0.001 °C
- Thermistor accuracy (1 s.d.) = ± 0.04 °C

Adding the uncertainties to determine the maximum possible uncertainty gives:

$$0.005 + 0.001 + 0.001 + 0.04 = 0.047 \text{ °C} \quad (2.3.8)$$

However, as the different sources of error are independent and approximately random, it is possible to determine the uncertainty in the temperature measurement as the quadratic sum (Taylor, 1997) as follows:

$$\sqrt{(0.001)^2 + (0.005)^2 + (0.001)^2 + (0.04)^2} = 0.040 \text{ °C} \quad (2.3.9)$$

Thus, following Taylor (1997) the net error associated with temperature measurements is ± 0.040 °C and the error in any individual case is not larger than ± 0.047 °C.

Assumptions made as a result of the calibration procedure

The accuracy of the thermistors was only evaluated over a small temperature range close to 0 °C (initial calibration at the ice point of distilled water and secondary calibration in a snow pack at just below zero). However, the thermistors are Unicurve matched (i.e. all the thermistors produce a uniform response within stated tolerance limits) with manufacturer's calibration over the temperature range - 60 to 300 °C. Thus, we assume that the error is the same at all temperatures experienced in the field, but uncertainties increase with distance from the calibration point (Figure. 2.20).

Empirical investigation of thermistor calibration drift over time

The error analysis above suggests temperature measurements at all locations at the three boreholes have an error of ≤ 0.04 °C. An empirical experiment to investigate how these errors vary over time as a result of possible calibration drift was made by installing two thermistors (16.0a and 16.0c) at the same depth in BH04-01. Figure 2.20 shows the results of 1 year's simultaneous temperature measurements made by thermistors 16.0a and 16.0c, with a 45 ° line indicating the theoretical relationship between the two sensors, should no calibration drift occur. It is clear that the thermistors exhibit a consistent relationship over time with a mean difference of

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

0.011 °C and a standard deviation of 0.014 °C. However, there is a trend of increasing deviation away from the theoretical value at colder temperatures, indicating, that although small over the period of a year in the temperature range experienced by the two sensors, calibration drift does occur and is of the order of $\pm 0.03 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ below 0 °C. Thus, we can be confident that errors in temperature measurement are stable over time and accurate to $\pm 0.04 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at all deployment locations.

Figure 2.20: Temperature recorded by thermistor 16.0a plotted against that recorded by thermistor 16.0c, located at the same depth in BH04-01 over a one year period.

Water pressure

Measurements of water levels in boreholes, either manually using EC probes to detect the water surface or automatically using pressure transducers have commonly been used to make inferences as to the nature of borehole connections to the subglacial drainage system and the drainage system configuration and hydrological properties. Measurements of borehole water pressure have become one of the key investigative tools used in the characterisation of subglacial hydrology. Measurements have been made successfully on a number of glaciers including the dense borehole array to the bed of Haut Glacier d’Arolla using Druck PDCR850 pressure transducers (Sharp *et al.*, 1993; Hubbard *et al.*, 1995; Tranter *et al.*, 1997) and at Trapridge Glacier (Fischer and Clarke (2001).

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

Pressure transducers record water pressure by measurements of the resistance of a metal membrane which flexes in response to pressure fluctuations either side of the membrane (Hubbard and Glasser, 2005). In most cases the pressure on one side of the membrane is fixed and sealed in the sensor, at for example atmospheric pressure at sea level and the other side of the membrane is exposed to the water pressure fluctuations in the borehole.

Two types of water pressure sensor were deployed near the bottom of boreholes in this study, TRAFAG – Switzerland self logging water pressure sensors and data logger controlled Honeywell 24PCG Type Gage Unamplified – Noncompensated pressure sensors.

Self logging sensors

Two stainless steel TRAFAG – Switzerland self logging water pressure sensors (Figure 2.21 b) were deployed on single wires (allowing future cable following using the reaming drill stem and tip for recovery and re-inclinometry of the hole) in boreholes in Tsanfleuron where access was not readily available to data loggers.

Data logger controlled sensors

Subglacial water pressure sensors were manufactured from Honeywell 24PCG Type Gage Unamplified – Non-compensated pressure sensors. One side of the sensor was capped at atmospheric pressure while the other was left exposed through the sensor housing. The sensor was constructed in-house within a clear plastic tube of diameter 34 mm and length 130 mm. The electrical connectors were potted in resin to provide structural integrity and prevent water ingress. Small amounts of lead were potted in space around the pressure sensor within the plastic tube to increase the mass of the sensor and prevent buoyancy in the water filled borehole, giving each sensor (excluding cable) a mass of 300 - 400 g (Figure 2.21 a). Cable lengths of 150 m and 200 m were attached to the sensors. Prototype sensors were successfully tested in the laboratory on a pressure rig at a range of pressures up to 100 psi (6.9 bar) with the desired results and no sensor degradation or failure.

Water pressure sensors were deployed in exactly the same way as the thermistor strings and where necessary weighted with sections of steel pipe. Sensors were lowered to the bed then raised ~ 1 m before being anchored at the surface with wooden poles.

Figure 2.21: Water pressure sensors (a) Honeywell 24PCG data logger controlled sensor. (b) TRAFAG self-logging sensor.

The Honeywell 24PCG Type sensors require typically 10 V excitation (Max 12 V) provided using the switched 12 V supply facility on the CR-10X data loggers, however, in lab tests they were found to be fully operational with a lower voltage supply. The sensors have a pressure range of 250 psi (17.58 bar), a maximum over pressure of 500 psi, a response time of 1.0 msec and an operating temperature range of - 40 to + 85 °C. Sensors were calibrated at a 2.5 V excitation in the laboratory. Pressure measurements were made as a differential voltage measurement using Instruction 8 [2.5 V excite, delay and measure].

The subsidiary role of the water pressure data (to qualitatively assist in basal process determination) does not require such a rigorous error analysis as that conducted for the thermistors. The TRAFAG self logging water pressure sensors use Druck transducers with a manufacturer's stated error of $\pm 1.5\%$ over an operation temperature range of -20 to $+80$ °C. The Honeywell 24 PCG water pressure sensors have a manufacturer's stated sensitivity of 0.85 mV psi^{-1} . The TRAFAG (Druck) sensors are believed to record water pressure to an accuracy of $\pm 0.5 \text{ m}$ (Hubbard *et al.*, 1995), with a similar accuracy obtained for the Honeywell sensors.

Electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity (EC) measurements provide a fast and efficient surrogate for the measurement of the total dissolved solids in a solution. EC probes for use in glacier boreholes have been designed and deployed at Trapridge Glacier, Canada (Stone *et al.*, 1993) and at Small River Glacier, Canada (Smart and Ketterling, 1997). These studies reported conductivities in the

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

range $15 - 75 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and $0 - 15 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Gordon *et al.* (2001) used borehole EC profiling as a way of investigating water flow in and out of boreholes at Haut Glacier d'Arolla, Switzerland. The basic sensor design involves two electrodes fixed at a set distance apart, which are completely immersed in the subglacial water.

The basic theory of electrical conductivity measurements using two electrode type sensors is based on a relationship in which the resistance between the two exposed electrodes decreases as the solute concentration and thus the electrical conductivity of the solution increases (Hubbard and Glasser, 2005). The electrical conductivity of the solution is then determined as the inverse of the resistivity of the water between the two electrodes.

An EC sensor is constructed from two electrodes across which a resistance measurement can be made, mounted in and separated by an inert material, with a known electrode spacing geometry. Two main designs exist for electrical conductivity probes; the two pin electrode configuration e.g. as used by Smart and Ketterling (1997) and Stone *et al.*, (1993) and a concentric ring electrode configuration e.g. as used by Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002c). Electrodes need to be made from a metal with a high resistance to corrosion, either stainless steel or brass are metals of choice. Simple EC sensors were constructed from 2 pin light sockets as suggested by Hubbard and Glasser (2005 p.98). Screw connections between the cable and the terminals were made and both ends of the light-bulb holder sealed with fast setting epoxy resin, leaving a sealed water tight unit with improved structural integrity and robustness for englacial deployment, with the brass pins exposed for conductivity measurements. The protective end of the light bulb fitting had a number of holes drilled through it to allow unrestricted water flow past the electrodes (Figure 2.22).

Figure 2.22 Electrical conductivity probe manufactured from 230 V light fitting deployed at Tsanfleuron.

EC sensors were calibrated in KCL solutions following the method outlined by Stone *et al.*, (1993) to determine the cell constant for each sensor (a function of the individual geometry of each electrode pair). Sensors were placed sequentially in 3 L beakers containing:

- distilled water,
- a solution of 0.7452 g KCl dissolved in enough distilled water to make exactly 1 L of solution, and
- as for (b) but with an additional 1 L distilled water added to give a KCl solution of 0.3726 g l⁻¹.

The 3 L beakers were placed in a water bath of distilled water ice cubes and distilled water and placed in a fridge for the duration of the experiment to maintain the temperature as close to 0 °C as possible. Solutions were also cooled in the fridge prior to use (due to the strong temperature dependence of electrical conductivity measurements made in aqueous solutions as a result of ion mobility increasing with temperature). The EC probes were monitored using a CR10-X and AM16/32 multiplexer as described for thermistors (above) at 2 minute resolution for a period of at least 1 hour per solution.

The cell constant is the constant of proportionality relating measured conductivity to material conductance (Stone *et al.*, 1993) in the form:

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

$$\sigma^* = K_c G \quad (2.3.10)$$

where

σ^* = conductivity,
 K_c = cell constant,
 G = conductance.

As conductance is the reciprocal of resistance, individual cell constants were determined from the known conductivity of the solution and the resistance measured across the two exposed electrodes using the equation:

$$K_c = R_{EC} \sigma_s^* \quad (2.3.11)$$

where

K_c = cell constant,
 R_{EC} = resistance of EC sensor,
 σ_s^* = conductivity of solution.

At 0 °C the 1 L solution containing 0.745263 g of KCL in distilled water has a conductivity of 0.07736 S m⁻¹, this conductivity was used to determine cell constants.

EC sensors were attached to the data logger through the AM16X32 multiplexer and controlled in exactly the same way as the thermistors using the same resistor bridge and were deployed in the field at the base of boreholes, in a similar way as thermistors.

Electrical conductivity measurements are made using exactly the same measurement instructions and resistance bridge as the temperature measurements yielding similar data logger induced errors. In terms of EC data logger errors were:

- Logger resistance measurement precision = $\pm 0.005 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
- Resolution of data storage = $\pm 0.001 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
- Logger accuracy = $\pm 0.001 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$

Empirical determination of the sensor error (determined using the same technique as for the thermistors) suggests an error of $\pm 1.600 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, combined in quadrature with the data logger errors to give an uncertainty in electrical conductivity measurements of $\pm 1.60 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ which at no time exceeds $\pm 1.607 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$.

2.3.4 Differential GPS

The locations of the boreholes on the surface of the glacier were measured using a Magellan Promark X 10/10CP differential GPS system, with external directional antenna, A base station was established off the glacier on solid bedrock at the col between the Oldenhorn (3122.5 m

CHAPTER 2: FIELD SITE AND METHODS

a.s.l.) and Oldensattel (2737 m a.s.l.) to the North of the glacier. The roving DGPS system was placed at the borehole locations and allowed to acquire a fix for at least 10 minutes at each location to determine the locations to centimetric accuracy. Repeat DGPS determinations of the locations of the boreholes allow determination of the surface velocity.

2.3.5 Inclinometry

Repeat inclinometry of boreholes allows measurement of motion by ice deformation and subsequent calculation of strain heating at periods of 1 year or greater (Copland *et al.*, 1997c). To achieve such measurements boreholes were initially inclinometered soon after drilling. A single reinforced cable was then deployed in the borehole and allowed to freeze in. After a period of time (in the case of this study, 1 to 2 years) the borehole was re-drilled using a shortened drill stem (~ 0.5 m length), a special cable-following attachment, and a conical low pressure reaming nozzle (Figure 2.23). Once followed to the base, the wire was removed from the hole and the re-drilled hole inclinometered allowing determination of the ice deformation over the elapsed time period. The assumption was made that the cable followed the deformation of the ice and did not regelate normal to itself through the walls of the deforming hole (periods of rapid reaming tip advance during re-drilling indicated the holes had not fully closed and the assumption that the inclinometry cable did not regelate into the walls was valid). Deformation rates were calculated from the borehole deformation during the study period. Basal motion can also be derived by subtracting ice deformation from total surface motion.

Field deployment of Inclinometer

The MI-3 Digital borehole survey tool, commercially available from Icefield Tools Corporation, Canada was used to inclinometer boreholes drilled at Glacier de Tsanfleuron in April 2004 and August 2005 and to re-inclinometer the holes in August 2006. The MI-3 series inclinometer consists of a triaxial accelerometer sensor with an accuracy stated by the manufacturer of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ to measure the borehole inclination (vertical) and a triaxial fluxgate magnetometer with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ$ to measure the azimuth of the hole (relative to local magnetic north) enclosed in a stainless steel and bronze casing 1.15 m long, 25 mm in diameter and weighing 1.9 kg (Icefield Tools Corp., 2005) (further details are available from Copland *et al.*, 1997c). The sensor was operated in the field by a Palm Pilot which synchronised the clock with the instrument, started the survey and determined the synchronicity of shot intervals. When a shot was required (at set depths, incrementing in 0.5 or 1 m intervals), the depth was entered into the Palm Pilot and the data collection initiated. When recovered from the borehole the data were downloaded from

the inclinometer either via a wireless blue-tooth connection to the Palm Pilot or a RS232 cable link.

Figure 2.23: Cable following reaming tip used to re-drill closed boreholes.

2.3.6 Ice thickness and ablation measurements

Ice thickness at the time of borehole drilling and instrumentation was determined from the drilling logs (Table 2.3) and corrected to an ice thickness from a hole length using the inclinometry data and verified against 50 MHz Ground Penetrating Radar data collected along the across glacier transect during April 2004. Continuous ablation and accumulation measurements were made using the SR50 ultrasonic sensor deployed as part of the basic meteorological station (Section 2.2.1). Ice ablation was determined by periodic measurement of surface lowering relative to the top of data logger support masts drilled into the ice and exposed thermistors from the near surface englacial thermistor string, assuming a constant density for ice.

2.4 Laboratory measurements of ice core density

Introduction

An accurate record of ice density variation with depth was required for glacier temperature profile modelling and was necessary to calculate the pressure melting point for temperate ice. Ice density theoretically increases with depth as a result of pressure increase driven principally by bubble compression, a phenomena parameterized empirically by Schytt (1958). However, expansion resulting from temperature increase with depth observed in many glaciers can, if sufficient, counteract the overburden pressure densification effect (Paterson, 1994). Ice core analysis provided a means of determining a density profile specific to Tsanfleuron.

Method of density measurement

Density measurements were made at ~ 5 m intervals on sections of two ice cores (T96-5 and T97-1), assuming no density change via relaxation during cold storage. The 75 mm diameter ice cores were recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron during 1996 and 1997 using an adapted RAND corer powered by a portable generator (see Tison and Hubbard, 2000 for details). These came from two locations on the glacier, T97-1 ending englacially at ~ 40 m depth in the accumulation zone, and T96-5 from the surface ending at the bed near the terminus in the ablation zone.

Measurements of ice core density were based on volume and mass measurements made in a cold laboratory at -10 °C. The ends of ice core sections were squared off using a band saw. Volume calculations used the average of 6 diameter measurements (3 on each end of the core) (Figure 2.24.b) and the average of 3 length measurements with an accuracy of ± 1 mm made on core sections of various lengths (Figure 2.24.c). The mass value of each core section used in the density determination was the mean of 3 values determined using an electronic scale with an accuracy of ± 1 g (Figure 2.24.d). Sample depths were determined from the mid point of analysed core sample and the depth of the sample at the time of field collection.

Figure 2.24: Ice core density measurements (a) Squaring off ice core ends. (b) Length measurements. (c) Diameter measurements. (d) Mass determination.

Chapter 3

Results I: Boundary layer meteorology and snow pack conditions.

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter data collected from Glacier de Tsanfleuron between April 2004 and February 2007 upon which the interpretations and discussions made in Chapters 5 and 6 are based are presented. Meteorological variables and components of the glacier surface energy balance are presented in Section 3.2, while snow depth, temperatures and snow pack physical properties are presented in Section 3.3.

3.2 Meteorology and glacier surface energy balance

3.2.1 Basic meteorological time series data

Two year meteorological time series

Meteorological records began in February 2005 and ran for a 702 day period until February 2007. Daily mean, air temperature and relative humidity data recorded at a height of ~ 3 m above the glacier surface at the basic meteorological station (see Figure 2.2 for location) between February 2005 and February 2007 are presented in Figures 3.1(a) and 3.1(b) respectively. Figures 3.1(a) and 3.1(b) show similar data recorded at a lower height of ~ 0.4 m between April and July 2005. Simultaneous two year time series of daily mean wind speed and net radiation are presented in Figures 3.2 (a) and 3.2 (b) respectively; wind speed data was recorded at ~ 3 m and ~ 0.4 m, but net radiation was collected at only one height of ~ 2 m. Wind direction data recorded at a height of ~ 3 m for the same period as Figures 3.1 and 3.2 is displayed in Figures 3.3, while Figure 3.4 depicts the heat flux between the snow pack and the glacier ice at the base of the snow pack. Monthly maximum values, mean and minimum values for the basic meteorological variables are depicted in Figure 3.5 with basic statistics displayed in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. Data were not recovered from all sensors for the period between day 87 (2006) through to day 115 (2006) as a result of certain sensor cables (the RM Young 01503 and the NR-Lite) pulling out of the terminal connections of the data logger under the weight of the compressing snow pack. Shorter periods of inoperability resulted from rime ice formation and freezing of sensors, though these occurrences were at times difficult to identify.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Air temperature

Daily mean air temperature time series (Figure 3.1 a) show a general sinusoidal pattern with an annual period; temperature maxima broadly occur in early summer and minima in early winter. Superimposed upon the general trend are smaller fluctuations of various shorter periodicities. Over the approximate two years of data collection (at 30 minute resolution) the mean air temperature was $-2.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a range from $-25.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (December 2005) to $15.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (August 2006). Daily mean temperatures on the coldest days in summer were comparable to the warmest days in winter. Air temperatures were below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 59 % of the study period and above $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for only 1.4 %. In general there was little difference between 2005 and 2006. 2006 was slightly warmer with a mean annual temperature of $-3.36\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a range of -23.7 to $14.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared with an annual mean of $-3.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a range of -25.8 to $15.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2005. The standard deviation of the 30 minute air temperature data for the two year period is $7.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Table 3.1). The time series for the two sensors match closely during the three month period of temperature measurement at two heights. The lower sensor generally recorded slightly lower temperatures, with a mean temperature over the period of collection of $1.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to $2.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $\sim 3.0\text{ m}$ above the surface (Table 3.2). Monthly maximum, minimum and mean air temperatures depicted in Figure 3.5 (a) show the monthly temperature range to be pretty stable throughout the period of data collection, although larger during the winter months.

Of specific interest in the temperature time series are the rapid temperature decrease of $\sim 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during mid October 2005 marking the beginning of winter and the relatively stable high temperatures in the range $+5$ to $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ occurring following a sharp temperature rise of $\sim 15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of May 2005, which persist without major fluctuation for the following two months during the period of most rapid snow pack ablation (Figure 3.15).

Relative humidity

Daily mean relative humidity time series (Figure 3.1 b) suggest the climate of Tsanfleuron to be wet, with an average relative humidity of 73 % over the two year period of measurement; humidity was above 80 % for 53 % of the study period and below 20 % for only 4.6 % of the time. The general trend is for higher values of $\sim > 60\text{ }%$ during the summer months (between April and August) and lower values, frequently as low as 10 to 20 %, during the winter months. Monthly average humidity values (Figure 3.5 b) show maximum values during August in both years and minima in January and December 2006. Daily maximum values showed only a small seasonal variation, but minima showed visibly more variability, resulting in a smaller range of generally high humidities during the summer months. Shorter period fluctuations generally

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

associated with synoptic weather patterns result in large humidity variations throughout the year, fluctuating within the range 4 to 100 %, evidenced in the standard deviation of 24.7% over the two year period. Basic statistics suggest that 2005 and 2006 were very similar in terms of their relative humidity characteristics (Table 3.1). During the period that data was collected at two elevations, the sensors closely tracked each other, but the lower sensor consistently recorded higher values at times of higher humidity during the 2005 ablation period.

Wind speed

Figure 3.2 (a) depicting daily mean wind speed formulated from the 30 minute average of wind measurements collected every 5 seconds, shows only a limited seasonal cycle. Wind speeds were generally low over the data collection period, with a mean value of 3.6 m s^{-1} , but individual gusts in excess of 25 m s^{-1} were recorded, with a maximum gust of 35.1 m s^{-1} (Table 3.1) recorded on day 296 (2006) (a similar magnitude gust was recorded simultaneously by a second meteorological station operating at the South site, suggesting that this gust was real and not an erroneous result caused by data logger malfunction). Average wind speed at $\sim 3 \text{ m}$ elevation was above 2.5 m s^{-1} for 66 % of the time and above 5 m s^{-1} and 10 m s^{-1} for 20 and 0.2 % of the time respectively, whilst being below 1 m s^{-1} for less than 0.5 % of the data collection period.

Between April and July 2005 the $\sim 3 \text{ m}$ wind was mostly higher than that at $\sim 0.4 \text{ m}$, with an average wind speed over that period of 3.5 m s^{-1} compared to 2.8 m s^{-1} and a maximum gust of 23.1 m s^{-1} compared with 17.8 m s^{-1} at the lower sensor. Similarly, the upper sensor displayed slightly more variability than the lower, with standard deviations of 1.6 m s^{-1} and 1.4 m s^{-1} respectively (Table 3.2). A wind speed minima of $\leq 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is reported in Table 3.1 rather than the recorded raw data values of 0 m s^{-1} to reflect the inertia of the 05103 RM Young wind monitor helicoid propeller and the associated measurement range minimum of 1 m s^{-1} (Campbell Scientific, 2002a).

Figure 3.1: Daily mean (a) air temperature and (b) relative humidity recorded at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007 at heights of ~ 3 m and ~ 0.4 m above the glacier surface.

Net radiation

Daily mean net radiation (Figure 3.2 b) exhibited a strong seasonal cycle with predominantly negative low values during the winter months during which time energy was lost from the glacier surface, for example September 2005 until February 2006, and with high positive values during the late spring and summer months when energy was transferred to the glacier. The mean net radiation for the period of observation (derived from the 30 minute average data) was -2.7 W m^{-2} , while over the whole period of observation net radiation was negative for 72 % of the time, with values fluctuating within the range -171.9 to 897.0 W m^{-2} (Table 3.1). Superimposed upon the annual cycle of radiation variation were a number of smaller fluctuations, the amplitudes of which were much lower in winter: $\sim 50 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ compared to fluctuation of $\sim 200 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ during the summer months. The standard deviation for the whole period of 111.8 W m^{-2} reflects this fluctuation (Table 3.2). 2006 displayed higher radiation than 2005, with an annual average value of 4.3 W m^{-2} and a range of -171.9 to 897.0 W m^{-2} compared to a mean annual value of -9.1 W m^{-2} and a range of -157.5 to 804.0 W m^{-2} for 2005, in part due to higher radiation values near 0 W m^{-2} experienced between October 2006 and January 2007. Diurnal cycles (not depicted in Figure 3.2 b) (see for examples Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8) driven primarily by the $\text{SW}\downarrow$ predominate on clear days. The amplitude of daily cycles was greatest during the summer months with values of up to $\sim 800 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ peaking in the early afternoon, with lower amplitudes in winter.

Maximum net radiation levels were reached during calm clear periods in late spring and early summer in both years, just as the remnants of the winter snow pack were ablating to expose the glacier ice surface. Following this period, a rapid decent to negative winter values occurred in September 2005, but the transition to lower values occurred towards the end of July in 2006. Differences between the autumn radiation values in 2005 and 2006 are clearly visible in Figure 3.2 (b). Between September 2005 and January 2006 radiation levels fluctuated between ~ -25 and -75 W m^{-2} , while during August 2006 to January 2007 levels fluctuated between ~ 50 and -70 W m^{-2} , predominantly centred about 0 W m^{-2} , with the amplitude of fluctuation decreasing as the winter progressed.

Figure 3.2: Daily mean (a) wind speed at a height of ~ 3 m and ~ 0.4 m above the surface and (b) net radiation recorded at a height of ~ 2 m above the glacier surface at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007.

Wind direction

At ~3 m elevation the wind blew from the dominant directions of West, West South West, South West and West North West 17.1 %, 16.0 %, 11.5 % and 9.9 % of the time, respectively, for the two year period (Figure 3.3), while at an elevation of ~ 0.4 m wind direction tracked the upper wind direction sensor for 69 days before jamming on day 181.

Figure 3.3: Wind rose direction plot for data recorded at a height of ~ 3 m above the surface between February 2005 and February 2007 (plot radius scaled to the modal wind direction, to which the other directional segments are represented).

Heat flux between the base of the snow pack and the ice surface

The heat flux plate at the bottom of the snow pack (Figure 3.4) was not installed until January 2006. Small negative heat fluxes in the range - 2 to 0 W m⁻² were recorded until day 137 (2006), when a rapid increase in heat flux occurred with values suddenly becoming positive, peaking the following day (138) at a daily average of ~ 5 W m⁻² and a 30 minute maximum value of 18.6 W m⁻² (Table 3.1). Comparatively high positive values proceeded for a number of days, then a sharp decrease followed by a more gradual decrease toward zero occurred. Data acquisition ceased on day 204 (2006) when the sensor cable snapped.

Figure 3.4: 30 minute mean heat flux from the base of the snow pack into the glacier ice surface (positive values indicate energy flow into the ice) recorded at the North site between January 2006 and July 2006.

<i>Meteorological variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>
Air temperature (°C)	-2.2	15.2	-25.8	7.0
Relative humidity (%)	73	100	4	24
Average 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)	3.6		≤1	1.9
Maximum 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)		35.1		3.0
Wind direction (°)	217			83.6
Net radiation (W m ⁻²)	-2.7	897.0	-171.9	111.8
Snow depth (m)	1.4	4.4	0.0	1.2
Snow pack / ice surface heat flux (W m ⁻²)	-0.3	18.6	-1.8	1.3

Table 3.1: Summary of basic meteorological variables recorded as 30 minute averages by the basic meteorological station at the North site over a two year period between February 2005 and February 2007 (all measurements were at ~ 3 m above the surface with the exception of the net radiation recorded at ~2 m above the surface and the snow pack / ice surface heat flux recorded at the interface with the ice surface at the bottom of the snow pack).

Figure 3.5: Monthly maxima, mean and minima (a) air temperature, (b) relative humidity, (c) wind speed and (d) net radiation, represented in dark grey, black and light grey respectively. (February 2005 and February 2007 not presented as data sets from both months are incomplete and thus monthly statistics are unrepresentative).

<i>Meteorological variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>
Upper air temperature (°C)	2.2	13.0	-10.0	4.5
Upper relative humidity (%)	81	100	8	19
Upper average 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)	3.5		≤1	1.6
Upper maximum 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)		23.1		2.6
Upper wind direction (°)	197.8			68.8
Lower air temperature (°C)	1.4	12.2	-15.3	4.5
Lower relative humidity (%)	85	100	7	16
Lower average 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)	2.8		≤1	1.4
Lower maximum 30 minute wind speed (m s ⁻¹)		17.8		2.3
Lower wind direction (°)	337.4			33.1

Table 3.2: Summary of basic meteorological variables at 30 minute resolution from the basic meteorological station at the North site over a four month period between April 2005 and July 2005, recorded simultaneously at two heights, ~ 3 m and ~ 0.4 m above the glacier surface respectively.

Summary

- Mean daily air temperatures follow a sinusoidal annual cycle overprinted with shorter periodicity fluctuations, the coldest summer temperatures equate to the warmer winter temperatures, while the average air temperature for the two year study period was below freezing.
- Relative humidity is generally high throughout the year, there is little annual variability in the maxima but the minima show more of an annual cycle with the lowest humidities occurring during the winter months.
- Wind direction was dominated at 3 m elevation by down glacier flow of winds from the West, West South West, South West and West North West.
- Wind speed shows only a limited annual cycle, but many of the higher values occur in winter.
- The net radiation is generally positive in summer and negative in winter, with a transition towards the end of April and values are negative for 72 % of the time, indicating that for nearly $\frac{3}{4}$ of the two year period energy in the form of radiation is lost from the glacier surface.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

- In 2006 the glacier received more net radiation than in 2005. The average daily net radiation for 2005 was negative while for 2006 it was positive.
- A sharp rise in the heat flux between the snow pack and ice surface occurred in mid May (day 137) (2006), representing a reversal of the heat flow into the ice after losses from the ice during the early winter.

Seasonal meteorological variations

Four different meteorological scenarios are chosen to outline the interactions between the different individual meteorological parameters experienced throughout the characteristic periods of winter snow accumulation (Figure 3.6), spring snow ablation (Figure 3.7), summer ice ablation (Figure 3.8) and summer snowfall events (Figure 3.9).

Winter snow accumulation period

The winter accumulation period depicted in Figure 3.6 is characterised by two periods of snowfall with rapid surface elevation increase and intervening periods of surface lowering associated with snow pack settling and densification. During the period of snowfall between day 337 and day 343 (2005) (characteristic of many other winter snowfall periods), a surface elevation increase of ~ 1 m occurred at a time of low, non-fluctuating air temperatures (between -6 and -10 °C), high relative humidity (~ 90 %), and no marked diurnal net radiation cycles, following a wind speed peak of ~ 11 m s⁻¹ towards the beginning of the precipitation. Following the snowfall event (day 337 to day 343 (2005)) the snow pack surface elevation gradually decreased ~ 0.3 m from day 343 to day 351 (2005), tracing the form of a commonly observed curve pattern with rapid initial elevation decreases gradually decreasing over time as the compaction processes slow. The period of snow pack settling was characterised by warmer air temperatures fluctuating over a larger range; diurnal cycles were more prominent and positive temperatures were recorded on day 347 (2005), relative humidities dropped considerably to between 20 and 40 % (day 344 to 347 (2005)), diurnal cyclicity in the net radiation increases and wind speeds tended to be lower, peaking at ~ 6 m s⁻¹.

Spring snow ablation period

Similar to the winter accumulation period, spring snow ablation depicted in Figure 3.7 was characterised by two distinct sets of meteorological variable combinations; times of rapid surface elevation lowering (ablation) were interspaced with quiescent periods with occasional snowfall (especially in the early spring). Periods of rapid snow pack ablation, e.g. days 174 to 182 (2005)

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

when ~ 0.6 m of surface lowering occurred, were dominated by high, positive, fluctuating air temperatures displaying clear diurnal cycles in the range 5 to 13 °C, relatively low humidity values fluctuating highly in the range 40 to 90 % and high net radiation values with clearly defined diurnal cycles peaking at $\sim 400 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in the early afternoon. The quiescent periods displaying little or no surface lowering, for example days 186 to 193 (2005), were however associated with lower air temperatures in the range - 3 to 3 °C, maximum relative humidities of 100 % or thereabouts for the duration of the period and low and very stable net radiation, fluctuating little from balance values with no diurnal cyclicity, suggesting cloudy conditions.

Summer ice ablation period

Summer ice ablation (Figure 3.8) follows very similar patterns to that of spring snow ablation with rapid surface lowering during periods of favourable weather, interspaced by periods of poor weather retarding ablation. Warm positive air temperatures (between days 237 and 253 (2005)) in the range ~ 0 to + 10 °C and high net radiation values exhibiting a daily range of $\sim - 100$ to 700 W m^{-2} , both with diurnal cycles peaking during the early afternoon characteristic of high energy input days, drove maximum ice ablation (~ 0.2 m). At the same time, relative humidity values were of moderate magnitude but highly fluctuating in the range 30 to 100 %, whilst in general wind speeds were low. Clear diurnal cyclicity was visible in the distance from the SR50 to the ice surface, with what appeared to be surface elevation increases (negative ablation) of the order of up to 5 cm during each evening (see Section 5.2.2).

Summer snow fall events

As outlined above, summer ice ablation under conditions of high energy receipt was rapid, but weather deterioration and associated summer snowfalls seriously slowed ice surface ablation. A large snowfall on day 223 (2006) (Figure 3.9) of ~ 1 m (followed by gradual surface lowering associated with densification and ablation) occurred at a time when air temperatures decreased rapidly down to as low as -5 °C, remaining negative for a 5 day period, humidity levels were consistently at 100 %, net radiation remained close to zero fluctuation while wind speed increased. The effect of this snow fall event was to eliminate ice surface lowering for approximately 1 month until the freshly deposited snow ablated and the ice surface was again exposed.

Figure 3.6: Two hour average air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period in the winter snow accumulation period between JD 334 (30th November) and JD 359 (25th December) 2005.

Figure 3.7: Two hour average air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period in the spring – early summer snow ablation period between JD 174 (23rd June) and JD199 (18th July) 2005.

Figure 3.8: Two hour average air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and distance from SR50 to glacier surface during a 25 day period in the summer ice ablation period between JD 237 (25th August) and JD 262 (20th September) 2005 (the horizontal dashed line on distance to surface plot, denotes the position of the glacier surface at beginning of illustrated period).

Figure 3.9: Two hour average air temperature, relative humidity, average wind speed, net radiation and snow depth during a 25 day period including a summer snow fall period between JD 209 (28th July) and JD 234 (22nd August) 2006.

Summary

- Snow accumulation during cold, humid, low radiation balance weather conditions in winter was interspaced with quiescent periods of snow pack settling characterised by warmer, less humid periods with greater fluctuation in radiation values.
- The general combinations of recorded variables characterising the periods of spring snow ablation were the mirror image of those driving winter snow accumulation. Surface ablation occurred during warm, lower humidity periods with higher daily fluctuating radiation values, while ablation ceased when conditions worsened.
- Diurnal cyclicality was visible in the position of the ice surface under conditions of summer ice ablation, mirroring the diurnal cycles evident in the positive air temperatures and net radiation data over the same interval.
- Apparent daily negative ablation rates of the order of up to 5 cm per day were observed at night during summer ice ablation.
- Summer snowfall events seriously retard ice surface ablation.

3.2.2 Eddy correlation and four component radiation measurements

The four individual components of the radiation balance (SW_{\downarrow} , SW_{\uparrow} , LW_{\downarrow} and LW_{\uparrow}) and the net radiation were measured over the glacier surface during two field campaigns in August 2006 and January / February 2007 are presented in Figures 3.10 and 3.11 respectively, while sensible and latent heat fluxes recorded simultaneously using eddy correlation instruments are presented in Figures 3.13 and 3.14. Net radiation and sensible and latent heat fluxes are combined over two 24 hour periods on day 230 (2006) and day 35 (2007) in Figure 3.14 (a) and (b) respectively, detailing the variation in surface energy balance through the day in summer and winter. Time series for reconstructed values of the individual four components of radiation and sensible and latent heat flux combined with a time series for the net surface energy balance for the whole two year period of meteorological data collection are presented along with the modelling procedures and equations used in their derivation in Section 7.3 and 7.4.

Radiation

August 2006

SW↓ radiation fluctuated diurnally between maxima of $\sim 1040 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ in the middle of the day when solar energy receipt peaks and a minimum values of 0 Wm^{-2} at night (Figure 3.10). High insolation, sunny weather, under clear sky conditions resulted in symmetrical radiation receipt curves reaching maximum values in excess of 1000 Wm^{-2} at solar noon, for example day 227 and 230 (2006), however, on overcast days e.g. day 223 (2006) radiation values were dramatically reduced to $\sim 250 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$. Days with fluctuating amounts of cloud cover resulted in distorted radiation receipt curves e.g. days 222 and 231 (2006). SW↑ radiation arose due to the reflection of SW↓ radiation at the glacier surface, controlled primarily by the surface albedo, the SW↑ time series thus closely match those for the SW↓ radiation but display lower maximum values of $\sim 700 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ under clear sky conditions such as day 230 (2006), again at night values drop to 0 Wm^{-2} in response to the cessation of SW↓ receipt.

LW↓ radiation for the duration of the August 2006 study period (Figure 3.10) approximates 350 Wm^{-2} . LW↑ similarly traces values of $\sim 350 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ for the duration of the sensor deployment with small minima closely matching the timing of the LW↓ time series with smaller drops. Net radiation fluctuates in the range ~ -100 to 300 Wm^{-2} , in general the diurnal cyclicality observed in SW↓ and SW↑ time series tends to be greatly reduced, leaving a smaller amplitude noisier diurnal cycle (visible on days 221, 222, 227, 229, 230 and 231), maximum values still tend to occur in the early afternoon with nocturnal minima.

January / February 2007

SW↓ radiation patterns in January and February 2007 (Figure 3.11) are identical in form to those occurring in August 2006 (Figure 3.10) though at a smaller amplitude (peaking at a maximum of $\sim 560 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ in the early afternoon on day 34 (2007)) reflecting the reduced intensity of the winter solar radiation receipt. Lower maxima are observed on days 38 to 41 (2007), peaking at $\sim 290 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ in response to snowing, overcast conditions also experiencing blowing snow, in comparison to clear sky conditions on days 33 to 36 (2007) with maxima of $\sim 560 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$. Less discrepancy exists between the magnitude of the SW↓ and the SW↑ fluxes during winter months, with maximum SW↑ values of $\sim 420 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ on days 34 and 35 (2007) under clear sky conditions and values of $\sim 260 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ on days 38 to 41 (2007) under overcast conditions compared with SW↓ maximum values of $\sim 560 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ and $\sim 290 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ respectively. Differences between summer and winter radiation receipt reflect the higher albedo of the fresh winter snow surface and the lower solar angle in winter, favouring greater reflection on contact with the surface.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

LW \downarrow radiation values are $\sim 175 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ under clear sky conditions, rising to $\sim 275 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ under overcast, snowfall conditions (an artefact of LW emission by snow crystals in the atmosphere and from the undersides of clouds). LW \uparrow radiation displays a relatively stable value in the range ~ 240 to 290 Wm^{-2} , small maxima are observed during the daylight hours on certain high SW \downarrow receipt days, as a consequence of warming at the snow surface increasing the LW \uparrow .

Winter net radiation (Figure 3.11) shows considerably more pronounced diurnal cycling than that recorded in August 2006 (Figure 3.10) during both overcast and clear sky conditions. Clear sky conditions display net radiation fluctuations in the range ~ -80 to 40 Wm^{-2} driven directly by the SW radiation balance, with negative nocturnal values of ~ -60 to -70 Wm^{-2} . Overcast and snowing conditions on the other hand show a reduced diurnal cycle, fluctuating about 0 Wm^{-2} with diurnal minimum values occurring during the early hours of day 39 to 41 (2007) as values drop to ~ -60 to -70 Wm^{-2} .

Sensible heat flux

Sensible heat flux time series (Figure 3.12 a and b) recorded over the same time period as the individual four component radiation time series (Figure 3.10 and 3.11) show noisy irregular trends in both August 2006 and January / February 2007 (Figure 3.12 a and b respectively). In August 2006 values fluctuated between -126 and 82 Wm^{-2} (Figure 3.12 a) while in January / February 2007 values of sensible heat flux ranged from -140 to 195 Wm^{-2} (Figure 3.12 b). Both time series show values predominantly clustered around 0 Wm^{-2} , small trends are visible in both records, in August 2006 flux values dropped to consistently less fluctuating, negative values between day 227 and 230, while in February 2007 a more stable, near 0 Wm^{-2} period occurred between day 38 and 41.

Latent heat flux

Latent heat flux time series in August 2006 and January / February 2007 (Figure 3.13 a and b respectively) show similar noisy, highly variable time series when compared with sensible heat fluxes (Figure 3.12 a and b). Fluxes range from -460 to 390 Wm^{-2} in August, dramatically reducing in amplitude to ~ -90 to $\sim 170 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ in January 2007. Turbulent heat flux values fluctuate about unity and contrary to the radiation fluxes show no diurnal cyclicality in either the latent or sensible heat time series.

Figure 3.10: Four components of radiation and net radiation during a 14 day period between day 220 and day 234 (8th to 22nd August 2006) recorded individually using the two CM3 pyranometers and the two CG3 pyrgeometers on the CNR1 Net Radiometer.

Figure 3.11: Four components of radiation and net radiation during a 12 day period between day 30 and day 42 (30th January to 11th February 2007) recorded individually using the two CM3 pyranometers and the two CG3 pyrgeometers on the CNR1 Net Radiometer.

Figure 3.12: Sensible heat flux measured over the glacier surface using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments between (a) day 220 to 234 (8th to 22nd August 2006) and (b) day 30 to 42 (30th January to 11th February 2007).

Figure 3.13: Latent heat flux measured over the glacier surface using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments between (a) day 220 to 234 (8th to 22nd August 2006) and (b) day 30 to 42 (30th January to 11th February 2007).

3.2.3 Surface energy balance

Surface energy balance over two 24 hour periods at two hour resolution have been calculated for day 230 (2006) and day 35 (2007), Figure 3.14 (a) and (b) respectively. During daylight hours SW radiation fluxes dominate the energy balance. LW fluxes tend to be relatively equal by day and by night, however, their relative contribution to the surface energy balance increases dramatically during the hours of darkness. Sensible and latent heat fluxes tend to be minimal compared to SW and LW heat fluxes, their relative contribution tends to be greatest at night and is somewhat higher in August on day 230 than in February on day 35 (with the exception of 0000 on day 35). Both summer and winter 24 hour energy balances show minimum energy receipts during the early hours of the morning, at 0600 on day 230 (2006) and 0200 on day 35 (2007) and maxima during the early afternoon at 1400 on both days. Differences exist in the maximum range of energy balances, in August 2006 the maximum of $\sim 1200 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ and a minimum of $\sim -800 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ at 1400 compare with a maximum of ~ 750 and a minimum of $\sim -750 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ at 1400 in February. Minimum range values of between ~ -300 to 300 Wm^{-2} at 0600 in August compare with minimum range values of ~ -200 to 200 Wm^{-2} in February.

Differences between $\text{SW}\downarrow$ values depicted in August and February reflect the changing number of daylight hours and solar radiation intensity between the two seasons. $\text{SW}\downarrow$ radiation receipt begins earlier in the day and lasts longer and achieves higher maximum values in summer compared to winter. $\text{SW}\downarrow$ was first noted at 0800, peaked at $\sim 900 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ and continued until 2000 on day 230, in comparison to first being noted at 1000, peaking at $\sim 600 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ and continuing to only 1800 on day 35. $\text{SW}\uparrow$ radiation values closely mirror $\text{SW}\downarrow$ values over the same daytime periods. The magnitude of the $\text{LW}\downarrow$ and $\text{LW}\uparrow$ radiation fluxes remain more or less constant over both 24 hour periods, however, values are higher in August than February. Sensible and latent heat appear small in comparison with radiation fluxes, in most cases their contribution to the surface energy balance appears negligible, exceptions to this include at 0000 on day 25 (2007) (Figure 3.14 b) when a positive sensible heat flux of $\sim 180 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ is observed. Latent heat flux values tend to be larger in August than in February and tend to roughly cancel sensible heat fluxes during the August time series (Figure 3.14 a).

Figure 3.14: Energy balance at the glacier surface over a 24 hour period on (a) day 230 (18th August 2006) and (b) day 35 (4th February 2007) derived from the four individual radiation components (recorded by the CNR1 radiometer) and measurements of sensible and latent heat flux (recorded using the CSAT 3 three dimensional sonic anemometer and the KH2O krypton hygrometer eddy correlation instruments).

Summary

- SW↓ radiation displayed distinct diurnal cycles, maxima during the early afternoon and minima during nocturnal conditions.
- Sky conditions, especially cloud cover directly influenced the radiation receipt, decreasing SW↓ and SW↑ and increasing LW↓.
- SW↑ radiation closely mirrored SW↓ radiation and was influenced by solar elevation changes and changes in the glacier surface.
- LW↑ radiation showed little fluctuation as a consequence of the limited range of temperatures experienced at the glacier surface.
- LW↓ radiation was greatest under overcast conditions.
- Net radiation time series were most greatly influenced by the SW radiation balance and to a much lesser extent by the LW balance.
- Sensible and latent heat time series showed no real cyclicality, though some general trends were identifiable, probably associated with synoptic meteorological variation.
- 24 hour surface energy balances in August 2006 and February 2007 were dominated by radiation exchange with turbulent heat fluxes making only minor contributions.

3.3 Snow pack

3.3.1 Snow depth

Snow depth was measured continuously over the glacier surface using an SR50 ultrasonic depth gauge (UDG) for the same 702 day period as the basic meteorological variables (Figure 3.15 a). Gaps in the SR50 time series data were filled using daily snow depth measurements made by the Glacier 3000 ski patrols. While daily mean snow surface elevation change derived from the SR50 time series is depicted in Figure 3.15 (b). Snow pits dug at various times throughout the winters of both 2005 / 06 and 2006 / 07 allowed accurate validation of the SR50 data at the three borehole locations, and snow water equivalent was calculated from snow density measurements (Section 3.3.2) to make comparisons between the sites and between years (Table 3.3). In addition

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

to snow pit derived snow depth, repeat snow depth transects were conducted across the glacier (Figure 3.16) to establish the spatial variability of snow depth in an attempt to determine how representative the point SR50 measurement of snow depth was for the glacier as a whole.

SR50 UDG time series data

The SR50 snow depth time series (Figure 3.15 a) shows a clear annual trend for snow depth maxima in late April, at 3.83 m on day 116 in 2005 and at 4.40 m on day 104 in 2006, rapidly decreasing through the months of May, June and July, and disappearing fully by day 209 in both 2005 and 2006 at the site of the meteorological station. Between days 143 and 209 in 2005, 3.39 m of snow ablated in 66 days at an average rate of $\sim 5 \text{ cm d}^{-1}$, while between days 165 and 209 in 2006, 3.45 m of snow ablated in 44 days at an average rate of $\sim 8 \text{ cm d}^{-1}$ (visible as a prolonged period of negative snow surface elevation change in Figure 3.15 b). The months of August and September were generally snow free with the ice surface exposed and ablating, but summer snowfalls can give ephemeral snow cover e.g. snowfall on day 224 in August 2006 deposited 1.11 m of fresh snow that remained on the surface until day 254 (Figure 3.15 a and b). At the meteorological station site, there were 42 snow free days in 2005 and 29 in 2006 between the first emergence of the glacier ice surface from under the previous winter's snow pack and the beginning of the following winter's snow pack. The first autumn snow falls that failed to fully ablate, marking the beginning of the winter snow pack, occurred on day 273 in 2005 and on day 279 in 2006 at the North site. Summer snow fall occurred in both the summers of 2005 and 2006 with 22 days snow cover out of 64 days between the elimination of one year's winter snow pack and the beginning of the subsequent year's winter snow pack in 2005 and 41 days cover out of 70 in 2006. As the autumn progresses the winter snow pack begins to develop. The autumn / early winter period in 2005 saw earlier, smaller snowfalls leading to a gradual winter snow pack accumulation, compared to the establishment of the winter pack in autumn / early winter 2006 by fewer but larger snowfall events (Figure 3.15 b).

The gap in the SR50 record (Figure 3.15 a) between day 91 and day 112 (2006), occurred when the distance to the surface dropped below the 0.5 m minimum range of the sensor and the sensor was buried by heavy snowfalls, data was reconstructed using snow depths recorded by Glacier 3000 ski patrols. Confidence in the quality of the secondary data used to infill the gap is gained from the manual snow depth measurement made on day 114 (2005), which corresponds well with the Glacier 3000 snow depth measurements made at an unknown location on the glacier (Figure 3.15 a). Over the 702 days of data collection the glacier surface was snow covered for 631 days and the ice surface was exposed for only 71 whole days (snow cover for 90.0 % of the

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

study time). The average snow depth for the period February 2005 to February 2006 was 1.47 m, while for the same period between 2006 and 2007 the average depth was 1.37 m. Snow depth was > 0.1 m, > 1.0 m and > 2.0 m for 74.1 %, 50.9 % and 31.3 % of the 702 day period of measurement, respectively.

<i>Site</i>	<i>Total snow depth (m)</i>	<i>Average density (kg m⁻³)</i>	<i>Snow Water Equivalent (mm WE)</i>	<i>Average temperature (°C)</i>
North (Apr 2005)	3.35	390.6	1308.5	Not measured
North (Jan 2006)	1.73	303.0	524.1	-8.56
South (Jan 2006)	1.69	304.0	513.7	-8.94
Central (Jan 2006)	1.74	327.1	569.1	-8.68
North (Apr 2006)	3.94	389.8	1535.8	-3.45
South (Apr 2006)	3.86	383.6	1480.7	-3.98
Central (Apr 2006)	4.12	394.4	1624.9	-3.02
North (Jan 2007)	2.18	367.6	801.3	-6.00
South (Jan 2007)	2.03	379.6	770.6	-6.90
Central (Feb 2007)	2.07	378.8	784.0	-5.82

Table 3.3: Summary of snow pit data collected at the North, South and Central sites in April 2005, January and April 2006 and January / February 2007.

Figure 3.15: (a) Snow depth recorded automatically by the SR50 (with periodic manually measured snow depths in red) and (b) daily mean snow surface elevation change at the basic meteorological station between February 2005 and February 2007.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Snow pits

Snow pits to the ice surface were dug at all three borehole locations in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007, and a pit was dug at the North site alone during April 2005. Depths of pits at the North site were used to validate and correct for drift in the SR50 automated snow depth record, as depicted together in Figure 3.15 (a). Of the three pits dug in January 2006, the Central site was the deepest at a depth of 1.74 m, but, the North and South sites were of very similar depths at 1.73 and 1.69 m respectively. In April 2006, the Central site was again the deepest pit at a depth of 4.12 m with 3.94 m at the North and 3.86 m at the South. The North site was the deepest pit in January 2007 at a depth of 2.18 m; the South and Central sites were slightly less deep at depths of 2.03 and 2.07 m respectively. The snow pit depths in January 2007 were deeper at the same locations than the pits dug in January 2006, while the pit dug in April 2006 at the North site was deeper than the pit dug at the same location in April 2005: 3.94 m compared to 3.35 m accordingly.

Snow water equivalent (SWE) was calculated for each snow pit (Table 3.3) using snow density data (see Section 3.3.2). In January 2006, the Central site had the greatest SWE at 569.1 mm, notably larger than those of 524.1 and 513.7 mm for the North and South sites respectively, despite similar snow depths, as a consequence of a markedly higher average snow density (Table 3.3). April 2006 saw the Central site again topping the three pits in terms of SWE with a value of 1624.9 mm. As discussed above, the January snow depth measurements in 2007 were distinctly higher than at the same time in the previous year. The same can be said for the SWE: values of 801.3, 770.6 and 784.0 mm for the North, South and Central sites are 153, 150 and 138 % of the 2006 values respectively. Thus, despite there being fewer snowfall events during the early 2006 / 07 winter than in the previous year (and the glacier pistes being opened to skiers as much as a month later than in 2005) the mass of snow deposited in the snow pack in the period up to day 32 (2007) in February was ~ 50 % greater than the previous year at the same time. These depth and SWE observations are in stark contrast with media reports suggesting that the start of the 2006 / 07 winter in the Alps would be remembered as “one of the worst on record” (Cove, 2006) in terms of poor snowfall leading to delays in the beginning of the ski season. By late December, following “the mildest autumn on record” (Swissinfo, 2006a) three World Cup ski events had been cancelled due to warm weather, many resorts had less than the 30 cm minimum snow depth judged necessary for skiing and those which were open relied heavily on artificial snow (Swissinfo, 2006a). Mild mountain temperatures and low snowfalls even at higher resorts above 1,800 m were attributed to a “constant influx of high pressure linked to subtropical conditions... not an extraordinary event in itself...its particularity comes from the frequency and the duration

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

of the event, which is not just exceptional for the South but also for the North of the Alps” (MeteoSwiss (in Swissinfo, 2006b)).

Depth transects

Extensive snow depth transects were conducted to assess the spatial variability of the snow depth over the glacier surface, the results of which are displayed in Table 3.4. A 10 m spaced cross glacier transect passed through the three borehole locations while a large cross shape transect extended over the top 2/3 of the glacier with data collection points at ~ 30 m spacing. Repeat depth transects following the same paths (Figure 3.16) (small variations between transects are due to slightly different locations of piste marker poles in consecutive years) were conducted in January 2006 and January / February 2007 to allow comparison between years, and an additional across glacier line was also surveyed in 2007.

The 10 m across glacier transect in January 2006 exhibited variation in range 146 to 270 cm with an average of 176 cm. The same transect repeated in January / February 2007 had a range of 159 to 254 cm and an average depth of 194 cm, suggesting that in keeping with the snow pit data greater snow had fallen in the second year. The same pattern was true for the 30 m transects with a range of 82 to 240 cm and an average of 156 cm in 2006 compared with a range of 111 to 235 cm and an average of 189 cm in 2007.

The standard deviations of the depth records (Table 3.4) suggests that the 10 m across glacier transect showed less variability than the ~ 30 m down glacier transects in both winters, 21.0 cm compared to 30.8 cm in 2006 and 17.2 cm compared to 21.9 cm in 2007 respectively, presumably reflecting some component of altitudinal variation in the snow depth. Both the 2007 transects displayed less variability than the 2006 transects indicating a more uniform snow cover at the time of sampling in the second winter. The histograms in Figure 3.17 (a) and (b) for the 2006 and 2007 transects respectively suggest that both data sets exhibit a symmetrical distribution, with deeper snow over a smaller range of values in 2007 than observed in 2006. The combined data set of 479 data collection points from all five transects has an average depth of 183 cm and a small standard deviation of 26.2 cm, suggesting that the SR50 data collected at the North site was representative of the snow depth over the glacier surface.

Figure 3.16: Route of the January 2005 and January 2006 snow depth transects, at ~ 30 m separation in undisturbed snow to the side of glacier pistes and passing through BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 at 10 m separation.

<i>Transect</i>	<i>Number of observations</i>	<i>Maximum depth (cm)</i>	<i>Minimum depth (cm)</i>	<i>Average depth (cm)</i>	<i>Standard deviation (cm)</i>
10 m across glacier Jan 2006	113	270	146	176	21.0
10 m across glacier Jan 2007	100	254	159	194	17.2
~10 m upper across glacier Jan 2007	84	233	172	200	14.3
~30 m piste following Jan 2006	86	240	82	156	30.8
~30 m piste following Jan 2007	96	235	111	189	21.9
Full data set	479	270	82	183	26.2

Table 3.4: Summary of the January 2006 and January 2007 snow depth transect data.

Figure 3.17: Histograms of (a) January 2006 and (b) January 2007 snow depths recorded on the ~ 30 and 10 m transects.

Summary

- The glacier surface was snow covered for 90.0 % of the data collection period.
- The maximum snow depth observed in the 2004 / 05 winter was 3.83 m, while the maxima in the 2005 / 06 winter was 4.40 m, occurring in late April in both years.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

- The winter snow pack had ablated by day 209 in both 2005 and 2006.
- Winter snow pack accumulation began on day 273 in 2005 and on day 279 in 2006.
- The ablation of the 2004 / 05 snow pack occurred at a rate of $\sim 5 \text{ cm d}^{-1}$, while the 2005 / 06 pack ablated at $\sim 8 \text{ cm d}^{-1}$.
- SWE values calculated in January 2007 indicate $\sim 50 \%$ more snow mass was present on the glacier than at the same time in the previous winter.
- Snow depth variability was greater down-glacier than across-glacier and more pronounced in January 2006 than in January 2007.
- Snow depth transects displayed very little variability across the glacier, suggesting that the SR50 point snow depth measurements were representative of the snow depth across the glacier as a whole for the purposes of modelling energy balance at the three sites.

3.3.2 Snow density and stratigraphy

Snow density measurements at 10 cm vertical resolution were sampled in snow pits dug at all three sites in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007; profiles of which are presented in Figure 3.18 (a), (b) and (c) respectively. In addition, measurements were made with a somewhat cruder technique in April 2005 (Figure 3.18 a).

Density profiles

Snow pit density profiles for all three sites (Figure 3.18) show a general trend of increasing snow density with depth in response to compaction and densification occurring within the snow pack under the weight of overlying snow. Contrary to this trend of increasing density with depth was a small density decrease of ~ 50 to 100 kg m^{-3} in a thin 0.1 to 0.4 m thick layer directly above the ice surface (visible in all profiles except those recorded in January 2007) caused by depth hoar formation at the base of the snow pack. Fresh powder snow at the top of the snow pack had a density of ~ 100 to 150 kg m^{-3} when it first settled on the glacier, quickly increasing to a density of $\sim 200 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ after a short period of settling (as depicted in the characteristic snow surface elevation decrease curves following snowfall (Figures 3.9 and 3.15 a)). At depth in the snow pack (under ~ 1 m or greater depth of overlying snow), densities increased to those of compact, old snow at $\sim 400 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. Densities in excess of 450 kg m^{-3} were rare but were observed to be as

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

high as 500 kg m^{-3} toward the base of the April profiles at the North site in 2005 and 2006 and at the Central site in 2006 (a phenomena noted in the field as requiring the use of a large rubber mallet to drive the density cutter into the snow pit wall).

January snow density profiles in all three pits in both 2006 and 2007 feature similar surface densities of $\sim 200 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. January 2006 profiles in all pits display a gradual, almost linear density increase to $\sim 400 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ at a depth of $\sim 1.5 \text{ m}$ below the surface where densities decrease by $\sim 100 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ in a layer $\sim 0.4 \text{ m}$ thick above the ice surface. The density profile directly below the surface layer was very different in January 2007 where densities rapidly increased to $\sim 400 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ within 0.4 to 0.6 m below the surface then remained in the range ~ 300 to 400 kg m^{-3} for the remainder of the profile to the ice surface. No density decrease near the base of the snow pack was observed in January 2007.

The April 2006 density profiles reveal similar quasi linear density increases from $\sim 300 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ near the snow surface to $\sim 450 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ at $\sim 0.3 \text{ m}$ above the ice surface, followed by density decreases of $\sim 100 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ toward the ice surface. Differences in the surface snow density reflect the meteorological conditions at the times of sample collection. The North pit was dug and sampled on day 115 (2006) and displayed a surface density of 365 kg m^{-3} . A fresh snow fall of $\sim 30 \text{ cm}$ was recorded over night between day 115 and 116 (2006), and consequently when the Central site was sampled on day 116 a surface density of 272 kg m^{-3} reflecting the fresh snow fall was noted, while in the South pit on day 118 a surface density of 316 kg m^{-3} was recorded following the initial stages of post-deposition densification. The crude density profile obtained in April 2005 was in keeping with the profile obtained in April 2006; density peaks approaching 500 kg m^{-3} during April 2005 at a depth of $\sim 0.3 \text{ m}$ above the surface are comparable with peaks of $\sim 470 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ at approximately the same depth the following year and a density of $\sim 500 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ at a depth of $\sim 0.4 \text{ m}$ above the ice surface at the Central site in April 2006. The higher peak of $\sim 500 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ at $\sim 1.1 \text{ m}$ above the ice surface may be an artefact of a less accurate density determination method or the existence of higher density ice layers.

The average snow pack density (Table 3.3) in January 2006 was greatest at the Central site at 327.1 kg m^{-3} , while the North and South sites return values of 303.0 and 304.0 kg m^{-3} respectively. The Central site was again the densest snow pack in April 2006 with an average of 394.4 kg m^{-3} , the North had a density of 389.8 kg m^{-3} and the South a density of 383.6 kg m^{-3} . The ~ 60 to 80 kg m^{-3} higher average density values in April compared to those in January reflected increased mass addition to the snow pack and longer metamorphism of the lower snow

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

layers occurring between the sample times. The average density values in January 2007 for the North, South and Central sites were 367.6, 379.6 and 378.8 kg m⁻³, 121, 125 and 116 % of the January 2006 values respectively.

Snow pack stratigraphy

Density data used in conjunction with stratigraphic logs of the snow pack layering (Table 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7) and crystallography aid interpretation of anomalous thermal features in snow pack temperature profiles. For example heat generation via refreezing of percolating melt water on contact with impermeable ice lenses and also reconstruction of the history of snowfall events and the position of previous snow pack surface layers. Previous snow surfaces were often visible in the form of ice lenses or dirty snow layers e.g. the bands of discoloured snow visible between 309 and 314 cm above the ice surface at the North site, at 320 to 325 cm at the South and between 349 to 353 cm at the Central site in April 2006 (Tables 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7 respectively). Contrasting the April 2006 stratigraphy with that of the January 2006 for each site, it was clear that as the winter progressed the number of ice lenses in the snow pack increased, presumably due to melt water generated within the near-surface snow, percolation and re-freezing on contact with cold snow layers at depth as the snow pack ripened and became isothermal.

Figure 3.18: Snow density profiles measured using samples extracted from the North facing wall of snow pits dug at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007 (and April 2005 at BH04-01).

<i>Snow pit stratigraphy at the North site (BH04-01)</i>					
January 2006 (day 20)		April 2006 (day 115)		January 2007 (day 30)	
Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy
173	Surface crust – no new powder	394	Surface crust	218 - 193	Soft snow
173 – 155	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	355 – 362	Large crystals - melting	193 - 183	Harder snow
155 – 95	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	355	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	183 – 160	Less dense snow
95	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	351	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	160 – 158	Ice layer ~ 2 cm
94 – 17	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	345	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	158 - 144	Hard snow
17 – ice surface	Depth hoar (faceted, granular unconsolidated crystals)	339	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm	144 – 143	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		324	Ice layer ~ 1.5 cm, crystals above the lens with crust at top of layer	143 - 131	Hard snow
		309 - 314	Band of discoloured snow – possibly from wind blown dust, larger grain size, below which, mix of faceted and rounded crystals	131 - 83	Very dense snow
		272	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	83 - 62	Hard snow
		245	Ice layer ~ 1.5 cm	62 - 61	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		243	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	60 – ice surface	Hard snow
		232	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm		
		221	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		217	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		211	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		204	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm		
		202	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		198	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		Possible vertical ice features at various depths in this vicinity			
		180	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		177	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		169	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		164	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		120	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		114	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		85	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm		
		85 - 14	Very hard dense homogeneous snow layer		
		14 – ice surface	Depth hoar – large crystals		

Table 3.5: The North site (BH04-01) snow pack stratigraphy, determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007.

<i>Snow pit stratigraphy at the South site (BH04-06)</i>					
January 2006 (day 23)		April 2006 (day 118)		January 2007 (day 31)	
Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy
169	Surface crust – no new powder	386 – 370	Fresh snow	200 - 193	Soft snow
169 – 134	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	370 – 368	Coarse crystals – old surface	193 - 151	Hard snow
134	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	368 – 367	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	151 – 150.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm
134 – 92	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	367 – 361	Coarse crystals	150.5 - 144	Hard snow
92	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	361 – 359.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm	144 – 143	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
92 – 26	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	359.5 – 353	Homogeneous snow	143 - 141	Hard snow
26 – ice surface	Depth hoar (faceted, granular unconsolidated crystals)	353 – 352.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm	141 - 140	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		352.5 – 342	Snow layer	140 – 139	Hard snow
		342 – 341	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	139 – 138	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		341 – 339	Snow layer	138 - 133	Hard snow
		339 – 338	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	133 – 132	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		338 – 320	Snow layer	132 - 115	Hard snow
		325 – 320	Dirty snow layer not as pronounced as in other pits	115 - 80	Very hard snow
		320 – 308	Homogeneous snow layer	80 – 63	Hard snow
		308 – 307	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	63 - 62	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		307 – 277	Snow layer	62 - 23	Hard snow
		277 – 276.5	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	23 - 18	Hard snow – faceted crystals
		276.5 – 274.5	Ice crystals	18 - 9	Hard snow
		274.75 – 271	Densely packed crystals	9 – 8.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm
		271 – 270	Packed crystals	8.5 – ice surface	Hard snow – larger faceted crystals
		270 – 267	Dense snow – small crystals		
		267 – 265.75	Denser snow crystals		
		265.75 – 265	Ice layer ~ 0.75 cm		
		265 – 263	Snow		
		263 – 260.5	Thick layer of rounded crystals, hard and dense		
		260.5 – 180	Densely packed snow		
		180 – 178	Ice layer ~ 2 cm		
		178 – 172	Densely packed snow		
		172 – 171.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm		
		171.5 – 150	Homogeneous snow		
		150 – 70	Homogeneous snow		
		70 – 16	Crystalline snow – not depth hoar		
		16 – ice surface	Depth hoar (faceted, granular unconsolidated crystals)		

Table 3.6: The South site (BH04-06) snow pack stratigraphy, determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007.

<i>Snow pit stratigraphy at the Central site (BH05-07)</i>					
January 2006 (day 24)		April 2006 (day 116)		February 2007 (day 32)	
Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy	Height (cm)	Stratigraphy
174	Surface crust ~ 3 mm – no new powder	412 – 397	Fresh snow	203 - 184	Soft snow
174 – 91	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	397 – 393	Poorly consolidated large crystals	184 - 157	Hard snow
91	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	393	Ice layer ~ 0.75 cm	157 - 152	Ice layer ~ 5 cm
91 – 60	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	393 – 382.5	Poorly consolidated larger crystals	152 – 135	Hard snow
60	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	382.5 – 381	Ice layer ~ 1.5 cm	135 – 134.5	Ice layer ~ 0.5 cm
60 – 14	Homogeneous layer – mixed rounded and faceted crystals	371	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	134.5 - 89	Hard snow
14 – ice surface	Depth hoar (faceted, granular unconsolidated crystals)	354	Ice layer ~ 1 cm	89 - 88	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		353 – 349	Band of discoloured snow – possibly from wind blown dust, larger grain size, below which, mix of faceted and rounded crystals	88 – 73	Hard snow
		328	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm	73 - 52	Hard snow – softer crystals becoming faceted
		297 – 291	Large crystals – not icy - hoar	52 - 51	Ice layer ~ 1 cm
		287 – 281	Large icy unconsolidated crystals deforming into ice - possibly a surface crust that didn't fully melt	51 - 17	Hard snow – crystals becoming faceted
		281 - 280	Snow layer	17 - 6	Mix of ice layers and conglomerates
		280 – 279	Large icy unconsolidated crystals deforming into ice - possibly a surface crust that didn't fully melt	6 – ice surface	Soft snow – large faceted crystals
		279 – 245	Less dense than layer below		
		245 – 201	No ice layers but increasing density as move up layer – less dense toward bottom of layer		
		152	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		125	Ice layer ~ 0.25 cm		
		111	Ice layer ~ 1.5 cm		
		97	Ice layer ~ 1 cm		
		97 – 10	Homogeneous dense snow layer		
		10 – ice surface	Depth hoar (faceted, granular unconsolidated crystals)		

Table 3.7: The Central site (BH05-07) snow pack stratigraphy, determined from snow pits in January 2006, April 2006 and February 2007.

Summary

- The snow pack was denser in the 2006 / 07 winter than in the 2005 / 06 winter, with average densities in January 2007 being, 121, 125 and 116 % of the average densities correspondingly for the North, South and Central sites in January 2006.
- Snow pack density increased with both depth below the snow surface and with age of the snow pack, reflected in the higher average density values of April 2006 compared to those determined in January 2006.
- Almost linear trends of density increase with depth were exhibited in the snow pack, peaking at densities of ~ 400 to 450 kg m^{-3} at a height of ~ 0.2 to 0.4 m above the ice surface in both January and April 2006.
- Density decreases of $\sim 100 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ in a thin layer up to $\sim 0.4 \text{ m}$ above the ice surface occurred due to depth hoar formation in January and April 2006.
- The number of ice lenses noted in the stratigraphy increased as the winter progressed.

3.3.3 Snow pack temperatures

Snow pack temperatures were recorded at 20 cm vertical separation throughout the snow pack above the glacier ice surface. Thermistors were installed prior to the winter snowfall, but results are only presented for the period when the thermistors were buried and recording snow temperature rather than air temperatures. The times of burial and melt-out are calculated from the SR50 snow depth data and compared against the thermistor time series. Details of thermistor locations relative to the ice surface, burial dates and melt out dates are presented in Table 3.8 (a), (b) and (c), referring to thermistor stations BH04-01 (the North site), BH04-06 (the South site) and BH05-07 (the Central site) accordingly. The full recorded temperature time series for BH04-01 in the 2004 / 05 winter and the 2005 / 06 winter are displayed in Figure 3.19 (a) and (b) respectively, Figure 3.20 (a) and (b) present the same time periods for BH04-06, while Figure 3.21 represents the 2005 / 06 winter at BH05-07. Figure 3.22 depicts in detail the temperature variation within the snow pack at BH04-01 at the beginning of the 2004 / 05 winter. Detailed plots have been produced for the period of spring warming, as the snow pack becomes isothermal and ablation begins; Figure 3.23 (a) and (b) display the temperature changes in the BH04-01 snow pack in spring 2005 and 2006, while Figure 3.24 exhibits the changes occurring in the

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

BH04-06 spring 2006 snow pack. In addition to time series, snow pack temperature profile plots are presented to show temperature variation with depth throughout the snow depth and as a comparison of snow temperatures between the different sites. Figures 3.25 and 3.26 demonstrate the bi-monthly (~ 2 weekly) average snow pack temperature profiles for the duration of the data collection periods for each borehole location in the 2004 / 05 and the 2005 / 06 winters respectively. Five-day average temperature profiles at the end of the winter (beginning from April 1st) for BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 are presented in Figure 3.27 (a), (b) and (c) depicting the ripening of the snow pack as isothermal conditions develop throughout the pack. Figure 3.28 displaying manually measured snow pack temperatures collected using stem thermometers in the wall of the snow pits, allows validation of the automated thermistor temperature records.

Temperature time series

No complete snow pack thermistor time series for an entire winter was recovered from the data loggers at Tsanfleuron owing mainly to data logger and multiplexer malfunction as a consequence of static charge build up and the inability to locate a buried logger under conditions of unexpectedly high snowfall. For the purposes of plotting snow pack temperature time series in the absence of complete time series to allow visual identification of burial and melt out rates, the burial dates for each thermistor were calculated by comparing the thermistor height above the ice surface with the SR50 snow depth record; inferred burial dates were evaluated where possible against the thermistor time series to visually check that the changes in the character of the temperature time series matched the calculated times. Temperature time series initially depicted highly fluctuating positive and negative temperatures, archetypal of autumn and winter air temperatures prior to burial, but damped, much lower amplitude negative temperatures (warmer than the temperature lows prior to burial) were recorded after burial. Full details of the thermistor locations above the ice surface, burial dates, and melt out dates are given in Table 3.8.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

(a)

<i>BH04-01</i>	<i>Winter 2004 / 05</i>			<i>Winter 2005 / 06</i>		
	Thermistor	Day of burial	Day of melt-out (calculated)	Thermistor	Day of burial	Day of melt-out (calculated)
Height above ice surface (m)						
0.0	10.4C	337 (2004)	208 (2005)	11.8C	332 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.2	10.2C	337 (2004)	207 (2005)	11.2A	339 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.4	11.2A	354 (2004)	205 (2005)	11.0A	339 (2005)	207 (2006)
0.6	11.0A	355 (2004)	201 (2005)	11.0C	340 (2005)	206 (2006)
0.8	Broken	N/A	N/A	10.8A	365 (2005)	204 (2006)
1.0	10.6A	361 (2004)	195 (2005)	10.8C	001 (2006)	197 (2006)
1.2	10.4A	001 (2005)	184 (2005)	10.6C	016 (2006)	194 (2006)
1.4	10.2A	019 (2005)	179 (2005)	10.4A	021 (2006)	191 (2006)
1.6	10.0A	020 (2005)	177 (2005)	10.6A	023 (2005)	187 (2006)
1.8	10.6C	021 (2005)	174 (2005)	10.4C	046 (2005)	185 (2006)
2.0	11.0C	021 (2005)	171 (2005)	10.2A	048 (2005)	182 (2006)
2.2	11.8C	042 (2005)	169 (2005)	10.2C	048 (2005)	179 (2006)
2.4	13.0C	043 (2005)	166 (2005)	10.0C	048 (2005)	177 (2006)
2.6	12.0C	044 (2005)	154 (2005)			
2.8	10.8C	097 (2005)	151 (2005)			
3.0	10.0C	098 (2005)	149 (2005)			

(b)

<i>BH04-06</i>	<i>Winter 2004 / 05</i>			<i>Winter 2005 / 06</i>		
	Thermistor	Day of burial	Day of melt-out (calculated)	Thermistor	Day of burial	Day of melt-out (calculated)
Height above ice surface (m)						
0.0	10.0B	318 (2004)	208 (2005)	14.0B	329 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.2	10.2B	323 (2004)	207 (2005)	10.0B	330 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.4	10.4B	324 (2004)	202 (2005)	10.2B	332 (2005)	207 (2006)
0.6	10.6B	337 (2004)	201 (2005)	10.4B	337 (2005)	205 (2006)
0.8	10.8B	354 (2004)	197 (2005)	10.6B	339 (2005)	204 (2006)
1.0	11.0B	354 (2004)	195 (2005)	10.8B	365 (2005)	196 (2006)
1.2	11.2B	003 (2005)	184 (2005)	11.0B	365 (2005)	194 (2006)
1.4	11.4B	018 (2005)	179 (2005)	11.2B	016 (2005)	191 (2006)
1.6	11.6B	019 (2005)	177 (2005)	11.4B	049 (2005)	187 (2006)
1.8				11.6B	049 (2005)	185 (2006)

(c)

<i>BH05-06</i>	<i>Winter 2005 / 06</i>		
	Thermistor	Day of Burial	Day of melt-out (calculated)
Height above ice surface (m)			
0.0	A	332 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.2	B	336 (2005)	208 (2006)
0.4	C	337 (2005)	207 (2006)
0.6	D	340 (2005)	205 (2005)
0.8	E	341 (2005)	204 (2005)
1.0	F	365 (2005)	196 (2005)
1.2	G	016 (2005)	194 (2005)
1.4	H	017 (2005)	191 (2005)
1.6	I	017 (2005)	187 (2005)
1.8	J	047 (2005)	185 (2005)
2.0	K	047 (2005)	181 (2005)
2.2	L	048 (2005)	179 (2005)
2.4	M	049 (2005)	176 (2005)

Table 3.8: Burial and melt-out dates for snow pack thermistors located at (a) BH04-01 (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 during the 2004 / 05 and 2005 / 06 winters (melt-out dates were calculated from snow depth time series (see Figure 3.15 a) as missing data often prevented determination from the thermistor temperature time series).

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Full three year time series

Air temperature was found to be the key variable controlling snow pack temperatures. The warmest, least fluctuating temperatures occurred at the ice surface, becoming colder and increasingly noisy towards the snow surface, where near surface snow pack temperatures closely followed air temperature trends. Thermistor time series depicted in Figures 3.19, 3.20, and 3.21 tend to follow a general pattern, displaying high amplitude fluctuations soon after burial (while still strongly influenced by air temperature changes). Gradually over a period of time (the duration of which was controlled by the rates of snow fall and rates of densification of fresh snow) the amplitude of these disturbances decreased as the thermistors became increasingly buried under greater depths of snow. Following burial, the insulating effect of the overlying snow limited the influence of the highly fluctuating cold winter air temperature; thermistor time series were seen to stabilize and follow a gradual upward trend throughout the winter until the snow pack began to become isothermal from the surface downwards and melting occurred generating liquid water which percolated down through the snow pack transferring heat to sequentially lower layers and eventually to the ice surface.

The North site (BH04-01)

During the 2004 / 05 winter (Figure 3.19 a) initial cooling of the temperatures of the ice surface and at 0.2 m occurred, temperature decreased rapidly over the first ~ 15 days following day 337 (2004) until sufficient snow accumulation insulated the thermistors and stabilisation began to occur (at the time of burial of thermistors at 0.4 and 0.6 m above the surface) at temperatures of ~ -4.1 and ~ -4.7 °C respectively which then gradually experienced slow warming until day 112 (2005) when the thermal regime of the whole snow depth was disrupted. In addition to the general trends experienced by most thermistors within the snow pack as outlined above, of specific interest are the low temperature spikes in the time series occurring on day 37 (2005) and day 57 (2005). Low temperature perturbations were greatest at the snow surface with the amplitude of disturbance decreasing with depth into the pack, for example on day 37 (2005) (see also Figure 3.22) temperatures of the near surface thermistor dropped to -15.65 °C while those at sequentially 0.2 m lower spacings within the pack displayed minimum temperature values of -13.26, -10.69, -9.52, -8.43 and -7.57 °C respectively. On day 57 (2005) a snow pit was dug to access the buried logger enclosure and to conduct snow pack studies; as a consequence of this disturbance temperatures at all depths within the pack decreased following exposure for approximately a day to cold mid winter air temperatures (subsequently taking 3 or so weeks to return to their undisturbed values). A minimum temperature of ~ - 22 °C was experienced at the snow surface, the amplitude of the disturbance decreased with depth below the snow surface.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Following the anthropogenic temperature disturbance on day 57 (2005) all thermistors displayed a warming trend. Between day 75 and 110 (2005) thermistors near the snow surface, initially at 2.4, 2.6 m and subsequently following snow fall and burial of additional thermistors at 2.8 and 3.0 m above the ice surface displayed large amplitude temperature variations of up to ~ 5 °C with periods of 5 to 10 days associated with corresponding fluctuations in the air temperature. A second smaller anthropogenically derived temperature decrease experienced again by all thermistors occurred on day 112 (2005) corresponding to the digging of the April 2005 snow pit to gain access the buried data logger enclosure. Following the disturbance on day 112 (2005) the snow pack thermistors rapidly displayed a temperature increase to near isothermal conditions propagating downwards from the snow surface, (Figure 3.23 a, and the associated discussion of the end of winter snow pack warming below).

During the 2005 / 06 winter (Figure 3.19 b) in general the snow thermistors exhibited similar characteristics and trends to those occurring in 2004 / 05. Near-surface thermistors again experienced the greatest temperature perturbations caused by air temperature fluctuations, with amplitude decreasing with distance below the snow surface e.g. the decrease on day 364 (2005) when the upper most recorded snow pack temperature was -14.36 °C with lower thermistors recording temperatures of -10.73 , -7.43 and -5.43 °C respectively. In contrast to early winter 2005 when ice temperatures cooled following burial, in 2006 the ice surface temperature rose rapidly from -9.01 °C on day 332 (2006) to its over-winter range of -4.95 to -3.88 °C. Disturbances were once again caused by the excavation of snow pits; the warm peak which occurred on day 21 (2006) was an artefact of the January snow pit dug on day 20 (2006) during conditions of warm near 0 °C air temperatures causing warming of the snow pack, a disturbance which was rapidly eliminated within a week. Day 115 (2006) saw the opening of a pit to the ice surface, followed on day 116 (2006) by a temperature increase at a height of 1.4 m above the ice surface from -5.04 to -1.17 °C, an increase matched by the other thermistors and replicating the changes experienced the year before. Day 61 (2006) features a temperature decrease experienced by the uppermost 5 thermistors; the thermistor nearest the surface (buried under a depth of 2 cm) displayed a temperature minima of -14.09 °C, with temperatures of other thermistors decreasing to -12.23 , -10.93 , -9.52 and -8.53 °C respectively at 0.2 m intervals below the surface in response to an air temperature fall on day 61 (2006) to -21.2 °C.

The range of snow temperatures experienced was smaller in the 2005 / 06 winter than in 2004 / 05, 0 to -16 °C compared to 0 to -22 °C in 2004 / 05. It appears that the 2004 / 05 range was enhanced as a consequence of the February snow pit perturbation dramatically lowering the

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

temperature minimum; no such pit was dug (exposing the entire snow depth to cooling during the period of the coldest winter air temperatures) in 2006.

The South site (BH04-06)

Figure 3.20 (a) depicting the full 2004 /05 snow thermistor time series terminates in early February as a consequence of power loss to the logger due to burial of the solar panel; the burial posed the additional problem that the instrumentation could not be located during winter field visits, preventing maintenance and downloading until July 2005. BH04-06 thermistors exhibit similar sequential burial of sensors above the ice surface, accompanied by gradual amplitude decrease of temperature fluctuation and stabilisation into a slow over-winter warming trend associated with increased gradual severance from the driving air temperatures as the snow pack developed, increasing insulation of deeper thermistors as the winter progresses, as displayed by BH04-01 (Figure 13.19).

Time series for the 2005 / 06 winter (Figure 3.20 b) reveal similar trends to BH04-01 (Figure 3.19 b) during the same period, but, the ice surface at BH04-06 was colder than the snow at 0.2 m above it by ~ 0.2 to 0.7 °C. A similar temperature minima occurred on day 364 (2005) associated with a sharp air temperature decrease and a similar fluctuation on day 23 (2006) allied to the January snow pit excavation. More pronounced than at BH04-01 was a temperature increase between days 16 and 23 (2006), which manifested itself as a near surface snow temperature increase from -14.45 to -8.42 °C in response to an air temperature rise from -21.1 to -10.96 °C on day 16 (2006) and a continued rise to -0.2 °C on day 20 (2006). On day 118 (2006) snow pit excavation again initiated dramatic warming at all depths within the snow pack, except the ice surface temperature which experienced a 1.2 °C temperature decrease before following the warming trend of the other thermistors though at a notably colder temperature.

Figure 3.19: Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 in (a) the 2004 / 05 winter between November and May and (b) the 2005 / 06 winter between November and May (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot). Both time series terminate before all the thermistors melted out of the snow pack due to data logger malfunctions (dashed line depicts the change of year).

Figure 3.20: Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-06 in (a) the 2004 / 05 winter between November and January and (b) the 2005 / 06 winter between November and June (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot). Both time series terminate before all the thermistors melted out of the snow pack due to data logger malfunctions (dashed line depicts change of year).

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

The Central site (BH05-07)

Temperature records for BH05-07 in the 2005 / 06 winter (Figure 3.21) terminate in late February on account of data logger malfunction; data stored on the logger would not fully download (despite repeated attempts to do so using three different techniques) and subsequent static charge build up later in the year resulted in corruption and data loss. Of particular interest in Figure 3.21 is the clearly visible disturbance reaching a minima on day 364 (2005) as reported in both BH04-01 and BH05-07. Near surface cooling of ~ 6 °C resulted from a period of colder air temperatures between days 361 and 364 (2005), air temperatures fell rapidly from fluctuating in the range -5 to -8 °C on day 358 (2005) to -23.95 °C on day 361 (2005) and remained in the range -22 to -24.5 °C until day 364 (2005) followed by a rapid warming to -4.96 °C on day 365 (2005), marking the beginning of a ~ 4 °C near surface snow temperature increase. Between days 15 and 45 (2006), during a period when no snow fall occurred and with a snow depth variation of less than 10 cm, large temperature fluctuations replicating the air temperature trends were observed. The temperature at 1.6 m above the ice surface (less than 10 cm below the snow surface) was ~ 2.8 to 3 °C warmer than the thermistor 0.2 m below for the duration of this period, it is postulated that uppermost thermistor may have been experiencing solar heating as a consequence of radiation penetration into the snow surface (Section 1.8.1). During this period, low snow pack temperatures on day 27 (2006) were a testament to an air temperature drop to -20.83 on the same day. Towards the bottom of the snow pack the thermistor at 0.4 m above the ice surface displays the warmest temperatures for almost the entire period of data collection, only dropping below the ice surface temperature briefly as a consequence of the day 364 (2006) surface cooling event.

Figure 3.21: Snow pack thermistor time series (following application of a 24 hour moving average) at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH05-07 in the 2005 / 06 winter between November and February, with erroneous time series removed (see Section 5.3.3) (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot). As for BH04-01 and BH04-06 the time series terminates before all the thermistors melted out of the snow pack due to data logger malfunction (dashed line depicts change of year).

Seasonal variation

Figures 3.22, 3.23 and 3.24 are presented to show in greater detail the snow pack temperature changes occurring during the accumulation and ablation periods, which are not clear from the locations displaying longer time series in Figures 3.19 and 3.20. Unfortunately data logger problems in both years at all sites prevented data collection during main period of pack ripening, snow ablation and thermistor melt out, data loss tended to stem from the final storage areas being corrupted by static build up and / or lightning strikes to the logger boxes during the early part of the summer prior to downloading.

Snow pack accumulation period (North site, winter 2004-05)

Figure 3.22 presents data having undergone only basic post collection processing and not having been smoothed with a 24 hour moving average as presented in Figures 3.19, 3.20 and 3.21, this data clearly shows diurnal cycles in the near surface snow temperatures, an effect of the forcing by fluctuating air temperatures e.g. at 1.0 and 1.2 m above the ice surface between days 3 and 17 (2005). As with the longer period temperature fluctuations, the amplitudes of diurnal variation

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

decreased exponentially with distance below the snow surface owing to the insulation effect of overlying snow. Though the temperature minima on day 37 (2005) occurred prior to automated meteorological data collection (commencing on day 57 (2005)) it seems likely that air temperatures at this time were of the order of $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (similar values were observed at this time in 2006) driving the snow cooling and near surface snow temperatures down to $\sim -18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 3.22: Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 in the accumulation period of the 2004 / 05 winter between November and February (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot) (dashed line depicts change of year).

Snow pack ablation period

Figure 3.23 (a) displays in greater detail the period of warming at the end of the 2004 / 05 winter at BH04-01 following the excavation of a snow pit on day 112 (2005) which caused a short period of snow cooling and more importantly for the warming of the snow pack, disturbed the stratification, which following backfilling of the hole provided a well aerated profile with many preferential drainage pathways devoid of impermeable ice lenses, favouring rapid percolation of any liquid water generated at and within the near surface snow layers. Near snow surface thermistors were the first to warm to near $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ gradually followed by deeper thermistors, the slowest of which to warm was that at the ice surface. Following some initial fluctuation in the range -4 to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperatures at all depths (except the snow surface which exhibits some cooling of $\sim 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ between days 127 and 135 (2005) in response to a small air temperature decrease) climb to stable, near-melting temperatures within a 10 day period between days 117 and 127 (2006).

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Once stable the ice surface remains the coldest snow pack temperature at ~ -0.35 °C. The diurnally oscillating temperature signal (at a maximum of ~ 0.6 °C at 0.8 m above the ice surface) visible at depths of 0.8, 0.6, 0.4 and to a lesser extent 1.0 m above the ice surface in Figure 3.23 (b) coincided with the location of the logger enclosure at ~ 0.8 m above the ice surface and was attributed (following the elimination of other possible causes) to the warming and cooling of the power supply battery in response to the daily charging cycle from the solar panel. These artificially induced periodic oscillations could have been removed by means of applying a 24 hour moving average to the series (as in Figures 3.19, 3.20 and 3.21), but this process results in loss of resolution, of interest in interpretation of the ripening of the snow pack. These highly uniform quasi sinusoidal cycles are also utilised in determination of the thermal conductivity properties of the snow pack as detailed in Section 5.5.3.

The rapid warming on day 115 (2006) (Figure 3.23 (b)) was an artefact of the snow pit initiated on day 114 (2006). Following the thermal and stratigraphical agitation temperature increases of ~ 5 °C to almost 0 °C were observed at 1.2 m above the ice surface with smaller magnitude increases occurring concurrently at 1.0, 0.6, 0.4 and 0.2 m. Similar to the previous year, the chaotic period of temperature fluctuation following excavation of the April snow pit rapidly abated within a period of ~ 10 to 20 days, by the end of which time stable near 0 °C temperatures were reached at all depths (with the exception of the thermistor at a height of 0.8 m above the ice surface, the reliability of which as noted above was compromised by the thermal effects of the data logger enclosure and may thus be disregarded in the explanation of snow temperature evolution). During the period of transition to isothermal conditions three prominent temperature rises at the ice surface accompanied by smaller slightly later peaking temperature augmentations at 0.2 m were evident, rising to -0.29 , -0.41 and -0.87 °C (allied to an undisturbed ice surface temperature at this time of ~ -3 °C) on days 124, 128 and 133 (2006) respectively. Comparing these temperature rises at the ice surface with the heat flux between the snow and the ice (Figure 3.4) it was apparent that the positive heat flux peak of 18.6 W m^{-2} occurred around this time (on day 137 (2006)) allowing the postulation to be made that these temperature peaks may be attributed to energy release at the ice surface via refreezing of percolating melt water (in the vicinity of the ice surface thermistor) generated at the surface, passing with little hindrance to the ice surface. The discrepancies in the timing of the peaks and the heat flux peak may be explained by the non coincident locations of the ice surface thermistor and the heat flux plate located away from the base of the thermistor mounting pole, snow pack spatial heterogeneity and the irregular locations of refreezing (controlled by ice surface micro-topography constraining small scale ponding of melt).

Figure 3.23: Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-01 during April and May in the ablation period of the (a) 2004 / 05 winter and the (b) 2005 / 06 winter (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot).

The period of snow pack warming at the end of the 2005 / 06 winter as displayed in Figure 3.24 again outlines a period of transition and rapid warming following disturbance in April by the

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

digging of a snow pit. Following the transition period, snow temperatures were stable with the warmest temperatures near the surface, became colder with depth in the snow pack, but in contrast to BH04-01 the BH04-06 snow thermistors exhibited small amplitude fluctuations superimposed on steady below 0 °C temperatures until the end of June, with a slight upward trend from day 170 (2006) onwards. Diurnal cycles were once more observed in the time series of the thermistor nearest to the logger enclosure (1.8 m above the ice surface at this location). The ice surface experienced cooling for ~ 5 days following the initiation of the snow pit (as the hole was not back filled due to time limitations, leaving the hole open to the atmosphere, allowing ponding of colder air driving the observed cooling). Ice temperatures warmed quickly, rising to -2.72 °C on day 129 (2006) more than likely resulting from the ice surface being covered as the hole was in-filled with blowing snow.

During the stable period following the transition, snow and ice temperatures were colder at BH04-06 than at BH04-01. At BH04-01 from day 134 (2006) all snow temperatures were > -1 °C (with the exception of the compromised thermistor at 0.8 m) (Figure 3.23 b) while at BH04-06 all snow temperatures from day 136 (2006) onwards were between -2 and 0 °C and the ice surface temperature was ~ -3 °C.

Summary

- Near surface thermistors buried under only a few cm of snow experienced large amplitude temperature fluctuations driven by air temperature variations.
- Thermistors at depth within the snow pack displayed similar trends to those at the surface but at warmer temperatures and over a markedly smaller amplitude range as a consequence of the insulating effect of the overlying snow.
- Near the base of the snow pack temperatures exhibited a gradual warming from their time of burial until rapid warming occurred as the snow pack became isothermal and water reached the bed.
- The excavation of snow pits disrupted the thermal structure of the snow pack exposing the thermistors to ambient air temperatures allowing both warming and cooling of the snow in the vicinity of the hole as a consequence. Anthropogenically derived snow pack warming (e.g. day 20 (2006) at BH04-01) disturbances were dissipated much quicker than cooling disturbances.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

- Ice surface thermistors at BH04-01 in May 2006 exhibited temperature increases attributed to refreezing of surface derived melt water at times corresponding well with the reversal of the snow to ice heat flux measured also at the ice surface.
- Thermistors in both BH04-01 and BH04-06 during the 2005 / 06 winter displayed prominent sinusoidal diurnal temperature cycles driven by warming associated with the daily charging of the logger batteries from the solar panel.

Figure 3.24: Snow pack thermistor time series at the ice surface and 0.2 m intervals there above at BH04-06 between April and June in the ablation period of the 2005 / 06 winter (refer to Figure 3.15 for snow depth time series plot).

Temperature profiles

Bi – monthly average snow pack temperature profiles are presented in Figures 3.25 and 3.26 for BH04-01 and BH04-06 in the 2004 / 05 winter and for BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 in the 2005 / 06 winter respectively, while profiles derived from temperature averages over 5 day periods at the end of the winter as the snow pack ripened towards isothermal conditions at all three locations are presented in Figure 3.27. Figure 3.28 displays manually measured temperature profiles at BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 collected during snow pit surveys in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007.

Bi - monthly average temperature profiles

2004 / 05 winter

Near surface snow temperatures showed a decrease as the winter progressed at both BH04-01 and BH04-06 (Figure 3.25 a and b respectively) for example from ~ -6 °C at the beginning of December, through ~ -10 °C in the second half of December to a minima of ~ -15 °C in the first half of March. Ice surface temperatures on the other hand displayed a gradual increase over a range of ~ -5.5 to -3.5 °C in the early part of the winter, then experienced a large jump to temperatures of greater than -1 °C in May as the whole snow pack warmed. Of specific interest in the temperature profiles for BH04-01 was the jump to warmer temperatures experienced at heights above 2.0 m in the snow pack during the first two weeks of February, this perturbation was a manifestation of the air temperature warming event noted above, occurring on day 37 (2005). During the period November to early March temperature gradients were for the most part negative (the ice surface was warmer than the ambient air temperature) temperatures at the base of the snow pack are warmer than at the surface, energy was lost from the snow pack and energy was replenished from the warmer ice to the colder snow pack. Towards the end of spring (during the second half of March in BH04-01 in 2005) a temperature gradient reversal occurs from the snow surface downwards in response to warming air temperatures and increasingly positive net radiation. Warmer snow near the surface overlay colder snow beneath, in turn overlying warmer snow towards the ice surface, the colder snow in the middle of the snow pack was warmed quickly from above by conduction and percolating melt generated at the surface and gradually by conduction and advective air flow of heat from the ice beneath driven by the negative temperature gradient through the upper ice layers (Section 4.1.2) and in the lower part of the snow pack. The end of April saw a sharp jump in snow pack temperatures of ~ 4 °C at all depths. By the beginning May 2006 the temperature of all bar the lower 1.0 m of BH04-01 had risen to ~ 0 °C with small remnants of cold snow still to fully warm in the metre directly above the ice surface, by the end of May the snow pack was pretty much isothermal at melting point.

Figure 3.25: Bi-monthly average snow pack temperature profiles derived from thermistor data collected during the 2004 / 05 winter at (a) BH04-01 and (b) BH04-06 (days of year over which averages taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

2005 / 06 winter

The general pattern of temperature profile change observed in BH04-01 in the winter of 2005 / 06 (Figure 3.26 a) was very similar to that in the previous winter (Figure 3.25a). Sequential warming at the surface occurred from the beginning of March and at the ice surface from the time of first snow cover. Again a large temperature jump was observed during second half of April with warming at the beginning of May slightly slower in 2006 than in 2005, but the 2006 snow pack was more or less isothermal by end of May as in 2005. The sequential gradual warming of bi-monthly temperature profiles as observed in all pits after burial, under sufficient depth of snow for an insulating effect to develop, occurred while the overall snow pack temperature gradient was negative. For warming to occur under negative temperature gradient conditions (preventing heat transfer via conduction downwards from the surface), energy must have been sourced from the balance between heat loss to the surface above (decreasing with increasing depth of overlying snow and progression to warmer air temperatures towards the end of the winter) and transfer from the warmer ice surface below.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

Both BH04-01 and BH04-06 showed positive temperature gradients near the surface in the second half of December when the surface temperature was ~ 2 °C warmer than the snow in the 0.4 m below it, as a result of snow pack surface warming driven by air temperature fluctuation. BH04-06 (Figure 3.26 b) depicted similar patterns of temperature change to BH04-01 (Figure 3.26 a), but BH04-06 was notably slower to warm than BH04-01. Both sets of profiles experienced jumps in temperature at the beginning of May, the difference being that BH04-01 evolved to an isothermal regime by the end of May while at the same time, below 1.8 m above the ice surface in BH04-06 all temperatures were ~ -2 °C and had not fully warmed to 0 °C by the end of June when records ceased. In BH04-06 the ice surface was ~ 1.5 °C colder than the snow 0.2 m above it from April onwards.

BH05-07 (Figure 3.26 c) depicted the general trend of warmer snow temperatures towards the bottom of the snow pack with heat loss to the pre April cold atmospheric boundary layer at the surface. BH05-07 profiles were much noisier however, with potentially spuriously warm snow (of the order of 1 to 2 °C) at depths of 0.4, 1.0, 1.6 and 2.2 m above the ice surface when compared to temperatures in other snow pits, resulting in non linear temperature profiles and thermal gradients which reverse a number of times with increasing depth below the snow surface. As a consequence of the potentially spurious thermistor data, temperature profiles with the suspect thermistors removed are presented in Figure 3.27 (d). The removal of the suspect thermistors results in profiles which appear to more resemble the profiles of the other two snow pack locations (see Section 5.3.3 for explanation of spurious thermistor results).

Figure 3.26: Bi-monthly average snow pack temperature profiles derived from thermistor data collected during the 2005 / 06 winter at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06, (c) BH05-07 and (d) BH05-07 re-plotted with suspect thermistors removed, (see Section 5.3.3.) (days of year over which averages taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

Snow pack “ripening” (becoming isothermal)

Figure 3.27 shows the period of snow pack ripening as isothermal conditions were approached as the average of 5 day periods at the end of the winter for thermistor station BH04-01 between April and June 2005 and for BH04-01 and BH04-06 during the same period in 2006 to characterise in greater detail the temperature changes occurring within the snow. Profiles for BH04-01 in 2005 showed surface snow temperatures increasing, responding more quickly than those deeper in the pack as energy input increased at the surface during April. During April minimum snow pack temperatures relocated from their surface position throughout March (Figure 3.26 a) to mid depth within the pack between 1.2 and 1.8 m above the ice surface. With colder snow sandwiched between warmer snow, temperature gradients drove energy transfer into the cold snow from warmer snow above and below. Between the 26th and 30th of April (days 116 to 120) a rapid temperature increase at the surface caused dramatic changes in the temperature profile and the thermal gradients, the snow pack became isothermal to a depth of 2.6 m above the ice surface and all depths below that experienced considerably warming from their over winter temperatures. The curved shape of the temperature profile between 26th and 30th of April suggests surface derived warming to be the driving force behind the changes, which continued into May with the snow pack becoming isothermal to a depth of 1.4 m above the ice surface 5 days later and almost over the entire depth by the May 16th (day 136). The ice surface exhibited warming during the same period in the form of two distinct steps, the shape of the temperature profile and the magnitude and timing of the ice surface temperature increases would seem consistent with the percolation and refreezing of surface derived melt.

BH04-01 in spring 2006 (Figure 3.27 b) revealed very similar temperature profiles to 2005 (note the lower height of the upper thermistor in 2006). Again the largest temperature increase occurred between the 26th and 30th of April (days 116 to 120) however contrary to 2005 the surface sourced heat penetrated to depth more quickly in 2006 making the temperature profile in this period less curved than the previous year. The ice surface was slower to warm in 2006 than in 2005 taking a number of smaller steps toward isothermal conditions as opposed to the two larger jumps in 2005, in both years the warming was complete to isothermal conditions by the end of May.

Variation between the 2005 and 2006 temperature profiles at the end of April and beginning of May suggested differences in the nature of the energy transfer through the snow pack from the surface. The 2005 warming seemed to have occurred more slowly but more extensively in the upper layers before gradually moving down through the pack, compared to the penetration to

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

depth in 2006 which appeared to have quickly reached the bottom of the pack but transferred energy more uniformly throughout the depth of snow. Differences in the heat transfer mechanisms are highly influenced by the snow stratigraphy and the anthropogenic disturbance outlined earlier, it is postulated from the form of the temperature profile changes that the nature of the preferential melt pathways in 2005 may be more tortuous (with impermeable ice layers possibly reforming within the in-filled pit) as the wetting front advance seemed to warm each layer extensively before progressing to sequentially lower layers. In contrast in 2006 the wetting front advance seemed to have reached the ice surface more quickly but without transferring as much heat laterally to the surrounding snow en-route, hence the more uniform approach to isothermal conditions at all depths simultaneously in 2006.

BH04-06 (Figure 3.27 c) in spring 2006 demonstrated gradual warming from the surface downwards, almost linear with depth over the early period of warming, the speed of energy transfer increased between the end of April and beginning of May as observed in BH04-01. Between the 6th and 10th of May (day 126 to 130) the temperature at 0.2 m above the ice surface increased by ~ 1 °C, more so than the other thermistors. On June 19th (day 170) snow temperatures below 1.6 m above the ice surface were still cold and below the melting point, in contrast to BH04-01 where the entire depth approached melting point by May 16th (day 136), little temperature profile evolution towards warmer conditions occurred in the period May 16th to June 19th (days 136 to 170). The thermal evolution of the ice surface at BH04-01 and BH04-06 were dissimilar. The BH04-06 ice surface thermistor remained ~ 1.5 °C colder than the snow thermistor directly above it for the duration of the warming period May 6th to June 19th (days 126 to 170) while at BH04-01 linear warming throughout the snow pack extended to the ice surface, it appears the “cold ice” near the surface at BH04-06 (Section 4.1.2) was controlling temperatures in the lower 0.2 m of the snow pack.

Summary

- The presence of a snow pack insulated the ice surface in winter, preventing ice surface temperatures from falling any lower than ~ -4 to -5 °C despite winter air temperatures at times approaching -25 °C.
- Temperature gradients within the snow pack were for the most part negative from the time of the first snow deposition until approximately April when gradients near the snow surface began to become positive in response to net energy input.

Figure 3.27: Snow pack temperature profiles over 5 day periods during the “ripening” of the snow pack, at the end of the 2004 / 05 winter at (a) BH04-01 and at the end of the 2005 / 06 winter at (b) BH04-01 and (c) BH04-06.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS I

- Progressive warming of bi-monthly temperature profiles following thermistor burial while temperature gradients were negative results, from the balance between heat loss to the snow surface above (decreasing with increasing depth of overlying snow and progression to warmer air temperatures towards the end of the winter) and heat addition from the warmer ice surface below.
- Temperatures below 1.8 m above the ice surface at BH04-06 were still significantly below 0 °C by the end of June 2006 while at the same time the whole snow depth at BH04-01 had become isothermal at ~ 0 °C by the end of May.
- The BH04-06 ice surface at the end of the winter in 2006 was ~ 1.5 °C colder than the snow 0.2 m above it.

Manual snow pit temperature profiles

Temperatures measured in snow pits at all three thermistor stations in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007 (Figure 3.28) show similar trends in all three locations and correspond well with the automated thermistor time series. The profiles displayed in Figure 3.28 are at a cruder resolution than the thermistor data reflecting the ± 1 °C accuracy of the stem thermometer in comparison to the ± 0.04 °C of the thermistors. January temperature profiles in both years displayed similar steep negative temperature gradients from the ice surface upwards, reversing to positive gradients in the top ~ 0.3 m as a consequence of a warmer surface snow layer, in both years the surface temperatures are much as 4 °C warmer than the layers below. The main difference between the 2006 and 2007 January temperature profiles was the height above the ice surface at which the characteristic changes in the temperature profiles occurred, ~ 0.5 m higher above the ice surface in 2007 (due to a deeper snow pack) the result of which, was that although the gradients of the temperature profiles were very similar for a given height within the snow pack the temperature in January 2007 was 3 to 5 °C warmer than at the same height in 2006, reflecting the insulation properties of the snow and the influence of the cold atmospheric boundary layer in contact with the upper surface. The April profiles clearly displayed melting point temperatures had been reached at the snow surface, varying in depth of penetration in all three pits. In the lower 2.5 to 3 m of the snow pack temperatures appeared yet to be disturbed, between - 4 and - 5 °C.

Figure 3.28: Temperature profiles recorded manually using a stem thermometer in the North facing wall of snow pits dug at (a) BH04-01, (b) BH04-06 and (c) BH05-07 in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007.

Chapter 4

Results II: Englacial and basal conditions.

4.1 Glacier ice

Ice surface ablation, ice temperatures, glacier ice strain rate (derived from borehole deformation) and ice core density data are presented in Section 4.1, while subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity measurements to aid thermistor data interpretation near the bed are presented in Section 4.2.

4.1.1 Ice thickness

Ice thicknesses at the locations of the thermistor strings were initially determined from the length of boreholes drilled to the glacier bed and from ground penetrating radar (GPR) surveys of the glacier conducted by colleagues from the University of Swansea during April 2004. Figure 4.1 showing a processed 50 MHz radar transect across the glacier passing through the locations of BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07, has had vertically scaled depictions of boreholes (determined from the drilling logs) superimposed at the correct locations and shows close agreement between the ice depth measured in the boreholes and the inferred position of the glacier bed from the GPR surveys. Following deployment and freeze in of thermistor strings, data logger enclosure mounting poles served as ablation stakes to chart the ablation of the glacier surface over three ablation seasons; where it was felt mounting poles may have dropped down the holes drilled to fix them in, a check was made against the melt out of the thermistor strings and inclinometry cables (the ice surface was marked with knots and tape at the time of installation). Manual ice surface location measurements made during repeat field visits and are depicted as “tie points” in Figure 4.2 (a), (b) and (c) displaying the snow and ice surfaces for the duration of the study period at BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 respectively. The manually measured tie points allow (where necessary) correction of the automated SR50 UDG distance to surface record for determination of the ice surface position. Manual measurements at the South and Central sites allowed adjustment of the single SR50 dataset recorded at the North site for derivation of an ice surface data set for the South and Central sites. The winter snow depth transects (Section 3.3.1) suggested that the point SR50 snow depth measurement at the North site was representative of the snow depth over the whole glacier. Measurements of snow depth at each borehole location allowed manipulation of the North site SR50 snow depth record to better account for small variations in the snow depth between the three locations. In deriving the ice surface elevation change and ice thickness it was assumed that when the ice surface was snow covered no ice

ablation occurred; no account was made for superimposed ice formation at the base of the snow pack.

Figure 4.1: Processed 50 MHz radar transect across glacier de Tsanfleuron conducted in April 2004 presented as instantaneous frequency, (Boreholes 04-01, 05-07 and 04-06 have been superimposed at their respective locations). Data courtesy of Dr Tavi Murray. Modified from: <http://ralph.swan.ac.uk/glaciology/projects/tsan/spring2004.html> Accessed 03/04/06.

The North site (BH04-01)

At the time of drilling in April 2004, the ice thickness at the North site (Figure 4.2 a) (back calculated from BH05-16 as BH04-01 terminated blind at ~ 90 m) was 131.43 m. During the 2004 summer ablation period 2.46 m of ice surface lowering occurred (Table A3 (see Appendix)), the ice surface over-wintered at 128.97 m above the bed, ablated another 0.63 m during the 2005 summer, remained at 128.34 m thickness over the 2005 / 06 winter and ablated a further 0.90 m in the 2006 ablation period. A total of 3.99 m of ice surface lowering occurred over the period of study.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

The South site (BH04-06)

April 2004 at the time of thermistor string installation saw the glacier surface (including an unmeasured snow pack) at BH04-06 (Figure 4.2 b) 60.40 m above the bed. During the 2004 summer ice ablation was estimated to be between 1.05 and 1.84 m of glacier ice (Table A3 (see Appendix)), resulting in an over-wintering ice thickness of between 59.35 and 58.56 m. Summer 2005 recorded an ice surface lowering of between 1.61 and 2.04 m, while during the 2005 / 06 winter the ice thickness remained at 57.00 m. 1.29 m of ice was ablated in the summer of 2006, resulting in a total ablation of 4.74 m of glacier ice between April 2004 and January 2007.

The Central site (BH05-07)

The ice thickness at BH05-07 (Figure 4.3) at the time of drilling on day 224 (2005) was 98.50 m. 0.98 m of ice ablation occurred from the time of borehole drilling to the stable winter ice surface position of 97.52 m above the bed. It was estimated that in the early summer of 2005, 0.56 m of ice had ablated at BH05-07 prior to drilling on day 224 (2005). Over the 2006 ablation period 0.42 m of surface lowering occurred up to day 233.

All thermistor locations within the boreholes were referenced relative to the immovable bed. Having measured and derived the surface lowering of the glacier over the study period, it was possible to calculate depths of thermistors below the ice surface at any time and calculate the thermistor melt-out dates. Table A4 (see Appendix) presents the deployment heights and melt out dates of thermistors in BH04-01, BH05-16 and BH04-06, while Table A5 (see Appendix) displays the depths and dates for BH05-07 and the adjacent crevasse.

Figure 4.2: Ice and snow surface elevation above the glacier bed for the duration of the study period between May 2004 and January 2007 at (a) BH04-01 and (b) BH04-06, determined from borehole drilling to the bed, melt-out of thermistor strings and data logger mounting poles and SR50 snow depth measurements, validated with periodic manual snow depth and ice surface location measurements (where a range of possible ablation values are presented in Table A3 a best estimate interpolation was used for the purposes of plotting).

Figure 4.3: Ice and snow surface elevation above the glacier bed for the duration of the study period between May 2004 and January 2007 at BH05-07, determined from borehole drilling to the bed, melt-out of thermistor strings and data logger mounting poles and SR50 snow depth measurements, validated with periodic manual snow depth and ice surface location measurements.

4.1.2 Ice temperature

Ice temperatures were recorded at various heights from the glacier bed up to the ice surface. As outlined in Tables 4.2 and 4.3 thermistors were not equally spaced throughout the ice thickness, greater spatial resolution was focussed in the top most ~ 20 m of the ice to characterise the layer exposed to annual temperature variation as a consequence of winter cooling as the winter cold wave penetrated down from the surface. Near-surface thermistor temperature time series were screened for the presence of transient effects due to thermistors logging water and / or air temperatures in open boreholes, when found, such effects were removed as displayed in Figure 4.4 and detailed in Table A6 (see Appendix). Temperature time series for all ice thermistors in the englacially terminating BH04-01 and the adjacent BH05-16 to the bed for the duration of the study period are presented in Figure 4.5, time series for BH04-06 are displayed in Figure 4.6 while Figure 4.7 depicts the BH05-07 data. Detailed plots of the initiation of winter cooling between November 2004 and February 2005 at BH04-01 and BH04-06 are presented in Figure 4.8 while Figure 4.9 correspondingly displays a detailed plot of the elimination of the winter cold wave during spring 2005 for BH04-01 and during the 2006 spring and summer for BH04-06 (plots (a) and (b) accordingly). A major positive thermal disturbance of basal borehole thermistors in BH04-06, believed to be a basal heat supply event is manifest in Figure 4.10 while

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

crevasse temperature time series are outlined in Figure 4.11. An explanation of ice melting point depression as a consequence of overburden pressure, air saturation and solute dissolution is presented with melting point temperature profiles depicted in Figure 4.12.

Monthly average ice temperature profiles for BH04-01 in the 2004 / 05 and 2005 / 06 balance years are presented in Figure 4.13 and 4.14, for BH04-06 in the 2004 / 05, 2005 / 06 and 2006 / 07 years in Figures 4.15, 4.16 and 4.17 and for BH05-07 in the 2005 / 06 and 2006 / 07 years in Figure 4.18 and 4.19 respectively, while Figure 4.20 outlines temperature profiles in the crevasse directly adjacent to BH05-07 in 2005 / 06 and 2006 / 07. Detailed bi-monthly average temperature profile plots are presented in Figures 4.21, 4.22 and 4.23 to outline the penetration of the winter cold wave, the elimination of the cold wave is displayed in Figures 4.24 and 4.25 accordingly.

Temperature time series

Removal of transient effects due to borehole thermistors logging water and / or air temperatures in open boreholes

Prior to presentation (Figures 4.5 to 4.25) 'ice' temperature data from the near-surface thermistors in all three boreholes were processed and 'non ice' temperatures or 'transient effects' eliminated as indicated in the example outlined in Figure 4.4 (a) and (b). The recorded non ice temperatures, visible between day 264 (2004) and 294 (2004) in Figure 4.4 (a) resulted from an open borehole top. As detailed in Section 2.3 boreholes required time to close via freezing and inward creep of the walls following drilling. Holes which close at the surface in one year often reopened via melt to various depths in subsequent summers due to surface ablation and radiation warming of the grey thermistor cables at their point of exit from the glacier surface. As a consequence of thermistors near the glacier surface sitting in either air filled or water filled boreholes, a true representation of summer and autumn ice temperatures required removal of air and or water temperatures (as indicated in Figure 4.4 b) on the basis of field observations and the physical plausibility of the recorded temperatures. For example: the time series for thermistor 14.0a (Figure 4.4 a) depicted temperatures as low as $-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ occurring mainly at night and as high as $2.57\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ by day, these temperatures are interpreted as air temperatures, following nocturnal drainage of cold air into the borehole and the warmer air during daylight hours and were subsequently removed (Figure 4.4 b). Additional evidence for such an interpretation and data removal originates from field observations on day 263 (2004) in which the borehole top was observed to be open and air filled to an unknown depth with thermistor 14.0a visible, partially frozen into the borehole wall at a depth of 85 cm below the surface. The removal of such

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

transient effects has been conducted for the near-surface thermistors located in all three boreholes, details of which are outlined in Table A6.

Figure 4.4: Temperature time series for thermistor 14.0a (0.92 m below the ice surface) (a) as recorded by the data logger and (b) with transient effects due to the borehole BH04-01 being open and the thermistor recording an air rather than ice temperature removed.

Full three year time series

For the purposes of presentation the thermistor temperatures in all three boreholes have been split into groups, near-surface ice temperatures, englacial ice temperatures and basal ice temperatures, respectively on the basis of height above the glacier bed and distance below the ice surface.

The North site (BH04-01)

All thermistors in BH04-01 (Figure 4.5) show discontinuities in the time series; between day 141 (2005) and day 272 (2005) and between day 136 (2006) and day 232 (2006) as a consequence of data logger and multiplexer malfunction and damage resulting from static charge build up generated by lightning strikes. In the case of the first gap it is however, reasonable to assume that the thermistors continued warming to their melting points over the summer and became gradually slightly warmer (with small diurnal cycles for thermistors near the surface) after reaching melting point, as their melting points increase in response to pressure release caused by ice ablation at the surface, with similar patterns also expected for the 2006 missing data.

Near-surface temperatures decreased rapidly during October from summer values of just below 0 °C, the initiation of temperature decrease occurred almost simultaneously at 0.85, 1.85 and 2.85 m below the surface and gradually later at greater depth. Temperature decrease was most rapid near the surface in response to ice surface cooling with temperature gradients steepest near the surface decreasing exponentially with depth into the ice accordingly. The uppermost thermistor at 0.85 m below the surface experienced a sharp temperature decrease at the end of November resulting in a minimum of ~ -4.4 °C followed by a period of warming of ~ 1 °C, a trend also present at the next sensor depth of 1.85 m below the surface (though over a considerably damped amplitude). Such cooling is attributed to air temperature fluctuations causing dramatic heat loss through the shallow immature snow pack, as the depth of overlying snow increased through the winter (Figure 3.15 a) the impact of such cooling events decreased. A second near-surface temperature depression occurred in February 2005 on day 61 when a minimum of - 3.77 °C occurred at 0.85 m depth. The cooling was anthropogenic in origin, as a snow pit was dug to access the data logger enclosure temporarily removing the insulation (snow) above the ice surface exposing the ice surface to cooling. Temperature minima occurred later in the winter at sequentially deeper depths, at -2.87 °C on day 67 (2005) at 1.85 m, -2.41 °C on day 95 (2005) at 2.85 m, -1.75 °C on day 117 (2005) at 4.85 m, -0.76 °C on day 118 (2005) at 8.85 m and at -0.13 °C on day 118 (2005) at 12.85 m. Rapid warming occurred during May (~ 3 °C in a few days at 0.85 m depth) initiated at the surface, with temperature increases quickly occurring at other depths. Only the deeper thermistors took longer to respond, by July and August the near-surface winter cooling had been eliminated and ice temperatures were again at melting point. A similar pattern of cooling and warming (initiated at the ice surface in November and eliminated by August) occurred in the 2005 / 06 winter as in the previous year, thermistor 14.0a is not displayed in the 2005 / 06 winter as it had by then melted out of the ice surface. Minima of -3.48,

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

-3.13 and -2.62 °C on days 48, 58 and 98 (2006) were recorded for thermistors 15.0a, 16.0a and 18.0a respectively.

Englacial temperatures for the duration of the study period were for the most part at close to melting point, the amplitude of variation was of the order of hundredths of a degree except for thermistor 110.0a which displayed an amplitude of ~ 0.5 °C centred about freezing point (with increased averaging this could have been reported as being at melting point, but for completeness the amplitude of variation is presented here). During the 2004 / 05 winter a slight gradual increase to small positive values was observed in thermistors 90.0a, 70.0a and 50.0a at 53.23, 73.23 and 93.23 m above the bed respectively. In the 2005 / 06 winter thermistor 90.0a at 53.23 m above the bed showed a small upwards temperature change from 0.11 to 0.20 °C while over the same period thermistor 110.0a at 41.23 m showed a gradual downward trend exhibiting a smaller amplitude of variation than experienced in the previous winter. Thermistor 30.0a at 113.23 m above the bed displayed consistently stable temperatures with little fluctuation at ~ -0.05 °C.

Basal thermistors were installed in BH05-16 adjacent to BH04-01 in August 2005. Between the time of installation on 24th August (2005) and 28th September (2005) only thermistor 150.0d (located 1 m above the bed) was logged (due to a shortage of data logger channels and bridge resistor configurations while the multiplexer was returned to the UK for repairs) during which period a gradual temperature rise from 0.25 to 0.39 °C was observed. Following day 270 (2005) thermistors 150.0d and 130.0d at heights above the bed of 1.0 and 8.5 m accordingly recorded borehole (not ice) temperatures in the range 0.5 to 0.6 °C. Thermistors 110.0e and 90.0b at 28.5 and 48.5 m above the bed respectively fluctuated around 0 °C with amplitudes of a few hundredths of a degree. From day 266 (2006) until the end of the record on day 276 (2006), thermistor 100.0e (at 28.5 m above the bed) exhibited diurnal temperature minima as cold as ~ -2.5 °C occurring at almost always 0600 each morning against a steady undisturbed melting point temperature, no other englacial thermistors showed evidence of this diurnal cycle (see Section 6.3.1).

The South site (BH04-06)

Temperature time series recorded at the South site (Figure 4.6) were similar to those recorded at the North (Figure 4.5), in as much as the near-surface thermistors exhibited winter cooling initiated in November and warming at the end of the winter, significant contrasts were however apparent. Missing data between February and August 2005 resulted from the inability to locate

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

the logger enclosure in February following its burial and subsequent power loss. The temperatures from which the ice began to cool from in autumn were markedly different to BH04-01. In contrast to all being at melting point, BH04-06 ice temperatures prior to the initiation of cooling in November were stable at ~ 0.0 °C at 0.35 m, ~ -0.1 °C at 1.35 m, ~ -0.4 °C at 3.35 m, ~ -0.6 °C at 11.35 m and ~ -0.8 °C at 7.35 m below the surface respectively. Near-surface ice temperature fluctuations and minima were again observed to occur in December at -4.5 °C in response to suspected air temperature cooling events (despite a field visit on day 337 (2004) no snow pit was dug). The sinusoidal annual temperature cycle was clearly visible for thermistor 22.0b, with a delayed summer peak in November each year and a minima of -2.10 °C in May 2006 (Figure 4.6).

Borehole temperatures at the glacier bed (thermistor 70.0b) in BH04-06 displayed temperature fluctuations in the range 0.20 to 1.14 °C between August and mid October 2004, decreased to a range of 0.23 to 0.29 °C through to February 2005 with a large positive perturbation raising borehole temperatures from 1.01 to 3.45 °C between May and July 2006 (see Figure 4.10 for more detail), superimposed on a steady background temperature of ~ 0.5 °C. Thermistors sequentially higher above the bed (50.0b at 24.0 m above the bed and 30.0b at 44.0 m) both displayed the same warming disturbances as thermistor 70.0b but amplitudes which decreased with increasing separation from the bed, for example temperature augmentations of ~ 0.63 °C and 0.55 °C at 24.0 and 44.0 m height respectively in response to the 2.44 °C warming of 70.0b between May and July 2006.

The Central site (BH05-07)

The main tendency of variation in BH05-07 (Figure 4.7) was similar to that in BH04-01 (Figure 4.5). Over the same period, near-surface thermistors experience cooling beginning in November warming back to melting point during the following summer and in early winter experienced dramatic cooling, depicting cycles of air temperature fluctuation e.g. the temperature minima of -3.73 °C occurring in late November 2005 at 1.0 m below the ice surface. Missing data between February and August 2006 were attributed to data logger problems, while data from thermistors 10.0d, 10.2d and 10.4d had transient effects removed following the suspected reopening of the borehole at the surface in the summer of 2006. Thermistors at all depths throughout the borehole experienced trends of temperature decrease between August and late September 2005 in response to cooling following the hot water drilling on day 224 (2005). Basal thermistors 110.0d, 90.0c and 70.0c at the bed and 18.5 and 38.5 m above respectively, display temperatures below those of melting point for the duration of the data collection period following the initial borehole cooling.

Figure 4.5: Temperature time series recorded by near surface, englacial and basal thermistors at the North site in BH04-01 (upper plots) and BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01) from September 2004 to October 2006.

Figure 4.6: Temperature time series recorded by near-surface and basal thermistors at the South site in BH04-06 from August 2004 to January 2007.

Figure 4.7: Temperature time series recorded by near surface, englacial and basal thermistors at the Central site in BH05-07 from August 2005 to January 2007.

Initiation of winter cooling in near-surface ice

Figure 4.8 (a) and (b) show near-surface thermistor temperature records during the period of initial ice cooling from stable summer temperatures during the onset of winter between day 299 (2004) and day 33 (2005) for BH04-01 and BH04-06 respectively. BH04-01 showed cooling from summer temperatures of ~ 0 °C at all depths while BH04-06 showed cooling from various sub melting temperatures. From the surface down in BH04-01 cooling initiation occurred sequentially later at lower depths, commencing on day 313 (2004) at depths of 0.85 and 1.85 m, on day 315 (2004) at 2.85 m, on day 321 (2004) at 4.85 m and on day 346 (2004) at 8.85 m. Over the same period in BH04-06 cooling began from a temperature of -0.02 °C at a depth of 0.35 m on day 314 (2004) progressing down through the borehole from a temperature of -0.16 °C at a depth of 1.35 m on day 316 (2004), from -0.42 °C at a depth of 3.35 m on day 322 (2004) and from -0.67 °C at a depth of 7.35 m on day 353 (2004) respectively.

The later initiation of the more staggered sequential cooling in BH04-06 compared to that in BH04-01 reflected more rapid heat loss from the near-surface ice in BH04-01 than BH04-06 driven by the temperature gradient generated between the cold snow pack and the ice surface. In BH04-01 the temperature gradient was greater than between the snow and the ice at BH04-06 soon after cooling began, as the ice in the top few meters of BH04-01 was initially warmer than that in BH04-06, resulting in a stronger negative temperature gradient and faster heat loss from the ice beneath. This temperature gradient difference was reflected in the earlier timing of the initiation of cooling at depths below the surface in BH04-01.

The most rapid heat loss occurred in the thermistor nearest the surface at both boreholes, following the initial period of post initiation cooling, in BH04-01 a minima of -3.63 °C was reached on day 322 (2004) while at the same time a minima of -3.20 °C was reached in BH04-06. Directly after the minima on day 322 (2004) gradual cooling occurred and reflected air temperature fluctuations (under shallow snow pack conditions) until more rapid cooling was experienced in both holes beginning on day 345 (2004), following which minima of -4.24 and -4.52 °C on day 352 (2004) were observed in BH04-01 and BH04-06 respectively. By day 33 (2005) near-surface thermistors had stabilised at temperatures of ~ -3.4 °C at 0.85 m below the ice surface, ~ -2.7 °C at a depth of 1.85 m and at ~ -2.2 °C at 2.85 m in BH04-01 and at temperatures of ~ -3.6 °C at a depth of 0.35 m and at ~ -3.0 °C at a depth of 1.35 m in BH04-06, while sequentially deeper thermistors continued cooling further into the winter.

Figure 4.8: Thermistor time series during the period of initial winter cooling of the near-surface ice (topmost ~13 m), between the end of November 2004 and beginning of February 2005 from (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06) (dashed vertical line depicts the change of year).

Elimination of winter cooling in near-surface ice

Figure 4.9 (a) and (b) show near-surface thermistor temperature records during the period of elimination of the winter cold wave between day 103 (2005) and 140 (2005) during the early part of the ablation period at BH04-01 and between day 108 (2006) and 320 (2006) BH04-06 for the duration of the ablation period respectively. Rapid warming following the initiation of the ablation period began from the surface downwards, first recorded by thermistor 14.0a at a depth of 0.85 m below the surface, beginning on day 119 (2005) in BH04-01 (Figure 4.9 a), where a temperature increase of 2.51 °C occurred in three days between day 119 (2005) and 122 (2005). Initiation of warming occurred almost simultaneously deeper in the same hole, with notable increases on day 119 (2005) from temperatures of -2.69, -2.36 and -1.72 °C at depths of 1.85, 2.85 and 4.85 m respectively, deeper thermistors took longer to respond.

The shape of the temperature time series for the BH04-01 thermistors was indicative of the processes driving the temperature warming, the near-surface thermistor depicts rapid warming followed by gradual temperature increase superimposed upon which were fluctuations of various amplitudes and periodicities driven by penetration of surface warming and cooling, while at sequentially lower thermistors the warming trends followed smoother curves reflecting the decreasing influence of surface processes with depth below the surface .

Figure 4.9 (b) depicting the whole ablation period for BH04-06 in the summer of 2006, similar to BH04-01 depicted warming from the ice surface downwards, in this case first experienced by thermistor 18.0b, 3.35 m below the surface with thermistors 22.0b and 26.0b below the surface at depths of 7.35 and 11.35 respectively showing more gradual temperature rises throughout the ablation period never reaching melting point, both reaching “cold ice” temperature maxima of -0.73 and -0.98 °C on day 297 (2006). The change in the nature of the temperature record to a lower temporal resolution following day 230 (2006) was not intentional and occurred due damage to the 12 V gel cell battery powering the data logger as a result of two splits developing in the battery and acid leakage rendering it unable to hold any charge, thus the only data collection occurred during daylight hours on sunny days when the solar panel powered the logger. Thermistor 18.0b reached melting point on day 215 (2006) following gradual warming disrupted by a large positive jump of ~ 2 °C occurring at the same time as the large thermal disturbance experienced at the glacier bed. Thus, appears that a connection had remained (or reopened) throughout the borehole from its time of drilling, allowing propagating of large heat supply events at the bed throughout the entire ice depth through air or water flow in the hole (the hole

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

could not have been permanently filled with liquid water in the presence of markedly sub zero cold ice).

Figure 4.9: Thermistor time series during the period of elimination of the winter cold wave in spring and summer of the near-surface ice (topmost ~13 m), (a) at the North site during April and May 2005 in BH04-01 and (b) at the South site between April and October 2006 in BH04-06.

Basal heat supply events

A number of periodic of basal heat supply events to the glacier sole at BH04-06 were observed over the duration of the study period (see Section 6.4 for further examples) the largest such event being depicted in Figure 4.10. Between days ~169 (2006) and 191 (2006) a large disturbance believed to originate at the glacier bed propagated up through the borehole, unfortunately the missing data between day 172 and 183 (2006) (the loss of which may or may not have resulted from the disturbance) prevents detailed characterisation of the event. The amplitude of thermal disturbance appears to decrease with distance from the glacier sole with amplitudes of 1.8 °C at the bed, decreasing to 0.40 °C at 24.0 m above the bed, 0.36 °C at 44.0 m and so on. The only thermistor not to follow this pattern of decreasing amplitude of disturbance was 18.0b which shows an anomalously large increase (~ 2 °C) compared to the other thermistors. Considering its position 3.35 m below the ice surface, this anomaly may be explained in terms of the time series for this thermistor also probably reflecting the effect of surface warming at the end of May as the snow pack began to ablate, transferring heat to the ice surface. Thermistors 18.0b, 22.0b and 26.0b all experienced positive trends following the disturbance, with the other thermistors (30.0b, 50.0b and 70.0b) deeper within the ice and at the bed experiencing cooling reflecting the ice surface warming and the elimination of the winter cold wave. See Section 6.4.2 for further analysis of this thermal event.

Figure 4.10: Temperature time series of thermistors at all heights above the bed at the South site in BH04-06 between mid May and late July 2006 during the occurrence of a large thermal disturbance originating at the glacier bed and propagating up the borehole.

Crevasse thermistor string

Figure 4.11 depicts the time series of thermistors deployed down a crevasse to a depth of 6 m below the surface directly adjacent to BH05-07 at the Central site. The missing data between February and August 2006 was the same gap observed in BH05-07 as the two sets of thermistor strings were recorded by the same data logger. The depth of the thermistors relative to the ice surface remained constant for the duration of the study period (unlike the borehole thermistors which overtime melted out of the surface) as the string was suspended from a ~ 3 m length of Dexian bridging the crevasse, melting down as surface lowering occurred. Temperatures recorded by the thermistor string are believed to be air temperatures for the duration of the data

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

collection period (as the string was weighted and hung in the middle of the crevasse not touching either wall at the time of deployment). However it is plausible that the lower thermistors (below the depths to which visual inspection during summer was possible) may have become frozen to the wall of the crevasse, also under snow cover conditions no data is available as to whether the crevasse was bridged to a shallow depth of less than 1.0 m below the surface with air below or if it was completely filled with snow (from observations of snow bridging in December 2004 and August 2006 the former seems likely).

General temperature trends were for highly fluctuating mainly positive air temperatures during summer months with dramatically less fluctuating negative air temperatures over winter. At 1 m down the crevasse between August and the mid September 2005 recorded temperatures in the range - 0.37 to 14.60 °C were indicative of ambient air temperatures (slightly lower than those recorded at 2 m by the meteorological station (due to the lower instrument elevation)). A change in the amplitude of the temperature variations occurred from mid September to late November (where temperatures fluctuated in the range 1.40 to 4.08 °C), from November until the missing data in February temperatures decreased and fluctuated in the range -2.55 to 0.40 °C. The second year of data collection in the crevasse showed a similar pattern of air temperatures in September, decreasing abruptly during November. Lower temperatures at 1.0 m down the crevasse in August 2006 compared to the previous year reflected the high summer snowfall which covered the ice surface bridging the crevasse, insulating the thermistors below from high day time air temperatures. At 2 m down the crevasse, temperatures followed a similar pattern to those at 1 m depth, though at a much lower amplitude of variation (fluctuations in the range 0.12 to 3.54 °C at 2 m depth in August and September 2005 compared to the range -0.37 to 14.60 °C at 1.0 m). Sequentially lower thermistors at 3, 4 and 6 m depth respectively show progressively lower temperatures, the lowest temperatures are recorded by thermistor 11.8d at 6m depth, showing a gradual cooling trend through each winter and drainage into and ponding of cold air in the crevasse during August 2005 (temperatures of ~ - 4.5 °C) (similar temperatures associated with cold air drainage were not recorded in August 2006, as the crevasse was snow bridged preventing drainage).

Summary

- Under early winter conditions in the absence of the deep snow insulation, near-surface ice temperatures showed fluctuation in response to short term meteorological variation and were susceptible to rapid cooling during periods of large air temperature perturbation, the influence of air temperature fluctuation was reduced as snow depth increased.

Figure 4.11: Temperature time series recorded by thermistors in a crevasse directly adjacent to BH05-07 at the Central site from August 2005 to January 2007.

- The initiation of winter cooling and the elimination of the winter cold wave occurred first at the ice surface propagating deeper into the ice over time.
- The South site (BH04-06) showed evidence of warming at the glacier bed, the influence of which was felt at distance above the bed but at lower amplitude.
- At ~ 7 m below the ice surface in BH04-06 an almost perfect sinusoidal ice temperature cycle was recorded, with maximum of ~ -0.7 °C in November and minimum of -2.1 °C in May.
- Near surface ice temperatures at the North site in BH04-01 all reached melting point at the end of the summer. At the South site in BH04-06 however, the stable temperatures reached in summer were below melting point indicating the presence of cold ice near the glacier surface.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

- Crevasse temperatures reflected air temperatures near the surface but showed stable colder temperatures at depth, with evidence of cold air drainage and ponding when the crevasse was snow free and open to the atmosphere.

Temperature profiles

Determination of ice melting point

The melting point temperature displayed in the temperature profiles, Figures 4.13 to 4.19 was calculated from the theory outlined by Paterson (1994 p 12) in which melting point depression allowing ice melt at temperatures below 0 °C was controlled by 3 factors:

- 1) Pressure of overlying ice,
- 2) The effect of ice forming water being air saturated,
- 3) Solute dissolved into the ice forming water.

Temperate glacier ice consists of water in both a solid and liquid state, air bubbles, dissolved salts and carbon dioxide (Paterson, 1994, p211). The melting point temperatures modelled in Figure.4.12 were calculated using the following equations (Paterson, 1994, p212):

For pure ice at absolute pressure

$$T = T_0 - \beta * p' \quad (4.1.1)$$

where:

T = Temperature (°C),

T_0 = Triple point temperature of water (0.01 °C),

β^* = Rate of change of melting point with pressure ($7.42 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K(kPa)}^{-1}$),

p' = Absolute pressure (kPa).

For ice formed from air saturated water

$$T = T_0 - \beta^{\wedge} P \quad (4.1.2)$$

where:

T = Temperature (°C),

T_0 = Triple point temperature of water (0.01 °C),

β^{\wedge} = Rate of change of melting point with pressure
($9.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K(kPa)}^{-1}$ or $8.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K m}^{-1}$),

P = Pressure (kPa).

For ice formed from air saturated water with dissolved impurities

$$T = T_0 - \beta^{\wedge} P - \frac{An'}{W'} \quad (4.1.3)$$

where:

T = Temperature (°C),

T_0 = Triple point temperature of water (0.01 °C),

β^{\wedge} = Rate of change of melting point with pressure
($9.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K(kPa)}^{-1}$ or $8.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K m}^{-1}$),

P = Pressure (kPa),

A = $1.86 \text{ K kg mol}^{-1}$,

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

n' = Impurity concentration (mol kg^{-1}),
 W' = Fractional water content by weight.

Figure 4.12(a) depicts melting points modelled from an average salt concentration of 0.929 g m^{-3} derived from the ice cores recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron (Hubbard *et al.*, (2000a) and Tison and Hubbard, (2000)). It can be seen in Figure 4.12 that at depths of 130 m (equivalent to the greatest borehole depth at Tsanfleuron (Figure 4.1 (BH05-16 reached a depth of 128.5 m when drilled in August 05)) water can exist in a liquid form at a temperature of $-0.11 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 4.12(b) shows melting points determined from ionic salt concentrations of 0.68, 1.23 and 7.34 g m^{-3} representing the three distinct layers, the Upper zone, Lower zone and Basal zone respectively used by Hubbard *et al.* (2003) in modelling the spatial variability of water content and rheology from ice cores (hence the kinks at depths of 62.5 m and 73.2 m representing the transition to zones of higher ice solute concentration at depth) and a fractional water content by weight of 0.02 chosen on the basis of previous measurements of water content in temperate ice e.g. Cohen, (1999) and Murray *et al.*, (2000).

Figure 4.12: Ice melting temperatures modelled from basic theory (Paterson, 1994) using both ice thickness and three solute concentrations from ice cores recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron assigned to different ice layers in ice flow modelling (Hubbard *et al.*, 2003) and average solute concentrations.

Monthly average temperature profiles

The North site (BH04-01)

August 2004 to August 2005

Figure 4.13 (a), (b), and (c) depict glacier ice temperatures throughout the entire depth of ice and the overlying snow pack, the lower 80 m of the glacier and the near-surface ice and snow pack respectively in the 2004 – 2005 balance year. The coldest ice temperatures occurred in a thin layer near the glacier surface, below which temperatures were considerably warmer and were close to melting point (Figure 4.13 a). Below 40 m above the bed, data was not collected in the period August 2004 to 2005 as BH04-01 terminated blind at ~ 90 m depth, from August 2005, BH05-16 to the bed adjacent to BH04-01 was instrumented (depicted as a dashed line to indicate data collection was in a different hole at the same location) allowing profiles to continue to the bed. Englacial and basal temperatures are depicted in Figure 4.13 (b) all monthly average temperatures plot to the right of the melting point (with the exception of the averages for September, October and November at a height of 40 m above the bed which were colder than melting point but then experienced warming in the following months), no order seems apparent in the temperature fluctuation at 40 m above the bed other than that the warmest temperatures occurred in December and January. At the bed the August 2005 temperature in BH05-16 of ~ 0.3 °C likely reflected warm drilling water standing in the bottom of the borehole following the drilling of the hole on day 232 (2005). Near the surface (Figure 4.13 c) an ice temperature minima of - 4.52 °C was observed at the ice surface (indicated as a horizontal dashed line), cooling of the ice (from melting point during August, September and October) was initiated in November and continued until April when snow pack temperatures began to warm. May saw the first warming within the ice from the surface downwards causing a reversal of the over-winter negative temperature gradient in response to heat transfer into the ice from the snow pack. Ice temperatures had warmed to near isothermal conditions just below melting point by July (no data are available in June due to data logger problems).

September 2005 to August 2006

Temperature profiles in BH04-01 and BH05-16 during the 2005 – 06 balance year presented in Figure 4.16 were similar to those experienced in the 2004 / 05 year (Figure 4.15), no substantial data were available during June and July again as a consequence of logger failure. Exceptions to the trends presented above occurred englacially and at the bed (Figure 4.16 b) where temperatures at ~ 54 m above the glacier bed were positive in the range 0.1 to 0.15 °C for all months except August 2006 where the temperature was ~ 0.5 °C, possibly suggesting warming

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

due to ablation season melt-water via the presence of some form of englacial drainage pathway (possibly down through a section of the borehole which had not fully closed). Below this anomalously warm thermistor temperature the ice at 40 m above the bed in BH04-01 had cooled to an average of ~ -0.5 °C from an average of ~ 0.1 °C in the previous year. Temperatures in BH05-16 between 30 and 50 m above the glacier bed conversely closely match the melting point to within the error of the temperature measurements. At the bed average monthly thermistor temperatures showed a sequential month on month increase in the range ~ 0.3 to ~ 0.8 °C, with a jump of ~ 0.2 °C to the August maximum (refer to Figure 4.5 for warming trend). For the duration of the winter the thermistor ~ 8.5 m above the bed showed almost identical temperatures to that at the bed, experienced a similar jump to August values but was at this time a fraction cooler than the bed, suggesting some form of basal warming.

Near-surface ice temperature variations (Figure 4.14 c) were also slightly different to the previous year, September and October again displayed melting point temperatures throughout, from which cooling again occurred in November. Cooling throughout the near-surface layer continued until May, a month later than in the 2005 / 06 winter. The snow temperature profile in April 2006 showed less warming than April 2005 while a discontinuity between the snow and ice temperature of ~ 2 °C at the ice surface occurred in May. Again temperature reached melting point throughout the borehole by August.

Figure 4.13: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2004 and August 2005 at BH04-01 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (above the dashed horizontal line depicting the location of the winter ice surface), (b) englacial and basal thermistors (the dashed line joining points near the bed indicates thermistors in the adjacent BH05-16) and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

Figure 4.14: Monthly average borehole temperatures between September 2005 and August 2006 at BH04-01 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (above the dashed horizontal line depicting the location of the winter ice surface), (b) englacial and basal thermistors (the dashed lines joining points near the bed indicate thermistors in the adjacent BH05-16) and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

The South site (BH04-06)

August 2004 to February 2005

Figure 4.15 (a), (b), and (c) depict glacier ice temperatures throughout the entire depth of ice and the overlying snow pack, the lower 30 m of the glacier and the near-surface ice and snow pack respectively during August 2004 to February 2005. Over the entire ice depth (Figure 4.15 a) it is evident that similar to BH04-01 the coldest temperatures occurred in a thin layer near the ice surface, with snow temperatures considerably colder than near-surface ice temperatures, contrary to the North site all isotherms were considerably below melting point to a depth of ~20 m below the ice surface, indicating the existence of cold ice near the glacier surface. Below 25 m above the glacier bed all temperatures plot to the right of the melting point suggesting thermistors in the borehole were recording either air or water temperatures. The positive temperatures recorded in the bottom half of the ice depth were clearly visible in Figure 4.15 (b), at the glacier bed, temperatures as high as 0.85 °C were recorded in August 2004, in following months the temperature at the ice bedrock interface successively cooled to a minimum of ~ 0.25 °C. This trend of cooling may have represented the recovery to undisturbed temperatures following the drilling of the hole in April 2004, delayed by the onset of the main melt period soon after drilling, on the other hand, the warm temperatures may have reflected some form of basal heat supply in the vicinity of the bottom of BH04-06. Figure 4.15 (c) indicated near-surface ice warming continued into October and initial winter cooling was initiated from the surface in November, proceeding through to February. Cold ice was visible to a depth of at least 12 m below the ice surface, this could not be classed as temperate as it did not reach melting point at any point during the 7 month period.

August 2005 to July 2006

The only complete 12 month ice temperature profile series, recorded between August 2005 and July 2006 in BH04-06 are presented in Figure 4.16 (a), (b) and (c) depicting temperature profiles for the full snow pack and glacier ice depth, the lower 30 m of the ice thickness and the near-surface layers respectively. Temperature profiles in the 2005 / 06 balance year (Figure 4.16 a) showed almost identical trends to those in the previous year (Figure 4.15 a) with cold ice near the surface not warming to melting point during any month of the year and positive borehole temperatures in the lower most 25 m of the ice. Temperatures at the glacier bed fluctuated between ~ 0.5 and 1.0 °C following no real trends between August and September, between January and April. There was a sequential warming and a large jump to values of ~ 1.5 °C in May, June and July at the time of a large heat supply event of basal origin (see Figure 4.10), the temperature gradient at this time indicated the direction of heat flow was away from the bed up

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

the borehole, supporting the connotation of a basal origin for the disturbance. Near the ice surface in Figure 4.16 (c) August and September temperatures were observed to be at approximately melting point at the surface but cooled to $\sim -1^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a depth of 5 m below the surface. October saw the first winter cooling of the near-surface ice, which accelerated into November. In April snow pack warming was evident with a reversal of temperature gradient, however, only a minimal influence on the ice surface was observed. As May and June progressed snow pack temperatures increased rapidly, though cold snow was still present in contact with the ice surface and ice temperatures near the surface were still as cold as -3°C . By July the ice temperature at the surface had reached 0°C as surface ablation occurred. A positive temperature gradient existed to ~ 5 m below the surface driving downward warming. At no point in the year did temperatures exceed -0.5°C in all but the uppermost near-surface ice indicating the existence of an upper cap of cold ice at the South site in the vicinity of BH04-06.

August 2006 to February 2007

Temperature profiles in BH04-06 between August 2006 and February 2007 (Figure 4.17 a, b and c) depict almost identical trends to those observed in previous years in BH04-06 with cold ice near the glacier surface just below a thin surface layer at melting point in summer (Figure 4.17 a and c) and positive temperatures between 0.5 and 1.0°C in the borehole at the glacier bed (Figure 4.17 b).

Figure 4.15: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2004 and February 2005 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (above the dashed horizontal line depicting the location of the winter ice surface), (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

Figure 4.16: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2005 and August 2006 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth including the snow pack (above the dashed horizontal line depicting the location of the winter ice surface), (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice and snow pack thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

Figure 4.17: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2006 and February 2007 at BH04-06 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

The Central site BH05-07

August 2005 to February 2006

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

Figure 4.18 (a), (b), and (c) depict glacier ice temperatures throughout the ice and snow pack, the lower 45 m of the glacier and the near-surface ice and snow pack respectively during the period August 2005 to February 2006. Figure 4.18 (a) indicates that the coldest temperatures were in the snow pack, the coldest ice temperatures occurred at the ice surface, following dramatic cooling during the winter. Surface ice temperatures warmed back to melting point in the following summer and deeper in the ice, no temperatures above 0 °C were observed with temperatures below melting point at the glacier bed. Below ~ 38 m above the glacier bed (Figure 4.18 b) borehole temperatures appear colder than melting point. At the glacier bed the warmest temperature of ~ - 0.15 °C occurred in August 2005 at the time of drilling, over the following 6 months, temperatures at the bed were observed to fall (probably as a consequence of post drilling cooling recovering back to equilibrium temperatures), reaching a minima of ~ -0.33 °C in December and January. Near the glacier surface (Figure 4.18 c) temperatures close to melting point were observed at most depths in August and September (despite some slightly below melting point temperatures), slight cooling, originating at the ice surface began in October and became more rapid in November, sequential cooling at greater depth below the surface occurred as the winter progressed, reaching a minimum in February.

August 2006 to January 2007

The general pattern of temperature change observed in Figure 4.18 was repeated the following year in Figure 4.19, between August 2006 and January 2007. Near-surface ice temperatures were again observed to decrease from melting point in the autumn, propagating from the surface downwards with initiation of cooling in October, becoming more rapid in November. An ice surface temperature rise was observed between November and December (probably as a consequence of snowfall beginning to insulate the ice surface) (Figure 4.19 c). The below melting point temperature at 95 m above the bed (Figure 4.19 c) was possibly erroneously low, while between ~ 94 and 87 m above the bed a small depth of ice appeared not to reach melting point during the summer, possibly indicating the existence of a small cold ice wedge encapsulated within the temperate ice. At depth in the ice (Figure 4.19 b) below 45 m above the bed, all temperatures were below melting point, suggesting the presence of cold ice towards the bed. At the bed the temperatures had warmed ~ 0.15 °C from the previous year (Figure 4.18 b), however, they remained below melting point and further cooling had occurred at a height of ~ 17 m above the bed by ~ 0.2 °C from the previous year, with a minima of ~ -0.4 °C occurring in December 2006. The nature of the cooling experienced at ~ 17 m above the bed indicated temperatures remained stable over the autumn (August, September and October) at just below -0.3 °C and then further cooling occurred during winter.

Figure 4.18: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2005 and February 2006 at BH05-07 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface snow and ice thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots). The August 2005 thermistor time series (see Fig 4.7) depicted borehole cooling following drilling. The cooling trend was not addressed during the process of transient effect

removal. It was thus necessary to replace the physically impossible (positive) near-surface ice temperatures (which occurred when water temperatures were logged) with melting point temperatures in the ice temperature profile plots.

Figure 4.19: Monthly average borehole temperatures between August 2006 and January 2007 at BH05-07 for (a) the entire glacier depth, (b) englacial and basal thermistors and (c) near-surface ice thermistors (melting point is depicted in red in all plots).

Crevasse thermistor string

Temperature profiles for the 6 m nearest the ice surface in a crevasse at the Central site separated from BH05-07 by only 1.75 m of ice are presented in Figure 4.20 (a) and (b) representing the period August 2005 to February 2006 and August 2006 to January 2007 respectively. At all times the general trend over the 6 m was for warmer temperatures near the ice surface and colder temperatures at depth. Monthly average temperatures in both years and at all depths fluctuated in the limited range of -3 to 3 °C. Temperatures at a depth of 6 m below the surface were negative during all periods of data collection, reflecting ponding of higher density cold air at depth within the crevasse. Near the surface positive monthly average temperatures were observed in August, September and October, reflecting atmospheric air temperatures when the crevasse was not snow bridged and open to the atmosphere, once bridging occurred monthly average temperatures dropped to ~ -1°C in the 2005 / 06 winter and to ~ 0 °C in the 2006 / 07 winter.

Comparisons between the crevasse temperature at each depth below the surface and the temperatures at the corresponding height in the adjacent BH05-07 (Figures 4.18 and 4.19) allowed determination of the horizontal direction of temperature gradient within the ice in the vicinity of the crevasse and whether or not the crevasse was acting as a heat source warming the ice in the vicinity of BH05-07 or whether it was acting as a heat sink and cooling the ice (Section 5.6). At 1 m below the surface in the 2005 / 06 period the crevasse was ~ 3 °C warmer in August, decreasing to ~ 1.2 °C warmer in February, thus the crevasse acted as a heat source for the duration of the data collection period. Over the same time period a year later the crevasse was once again a heat source, being ~ 3 °C warmer in August, decreasing to ~ 2 °C warmer in January and at a maximum of 3.6 °C warmer in November. At 2 m below the ice surface a similar pattern was observed in both years with the crevasse acting as a heat source to the surrounding ice in all months, at 3 m below the ice surface the crevasse was a weak heat sink. At depths below 4 m, crevasse temperatures were consistently below those of the adjacent ice, thus the crevasse acted as a heat sink deeper below the ice surface. At 6 m depth the air temperatures in the crevasse were colder than the adjacent ice temperatures by ~ 2.5 °C in the 2005 / 06 period and ~ 2.0 °C in the 2006 / 07 period, accordingly the crevasse was a heat sink with energy being transferred out of the warmer ice to raise air temperatures in the crevasse.

Figure 4.20: Monthly average crevasse temperature profiles between (a) August 2005 and February 2006 and (b) August 2006 and January 2007. Sensor heights do not remain constant, decreasing in distance above the bed over time due to surface ablation as the thermistor string was supported below a length of Dexian bridging the crevasse at the glacier surface.

Seasonal ice temperature profile variation

Bi-monthly average near surface ice temperature profiles are presented in Figures 4.21 and 4.22 detailing the near-surface ice cooling as the winter developed and the penetration of the winter cold wave in the 2004 / 05 and the 2005 / 06 winters respectively. The depth of penetration of the winter cold wave was determined to be the depth at which the fluctuation between the isotherms for different bi-monthly periods was eliminated to within the ± 0.04 °C error in the temperature measurements. In BH04-01 during the 2004 / 05 winter (Figure 4.21 a) cooling from near melting point temperatures at the surface occurred from November onwards when temperatures at the surface initially dropped to -1.25 °C during the period 1 – 15th November and continued to do so until a minima of -3.92 °C was reached at the end of December. Below the ice surface sequentially lower thermistors experienced successive cooling, at 8 m below the ice surface for example temperatures dropped by 0.09 °C every two weeks during the cooling

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

period until the end of April when elimination of the winter cooling began. The depth of penetration of the winter cold wave in BH04-01 in the 2004 / 05 winter was 13.24 m below the ice surface. In BH04-06 during the same period (Figure 4.21 b), winter cooling from near-surface melting point temperatures again first occurred in November, temperatures at the ice surface fell from - 0.56 to - 3.16 °C over a 2 week period in November, reaching a minima of - 4.06 °C at the ice surface at the end of December. Sequential cooling with depth was again observed and at the time of cessation of data collection in February 2005 the depth of penetration of the winter cold wave had reached 9.96 m below the ice surface (it is assumed that this depth would have increased further as the remainder of the winter cooling occurred).

During the 2005 / 06 winter cooling period BH04-01 (Figure 4.22 a) displayed almost identical cooling characteristics to the previous winter, with near surface cooling being initiated from melting point temperatures in November with temperatures at the surface dropping from -0.40 to - 2.12 °C over a two week period in November. The surface ice temperature winter minimum occurred in February at a temperature of - 3.45 °C, while sequential cooling at depth progressed throughout the winter as in the previous year, though at the slightly higher rate of a ~ 0.12 °C temperature drop over each 2 week period at a depth of 7 m below the ice surface. The depth of penetration of the winter cold wave in BH04-01 in the 2005 / 06 winter was 15.11 m below the ice surface. Winter cooling in BH04-06 (Figure 4.22 b) was somewhat more complex in the 2005 / 06 winter than the year before. During early August ice temperatures at - 6.48 m below the ice surface were -1.17 °C, while the surface was at melting point, over the following period until the end of November ice at this depth continued to warm in response to surface derived heating, reaching a “cold ice” maximum temperature of - 0.83 °C. The ice surface on the other hand began to cool at the beginning of October, falling to a temperature of - 1.87 °C, temperatures subsequently warmed back to - 0.66 °C 2 weeks later before cooling continued following the beginning of November, continuing to an ice surface temperature minima of - 4.55 °C at the end of November. The depth of penetration of the winter cold wave at BH04-06 in the 2005 / 06 winter was 12.68 m below the ice surface. BH05-07 (Figure 4.22 c) experienced cooling from near melting point temperatures beginning at the start of October, undergoing slight re-warming in the second half of October (as observed in BH04-06) before rapid cooling occurred in November, to a near-surface ice minima of - 2.96 °C at the end of November. At the time of cessation of data collection in February 2006 the depth of penetration of the winter cold wave had reached 10.55 m below the ice surface (it is assumed that this depth would have increased further as the remainder of the winter cooling occurred).

Figure 4.21: Penetration of the 2004 / 05 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the winter cooling period at (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06) (days of year over which averages were taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

Figure 4.22: Penetration of the 2005 / 06 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the winter cooling period at (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06) (days of year over which averages were taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

Figure 4.22 continued: Penetration of the 2005 / 06 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the winter cooling period at (c) the Central site (BH05-07) (days of year over which averages were taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

Elimination of winter cold wave

Figures 4.23 and 4.24 (a) and (b) detail winter cold wave elimination in the near-surface ice in BH04-01 in the spring and summer of 2005 and in BH04-01 and BH04-06 in the spring and summer of 2006 respectively. Elimination of the cold wave in BH04-01 in 2005 (Figure 4.23) was driven by surface warming, in early May ice surface temperatures rose from winter minima to $-0.52\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a positive temperature gradient was established to the colder ice beneath (at a temperature of $-1.29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a depth of $\sim 2.5\text{ m}$), continued rapid near-surface warming in the second half of May resulted in a surface ice temperature of $-0.21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a temperature of $-0.92\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $\sim 2.5\text{ m}$. Unfortunately no record of the nature of the warming during June is available due to data logger malfunction. By the beginning of July the curved shape of the temperature profile was considerably reduced with a minima of $-0.14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $\sim 3.5\text{ m}$ below the ice surface, further warming occurred to $-0.08\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ by the beginning of August. Cold wave elimination in BH04-01 in 2006 (Figure 4.24 a) was slightly less well recorded than in 2005, no data was recovered for the period between the end May and the third week of August due to data logger problems, though it can be seen that near-surface ice warming again began at the beginning of May when the surface temperature reached $-2.95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and continued to $-2.66\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

the second half of May, driving elimination of the cold wave, which had to all intents and purposed occurred by the time of data acquisition resumption in the second half of August. In BH04-06 (Figure 4.24 b) warming from the surface ice minimum of - 4.01 °C at the end of April began initially in the second half of April, gradually warming to - 2.94 °C in the second half of June from which a large jump to melting point at the surface occurred over a 2 week period. Ice temperatures below the surface were somewhat slower to respond, continuing to warm at depths of ~ 4 and ~ 8 m depth until reaching “cold ice” negative temperature maxima of - 0.77 and -1.04 °C at the end of October, from which point the following winter’s cooling began.

Figure 4.23: Elimination of the 2004 / 05 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the spring warming period at the North site (BH04-01) (days of year over which averages were taken are indicated in brackets on the legend).

Figure 4.24: Elimination of the 2005 / 06 winter cold wave: bi-monthly average near-surface ice temperature profiles during the spring warming period at (a) the North site (BH04-01) and (b) the South site (BH04-06) (days of year over which averages were taken are indicated in brackets on the legends).

Summary

- The North site (BH04-01) contained temperate ice near the surface, reaching melting point at all depths in the near surface zone by the end of the ablation season. At depth near the bed there appears to be some form of basal heat source warming the thermistor in the bottom of BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01).
- Cold ice temperatures were recorded near the ice surface (below a thin layer at the surface which seasonally reaches melting point) at the South site in BH04-06.
- Similar to BH04-01, energy appears to be been added periodically to the base of BH04-06 causing a warming of borehole temperatures to positive values.
- Ice near the surface at the Central site (BH05-07) in general reached melting point by the end of the ablation season. However, at the end of the 2006 ablation period a wedge of cold ice existed between 87 and 95 m above the glacier bed.
- Cold ice appeared to exist at the bottom of BH05-07 below 45 m above the bed.
- The crevasse at the Central site, adjacent to BH05-07 acted as a heat source to the surrounding ice from the surface to a depth of 3 m and a heat sink from 3 to 6 m below the surface.
- The winter cold wave penetrated to a depth of 13.24 m and 15.11 m in BH04-01 in the winters of 2004 / 05 and 2005 / 06 respectively and to a depth of 12.68 m in BH40-06 in the 2005 / 06 winter (at all other times and in other boreholes incomplete data sets prevented full determination of the complete depth of cold wave penetration).

4.1.3 Ice core density

To construct a glacier ice density profile from the surface to the bed, density measurements were made on sections of two ice cores (T96-5 and T97-1) recovered from an along flow parallel transect on Glacier de Tsanfleuron in 1996 and 1997, detailed in Tison and Hubbard (2000). The two cores were combined as outlined in Figure 4.25 following the detailed core stratigraphical observations suggested by Tison and Hubbard (2000) to generate a single core profile, from which a density profile through the various ice facies has been generated. Combination of the cores was based on a suggested overlap between the bottom 15 m of core 97-1 and the upper

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

35 m of core 96-5 (Tison and Hubbard, 2000), for further details of core stratigraphy see Hubbard *et al.*, (2000a) and Tison and Hubbard (2000).

Figure 4.25: Schematic representation of how the longest two Tsanfleuron cores, core 97-1 recovered from the accumulation area near the present location of BH04-01 and core 96-5 recovered from the glacier snout can be combined to provide a core sequence from the glacier surface to the bed, for use in laboratory characterisation of ice density.

It is noted that any derived density profile based on the recovered ice cores, is not from the same location as the thermistor string deployments (though BH04-01 was drilled at a location very close to where core 97-1 was recovered from). However, it is assumed that a characterisation of the Tsanfleuron ice density is more accurate for the purpose of modelling and determination of thermal properties, than simply accepting an assumed density profile determined from published glacier ice density values. Ice density measurements from the 96-5 and 97-1 cores are presented in Figure 4.26. Measurements in the upper 8 to 10 m of 97-1 reflect the presence of firn at the top of the core, below 10 m in core 97-1 and throughout core 96-5 density values are relatively uniform with depth. The average ice density for cores 96 – 5 and 97 -1 (below the influence of the firn in 97-1) is 894 kg m^{-3} for both cores throughout the profile. Laboratory determined

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

density measurements made from the Tsanfleuron ice cores agree closely with published values of firn to glacier ice transition density of 830 kg m^{-3} and glacier ice density of 917 kg m^{-3} Paterson (1994).

Figure 4.26: Ice density profiles for (a) core 97-1 and (b) 96-5, the red line indicates the average density determined for Tsanfleuron ice of 894 kg m^{-3} , the dashed black line depicts published glacier ice density of 917 kg m^{-3} (Paterson, 1994). The horizontal error bars were derived using the standard deviations of multiple measurements of core diameter and length at each depth (as outlined in Section 2.4).

4.1.4 Repeat borehole inclinometry

Repeat borehole inclinometry of borehole BH05-12 (in the vicinity of BH04-06 at the South site) allowed determination of borehole deformation between August 2005 and August 2006. From the derivative of this borehole deformation, ice strain rate variation with distance above the bed has been calculated in an across glacier and a down glacier direction (Figure 4.27), for use in determination of deformation induced strain heating (Section 7.6). The down glacier strain rate (Figure 4.27) shows the values nearest the bed at 0.15 yr^{-1} decreasing in amplitude with distance above the bed to a minimum of 0 yr^{-1} at the ice surface. Calculated strain rates in an across

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

glacier direction are negative below 30 m above the bed and positive above 30 m, and are (with only slight exception near the bed) all less than 0.05 yr^{-1} . Comparisons between the two profiles suggests borehole deformation was greatest near the glacier bed and deformed to a smaller extent in the across glacier than the down glacier direction.

Figure 4.27: Borehole deformation induced strain rate variation with height above the glacier bed in (a) a down glacier and (b) an across glacier direction derived from repeat inclinometry at the South site, near the location of BH04-06 (Data courtesy of D. Chandler).

4.2 Subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity (to aid interpretation of temperature data)

4.2.1 Water pressure time series

Water pressure time series from transducers deployed in BH05-13 (~ 50 m down glacier of the Central site), BH05-07 and BH05-12 are presented in Figures 4.28 (a), 4.28 (b) and 4.29 respectively. Two types of water pressure sensor were deployed, self logging TRAFAG sensors in BH05-13 and BH05-17 (adjacent to BH04-01) and Honeywell 24PCG data logger controlled sensors in BH05-07 and BH05-12 (adjacent to BH04-06). No data was recovered from BH05-17 as the self logging sensor could not be recovered from the borehole on re-drilling (the same problems which prevented presentation of repeat inclinometry in the vicinity of BH04-01).

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

Water pressure in BH05-13 (Figure 4.28 a) shows a rapid increase from ~ 0.7 m to ~ 33.5 m (and an equally rapid decrease back to ~ 0.7 m) during August 2005 (probably in response to readjustment of the drainage system and connection to the borehole following drilling), following which a gradual increasing trend was observed over the autumn and winter to a pressure of 6.41 m in April at which time a sharp decrease to 1.7 m occurred. Following the April water pressure fall, values remained relatively stable increasing slightly to a value of 2.05 m in June, from which a steady pressure increase was instigated, peaking at 32.25 m in August 2006 just prior to sensor recovery and download.

Water pressure fluctuations at the Central site in BH05-07 (Figure 4.28 b) (~ 50 m up glacier from BH05-13) showed totally different trends to BH05-13, reflecting different hydrological connections. Between February and July 2006 missing data were attributed to the data logger problems outlined earlier for thermistors in BH05-07. Following deployment in August 2005 water pressure initially rose to ~ 2.0 m over a period of ~ 2 weeks and remained relatively stable at ~ 2.0 m until mid November when pressure increased dramatically from 1.71 to 14.09 m over a period of approximately 1 month (coinciding with the period of rapid near-surface ice cooling as winter air temperatures drop (see Figures 4.7 and 3.1). Rapid pressure increases in late autumn and early winter have been reported elsewhere under temperate glaciers and are archetypal of subglacial drainage system winter close down phenomena, under which, surface melt water inputs to the subglacial system cease, large drainage channels are no longer able to remain open and over the winter distributed, high pressure drainage establishes itself (Hubbard and Nienow, 1997). During January 2006 pressure dropped from ~ 10.1 m to ~ 5.4 m but recovered quickly just prior to the period of missing data. At the time of data logger repair in early August 2006 pressure values were close to 0 m. An increase to ~ 5.8 m was observed to occur through August, the autumn and early winter did not show the rapid water pressure increase to high values observed in the previous year, but showed fluctuation between ~ 5.8 and 1.0 m, decreasing to 0 m at the end of January 2007.

Figure 4.28: Water pressure time series in (a) BH05-13 (~ 50 m down glacier from BH05-07) and (b) at the Central site (BH05-07) from August 2005 to August 2006 and January 2007 respectively, adjusted for atmospheric pressure and sensor location in the boreholes.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

The water pressure time series recorded at the South site in BH05-12 (Figure 4.29), adjacent to BH04-06 is represented at a cruder resolution to that in Figure 4.28 (b) despite being recorded by an identical sensor, logged using the same data logger commands, a fact attributed to data logger malfunction. Figure 4.29 shows high water pressures from the time of first data acquisition on October 2005, through the winter increasing to overburden pressure of 56.9 m in August 2006, suggesting that BH05-12 was probably isolated from the subglacial drainage system in the vicinity of BH04-06.

Figure 4.29: Water pressure time series at the South site in BH05-12 (adjacent to BH04-06) from October 2005 to July 2006, adjusted for atmospheric pressure and sensor location in the borehole.

4.2.2 Electrical conductivity time series

Electrical conductivity (EC) time series recorded in BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01), BH05-10 (adjacent to BH04-06) and BH05-07 are presented in Figures 4.30 (a), 4.30 (b) and 4.31 respectively. In BH05-16 (Figure 4.30 a) EC rose quickly over a period of ~ 2 weeks from an initial value of $49 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ at the time of first data collection in September 2005 to a stable value of $\sim 61 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ which predominated for the remainder of the time series with small fluctuations thereabouts, suggesting the sensor to be in contact with isolated waters of subglacial origin. Missing data between May and August 2006 was attributed to data logger problems as explained

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS II

above for the thermistor time series. Time series of EC recorded in BH05-10 (Figure 4.30 b) showed an increase of ~ 15 and $20 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ at heights of 16 and 6 m above the bed during October 2005, peaking in early November at 29.2 and $73.1 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ respectively, followed by a rapid decrease in mid November, corresponding with the timing of the water pressure increase observed in BH05-07 (Figure 4.29b). EC values over winter were stable in the range 6.5 to $8 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ at both heights above the bed until they dropped further during May and June just prior to an incompletely documented disturbance in June and July, recorded by the EC sensor at 6 m above the bed (but unfortunately not at 16 m above the bed due to missing data). The disturbance in June 2006 saw EC at the bed rise to at least $25.63 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ at the same time as a large thermal disturbance was observed in the temperature time series (see Figure 4.10), following the disturbance EC levels decreased back to low stable values in the range 3 to $6 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$.

EC time series in BH05-07 (Figure 4.31) show initially low values of $\sim 9.8 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ at the time of instrumentation (likely representative of low conductivity drilling waters), in early September a sharp jump to EC values of the order of $80 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ was observed, a value which was maintained with only small fluctuation until a break in the data collection occurred between February and August 2006. After data logger overhaul in early August high EC values again of the order of $80 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ were recorded but with larger fluctuations of up to $107 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ until the end of September, following which fluctuation was dramatically reduced.

Figure 4.30: Electrical conductivity time series in (a) BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01) at the North site from September 2005 to September 2006 and (b) BH05-10 (adjacent to BH04-06) at the South site from October 2005 to January 2007.

Summary

- BH05-07 appeared to have connected to the subglacial drainage system.
- Water pressure in BH05-07 showed rapid increase during late autumn 2005 to higher pressures archetypal of winter close down of the subglacial drainage system.

Figure 4.31: Electrical conductivity time series at the Central site in BH05-07 from August 2005 to January 2007.

- Water pressure records from BH05-12 depicting high values with little seasonal variation suggested BH05-12 was not connected to the subglacial drainage system in the vicinity of BH04-06.
- No water pressure records exist for the North site as the self logging pressure sensor could not be recovered from the glacier bed.
- BH05-16 and BH05-07 EC time series were stable following adjustment after deployment, displaying EC values indicative of waters of subglacial origin.
- EC time series from BH05-10 provided additional evidence for winter close down of the subglacial drainage system in late autumn and a propagation of waters of a basal origin with a higher dissolved solute content up partly open boreholes in June 2006 at the South site.

Chapter 5

Interpretation I: Meteorology, snow pack and near-surface ice temperatures.

5.1 Introduction

Glacier surface meteorology directly controls the energy exchange between the snow pack and the surface ice, through the glacier surface energy balance and meteorological influence over the glacier surface morphology. Measurement of every component of the surface energy balance was not possible. However, modelling reconstructions based on the meteorological observations made at Tsanfleuron have allowed determination of the surface energy balance (see Section 7.4, where a full characterisation of the glacier surface energy flux is presented). For much of the year the snow pack mediates energy transfer between the glacier and the atmosphere via processes and physical properties allied to, but distinctly different from, those of the underlying glacier ice upon which it lies. The near-surface glacier ice constitutes a thermally active layer, displaying temperature change in response to energy addition and loss, at a range of time scales, dominated by the annual temperature cycle.

This chapter outlines a discussion of the meteorology and surface energy balance of Tsanfleuron (Section 5.2), snow pack and near-surface ice temperatures (Sections 5.3 and 5.4 respectively), a discussion of the influence of the snow cover over the near-surface ice temperatures (Section 5.5), discussion of the influence of fractures and crevasses over ice temperatures (Section 5.6) and comments on the observed differential surface ablation at similar altitudes across the glacier (Section 5.7).

5.2 Meteorology and surface energy balance

The balance of energy fluxes to and from the glacier surface is dominated by the seasonal radiation cycle, superimposed upon which are diurnal cycles and other short term fluctuations (often of the duration of a few days) resulting from synoptic meteorological conditions. Meteorology directly influences energy exchange between the glacier surface and the lower atmosphere in terms of alteration of the radiation budget under overcast and clear sky conditions. Surface albedo changes result from fresh snowfall, while temperature, humidity and wind speed fluctuations influence the turbulent sensible and latent heat exchange.

5.2.1 Meteorology

Air temperature

Air temperature influences conductive heat transfer to and from the glacier surface, the LW↓ from the atmosphere, and the sensible heat exchange between the glacier surface and the atmosphere. Over the period of data collection, Tsanfleuron air temperatures fluctuated between 15.2 and - 25.8 °C with a mean of -2.2 °C. The annual air temperature cycle was sinusoidal in form (Figure 3.1 a), as a consequence of the annual cycle of SW↓, which warmed the atmosphere. Monthly mean air temperatures (Figure 3.5 a) were positive between June and September, close to 0 °C in May and October marking the transition between summer and winter and were negative during winter months of November to April. Differences between air temperatures and glacier surface temperatures initiated energy flows within the snow and near-surface ice at both seasonal and diurnal scales. Transfer of heat to or from the glacier via conduction and radiation reduced this temperature difference. Positive summer air temperatures promoted warming and ablation of the snow pack and near-surface ice, while negative winter temperatures resulted in snow pack cooling when air temperatures were colder than snow surface temperatures and warming when the air temperatures were warmer than those of the snow surface. Monthly mean air temperature peaks in June and July in both 2005 and 2006 (Figure 3.5 a), corresponded to the time of maximum snow melt (Figure 3.15 a and b), reflecting a warming of the atmospheric boundary layer, reversing the over winter temperature gradient at the glacier surface and energy supply, driving snow pack ablation and near-surface ice warming. The air temperature minima experienced in December, January and February were a consequence of shorter daylight hours and the associated winter reduction in SW↓ in conjunction with synoptic weather systems often dominated by continental air masses, with high pressure. This situation caused cold, cloud free atmospheric conditions, resulting in rapid cooling of the surface boundary layer and consequent energy loss from the glacier surface via LW↑ emission.

At the diurnal scale the amplitude of air temperature fluctuations were slightly greater in winter than in summer. During summer, nocturnal air temperatures often dropped below 0 °C driving refreezing over the ablating glacier ice surface and cooling of a thin layer of near-surface ice, forming surface crusts over slush zones, ice layers over water pools and rime. As a consequence a proportion of the energy from the following morning SW↓ and conduction from rising air temperatures was required to melt the nocturnally formed crusts and ice layers and to warm near-surface ice before ablation could continue. Positive daytime air temperatures on the other hand tended not to cause much melt in winter as snow surface temperatures were usually considerably below 0 °C. During spring however, positive day time air temperatures were responsible for melt

generation at the snow surface as the snow pack began to become isothermal from the surface downwards.

Relative humidity

Relative humidities at Tsanfleuron ranged between 4 and 100 % with a mean of 73 %. Summer months saw the highest relative humidities, with daily mean values rarely dropping below 50 % (Figure 3.1 b). The lowest values were recorded during winter months, during cold cloud free periods characteristic of the dominant blocking anti-cyclones which sit over continental Europe during winter months. The trend of higher relative humidity in summer than winter was closely related to the availability of liquid water at the glacier surface. As relative humidity is the ratio of the amount of water vapour in the air to the maximum amount of vapour that would be present if the air were saturated, lower winter values do not represent the lower water carrying capacity of colder air, but a lower availability of liquid water due to the frozen glacier surface and dramatically reduced sublimation and evaporation rates relative to summer values.

In the absence of continuous observations of cloud cover, relative humidity provided an insight into the synoptic weather conditions, especially in winter where lower net radiation values and increasing snow depth often coincided closely with periods of high relative humidity and less negative nocturnal temperatures, suggesting overcast sky conditions with snow fall. Low winter relative humidities tended to coincide with relatively high daytime net radiation values and low nocturnal air temperatures, while snow depth remained stable, suggesting clear skies resulting in high nocturnal heat loss in the absence of insulating cloud cover and loss of water vapour in the air during winter via rime ice formation. In summer saturated low pressure air masses tended to dominate the synoptic weather patterns, humidities remained high even during warm clear sky conditions as a result of the abundance of liquid water available at the melting glacier surface and the high evaporation and sublimation rates. The highest summer relative humidity values (up to 100 %) tended to occur during conditions of increased air temperatures and positive net radiation, which gave rise to high evaporation and sublimation rates supplying water to the atmosphere triggering early afternoon thunderstorms which were common at Tsanfleuron. The abundance of liquid water at the glacier surface as a consequence of summer surface melting led to the development of relative humidity gradients between the glacier surface and the atmosphere which drove turbulent latent heat transfer.

Wind speed and direction

Wind speed time series (Figure 3.2 a) showed no cyclicity (though many of the days with higher average wind speeds tended to occur during winter months), the peaky nature of the time series likely reflected the passage of weather systems. Wind speed controlled snow redistribution and wind crust formation at the snow surface, higher wind speeds led to greater redistribution of blowing snow and harder crust formation (which often developed into impermeable layers within the snow pack stratigraphy). In addition wind speed (specifically differences in wind speed between the glacier surface and that higher above the surface) drove turbulent heat and moisture exchange between the glacier surface and the atmosphere. Under conditions of higher wind speed, turbulent mixing near the surface would have increased resulting in greater turbulent heat exchange between the glacier surface and the atmosphere.

The wind direction at ~ 3 m above the surface was predominantly from the West (Figure 3.3), the direction of prevailing wind in this region of the Swiss Alps. However, the dominant Westerly and West South Westerly winds also reflect “glacier or katabatic” winds, a common phenomena on temperate glaciers driven by surface melting causing turbulent cooling of the boundary layer air directly above the surface, which consequently becomes more dense and flows down glacier under the influence of gravity (Martin, 1975). Under such conditions, low level forcing combined with turbulent exchange often resulted in a characteristic wind speed maxima close to the surface (Denby and Greuell, 2000). Katabatic glacier winds thus exert a strong influence over the surface energy balance and glacier melt energetics as they reportedly regulate the turbulent fluxes to and from the glacier surface and are regarded as the dominant forcing for turbulent heat exchange on temperate glaciers (such as Tsanfleuron) (Denby and Smeets, 2000). Obleitner (1994) showed glacier wind dominated wind patterns over melting glaciers, while Oerlemans, (unpublished) suggested katabatic flows were observed to be relatively undisturbed by the large scale synoptic wind flows over other glaciers in the Swiss Alps e.g. Morteratschgletscher. Analysis of the direction of wind flow over Tsanfleuron suggests wind from the direction possibly influenced by katabatic flow dominated for 54.5 % of the study period, clearly visible in Figure 5.1 where clustering of data points between 225 and 315 ° follow the direction of glacier flow and maximum slope. In addition to influencing the turbulent exchange, katabatic flows on Tsanfleuron would have influenced the meteorology of the study sites as air moving over the glacier surface, would have been influenced by the properties of the glacier surface. Thus, the wind experienced at the meteorological station and the three borehole sites would have had its properties influenced by processes occurring at higher altitudes up glacier. For example the transport of colder air originating at higher elevation to the study sites.

Additionally, following the same argument, the volume of snow available for wind redistribution down glacier from the accumulation area to the ablation area was limited by the cliffs to the West of the glacier below Sex Rouge and the ice divide to Glacier de Prapio (Figure 2.1)

Figure 5.1: Plot of wind speed against wind direction for the 30 minute averages recorded over the two year period of data collection at Tsanfleuron

Net radiation

Net radiation was the dominant energy flux at the glacier surface on Tsanfleuron displaying a clear annual cycle, with a positive maximum (into the glacier) in summer and a negative minimum in winter (Figure 3.2 b). Of the four components of net radiation flux the annual cycle in $SW\downarrow$ dominated energy transfer to the glacier surface. By day in summer $SW\downarrow$ radiation peaks of $\sim 800 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ resulted in the warming and ablation of the snow pack and near-surface ice. When averaged over daily and monthly timescales the influence of $SW\downarrow$ relative to the other radiation fluxes was drastically reduced due to the lack of $SW\downarrow$ overnight. During daylight hours the effect of $SW\downarrow$ was to provide considerable energy to the glacier surface (Figure 3.14). $SW\uparrow$ radiation was controlled by the glacier surface albedo: under snow cover $SW\uparrow$ closely tracked $SW\downarrow$ at a slightly lower level. However, once glacier ice was exposed, surface albedo fell significantly and $SW\uparrow$ decreased correspondingly (Figure 7.10) with the effect of significantly reducing energy loss from the glacier surface. $LW\downarrow$ tended to be higher in summer than winter in

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

response to the temperature of the atmosphere and the higher total water vapour content of the air in summer, while LW \uparrow remained the most stable radiation flux.

It is to be noted that the interception of solar radiation by surrounding mountains casting shadows over alpine glaciers can exert a large control over the glacier net radiation balance. However, this was not the case over Tsanfleuron as there exist no significant topographic features to the East and South (Figure 2.1) with only limited shading occurring from the West when the sun was low in the sky (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2: Hemispherical photograph captured using a 180 ° “fish eye” lens indicating sky view as seen by radiometers at the meteorological station deployed on Tsanfleuron in August 2006 (Note: North is at the top of the image and because the photo was taken looking upwards, West is on the right-hand side of the image) (Photograph: N. Rutter).

Maximum net radiation values of $\sim 800 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (Figure 3.5 d) occurred during the early afternoon in late July and August in both 2005 and 2006. However, the monthly average values were considerably lower at $\sim 30 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ reflecting much lower fluxes in the early morning and late afternoon and negative overnight values. During the summer months (May to September) the average daily net radiation flux was positive, providing energy at the surface to warm the snow pack, ablate snow, warm the near-surface ice and ablate ice, represented clearly by the rapid snow depth reduction (Figure 3.15 a and b). June displayed the second highest mean monthly net radiation (Figure 3.5 d), despite there still being a $\sim 2 \text{ m}$ snow pack to reflect SW \downarrow . High June

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

net radiation values were attributed to the decreased albedo as the snow pack surface aged and the annual maximum $SW\downarrow$ which occurred on the summer solstice during this month.

At the end of July 2006 the daily mean net radiation experienced a sharp decline (Figure 3.2. b) when a large summer snowfall occurred (Figure 3.15 a) and the glacier surface was covered in fresh snow to a depth of ~ 1 m. Gradually over the following few weeks the net radiation slowly increased as the snow pack aged, underwent densification and metamorphosis, degraded, a surface crust developed and gradually ablated. In contrast August 2005 exhibited very high net radiation (Figure 3.2 b) due to the low albedo of the dirty ice surface, reducing reflection and increasing radiation absorption causing maximum ice ablation at this time of year.

Net radiation fell from September onwards due to decreasing $SW\downarrow$ as summer ended and $LW\uparrow$ increased as the atmosphere cooled (Figure 3.1 a). Net radiation fell further following the first fresh snowfall of the winter in early November in 2005 which raised the surface albedo reflecting most of $SW\downarrow$ away from the surface, increasing the cooling effect on the near-surface ice under shallow snow conditions. The first light snowfalls in late autumn and early winter may thus have actually increased cooling of the glacier surface, contrary to the opinion that snow cover reduces energy loss via insulation. The first snowfalls of the 2006 winter were later than those in 2005 (Figure 3.15 a), a fact reflected by the higher near zero net radiation values in early winter of 2006 compared to $\sim -50 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ during the same period in 2005. The later snowfalls resulted in the dirty surface ice being exposed for longer, with a lower albedo causing greater absorption of $SW\downarrow$, raising the daily net radiation values (Figure 3.2 b).

Monthly net radiation minima (Figure 3.5 d) remained stable throughout most of the year, as daily minima occurred at night, when the radiation budget was dominated by $LW\uparrow$ and the SW radiation balance was negligible. The glacier surface temperature (and consequently the $LW\uparrow$) was limited to a maximum of $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ hence the $LW\uparrow$ was capped at 315.64 W m^{-2} , varying only slightly over the year as a consequence of nocturnal cooling if the glacier surface froze in summer and winter surface cooling.

Turbulent fluxes

Numerous problems were encountered in the measurement of turbulent and sensible heat fluxes over Tsanfleuron using eddy correlation methods, not least the fact that the CSAT3 sonic anemometers do not work during rainfall, a major problem, when deployed during the one of the wettest Augusts on record in 2005. In summer 2006 recorded sensible heat fluxes fluctuated

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

highly between 82 and - 126 W m⁻² (Figure 3.12 a), while latent heat fluxes also fluctuated between 390 and - 460 W m⁻² (Figure 3.13 a). Sensible heat fluxes were generally towards the glacier surface and notably lower than the net radiation flux (Figure 3.10) while latent heat fluxes were more varied in the direction of heat flow, but exhibited peak values comparable to those of net radiation. During January and February 2007 sensible heat fluxes and latent heat fluxes were more comparable in magnitude, varying between - 140 and 195 W m⁻² (Figure 3.12 b) and between - 90 and 170 W m⁻² (Figure 3.13 b) respectively and were often larger than the net radiation flux which fluctuated between -80 and 40 W m⁻² (Figure 3.11). Sensible heat fluxes tended in general to be towards the glacier surface, while latent heat fluxes tended to be away, indicating there were periods of the day when atmospheric temperatures were above those of the snow surface facilitating energy transfer to the surface and that the glacier surface was acting as a water vapour source even under the cold winter snow surface temperatures, presumably via sublimation. Sensible and latent fluxes were of similar magnitude in winter due to the reduced availability of water vapour at the ice surface and the lower water vapour carrying capacity of the colder air (carrying capacity increases exponentially with air temperature) reducing the vapour gradients between the glacier and the atmosphere. Thus, limiting the latent heat flux from reaching the high values experienced in summer under an almost unlimited water supply from the melting glacier surface. For details of turbulent and sensible heat fluxes over the full period of data collection see the modelling reconstructions in Section 7.4 and Figures 7.6 and 7.7.

Meteorological control over glacier surface morphology

In addition to determining energy transfer, driving temperature change at the glacier surface, meteorology directly influences glacier surface morphology (which in turn impacts supraglacial drainage and ice surface ablation (Section 5.7)). Meteorological impacts on glacier surface morphology included:

- High air temperatures driving snow and ice ablation (Section 5.7), lowering the glacier surface and generating melt water.
- Nocturnal cooling resulting in surface freezing, the formation of surface crusts and rime deposition.
- Snowfall burying both small scale and larger surface roughness elements, lowering surface roughness.
- Wind redistributing snow and forming wind crusts, lowering surface roughness.
- Rainfall on to snow, resulting in snow pack saturation, water ponding (if impermeable ice layers are present) and slush flows (Section 5.7).

- Rainfall onto glacier ice, resulting in melt water channel development increasing surface roughness, effecting SW radiation interaction with the surface and turbulent exchange (Section 5.7).

5.2.2 Surface energy balance

The magnitude of energy transfers to and from the glacier surface were at least, an order of magnitude greater than the other major heat sources to the glacier (geothermal heating, sliding induced friction and strain heating at the bed). Thus the surface energy balance of the glacier was key to driving seasonal and shorter scale warming and cooling of the ice and ultimately the thermal regime of the glacier. The surface energy balance for the full period of data collection has been derived from modelling investigations (Section 7.4). Presented here is a comparison of energy fluxes between summer and winter, along with a discussion of the diurnal variation in surface energy fluxes at the glacier surface (measured using the CNR1 four component radiometer and eddy correlation method for the turbulent fluxes) by comparing summer day 230 (2006) and winter day 35 (2007) (Figure 3.14 a and b).

Seasonal variation

Maximum energy fluxes occurred at the same time of day, 1300, in both summer and winter (Figure 3.14 a and b). On day 230 the maximum energy flux into the glacier surface was 1177 W m^{-2} with a simultaneous loss of 874 W m^{-2} resulting in net transfer of energy to the glacier of 302 W m^{-2} . On day 35 at 1400 the energy fluxes had reduced, with 748 W m^{-2} into the ice, while 715 W m^{-2} was emitted from the surface, resulting in a net gain of 33 W m^{-2} . The seasonal difference in the magnitude of the daily maximum flux to the glacier surface reflected the seasonal cycle of SW and the associated cycle of LW. $\text{SW}\downarrow$ exhibited a winter daily maximum of 555 W m^{-2} at 1400 compared to 934 W m^{-2} in summer resulting from reduced winter $\text{SW}\downarrow$ intensity. $\text{SW}\uparrow$ experienced a similar seasonal difference (due to the reduced winter $\text{SW}\downarrow$) of -418 W m^{-2} at 1400 on day 35 compared to -619 W m^{-2} on day 230. In addition to a seasonal reduction in SW fluxes, $\text{LW}\downarrow$ and $\text{LW}\uparrow$ also exhibited seasonality. The $\text{LW}\downarrow$ flux was higher on day 230 than day 35 due to the warmer atmosphere, with fluxes averaging 264 W m^{-2} in summer compared to 178 W m^{-2} in winter. $\text{LW}\uparrow$ displayed the smallest seasonal variation of the radiation fluxes between day 230 and day 35. However, a lower average winter emission of -254 W m^{-2} on day 35 compared to -264 W m^{-2} in summer reflected the colder winter glacier surface temperature. Sensible and latent heat fluxes were of similar small magnitude throughout day 230 and day 35, displaying no significant seasonal amplitude variation.

Diurnal variation

Flux variations at the diurnal scale were dominated by the variation of $SW\downarrow$. $SW\downarrow$ and $SW\uparrow$ were significant between 0800 and 2000 in summer, reducing to between 1000 and 1800 in winter due to reduction in winter daylight hours (Figure 3.14 a and b). The $LW\downarrow$ flux peaked at 1400 on both days (though only $\sim 2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ higher than adjacent values) suggesting an increase in the early afternoon in response to the daily warming of the atmosphere by $SW\downarrow$ resulting in the emission of slightly more $LW\downarrow$. The $LW\uparrow$ flux remained relatively stable on both days due to little variation in the glacier surface temperature throughout either day. Sensible heat and latent heat fluxes were small relative to the other fluxes, an order of magnitude smaller than each of the radiation fluxes, with little diurnal variation. One anomaly to this general trend was observed in winter, at midnight on day 35, (Figure 3.14 b) when an energy loss of -170.7 W m^{-2} due to sensible heat transfer was recorded. It is concluded that this higher flux occurred due to the establishment of a strong temperature gradient between the glacier surface and the atmosphere in response to nocturnal cooling of the atmosphere while the glacier surface remained relatively warm, initiating a large sensible heat loss, aided by a wind speed of 5.18 m s^{-1} driving turbulent mixing and promoting energy exchange.

Summary

- Tsanfleuron air temperatures fluctuated within the range $15.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $-25.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a mean of $-2.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
- Air temperature followed a strong seasonal cycle, causing glacier surface warming and melting in summer and freezing and cooling in winter. Differences in temperature between the glacier surface and the air above the glacier drove sensible heat transfer.
- Relative humidities at Tsanfleuron ranged from 4 % to 100 % with a mean of 73 %, with generally higher values in summer than winter.
- Relative humidity measurements proved a useful surrogate for the lack of continuous cloud cover measurements, allowing inferences to be made as to synoptic meteorological conditions.
- Wind direction appears to have been dominated by down glacier katabatic flow.
- Net radiation was the dominant energy flux at the glacier surface, with values ranging from 897 W m^{-2} in summer to -172 W m^{-2} in winter, with a mean value of -3 W m^{-2} .

- At Tsanfleuron shading of the glacier did not significantly influence the $SW\downarrow$ radiation as there were no major topographic features to the East and South, and only limited shading occurs from the West when the sun is low in the sky.
- Meteorology influences the glacier surface morphology through air temperature driven ablation, smoothing of surface roughness elements by snow fall, and wind redistribution of snow, surface crust development (as a result of nocturnal freezing of the glacier surface), rainfall saturating snow packs initiating slush flows and the ablation of small scale surface meltwater channels following intense rain storms over impermeable ice.
- Energy supply to the glacier surface was at least an order of magnitude greater than heat supply to the glacier by the main basal processes. Radiation dominated the surface energy balance, with seasonal and diurnal cycles in the intensity of $SW\downarrow$ exerting a large influence over the other radiation fluxes.
- Sensible and latent heat fluxes tended to fluctuate in direction and were small in magnitude relative to the radiative flux components of the surface energy balance. Exceptions to this rule were noted in response to the establishment of strong gradients of temperature and water vapour between the glacier surface and the atmosphere, often accentuated by high winds driving turbulent mixing.

5.3 Snow pack temperatures

The snow pack for most of the year mediated energy transfer between the atmosphere and the ice surface. Snow is highly permeable to liquid water, limited only by the presence of impermeable ice layers, is an excellent insulator and a poor heat conductor as a result of its low thermal conductivity. At Tsanfleuron recorded snow pack temperatures fluctuated between $\sim -22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in mid winter and $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ towards the end of the ablation season. Figure 5.3 shows contour plots of snow pack temperatures bounded by the snow depth time series plot. Temperatures at the three thermistor sites showed similar patterns, with the coldest snow temperatures occurring during the mid winter accumulation period, nearest the snow surface due to conductive heat loss under conditions of low atmospheric air temperatures and $LW\uparrow$ from a snow surface which, though cold, was warmer than the atmosphere. As snow depth increased, upward sloping isotherms developed in response to a warming of deeper snow layers via the conductive heat flux upwards from the underlying warmer ice. Temperatures at the base of the snow pack were prevented from cooling as low as those nearer the snow surface by the insulation provided by the overlying snow,

and quickly stabilised, gradually increasing over the winter. Following the winter snow depth maximum (occurring in mid April each year) warming began rapidly from the surface down, following the development of melt at the snow surface and percolation through the snow pack (displayed best at BH04-06 in Figure 5.3) as the snow pack evolved to isothermal conditions at melting point throughout and began to ablate. Snow pack temperature variations are described fully in Section 3.3.3.

Figure 5.3: Contour plots of daily snow temperatures, bounded by snow depth at all three borehole locations over the period of data collection February 2004 to February 2007 (expressed for the purposes of plotting as cumulative day since the beginning of 2004, with periods of missing data blanked out). Where snow depth was greater than the maximum height of thermistor deployment, temperatures have been extrapolated to the snow surface.

5.3.1 Near-surface snow temperatures

The upper-most snow layer was the most thermally active; i.e. the coldest layer of the whole glacier during the accumulation period, and one of the warmest during the ablation period. Early in the winter accumulation period, freshly deposited snow temperatures closely reflected the air temperature at the time of the snow fall, with rapid cooling of up to 4 °C soon after deposition in

response to nocturnal conductive and LW \uparrow losses e.g. the temperature records for 0.2 and 1.0 m above the ice surface in November and December 2004 at the North site (BH04-01) (Figure 3.22). The upper-most thermistors nearest the snow surface exhibited temperature fluctuation at a range of scales from diurnal, driven by daytime warming of the snow surface via conduction, sensible and latent heat transfer and penetration of SW \downarrow and nocturnal conductive, sensible heat transfer and LW \uparrow cooling, to periods of a number of days resulting from the passage of synoptic weather patterns. The amplitude of diurnal snow surface temperature cycles increased as the winter progressed and air temperatures dropped, from an amplitude of ~ 0.8 °C on day 347 (2004), to ~ 2 °C on day 8 (2005) and to a maximum of ~ 2.5 °C on day 40 (2005) (Figure 3.22). Blocking anticyclones which sit over continental Europe during winter tended to produce the most intense cold periods due to their cold, high pressure air, low humidity and clear skies allowing maximum nocturnal LW \uparrow , e.g. the cooling on day 37 (2005) where heat loss at the glacier surface resulted in a cooling of ~ 7.1 °C at the snow surface, decreasing in amplitude with depth below the surface, to ~ 0.3 °C at 1 m above the ice while completely eliminated by a height of 0.6 m above the ice (Figure 3.22). In contrast, the passage of low pressure systems characterised by warmer air, cloud and often snowfall tended to result in warmer conditions, reflected in the near-surface snow temperatures. As a result of the relatively low thermal conductivity of snow (Section 5.5), winter air temperature minima, occurring in January and February (as low as ~ -26 °C) in direct contact with the snow surface influence only a thin layer near the snow surface, with steep temperature gradients established within the snow pack. However, layers near the base of the snow pack which had stabilised remained relatively unaffected (e.g. Figure 3.19 b).

Once air temperature and SW \downarrow began to increase in spring, snow surface temperatures were the first to warm, gradually reaching 0 °C from which point snow pack warming increased rapidly due to the high permeability of snow, as percolating melt allowed advection of heat down to the sequentially warmer snow layers beneath. Though no such warming is evident in the thermistor time series or temperature profile plots due to the snow surface being high (~ 1.5 to 2 m) above the upper-most thermistor, manually measured snow pit temperature profiles (Figure 3.28) suggest by late April 2006, the snow surface had become isothermal at 0 °C and percolation to a depth of ~ 0.60 m had occurred at BH05-07 (Central site). Unfortunately, this snow pit digging disturbed the snow pack temperature profiles and initiated rapid warming near the thermistors, explained in more detail below.

5.3.2 Snow temperatures at depth within a snow pack

At the time of the first snowfall in November, snow temperatures near the ice surface exhibited temperature fluctuations on the diurnal scale and over a number of days. Following deposition, further cooling of the snow occurred in response to air temperature changes and LW \uparrow . Snow temperatures quickly stabilized and ceased cooling, no longer displaying diurnal fluctuations once they were buried under \sim 40 to 60 cm of further snow. Under such shallow snow cover, lower thermistors occasionally exhibited a response to higher amplitude cooling associated with the passage of air masses and weather systems (though the intensity of the associated cooling was not as great as later in the winter when a deeper snow pack covers the ice surface). Gradually, following increased burial, near-ice-surface temperatures began to warm and from \sim mid December began to stabilise at a temperature of \sim - 4.5 to - 4 $^{\circ}$ C. A similar stable pattern developed, with thermistors located higher above the surface stabilising at progressively lower temperatures, e.g. between day 8 and 50 (2005) the ice surface stabilised at a temperature of \sim - 4.2 $^{\circ}$ C, temperatures at 0.2 m above the ice stabilised at \sim 0.4 $^{\circ}$ C colder, \sim 0.8 $^{\circ}$ C at 0.4 m height, \sim 1.6 $^{\circ}$ C at 0.6 m height and \sim 3.1 $^{\circ}$ C colder at 1.0 m above the ice surface (Figure 3.22). Here, the colder overlying snow insulated the deeper snow layers. Near-ice-surface thermistors within the lower layers of the snow pack experienced a gradual warming over the winter, while the snow pack temperature gradient was negative. Under such conditions energy could not be conducted downwards for the surface against the temperature gradient; rather for such warming to have occurred at depth in the snow pack, energy was sourced from heat conduction upwards through the near-surface ice from warmer ice beneath. Thus, if at the time of deposition (or as a consequence of post deposition cooling in the absence of sufficiently rapid burial) snow temperatures were colder than near-surface ice temperatures, gradually following further burial and insulation from the atmosphere, these basal snow pack temperatures increased due to warming from below. Snow temperatures at depth were warmer than those above in early and mid winter but this was reversed once warming began from the surface downwards (Figure 3.25 and 3.26).

The relatively warm near-ice-surface snow temperatures and cold snow surface temperatures in early to mid winter resulted in the establishment of strong negative temperature gradients through the snow pack, as high as -4.86 $^{\circ}$ C m^{-1} (in January 2006 at the North site) forcing heat loss to the atmosphere. This gradient reversed to a positive gradient, as high as 1.32 $^{\circ}$ C m^{-1} (in June 2006 at the South site) driving heat gain in early summer as the snow pack began to become isothermal, details of which for the three sites (when available) are presented in Table 5.1.

	<i>Bulk snow pack temperature gradient ($^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$)</i>				
	North site (BH04-01)		South site (BH04-06)		Central site (BH05-07)
	2004/05	2005/06	2004/05	2005/06	2005/06
December	-4.38	-3.2	-3.93	-3.69	-1.21
January	-3.17	-4.86	-3.66	-3.54	-1.03
February	-3.80	-2.29		-1.54	-1.29
March	-0.55	-1.78		-1.40	
April	0.11	-0.59		-0.27	
May	0.06	0.15		1.31	
June				1.32	

Table 5.1: Bulk snow pack temperature gradients determined monthly for each of the three thermistor sites.

Exceptions to the outlined pattern of temperature variation occurred as a consequence of snow pits being dug near the thermistors. Snow pits dug in January (2006 and 2007) and February (2005) resulted in cooling, through exposure of the snow pack to cold atmospheric air, while snow pits dug in April (2005 and 2006) resulted in an initial warming by day and overnight cooling (when left open). The net effect of the April pits was a speeding up of the snow pack to isothermal conditions as surface melting had already been initiated at the time of pit excavation and pit excavation breached impermeable ice layers and generated macro-scale preferential pathways to the ice surface in the vicinity of the thermistors. Further details are given in Section 5.3.3.

In Figure 3.21 the thermistor located 1.6 m above the ice surface between days 15 and ~ 50 (2006) was warmer than the thermistors directly below it by ~ 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, at a time when it would have been expected that the uppermost snow thermistor would have exhibited the lowest temperatures. This local temperature reversal was attributed to the fact that this anomalously warm thermistor was located at the same height as the data logger enclosure (the base of which was measured to be 1.58 m above the ice surface). For the period in question this logger was partly buried and partly exposed above the snow / air surface. The effect of the partly exposed thermistor enclosure over the thermistor at 1.60 m above the snow / air surface, apart from the probable formation of a wind driven ablation hollow around the thermistor, would have been SW \downarrow warming of the logger box and due to its higher thermal inertia than the low density near-surface snow warming of the surrounding snow, resulting in the observed temperature anomaly at 1.60 m above the ice surface.

Snow pit temperature profiles

Snow pit temperature surveys were conducted as a means of validating thermistor-derived snow pack temperatures. January temperature profiles in both 2005 and 2006 (Figure 3.28) indicated the warmest temps were at the base of the snow pack, at the ice surface interface, in all three pits, reflecting heat loss to the atmosphere through the snow pack. Minimum temperatures in all three pits were at depths of 10 – 20 cm below the snow / air surface rather than at the snow / air surface, with relatively steep negative temperature gradient in the snow layers between. April 2006 snow pit temperature profiles suggested a general warming from January values had occurred in all three pits; maximum temperatures of 0 °C were recorded at the snow / air surface in all pits, with a steep temperature decline to a height of ~ 3 m above the ice surface, below which temperatures were uniform at either - 4 or - 5 °C down to the ice surface (Figure 3.28). These temperature profiles suggest the snow at all sites had began to become isothermal at 0 °C at the snow surface to a depth of ~ 0.5 m at the time of pit excavation, with warmer temperatures sequentially working their way down through the snow pack through percolation of melt and conduction.

5.3.3 Temperature changes and snow pack processes as the pack becomes isothermal

By the time snow pits were dug in April 2006 (on days 115, 118 and 116 at the North, South and Central sites respectively) surface snow layers at heights of > 3.5 m above the ice surface had reached melting point (Figure 3.28) (not displayed in thermistor time series or temperature profile plots due to a lack of thermistors that high in the snow pack (maximum thermistor height above the ice surface was 3.0 m at the North site in the 2004/05 winter)). The excavation of the April snow pits disturbed the temperature profiles in all three boreholes, exposing the deeper snow layers (sensed by the thermistors) to rapid warming of ~ 3 °C at the North site (Figure 3.19 b and 3.23 a) and ~ 2 to 3 °C at the South site (Figure 3.20 b and 3.24), (missing data prevented analysis of the warming of the Central site). Warming occurred during the period for which the holes were open during daylight hours and the air temperature was warmer than the snow. Heat transfer between the air and the adjacent snow pit walls occurred by conduction. The duration for which the hole was left open and the means of backfilling influenced the different temperature characteristics observed in the days following digging. Both the North and the South sites displayed highly fluctuating temperatures in the days immediately after excavation. The pit at the North site was manually back filled soon after digging on day 115. All thermistors experienced rapid temperature increases, decreasing in amplitude towards the ice surface. Following the initial disturbance, temperatures recorded by the upper thermistors cooled between day 117 and 123 in response to a period of low air temperatures when temperatures remained negative

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

between day 116 and 122, reaching a minima of $-15.45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 120, before warming again on day 122. The snow pit at the South site remained open following excavation (due to a shorting of time preventing back filling) and filled naturally by blowing snow. Consequently both daytime warming and nocturnal cooling were measured (most notably in the thermistor at 1.8 m above the ice surface on day 118 (Figure 3.24)). Here, cooling of the ice surface by $\sim 1.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ resulted from the hole remaining open and filling with wind redistributed snow.

Temperature peaks at the ice surface at the North site from $\sim -3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to between ~ -0.25 and $-0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on days 125, 128 and 133 (2006) (Figure 3.23 b) likely represented the arrival of pulses of percolating melt water (corresponding with the times that upper thermistors reached stable near $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperatures). The lack of evidence of warming at thermistors above, other than that at 0.2 m above the ice surface indicates the route taken by the melt was not in the vicinity of the other thermistors. Thus, it is possible that melt which accessed the ice surface away from the thermistor string and ponded in the vicinity of the ice surface thermistor as a consequence of micro-scale ice surface topography. Similar temperature peaks were observed at the South site on days 126, 129 and 134 (2006) at 0.2 m above the ice surface (Figure 3.24) also interpreted as marking the arrival of percolating melt at this depth in the snow pack.

After the transition to warmer snow pack temperatures following snow pit digging and the arrival of the wetting front at the ice surface by the end of May, snow temperature profiles at the North site were notably warmer than those at the South (Figure 3.27 a and b), especially near the ice surface. The ice surface at the South site was $\sim 1.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ colder than, and did not experience warming at the same time as that of, the North site in the period April to June 2006. Differences in ice surface temperature and those in the lower snow pack during this period are attributed to differences in the interaction of percolating melt water with the underlying ice surface. It is believed the melt reaching the ice surface at the North site quickly penetrated into the ice surface advecting heat and refreezing within the ice, quickly warming near-surface ice layers, reducing the cooling effect of the ice on the warming snow pack. It is also suggested that the “ice surface” thermistor at the South site may no longer have been at the ice surface and may have been frozen into the ice via the formation of clear bubble free superimposed ice, observed to have formed at the South site by January 2006. Warmer temperatures (by $\sim 2.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 0.2 m above the “ice surface”) compared to temperatures at the “ice surface” and 0.4 m above, were recorded in the last 2 weeks of November 2005 at the South site, possibly caused by latent heat release on refreezing of melt water (Figure 3.26 b), suggest the formation of the superimposed ice. Movement of the ice surface upwards to the vicinity of the thermistor at 0.2 m above the early

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

winter ice surface location, may explain the sharp jump in basal snow temperatures between May 6th and 10th of ~ 1.75 °C at the same time as a jump of ~ 0.75 °C in the postulated superimposed ice. In early spring melt reaching the ice surface resulted in refreezing and latent energy release evidenced by the 0.2 m thermistor (suggested new basal snow pack / ice surface thermistor) and the smaller warming of the original ice surface thermistor. However, later in the melt season when an increasing amount of water would have reached the impermeable ice surface, it appears from the lack of subsequent warming (which one would expect if refreezing of melt continued at the ice surface) that melt may not to have refrozen in the vicinity of the near ice surface thermistor (at least up until the end of the second week in June when the data set ends). Rather it appears the water drained over the impermeable, cold ice surface leading to the development of sub nival drainage channels (see Section 5.7). Drainage channels incised into the ice surface developed as a consequence of the topographic concavity in which the South site was located, allowing the ice surface to maintain its cooling effect over the lower snow layers and leaving snow pack warming to the slower process of conduction and sub-surface warming via the penetration of SW↓.

The importance of advective heat transfer by percolating melt water, relative to that of conduction, is considerably greater in snow than in ice, as a consequence of the higher permeability and lower thermal conductivity of snow (see Table 1.1). Thus, water flow through the snow pack is a key heat transfer process, especially at the beginning of the melt period (Wendler and Weller, 1974). Ice layers and lenses within the snow pack act to retard the percolation of surface derived melt. Snow pit digging, in addition to thermally disrupting the snow pack, had the effect of breaking through impermeable ice layers and, when randomly backfilled, macro-scale preferential drainage pathways were generated within the snow pack. This facilitated rapid arrival of surface-derived melt soon after snow pit excavation, earlier than would have been the case without the disturbance. In the absence of anthropogenic disturbance, the relatively similar snow packs at all 3 borehole locations would become isothermal at different times at each site, as a consequence of stratigraphic heterogeneity within the snow packs, different processes operating at the underlying ice surface, and near-surface ice differences controlling melt transfer and energy release.

The snow temperature profiles above BH05-07 at the Central site depict highly fluctuating temperatures vertically within the snow pack over a range of ~ 2 °C, not observed at either of the other sites (Figure 3.26 c). There appears to be a cyclicity in the fluctuation with every 3rd thermistor registering what appear to be anomalously high temperatures. It is postulated that the

temperatures presented at 0.4, 1.0, 1.6 and 2.2 m above the ice surface are erroneously high, when removed (Figure 3.26 b), snow temperatures profiles follow those in the other two holes more closely. The cyclicity of the erroneous thermistors points to a multiplexer problem, as the thermistors were wired to the multiplexer in “SETs” of three (Figure 2.14 a). It appears that either one of the data logger channels (1H, 1L or 2H), one of the COM ports on the multiplexer (COM L (ODD), COM H (EVEN) or COM L (EVEN)) or one of the bridge resistors between the multiplexer and the logger was malfunctioning. Temperature plots of ice temperatures in BH05-07 (Figure 4.18 c and 4.19 c) also display what appear to be anomalously high temperatures from thermistors in the same wiring sequence. As the logger and multiplexer appear to be recording correct values for the remaining thermistors it is suggested that resistor degradation may be the source of the problem, though detailed investigation of the logger and the multiplexer channels and ports or the integrity of the resistor have not been conducted. Analysis of the warming of the Central site snow pack could not be conducted due to insufficient data resulting from data logger failure in February 2006.

Heat flux between the base of the snow pack and the ice surface: evidence of the arrival of percolating melt water

The heat flux between the snow pack and the ice surface, measured at the meteorological station (close to BH04-01) reached a positive peak on day 138 (2006) following rapid increase to positive values on day 137 (Figure 3.4). Prior to day 137 the flux had been negative, indicating a small heat loss from the glacier ice into the snow pack replacing that lost upwards through the snow pack to the atmosphere. The magnitude of the flux gradually decreased over winter as the snow pack thickness increased (Figure 3.15 a) developing greater insulation and as the mean daily air temperature increased towards the end of the winter into spring (Figure 3.1 a).

The reversal in the direction of the energy flux to positive values and the peak on day 138 (18th May) suggests the time at which the wetting front first reached the glacier ice surface, as the snow pack became isothermal and energy was advected through the snow to the ice surface. On contact with the ice surface it is likely that the percolating water partially infiltrated into open cracks in the ice surface and / or refroze at the ice surface near the heat flux plate. On refreezing, latent heat of fusion would have been released resulting in further warming of the basal snow layers (primarily the colder snow between the preferential melt “fingers” through which the percolating melt reached the ice surface) and the ice beneath. Gradually following this period, increasing amounts of melt water percolated down through the rapidly ablating, saturated, isothermal snow pack, refreezing at the ice/snow interface or within the ice, making the heat flow

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

positive into the ice. The decline after the initial heat flux peak was an artefact of the warming of the ice surface to the same temperature as that of the bottom of the snow pack. The heat flux plate was a thermopile sensor which measured the differential temperature across the two sides of the sensor body, as the ice surface warmed to that of the snow pack base, the temperature difference decreased and thus the recorded heat flux decreased accordingly, to zero once both sides of the sensor were in thermal equilibrium.

Summary

- Snow temperatures on Tsanfleuron fluctuated between ~ -22 °C and 0 °C.
- The snow pack insulates the ice surface in winter, considerably reducing the heat loss from the near-surface ice. Ice surface temperature fluctuations reduced considerably once a few 10s of cm of snow were deposited.
- The warmest snow pack temperatures occurred at the base of the snow pack, insulated from cold atmospheric air and warmed by energy from the underlying ice.
- Near air / snow surface snow thermistors experienced temperature fluctuation on both the diurnal scale and that of a few days in response to the passage of synoptic weather systems.
- The coldest snow temperatures occurred nearest the snow surface in response to cold atmospheric air. The upper layers of snow were prevented from effective warming from below by the low thermal conductivity of snow.
- The snow pack controls the timing of arrival of wetting front to the ice surface which is instrumental in the initial elimination of the winter cold wave.
- The ice surface thermistor deployed at BH04-01 (the North site) experienced periods of warming in spring 2006 attributed to refreezing of percolating melt at the ice surface. These events corresponded closely with the time of reversal of the energy flux between the ice and snow pack measured by the heat flux plate, explained in terms of the arrival of the wetting front to the ice.

- Superimposed ice was observed at BH04-06 (the South site) in January 2006. It is suggested that this formed early in the winter, possibly during November (observed at base of January 2007 snow pit), burying the ice surface thermistor within the ice and accounting for the lower and slower warming of this thermistor relative to other thermistors above the ice surface at that location.
- The digging of snow pits resulted in temperature decrease in early winter through exposure of previously warmer lower snow pack layers to cold atmospheric air temperatures. In spring, however, snow pits dug in April had the opposite effect, resulting in warming following the exposure of deep snow pack layers to warmer atmospheric air (during daylight hours) and through the disruption of the stratigraphy forming macro-scale preferential pathways for percolation of surface derived melt, speeding the development of isothermal conditions.
- Snow pit temperature profiles indicate surface melting and percolation of melt-water (to a depth of up to 0.60 m) had begun by late April 2006.

5.4 Near-surface ice temperatures

5.4.1 Ice temperatures

Near-surface ice temperatures fluctuated in response to seasonal, diurnal and longer period changes in energy receipt at the ice surface - directly to the ice in summer and mediated by the overlying snow pack in winter.

Temperature response of near-surface ice to seasonal variation in energy supply to the glacier surface

With one exception winter cooling of the near-surface ice, saw temperatures decrease from melting point throughout the depth of all boreholes. The exception was BH04-06 at the South site, which displayed perennially sub freezing ice temperatures down to ~ -1 °C, over the two year study period, below a depth of ~ 1 m.

Winter cooling

In October 2005 prior to the onset of winter cooling, transient temperature falls of ≤ -1 °C were experienced by thermistor 15.0A (removed from the time series as outlined in Section 4.1). These perturbations may be attributed to the thermistor melting out of the ice surface towards the end of September, lying on the glacier surface and subsequently being covered by shallow, early

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

winter snow falls. The location of the thermistor under a thin autumn snow pack, the high albedo of fresh snow causing high SW reflection and decreasing daily average air temperatures as winter approached would have prevented temperatures above 0 °C being recorded. However, night time energy loss led to cooling of the shallow snow pack resulting in the temperature falls to -1 °C originally in the thermistor 15.0A time series.

The onset of winter cooling each year followed a similar pattern in all boreholes. At the North site at the beginning of the 2004/05 winter, cooling began in BH04-01 on day 313, with ice temperatures recorded by thermistor 14.0A (0.95 m below the ice surface) falling 3.51 °C from -0.08 °C to -3.59 °C over a 10 day period (Figures 4.8 a and 4.13 c). Temperatures fluctuated around ~ -3.6 °C before a further period of cooling from -3.49 °C to the winter minima of -4.28 °C between days 346 and 353. It is suggested that this second period of cooling (and similar cooling at the same time in BH04-06) resulted from exposure of the glacier surface to cold air temperatures and high nocturnal LW↑ in response to the passage of a high pressure meteorological system over a relatively shallow snow cover. Following day 353 temperatures slowly warmed back to ~ - 3.5 °C (Figure 4.8 a). A third period of cooling was observed following day 55 (Figure 4.5 (upper plot)) as a result of snow pit excavation, details of which are given below. At the South site (BH04-06) cooling began on day 311 (slightly earlier than observed at BH04-01 as thermistor 15.0B was nearer to the surface than thermistor 14.0A), with ice temperatures recorded by thermistor 15.0B (0.35 m below the ice surface) falling 3.20 °C from -0.02 °C to -3.22 °C over a 16 day period (Figures 4.8 b and 4.15 c). Similar to BH04-01, after a period of fluctuation around ~ -3.5 °C a second period of more rapid cooling was observed from -3.29 °C on day 342 to -4.52 °C on day 352 and subsequent warming to a stable temperature of ~ - 3.5 °C (Figure 4.8 b). No snow pit was dug at the South site as the logger was buried and lost during the second half of the winter, resulting in power loss and cessation of recording on day 35 (recording resumed in August 2005), preventing determination of winter ice temperature minima.

At the beginning of the 2005/06 winter, patterns of near-surface ice temperature decrease were similar to those displayed in the previous winter. At the North site (BH04-01) temperatures began to fall on day 312, with thermistor 15.0A (0.05 m below the ice surface) recording a decrease of 3.11 °C from -0.09 °C to -3.20 °C over a 27 day period, somewhat slower than in 2004 (Figure 4.14 c). Again a short period of warming was observed to a temperature of - 2.93 °C on day 362, from which cooling continued gradually to the winter minima of -3.49 °C on day 49. An early period of thermal disturbance not observed in BH04-01 or BH05-07 occurred between day 270

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

and 292 (Figure 4.6 (upper plot)) at the South site (BH04-06) with temperatures falling from $-0.08\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-1.64\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and quickly warming back to $\sim -0.60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The main winter cooling began on day 311, with temperatures recorded by thermistor 18.0B (1.02 m below the ice surface) decreasing $2.63\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ from $-0.60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-3.23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ over a 26 day period (Figures 4.16 c). A small warming to $-3.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 360 then occurred, followed by a further cooling to the winter minima of $-3.67\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 56 (Figure 4.6 (upper plot)). The Central site (BH05-07) saw winter cooling begin on day 309, with temperatures recorded by thermistor 10.0D (0.02 m below the ice surface) falling $3.72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ from $-0.01\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-3.73\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ over a 20 day period (Figure 4.18 c), a subsequent warming period as observed at the other two holes occurred with temperatures rising to $-2.14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 360. Data logger malfunction from February 2006 (recording resumed in August 2006) prevented determination of winter ice temperature minima in BH05-07.

The most rapid near-surface ice cooling (~ 4 to $4.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature loss in 2 to 4 weeks) occurred during November at all three sites over both study years, in response to brisk air temperature and SW \downarrow decrease (Figures 3.1a and 7.4 respectively) at the beginning of winter. Rapid energy loss from the ice surface occurred via conduction, radiation (LW \uparrow) and sensible heat transfer as large temperature gradients were established between the relatively warm ice surface (initially at melting point following warming during the summer ablation season) and the rapidly cooling atmosphere (recorded November air temperature minima dropped as low as $-22.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2005 and $-16.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2006). Heat loss from the ice, quickly cooled the ice surface, initiating a steep negative temperature gradient in the near-surface ice. Following the development of a snow pack in excess of $\sim 0.3\text{ m}$ (day 328 (2005) and day 318 (2006)), the rate of decrease of ice surface temperature declined, resulting from the insulation effect of the snow cover reducing heat loss (see Section 5.5). Following the development of snow insulation, near-surface temperatures began to rise slowly in response to conduction of heat from warmer ice layers at depth in the ice, driven by the negative temperature gradient. Gradually over a ~ 3 to 4 week period the temperature gradient and heat flux between the ice at lower depths and that at the surface reduced, as the ice surface warmed and sequentially deeper ice layers experienced cooling. After the initial influx of energy from the deeper ice and the subsequent reduction in the flux, cooling from the surface in response to the transfer of energy into the snow pack (to replace that lost to the atmosphere at the snow surface) drove further ice cooling, though less intense than the early winter cooling due to the presence of the snow pack. The near-surface ice gradually cooled towards the winter minimum, recorded in late February. The sequence of rapid initial cooling followed by a small warming, then further cooling to the winter minimum was experienced only by thermistors within $\sim 2\text{ m}$ of the ice surface. Deeper thermistors did not experience a warming

following the initial cooling, but displayed gradual cooling, reducing in intensity somewhat after the period of warming experienced by the thermistors in the upper ~ 2 m (Figures 4.5, 4.6, 4.7 (upper plots) and Figure 4.8).

The maximum winter thermal changes recorded at thermistors in the near-surface ice due to the seasonal cycle of surface energy receipt were greatest nearest the ice surface (4.20 °C at 0.95 m depth in BH04-01 and 4.50 °C at 0.35 m depth in BH04-06 during the 2004/05 winter), and decreased exponentially with depth (-2.79 °C at 1.95 m, -2.35 °C at 2.95 m, -1.69 °C at 4.95 m, -0.77 at 8.95 m, -0.11 at 12.95 m and < 0.04 °C at 16.95 m depth in BH04-01). The winter cold wave was eliminated in both BH04-01 and BH 04-06 by depths of between ~ 13 to ~ 16 m (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: Maximum winter thermal disturbance due to cooling, experienced by near-surface thermistors at each depth below the ice surface in BH04-01 and BH04-06. BH05-07 data are not presented due to data logger malfunction.

Late spring and summer warming

Analysis of near-surface ice warming was based only on data from BH04-01 in 2005 and from BH04-06 in 2006, due to gaps in the data sets. Rapid warming of near-surface ice at the North site in BH04-01 during the late spring of 2005 began in April on day 119, when temperatures of thermistor 14.0A rapidly began to increase from -3.47 °C to -0.20 °C by day 130: a 3.27 °C

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

warming over 11 days (Figures 4.9 a and 4.13 c). Temperature increase was initiated simultaneously in thermistors 15.0A, 16.0A and 18.0A (1.95 m, 2.95 and 4.95 m below the ice surface respectively), presumably via percolation of melt to depth and refreezing in the ice. In the spring of 2006 warming of the near-surface ice at the South site began with thermistor 18.0B on day 128 (Figure 4.9 b). In contrast to the warming at the North site lower thermistors did not experience instantaneous warming, attributed to the impermeable ice surface preventing percolation of melt. This warming was disturbed by a large basally-derived thermal disturbance (Section 6.4 and Figure 4.10) beginning on day 170.

After the near-surface winter temperature minimum was reached in February, thermistors near the ice surface began to warm gradually in response to a reduction in the energy loss through the snow pack due to further insulation from the cooling influence of the atmosphere, under an increasing depth of snow (maximum snow depth occurred in mid to late April in 2005 and 2006). Conduction upwards through the ice continued in response to the temperature gradient established earlier in the winter. However, a decrease in heat loss to the snow pack occurred as near-surface ice temperatures began to rise (once the heat flux from the ice below exceeded the flux lost to the snow pack). In response to the gradual warming of the near-surface ice due to a reduction in heat loss to the snow, heat loss from sequentially deeper ice layers reduced until warming of the ice surface began. Once warming of the ice surface was initiated by the advance of the snow pack wetting front to the ice surface, rapid warming of near-surface ice layers occurred. The temperature gradient established over winter between the relatively warm ice and the cold snow pack was reversed as the snow pack warmed to isothermal melting conditions, promoting heat conduction to the colder ice below. Heat flux plate measurements of the energy flux between the snow pack and the ice surface conducted at the North site (Figure 3.4) suggested the wetting front reached the ice surface on day 137 in 2006. Unfortunately, the thermistor data logger failed on day 136 preventing assessment of the near-surface ice temperature changes as a result of the arrival of this wetting front. Comparison with ice temperatures at the South site suggested the ice temperature increase beginning on day 128 likely occurred due to the arrival of the wetting front at the ice surface (the 9 day discrepancy between the arrival date at the North site and the suggested arrival date at the South was feasible when considering the heterogeneity within the snow pack and the tortuous pathway development for percolation of melt through the various impermeable ice layers within the snow pack). On arrival of percolating melt waters to the ice surface, advected heat instantly warmed the ice surface, liquid melt either percolated quickly to depth through macro-porous cracks and fractures (which may have developed over the winter and remained open in the absence of liquid water to freeze them closed), refreezing and

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

releasing latent heat (at the North and Central sites (BH04-01 and BH05-07)), or refroze or runoff on contact with an impermeable ice surface (the South site (BH04-06)). The upper near-surface ice temperatures rapidly rose establishing a high localised reversal of the ice temperature gradient, and conduction then began transferring heat downwards into the ice propagating the reversal of the thermal gradient to depth. The speed at which thermistors at depth began to increase in temperature depended on the process by which energy was transferred. At the North and Central sites energy transfer to depth occurred via conduction and percolation of water. At the South site where the impermeable surface ice prevented penetration of melt, any refreezing occurred at the ice surface leading to the formation of superimposed ice (observed in the field at the base of the snow pack in January 2006 presumably formed by percolation and refreezing of early winter surface derived melt) with the associated heat release focused at the upper layer of the ice. Thus, heat transfer to depth in the ice occurred here solely via conduction, taking somewhat longer. This warming sped up once the snow pack fully ablated and the ice surface was exposed by day 209 in both years. Once exposure of the ice surface occurred energy received there was partitioned between that which was conducted to depth to continue the warming of the lower ice layers and that which drove melting and ablation of the ice surface. By the end of the ablation season the depth of ice which had cooled in the previous winter had been returned to melting point at the North and Central site. However, at the South site cold ice remained at depth below the surface, mainly due to the impermeable ice surface which limited heat transfer to depth to conduction, resulting in higher ablation at the South site as that surplus energy which could not be conducted to depth drove greater surface lowering than observed at the other two sites (Figure 4.2 and Table A3).

Differences between the speed of winter cooling and spring warming of the near-surface glacier ice

Winter 2004/05 cooling at the North site in BH04-01 was initially registered by thermistors 14.0A and 15.0A on day 313 (2004), sequentially lower thermistors of 16.0A, 18.0A, 22.0A and 26.0A began cooling on days 316 (2004), 320 (2004), 345 (2004) and day 48 (2005) respectively. On account of the time required for temperature gradients to be established and conductive heat loss to work its way down through the ice, a total of 101 days elapsed between the cooling being registered near the surface and the time it was registered at the deepest thermistor to be influenced by the seasonal cooling cycle, at a depth of 12.95 m. In contrast spring warming was initially registered on day 119 by thermistors, 14.0A, 15.0A, 16.0A and 18.0A, with thermistors 22.0A and 26.0A displaying warming trends from day 126, only 7 days after the near-surface first experienced warming. Similar trends were observed in the 2005/06 winter with the time from the

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

initial cooling at the surface to that at the deepest influenced thermistor being 87 days while missing data prevented analysis of the timing of ice warming. It was concluded that while conduction was responsible for the slow process of cooling, the initiation of warming at depth occurred considerably sooner as a consequence of the percolation of melt rapidly transferring energy to depth in the ice.

At the South site in BH04-06 thermistor 15.0B registered the initial 2004/05 winter cooling on day 311, sequentially lower thermistors 16.0B, 18.0B and 22.0B registered cooling on days 316, 324 and 342 respectively before data logger failure occurred. In the 2005/06 winter thermistor 18.0B registered the first cooling on day 311 (2006), 22.0B began cooling on day 337 (2005) and 26.0B on day 5 (2006), a total of 59 days after thermistor 18.0B at a depth of 9.02 m. Spring warming began on day 126 at 18.0B, day 148 at 22.0B and day 153 at 26.0B (27 days after the first warming at thermistor 18.0B). Cooling at the South site seems similarly slow as that in BH04-01 at the North site. However, in contrast to the rapid initiation of warming displayed at each depth in BH04-01 the warming at BH04-06 took noticeably longer to penetrate to depth, resulting from the fact that warming under the impermeable ice surface occurred via conduction alone in the absence of melt percolation.

Anthropogenic near -surface winter ice temperature disturbances

Near-surface ice temperatures at the North site in BH04-01 experienced cooling on two occasions for anthropogenic reasons. In February 2005 following the excavation of 4 pits to the ice surface in the immediate vicinity of BH04-01 (to anchor meteorological station guy lines and to recover the buried data logger). Pits dug on day 55 remained open overnight, as a consequence temperatures at 0.95 m below the ice surface (recorded by thermistor 14.0A) fell by 0.34 °C from -3.45 °C to -3.79 °C over an 11 day period (Figure 4.5 (upper plot)) due to conductive cooling initiated by temperature gradients established in the upper ice layers over the short period of exposure to air temperatures as low as ~ -20 °C. The effects of the thermal disturbance were felt by thermistor 14.0A until day 98, 43 days after the holes were dug, when temperatures had returned to the undisturbed level via conduction of heat from warmer ice below. The thermal disturbance was felt to a lesser extent by thermistor 15.0A at a depth of 1.95 m.

A similar cooling of near-surface ice temperatures at BH04-01 occurred in April 2005 for the same reason as that in February, following the digging of a pit to access the buried data logger and conduct snow pit analysis on day 111. Contrary to other holes dug on Tsanfleuron, the April BH04-01 hole was left open for a number of days to allow seismic snow pack experiments to be

conducted by colleagues from the University of Wales, Swansea. Consequently the ice surface was exposed to cold nocturnal air temperatures of as low as $-11.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (at 0100 on day 112), the cooling effect of which on ice surface and the establishment of a large negative near-surface temperature gradient, led to a temperature decrease of $0.29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, from $-3.19\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-3.48\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ rapidly over a 2 day period, which was then eliminated within 7 days by day 119. The more rapid elimination of the thermal disturbance in April 2005 was a result of the disturbance occurring at a time when the snow pack was becoming isothermal and energy transfer through the snow pack was reversed, toward the ice surface rather than away from as was the case during the February disturbance. Cooling of the near-surface ice was not observed at the other borehole locations or at the North site when other holes were dug, due to the short period of time for which the ice surface was exposed, with the holes rapidly backfilled once the loggers had been accessed or the snow pit analysis conducted, to minimise the thermal disturbance.

Near-surface summer ice temperatures

Following summer warming from the winter minimum, near-surface ice temperatures in BH04-01 were close to melting point throughout the whole seasonally active thermal layer by the end of August 2005 (Figure 4.23) and had reached melting point ($\pm 0.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) by the end of September 2005 (Figure 4.22 a) due to warming via conduction and percolation. A similar pattern of warming was observed in the 2006 ablation season (Figure 4.24 a). In both cases the surface was first to respond and displayed the greatest warming. Sequentially deeper thermistors were warmed by decreasing amounts via conduction. However, the small amount of advective heat transfer and latent heat release experienced by the deepest thermistors, disturbed least by winter cooling was sufficient to warm the deep ice back to melting point, prior to the establishment of a positive temperature gradient down through the ice. A negative temperature gradient existed between the deepest thermistors and those above, with a temperature minima between 2 and 6 m below the ice surface remaining through most of the summer, gradually eliminated as conductive heat moved down through the ice (Figure 4.23).

Temperatures at the South site in BH04-06 warmed more slowly than BH04-01 in the 2006 summer (Figure 4.24 b) (missing data prevented discussion of the 2005 summer). Ice surface temperatures were swift to respond to energy input, warming $\sim 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2 weeks at the end of June, resulting in the ice surface reaching melting point by the beginning of July and remaining so for the duration of the summer. Below the ice surface, warming only occurred via conduction, thus before energy could be transferred to depth a reversal of temperature gradient was required. Gradually as the summer progressed, sequentially deeper thermistors began to warm and heat was

conducted slowly downwards. However, no simultaneous warming of deep thermistors could occur until those above were raised to a higher temperature (unlike in BH04-01 under the influence of water penetration). By the end of October 2006 the deepest thermistor to have experienced warming via conduction in BH04-06 was located at just ~ 8 m below the surface (Figure 4.24 b) the deeper thermistors at ~ 12 m and below experienced no summer warming at all (with the exception of all thermistors which experienced warming between June 16 – 30th (days 167 – 181) as a consequence of the large basal heat supply event depicted in Figure 4.10 and propagation of heat up the not fully closed borehole (see Section 6.4.2)). As a result of the slow and limited summer heat conduction through the seasonal thermally active ice layer at BH04-06, thermistors below ~ 12 m in the 2005/06 glacier year experienced only cooling. At the beginning of the 2006/07 winter the near-surface ice had not all reached melting point, all the ice below ~ 0.5 m in the near-surface layer (to depth of ~ 25 to 30 m, see Figure 4.17 a) was cold, with a temperature minima of ~ -1 °C at ~ 8 m below the ice surface.

Diurnal response of near-surface ice temperature to variation in energy input at the glacier surface

Time series of thermistors in the near-surface ice at the South site in BH04-06, recorded under snow free conditions in September 2005 (Figure 5.5) exhibited distinctive diurnal temperature cycles, with the largest amplitude of ~ 0.12 °C revealed by the thermistor nearest the ice surface (18.0B at ~ 1 m depth), decreasing to an amplitude of ~ 0.07 °C at the next thermistor (22.0B located at ~ 5 m depth). Below 5.05 m depth diurnal cycles were still identifiable visually in the temperature record to greater depths. However, these amplitudes of less than the ± 0.04 °C were \approx the error associated with the temperature measurements (Section 2.3.3). Examination of meteorological data collected over the same period indicated the dominant well reported diurnal cycles of the air temperature and net radiation were in phase with the diurnal ice temperature cycles (Figure 5.5). It was therefore suggested that diurnal energy receipt and thermal forcing by air temperature and net radiation drove diurnal cycles in near-surface ice temperatures under snow free conditions. Similar diurnal temperature cycles under snow free conditions were visible in the near-surface ice of BH04-01 at the North site. Under snow cover conditions diurnal temperature cycles in the near-surface ice were not present, presumably eliminated by the insulation effect of the snow preventing the air temperature and net radiation diurnal cycles from penetrating to the ice surface; instead diurnal temperature cycles were visible in the near-surface snow.

Figure 5.5: Thermistor time series showing diurnal temperature cycles under snow free conditions at 1.05 and 5.05 m below the ice surface in BH04-06 in September 2005, also displayed air temperature (blue line) and net radiation (red line) for the same period.

Summary

- Temperatures recorded by the uppermost ice thermistors in all boreholes experienced an initial rapid temperature decrease in November each year, followed by a small temperature rise once an insulating snow pack developed, then a second more gradual

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

temperature decrease to a winter minimum in February. Sequentially deeper thermistors experienced lower cooling rates, reaching warmer winter minima at later dates.

- Percolation of melt water into macro-porous drainage pathways in the ice at BH04-01 in the spring of 2005 initiated simultaneous warming in the four uppermost thermistors. This is interpreted in terms of heat transfer occurring via advection (and latent heat release on refreezing) as well as conduction. In contrast at BH04-06 in the following spring the prevention of melt percolation by the impermeable ice surface, resulted in warming being initiated only in the thermistor nearest the surface as heat transfer was limited to simply conduction.
- Heat flux plate measurements at the North site, indicating the arrival time of the wetting front and advected heat to the ice surface, coincide with observed near-surface ice temperature increases (at the South site) to within 9 days, suggesting the arrival of percolating melt water at the ice surface initiated rapid near-surface warming.
- Anthropogenic cooling of the near-surface ice in BH04-01 at the North site occurred in February and April 2005 in response to excavation of snow pits and exposure of the ice surface to cold nocturnal air temperatures.
- The entire depth of seasonal thermally active ice at BH04-01 was warmed to melting point in summer. In contrast only ice to a depth of ~ 8 to 10 m experienced warming and not to melting point in BH04-06. Only ice to a depth of ~ 0.5 m reached melting point in summer at BH04-06, with ice below remaining cold with a minimum temperature of ~ -1 °C at ~ 8 m depth.
- Diurnal cycles in air temperature and net radiation drove in phase diurnal cycles in near - surface ice temperatures, decreasing in amplitude below the surface under snow free conditions; such ice temperature cycles were not present (or were severely attenuated) under snow cover.

5.5 The influence of the snow cover over near-surface ice temperatures

Snow cover mediated energy transfer between the near-surface glacier ice and the atmosphere (the direction of which varied over an annual cycle) and thus directly influenced near-surface ice temperatures. In addition to mediating energy transfer the snow cover also limited the magnitude of the radiation flux at the glacier surface, as the albedo of the snow surface was considerably higher than that of glacier ice, reflecting a greater proportion of $SW\downarrow$ than would be the case if the snow were not present.

Energy transfer between the snow surface and the ice surface was via conduction, upwards from the ice to the snow surface replenishing energy lost to the atmosphere during winter and downwards from the snow surface to the ice in spring and early summer as the annual surface energy receipt increased and the snow pack ablated. In addition to conduction, melt generated at the snow surface percolated down through the snow pack, advected heat and transferred latent heat (released on refreezing) to the ice surface, the snow depth and snow stratigraphy influenced the time and path ways taken for this melt to reach ice surface.

5.5.1 Seasonal “winter” snow pack effects

Over a total period of 702 days meteorological data collection, the glacier surface was snow covered for 631 (90 % of the time), of which 134 days of the snow cover were classed as “summer” snowfall, indicating that the seasonal “winter” snow pack covered the glacier surface for 71 % of the year. Winter snowfall began on day 273 (2005) and 279 (2006), reached maximum depths of 3.83 m on day 116 (2005) and 4.40 m on day 104 (2006) and had fully ablated by day 209 in both years. Snow depth was relatively uniform across the glacier (Figure 3.16 and Table 3.4). Spatial variations in snow depth would have had the greatest influence over near ice surface heat fluxes early in the winter (November and December) under a relatively shallow snow pack, with the influence decreasing as the snow pack evolved towards its seasonal peak in April.

The seasonal snow pack insulated the ice surface from the cold winter atmospheric air temperatures limiting cooling of the near-surface ice and also insulated the ice surface and the deeper snow layers from warming by increasing air temperatures and $SW\downarrow$ during spring. Conduction of the warm air temperatures to the ice surface were limited as a consequence of the low thermal conductivity and diffusivity of the snow pack (Section 5.5.3). Energy transfer through the snow pack to the ice was mainly in the form of advection as the wetting front

advanced downwards through the snow pack. Data logger malfunction resulted in missing data during the spring in all years preventing a detailed analysis of the warming of the near-surface ice and the influence of the snow pack. However, it is postulated that near-surface ice thermistors would display an initial period of warming resulting from the penetration of melt water through the snow pack and refreezing at the ice surface releasing latent heat. A second period warming would likely have occurred coinciding with the full ablation of the winter snow pack and the exposure of surface ice. Following exposure of the ice surface SW_{\downarrow} absorption would likely have increased and SW_{\uparrow} decreased as a consequence of increased penetration and a reduction in surface albedo from that of an old snow pack to that of glacier ice (see Section 5.3.3 for details of snow hydrological processes as the snow pack became isothermal).

The interaction of radiation with the surface was different under snow cover conditions relative to those of exposed glacier ice. SW_{\downarrow} penetrated deeper into snow than ice (Williams, 1971) and experienced greater scattering at the surface and within the snow pack. In early winter (late October and November) the first snows of the year increased the surface albedo. The high albedo under conditions of shallow snow cover resulted in high SW_{\downarrow} reflection combined with high LW_{\uparrow} nocturnal emission (due to the cold nocturnal atmospheric air temperatures prior to the development of a deep insulating snow pack) the effect of which was considerable heat loss at night and a reduction in the efficiency of day time warming from the available SW_{\downarrow} , resulting in a rapid cooling of near-surface ice (Figure 4.8) despite a positive average air temp in October (Figure 3.1 a).

5.5.2 Transient “summer” snowfall effects

Transient “summer” snow falls covered the glacier surface for 19 % of the study period. During the 2005 summer the ice surface at the thermistor sites was exposed for a total of 42 days and snow covered for 22 days (between the elimination of the previous winter’s snow pack and the first non ablating snowfalls of the following winter). In the 2006 summer the surface was snow covered for 41 days and snow free for 29 days (Figure 3.9 and 3.15 a). These snowfalls influenced the near-surface ice temperatures in exactly the same way as the seasonal snow pack in terms of an insulation effect and altering the glacier surface albedo. The impact of summer snowfalls on albedo and the consequential dramatic increase in SW_{\uparrow} , the net effect of which was to reduce the energy input at the glacier surface, retarding ablation and temporarily halting the warming of the ice can clearly be seen in Figures 7.9 and 7.10.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

The effect of “summer” snowfall on near-surface ice temperatures depends on the timing of the snowfall. If snow fell early in the summer (soon after exposure of the ice surface), before the winter cold wave has been eliminated, then the impact on near-surface ice temperatures would have been to slow near-surface ice warming and the elimination of the cold wave. Were the snow pack sufficiently deep and to remain on the surface for a sufficiently long period, an insufficient amount of energy would have been supplied to the near-surface ice, preventing warming to pmp throughout its depth before the onset of the following winter. Under such conditions full elimination of the winter cold wave would have been prevented, with implications for the classification of the glacier ice as “temperate” (Section 6.3). If in contrast the “summer” snow fell towards the end of the ablation season in autumn (when the winter cold wave had been eliminated) the effect on the near-surface ice temperatures would be reduced (as the temperature profile would be at melting point throughout), however the snowfall would have implications for ice surface ablation.

Summer snowfall retards ice surface lowering again via its insulating effects, this time from the warm summer air temperatures, and by adding mass to the glacier surface which must be ablated prior to continuation of ice ablation.

5.5.3 Thermal conductivity of snow

Heat transfer through snow or ice via conduction depends on the material’s thermal diffusivity (Carslaw and Jaeger, 1959). As indicated in Equation 1.6.5 thermal diffusivity is governed by thermal conductivity, density and specific heat capacity. Thermal conductivity is defined as the constant of proportionality between the heat transport and the temperature gradient (Sturm *et al.*, 1997). Heat transport through snow is more complex than for solid ice operating via 3 heat transfer processes, in the absence of liquid water in the snow pack, outlined by Sturm *et al.* (1997):

- Conduction through the ice lattice
- Conduction through the air in the pore spaces
- Latent heat transport across pore spaces due to vapour sublimation and condensation.

Results to thermal conductivity calculations in this study are thus interpreted as being effective thermal conductivities including the effects of conduction through the ice lattice, natural and forced convection and latent heat transfer. Calculated thermal conductivity values were compared with upper and lower limits derived from the relations of Van Dusen (1929) and

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

Schwerdtfeger (1963) (Equations 1.6.3 and 1.6.4 respectively) and the range of snow thermal conductivities reported by Sturm *et al.*, (1997).

Background to thermal conductivity determination

Numerous studies using different methods have attempted to quantify the thermal conductivities of snow and ice, from simple temperature change studies as early as Andrews (1886), Hjelstrom (1889) and Abels (1893), laboratory investigations (Yen, 1962), through to recently more complex needle probe studies (Lange, 1985, Sturm and Johnson, 1987, Murakami and Maeno, 1989, Sturm and Johnson, 1992, Sturm *et al.*, 1997). A range of different conductivities has been reported, reflecting the different crystallographic structure, densities and temperatures of the analysed snow.

The basic principle of thermal conductivity determination applied in this study involved monitoring the temperature at a number of depths within the snow pack and ice and calculating thermal diffusivity and conductivity from the attenuation and phase shift of the penetrating temperature cycle compared to the surface temperature forcing cycle (see Figure 5.6 for a diagrammatical representation). Analysis of temperature measurements on other glaciers (e.g. Cameron and Bull, 1962) indicate ice thermal diffusivity and conductivity can be successfully determined from the velocity of penetration and exponential decrease with depth of the amplitude of the annual sinusoidal temperature wave within the near-surface ice. Diurnal sinusoidal temperatures signals originating at depth within the snow pack at BH04-01 and BH04-06, identified as originating from the diurnal charging of the battery in the data logger enclosure, were utilized for determination of snow thermal conductivity (see Figure 3.23 b). Similar diurnal snow temperature cycles of anthropogenic origin have been observed in data sets recovered from Antarctic and Greenland snow packs (Cathles *et al.*, 2007). Cathles *et al.* (2007) attribute the cycles to voltages generated by the data loggers, wire heating and thermistor errors within the data logger enclosures.

Figure 5.6: Diagrammatical representation of the phase lag and amplitude attenuation methods of thermal conductivity determination from recorded temperature cycles.

Method of thermal conductivity calculation

Standard heat flow theory (e.g. Ingersoll *et al.*, 1954; Carslaw and Jaeger, 1959) provides analytical solutions relating the propagation velocity and the amplitude attenuation of temperature waves to the thermal conductivity of the ice / snow layers through which they propagate. Under steady state conditions the flow of heat between two surfaces at different temperatures is proportional to the difference in temperature between the two surfaces (Carslaw and Jaeger, 1959). Fourier’s law of thermal conduction as outlined by Carslaw and Jaeger (1959) states the heat flux is proportional to the temperature gradient, controlled by the thermal conductivity (Equation 1.6.2).

Following the theory outlined by Paterson (1994, p206) for a body with unit cross-section and thickness δz , heat flow at one face is Q whilst at the other it is $Q + (dQ/dz) \delta z$, the difference being $(dQ/dz) \delta z$. The definition of specific heat capacity, c , states that; the change in heat per unit time is $-\rho c(dT/dt) \delta z$, where ρ is the ice density and t is time. Thus it can be written that:

$$-\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial z} = -K \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \tag{5.5.1}$$

where:

- ρ = Density (kg m^{-3}),
- T = Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
- t = Time (s),
- Q = Heat flux (W m^{-2}),
- z = Length (m),

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
 K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),

which can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \kappa \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \quad (5.5.2)$$

where κ is the thermal diffusivity defined in Equation 1.6.5

The penetration and decay of temperature cycles of different periodicities within the top few meters of snow and ice have been used to calculate thermal conductivity based on conduction (Fourier) theory provided a number of assumptions are made (outlined below). Temperature fluctuations near the glacier surface are assumed to be driven only by glacier surface temperature change (or heat generated by battery charging in the case of snow conductivity determination), assumed to take the form:

$$T(0, t) = T(0, 0) + \Delta T_0 \sin(\omega t) \quad (5.5.3)$$

where:

$T(0, t)$ = Surface temperature at time t ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 ΔT_0 = Amplitude of temperature variation ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 $\omega/2\pi$ = Frequency of temperature variation,
 t = Time (s).

For depth z below the surface at time t , the temperature can be calculated from:

$$T(z, t) = T(0, 0) + \Delta T_0 \exp\left(-z\sqrt{\omega/2\kappa}\right) \sin\left(\omega t - z\sqrt{\omega/2\kappa}\right) \quad (5.5.4)$$

where:

$T(z, t)$ = Temperature at depth z at time t ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 ΔT_0 = Amplitude of temperature variation ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
 z = Depth (m),
 $\omega/2\pi$ = Frequency of temperature variation,
 κ = Thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$).

so the amplitude of temperature variations at depth z is:

$$\Delta T_z = \Delta T_0 \exp\left(-z\sqrt{\omega/2\kappa}\right) \quad (5.5.5)$$

Thermal diffusivity can then be found from amplitudes at two depths as:

$$\kappa = \frac{\omega}{2} \left[\frac{z_2 - z_1}{\ln(\Delta T_1 / \Delta T_2)} \right]^2 \quad (5.5.6)$$

or from the time lag between peaks at two depths as:

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{2\omega} \left[\frac{z_1 - z_2}{t_1 - t_2} \right]^2 \quad (5.5.7)$$

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

substituting these values of κ into Equation 1.6.5 and using the specific heat capacity of snow or ice allows determination of the thermal conductivity.

Over diurnal cycles the two hour sampling interval for snow pack temperature data collection was too long to detect accurately differences in the times of temperature peaks and troughs in the vicinity of the different thermistors, preventing use of the time lag method. Thus determination was based on the amplitude attenuation method only (Equation 5.5.6), the equation for phase lag (Equation 5.5.7) is presented above only for completeness.

For snow conductivity determination the specific heat capacity of ice (2097 J kg⁻¹K⁻¹ (Paterson, 1994 p205)) was replaced by the product of the snow density and the heat capacity of the ice to give the specific heat capacity of snow (Langham, 1981). Density values for each snow layer used in the conductivity determination were derived from snow pit density profiles collected on day 114 at BH04-01 and on day 118 at BH04-06 (see Figure 3.18).

Assumptions of the Fourier method

In utilising the Fourier method of thermal conductivity determination the following assumptions were made:

- The annual temperature variation near the surface was a sinusoidal wave of period one year, for the ice thermal conductivity determination and the diurnal snow pack cycles used for snow thermal conductivity had a period of 24 hours.
- Smaller amplitude components of shorter periods superimposed on the annual (or diurnal in the case of the snow) sinusoidal temperature cycles did not influence the penetration of the temperature waves.
- The temperature waves penetrated perpendicular to the ice surface.
- Ice (or snow) throughout the depth subject to the annual or diurnal temperature cycle was homogeneous. This was not the case at Tsanfleuron in the ice determination and especially in the snow determination, thus the analysed ice depth and the snow pack were split into different layers with the physical properties of each individual layer being used to work out the thermal properties.

Sources of error using the Fourier method, which prevent determination of thermal conductivity and only facilitate effective thermal conductivity determination (Sturm *et al.*, 1997) include:

- Solar radiation, convection and wind pumping may enhance heat flow,
- Compaction of the snow during sensor installation may bias results to higher values,

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

- Complex air temperature fluctuations may produce a series of downward propagating temperature waves, incompatible with the simple boundary conditions required for determination.

Pervious studies using this method seemed to produce the best results under conditions of a strong diurnal temperature cycle (Sturm *et al.*, 1997), such as the ~ 0.6 °C amplitude snow temperature variation used in this study.

Tsanfleuron snow thermal conductivity values

Snow thermal conductivities were determined from diurnal temperature cycles recorded at BH04-01 and BH04-06 over an 8 day period in April 2006 (day 108 – 114), the distance above and below the logger enclosure heat source to which analysis could be conducted and the thermal conductivity could be determined was limited by the amplitude of the signal, which was too weak to propagate over a long distance (the effective range of the signal was < 0.4 m). Determination of thermal conductivity values for individual snow layers resulted in a wide range of thermal conductivities related to the physical properties of each snow layer. As the logger enclosures were located at different heights in the snow pack at BH04-01 and BH04-06 (0.75 m and 1.80 m above the surface respectively), combination of the thermal conductivity values determined at different heights at the North and South sites allowed generation of a more detailed profile of snow pack thermal conductivity (see Figure 5.7).

Figure 5.7: Tsanfleuron snow pack thermal conductivity profile determined from attenuation of diurnal anthropogenically derived temperature cycles at BH04-01 and BH04-06 over an 8 day period in April 2006 (day 108 – 114), presented with Sturm *et al.* (1997)’s published snow thermal conductivity range and the upper limit presented by Lange (1985).

Snow thermal conductivities derived at Tsanfleuron ranged between 0.19 and 1.78 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Figure 5.7) compared with a published range of 0.021 to 0.654 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ (Sturm *et al.*, 1997). Thermal diffusivities ranged between 0.22 and 1.91 m² s⁻¹ x 10⁻⁶. Conductivities calculated for BH04-06 at a height of between 1.4 and 1.8 m above the ice surface fell comfortably within the published range (Figure 5.7) and require no further discussion. The anomalously high conductivities of 1.78 and 1.48 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ between 0.4 and 0.8 m above the ice surface in BH04-01, correspond to what was logged in the snow pit stratigraphical survey (conducted on day 114, 2006) as a “Very hard dense homogeneous snow layer” (see Table 3.5). Additionally field notes recorded during the digging of the pit note the exceptional effort required to break through this layer to access the depth hoar and glacier ice surface beneath, resulting in the bending of an aluminium snow shovel. Later notes during the density profiling recorded the fact that it was impossible to insert the density cutter into this layer by hand, necessitating the use of a mallet to drive the cutter into the snow pit wall (results show the density of this cold snow layer to have been 472 kg m⁻³).

Conduction along the steel data logger and solar panel mounting pole (thermal conductivity $17 - 34 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) was initially thought to have contributed to the observed anomalously high snow thermal conductivity at depth in BH04-01. If this were the case one would expect to have observed similarly high thermal conductivities in the vicinity of the BH04-06 mounting pole (as the two logger mounting setups and poles were identical), which was not the case. Additionally if conduction along the pole were augmenting the observed conductivity, one would furthermore logically expect the conductivity of $0.26 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ at $0.8 - 1.0 \text{ m}$ above the ice surface to also be somewhat elevated and out of range – also not the case. Calculated conductivity values at other heights within the snow pack validated the method of derivation and as such combined with the compelling field evidence collected during snow pit excavation and stratigraphical analysis detailing the existence of a very hard snow layer between 0.14 and 0.85 m above the ice surface. It is suggested that these thermal conductivities are real, resulting from the density and hardness of this anomalous snow layer.

The snow pack as an insulator

Snow is an excellent thermal insulator (primarily as a consequence of air trapped within the snow), moderating the conductive, sensible and latent heat transfers between the glacier surface and the atmosphere (Liston, 1995, Hinzman *et al.*, 1998, Nelson *et al.*, 1998 and Liston and Elder, 2006b). The thicker the snow the greater the insulating effect. Near-surface ice temperatures drop rapidly at the end of the ablation season under exposed or shallow snow cover, however, they remain stable over the winter once covered by a sufficiently deep snow pack (a few decimetres (Pettersson *et al.*, 2007)). The insulating effect of the seasonal snow pack at Tsanfleuron is graphically illustrated by the sharp near-surface ice temperature drops experienced following the excavation of snow pits exposing the ice surface at BH04-01 on days 335 (2004), 56 (2005) and 112 (2005) followed by gradual warming back to the pre disturbance temperatures (Figure 4.5 and 4.8 a).

5.5.4 Internal snow pack energy

During the late spring / early summer melt period the snow pack was a significant surface energy sink due to the large amount of energy addition required to generate melt, resulting from the relatively high latent heat of fusion and the “cold content” of the snow pack. The internal energy of the snow pack or “cold content” refers to the amount of energy required to raise the average snow pack temperature to melting point. The snow pack can be considered as an energy reservoir storing energy input during the early ablation season using it to ripen the snow pack, making it

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

isothermal at 0 °C before melt water percolates through to the ice surface and begins warming the near -surface ice later in ablation season. The internal energy was calculated in the form:

$$Q_{IE} = C_i \rho_s h_s (T_s - T_m) \quad (5.5.8)$$

where:

- Q_{IE} = Internal energy or cold content ($J m^{-2}$),
- C_i = Specific heat of ice ($2097 J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$ at 0 °C (Paterson, 1994, p205)),
- ρ_s = Snow density ($kg m^{-3}$),
- h_s = Snow height (m),
- T_s = Average snow temperature (°C),
- T_m = Melting temperature of ice (°C).

An alternative way to consider the cold content of the snow pack is in terms of the number of millimetres of water required to be added to the snow pack which on freezing would raise the snow pack temperature to 0 °C, in the form:

$$W_c = \frac{\rho_s h_s T_s}{(1000 L_f / C_i)} \quad (5.5.9)$$

where:

- W_c = Cold content of the snow expressed as an amount of liquid water (mm),
- ρ_s = Snow density ($kg m^{-3}$),
- h_s = Snow height (m),
- T_s = Average snow temperature (°C),
- L_f = Latent heat of fusion ($333.5 kJ kg^{-1}$ at 0 °C (Paterson, 1994, p205)),
- C_i = Specific heat of ice ($2097 J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$ at 0 °C (Paterson, 1994, p205)).

Table 5.2 presents a summary of the manually measured snow pack temperature gradients, conductive heat fluxes through the snow packs, snow pack internal energy content and the depth of water addition required to ripen the snow pack at each of the three sites at the times of snow pit analysis.

		<i>Temperature gradient</i> (°C m ⁻¹)	<i>Snow Depth</i> (m)	<i>Conductive heat Flux</i> (W m ⁻²)	<i>Snow pack internal energy</i> (kJ m ⁻²)	<i>Depth of water refreezing to ripen snow pack</i> (mm)
Jan 2006	BH04-01	-1.16	1.73	-0.29	-9409	28.0
	BH04-06	-2.96	1.69	-0.74	-9631	28.7
	BH05-07	-4.02	1.74	-1.01	-10359	30.9
Apr 2006	BH04-01	-1.02	3.94	-0.26	-11111	33.1
	BH04-06	-1.04	3.86	-0.26	-12357	36.8
	BH05-07	-0.97	4.12	-0.24	-10290	30.7
Jan 2007	BH04-01	-3.67	2.18	-0.92	-10082	30.1
	BH04-06	-3.94	2.03	-0.99	-11149	33.2
	BH05-07	-3.38	2.07	-0.85	-9569	28.5

Table 5.2: Temperature gradient, conductive heat flux and internal energy of Tsanfleuron snow packs at the times of snow pit analysis in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007. Conductive fluxes were determined assuming a snow effective thermal conductivity of 0.25 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹.

Considering for example the January 2006 snow pits, (the thermal properties of which are summarized in Table 5.2) BH05-07 appears to have experienced the greatest cooling due to a temperature gradient across the snow pack of - 4.02 °C m⁻¹ resulting in a conductive heat flux toward the atmosphere of -1.01 W m⁻² compared to a conductive heat flux to the atmosphere of - 0.029 W m⁻² for BH04-01 and - 0.74 W m⁻² for BH04-06. If this pattern of non uniform cooling were not an isolated incident and occurred over the duration of the winter, the timing of snow pack ripening and thus the subsequent beginning of near-surface ice warming would consequently vary across the glacier surface. Assuming the pattern of warming reflected the pattern of cooling, ice temperatures would first have experienced warming at BH04-01, as this site would have been the first to become isothermal at 0 °C and transfer liquid water and advected heat to the base of the snow pack, secondly at BH04-06 and finally at BH05-07. This predicted pattern of warming reflected the lower average density of snow at BH04-01 and BH04-06 (see Table 3.3) and greater conductive heat loss at BH05-07 resulting in a higher cold content, - 10359 kJ m⁻² compared to - 9409 kJ m⁻² and - 9631 kJ m⁻² for BH04-01 and BH04-06 respectively (assuming uniform surface energy receipt across the glacier surface for snow pack warming). Data logger malfunction and missing thermistor data as a result, prevented evaluation of this theory.

Conductive heat flux through the snow pack

Conductive heat fluxes through the snow pack at the times of the winter snow pits ranged from - 0.24 to - 1.01 W m⁻². The direction of heat flow was toward the atmosphere away from the

glacier surface in all cases. January in both years exhibited larger and more variable fluxes than April 2006 (-0.29 to -1.01 W m⁻² compared to -0.24 to -0.26 W m⁻² respectively) as a consequence of the shallower January snow pack and the colder near-surface snow layers. The average snow effective thermal conductivity derived for the Tsanfleuron snow pack (excluding the anomalously high conductivity layers in BH04-01) was 0.25 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, compared to the glacier ice thermal conductivity of 1.96 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹. Thus for a given temperature gradient the conductive heat flux through snow at Tsanfleuron would only be ~ 13 % of that through ice.

Summary

- The main influence of the snow pack over near-surface ice temperatures stems from:
 - i. its insulating properties,
 - ii. the control of melt water (and thus advected and latent heat) supply to the ice surface,
 - iii. the control of the SW_↓ and SW_↑ radiation interaction at the glacier surface through albedo.
- The seasonal winter snow pack insulates the ice surface, limiting heat loss and keeping near-surface temperatures considerably warmer than if the snow pack were not present. The over winter snow pack also controls that rate of ice surface warming in spring and early summer by mediating energy transfer to the ice surface as air temperatures and SW_↓ increased.
- Snow pack hydrological processes controlled the transfer of surface-derived melt supplying advected heat and liquid water for refreezing and latent heat release to the ice surface during spring. This, in turn controlled the warming of the near-surface ice and the initiation of the elimination of the winter cold wave.
- Transient summer snowfalls dramatically increase the surface albedo, reduce the net energy input to the glacier surface, decrease energy transfer to the ice surface, and add mass, which required ablating before further ice surface lowering could proceed.
- Snow thermal conductivity determined using the Fourier temperature wave attenuation method ranged between 0.19 and 1.78 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹.
- Snow thermal diffusivities ranged between 0.22 and 1.91 m² s⁻¹ x 10⁻⁶.

- Abnormally high conductivities of 1.78 and $1.48 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ between 0.4 and 0.8 m above the ice surface at BH04-01 are considered real and a result of a “Very hard dense homogeneous snow layer” (472 kg m^{-3}) studied during the snow pit analysis.
- Conductive heat fluxes through the snow pack at the times of the winter snow pits were away from the surface, higher in January than April and ranged from -0.24 to -1.01 W m^{-2} .

5.6 The influence of fractures and crevasses on ice temperatures

Crevasses form when ice is subjected to a super-critical tensile stress. The ablation zone of Glacier de Tsanfleuron is highly crevassed with small closely spaced crevasses. On the North side of the glacier, in the shadow of the Oldenhorn, transverse crevasses form high on the glacier (at an altitude of ~ 2800 m, Figure 2.1) and widen as the ice flows down slope towards the snout. On the South side of the glacier between an elevation of ~ 2800 and 2700 m ice flows through a surface topographic depression, in this region crevasses are closed via compressional flow in the concavity, below ~ 2700 m crevasses reopen. The presence of crevasses in the glacier surface ice has a profound effect on the supraglacial drainage and energy transfer downwards into the near-surface ice. BH04-01 and BH05-07 (the North and Central sites respectively) were both located in close proximity to small crevasses. BH04-01 was situated ~ 1 m up glacier of a 1.2 m wide crevasse in August 2005, by September 2005 the crevasse wall had melted backwards to a distance of ~ 0.5 m from the borehole. Over winter no changes in crevasse position relative to the borehole were recorded, while little melt back of the crevasse wall occurred in the summer of 2006 as a consequence of prolonged summer surface snow cover. At BH05-07 a 1.4 m wide crevasse located 1.75 m up glacier of the borehole was instrumented in August 2005 with thermistors to a depth of 6 m to investigate the thermal influence of the crevasse on the surrounding ice. Melting from the time of thermistor deployment to September 2005 resulted in dramatic surface lowering (0.98 m), but little melt back of the crevasse wall and similar characteristics to the crevasse at the North site over winter and during summer 2006. BH04-06 (the South site) was located in region devoid of fractures and crevasses and consequently exhibited a well developed supraglacial drainage network.

5.6.1 Crevasse temperatures and heat transfer processes

Crevasses act as both heat sources and sinks, transferring energy to the adjacent ice via:

1. Conduction of heat from warmer air in the crevasse, the temperature of which is controlled by atmospheric processes when the crevasse is open to the atmosphere,
2. Advection of heat via macro-porous flow of surface-derived meltwater into englacial locations,
3. Latent heat release on refreezing of water running down the crevasse walls and ponding at depth within crevasses.

Heat conduction between crevasses and adjacent ice is controlled by the temperature difference between the ice and the air. Air temperatures in the crevasse are controlled by the atmosphere in summer and early autumn, when the crevasse is open and devoid of snow bridging. Air temperatures in the crevasses in summer were lower than the 2 m air temperature as colder air is denser and consequently sits lower to the glacier surface and flows under gravity into the crevasses. Such ponding of cold air in crevasses results in an air temperature profile in the crevasse, with the warmest air near the glacier surface and the coldest temperatures at the bottom of the crevasse (Figure 4.20). The first ~ 1 m or so of air in the crevasse below the surface is subject to turbulent mixing with the atmosphere, the effect of which is to incorporate warmer air (in summer), maintaining the temperature profile of warmer air near-surface. Further down the crevasse, mixing is reduced with isolation from the glacier surface and colder air at the bottom of the crevasse is warmed only slowly, even during warm summer periods.

During winter, conditions the crevasses are snow bridged and isolated from the atmosphere. At this time the temperature of air trapped in the crevasse will likely gradually equilibrate with the surrounding ice, before again becoming a heat source when ablation of the snow bridge occurs the following summer.

Air temperature measurements in the instrumented crevasse show seasonal variation (Figure 4.11), with highly fluctuating positive temperatures, of up to 14.5 °C at a depth of 1 m below the surface in the summer of 2005. Temperatures decrease and fluctuate less deeper below the ice surface. The time of snow bridging can be inferred from the rapid temperature drop observed in the near-surface thermistors, at the beginning of November in 2005 and in mid October in 2006 (Figure 4.11), which correspond with the first winter snow falls (Figure 3.15 a). The early bridging of the crevasse under a relatively shallow snow pack, allied to an absence of change in the temperature profile at depth in the crevasse suggests closure by a surface crust rather than by snow-filling to depth.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

A steep vertical crevasse air temperature gradient of $\sim 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ from surface to the colder air at 6 m depth in the crevasses existed in August 2005 and 2006 (Figure 4.20). This gradient decreased to $\sim 0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ during winter, in response to snow bridging of the crevasse preventing drainage of much colder winter atmospheric air and a gradual cooling of trapped air near the top of the crevasse. Locally, positive daily mean air temperatures of as high as $4.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded in the upper 2 m of the crevasse during summer months (Figure 5.8 and Figure 4.20). During such positive temperatures the crevasse acted as a heat source. Between 2 and 4 m below the ice surface, air temperatures were close to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in summer, decreasing to as low as $\sim -2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in winter. With local ice temperature below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the crevasse remained a heat source in this zone, though of reduced magnitude relative to that near the surface. Below 4 m depth in the crevasse daily mean temperatures dropped as low as $\sim -3.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in winter and did not (for the duration of this study period) exceed $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 5.8) and, as such, whether or not the crevasse acted as a heat source or sink was dependent upon the temperature difference between the adjacent ice and the sub zero air temperatures.

Figure 5.8: Contour plot of daily mean temperature variation with depth below the ice surface in the crevasse adjacent to BH05-07 over the period of data collection, August 2005 to February 2007 (expressed as cumulative day since the beginning of 2004 with the period of missing data (day 786 to 946) blanked out).

The temperature difference between the crevasse air and the BH05-07 borehole thermistors allowed determination of the horizontal temperature gradient through the $\sim 1.75\text{ m}$ of ice separating the borehole and the crevasse. Figure 5.9 depicts the horizontal ice temperature gradient for the duration of the study period. From the ice surface to a depth of $\sim 2\text{ m}$ for the period for which data is available, the temperature gradient was positive for all but a short period in winter, indicating the direction of energy flow was from the crevasse into the ice, with a very

small reversal for short periods in winter. Between ~ 2 and ~ 3.5 m below the surface temperature gradients were close to zero suggesting little or no horizontal energy transfer, while below 3.5 m horizontal ice temperature gradients were negative indicating energy flows towards the crevasse out of the ice.

Figure 5.9: Contour plot of horizontal daily mean temperature gradient between the crevasse and the thermistor string deployed in the adjacent BH05-07 over the period of data collection August 2005 to February 2007 (expressed as day since the beginning of 2004, with the period of missing data (day 786 to 946) blanked out).

5.6.2 Crevasses as heat sinks

Negative horizontal temperature gradients (air to ice) below ~ 3 m depth in the crevasse (Figure 5.9) indicate the crevasse was acting as a heat sink, drawing energy from and cooling the surrounding ice. Below ~ 3 m depth the crevasse acted as a heat sink throughout both years, even in summer. The magnitude of the horizontal temperature gradient at depth in the crevasse shows only a limited annual cycle, with the gradient becoming slightly less in late summer and autumn. The greatest horizontal energy flows out of the ice to the crevasse occurred on day 783 (21st February 2006) at a depth of 6 m under a temperature gradient of -2.39 $^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$, which equates to a lateral heat flux of -4.68 W m^{-2} (based on an ice thermal conductivity of 1.96 $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, Section 6.2.1).

Winter maximum heat loss from the ice to the crevasse occurs as a result of the ponding of the coldest air at the bottom of the crevasse. The coldest air entered the crevasse in early winter prior to the development of the snow bridge, sunk to the bottom of the crevasse and experienced further limited cooling as the winter progressed. The lack of notable summer warming below

~ 3 m depth in the crevasse suggested warmer atmospheric air did not sink or mix with the air in the bottom of the crevasse, due to density differences and a lack of turbulent mixing. The air at the bottom of the crevasse remained below zero and was only warmed by conduction of heat from the adjacent ice which in turn was warmed via conduction and advection of heat downwards from the ice surface.

5.6.3 Crevasses as heat sources

Positive horizontal temperature gradients (air to ice) in the upper ~ 2 to 3 m of the crevasse (Figure 5.9) indicated the crevasse was acting as a heat source, adding energy to, and warming, the surrounding ice. Crevasse air temperature maxima of ~ 14.5 °C were observed at a depth of 1 m below the ice surface during August 2005. Daily mean horizontal temperature gradients in the ice between the crevasse and the borehole exhibited a maximum of 7.95 °C m⁻¹ at 1 m below the ice surface in September 2005 and minima of - 0.09 °C m⁻¹ in winter (indicating a small reversal of the temperature gradient for a short period when air temperatures dropped below those of the adjacent ice) equating to positive energy fluxes into the ice of 15.58 W m⁻² and -0.18 W m⁻² respectively.

In summer, when the crevasse was snow free and open to the atmosphere, surface meteorological processes and turbulent mixing warmed the crevasse air just below the ice surface. Near-surface crevasse air temperatures were thus closely linked to air temperature recorded by the meteorological station and the magnitude of the heat source varied with air temperature (Figure 5.10). Summer diurnal fluctuations in the magnitude of the energy flux between the crevasse and the adjacent ice varied considerably in response to the daily air temperature rise and nocturnal cooling, for example day 616 (8th September 2005) (Figure 5.10).

Figure 5.10: Time series plot of horizontal ice temperature gradient at 1 m below the surface between the crevasse and the adjacent BH05-07 and 2 m air temperature between cumulative time day 610 and 620 (JD244 to 254, 2005).

In addition to conduction controlled by air temperature, meltwater derived from the ablating snow pack in late spring drained through the crevasses (running down the ice walls). This heat flux was not measured by the thermistor string suspended vertically down the middle of the crevasse. Thus, a potentially large heat source associated with the crevasses remains unquantified. These may have provided a large amount of heat in the late spring and early summer, before the snow bridge collapsed, and later in the summer, once melt was generated by surface ice lowering. If ponding of this water occurred at depth in spring and summer, the crevasse would further have acted as a heat source as water froze and latent heat was released leading to a large localised heat addition to the surrounding ice. Snow bridging of crevasses has been reported to, facilitate the presence of liquid water at the base of crevasses during the winter at a depth below the penetration of the winter cold wave (Miller, 1954). Such liquid water would also act as a localised heat source warming the surrounding ice. No evidence for ponding of water in the instrumented Tsanfleuron crevasse has been recorded (at least to depths which are visible from the surface and to which sensors have been deployed): temperatures at 6 m below the surface remained negative (~ -3 °C) throughout the year, suggesting no occurrence of liquid water at this depth. This lack of water ponding in the instrumented crevasse indicates drainage from the crevasse to the englacial drainage system. It is thus assumed that positive heat transfers from the

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

crevasse to the adjacent ice occurred via conduction (as well as the unmeasured advection of heat by melt water running down the crevasse wall) and not by englacial heat supply from ponded water.

The crevasse in the vicinity of BH05-07 provided a continuous heat source to the adjacent ice to a depth of ~ 2 to 3 m throughout the year (similar effects were probably felt at BH04-01, assuming that the adjacent crevasse exhibited similar temperature patterns and energy fluxes). In summer the magnitude of this energy flux increased, providing a mechanism to speed the near-surface ice temperature rise to melting point (eliminating the winter cold wave more quickly than if the crevasse were not present e.g. at BH04-06). However, the crevasse acted as a less effective heat sink (below 4 m depth), locally slowing the elimination of the winter cold wave.

In the absence of crevasses and any form of macro-scale drainage into the englacial system, energy transfer at the South site was limited to vertical conduction through the ice and very limited advection and latent heat release on refreezing of micro-porous water percolation. Thus, it is postulated that if BH04-06 were not in a zone of flow compression and crevasses were present, melting point would be reached to a greater depth than was reached under current conditions. This absence of crevasses at BH04-06 means that the site does not experience macro-scale surface permeability, facilitating heat and water transfer into the ice surface and removing the surface slush and limiting the associated processes (see Section 5.7). The heating effect of crevasses however, can only serve to increase the ice temperature locally.

Summary

- Crevasses can act simultaneously as both heat sources and sinks to the near-surface ice, depending on depth in the crevasse.
- The magnitude of the heat source effect measured in the instrumented crevasse is likely an underestimate of the true thermal effect of the crevasse as calculations are based solely on air temperatures. No account is made for heat advection by meltwater running down crevasse walls or the refreezing of that water.
- To a depth of ~ 2 to 3 m below the ice surface the instrumented crevasse acts as a heat source in both summer and winter, occasional small reversals occur in the direction of the flux in winter.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

- Crevasse air temperatures, and consequently heat supply to the adjacent ice, were closely linked to the 2 m air temperature recorded at the meteorological station in summer when the crevasse was snow free.
- Below 4 m depth, the crevasse acts as a heat sink in both summer and winter, characterised by limited seasonal variability.
- Vertical air temperature gradients in the crevasse peak in summer at $\sim 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C m}^{-1}$ when the crevasse was open to the atmosphere, decreasing to $\sim 0.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C m}^{-1}$ during winter when the crevasse was snow bridged.
- The maximum positive lateral heat flux of 15.58 W m^{-2} into the ice between the crevasse and BH05-07 occurred on day 624 (16th September 2005).
- The maximum negative lateral heat flux out of the ice was equal to -4.68 W m^{-2} on day 783 (21st February 2006).

5.7 Differential across-glacier ice ablation

Surface elevation change was measured at the North site (BH04-01) continuously by means of an SR50 UDG, and basic ice surface ablation measurements were made at all three sites during field visits using the “straight edge” method (Muller and Keeler, 1969) for the determination of the location of near-surface thermistors. A number of problems were encountered with the SR50 UDG data especially in terms of noise from late spring 2006 onwards. Comparison of records between the SR50 at the North site (installed in February 2005), and a shorter time series from an SR50 at South site (BH04-06) (installed in August 2006), between August 2006 and February 2007 suggested very similar snow depth records, but with considerably more noise at the North SR50. This increasing noise was probably due to sensor deterioration (most probably degradation affecting the diaphragm used to produce the ultrasonic pulse) and oscillation and fluctuation of the SR50 in the wind. The noise is unlikely to be due to the interaction of the sound pulse with sloping or an uneven glacier surface as the sensor detects and makes its calculations from the first detected signal return and not from a distribution of the return signal. Other problems encountered using the SR50s included small diurnal fluctuations in the position of the surface, probably due to incomplete temperature correction as a consequence of the non-coincident heights of the temperature sensor and the SR50 and apparent accumulation observed during

summer 2005 (of up to 5 cm at night (see Figure 3.8)). Willis *et al.*, (2002) outline three possible explanations for this apparent nocturnal accumulation:

- 1) “error associated with the contraction of the vertical instrument mounting pole as it cools (likely to be only on the order of $\pm 0.05 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$).”
- 2) “error in the estimation of distance between the SR50 and the surface, due to error in the temperature measurement and subsequent air density correction due to the temperature measurement being made at a different height. (especially if the temperature relationship above the surface varied with time e.g. from log-linear by day to logarithmic at night resulting in greater over estimation by day than at night which would manifest itself as a nocturnal accumulation).”
- 3) “freezing of water or water vapour on to the glacier surface.”

An additional possible explanation may in part be due to thermal expansion (by day) and contraction (by night) of the SR50 itself (N.Rutter, Pers.comm.)⁶ or a combination of the above.

Snow pack ablation at the North site (determined by SR50; Figure 3.15), removed 3.6 m of snow in 2004, 3.83 m in 2005 and 4.40 m in 2006. Estimates of snow ablation at the Central site (BH05-07) had to be made as no SR50 measurements were recorded here (a second SR50 was deployed at the South site in August 2006). Intermittent manual point measurements of snow depth in winter (and ice surface position in summer) were recorded at all three sites. Point summer ice ablation measurements were based on a selection of different measurements including: melt-out of thermistor cables, measured lowering around data logger and thermistor mounting poles, measured height of meteorological instruments, and field photography. To derive a surface elevation time series for South and Central site, SR50 measurements from North site were transformed to fit manually derived ice surface “tie points” (as outlined in Section 4.1.1).

5.7.1 Across glacier ice surface ablation variation

Large differences were measured in rates of surface ablation between the three boreholes located at approximately the same altitude in a line across glacier. Similar variability in across glacier ablation to that observed in this study has been reported e.g. by Konya *et al.* (2004) and Fountain and Vecchia (1999) using datasets collected by Meier *et al.* (1971) and Tangborn *et al.* (1977) from South Cascade Glacier and Maclure Glacier respectively. At South Cascade Glacier,

⁶ Dr Nick Rutter, Centre for Glaciology, University of Wales Aberystwyth.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

ablation stake mass balance differences of up to 2 m water equivalent (in 1965) were reported at a given altitude across the glacier, while the 1967 data from Maclure Glacier display differences of up to 4 m of water equivalent. Such differences were explained by Van de wal *et al.* (1992) to be due entirely to variations in surface albedo.

Ice surface ablation in the summers of 2005 and 2006 was considerably greater at the South site than at North and Central sites (Table A3). Between 1.61 m and 2.40 m of ice in 2005 (Table A3) and 1.29 m of ice in 2006 were ablated at the South site, compared with 0.63 m and 0.90 m of ice surface lowering at the North site and ~ 0.98 m and 0.42 m of lowering at the Central site (Table A3 and Figures 4.2 and 4.3). In the absence of high resolution ablation data for the three locations, only an evaluation of the annual absolute values of surface lowering can be carried out.

5.7.2 Controlling processes

Possible causes of the observed differential ablation rates are considered below:

Air temperature

One would not expect a large air temperature difference between the North, Central and South sites as the three sites are at approximately the same altitude (2792 m, 2803 m and 2777 m a.s.l. respectively) with an elevation change of 26 m yielding a temperature difference of 0.17 °C (assuming a lapse rate of 0.65 / 100 m). During a period of simultaneous meteorological station operation at the North and South sites (between August 2006 and January 2007) temperatures were observed to vary together, identical maxima of 14.4 °C, minima of -22.56 °C at the North and -20.47 °C at the South were recorded. When plotted against each other, the time series produce a linear relationship with an R^2 value of 0.98. It is thus concluded that air temperature differences were unlikely the cause of the differential ablation rates.

Wind

The three sites were in slightly different settings, the North and Central site were exposed near the crest of a large scale surface undulation and the South site was in a hollow. These locations could have a role to play in terms of local wind variability. If the three sites were influenced by contrasting wind regimes, there is a possibility that transport of warmer air (possibly in summer, originating over the warmer exposed bedrock in closer proximity to the South site) could be linked to the higher ablation rates. Simultaneous wind data collection at the North and South sites between August 2006 and January 2007 indicate very similar wind regimes at both

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

locations, blowing predominantly down glacier at similar speeds. Thus contrasting wind regimes are considered unlikely to cause the ablation differences.

Shading by surrounding topography

Surrounding topography can influence ablation through shading (influencing the SW↓ and SW↑ balance). The lack of large relief features to the South and West of Tsanfleuron results in minimal shading during daylight hours (Figure 5.2), yielding a near uniform distribution of global radiation over the whole glacier, eliminating topographic shading as a cause of variability.

Glacier surface topography

Depressions in the glacier surface can affect the radiation receipt on a local scale, primarily influencing the SW↓ interaction with the surface. In contrast to a level plane, depressions alter the angle of incidence at which the SW↓ flux strikes the sloping faces. On the South facing side of a concavity, the angle of incidence is increased, increasing absorption and thus ablation. The South site was located at the bottom of such a depression. This concavity may result in slightly higher SW↓ absorption on the South facing slope, compared to that at the relatively flat-surfaced North and Central sites, especially when the sun is lower in the sky later in the ablation season. An examination of the net radiation time series over the period August 2006 to November 2006 (when two NR Lite net radiometers were running simultaneously at the North and South sites) suggests the South site receives slightly higher net radiation than the North indicating more energy is available for melt. SW↓, LW↓ and LW↑ are likely very similar at both locations thus the differences in net radiation are most probably due to SW↑ variations between the two sites. Lower SW↑ at the South site relative to the North may be accounted for if absorption into the surface were higher as a consequence of the local topography increasing the angle of incidence of SW and or the presence of a rougher surface at the South site (see below). However, it cannot be overlooked that the radiation differences may completely or in part be an artefact of sensor degradation, calibration drift and or changes in the angle of either sensor following installation. Though the argument for topographically controlled increased SW↓ absorption at the South site is compelling, a definitive answer cannot be reached based on the available evidence.

Snow depth differences

Snow depth transects across the glacier (Figures 3.17 and 3.18 and Table 3.3) and snow pits dug in January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007 (see Tables 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7) indicate little variation in the snow depths between the three sites, with depths of 1.73, 1.69 and 1.74 m in January 2006, 3.94, 3.86 and 4.12 m in April 2006 and 2.18, 2.03 and 2.07 m in January 2007

respectively. Snow density profiles in the pits (Figure 3.17) and snow water equivalent (SWE) calculations (Table 3.3.) also suggest similar masses of snow are present across the glacier.

Albedo

Glacier surface albedo during the early ablation season is likely similar at all three borehole locations, reflecting that of an aging, decaying, waterlogged snow pack. Once the snow pack had ablated the albedo drops drastically to that of dirty glacier ice, again similar at all three locations. Albedo differences with the potential to initiate different ablation rates, and thus different annual ablation totals could arise through the snow pack ablating more quickly at one location than the others, thereby exposing the ice to ablation for longer. The same is true in terms of the speed of removal of any summer snowfalls. Thus if a mechanism were identified which could remove the snow pack more quickly at the South site than the others the surface energy balance and ablation would be notably affected by the associated albedo changes and the measured ablation differences could also be explained.

Having eliminated a number of possible controlling factors an explanation for the differences in ice surface ablation between the three across glacier sites, directly influenced by the glacier geometry, is outlined below. Higher rates of ice surface lowering at the South site relative to the other sites are explained via its location in a surface hollow. The presence of the ice surface concavity results in different surface drainage characteristics at the South site, affecting the glacier surface morphology and enabling the initiation of snow pack removing slush flows.

5.7.3 Glacier surface morphological control

The South site was located just above the bottom of a small South facing concavity in the ice surface (Figure 6.5). Small ephemeral channels feeding a supraglacial stream (Figure 2.2) were observed to develop during the summer of 2005 and at the end of the 2006 summer on the South and East facing slopes of the concavity, and rapid thawing of snow prevails during late May, June and July. No macro-scale drainage into the ice can occur through crevasses (which open in response to strain rate; a function of local bed geometry and velocity field) (Section 5.6). The low surface permeability has resulted in the formation of a network of small anastomosing drainage channels in the ice surface, which allow advection of heat across the glacier surface via water flow from up-glacier. In summer, when the snow pack has ablated, slush pools form (to a depth of ~ 15 cm for much of the 2005 ice ablation season). Ice surface ablation beneath standing surface water in the form of supraglacial lakes has been reported to be enhanced by up to 170 % compared to that for bare ice (Luthje *et al.*, 2006). As water depth increases, surface

reflection is decreased by increasing scattering and absorption (Morassuti and LeDrew, 1996), which amplifies melt (Curry *et al.*, 1995; Perovich *et al.*, 2002). Perovich *et al.* (2002) argued that the presence of melt ponds decreases summer sea ice albedo from 0.65 to 0.4, enhancing surface ablation. Similarly, melt rates beneath standing water on Arctic sea ice have been quoted as being 2 to 3 times higher than for bare ice (Fetterer and Untersteiner, 1998). Thus, advected heat across the ice surface and standing water enhancing surface lowering may in part explain the higher ablation rates at the South site relative to the North and Central sites.

The ice surface at the North and Central sites differs considerably from that at the South site. The ice surface at the South site was rougher over a larger micro-scale vertical range than the North and Central sites as a consequence of the small anastomosing melt channels present there. Additionally, nocturnal freezing of the slush surface later in the ablation season, formed a coarse surface crust, increasing surface roughness. Thus, in addition to routing water and advecting heat over the glacier surface, the supraglacial melt channels increase $SW\downarrow$ absorption (and thus ablation) due to multiple reflections between coarse crystals and ice forms, and as such the South site absorbed greater amounts of energy than the other sites promoting enhanced surface lowering.

5.7.4 Slush flows

The insulating properties of the remnant winter snow pack (Section 5.5) protect the ice surface from warming air temperatures and increasing $SW\downarrow$ until the snow pack fully ablates towards the end of July. However, the removal of large volumes of snow at the South site, would expose the ice surface earlier, allowing a longer period of ablation relative to the North and Central sites. In addition to morphologically controlled surface ablation, the low permeability of the ice surface at the South site and the topographic drainage focussing in the hollow present ideal conditions for slush flow formation.

Slush flows are rapid down-slope movements of wet snow (Washburn, 1979), often seasonal in nature, occurring where the water table reaches the snow / firn surface. Factors influencing the formation of slush flows are deep snow, an ice surface beneath the snow, topographical features which may dam melt-water and rapid thawing of snow (Rapp, 1960; Jahn, 1967 and Clarke and Seppala, 1988), they are therefore repeatable at a given location (Clarke and Seppala, 1988). Certain meteorological conditions including intense rainfall (Hestnes, 1985 and Clarke and Seppala, 1988), abnormally high relative humidity (Clarke and Seppala, 1988) and sustained air temperatures above 0 °C (Onesti, 1985) also favour slush flows. Slush flows are topographically

controlled (but have been observed to occur on gentle slopes, below 10° (Nyberg, 1989)), converge into depressions and tend to follow the head-ward retreat of broad channels on the glacier surface, often clearing supraglacial streams of snow earlier than surrounding slopes (Smart *et al.*, 2000). The strong ablation effects of slush flows result from their catastrophic nature, implying a concerted short phase of erosion, similar to a flash flood (Nyberg, 1989). On Brewster Glacier, New Zealand (a similar sized “temperate” valley glacier to Tsanfleuron) slush flows induced by heavy rainfall saturating the snow pack over impermeable ice accounted for up to 5 m of snow surface lowering over a 26 day period in early summer (Smart *et al.*, 2000).

All four of the factors favouring slush flow formation as outlined above occur at the South site in early summer of both 2005 and 2006, snow depth was > 3 m, the ice surface was cold, devoid of crevasses and surface cracks and was impermeable (to within a ~ 200 m radius of BH04-06), supporting a small, fast flowing supraglacial stream. Slush flows occur regularly in the vicinity of the South site on Tsanfleuron and may therefore help to explain the larger ablation rates (relative to the other sites) recorded there (Table A3). The slush flow observed in August 2005 during the ablation of a summer snowfall was captured in a series of time lapse photographs (Figure 5.11). It is suggested that similar or larger slush flows would also have occurred before this period of observation, during the early summer (when the main snow pack was saturated and ablating).

Heavy convective rainfall events in the later afternoons were common during the spring ablation season, and have the capability to increase dramatically the snow pack water level to saturation point, triggering slush flows at the South site. During the 2005 ablation season, a distinct rainfall event occurred during a late afternoon thunderstorm on the 24th June (day 175) which was noted in the local media as exhibiting “a very high rain fall rate” (news.search.ch, 2005) causing local flash flooding and a 0.6 m mud slide into the town of Les Diablerets (F.Labarre, Pers.comm)⁷. This, combined with sustained temperatures of in the range 5 to 12 °C for the preceding 7 days (Figure 3.1 a) and the presence of 1.67 m snow (measured at the North site), presumably under saturated isothermal snow pack conditions suggest ideal conditions for slush flow initiation. Similar meteorological conditions favouring slush flow formation also occurred in the 2006 ablation season. For example, heavy precipitation events on isothermal snow occurred on the 29th May (day 149), depositing 34 – 44 mm precipitation, on June 25th (day 177) and again on July 5th (day 186) when up to 50 mm of precipitation fell, accompanied by very high air

⁷ Ms Florence Labarre, Glacier 3000, Les Diablerets, VD, Switzerland.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

temperatures (Meteosuisse.ch, 2006) providing considerable amounts of water to saturate the melting snow pack. If slush flows had occurred at these times, the potential existed for erosion of some or all of the over-winter snow pack, exposing the ice surface to ablation 34 days before the North and Central sites in 2005 and 23 or 32 days before the North and Central sites in 2006. If the ice surface were exposed earlier at the South site than at the North and Central site, the ice would thus have been subjected to a longer ablation season (and at a time of greater intensity $SW\downarrow$ (Figure 7.4), providing a possible explanation for the greater ablation observed at the South site. Modelling experiments to investigate the influence of slush flows over ice surface lowering are presented in Section 7.6.4.

Slush flows will not occur to such a degree at the North and Central sites due to the absence of flow focussing concavities and the presence of crevasses in these areas. Over a number of ablation seasons slush and melt drainage have probably accentuated the concavity, capturing more surface drainage. As the concavity has developed the radiation balance changed and an increasing amount of $SW\downarrow$ is absorbed on the South facing slope (due to an increasing angle of incidence as the depression deepens), increasing the ablation rate and further accentuating depression formation. This feedback is restricted spatially by the presence of permeable ice and crevasses, limiting slush flows by transferring surface melt-waters into the glacier.

Figure 5.11: Time lapse images (in the order (a)-(f)) of a small slush flow (~ 70 m long) over a ~ 30 second period at approximately 1300 on day 221 (2005) in the topographic concavity in which the South site is situated (photos taken by the author whilst standing at the BH04-06 borehole conducting routine maintenance of the thermistor station, alerted to the occurrence by the characteristic roaring sound).

Summary

- The South site experienced notably greater (~ 20 % averaged over 3 ablation seasons) surface ablation than North and Central sites over the 2005 and 2006 ablation season.
- Surface topography appears to influence the radiation budget at the South site, facilitating greater SW↓ absorption, enhancing ablation.
- Ice surface permeability influences the rate of surface ablation by influencing the flow paths for surface melt and the micro-scale ice surface morphology and its interaction with incident SW↓ radiation.
- Slush flows (commonly observed at the South site) are outlined as a mechanism capable of removing the snow pack more rapidly at the South site than at the North and Central sites, exposing the ice surface to ablation processes for longer.

5.8 Chapter summary

- Tsanfleuron air temperatures fluctuated between 15.2 °C and - 25.8 °C with a mean of - 2.2 °C, and exhibiting a strong seasonal cycle, causing glacier surface warming in summer and cooling in winter. Differences in temperature between the glacier surface and the air above the glacier drove sensible heat transfer.
- Wind direction at Tsanfleuron, like many other alpine temperate glaciers in the Swiss Alps appears to have been under the influence of down-glacier katabatic flow.
- Energy supply to the glacier surface through the surface energy budget was at its smallest an order of magnitude greater than heat supply to the glacier via the main basal processes. Radiation dominated the surface energy balance, with seasonal and diurnal cycles in the intensity of SW↓ and SW↑, while glacier and atmospheric temperatures influence the LW↓ and LW↑ fluxes. Glacier shading did not significantly influence the SW↓ radiation as there are no significant topographic features to the East and South, and only limited shading occurring from the West when the sun was low in the sky. Net radiation values at the ice surface ranged from 897 W m⁻² in summer to -172 W m⁻² in winter, with a mean value of -3 W m⁻².
- Measured snow temperatures on Tsanfleuron fluctuated between ~ - 22 °C and 0 °C.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

- The warmest snow pack temperatures occurred at the base of the snow pack, insulated from cold atmospheric air and warmed by energy from the ice beneath.
- The coldest snow temperatures occurred nearest the snow surface in response to cold air temperatures and were prevented from influencing snow temperatures deeper in the snow pack by the low thermal conductivity of snow.
- The ice surface thermistor deployed at BH04-01 (the North site) experienced periods of warming in spring 2006 attributed to refreezing of percolating melt at the ice surface at the base of the snow pack. This period corresponded closely with the time of reversal of the energy flux between the ice and snow pack measured by the heat flux plate and is explained in terms of the arrival of the wetting front to the ice.
- Anthropogenic snow pack disturbance during the digging of snow pits resulted in temperature decrease in early winter through exposure of lower snow pack layers to cold atmospheric air temperatures. In spring, however, April snow pits had the opposite effect, resulting in warming following the exposure of deep snow pack layers to warmer daytime atmospheric air, and through the disruption of the stratigraphy forming macro-scale preferential pathways for percolation of surface derived melt speeding the development of isothermal conditions.
- Snow pit temperature profiles indicate surface melting and percolation of meltwater (to a depth of up to 0.60 m) had begun by late April 2006.
- Temperatures recorded by the uppermost ice thermistors in all boreholes experienced an initial rapid temperature decrease in November each year, followed by a small temperature rise once an insulating snow pack developed, followed by a second more gradual temperature decrease to a winter minimum during February. Sequentially deeper thermistors experienced lower cooling rates, reaching warmer winter minima at later dates.
- Heat flux plate measurements at the North site, indicating the arrival time of the wetting front and advected heat to the ice surface. The arrival coincides with observed near ice surface temperature increases (from the South site) to within 9 days, suggesting the arrival of percolating melt water at the ice surface initiated the rapid near ice surface warming.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION I

- Heat transfer by conduction led to progressively deeper thermistors warming through the summer. However, whenever this conduction was supplemented by percolation, warming could occur dramatically and simultaneously throughout the seasonal thermally active near-surface ice zone.
- The full depth of seasonal thermally active ice at BH04-01 was warmed to melting point over the summer. In contrast, only ice to a depth of ~ 8 to 10 m was warmed, and not to the melting point in BH04-06. Only ice to a depth of ~ 0.5 m reached melting point in summer at BH04-06, with ice below remaining cold, with a minimum temperature of ~ -1 °C at ~ 8 m depth.
- The seasonal winter snow pack insulated the ice surface, limiting heat loss, keeping near-surface temperatures considerably warmer than if the snow pack were not present. The over winter snow pack also controlled that rate of ice surface warming in spring and early summer by controlling the rate of energy transfer to the ice surface as air temperatures and $SW\downarrow$ increased.
- Snow thermal conductivity determined using the Fourier temperature wave attenuation method ranged between 0.19 and 1.78 $W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$ and snow thermal diffusivities ranged between 0.22 and 1.91 $m^2\ s^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$. The highest of these values were considerably higher than any reported elsewhere and related to particularly dense, old, wind-packed snow layers.
- The instrumented crevasse acted simultaneously as both a heat source and a heat sink to the near-surface ice, depending on depth. The crevasse was a heat source to a depth of ~ 2 to 3 m below the ice surface in both summer and winter, exhibiting seasonal variation only in the magnitude of the heat flux. Below 4 m depth, the crevasse acted as a heat sink with limited seasonal heat flux variation in direction and magnitude.
- Different surface ablation rates recorded at similar altitudes are explained in terms of differences in macro-scale surface porosity specifically, the presence or absence of crevasses. This in turn, influenced (a) surface drainage, with more drainage causing greater melting, and (b) slush flows caused by meltwater ponding in the snow, removing the winter snow pack more rapidly than where crevassing prevented slush flows.

Chapter 6

Interpretation II: Glacier thermal properties, englacial and basal heat sources, sinks and energy fluxes.

6.1 Introduction

The upper 10 to 15 m of temperate glacier ice is the most thermally active of the whole glacier, experiencing intense winter cooling and subsequent warming back to melting point the following summer. The initiation and elimination of the winter cold wave is the thermal response of the glacial ice to the annual cycle in energy receipt at the glacier surface. Ice cooling and winter cold wave initiation begins as a consequence of air temperature and $SW\downarrow$ decrease following the onset of winter and becomes more intense as the winter progresses. Ice warming at the end of the spring begins the elimination of the cold wave, as air temperatures and $SW\downarrow$ increase. Melt is generated at the snow surface and percolates down to the ice surface advecting heat. At the ice surface heat is conducted into the near-surface ice, and where permeable, melt infiltrates the ice advecting heat deeper into the ice. Following the ablation of the snow pack, the rate of near-surface ice warming increases via direct conduction from warmer air temperatures and penetration of higher intensity summer $SW\downarrow$. At depth within the ice, englacial heat transfer continues via conduction and advection of percolating melt. Various heat sources and sinks are present within the ice acting to drive energy fluxes and generate localised melting. In the subglacial zone, energy fluxes between the bedrock and the basal ice are controlled by; geothermal heating, sliding-induced frictional heating, water and air flows to and from the glacier bed.

This chapter details the initiation and elimination of the winter cold wave, a determination of the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of glacier ice and the depths of penetration of the winter cold wave at three borehole sites (Section 6.2). Englacial temperatures, heat sources and heat sinks are discussed and the locations of englacial cold ice are described (Section 6.3). Basal ice temperatures, heat sources, heat sinks and thermal interaction with the subglacial karst drainage system are outlined in Section 6.4, supported by subglacial water pressure and electrical conductivity measurements.

6.2 Winter cold wave

The development and elimination of the winter cold wave is fundamental to the definition of a temperate glacier. The annual cycle of near-surface ice temperatures is driven by the seasonal

cycle of the surface energy balance, driving winter ice cooling and warming back to melting point in summer. A popular misconception is that of the penetration of “winter cold”. In reality, cold does not penetrate into the ice but energy is lost from the ice, via conduction upwards to the surface to replace energy lost to the atmosphere. The heat loss from the ice (and part of the subsequent warming in summer) occurs via conduction and is thus strongly influenced by the thermal conductivity of the ice.

6.2.1 Thermal conductivity of glacier ice

Heat transfer through near-surface glacier ice was primarily via conduction. Other transfer processes in spring and summer included advection of heat via percolation of melt water and precipitation, and the penetration of $SW\downarrow$. However, these additional transfers only occurred through permeable ice when melt was present i.e. not during winter. A determination of ice thermal conductivity was required to allow calculation of the conductive heat fluxes through the ice from measured temperature gradients.

The method of determining the thermal conductivity of glacier ice was the same as that used for the overlying snow pack (Section 5.5.3). Calculations were based on the penetration of the annual temperature signal, through the uppermost 12 – 13 m of ice in BH04-01 and BH04-06. Thermal conductivities were determined using the amplitude attenuation method only and not phase lag, as over the period of the one year cycle, gaps in the data made determination of the exact timing of the winter minimum difficult. Also the non-perfect sinusoidal waveform, with temperatures reaching minimum values and remaining stable for a long period before warming again made phase comparison difficult. A similar situation occurred with the summer temperature maximum, which was capped (at 0 °C) for a prolonged period. However, it was possible to determine the annual temperature wave amplitude and attenuation with depth.

Thermal conductivity determination used near-surface ice thermistor time series between September 2004 and July 2005 at the North site (in BH04-01). Results from the 2005-06 winter were excluded on the basis that data logger failure towards the end of the winter, from cumulative day 868 (17th May 2006) occurred before the winter minimum was reached at depths below 3.05 m (Figure 4.5). Additionally, temperatures recorded at the South site (in BH04-06) between August 2005 and September 2006 were used. Determination was not possible for the 2004-05 winter as missing data from cumulative day 401 (4th February 2005) until day 589 (11th August 2005) prevented determination of the winter minimum in a similar way to the 2005-06 year in BH04-01. Data from BH05-07 were not used as missing data from day 788 (26th February 2006) prevented determination of the minimum winter temperatures. In conjunction with the thermistor

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

data, a value of 894 kg m^{-3} for ice density, determined from the Tsanfleuron ice cores (Section 4.1.3) was used in thermal conductivity calculations along with an ice specific heat capacity of $2097 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Paterson, 1994) in Equation 1.6.5, to determine the thermal diffusivity. The effect of ice water content was also considered by varying the specific heat capacity of ice to include up to 5 % liquid water (specific heat capacity of $4184 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), allowing the specific heat capacity of bulk glacier ice to be as high as $2201 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

The calculated bulk effective thermal conductivity of ice from the surface to a depth of 11.74 m in BH04-01 was $1.95 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and $1.97 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in BH04-06 from the surface to a depth of 13 m (depths varied as a result of analysis in different years and thermistor melt out). A mean value of $1.96 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is thus considered as representative of the near-surface ice at Glacier de Tsanfleuron at this altitude (Section 7.6). This yields a value of $1.05 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the thermal diffusivity. In both boreholes attempts to calculate the thermal conductivities of different ice layers of 1 – 2 m thickness in the near-surface ice, determined on the basis of individual thermistor location produced widely varying conductivity values, at times beyond published ranges for ice. Thus only bulk values are presented.

Paterson (1994, p205) published an ice thermal conductivity value of $2.10 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for pure ice at 0°C . The difference between this and the calculated Tsanfleuron glacier ice value of $1.96 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ likely stems from the fact that the latter value was derived from temperature variations as low as $\sim -4^\circ\text{C}$, not ice at a constant temperature of 0°C , and glacier ice differs physically from pure, lab ice. For example Cameron and Bull (1962) suggested the effects of impurities, orientated crystals and thermal and solar radiation within the ice, and cause in situ calculated thermal conductivity values to differ from published pure ice values.

6.2.2 Conductive heat flux through the surface glacier ice

Using the thermal conductivity value derived above, allied to the thermal gradients measured by the thermistor strings, allows the conductive heat flux in the near-surface ice at Tsanfleuron to be calculated from Equation 1.6.2.

For the purposes of analysis of the conductive fluxes during the winter cooling, the period August 2005 to April 2005 in both BH04-01 and BH04-06 was identified as the most suitable data set (Figure 4.22a and b). Bi-monthly mean bulk conductive heat fluxes through the seasonal thermally active ice layer in both 2004/05 and 2005/06 are presented in Figure 6.1. Heat loss in the 2004/05 winter (Figure 4.21) followed the same general trends in each borehole. Cooling occurred from a near melting point temperature profile in BH04-01 in September (Figure 4.22 a)

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

where equal temperatures throughout the near-surface ice prevented heat transfer via conduction. The onset of ice surface cooling in the second week of November initiated a bulk negative temperature gradient of $0.13 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ in the near-surface ice, driving a conductive flux of 0.26 W m^{-2} toward the ice surface from the warmer ice beneath. The negative temperature gradient driving conductive cooling over the winter with heat transfer from depth to the ice surface reached a maximum of $0.22 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ in the second half of February in response to an ice surface temperature minimum of $-3.45 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This, in turn initiated a maximum conductive heat flux of 0.42 W m^{-2} upwards to the ice surface. Cooling over the same period in BH04-06 was slightly different (reflecting the presence of cold ice below the surface) and ice surface temperatures fell to slightly lower values than at BH04-01 (Figure 4.22 b). Figure 6.1 displays positive conductive fluxes in BH04-06 during August and September 2006 (and August to October 2004): these fluxes were an artefact of melting point surface temperatures directly overlying cold ice (yet to be eliminated from the previous winter) driving conduction downwards from the ice surface into the ice. A temperature minimum of $\sim -1 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 6.49 m below the surface in the first week of August, resulted in a positive temperature gradient of $0.18 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ between the ice surface and 6.49 m, driving conduction of heat downwards from the surface, at a flux of 0.35 W m^{-2} . Interestingly, this occurred simultaneously with an upwards flux to 6.49 m of 0.06 W m^{-2} from below. The bi-monthly mean bulk near-surface fluxes for this period (Figure 6.1b) suggest a positive flux (downwards into the ice) of 0.06 W m^{-2} . This combines both positive and negative fluxes (upwards out of the ice) to a total depth of 16 m, allowing comparison with BH04-01. The two week periods of October and the first half of November recorded moderate ice surface cooling, reflected in the bulk conductive cooling fluxes of 0.17, 0.02 and 0.13 W m^{-2} (Figure 6.1b) respectively, which increase with further ice surface cooling to a winter maximum upwards conductive flux of 0.49 W m^{-2} .

Figure 6.1: Bi-monthly mean bulk conductive energy flux into the ice surface in the seasonally active thermal layer at the North and South sites (BH04-01 and BH04-06 respectively) during the period of winter cooling and penetration of the winter cold wave in (a) the 2004-05 winter and (b) the 2005-06 winter.

Data logger failure during the period of cold wave elimination was common due to static build up associated with early summer thunderstorms, causing gaps in the temperature profile plots used for analysis of the elimination of the cold wave (Figures 4.23 and 4.24).

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

During the first two weeks of May 2005 an average positive temperature gradient of $1.01\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ in BH04-01, drove a conducted heat flux of 1.99 W m^{-2} downwards from the surface to a depth of 0.74 m (Figure 4.23). At the same time, the average negative temperature gradient of $-0.09\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ between the depths of 1.74 and 15.74 m, established earlier in the winter, continued to force a conductive heat flux of 0.18 W m^{-2} upwards from the underlying warmer ice towards the thermistor at 1.74 m depth. Thus, the elimination of the winter cold wave occurred via conductive fluxes both downwards and upwards through the ice. In the second half of May 2005 the downwards flux decreased to 0.37 W m^{-2} as a consequence of further warming of the ice surface from $-0.53\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-0.22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, the flux influenced thermistors as deep as 3.74 m below the surface, while the upwards flux similarly decreased to 0.15 W m^{-2} . By the first two weeks of August the downwards conductive flux had further reduced to 0.03 W m^{-2} , while the upwards flux had reduced to 0.01 W m^{-2} as the cold ice had warmed further. A similar pattern of energy transfer via conductive fluxes is expected to have occurred at the same site in the summer of 2006 (Figure 4.24 a).

Conductive heat fluxes during cold wave elimination at the South site in the spring and summer of 2006 (Figure 4.24 b) were somewhat different from those at the North site (Figure 4.24 a). Ice surface warming occurred without the establishment of positive temperature gradients from the surface between the beginning of April and the end of June. Over this period the bulk conductive heat flux up from the near-surface ice decreased from 0.43 W m^{-2} to 0.33 W m^{-2} . This is explained by gradual warming by the upwards conductive flux under conditions of a reversing basal snow temperature gradient (Figure 3.27 c), and thermal disturbance from a large basally-derived heat flux propagating up the borehole (Figure 4.10 and Section 6.4.2). The beginning of July saw a large jump in ice surface temperature of $2.49\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to melting point, which initiated a positive temperature gradient in the upper ice layers of $0.32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$, driving a conductive heat flux of 0.63 W m^{-2} down to a depth of 5 m below the surface. At the same time the negative over winter temperature gradient below 5 m depth remained, conducting an upwards flux of heat from the less cold ice beneath at a rate of 0.20 W m^{-2} . Over the course of the summer, as more heat was conducted downwards from the ice surface, the positive temperature gradient penetrated deeper, to a depth of $\sim 8\text{ m}$. However, a negative temperature gradient remained below 8 m, maintaining a small conductive heat flux upwards towards the cold ice temperature minimum of $-0.97\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 7.75 m below the ice surface at the end of October 2006.

The establishment of negative winter temperature gradients in the near-surface ice occurred at approximately the same time during the cooling of both BH04-01 and BH04-06 - in direct response to an ice surface temperature decrease driven by surface energy balance change.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

However, prior to the establishment of conductive heat fluxes upwards through the ice, no conduction occurred at BH04-01 at the end of the summer due to the evolution of the ice to isothermal status. In BH04-06 positive and negative conductive fluxes to the depth of the cold ice minima were observed in both years in response to remnants of cold ice near the surface. During the warming of the ice, near-surface positive temperature gradients were established more quickly in BH04-01 than BH04-06. The positive heat flux from the surface dominated the elimination of the winter cold wave, aided by the smaller upwards flux from the warmer ice beneath. For full isothermal status to be achieved all of the energy lost via upwards conduction was replaced from the surface (via conduction and percolation) late in the summer in BH04-01. However, this did not occur in BH04-06 which failed to eliminate the winter cold wave in both summers.

6.2.3 Initiation of the winter cold wave

As outlined above, conductive heat loss was the key energy transfer process driving the development and “penetration” of the winter cold wave in response to the annual cycle of air temperature and SW↓.

During the autumn and winter, cooling of the near-surface ice temperatures at all three boreholes (Figures 4.5, 4.6 and 4.7) occurred as a result of heat loss to the atmosphere via LW↑, conduction and sensible heat transfer from the glacier surface. Rapid winter cooling of the near-surface ice at BH04-01 from isothermal ~ melting temperatures (Figure 4.5 a and 4.8 a) began in November in both 2004 and 2005 (continuing until April in 2005 and May in 2006). At BH04-06 cooling from various sub-melting point temperatures (Figure 4.8 b) began in November in 2004, gently in October 2005 accelerating rapidly in November, and again in November 2006. At the Central site, BH05-07 cooled slowly in October and accelerated in November in both 2005 and 2006. Missing data due to data logger malfunction prevented analysis of the initiation of winter cooling in 2006 at BH04-01 and BH04-06 and the continued cooling in the later stages of the winter of BH04-06 in 2004/05 and BH05-07 in 2005/06. Near-surface ice temperature profiles during the penetration of the winter cold waves are presented in Figures 4.21 and 4.22.

Falling air temperatures, resulted in the glacier surface becoming notably warmer than the boundary layer air directly in contact with it. Consequently, a negative temperature gradient developed in the ice, transferring energy out of the glacier surface to the atmosphere via LW↑ and conduction, in turn leading to rapid ice surface cooling before the snow pack developed or under a shallow snow pack. As heat was conducted upwards toward the glacier surface, energy was gradually lost to the surface from deeper in the glacier, initiating cooling in vicinity of

sequentially lower thermistors. As the snow pack developed, a slight warming of the near-surface ice occurred as the ice surface became gradually more insulated from the atmosphere and the temperatures at the base of the snow pack stabilised. Progressively deeper ice thermistors subsequently experienced cooling as the winters continued, in response to a decrease in energy transfer with distance from the surface. The rate of energy loss to the atmosphere decreased as the winter progressed (Section 5.5) and penetration ceased when the ablation season commenced and the direction of energy transfer at the ice surface reversed from loss to gain.

6.2.4 Elimination of the winter cold wave

Glacier ice warming from cold winter temperatures towards the melting point began under full snow pack conditions by two heat transfer mechanisms: (a) advection of heat through percolation into the temperate surface ice and subsequent refreezing of meltwater releasing latent heat of fusion and (b) conduction of heat downwards from the base of the snow pack and upwards from the underlying ice. As the snow melted the albedo decreased as debris such as soot, dust, particulate pollutants and near valley sides, rock debris, deposited during the winter concentrated at the surface, increasing the absorption of SW_{\downarrow} , initiating a positive feedback mechanism to speed surface melting (however, the mechanism was retarded by fresh snowfalls although melting continued rapidly once fresh snow was ablated). Percolating meltwater initially refroze in the snow pack on contact with colder snow at depth, forming ice layers, gradually preferential flow paths developed through the snow pack routing melt water to the ice surface.

Once snow pack derived meltwater reached the ice surface it refroze forming superimposed ice (evidenced at the South site in January 2006, where the bottom of scaffolding poles, suspended just above the ice surface in late summer, had become frozen to the surface in clear, debris-and-bubble free ice to a depth of ~10 to 15 cm in the autumn snow pack) releasing latent heat of fusion and / or percolated into the glacier ice. Percolation of water into the glacier surface ice occurred at two scales: at a macro-scale through cracks and crevasses (visible during the absence of snow at the North site ranging in scale from a few mm up to a ~1 m wide crevasse less than 2 m down glacier) and at the micro-sale the temperate ice was porous with water passing through veins at triple grain boundaries with in the ice. Latent heat released by freezing at the ice surface was conducted downwards into the ice.

Elimination of the winter cold wave began at different times in each borehole (Section 5.3.3). Small amounts of warming in the vicinity of the uppermost ice thermistor were observed in mid winter, before the main period of temperature increase, in response to insulation by the snow pack as the winter progressed and conduction from the warmer ice beneath. BH04-01 warmed

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

from a winter near-surface minimum of $-3.92\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of December 2004 and $-4.00\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of December 2005, BH04-06 warmed from $-4.55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of November 2005, while BH05-07 also recorded warming from $-2.96\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the end of November 2005. Following this gradual over-winter warming (of up to $\sim 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) the main period of rapid heat transfer to the ice began in late spring.

Winter cold wave elimination at the North site began in May 2005 and 2006, reaching isothermal status by the end of August in both years. Elimination of the winter cold wave in the near-surface glacier ice during spring 2005 at BH04-01 began more uniformly in the upper ice layers than did the onset of winter cooling, beginning quite dramatically in the uppermost four thermistors on day 119 (2005) (Figure 4.9 a). The negative temperature gradient established in the near-surface ice during winter cooling, prevented conductive energy transfer to depth until, a gradual reversal of the temperature gradient occurred, as successively deeper ice layers warmed to their melting point in response to the rise in ice surface temperature. The time taken for this temperature gradient reversal, and the addition of the necessary energy at depth, resulted in a spring “hang over effect”, where cold ice underlay warm ice and the delayed response of deeper thermistors to surface warming was observed (Figure 4.23 and 4.24). Thus, simultaneous commencement of warming to a depth of $\sim 5\text{ m}$ in BH04-01 was aided by percolation of melt through macro-porous pathways opened via ice fracture over winter (but not filled in the absence of melt until spring), rapidly transferring heat to depth. Although observed at this site, the glacier wide spatial extent of percolation such as this is not known.

The amount of heat transferred via water flow would probably have been restricted to near-surface ice. However, allied to the warmer ice temperatures at depth the energy transferred by percolating water could conceivably initiate the observed warming at $\sim 12\text{ m}$ depth under negative temperature gradients in the second half of May 2005 in BH04-01 (Figure 4.23). Refreezing would have blocked any small macro-scale pathways not connected to the englacial conduit system (evidenced at the North site by narrow ($\leq 1\text{ cm}$), long ($> 1\text{ m}$), clear, bubble free positive relief ice features of heights up to $\sim 1\text{ cm}$, visible on the ice surface in summer. These features are suggested to have formed by refreezing of melt in small fractures and cracks, with subsequent more rapid ablation of the surrounding older bubble rich glacier ice) focussing a larger proportion of later latent heat release at the surface. Gradually over the next couple of months micro-scale percolation and conduction of latent heat transferred heat to depth, cancel out winter cooling, as depicted in Figure 4.5. Warming of the thermistor at $\sim 12\text{ m}$ below the ice surface in early July 2005, in the presence of a negative temperature gradient (due to the cold ice above), can not have

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

been sourced from the ice surface via conduction. Thus, it is assumed that cold ice was warmed by upwards conduction from below (which did not penetrate as deep as the thermistor at ~ 16 m depth) and from surface-derived melt advection through non blocked macro-scale melt pathways and latent heat release on refreezing.

At the South site, cold wave elimination began slowly between April and the end of June 2006, while still under a cold basal snow pack. Such warming may have resulted from latent heat release associated with superimposed ice formation at the ice surface. Energy transfer to the near-surface ice increased dramatically at the beginning of July with a jump of ice surface temperatures to melting point and the establishment of a positive temperature gradient to a depth of ~ 5 m (see above) (Figure 4.24 b). Missing data prevented discussion of the cold wave elimination at the South site in 2005. However, the melting point had been reached at the ice surface by August 2005, although cold ice (at ~ -1 °C) persisted through the summer at a depth of 5 m.

An ice surface temperature jump of 2.94 °C occurred between the end of June and the beginning of July 2006 at BH04-06 (Figure 4.24 b), which accelerated warming of the near-surface ice. Two possible explanations for this temperature increase are presented: Firstly, latent heat was released at the ice surface via refreezing. Second, the ice surface warmed from exposure to SW↓ following removal of the snow pack earlier (\sim day 180) than at the North site.

Under impermeable ice surface conditions at the South site (BH04-06), in the absence of percolation of melt, cooling by the winter cold wave continued longer than that under permeable ice conditions at the North site. Over the period July to October 2006, conduction downwards from the surface at a rate of ~ 0.6 W m⁻² served to eliminate the cold wave at the surface, gradually reversing the temperature gradient to a depth of ~ 8 m (Figure 4.24 b). The remaining negative temperature gradient deeper in the seasonally-active layer facilitated continuing conductive heat transfer upwards through the ice at a rate of ~ 0.2 W m⁻², allowing cold wave penetration to continue (despite ice surface warming). This is evidenced by the continued cooling of the thermistor at a depth of ~ 8 m below the surface between the first two weeks and second two weeks of July (Figure 4.24b). Thus, the “winter” cold wave continued to penetrate at depth through the summer at the South site due to the presence of the cold ice just below the ice surface, driving a small but continuous conductive heat flux upward to the temperature minima at ~ 8 m depth. Once ice surface temperatures reached melting point ablation occurred. The cold ice below the ablating ice surface warmed only slowly to melting point because of the limited

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

positive temperature gradient. In contrast, the cooling which initiated the cold wave occurred more rapidly under the influence of larger negative temperature gradients established between the ice surface and low atmospheric air temperatures. Thus, development of the winter cold wave was driven by cooling which occurred over a short period of time, while its elimination required considerably longer to transfer the same amount of heat through the same ice thickness. Thermistors below ~ 8 m depth in BH04-06 showed no warming in the period April to October 2006 (Figure 4.24 b), presumably due to a lack of percolation preventing heat advection and refreezing at depth, limiting warming to the slow process of conduction. An exception to this was the warming in June 2006 caused by a basal heating event which propagated upwards to the surface (Figure 4.10, Section 6.4.2 below).

The effects of this limited heat conduction under warming conditions resulted in a “hangover effect” in temperature profiles (Figures 4.23 and 4.24). If the “hangover effect” was too great then cold ice at depth remained at the end of the ablation period and cooled further during the following winter (as was the case at BH04-06). Under this condition the glacier ice violated the requisite that temperate ice be warmed to melting point for a period each year and thus the glacier cannot be strictly classed as temperate.

Although possibly beginning later, the North site displayed more rapid cold wave elimination than the South site. In both 2005 and 2006 summers, elimination of the winter cold wave at the North site occurred via percolation of melt advecting heat and latent heat as well as by ubiquitous conduction.

Influence of summer snowfall on the elimination of the winter cold wave

Summer 2006 saw a long period of snow cover on the ice surface as a result of repeated summer snowfalls and poor weather hampering its ablation (Figure 3.15 a). Such summer snowfall occurring at possibly the most energetic period of the annual energy transfer to the ice surface (Figure 7.10), can seriously retard the elimination of the winter cold wave. This is mainly due to the low thermal conductivity of snow, curtailing conduction from the warm atmosphere (Figure 3.1a), and a step increase in albedo decreasing the absorption of $SW\downarrow$ and increasing $SW\uparrow$. Furthermore the additional snow itself required ablating before ice melting could continue. Thus, there was a prolonged effect on the ice surface energy budget even as a consequence of small snowfalls. If sufficiently deep, summer snowfall was accompanied by an early winter, relatively minor summer snowfalls could have been sufficient to prevent ice temperature (at depth below

the surface) from rising to the melting point at all, resulting in the incomplete elimination of the winter cold wave.

Climate change (at least in the Swiss Alps) seems to be resulting in the first winter snowfalls occurring later in the year (Cove, 2006; Swissinfo, 2006a). This may have two implications for the elimination of the winter cold wave. First, warmer autumn air temperatures and later winter snowfalls could extend surface ice warming later into the autumn. Second, a later snow pack without autumn warming will increase heat loss from the near-surface ice, resulting in the deeper penetration of the winter cold wave and commensurately greater cooling at depth. Contributing to the theme of “cooling glaciers in a warming world” and adding to the non-linearity of glacier response to climate change.

6.2.5 Depth of penetration of the winter cold wave

The depth of penetration of the winter cold wave was determined to be the depth at which the winter cooling between the isotherms for different bimonthly periods (Figures 4.21 and 4.22) was eliminated to within the ± 0.04 °C error in temperature measurement. Penetration depths for the three borehole locations are presented in Table 6.1.

<i>Location</i>	<i>Winter</i>	<i>Depth of penetration (m)</i>	<i>Comment</i>
North site	2004-05	13.24	
	2005-06	15.11	
South site	2004-05	> 9.96	Up to data logger failure in February
	2005-06	12.68	
Central site	2005-06	> 10.55	Up to data logger failure in February

Table 6.1: Depths of penetration of the winter cold wave at the North, South and Central sites (BH04-01, BH04-06 and BH05-07 respectively) in the 2004-05 and the 2005-06 winters.

The deeper penetration depth at the North site (BH04-01) compared to those at the South site (BH04-06) 15.11 m compared to 12.68 m in 2005/06, are attributed to differences in the temperature to which the ice surface cooled. This drove differences in the ice temperature gradients and the conducted heat flux from depth in the thermally active layer. Deeper penetration at the North is attributed to the steeper temperature gradient at depth below ~ 8 m in BH04-01 compared to that in BH04-06 (Figure 4.22). In BH04-01 temperatures tended to melting point at a depth of ~ 16 m, while in BH04-06 the temperature gradients below a depth of ~ 8 m were not as steep. At BH04-06 the presence of cold ice, limited temperatures to ~ -0.5 °C at 16 m. The bulk conductive flux (Figure 6.1) suggested the overall heat loss from the South site was greater than that at the North, in part due to the colder ice surface temperatures at the former.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

More detailed study of the temperature gradients (Figure 4.22), however, suggests cooling at the North site occurred more evenly throughout the depth of the active layer than at the South site, where a greater focus of cooling occurred in the layers above ~ 8 m depth. The cold ice below ~ 8 m here caused a less steep temperature gradient between ~ 8 m and 16 m compared to that in BH04-01. This reduced the upwards conductive heat flux from deep ice, allowing greater cooling of the upper layers (and the ice surface) and less deep penetration of the cold wave in comparison to the North site, i.e. conduction was less effective at the South site because ice temperatures there were already colder, leading to generally reduced thermal gradients and heat transfer to and from the cold wave.

Summary

- Penetration of the winter cold wave resulted from heat loss via conduction upwards through the near-surface ice. The rate of heat loss was driven by the temperature gradients established between the ice surface and the warmer ice beneath and the thermal conductivity of the ice.
- Effective glacier ice thermal conductivity determined using the Fourier method was $1.96 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.
- Thermal diffusivity of the glacier ice was calculated to be $1.05 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.
- Winter cold wave cooling initiated at the North site (BH04-01) in November 2004 and November 2005, at the South site (BH04-06) in November 2004, October 2005 and November 2006, and at the Central site (BH05-07) in October 2005 and October 2006.
- Elimination of the winter cold wave began at the North site (BH04-01) in May 2005 and May 2006, and at the South site (BH04-06) in May 2006.
- The winter cooling was eliminated at the North site (BH04-01) by the end of August in both 2005 and 2006.
- Summer snowfalls retard the elimination of the winter cold wave by reducing the energy flux to the near-surface ice for potentially long periods during the most energetic period of energy transfer.

- In both the 2005 and 2006 summers, elimination of the winter cold wave at the North site (BH04-01) occurred by percolation of melt advecting heat and latent heat release at depth as well as conduction. In contrast at the South site (BH04-06) the winter cold wave was reduced by conduction alone and resulted in all years in its incomplete elimination.
- At the North site (BH04-01) the winter cold wave penetrated to a depth of 13.24 m in the 2004/05 winter and to a depth of 15.11 m in the 2005/06 winter. At the South site (BH04-06) the winter cold wave penetrated to a depth of 9.96 m in the 2004/05 winter prior to the cessation of the data record in February and to a depth of 12.68 m in the 2005/06 winter. At the Central site the cold wave penetrated to a depth of 10.55 m in the 2005/06 winter prior to the cessation of the data record.
- Ice in the seasonal thermally active layer only reached melting point throughout at certain glacier locations for a few weeks, and not at all at other sites. Thus, to assume for the purposes of modelling that temperate ice is at melting point throughout is an oversimplification.
- Ice at the South site (BH04-06) cannot be classed as “temperate”, as cold ice remained below a depth of ~ 0.5 m at the end of the 2005 and 2006 ablation seasons. As a consequence Glacier de Tsanfleuron is not strictly a “temperate” glacier because it contains ice that is below melting point for the whole glacier year. Technically the glacier is “polythermal”.

6.3 Englacial temperatures, cold ice, heat sources and sinks

According to the definitions of a temperate glacier (Section 1.2) below ~ 15 m depth (the depth to which the winter cold wave is suggested to penetrate) all englacial ice temperatures should be perennially at melting point down to the bed. Thermistor measurements in the three boreholes at Tsanfleuron indicate this is not the case, with temperatures below melting point at various depths within the three boreholes, indicating the presence of cold ice and borehole temperatures in excess of melting point due to the presence of englacial and basal heat sources.

6.3.1 Englacial temperatures

The theoretical variation of melting point temperature with depth was derived in Section 4.1.2 and is displayed in Figure 4.12. Measured deviations from this temperature profile arose due to the presence of englacial heat sources and sinks considered below in Sections 6.3.3 and 6.3.4.

The North site (BH04-01)

Figure 6.2 displays a contour plot of ice temperature variation with height above the bed (a.b. from here on) in BH04-01 and BH05-016 between August 2004 and October 2006. Cold ice occurs primarily near the surface in response to the winter cooling and to a lesser extent at a height of ~ 40 m a.b. Above melting point temperatures suggest thermistors recording air or water temperatures in the presence of melting, specifically at the ice bed interface. Many of the recorded temperatures at the North site in BH04-01 were at or warmer than the theoretical pressure, bubble and solute melting point (referred to hereafter as “melting point”) (Figure 4.13 b). At heights above the bed of 41.2 to 113.2 m in the 2004-05 year (Figure 4.13b) ice temperatures were warm (i.e. at melting point), whereby many of the apparently above melting point temperatures were less than their ± 0.04 °C error from the melting point. Where positive temperatures were > 0.04 °C above the melting point, it is postulated that the existence of englacial conduits or cracks near the thermistors may have allowed liquid water from the melting snow and ice surface (the largest positive temperature occurred in May at the time of initial meltwater percolation into the ice surface) to have advected warmer water to depth in the ice, possibly down a non-fully closed borehole. Another possible mechanism that may have allowed slightly warmer ice temperatures than those of the calculated melting point was the existence of locally more pure, bubble-free ice, causing a small localised melting point increase.

The drilling and instrumentation of BH05-16 in August 2005 to the bed adjacent to BH04-01 allowed temperature measurements in the deepest part of the glacier (Figure 4.1). At and in close proximity to the glacier bed, temperatures appear to be ~ 0.5 °C decreasing to melting point at ~ 40 m a.b. (Figure 6.2 and 4.14 b). This pattern may be attributed to one of two possible causes:

1. The borehole may have remained water filled and did not recover from the thermal disturbance of drilling.
2. A basal heat source was present (Section 6.4.2).

In direct contrast to the melting point temperatures recorded between the heights of 30 and 50 m a.b. in BH05-016, thermistor 110.0a located at 41.23 m a.b. in adjacent BH04-01 registered temperatures ~ 0.5 °C colder than the melting point during the period September 2005 to August 2006 (Figure 4.14 b). These colder temperatures suggest either the existence of a cold ice layer or the drainage of cold air down a partially drained open borehole, ponding at the bottom of BH04-01 which terminating englacially. Cold air drainage connecting to the open borehole via fractures and cracks seems the most plausible explanation, though the existence of a mass of cold ice advected to depth and not intersected by BH05-16 cannot be eliminated. During the same

period temperatures at locations more than ~ 50 m a.b. were warm and followed a similar pattern to the previous year (detailed above).

Figure 6.2: Contour plot of temperature with height above the bed in borehole BH04-01 combined with the adjacent BH05-16 over the period of data collection August 2004 to October 2006 (expressed as day since the beginning of 2004, with the periods of missing data blanked out).

The temperature jump measured in August 2006 at 53.2 m a.b. (Figure 4.14 b and visible in Figure 6.2) was likely due to the warming effect caused by the hot water, cable following, re-drilling of the adjacent BH05-17 on day 229 and 230 (cumulative days 960 and 961). During re-drilling, drainage of BH05-17 occurred at 108 m and 43.5 m a.b. If the path of such an englacial connection passed in the vicinity of the thermistor at 53.2 m a.b. in BH05-16 or water percolated through the warm ice, heat would be transferred to the thermistor explaining the observed temperature rise.

The South site (BH04-06)

Temperature stratification at the South site (Figure 6.3) showed more simple variation than that at the North, with the coldest temperatures near the surface illustrating the penetration of the winter cold wave, and warming towards the bed. Comparable to BH04-01, the near-surface thermistors in BH04-06 displayed winter cooling to a minimum of ~ -4.5 °C at the ice surface (Figure 4.6). In contrast to the North site (Figure 6.2) layers of ice at the South site remained cold all year. Below the depth of penetration of the winter cold wave (9.96 m in the 2004-05 winter and 12.68 m in the 2005-06 winter (Table 6.1)) down to a depth of ~ 25 m a.b., ice temperatures were considerably below the melting point (to a minimum of -1 °C) for the duration of the study period and did not at any time warm to melting point (Figures 4.15, 4.16 and 4.17),

suggesting the existence of advected cold glacier ice overlying warm ice below. Below the cold ice, in the ~ 25 m above the glacier bed, temperatures suggest ice was warm. At the bed, positive temperatures of as high as ~ 3.5 °C were recorded, decreasing with height above the bed (Figure 4.6, lower plot and 4.10). This warming could be clearly seen to propagate up the (inferred partially open) borehole, for example the specific warming event soon after cumulative day 900 (see Figure 4.10). Temperatures of > 0 °C at the bed are interpreted as air and water temperatures in a subglacial cavity connected to the karst system underlying the glacier (Section 6.4.1 and 6.4.2).

Figure 6.3: Contour plot of temperature with height above the bed in borehole BH04-06 over the period of data collection August 2004 to February 2007 (expressed as day since the beginning of 2004, with the period of missing data blanked out).

The Central site (BH05-07)

Near-surface ice temperatures at the Central site (BH05-07) (Figure 6.4), displayed similar seasonal fluctuation in response to the penetration of the winter cold wave. However, here did not drop as low as at the North and South sites, reaching a minimum of ~ -3.5 °C. Immediately below the ice surface, cold ice was eliminated in summer except for a region between 88 and 93 m a.b., where a temperature minimum of ~ -0.4 °C remained. Temperatures were at melting point from a height of 88 m to ~ 35 m above the bed, below which cold ice temperatures were observed. No positive temperatures were measured in this borehole, even at the bed where basal heat sources may have been expected to drive melting.

Temperatures from the ice surface down to ~ 60 m a.b. were below melting point during the autumn and early winter of the 2005-06 season (Figure 4.18), reflecting either an upper layer of

cold ice (somewhat warmer than in BH04-06) near the glacier surface, or the drainage of cold air down the borehole BH05-07. The latter may be supported by the observation that BH05-07 drained to an unknown level on day 215 (2005) and remained open and air filled on day 231. At a height of 60 m a.b. the ice warmed to melting point (Figure 4.18 a) and remained so to a height of ~ 35 m a.b., below which colder ice temperatures were observed. Thermistor 90.0c at 18.5 m a.b. displayed cooling over the whole period of instrumentation, decreasing to a minimum of ~ -0.4 °C in January 2007 (Figure 4.19 b), presumably continuing the elimination of the thermal disturbance of a region of advected colder ice, caused by the drilling. Between August 2005 and February 2006 a cold ice minimum of ~ -0.3 °C was observed at the bed (Figure 4.18 b). Basal temperatures increased to within ± 0.04 °C of melting point (to a height of ~ 0.6 m a.b.) between February 2006 and August 2006, in response to some form of basal heating. It is suggested that with continued warming at the bed, the temperatures of sequentially higher basal ice layers would continue to increase, with melt generation at the ice rock interface, similar to that at the bed at the North and South sites.

Figure 6.4: Contour plot of temperature with height above the bed in borehole BH05-07 over the period of data collection August 2005 to February 2007 (expressed as day since the beginning of 2004, with the period of missing data blanked out).

Englacial cold ice

Cold ice does not warm to melting point at any time during the year in BH04-06 and BH05-07. Temperate glaciers by definition cannot contain any perennial cold ice. Though Glacier de Tsanfleuron was generally considered in the literature to be a temperate glacier (e.g. Tison and Hubbard, 2000; Hubbard, 2002 and Hubbard *et al.* 2003) this study has revealed the presence of perennial cold englacial ice. Such cold ice is permanent and below the influence of the

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

penetration of the winter cold wave and probably resulted from advection down glacier of colder ice formed at higher elevation in the accumulation area under high accumulation rates.

It is suggested from the temperature profiles at the South site (Figures 4.15, 4.16 and 4.17) and the absence of scattering in the 50 MHz radar returns (collected as part of the NERC project by Tavi Murray) (Figure 6.5) in the vicinity of BH04-06 that a layer of cold ice ~ 35 m thick (the upper part of which was subject to seasonal temperature fluctuation due to the penetration of the winter cold wave) existed on top of a 25 m thick layer of temperate ice. The cold ice at BH04-06 extended all the way to the glacier surface, with a thin surface layer ~ 0.5 to 1 m thick which warmed to melting point and ablated in summer. Cold ice temperatures (other than those driven by seasonal near-surface cooling) reached a minimum of -0.99°C in November 2005 at a height of 52 m a.b. (~ 5 m below the ice surface). The radar interpretation and measurements of cold ice in the first 35 m below the ice surface at the South site, are additionally supported by the apparent lower ice permeability in the vicinity of BH04-06, where the glacier surface supported a well developed supraglacial stream and had a slushy surface appearance in summer.

In addition to the abundant cold ice recorded at the South site, regions of englacial cold ice of as low as $\sim -0.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\sim -0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$ have been identified at the North site at a depth of 49.5 to 40.0 m a.b. in BH04-01 (Figure 4.14) and at the Central site in BH05-07 below a height of ~ 35 m a.b. (Figures 4.18 b and 4.19 b). Unfortunately, the greater ice depths at the Central and North sites combined with near-surface attenuation of the 50 MHz radar wave prevent radar data being used to validate and map the cold ice revealed by the thermistor temperature profiles. Of the cold ice (not formed by the winter cold wave) observed at Tsanfleuron, minimum temperatures did not fall below -1°C . Full details of the stratigraphic locations of warm and cold ice in each of the instrumented boreholes and the three drill sites are outlined in Table 6.2.

Figure 6.5: Processed 50 MHz radar transect across Glacier de Tsanfleuron conducted in April 2004, presented using a constant gain. Boreholes 04-01 and 05-16, 05-07 and 04-06 have been superimposed at their respective locations. The thin layer (10 to 15 m depth) of near-surface low scattering along the full length of the transect, represents the penetration of the winter cold wave, as data collection was conducted at the end of winter. Data courtesy of Prof. Tavi Murray.

	<i>Warm and cold ice thermal stratification</i>		
	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07
North site (BH04-01 & BH05-016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 115.7 m = disturbed by winter cold wave • 115.7 m to 41.2 m = warm ice • 41.2 m to bed = not instrumented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 113.2 m = disturbed by winter cold wave • 113.2 m to 49.5 m = warm ice • 49.5 m to ~ 40.0 m = cold ice • ~ 40.0 m to bed = warm ice 	Instrumented but no available data
South site (BH04-06)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 48.3 m * = disturbed by winter cold wave • 48.3 m to 21.9 m = cold ice • 21.9 m to bed = warm ice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 44.0 m = disturbed by winter cold wave • 44.0 m to 26.8 m = cold ice • 26.8 m to bed = warm ice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 44.0 m * = disturbed by winter cold wave • 44.0 m to 25.5 m = cold ice • 25.5 m to bed = warm ice
Central site (BH05-07)	Not instrumented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 86.9 m * = disturbed by winter cold wave • 86.9 m to 67.5 m = cold ice • 67.5 m to 33.5 m = warm ice • 33.5 m to bed = cold ice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice surface to 84.5 m * = disturbed by winter cold wave • 84.5 m to 38.5 m = warm ice • 38.5 m to 0.6 m = cold ice • 0.6 m to bed = warm ice

Table 6.2: Summary of warm and cold ice thermal stratification at each of the instrumented borehole sites in the 2004-05, 2005-06 and 2006-07 glacier years (all heights measured

above the bed). Asterices denote periods when data collection ceased before full penetration of the winter cold wave.

6.3.2 Englacial heat sources

Heat sources within the glacier ice induce localised temperature gradients, transferring energy to regions of colder ice, generating warming and melting where temperatures reach melting point. Identification of the locations of englacial heat sources is difficult due to the nature of the transfers deep within the ice. A number of inferences can be made from borehole drilling logs, video observations and analysis of the temperature profiles and time series. However, it is noted that identification of englacial heat sources can only occur in otherwise cold ice, as elsewhere warming leads to melting – which may not be identified from temperature change. In such situations the presence of heat sources can only be inferred from theory or if thermistors in the vicinity record melting temperatures in a region of cold ice. Deformation induced strain heating, heat advection and latent heat release by refreezing on contact with colder ice are anticipated from theoretical considerations.

Deformation-induced strain heating

Ice flow (at Tsanfleuron) and its associated deformation, generates heat within the glaciers. Repeat borehole inclinometry in 2005 and 2006 allowed determination of deformation rates, from which heat generation at the South site was calculated (Figure 6.6). Figure 6.6 shows deformation and strain heating was greatest in the vicinity of the bed (due to the high over-burden pressure and resistance to flow between the ice and the glacier bed). This heating peaked at $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and decreased in amplitude towards the surface where heat generation tended to zero. Strain heating generated heat throughout the ice depth. This characteristic profile of heat generation may help to explain the absence of colder ice at the base of BH04-06, where deformation fluxes were larger and combined with heat fluxes of basal origin to warm the lower ice layers and the survival of colder ice further from the bed where strain heating was much reduced and englacial heat transfer by water flow was limited due to the impermeable ice surface. Unfortunately no such profile of heating could be determined for the North site due to cable following problems during re-drilling of BH05-17, preventing repeat inclinometry.

Figure 6.6: Deformation-induced strain heating with height above the glacier bed, derived for the South site from repeat inclinometry determination of borehole deformation and strain rate calculation in a borehole adjacent to BH04-06 (Data courtesy of D. Chandler).

Englacial water flow and latent heat release upon refreezing

At the macro scale englacial water flow occurs through Tsanfleuron via englacial conduits and hydraulically connected fractures (Fountain *et al.*, 2005b). Stenborg (1973) suggested that the majority of rainfall and surface derived melt enters the glacier surface via crevasses and moulins. Crevasses connected to englacial drainage conduits and moulins provide route-ways deep into the ice and to the glacier bed through which running water may advect heat to the surrounding ice. On contact with regions of colder ice, refreezing of liquid water on to the channel walls releases latent heat of fusion, warming the colder ice. The lack of evidence for ponding of meltwater in the instrumented crevasse adjacent to BH05-07 at the Central site, implies the operation of such processes of drainage connection to the englacial hydrological system (see Section 5.6.3), transferring the surface derived melt to depth in the ice.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

Boreholes drilled in various glacial studies have intersected englacial conduits, e.g. Engelhardt (1978); Hantz and Lliboutry (1983); Fountain (1994); Pohjola (1994) and Fountain *et al.* (2005b). Similarly many of the boreholes drilled on Tsanfleuron during April 2004 and August 2005 intersected englacial conduits and cavities of various sizes at a range of depths from within a few meters of the surface to the bed. At the North site, holes BH04-02, BH04-03, BH04-04 and BH05-16, at the South site, holes BH04-05, BH05-08 and BH05-10 and at the Central site, holes BH05-03, BH05-04 and BH05-05 all intersected englacial cavities or conduits providing evidence for the existence of the water pathways (and thus pathways for advection of heat) through the ice, with the potential to warm the surrounding ice. In addition to partial or full drainage of boreholes following connection to conduits and cavities, borehole video, deployed in many of the holes drilled in April 2004 by colleagues at Swansea University, facilitated visual identification of small conduits (of diameter ~10 to 20 mm) intersecting the borehole walls within a few tens of metres of the ice surface at the North site.

At the micro scale, water flows through the glacier ice in the vein system between ice crystals. At this scale, water flow over short distances transfers heat from warm regions, to colder regions where refreezing occurs, releasing latent heat and warming the surrounding ice.

6.3.3 Englacial heat sinks

Numerous possible explanations have been outlined to explain temperatures below melting point observed in so called "temperate ice". These include impurities within the ice, curvature of ice water interfaces and air bubbles (Paterson, 1971) and air circulation within open boreholes (Zagorodnov *et al.*, 2006). Advection of colder ice from its formation area in the accumulation zone and the cooling influence of crevasses are identified as englacial heat sinks exerting a notable influence within Tsanfleuron.

Wedges of advected cold ice

Advected cold ice absorbed energy transferred through the ice or generated internally and formed localised reversed temperature gradients, drawing energy from the surrounding warmer ice. It is assumed that the cold ice observed at the South site in BH04-06 between the depths of ~ 0.5 m below the ice surface and 22 to 27 m a.b. (Figures 4.15 b, 4.16 b, 4.17 b and 6.3) was the result of the advection of colder ice from further up glacier. Similarly the cold ice below ~ 34 to 38 m a.b. in BH05-07 at the Central site (Figures 4.18 b and 4.19 b) was also attributed to advection from higher up glacier. However, in the presence of permeable ice, believed to be connected to a component of the subglacial drainage system in the 2006 summer, warming of the colder ice at the base of BH05-07 allowed melting point to be reached and conducted upwards to a height of

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

~ 0.6 m a.b. The postulation that colder ice had been advected down glacier from higher elevation implies the presence of cold ice up glacier of BH04-06, warranting further investigation (see Section 8.4.1). Similar advection of cold ice has been reported at other glaciers in the Swiss Alps e.g. Grenzletcher (Suter *et al.*, 2001), while Blatter and Haeberli (1984) report advection of cold ice over long distances within zones of temperate surface ice.

It is possible that the cold ice at BH04-06 may have previously extended to depths below ~ 22 m a.b., but has subsequently been warmed to melting point by the active basal heat sources (Section 6.4.2). It is more likely, however, that the cold ice was of surface origin, higher up glacier in the accumulation zone and became incorporated above warmer ice in response to a period of cooling or high accumulation and was subsequently advected down glacier to its current location in BH04-06. It is probable that ice flow from up glacier into the zone of compressional flow in the vicinity of BH04-06 experienced thrusting and folding, forcing cold ice formed at the surface to depth in BH04-06. The absence of crevasses at the South site allowed the advected cold ice to survive.

In addition to the lack of meltwater percolation here at the South site, a number of other reasons are outlined for the survival of cold ice:

- The location of the cold ice extended too deep below the surface for conduction downwards to drive warming and eliminate all the cold ice.
- Strain heating is low due to low surface velocity and relatively high basal velocity (~ 50 % of surface).
- Only minimal energy was conducted upwards through the ice from basal heat sources identified in the vicinity of BH04-06. The overall negative temperature gradient from the bed to the temperature minimum at ~52 m a.b. drove a small continuous conducted heat flux upwards through the ice at a maximum mean monthly flux of 0.103 W m^{-2} (June 2006). Such a flux was insufficient to eliminate the advected englacial cold ice.

Crevasses

The instrumented crevasse – adjacent to BH05-07 at Central site has been shown at a depth of ~ 3 to 6 m to act as a heat sink throughout the full period of data collection (the maximum depth to which instrumentation occurred) (Figure 5.9). Given the warmer ice temperatures at depth and the ability of cold dense air to sink, these data indicate that crevasses at Tsanfleuron served to cool the ice at depths of > 3 m.

Summary

- Much of the temperature profile in each instrumented borehole was within ± 0.04 °C of melting point.
- Cold ice was identified at the North site (BH04-01), at height of ~ 40 m a.b., at the South site (BH04-06) between heights of 25 and 56 m a.b., and at the Central site (BH05-07) below 35 m a.b.
- The coldest ice temperature measured was ~ -4.5 °C, measured at the ice surface at the South site (in winter). This was an ephemeral minimum associated with the winter cold wave.
- Excepting the winter cold wave, the lowest ice temperature was -0.99 °C recorded at ~ 8 m below the ice surface at the South site (BH04-06).
- A 50 MHz radar transect conducted in April 2004 supported the presence of cold ice from the surface to ~ 25 m a.b. at the South site (BH04-06).
- Deformation-induced strain heating, englacial water flow, and latent heat release are identified as englacial heat sources, with the capacity to warm cold ice and / or melt warm ice.
- Cold ice (advected from the accumulation area) and cold air in crevasses are identified as englacial heat sinks, reducing melt and / or cooling ice.
- Areas of the glacier are characterised by the perennial presence of cold ice. Glacier de Tsanfleuron therefore violates the strict definition of a temperate glacier and may be better described as polythermal.

6.4 Basal temperatures, heat sources and sinks

Basal ice temperatures and subglacial processes are closely interlinked. Subglacial processes control energy fluxes to and from the base of the ice, while temperatures at the glacier bed influence the operation of certain processes (sliding and erosion), mainly through the presence or absence of liquid water. The ice/bed interface represents the lower boundary to the glacier thermal system and is the second most thermally active ice layer after the surface - though the heat fluxes are often at least an order of magnitude smaller at the base. Recognised positive

energy fluxes to the ice at the bed include: geothermal energy, heat generated due to sliding-induced friction, latent heat release on re-freezing of melt, advection of heat via water flow and energy can be lost via the advection of colder ice from up glacier. In addition heat can be lost to the bed from meltwater loss specifically over karstified rock.

6.4.1 Basal ice temperatures

Ice temperatures cannot exceed 0 °C, though temperatures recorded by thermistors deployed at the base of some boreholes in this study recorded positive temperatures. At the North site no basal temperatures were recorded before August 2005 (BH04-01 terminated blind at 41.23 m a.b.) and the nearby BH05-16 was only drilled to the bed and instrumented in August 2005. Over the following 12 months the temperature at 1 m a.b. stabilised at ~ 0.5 °C (Figure 4.5). At the South site, BH04-06 intercepted a freely-drained subglacial cavity during drilling in April 2004. Thus, the thermistor deployed at the bed was not located within the ice borehole, but was believed to be resting on the bedrock at the base of the cavity. Temperatures recorded by this cavity thermistor were for the most part in the range 0.5 to 1.0 °C, peaking at ~ 3.5 °C during an extreme warming event, and never fell to or below 0 °C (Figure 4.6). The thermistor deployed at the bed at the Central site (BH05-07) recorded consistently negative temperatures, between -0.4 and 0.0 °C (Figure 4.7), at the local melting point between August 2006 and January 2007 (to within the accuracy of the temperature measurements). These basic patterns are investigated in more detail below.

The North site (BH05-16)

Basal temperatures in BH05-16 in August 2005 were initially attributed to warm drilling water (~ 0.28 °C) remaining in the borehole. However temperatures continued to rise until the end of data collection in September 2006 (Figure 4.5, lower plot), reaching a maximum of ~ 0.8 °C in August 2006. It appeared that thermistor 150.0d, located 1 m above the glacier bed was experiencing some form of basal warming in a water- or air-filled borehole, that was probably open at its base. This warming was likely due to water in a distributed section of the subglacial drainage system. EC time series (Figure 4.30 a) indicate BH05-16 was water-filled and that, after an initial period of post installation disturbance when drilling waters influenced the electrical conductivity, values were consistently high at ~ 61 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, indicative of concentrated waters in the distributed drainage system. The absence of water pressure data from the North site limits further investigation of the nature of the subglacial drainage connection. The higher water temperatures observed in August 2006 (Figure 4.14 b) were likely the consequence of warm water used in the re-drilling of the adjacent BH05-17 accessing the bed, though conceivably this warming may have resulted from a seasonal change in the subglacial drainage system.

The South site (BH04-06)

Temperatures > 1 °C have been routinely recorded at the base of BH04-06, by thermistor 70.0b (Figure 4.6). The general trend of basal thermistor cooling between August 2004 and November 2004 (Figure 4.6, lower plot) was initially thought to represent cooling following the hot water drilling in April 2004. However, temperatures did not drop any lower than ~ 0.25 °C and distinct periods of warming of $\leq \sim 1.5$ °C were measured. These excursions were measured throughout the thermistor time series (Figures 4.6 and 6.3), peaking during the large disturbance in spring 2006 (Figure 4.10) when temperatures reached ~ 3.5 °C. These temperatures and the nature of the fluctuations suggest the subglacial cavity in which the thermistor was deployed, was under the influence of some form of periodic basal heat source. These ‘events’ caused warming which decreased in amplitude up the borehole e.g. the period August to December 2004 (Figure 6.7). These temperature changes displayed no phase lag with distance from the bed (at the 2 hour sampling interval) (Figure 6.7). This lack of time lag indicates the borehole remained at least partially open throughout the ice depth (presumably via melting driven by the heat fluxes at the bed, the influence of which were felt up the borehole) and the observed heat transfer from a basal origin was via a process other than conduction (which would result in a larger and increasing lag up the borehole). Water or air flow into the bottom of the borehole, and subsequent rapid heat transfer either via convection of water or air are the two most probable heat transfer mechanisms. Thermistor 70.0b (recording the greatest disturbance) in Figure 6.7 appears to show periodic heating of up to $+ 1.5$ °C against a basal thermistor background level of $\sim + 0.5$ °C.

Fourier analysis of the basal thermistor time series (Figure 6.8), indicates a strong diurnal cycle in the basal heat source over the period August to December 2004. Surface-derived melt reaching the bed at a diurnal time scale was eliminated as a possible cause as melt generation could not have continued into December due to sub-freezing air temperatures and the development of the cold winter snow pack by this time (Section 5.3.2). Also if solar heating of cables or the recording equipment were the cause, one would expect all thermistors to display similar disturbances of the same amplitude, which was not the case. Given the evidence that the amplitude of the disturbance decreased systematically with distance from the bed, it is concluded that these disturbances are (a) real and (b) generated at the bed. As to the cause of the disturbances differentiation cannot be made between water flow or air flow. However, given the rapidity and magnitude of the temperature changes air flow, most likely associated with the karst system, seems the more likely explanation (Section 6.4.2).

Figure 6.7: Temperature time series of BH04-06 deep thermistors at the South site between mid August and early December 2004 during the occurrence of basal heat supply events.

Figure 6.8: Normalized power spectra periodogram for the temperature time series of thermistor 70.0b at the base of BH04-06 at the South site, between day 236 and day 337 (mid August to early December 2004, the same period as depicted in Figure 6.7).

The Central site (BH05-07)

Basal temperatures at the Central site in BH05-07 decreased rapidly following drilling in August 2005 to ~ -0.33 °C (~ 0.2 °C below melting point) and remained relatively stable until data logger failure in February 2006 (Figure 4.7, lower plot). These temperatures suggest the presence of cold ice at the bed. Following logger repair in August 2006 basal temperatures remained stable at ~ -0.11 to -0.14 °C, within ± 0.04 °C the measurement error of the local melting point of -0.095 °C (Figure 4.19 b). This temperature rise (and the associated change in direction of the temperature gradient between February 2006 and August 2006 (Figure 4.18 b and Figure 4.19 b) from thermistor 110.0d at the bed to thermistor 90.0c at 18.5 m a.b.) suggests cold basal ice warmed during the period of data logger malfunction. Warming of the cold ice at the base of BH05-07 was most probably due to liquid water advected near the borehole base by changes in the subglacial drainage system occurring during the early summer of 2006. Spikes in the EC of up to ~ 30 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ above the stable conductivity of ~ 80 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (Figure 4.31) at the base of BH05-07 from August to September 2006 indicate the warming waters were of high solute content, either originating from isolated regions of the basal drainage system or from the karst aquifer.

6.4.2 Basal heat sources

Various energy transfer mechanisms may be proposed at the base of Tsanfleuron (outlined below). Combinations of these fluxes may explain the small positive temperatures measured at the bottom of the boreholes at the North and South sites and the warming of the cold ice at the base of the Central site.

Geothermal heat flux

Without being able to measure the geothermal heat flux directly at the glacier bed, an assumed temporally and spatially uniform value of $80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (Sclatter *et al.*, 1980) for European rocks of age 0 – 250 Ma was adopted.

Frictional heat flux at the bed due to sliding

Basal velocity at Tsanfleuron was low and relatively steady. Hubbard (2002) measured basal sliding of 10.55 mm d^{-1} . Basal shear stresses at the glacier are also generally $< 1 \text{ bar}$ since surface slope is low ($\sim 5^\circ$) and ice depth is less than $\sim 130 \text{ m}$ (Tables 2.3 and 2.8, and Figure 4.1). As outlined in Section 7.6.1 the frictional basal heat flux derived using Equation 1.10.1 was $9.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W m}^{-2}$. As geothermal and frictional heat fluxes were considered to be temporally and spatially constant, additional heat sources were required to explain the observed basal thermistor temperature variations.

Water flow at the bed

Water flow at the glacier bed transferred energy to the basal ice, driving thermistor temperature rise, particularly at the South site but also to a lesser degree at the North site. The substantial basal heat supply event in BH04-06 (Figure 4.10) between day 170 and 190 (late June to mid July, 2006) may have occurred due to a large water flow into the subglacial cavity, filling the cavity and propagating up the partially-open borehole (Figure 6.3). The magnitude of the thermal disturbance decreased up the borehole. Assuming the disturbance was caused by the water flow into the cavity, heat transfer would have occurred via advection if the water flowed up an initially empty borehole or via convection with the water column if the hole were already water filled.

Water pressure and electrical conductivity sensors were deployed in boreholes BH05-12 and BH05-10 respectively, drilled in close proximity to BH04-06 at the South site during August 2005 (Figure 2.2). As the sensors were not all deployed in the same hole, the following discussion is conducted under the caveat that the 2005 boreholes may not have connected fully with the same subglacial cavity as did BH04-06. Water pressure records in BH05-12 (Figure 4.29) show a small increase from $\sim 35 \text{ m}$ of water to $\sim 55 \text{ m}$ of water from mid June to July 2006.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

The EC of waters in BH05-10 dropped at the end of the second week of May 2006 at 6 m a.b., from a stable over winter conductivity of $\sim 10 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (representative of englacial waters), to a conductivity of $\sim 2 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (probably of supraglacial origin), once the snow pack melt reached the glacier bed (Figure 4.30 b). A jump in EC at 6 m a.b. occurred from the spring melt value of $\sim 2 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ to $\sim 25 - 30 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at the time of the temperature increase in BH04-06. A corresponding water pressure increase was measured in BH05-12, followed by a decrease back to low levels as the temperature perturbation abated. These water pressure and EC increases at the time of the temperature rise provide support for the observed temperature increase being caused by subglacial water flowing into the cavity and propagating up the partially open holes.

Analysis of air temperature, net radiation and snow depth time series between days 169 and 191 (2006) (Figures 3.1 a, 3.2 a and 3.16 a) show no evidence of disturbance or departure from expected trends to which the basal warming event may be attributed. The timing of the warming and the missing thermistor data do, however, correspond closely with the time at which the heat flux plate at the ice surface registered 0 Wm^{-2} at the North site (day 172) (Figure 3.4). The 0 Wm^{-2} heat flux indicated that the temperature difference between the snow pack and the ice surface was $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, i.e. that the snow pack had become isothermal and the ice surface had warmed to $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in response to the arrival of the penetrating melt (Section 5.3). Melt generated at the surface would have penetrated into the glacier and drained to the bed through macro-porous pathways. Such events, termed the “Spring Event” (Mair *et al.*, 2001; 2002a; 2002b; 2003) (and the “May Event” by Kulesa (2000)), cause initial disruption of the winter drainage system. It seems plausible that surface-derived meltwater may have transferred water to the bed of Tsanfleuron (and into the karst system beneath). This water-induced heat supply event however, (Figure 4.10) is unlikely to have been directly the effect of local supraglacial melt for a number of reasons:

- The glacier surface at the South site, in the vicinity of BH04-06 was highly impermeable, and the borehole was frozen closed for some metres at the surface.
- Had the thermal disturbance been driven directly by the percolation of surface melt the magnitude of the disturbance would have been expected to decrease in amplitude from the surface downwards, the reverse was true, supporting a basal origin for the heat flux.
- It is highly unlikely that local surface melt temperatures could be warmed as high as the $\sim 3.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ thermal disturbance measured at the bed.
- EC measurements in the adjacent BH05-10 indicate the inflowing waters had a conductivity of $25 - 30 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. Waters of this conductivity were identified by Tranter *et al.* (1997) to be bulk glacial runoff from the channel marginal zone, while supraglacially

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

derived melt waters were reported to exhibit conductivity values in the range $0 - 10 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$.

Thus although the seasonal “Spring event” surface derived water flux entered the glacier at or very close to the time of the observed basal temperature disturbance, at the local scale this water could not have been the direct cause of the warming.

Glacier de Tsanfleuron overlies extensive macro-porous limestone caves (Section 2.1) (the limestone is strongly karstified where exposed) and, as such, air and water flows between the cave system and the glacier bed form an integral part of the subglacial environment. Water stored in the subglacial karst aquifer during winter months, isolated from the subglacial drainage system, would have gained heat from positive rock temperatures and acquired solute whilst in contact with the rock. The plausibility of such heating is supported by rock temperature measurements collected in a borehole into the bed rock beneath Glacier d’Argentiere (Vivian, 1980) in which rock temperatures of $1.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were recorded at 5 m depth and $2.7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 40 m depth. Ford *et al.* (1976) also reported warming of $\sim 1.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for waters of subglacial provenance flowing through the Big Springs cave at Castlegaurd under the Columbia Icefield, Canada. If some form of hydrological change occurred distant from or more general to BH04-06 which resulted in flow from the glacier bed into the karst aquifer up glacier of BH04-06, the observed large thermal disturbance between June 19th and July 9th may therefore be explained by a large flow of over-winter warmed ground water from the karst aquifer towards the glacier bed in the vicinity of BH04-06.

This input may have been triggered / enhanced by heavy rain augmenting melt infiltration. Gordon *et al.* (2001) observed drainage system reorganisation at Haut Glacier d’Arolla in 1993 triggered by such events, similar to those at Tsanfleuron on day 177 (2006) (highlighted as possible triggers for slush flows at the glacier surface in Section 5.7). It must also be considered, however, that the process may have been deep within the karst aquifer detached from the glacier bed. Nevertheless it seems likely that subglacial drainage was involved in the initiation of this heat supply event. It is probable that these changes flooded a section of the karst system at a higher elevation, driving warmer, higher solute water flow out of the caves at a lower elevation into the subglacial drainage system and the cavity which BH04-06 intersected, causing the observed basal temperature rise.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

The gradual EC drop in BH05-10 observed to occur almost simultaneously with the temperature decrease recorded in BH04-06 (~ day 185 (Figure 4.10)) is attributed to drainage of the karstic waters from the system and mixing with more dilute supraglacial and englacial waters as the melt season progressed, after the initial influx of higher EC waters which acquired solute in the karst aquifer over-winter.

The water-driven heat supply event outlined above (Figure 4.10) appears to be a one off drainage event; no record of such an event is seen elsewhere in the thermistor record at any site (Figure 4.6). However since no data are available for the previous summer (due to data logger malfunction), there is no evidence to disprove the possibility that this is an annual event, triggered by the seasonal drainage system reorganisation.

Latent heat release on refreezing of melt

Similar to surface and englacial refreezing, water flowing to the bed englacially or from the karst aquifer will partially refreeze as it contacts cold ice refreezing, releasing latent heat. In the distributed sections of the subglacial drainage system this release, in combination with the process of water advection at the ice rock interface, provides an efficient means of transferring energy from areas of warm ice to areas of cold based ice, reducing the temperature difference.

Air flow at the bed

The general pattern of basal temperatures at the South site between August 2004 and January 2007 (Figure 4.6) suggests water flow was responsible for periodic large-scale water driven heat supply events superimposed on smaller amplitude, higher frequency air flow warming events (air flow events are inferred from temperature changes in the absence of associated changes in the EC and water pressure time series and from the scale and rate of warming events). Temperature records suggest the partially open BH04-06 borehole was predominantly air filled and under the influence of air flow driven temperature change, but subject to water inflow during subglacial drainage recharge from the karst aquifer (above).

Air flow within and into and out of caves (termed “cave breathing” (Faust, 1947; Wigley, 1967; Plummer, 1969)) is driven by buoyancy whereby air is forced to rise or sink through the cave system because of thermal differentials between the interior and the exterior of the cave (Freitas *et al.*, 1982). As a general model, winter air within caves is warmer than the outside ambient air temperature and cave air rises towards its upper entrances. The converse occurs in summer. Freitas *et al.* (1982) reported diurnally oscillating air flow directions within caves linked to the

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

diurnal solar heating cycle during the spring and autumn. If the upper entrances of the cave have the form of sinkholes under a glacier (commonly found over the limestone bedrock exposed by the post Little Ice Age retreat of Tsanfleuron (Figure 6.9 a and b)) then it is logical that air flow between the cave system and the glacier bed has the potential to supply additional energy to the glacier sole.

Ford *et al.* (1976) investigated Castleguard cave, located directly beneath the Columbia Icefield and found passageways blocked with glacial ice intruded to an unknown distance into the cave. During winter a strong air current was observed to flow upwards within the cave. Its exit point was not known, but was postulated to be “into the base of the icefield through exits that are not sealed air tight by ice... into the base of the glacier through open sink holes” Ford *et al.* (1976, p223). Similar strong air flow was reported by Atkinson *et al.* (1983), who also noted the reversal of flow during summer. Air temperatures within the Castleguard cave during winter were reportedly as high as + 3.6 °C, decreasing toward 0 °C in contact with the intruded ice in the explored, blocked passage (Ford *et al.*, 1976). Vivian (1980) reported the existence of “highly positive ambient air temperatures” of + 0.5 °C in natural cavities formed on the downhill slope of rock bars under Glacier d’ Argentiere. Vivian and Bocquet (1973) reported air temperatures fluctuating around + 0.5 °C in tunnels under the same glacier. The only feasible heat source to explain the warm air temperatures within such caves and those beneath Tsanfleuron was geothermal. Investigations found water flow within the Castleguard cave originated from the ice field bed and that this was removing energy away from the glacier sole. The effect of this water flow was to reduce the local geothermal heat flux to 10 – 40 % of its expected value. Further seasonal variations in cave air temperature were considered to be caused by the inflow of external air through the cave entrance (cave breathing) or by water flows through the cave. Such karstic warm air flows would explain the warm basal temperatures (Figure 4.6) and the fluctuations at the base of the South drill site at Tsanfleuron.

Strong evidence for subglacial karst interaction was reported by Ford (1971), where large sinkholes developed at the bottom of closed depressions created by glacial action in the forefield of the Columbia Icefield. The presence of such sinkholes infers integrated channels exist beneath (very similar to those observed in the forefield of Tsanfleuron (see Figure 6.9 a and b)). Provided sinkholes are not sealed with clastic debris or plugged with ice, karstification can be “very vigorous” in such regions (Ford, 1971). Massive carbonates such as the Mesozoic, Cretaceous (Urgonian) and Tertiary limestones underlying Tsanfleuron produce little drift (Smart, 1983).

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

Hence, under such lithological conditions little debris is generated by glacial erosion to block sinkhole openings, making development of karst connections over the hard bed very common.

Evidence for the existence of cavities, karst connections and thus a plausible basal heat supply mechanism under Tsanfleuron is compelling. Bedrock topographic depressions characterized by (in a down slope direction) striations on the stoss face of obstacles with evidence of plucking on lee side, a striation free area of negative topography (often with sinkholes situated within it) then the resumption of striations further down slope (Figure 6.9 c) suggesting widespread cavity formation under the glacier. Additional supporting evidence is provided by Chandler *et al.* (2006) who stated that “extensive cavity formation is consistent with studies of basal ice in this area which point to its formation in and around basal cavities (Tison and Lorrain, 1987)”. The drilling log for BH04-06 suggested evidence of a subglacial cavity at the time of drilling on day 133 (2004): just before drilling ceased the stem free fell for ~1 m and a hard contact was felt at a depth corresponding to the ice depth measured from the GPR survey. The drill stem became noticeably heavier indicating loss of buoyancy associated with hole drainage. Though no direct evidence is available for subglacial drainage connection to the karst system with BH04-06 (other than the observed temperature fluctuations), it is widely accepted that Tsanfleuron is predominantly drained through the cave system (Section 2.1). Such a connection therefore seems highly probable. Such a drainage mechanism into the permeable limestone has been invoked by Chandler *et al.*, (2006) as a means of preventing summer water pressure increases necessary for seasonally increased sliding velocities, to explain the velocities observed at the glacier surface.

It is therefore proposed that cave breathing provided a basal heat source, during the periodic temperature rises measured by the thermistor temperature time series at the South Site (Figures 4.6, 6.3 and 6.7).

Figure 6.9: Examples of sinkholes developed in the bottom of glacially formed cavities in exposed limestone in the forefield of Tsanfleuron (note the camera case and rucksack for scale respectively) ((a) and (b)), (c) Exposed striated bedrock with water pools in former subglacial depressions formed by over deepening in the lee of bed rock bumps (researcher for scale), and (d) diagrammatical representation of the heat flux at the glacier bed owing to “cave breathing”.

The following heating mechanism in the subglacial cavity below BH04-06 is proposed. Separation between the glacier ice and the bed in lee a bedrock bump allowed the formation of an air-filled cavity (Figure 6.9 d). If the cavity formed over a limestone sinkhole then an air contact could exist between the cave system and the glacier sole. Any liquid water flowing at the bed, or generated by regelation around the bedrock bump (or drainage from upslope) drained into the sinkhole rather than refroze on the lee side of the obstruction. If cave air temperatures and air flow patterns were similar to those reported by Ford *et al.* (1976) or Vivian (1980) then one would expect a flow of warm air toward the bed and out of the sink hole to the glacier sole. If the bottom of the borehole intersected one of these air filled cavities connected to the cave system

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

below, the borehole may have been kept open to a large distance above the bed by warm air rising up the borehole (Figure 6.9d). Periodic influxes of warm air from deeper caves are believed to have travelled up the borehole, warming the ice. As the air rose further up the borehole it transferred heat to the surrounding ice, cooling greater distances from the bed. Hence, the smaller-amplitude temperature variations higher up borehole (Figure 6.7). The periodic nature of the larger warming events (Figure 6.7) may be explained by processes within the karst system detached from the glacier bed; for example episodic drainage of other karst channels in response to changes in melt water supply in summer or early autumn or possibly due to basal sliding blocking and unblocking adjacent fissures in the rock.

In the absence of a partially open borehole, karstic basal heating would be limited to the glacier / rock interface. Depending on local ice flow this would tend to cause high local basal melting forming small subglacial cavities (such as that intercepted on contact with the bed during the drilling of BH04-06). The resulting meltwater would lubricate the glacier sole in the vicinity of the sinkhole, with implications for glacier sliding.

6.4.3 Basal heat sinks

Three processes are proposed as basal heat sinks or mechanisms by which energy fluxes at the bed of Glacier de Tsanfleuron may have been reduced (i) advection of cold ice; (ii) karstic water flow; and (iii) depression of geothermal heat flux by cooling at the last Glacial Maximum. These are considered below.

Advection of cold ice

The presence of sub-melting-point englacial and basal ice temperatures likely stems from advection of colder ice, formed at higher elevation. Continued burial gradually lowers the melting point (Section. 4.1.2). However, if advection and deformation transfer the ice quickly to depth or the ice was sufficiently cold after formation, situations can arise where colder ice exists out of thermal equilibrium with its surroundings.

Karstic water flow

Water flow is considered to have advected heat to the glacier sole and provided an efficient energy transfer mechanism from one basal location to another. Water flow has been shown to have both warming and cooling effects under various subglacial conditions and locations.

Favourable conditions for the prolonged survival of cold ice can result from the drainage of subglacial water into the underlying karst system. Under such scenarios small regions of the bed

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

immediately down glacier of the drainage capture lose the heat advection and liquid required for latent heat release, which would otherwise have warmed and / or melted cold ice locally.

Additionally, Ford *et al.* (1976) suggested that in heating near-surface subglacial rock, such ‘invasion’ waters effectively caused further ice cooling by reducing the local geothermal heat flux by up to 90%.

Depression of geothermal heat flux by cooling at the last Glacial Maximum

Haebereli *et al.* (1984) suggested that extensive permafrost may have reduced the geothermal flux in Switzerland by as much as 20 to 30 %. In some areas permafrost survives at depth from the Last Glacial Maximum. No account is made for such a reduction.

Summary

- Basal temperatures > 0 °C were measured at the South and North sites. At the South site, these temperatures were identified as air and water temperatures in a subglacial cavity connected to the karst aquifer. At the North site they were considered to be water temperatures in a partially open borehole connected to an isolated section of the distributed drainage system (not under connected to the karst aquifer).
- At the Central site (BH05-07) basal temperatures for the period following drilling (in August 2005) cooled to a minimum of ~ -0.33 °C in response to the presence of advected colder ice. After this, the basal temperatures warmed by a variety of processes to the local melting point. This exact correspondence of the measure temperature with the calculated melting point validates the method of melting point calculation outlined in Section 4.1.2.
- Heat sources to the basal ice varied in time and with location, but included some combination of: (i) geothermal heating; (ii) sliding-induced frictional heating; (iii) water flow at the bed and between the karst aquifer and the bed; (iv) latent heat release on refreezing and (v) air flow from the karst to the bed.
- The rapid propagation of basal heat fluxes up through the ice at the South site suggests the boreholes, particularly BH04-06, remained partly open throughout most of the ice depth for at least 33 months.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

- Water flow from the subglacial karst cave system in spring is invoked to explain the large positive basal thermal disturbance recorded in BH04-06 during the early summer 2006 (Figure 4.10).
- Cave breathing is outlined as the mechanism controlling diurnal and smaller amplitude longer duration heat supply events to the thermistor in the subglacial cavity at the South site.
- Advection of cold ice to the bed, abstraction of heat from the bed by waters draining into the subglacial karst, and a reduction in the geothermal heat flux (possibly as a consequence of subglacial water loss or permafrost cooling during the Last Glacial Maximum) are identified as mechanisms which acted as basal heat sinks.

6.5 Chapter summary

- Penetration of the winter cold wave resulted from heat loss via conduction upwards through the near-surface ice, at a rate driven by (i) the temperature gradient established between the ice surface and (ii) the warmer ice at depth and the thermal conductivity of the ice.
- Effective glacier ice thermal conductivity determined using the Fourier method was $1.96 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The calculated thermal diffusivity was $1.05 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.
- At the North site (BH04-01) the winter cold wave penetrated to a depth of 13.2 m in the 2004/05 winter and to 15.1 m in the 2005/06 winter. At the South site (BH04-06) the winter cold wave penetrated to 12.6 m in the 2005/06 winter. Data logger failure prevented other depth determinations.
- In both the 2005 and 2006 summers, elimination of the winter cold wave at the North site (BH04-01) occurred via the processes of conduction, percolation of melt advecting heat and latent heat release at depth in the ice. In contrast, at the South site (BH04-06) warming by conduction alone (with meltwater percolation inhibited by the absence of local crevassing) failed to eliminate the winter cold wave.
- Large sections of the temperature profile in each instrumented borehole were at or within $\pm 0.04 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$ of melting point.

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

- The seasonal thermally active layer was only at melting point throughout its whole depth at certain glacier locations for a few weeks. Thus, it is an oversimplification to assume that temperate ice is at the melting point throughout.
- Englacial heat sources, with the capacity to warm cold ice, include deformation- induced strain heating, englacial water flow and latent heat release.
- Englacial heat sinks, favouring the presence of below melting point cold ice, include advection of cold ice from higher elevation in the accumulation area and the cooling influence of crevasses.
- Basal temperatures >0 °C were measured at the South and North sites. At the South site, this was associated with air and water in a subglacial cavity connected to the karst aquifer. At the North site it was associated with water temperatures in a partially open borehole connected to an isolated section of the distributed drainage system not connected to the karst aquifer.
- At the Central site (BH05-07) basal temperatures following drilling cooled to a minimum of ~ -0.33 °C in response to the presence of advected colder ice. During the period August 2006 to January 2007 basal ice temperatures warmed to the local melting point in response to advection of heat via water flow and latent heat release in the vicinity of the borehole base.
- A large positive basal thermal disturbance recorded in BH04-06 during the early summer 2006 (Figure 4.10) is interpreted in terms of the inflow of warm water from the subglacial karst cave system probably driven by a higher elevation influx of water in spring. Waters stored over-winter in the cave system are likely to be warmer than those located at the ice bed interface.
- Cave breathing is outlined as the mechanism controlling diurnal and smaller amplitude longer duration heat supply events to the thermistor in the subglacial cavity at the South site.
- Perennial cold ice (i.e. that not resulting from the penetration of the winter cold wave or other short term disturbances) was identified at the North site at height of ~ 40 m a.b. in

CHAPTER 6: INTERPRETATION II

BH04-01, at the South site in BH04-06 between heights of 25 and 56 m a.b. and at the Central site below 35 m a.b. Thus regions of the glacier ice cannot be classed as temperate and must be reclassified as polythermal. The glacier is therefore reclassified as polythermal. A cold ice temperature minimum of $-0.99\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded at the South site, caused by advection of cold ice from up-glacier with insufficient heat available locally to warm it to melting point.

Chapter 7

Modelling: Energy balance and glacier temperatures.

7.1 Introduction

Modelling of glacier mass and energy balance is important for assessing the sensitivity of glaciers to climate change, for use in water resource management in mountain regions and for incorporation into studies of glacier dynamics and hydrological processes. Many models (as outlined in Section 1.11) have focussed on quantification and replication of simplified versions of the surface energy balance and mass balance without consideration of the conduction of heat into the snow pack and glacier ice e.g. Brock and Arnold (2000). Price (1986) and Braithwaite (1995a) have incorporated conduction of heat into the glacier surface into more complex models.

This chapter outlines an attempt to reconstruct non measured meteorological variables required for surface energy balance models, and to model the one dimensional, point surface energy balance, surface lowering and snow pack and ice temperatures of Glacier de Tsanfleuron from the atmospheric boundary layer to the glacier bed (by considering englacial and basal heat fluxes at depth in the ice). Measurements and derivations of the physical and thermal properties of the Tsanfleuron snow and ice are incorporated into the models in preference to generic published values. Comparisons are drawn between measured and modelled snow depth, ice ablation and snow and ice temperatures and consideration is given to the observed differences.

IPCC (2007) climate change predictions based on SRES emission scenarios (Nakicenovic and Swart, 2000), suggest a globally averaged surface temperature increase of between 1.1 to 6.4 °C and a best estimate of 1.8 to 4.0 °C by the year 2100, similarly precipitation is expected to rise under global warming scenarios (though less may fall as snow, particularly in summer). The snow and ice temperature models will further be used to asses the likely impact of such air temperature and precipitation increases on glacier temperatures within Tsanfleuron.

The basic glacier surface energy balance is outlined below. Fluxes into the glacier surface (providing energy for temperature change of the snow and near-surface glacier ice or melt once surface temperatures have reached melting point) are considered positive, with the exception of the turbulent fluxes which by convention are considered positive towards the atmosphere. The precipitation heat flux is considered negligible at Tsanfleuron (on the basis that very little liquid

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

precipitation falls in winter and that which falls over ice in summer quickly runs off) and thus was not incorporated into the energy balance equation in the form:

$$Q_{Sur} + Q_M = SW \downarrow - SW \uparrow + LW \downarrow - LW \uparrow - Q_{LE} - Q_H \quad (7.1.1)$$

where:

Q_{Sur} = Energy flux available for warming the surface,

Q_M = Energy flux available for generating melt,

$SW \downarrow$ = Short wave incident radiation flux,

$SW \uparrow$ = Short wave outgoing radiation flux,

$LW \downarrow$ = Long wave incoming radiation flux,

$LW \uparrow$ = Long wave emitted radiation flux,

Q_{LE} = Latent heat flux,

Q_H = Sensible heat flux.

Figure 7.1 outlines the interlinkage of the various modelling components and driving datasets involved in modelling the surface energy balance, snow and ice temperatures and snow and ice surface elevation changes. Section 7.2 details the process of quality control and infilling of missing driving data. Section 7.3 outlines the derivation of non measured meteorological variables ($SW \downarrow$, $LW \downarrow$ and snowfall), Section 7.4 presents sensible and latent heat flux determinations using bulk parameterizations, and a full characterization of the surface energy balance over the two year period of meteorological data collection. Snow pack evolution and temperature are modelled in Section 7.5, Section 7.6 addresses the ice surface ablation and glacier ice temperatures to the bed, incorporating englacial and basal heat sources, while an assessment of the snow and ice temperature change under global warming and precipitation increase best estimates is given in Section 7.7.

Figure 7.1: Flow diagram of the various stages involved in modelling of snow and ice temperatures.

7.2 Quality control and infilling of missing data in recorded meteorological time series

The snow depth, air temperature, relative humidity and wind speed time series collected by the AWS at the North site between February 2005 and February 2007 all had erroneous and missing data to various degrees. Erroneous and spurious data were recorded for a number of reasons including: icing of sensors preventing ventilation of the MP100A radiation shield and / or rotation of the RM Young propeller, build up of snow decreasing the distance between the SR50 and surface below the minimum range of 0.5 m (resulting in out of range data being recorded) and erroneous data resulting from data logger malfunction and idiosyncrasies. Erroneous data were removed manually following visual and statistical inspection of the raw data sets. In addition to time series gaps as a consequence of erroneous data removal, missing data arose from periods when sensor cables pulled out of the data logger in the snow pack due to balling of ice around spare cable and subsequent downward movement in the snow associated with compaction, a period when the meteorological station blew over in July 2005 and short periods when data collection was interrupted during routine maintenance.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

Complete data sets were required to provide driving data for non measured parameter reconstruction and energy balance modelling, thus the quasi physically based, MicroMet (Liston and Elder, 2006a) pre processing algorithms were used to fill missing data segments with realistic values, based on a variety of in filling procedures which included an “autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) calculation for diurnally varying variables” (Liston and Elder, 2006a).

Gaps in the data identified at the quality control and assurance stage were filled with calculated values. The missing data calculation procedures relied on the assumption that as long as the data lie within a given synoptic cycle, persistence is a reasonable approximation (Lister and Elder, 2006a). Based on the suggestion by Jolliffe and Stephenson (2003) that today’s weather is similar to the weather yesterday and tomorrow’s will be similar to today etc, three different conditions of missing data were identified with associated different data fill procedures (Lister and Elder, 2006a) as follows:

1. Single missing data values. These gaps were filled with the average of the preceding and following data points.
2. Missing data values in time segments ranging from 2 to 24 hours. These data were reconstructed from an average of the values from 24 hours before and 24 hours after each of the missing data points.
3. Missing data values in segments larger than 24 hours. These data were reconstructed in the MicroMet model by means of an ARIMA model subroutine devised by Box and Jenkins (1976). The ARIMA subroutine forecasts into the missing segments using the data preceding the gap and, backcasts into the segment using the data succeeding the gap. The two predictions are then linearly interpolated across the data gap (Lister and Elder, 2006a).

Outlined below in Figure 7.2 as an example of reconstructed missing data is a section of the wind speed time series showing a gap between day 87 and 115 (2006) caused by the sensor cables becoming detached from the data logger terminals. Use of the ARIMA model to forecast and backcast through the window of missing data and incorporation of the two derived datasets via linear interpolation produced the data displayed in grey, completing the data set, facilitating its use in the modelling of turbulent heat fluxes (Sections 7.4).

Figure 7.2: Gap filled wind speed data between day 60 and day 150 (2006), depicting the period when the RM Young wind monitor cables detached from the data logger terminals due to compaction in the snow pack pulling downwards on the excess cable looped below the logger enclosure (between day 87 and day 115).

7.3 Derivation of un recorded variables

7.3.1 Reconstruction of solid precipitation from snow depth measurements

Solid precipitation was not recorded at Tsanfleuron mainly due to the problems associated with snowfall gauges, e.g. under catch, evaporation and sublimation from the gauge and burial, especially during unattended deployment in a location which can experience in excess of 4 m of annual snowfall. A snowfall record was required for use in the energy balance model, and thus was derived from the gap filled SR50 snow depth and air temperature time series (Figure 3.15 and 3.1 a respectively). Reconstructions of this form, on the basis of how much snow had fallen to produce an observed snow depth, have been shown to accurately produce snowfall time series (Cherry *et al.*, 2005). A smoothed form (24 hour moving average) of the SR50 snow depth was used in preference to the raw snow depth data, as the smoothing procedure removed spikes which would have resulted in spurious snowfall generation. These data were read into a model which generated a snowfall data set (in the form of snow water equivalent of fresh snow at 30 minute resolution). The model also generated modelled snow depth (for comparison with the SR50 record), snow density and a record of snow water equivalent (SWE). When the driving, smoothed SR50 snow depth increased between time steps and the air temperature was below 2 °C (threshold temperature for solid precipitation), the fresh snowfall was calculated as:

$$S_f = \rho_0 \Delta SR50 \quad (7.3.1)$$

where:

S_f = Water equivalent fresh snowfall (mm W.E.),
 ρ_0 = Fresh snow density (kg m^{-3}) (calibrated value),
 $\Delta SR50$ = Depth increase in smoothed SR50 snow depth (m).

The modelled snow depth was incremented for snowfall in the form:

$$d_s = \frac{SWE}{\rho_s} + \frac{S_f}{\rho_0} \quad (7.3.2)$$

where:

d_s = Modelled snow depth (m),
 SWE = Modelled snow water equivalent (mm W.E.),
 ρ_s = Modelled snow density (kg m^{-3}),
 S_f = Water equivalent fresh snowfall (mm W.E.),
 ρ_0 = Fresh snow density (kg m^{-3}) (calibrated value).

Over time following snowfall, snow pack densification occurs. To take account of this compaction, the density was recalculated at each model time step in the form:

$$\rho_s = (\rho_s - \rho_m) \exp(-\Delta t / t_p) + \rho_m \quad (7.3.3)$$

where:

ρ_s = Modelled snow density (kg m^{-3}),
 ρ_m = Maximum snow density (kg m^{-3}) (calibrated value),
 Δt = Length of time step (s),
 t_p = Densification time constant (calibrated value).

The density was then recalculated as a mass – weight average of old and new snow densities in the form:

$$\rho_s = \frac{\rho_s SWE + \rho_0 S_f}{SWE + S_f} \quad (7.3.4)$$

where:

ρ_s = Modelled snow density (kg m^{-3}),
 SWE = Modelled snow water equivalent (mm W.E.),
 ρ_0 = Fresh snow density (kg m^{-3}) (calibrated value),
 S_f = Water equivalent fresh snow fall (mm W.E.).

Melt of the snow pack was calculated for temperatures above 0 °C in the form:

$$M_E = f_m \max(T, 0) \quad (7.3.5)$$

where:

M_E = Melt (mm W.E.),
 f_m = Temperature index melt factor (calibrated value),
 T = Air temperature (°C).

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

The SWE was then updated at each model time step from the value at the previous model time step, accounting for fresh snowfall and melt such that:

$$SWE^n = SWE^{n-1} + S_f - M_E \quad (7.3.6)$$

where:

- SWE^n = Modelled snow water equivalent at time step n (mm W.E.),
- SWE^{n-1} = Modelled snow water equivalent at time step n-1 (mm W.E.),
- S_f = Water equivalent fresh snow fall (mm W.E.),
- M_E = Melt (mm W.E.).

Model parameters were calibrated by means of a process involving the calculation of the RMS error in the simulated snow depth and readjustment of the model parameters to minimise these errors. The four calibrated parameters (maximum snow density = 400 kg m^{-3} , density time scale = 352, melt factor = 0.09 and the new snow density = 200 kg m^{-3}) required a search in a four dimensional space to find the optimum parameter combination.

The reconstructed snowfall time series is depicted in Figure 7.3 alongside a gap filled, smoothed version of the SR50 snow depth record; snow depth increases coincide closely with the periods of maximum snowfall. Snowfall is generally highest and most frequent during the winter months and considerably lower and more infrequent during summer months; one exception to this trend occurred with the snowfall rate of $0.0021 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($3.78 \text{ mm} / 30 \text{ min}$) in August 2006 on day 233, when heavy snowfall resulted in the deposition of a summer snow pack which remained on the glacier surface for a number of weeks. A maximum snow fall rate of $0.0025 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($4.50 \text{ mm} / 30 \text{ min}$) occurred on day 001 in January 2007.

Figure 7.3: Gap filled and smoothed snow depth and reconstructed snowfall between February 2005 and February 2007.

7.3.2 Reconstruction of shortwave incoming radiation (SW↓)

SW↓ was determined from a model incorporating the effects of the time of day and year, cloud cover, direct and diffuse solar radiation on the modelled SW↓ (Liston *et al.*, 1999).

Cloud cover was modelled from the surface air temperature and dew point temperature and applying lapse rates to calculate the temperature and dew point temperature at 700 mb level of the atmosphere. The 700 mb temperatures and dew point temperatures were then used to calculate the relative humidity at 700 mb. Liston and Elder (2006b).

$$RH_{700} = 100 \frac{e}{e_s} \quad (7.3.7)$$

where:

RH_{700} = Relative humidity at 700 mb level of the atmosphere (%),

e = Vapour pressure (Pa),

e_s = Saturation vapour pressure (Pa).

Saturation vapour pressure at the 700 mb level of the atmosphere was defined as:

$$e_s = a \exp\left(\frac{bT_{700}}{c + T_{700}}\right) \quad (7.3.8)$$

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

where:

- e_s = Saturation vapour pressure (Pa),
- $a = 611.15$ Pa for ice (Buck, 1981),
- $b = 22.452$ for ice (Buck, 1981),
- $c = 272.55$ °C for ice (Buck, 1981),
- T_{700} = Air temperature at 700 mb level of the atmosphere (°C).

From the relative humidity at 700 mb cloud fraction was derived following Walcek (1994) in the form:

$$\sigma_c = 0.832 \exp\left(\frac{RH_{700} - 100}{41.6}\right) \quad (0 \leq \sigma_c \leq 1) \quad (7.3.9)$$

where:

- σ_c = Cloud fraction,
- RH_{700} = Relative humidity at 700 mb level of the atmosphere (%).

$SW\downarrow$ incident upon the surface, assumed to be level, was formulated from:

$$SW\downarrow = S^*(\psi_{dir} + \psi_{dif})\cos Z \quad (7.3.10)$$

where:

- $SW\downarrow$ = Short wave incident radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$),
- S^* = Irradiance of the solar beam striking the top of the atmosphere (“Solar constant”) ($1370\ W\ m^{-2}$ (Kyle *et al.*, 1985)),
- ψ_{dir} = Direct net sky transmissivity,
- ψ_{dif} = Diffuse net sky transmissivity,
- Z = Solar zenith angle (°).

Solar zenith angle was formulated as:

$$\cos Z = \sin \delta \sin \varphi + \cos \delta \cos \phi \cos \tau \quad (7.3.11)$$

where:

- Z = Solar zenith angle (°),
- δ = Solar declination angle (°),
- φ = Latitude (°),
- τ = Hour angle measured from solar noon (°).

Hour angle was calculated from:

$$\tau = \pi \left(\frac{h_d}{12} - 1 \right) \quad (7.3.12)$$

where:

- τ = Hour angle measured from solar noon (°),
- h_d = Hour of the day.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

Solar declination angle was calculated from:

$$\delta = \phi_T \cos \left[2\pi \left(\frac{d - d_r}{d_y} \right) \right] \quad (7.3.13)$$

where:

- δ = Solar declination angle ($^{\circ}$),
- ϕ_T = Latitude of the tropic of Cancer ($^{\circ}$),
- d = Day of year,
- d_r = Day of the summer solstice,
- d_y = Average number of days in a year.

SW \downarrow was scaled following Burridge and Gadd, (1974) to account for the interaction of solar radiation with clouds (with an additional scaling factor of 1.21 added at Tsanfleuron to account for higher recorded SW \downarrow measurements) for direct radiation in the form:

$$\psi_{dir} = 1.21(0.6 + 0.2 \cos Z)(1.0 - \sigma_c) \quad (7.3.14)$$

where:

- ψ_{dir} = Direct net sky transmissivity,
- Z = Solar zenith angle ($^{\circ}$),
- σ_c = Cloud fraction.

and for diffuse radiation in the form:

$$\psi_{diff} = 1.21(0.3 + 0.1 \cos Z)\sigma_c \quad (7.3.15)$$

where:

- ψ_{diff} = Diffuse net sky transmissivity,
- Z = Solar zenith angle ($^{\circ}$),
- σ_c = Cloud fraction.

When measured SW \downarrow values were available from the CNR1 and SP LITE (deployed at the South site) measurements (August 2005 and July 2006 onwards), these were incorporated into the reconstructed SW \downarrow time series (Figure 7.4). The reconstructed SW \downarrow radiation time series (Figure 7.4) follows a sinusoidal pattern over an annual period, in response to changes in the zenith angle of the sun, with daily maxima peaking in excess of 1000 W m $^{-2}$ during the summer months of June and July and with winter minimum values during December. At the diurnal scale SW \downarrow radiation peaks at solar noon and decreases to 0 W m $^{-2}$ at night. The duration of nocturnal minima at 0 W m $^{-2}$ was greatest during winter and shortest during summer reflecting the annual variation in day length. The large number of low daily maximum values during the summer and autumn of 2006 reflect the influence of cloud cover reducing SW \downarrow , during completely overcast periods of summer snow and rainfall.

Figure 7.4: Daily maximum and mean reconstructed $SW\downarrow$ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

A limitation of the MicroMet cloud cover determination was that it did not accurately predict cloud cover in certain situations, e.g. under clear sky conditions where nocturnal, $LW\uparrow$ driven cooling could result in high near-surface relative humidities while cloud cover remained low. Improvements to account for such an oversimplification have been suggested based on incorporation of coincident surface and 700 mb meteorological data (Liston and Elder, 2006b) though such alterations are not implemented in this study. A further limitation of the reconstructive ability of the MicroMet model is visible in Figure 7.4, where $SW\downarrow$ values become considerably noisier during a short period in summer 2005 and from July 2006 onwards. Increased $SW\downarrow$ variability corresponds to the times of $SW\downarrow$ measurement and the incorporation of field data into the reconstructed time series, indicating the model does not replicate the full range of variability observed in the field.

7.3.3 Reconstruction of long wave incoming radiation ($LW\downarrow$)

$LW\downarrow$ was determined from a model incorporating the effects of air temperature, cloud cover amount and elevation related variations following Iziomon *et al.*, (2003). $LW\downarrow$ at the glacier surface was formulated as:

$$LW\downarrow = \varepsilon_a \sigma T^4 \quad (7.3.16)$$

where:

$LW\downarrow$ = Long wave incident radiation ($W\ m^{-2}$),
 ε_a = Atmospheric emissivity,

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$),
 T = Air temperature (K).

Atmospheric emissivity was modelled as:

$$\varepsilon_a = \kappa_c (1 + Z_s \sigma_c^2) [1 - X_s \exp(-Y_s e / T)] \quad (7.3.17)$$

where:

ε_a = Atmospheric emissivity,
 κ_c = Calibration parameter,
 Z_s = Elevation dependant coefficient,
 σ_c = Cloud fraction,
 X_s = Elevation dependant coefficient,
 Y_s = Elevation dependant coefficient,
 e = Atmospheric vapour pressure (Pa),
 T = Air temperature (K).

Elevation dependent coefficients X_s , Y_s and Z_s (based broadly on Iziomon *et al.*, 2003) were determined from the following:

$$\begin{aligned} C_s &= C_1 & z_L < 200 \\ C_s &= C_1 + (z_L - z_1) \left(\frac{C_2 - C_1}{z_2 - z_1} \right) & 200 \leq z_L \leq 3000 \\ C_s &= C_2 & 3000 < z_L \end{aligned} \quad (7.3.18)$$

where:

C = Can be substituted with X , Y and Z . $X_1 = 0.35$, $X_2 = 0.51$, $Y_1 = 0.100 \text{ K Pa}^{-1}$, $Y_2 = 0.130 \text{ K Pa}^{-1}$, $Z_1 = 0.224$ and $Z_2 = 1.100$,
 z_L = Elevation of the land surface,
 $z_1 = 200 \text{ m}$,
 $z_2 = 3000 \text{ m}$.

When measured $\text{LW}\downarrow$ were available from the CNR1 measurements (August 2005, August 2006 and January 2007), these were incorporated into the reconstructed $\text{LW}\downarrow$ time series (Figure 7.5). Reconstructed $\text{LW}\downarrow$ time series (Figure 7.5) follow a similar sinusoidal cycle with an annual periodicity, to that of the reconstructed $\text{SW}\downarrow$ radiation (Figure 7.4), reflecting the influence of water vapour increasing the thermal emissivity of the atmosphere. Diurnal maxima are lower than those of $\text{SW}\downarrow$, peaking at $\sim 375 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ during July and August and reaching minima of $\sim 150 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ during November and December. Contrary to the $\text{SW}\downarrow$ flux, values remain positive during nocturnal hours as emission from atmospheric sources continues in the absence of solar receipt at night. The largest $\text{LW}\downarrow$ fluxes are recorded on overcast days, in direct contrast to the magnitude of $\text{SW}\downarrow$ fluxes which peak under cloud free sky conditions.

Figure 7.5: Daily maximum and minimum reconstructed LW↓ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

7.4 Characterization of the full surface energy balance for the two year meteorological study period

The missing, non measured components of the surface energy balance over the full period of meteorological data collection were modelled using the “surf” subroutine of the “tsanf” glacier model (Essery, unpublished).

7.4.1 Turbulent heat flux determination

Turbulent heat flux calculations in the form of sensible and latent heat fluxes were determined using the bulk method, allowing closure of the surface energy balance equation (7.1.1).

Sensible heat flux was determined from the following:

$$Q_H = C_a \rho_a C_h u [T_s - T_a] \quad (7.4.1)$$

where:

- Q_H = Sensible heat flux ($W m^{-2}$),
- C_a = Specific heat capacity of dry air ($1005 J Kg^{-1} K^{-1}$),
- ρ_a = Density of air ($kg m^{-3}$),
- C_h = Bulk exchange coefficient,
- u = Wind speed at the height of measurements ($m s^{-1}$),
- T_s = Glacier surface temperature ($^{\circ}C$),
- T_a = Air temperature at the height of measurements ($^{\circ}C$).

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

Air density was determined from:

$$\rho_a = \frac{P_s}{R(T_a + 273.15)} \quad (7.4.2)$$

where:

- ρ_a = Density of air (kg m^{-3}),
- P_s = Surface air pressure (73000 Pa (imposed for an altitude of 2800m)),
- R = Specific gas constant for dry air ($287 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$),
- T_a = Air temperature at the height of measurements ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The bulk exchange coefficient was in the form:

$$C_h = \frac{k_V^2}{\ln\left(\frac{z_u}{z_0}\right) \ln\left(\frac{z_t}{0.1z_0}\right)} \quad (7.4.3)$$

where:

- C_h = Bulk exchange coefficient,
- k_V = Von Karman constant (0.40),
- z_u = Wind speed measurement height (m),
- z_0 = Surface roughness length (m),
- z_t = Air temperature measurement height (m).

As snowfall and snow and ice surface ablation occurs throughout the two year period of calculation, account was taken for the changing position of the glacier surface using the SR50 UDG time series combined with periodic measurements of instrument heights.

Latent heat flux was determined in the form:

$$Q_{LE} = L_s \rho_a C_h u [Q_s - Q_a] \quad (7.4.4)$$

where:

- Q_{LE} = Latent heat flux,
- L_s = Latent heat of sublimation (2845 kJ Kg^{-1}),
- ρ_a = Density of air (kg m^{-3}),
- C_h = Bulk exchange coefficient,
- u = Wind speed at the height of measurements (m s^{-1}),
- Q_s = Saturation specific humidity at the surface temperature (kg kg^{-1}),
- Q_a = Specific humidity at the height of the air temperature measurement (kg kg^{-1}).

The saturation specific humidity at the surface temperature was formulated as follows:

$$Q_s = \frac{0.622}{P_s} 611.213 \exp\left(\frac{17.5043T_s}{241.3 + T_s}\right) \quad (7.4.5)$$

where:

- Q_s = Saturation specific humidity at the surface temperature (kg kg^{-1}),
- P_s = Surface air pressure (73000 Pa (imposed for an altitude of 2800m)),
- T_s = Glacier surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

Glacier surface temperature was not measured directly (due to problems associated with unattended sensing over long periods of time under accumulation and ablation conditions), thus for the purposes of turbulent heat flux determination surface temperatures were derived from LW \uparrow time series (see Section 7.4.2) using the following formulation:

$$T_s = \left(\frac{LW \uparrow}{\varepsilon \sigma} \right)^{1/4} - 273.15 \quad (7.4.6)$$

where:

T_s = Glacier surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),

$LW \uparrow$ = Long wave radiation emitted by the glacier surface (see section 7.4.2)
(W m^{-2}),

ε = Emissivity of the surface (assumed to be 1.00),

σ = Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}$).

The specific humidity at the height of the air temperature measurement was formulated as:

$$Q_a = \frac{0.622(RH/100)}{P_s} 611.21 e^{\left(\frac{17.5043T_a}{241.3+T_a} \right)} \quad (7.4.7)$$

where:

Q_a = Saturation specific humidity at the height of the air temperature measurement
(kg kg^{-1}),

RH = Relative humidity (%),

P_s = Surface air pressure (73000 Pa (imposed for an altitude of 2800m)),

T_a = Air temperature at the height of measurements ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The bulk parameterizations were initially applied to the period between day 220 and day 240 (2006) over which eddy correlation measurements of sensible and latent heat flux allowed calibration of the model parameters. The surface roughness length (z_0) was optimised such that the RMS errors in the sensible heat calculation were minimised (optimisation using the latent heat measurements proved problematic due to extreme noise in the data set), this was achieved at a roughness length of 1×10^{-3} m. The bulk exchange coefficient (C_h) was thus determined to be 1.67×10^{-3} . Extreme noise in the measured latent heat flux was attributed to rainfall events, mechanical problems with the CSAT 3 and KH20 and difficulties in fixing the CSAT 3 head parallel to the ice surface and surface roughness elements over a spatially heterogeneous ice surface.

7.4.2 Modelling long wave radiation emission (LW \uparrow)

Having reconstructed LW \downarrow (see Section 7.3.3) the surface energy balance model sub-routine calculated net LW in the form:

$$LWn = LW\downarrow - \sigma T_s^4 \quad (7.4.8)$$

where:

LWn = Net long wave radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 $LW\downarrow$ = Long wave incoming radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 σ = Boltzmann's constant of proportionality ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} W m^{-2} K^{-4}$),
 T_s = Surface temperature (K).

With calculated values for LWn and $LW\downarrow$, $LW\uparrow$ was calculated from:

$$LW\uparrow = LW\downarrow - LWn \quad (7.4.9)$$

where:

$LW\uparrow$ = Long wave outgoing radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 $LW\downarrow$ = Long wave incoming radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 LWn = Net long wave radiation ($W m^{-2}$).

Glacier surface temperatures cannot exceed $0^\circ C$, resulting in an upper limit for $LW\uparrow$ from the glacier surface of $315.64 W m^{-2}$.

7.4.3 Modelling short wave radiation emission ($SW\uparrow$)

$SW\uparrow$ was determined from net SW , which was calculated by the surface energy balance model as a function of the reconstructed $SW\downarrow$ (see Section 7.3.2) in the form:

$$SWn = (1 - \alpha)SW\downarrow \quad (7.4.10)$$

where:

SWn = Net short wave radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 α = Albedo,
 $SW\downarrow$ = Short wave incoming radiation ($W m^{-2}$).

Expanding and simplifying Equation. 7.4.10 in terms of $SW\uparrow$ gave:

$$SW\uparrow = \alpha SW\downarrow \quad (7.4.11)$$

where:

$SW\uparrow$ = Shortwave outgoing radiation ($W m^{-2}$),
 α = Albedo,
 $SW\downarrow$ = Short wave incoming radiation ($W m^{-2}$).

Glacier surface albedo was modelled using an exponential decay function, decreasing albedo from that of freshly deposited snow at 0.95.

7.4.4 Results

Presented in Figures 7.6 and 7.7 are time series of sensible and latent heat respectively, determined over the two year period of meteorological data collection between February 2005 and February 2006. The sensible heat flux was predominantly negative over the two year period, indicating that for the most part, energy is being transferred from the atmosphere to the glacier

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

surface as a consequence of the temperature gradient generated by warmer air overlying a cold glacier surface. Superimposed upon the negative values was a general trend for higher less negative fluxes in summer and lower more negative fluxes in winter. Peak energy fluxes into the glacier of $\sim 80 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ occurred in February 2005, December 2006 and January 2007 respectively. Maximum energy losses via sensible heat transfer of $\sim 20 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ occurred in April 2006. The two year latent heat flux time series fluctuates highly about 0 W m^{-2} , the general trend was for lower more negative values during summer periods between mid May and September (Figure 7.7) transferring heat from the atmosphere to the glacier surface. Peak energy transfers of ~ 60 and $\sim 40 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ from the atmosphere to the glacier surface occurred in July 2005 and July 2006. Latent heat transfer to and from the glacier occurred in response to the establishment of specific humidity gradients between the atmosphere and the glacier surface. Energy transfer to the surface occurred when the atmospheric humidity exceeded the saturation humidity of the surface and water vapour condensed and / or froze on the glacier surface. Latent heat loss from the glacier, predominantly in the period March to May, was driven by evaporation and sublimation from the melting snow surface to the atmosphere, as a consequence of a profile of decreasing air water vapour content with height.

Figure 7.6: Reconstructed sensible heat flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Figure 7.7: Reconstructed latent heat flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Reconstructed daily maximum LW \uparrow depicted in Figure 7.8, remained almost constantly at a value of 315.64 W m^{-2} during summer months, reflecting the maximum possible temperature of $0 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to which the glacier surface temperature could rise. During the winter months LW \uparrow levels dropped noticeably, reaching a minimum of $\sim 276 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in December 2005 as a direct influence of boundary layer cooling of the glacier surface. LW \uparrow values decreased slightly during the night associated with nocturnal surface cooling, but did not decrease to 0 W m^{-2} in contrast to SW values.

Figure 7.8: Daily maximum and minimum reconstructed LW \uparrow flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Reconstructed SW \uparrow time series (Figure 7.9) show a clear annual cycle in the daily maximum and daily mean radiation values, reflecting the annual cycle in the SW \downarrow . SW \uparrow levels were directly related to the SW \downarrow through the surface albedo and as such the maximum SW \uparrow radiation values of $\sim 1000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ which occurred in May 2005 and August 2006 respectively, occurred at times of intense SW \downarrow and a high albedo controlled reflection from snow covered surfaces (see Figure 7.3). Dramatic decreases in SW \uparrow were observed when surface glacier ice was exposed during July to September 2005, between the end of July and beginning of August 2006 and September to mid October 2006 with values dropping by $\sim 400 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ from $\sim 600 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ under snow cover conditions to $\sim 200 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ under ice surface conditions. The lower SW \uparrow values under exposed ice surface conditions were a consequence of the lower albedo and hence higher absorption by the ice surface, with energy used to warm and melt the ice surface and transferred to depth to eliminate the winter cold wave, rather than being reflected back to the atmosphere. During the 2006 summer, the daily maximum and daily mean SW \uparrow fluxes were notably higher than the preceding summer and became a lot noisier (with large low spikes) from the end of July onwards (Figure 7.9) corresponding closely with the period when the glacier surface was snow covered (see Figure 7.3) and poor weather, atypical summer snow and rain storms dominated the meteorology. At the diurnal timescale SW \uparrow values closely mirrored those of the SW \downarrow , similar to the SW \downarrow flux, the SW \uparrow was 0 W m^{-2} during nocturnal hours.

Figure 7.9: Daily maximum and mean reconstructed $SW\uparrow$ flux for the period of basic meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Comparison of the smoothed daily mean values of the four individual components of radiation (Figure 7.10) suggests that, although over any 30 minute day time period of data collection $SW\downarrow$ would be significantly greater than both $LW\downarrow$ and $LW\uparrow$, averaged over the full 24 hour period in summer the fluxes are of similar magnitude and during winter the long wave fluxes were notably higher. $SW\downarrow$ exhibits the largest daily average flux of $\sim 350 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in June of both 2005 and 2006. During summer months the difference between $SW\downarrow$ and $SW\uparrow$ drove near-surface snow and ice diurnal temperature cycles and melting. During the winter months, $SW\downarrow$ was approximately half $LW\downarrow$ due to the seasonal decreased $SW\downarrow$ and a higher frequency of overcast (high $LW\downarrow$ emitting) conditions. Equally during the winter months (specifically October to April) $SW\downarrow$ and $SW\uparrow$ fluxes were similar in magnitude (reflecting the high albedo of fresh snow), but over the same period the $LW\uparrow$ flux was consistently higher than the $LW\downarrow$ flux (by as much as 150 W m^{-2} per day), contributing directly to a net energy loss at the glacier surface (Figure 7.12) and the observed glacier surface cooling (Figures 4.5 to 4.8). Over the two year period, $LW\uparrow$ is the least varying radiation component, reflecting the limited range of temperatures experienced by the glacier surface.

Figure 7.10: Reconstructed time series of the four individual radiation components (smoothed with a 10 day moving average).

7.4.5 Glacier surface energy balance discussion

The energy budget column plot (Figure 7.11) allows consolidation and visual comparison of the six main heat sources and sinks occurring at the glacier surface. Clear annual trends are visible in both energy addition and loss. Winter months, December in particular, saw the smallest combined energy transfers, while summer months exhibited the most dynamic energy transfers. Maximum monthly average energy transfers (both to and from the glacier surface) occurred in June in both 2005 and 2006, reflecting the dominant control $SW\downarrow$ exerts over the surface energy balance. When compared to the SW and LW radiative fluxes at a monthly scale, the turbulent heat fluxes were of limited importance at Tsanfleuron (at shorter time scales their relative contribution was greater). Monthly average sensible heat fluxes were negative throughout the two years of data collection while latent fluxes were more variable, acting as a surface heat source and sink in different months.

Figure 7.11: Modelled monthly average energy fluxes for each surface energy source over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection.

Totalling the daily mean energy additions and losses at the glacier surface determined the surface energy flux (Figure 7.12). Annual cyclicality prevails throughout this flux, reflecting the annual cycle in the dominant radiation components (especially SW↓) (Figures 7.10 and 7.11). The surface energy flux was positive resulting in a net energy gain in summer between May and September 2005 and April and October 2006 and negative resulting in a net energy loss during the winter between October and April. Maximum daily average values of $\sim 300 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ were calculated for July 2005 and 2006, at times of high SW↓ and an exposed ice surface, displaying a low albedo resulting in high energy absorption driving ice warming and melt. A dramatic decrease in surface energy flux occurred at the end of July and during August 2006 attributed to changes in the surface albedo from that of glacier ice to that of fresh snow following a large summer snowfall event. This reduction in the net energy addition would have resulted in a slowing of the elimination of the ice “winter cold wave”. Minimum daily average flux values of $\sim -100 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ were calculated for the period between October and March.

Analysis of snow and ice temperature time series (Figures 3.20 b, 4.5 and 4.9 b) indicate changes in the surface energy flux (Figure 7.12) drive rapid changes in the ice temperatures, through alterations of temperature gradients near the glacier surface. Somewhat counter intuitively snow temperatures do not follow changes in the surface energy flux as closely as those recorded in the ice (reductions in snow temperatures caused by surface energy loss are replenished by energy transfer from the ice beneath). Initiation of near-surface ice cooling and the re-establishment of

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

the “winter cold wave”, in the 2005 – 2006 winter, began in October and ceased at the end of April (Figure 4.5) when warming and “cold wave” elimination began in May (Figure 4.9 b), closely following the changes in the surface energy flux. Ice cooling began when the surface heat flux became negative initiating conductive heat transfer towards the glacier surface following establishment of negative temperature gradients in the near-surface ice. During the spring, the near-surface glacier ice began to warm shortly after the surface energy flux became positive in April. Once the heat flux became positive, melt-water would have begun to percolate through the snow pack transferring heat to the ice surface, reversing the temperature gradient in the immediate vicinity of the surface, allowing conduction of heat to begin downwards into the ice surface, initiating the process of elimination of the “winter cold wave”

Figure 7.12: Modelled daily mean energy flux at the glacier surface available for surface temperature change or melt over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection.

Summary

- $SW\downarrow$ displays a clear annual cyclicality and directly influences both the $SW\uparrow$ and the $LW\downarrow$ fluxes and thus the glacier surface energy flux also exhibits a strong annual cycle.
- Sensible and latent heat fluxes predominantly add energy to the glacier surface, however, their relative magnitudes are small in comparison with the dominant radiation fluxes at Tsanfleuron.

- Glacier surface albedo exerts a strong control over $SW\uparrow$, with large amounts of $SW\downarrow$ reflected from snow surfaces and large amounts of $SW\uparrow$ absorbed by exposed ice.
- Summer snowfall events have the capacity to dramatically reduce the surface energy flux via alteration of the surface albedo, greatly reducing the energy available for elimination of the ice “winter cold wave”.
- Changes in the direction of heat conduction in the near-surface ice closely follow changes in the direction of the glacier surface energy flux. Positive summer energy fluxes drive ice warming and melt, while negative winter fluxes result in ice cooling.

7.5 Modelling snow pack evolution and temperatures

Snow pack and glacier ice temperatures, snow accumulation and ablation and ice surface lowering were modelled using the one dimensional (1D) modular “tsanf” glacier model (Essery, unpublished). The model was driven by: $SW\downarrow$ ($W\ m^{-2}$), $LW\downarrow$ ($W\ m^{-2}$), snowfall ($kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-2}$), air temperature (K), wind speed ($m\ s^{-1}$), surface pressure (Pa) and relative humidity (%). Whenever available, snow and ice physical and thermal properties specific to Tsanfleuron were implemented in preference to published values (values of which are outlined in Table 7.1), with model output being compared directly against field data (presented in Chapters 3 and 4).

<i>Modelling parameter</i>	<i>Tsanfleuron values</i>	<i>Published value</i>
Snow density	176 to 497 $kg\ m^{-3}$	50 to 400 $kg\ m^{-3}$ (Paterson, 1994)
Snow thermal conductivity	0.19 to 1.78 $W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$	0.021 to 0.654 $W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$ (Sturm <i>et al.</i> , 1997)
Ice density	894 $kg\ m^{-3}$	830 to 917 $kg\ m^{-3}$ (Paterson, 1994)
Ice thermal conductivity	1.96 $W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$	2.10 $W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$ (Paterson, 1994)

Table 7.1: Tsanfleuron snow and ice properties used in the “tsanf” glacier model (Essery, unpublished) with published values for comparison.

7.5.1 Model description

The evolution of snow depth and temperatures were modelled using the “snow” subroutine of the “tsanf” model, based largely on the JULES (Joint UK Land Environment Simulator) multi layer snow model (Essery, 2005). A variable number of layers were used in the model as the snow depth changed, solid precipitation and melting snow were added or removed from the top of the snow pack and melt-water drained immediately from the snow pack (Essery, 2005). Prescribed snow physical and thermal properties remained constant throughout the modelling period. At

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

each model time step, the number and depth of snow layers were determined, heat conduction between each layer was calculated, snow temperatures were determined and surface albedo evolved from that of 0.95 for fresh snow, decreasing over time, driven by an albedo decay time constant. Similarly at each time step the snow mass balance was updated, accounting for the processes of surface snow melt, snow removal via sublimation and fresh snow and frost deposition.

The “snow” model subroutine did not consider the effects of:

- Percolation of liquid water through the snow, sourced either from liquid precipitation or surface derived melt and the associated heat advection.
- Latent heat release due to refreezing of water within the snow pack or at the snow, ice surface interface.
- Freezing of the snow pack at night and during cold periods in the ablation season, (though the snow temperature falling to below 0 °C was included).
- Changes in the snow pack thermal conductivity and porosity due to densification.
- Penetration of SW↓ into the snow pack and the associated heating below the surface.
- Mechanical snow ablation processes specifically slush flows, but also wind scour.

7.5.2 Results

Modelled and measured snow depth correspond well for the period of investigation (Figure 7.13). Measured maximum snow depth was slightly higher than that produced by the model in both 2005 and 2006, 3.80 and 4.38 m compared to 3.49 and 4.05 m respectively, though the maxima occurred simultaneously in both data sets. The modelled snow depth is not as noisy as the measured record, possibly reflecting removal by the model of some noise in the SR50 data attributed to non snowfall processes e.g. the passage of sastrugi and blowing snow beneath the UDG. Slight differences in the rate of snow ablation occurred from the maximum depth in May 2005. Both the measured and modelled snow packs began to ablate within 2 days of each other. However, the measured ablation rate was faster than the modelled over the period; day 510 to 558 (144 to 192, 2005) to the extent that on day 522 (156, 2005) the remaining modelled snow pack was 0.52 m deeper than that measured by the SR50. Following day 558 (192, 2005) measured and modelled ablation rates coincide perfectly, with the ice surface exposed on day 574 (209, 2005). Accumulation during the 2005-06 and 2006-07 winters is accurately represented in the model. Discrepancy between the two data sets in the period; day 837 to 869 (106 to 138, 2006) is attributed to burial of the SR50 (or reduction of the distance to the snow surface to below its minimum range of 0.5 m) and infilling of the missing data with daily snow depth measurements

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

made by Glacier 3000 ski patrols elsewhere on the glacier (intermediate values were generated during the gap filling procedure (see Section 7.2)). Modelled snow time series in this period may be more accurate than the time series against which it is being validated (a conclusion based on the good co-variation of modelled and measured snow depth over the remainder of the data set). Rapid ablation of the snow pack in 2006 was predicted to be slightly faster by the model than that measured at the SR50, with the model predicting ice surface exposure on day 934 (203, 2006) compared with the measured exposure on day 940 (209, 2006). From the comparisons drawn from Figure 7.13 it is fair to conclude that the parameterisation of snow accumulation and ablation is significantly well represented in the “tsanf” model.

Figure 7.13: Comparison of modelled and measured snow depth over the two year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Comparing the measured and modelled 0.2 m snow temperature time series (Figure 7.14) it is clear that for the most part modelled temperatures are considerably colder ($\sim 4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) than those measured with thermistors. Late March 2005 is the only period when measured and modelled temperatures coincide. For the whole of the 2005-06 winter, modelled snow temperatures were ~ 5.4 to $7.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ colder than the measured. Discrepancy between measured and modelled snow temperatures was primarily an artefact of the relation of the snow temperature to air temperature in the “tsanf” model, which resulted in a 0.2 m snow temperature minima of $-30.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (not displayed on in Figure 7.14 due to the scale of the axis) at the time of and soon after deposition on day 689 (323, 2005). Temperature minima at the time of deposition resulted in a “hangover

effect” for the remainder of the winter snow cover period in the absence of sufficient heating processes included in the model to warm the snow following deposition.

The timing of the sharp increases in temperature towards late spring in both years are driven by the percolation of the wetting front as the surface derived melt transfers heat through the snow pack to the ice surface and the snow pack becomes isothermal. In 2005 the measured temperature increase began on day 486 (120) and was completed by day 508 (142) while the modelled temperature increase began on day 550 (184) and was completed by day 571 (205). In 2006 the measured temperature increase began on day 846 (115) and would have been complete by ~ day 870 (139) (had the data logger not failed) while the modelled temperature increase occurred between day 918 (187) and day 956 (195). The delay between the timing of the modelled temperature increases relative to the measured values is explained by the lack of incorporation of melt water transport and heat transfer through the snow pack in the “tsanf” model, which relies purely on conductive heat transfer to warm the snow pack.

Figure 7.14: Comparison of modelled and measured snow temperature time series.

All snow temperature profiles except that on day 59 (immediately after initiation of the model) exhibit colder modelled temperatures than those measured by the thermistor strings (Figure 7.15). The warmer modelled than measured snow temperature on day 59 (February) 2005 reflects the fact that the profile used for initialisation of the model was too warm. This problem is quickly rectified in the model and by day 80 (March) 2005 the modelled temperature had cooled to below

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

that of the measured profile, 5.35 °C colder at a height of 2.4 m above the ice surface. On day 340 (December) 2005 under a shallow early winter snow pack, modelled temperatures were again notably below those measured, though the shape of the profile was well represented with the coldest snow temperatures nearest the surface. The modelled temperature profile on day 100 (April) 2006 displays a temperature difference of ~ 5 °C throughout the full snow depth for which thermistor records were available, with measured temperatures once again warmer. The day 100 modelled profile is beneficial as even though it exhibits a - 5°C shift in temperature, it allows the conclusion to be drawn that; by this date snow temperatures had begun to warm from the surface, a conclusion which could not have been drawn from the thermistor time series alone. Profiles for days 138 (May) 2005 and 136 (May) 2006 indicate that although the measured snow temperatures had become more or less isothermal at 0 °C by these dates in both years, the model does not replicate this with temperature minima of - 6.1 °C at 2.0 m above the ice surface in 2005 and - 9.1 °C at 1.7 m in 2006. Both modelled profiles show evidence of surface derived warming conducted downwards through the snow pack. The time lag of modelled temperatures behind those measured is attributed to incomplete parameterisation of the heat transfer processes through the snow in the “tsanf” model, specifically in terms of the routing of surface derived melt, which was assumed to instantaneously “runoff” where as in reality it percolates through the snow pack providing a key heat transfer mechanism dominating the thermal evolution of the snow pack towards isothermal status. Other snow pack warming processes speculated to occur at Tsanfleuron, not included in the model which may impact on the discrepancy between measured and modelled temperature profiles include; penetration of SW↓ into the upper layers of the snow pack and warming below the surface as a consequence (see Section 1.8.1) and localised melt generation and percolation for a short period around noon on warm days with high SW↓ receipt before the snow surface warms to 0 °C later in the year.

Figure 7.15: Comparison of selected modelled and measured snow temperature profiles.

Summary

- Snow accumulation and ablation are well predicted by the “tsanf” model.
- Snow temperature time series and profiles are notably colder than measured values.
- Heat transfer through the snow pack is represented in the model as occurring purely via conduction, this is an oversimplification.

- Percolation of surface derived melt water into the snow pack and the associated heat advection and latent heat release upon refreezing at depth in the snow pack are not considered in the model and are identified as key processes requiring parameterisation to improve the co-variation of measured and modelled snow temperatures.

7.6 Modelling ice surface ablation and glacier ice temperatures

7.6.1 Model description

Ice temperatures and surface ablation were modelled using the “ice” subroutine of the “tsanf” model (Essery, unpublished), details of the parameterization of the various heat sources within the ice are outlined below. At each time step conduction within the ice column and the resulting ice temperatures were calculated, incorporating the effects of the energy flux at the ice surface, geothermal and sliding induced frictional heating at the bed and englacial heat generation via deformation driven strain heating and when melt occurs, ice surface lowering.

This study deals with temperature profiles measured in boreholes which move down glacier with the glacier ice, thus the effect of heat transfer via horizontal ice advection need not be considered, as the analysis is not dealing with a fixed point in space with different temperature ice being advected through that specific location. Heat transfer was only considered in the vertical dimension. As surface slopes on Tsanfleuron are relatively low ($\sim 3 - 5^\circ$ in the immediate vicinity of the boreholes) and surface velocity is also low, in the range 3.7 to 46.4 m yr⁻¹ (Chandler, 2005), warming of the ice via transport to lower altitudes where air temperature is higher, a warming mechanism outlined by Jenssen and Radok (1963) need not be considered either.

In addition neither does the “ice” model subroutine consider the effects of:

- Firn compaction, as all three boreholes were located in the ablation area,
- Crevasses and cracks acting as near-surface heat sources and sinks,
- Heat advection at the ice surface via water flow from up glacier (only likely to be important at the South site where the ice surface is impermeable),
- Penetration of melt-water into the ice surface and the associated heat advection,
- Englacial water flows, storage and refreezing,
- Water flow at the bed advecting heat from up glacier and from the subglacial karst system,
- Air flow between the glacier bed and the subglacial karst system,

- Superimposed ice formation (observed to occur at the South site).

Conductive heat fluxes within the ice column

Surplus or deficit from the surface energy balance is accounted for by means of the conductive heat flux in the near-surface ice, into the glacier during times of surplus in the summer and out of the ice towards the atmosphere to replace energy lost through the snow pack during times of deficit in winter. The “ice” subroutine of the “tsanf” model considers conductive heat transfer through the ice column by means of dividing it into 0.2 m thick layers. The change in ice temperature over time between two intermediate layers in the ice column was expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial T_n}{\partial t} = \frac{[Q_{n-1} - Q_n]}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n} + \frac{H_s}{\rho_i c} \quad (7.6.1)$$

where:

- $\partial T_n / \partial t$ = Rate of change in temperature of the nth ice layer (K s⁻¹),
- Q_{n-1} = Conductive heat flux into the nth ice layer from the layer above (W m⁻²),
- Q_n = Conductive heat flux out of the nth ice layer to the layer below (W m⁻²),
- ρ_i = Ice density (kg m⁻³),
- c = Specific heat capacity (J K⁻¹ kg⁻¹) (2097 J K⁻¹ kg⁻¹ for ice),
- Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m),
- H_s = Strain heating (W m⁻³) (see below).

The conductive heat flux (defined as positive into the ice) was parameterized as:

$$Q_n = -K \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) \quad (7.6.2)$$

where:

- Q_n = Conductive heat flux (W m⁻²),
- K = Thermal conductivity (W m⁻¹ K⁻¹),
- T = Ice temperature (K),
- z = Depth below the ice surface (m).

Expressing the conductive heat flux as a function of the temperature difference between two layers rather than a temperature gradient, gave:

$$Q_n = K \frac{(T_n - T_{n+1})}{\Delta z} \quad (7.6.3)$$

where:

- Q_n = Conductive heat flux (W m⁻²),
- K = Thermal conductivity (W m⁻¹ K⁻¹),
- T_n = Temperature of the nth ice layer (K),
- T_{n+1} = Temperature of the ice layer below the nth ice layer (K),
- Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m).

Converting $\partial T / \partial t$ to a temperature difference equation gave:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \approx \frac{T_n^{(i+1)} - T_n^{(i)}}{\Delta t} \quad (7.6.4)$$

where:

$\partial T/\partial t$ = Rate of temperature change over time (K s^{-1}),
 $T_n^{(i+1)}$ = Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer at time step $i+1$ (K),
 $T_n^{(i)}$ = Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer at time step i (K),
 Δt = Length of time step (s).

Substituting Equation. 7.6.3 into Equation. 7.6.1 gave:

$$\frac{\partial T_n}{\partial t} = \frac{K}{\rho c \Delta z^2} [(T_{n-1} - T_n) - (T_n - T_{n+1})] + H_s \quad (7.6.5)$$

Substituting Equation. 7.6.4 and 7.6.13 into Equation. 7.6.5 and rearranging, gave the temperature change of the temperature of the n^{th} layer:

$$\Delta T_n = \frac{K \Delta t}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n^2} [T_{n+1} + T_{n-1} - 2T_n] + \frac{2 \times 10^{-6} e^{0.0906z}}{\rho_i c} \quad (7.6.6)$$

where:

ΔT_n = Temperature change of the n^{th} ice layer (K),
 K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
 ρ_i = Ice density (kg m^{-3}),
 Δt = Length of time step (s),
 c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$),
 Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m),
 T_{n-1} = Temperature of the ice layer above the n^{th} ice layer (K),
 T_n = Temperature of the n^{th} ice layer (K),
 T_{n+1} = Temperature of the ice layer below the n^{th} ice layer (K),
 z = Depth below ice surface (m).

For the surface layer, the temperature change at each time step was calculated as:

$$\frac{\Delta T_1}{\Delta t} = \frac{[Q_0 - Q_1]}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n} \quad (7.6.7)$$

where:

ΔT_1 = Temperature change of the top ice layer ($n = 1$) (K),
 Δt = Length of time step (s),
 Q_0 = Conductive heat flux from the surface energy balance (W m^{-2}),
 Q_1 = Conductive heat flux out of the top ice layer to the layer below (W m^{-2}),
 ρ_i = Ice density (kg m^{-3}),
 c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$),
 Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m).

The conductive heat flux into the top ice layer was output directly from the surface energy balance thus:

$$Q_0 = G_s \quad (7.6.8)$$

where:

Q_0 = Conductive heat flux from the surface energy balance (W m^{-2}),
 G_s = Heat flux at the ice surface output from the “surf” subroutine of the “tsanf” glacier model (Essery, unpublished) (W m^{-2}).

The conductive heat flux out of the top layer to the layer below was:

$$Q_1 = K \frac{(T_{(1)} - T_{(2)})}{\Delta z_n} \quad (7.6.9)$$

where:

Q_1 = Conductive heat flux out of the top ice layer to the layer below (W m^{-2}),
 K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
 $T_{(1)}$ = Temperature of the top ice layer (K),
 $T_{(2)}$ = Temperature of the second ice layer below (K),
 Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m).

Combining Equations. 7.6.7, 7.6.8 and 7.6.9 gave the temperature of the uppermost ice layer at each time step in the form:

$$\frac{\Delta T_1}{\Delta t} = \frac{G_s}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n} - \frac{K}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n^2} (T_{(1)} - T_{(2)}) \quad (7.6.10)$$

where:

ΔT_1 = Temperature change of the top ice layer (K),
 Δt = Length of time step (s),
 G_s = Heat flux at the ice surface output from surface energy balance model (W m^{-2}),
 ρ_i = Ice density (kg m^{-3}),
 c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$),
 Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m),
 K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
 $T_{(1)}$ = Temperature of the top ice layer (K),
 $T_{(2)}$ = Temperature of the second ice layer below (K).

The temperature of the basal ice layer at each time step was modelled as:

$$\frac{\Delta T_N}{\Delta t} = \frac{[Q_{N-1} - Q_N]}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n} + \frac{H_S}{\rho_i c} \quad (7.6.11)$$

where:

ΔT_N = Temperature change of the bottom (N^{th}) ice layer (K),
 Δt = Length of time step (s),
 Q_N = Conductive heat flux from the glacier bed (W m^{-2}),
 Q_{N-1} = Conductive heat flux from the layer above the bottom layer (W m^{-2}),
 ρ_i = Ice density (kg m^{-3}),
 c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$),
 Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m),
 H_S = Strain heating (W m^{-3}) (see below).

The conductive heat flux into the bottom ice layer (Q_N) was assigned a constant value of $89.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W m}^{-2}$, to account for the geothermal and sliding induced frictional heating. The geothermal heat flux (occurring perpendicular to the glacier sole) was a constant energy input to the bottom ice layer of $80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W m}^{-2}$, from Sclatter *et al.* (1980) for European rocks in the age bracket 0 to 250 Ma, while heat generation at the glacier bed caused by friction as the ice slid over the hard bed rock was calculated using Equation 1.10.1. Input values of: ice density at 894 kg m^{-3} (derived from the Tsanfleuron ice core analysis (Section 4.1.3)), ice thickness of 128.5 m, an assumed sliding velocity of 10.55 mm d^{-1} (based on the Tsanfleuron subglacial velocity measurements (Hubbard, 2002)) and a surface slope value of 5° resulted in a constant friction derived heat flux of $9.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W m}^{-2}$. The conductive flux from the layer above that at the bed was parameterized as:

$$Q_{N-1} = \frac{K}{\rho_i c \Delta z_n} (T_{N-1} - T_N) \quad (7.6.12)$$

where:

- Q_{N-1} = Conductive heat flux from the layer above the bottom layer (W m^{-2}),
- K = Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$),
- ρ_i = Ice density (kg m^{-3}),
- c = Specific heat capacity ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$),
- Δz_n = Ice layer thickness (m),
- T_{N-1} = Temperature of the ice layer above that at the bed (K),
- T_N = Temperature of the basal ice layer (K).

Incorporation of deformation-driven strain heating

Repeat inclinometry of boreholes at the South site, in the vicinity of BH04-06 produced datasets of ice deformation variation with depth, the differentiation of which produced profiles of strain with height above the bed (data for the North site were not available due to problems encountered when re-drilling holes prior to re-inclinometry). Strain rate in conjunction with stress after Pohjola and Hedfors (2003), permitted determination of the deformation-driven strain heating at 1 m separation depths within the ice using the repeat inclinometry data, following Equation 1.9.3. An exponential curve was fitted through the South site strain heating values, allowing deformation-driven strain heating flux incorporation into the “ice” subroutine of the “tsanf” model and extrapolation to a depth of 128.5 m (assuming glacier surface slope was the same at both sites). Strain heating was modelled in the form:

$$H_S = 2 \times 10^{-6} e^{0.0906Z} \Delta Z \quad (7.6.13)$$

where:

- H_S = Strain heating (W m^{-3}),

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

z = Depth below ice surface (m).

The model was initiated with an ice temperature profile assuming the ice to be at melting point below 20 m, and no heat sinks are modelled in the englacial and basal ice, thus, the effects of geothermal, frictional and strain heating fluxes are not visible in the ice temperature profiles (Figure 7.18) as the ice temperature cannot exceed melting point. The effects of these heating fluxes would be apparent if heat loss at depth occurred where they would act to counteract the cooling, in the absence of such cooling, energy from these fluxes melts ice. The amount of melt generated due to strain heating throughout the entire ice column (assuming the ice temperature to be at melting point and ice velocity remains constant) is calculated as the integral of Equation. 7.6.13 in the form:

$$Melt = \frac{a}{bL_f} (e^{bz_i} - 1) \quad (7.6.14)$$

where:

$$a = 2 \times 10^6,$$

$$b = 0.0906,$$

$$L_f = \text{Latent heat of fusion } (0.334 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}),$$

$$Z_i = \text{Total ice depth (m)}.$$

such that 214 mm a⁻¹ of ice is melted throughout the column by strain heating.

7.6.2 Results

Modelled ice surface ablation (Figure 7.16) was greater than measured ablation, 2.55 m compared to a measured 0.63 m during the 2005 summer and 2.26 m compared to 0.90 m in 2006 respectively. Comparison of the modelled and measured ice temperatures (see Figures 7.17 and 7.18) indicates however, that at the same time, modelled ice temperatures were notably colder than those measured in the field, suggesting that the heat flux at the ice surface was not being conducted fast enough into the ice, rather remaining at the surface melting ice. It is apparent that the partitioning of the ice surface heat flux, between that for surface warming and melting and that transferred to depth for elimination of the “winter cold wave” was incorrectly represented in the model with too little energy transferred downwards into the ice and too much driving ice surface melt.

The parameterization of ice thermal conductivity used in the “tsanf” model was based on calculations derived from BH04-01 temperature measurements (see Section 6.2.1) (resulting in the Tsanfleuron specific thermal conductivity value of 1.96 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹), it may thus be assumed that the thermal conductivity of the ice was adequately represented in the model. To improve the representations of ice surface ablation and provide more accurate ice temperature predictions it

appears additional heat transfer processes, currently not incorporated in the model are required to transfer heat downwards through the ice. It is postulated that such missing processes may include; liquid water (sourced from snow pack melting or ice surface melting) percolation through macro-porous cracked and crevassed ice, transferring heat via advection and subsequent latent heat release on refreezing on contact with colder ice layers beneath. In the model ice surface and snow surface derived melt immediately “runoff” with no consideration of where the melt went and much heat transfer into the ice occurred as a result. The absence of such additional processes from the model may explain the over estimated ice surface ablation and the modelled ice temperatures which are at times up to 3 to 4 °C colder than the measured temperatures.

Figure 7.16: Comparison of modelled and measured ice ablation over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007 at the North site.

It is to be noted that in the comparison of measured and modelled ice temperature time series, only the most basic account was made for the thermistors getting nearer to the surface due to ice surface ablation, through a switch to a sequentially deeper thermistor pair following the 2005 ablation season. Such a procedure is an over simplification, however, in the absence of higher spatial resolution thermistors in the near-surface (allowing sequential switching to deeper thermistors as surface lowering occurred throughout the ablation season) the effect of the thermistors becoming progressively closer to the surface needs to be considered when studying Figure 7.17.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

Comparison of the modelled and measured ice temperatures at 0.7 and 1.7 m below the ice surface (Figure 7.17) reveal modelled temperatures to be continually colder than measured temperatures, by as much as 1 to 2 °C in summer and as much as 3 to 4 °C in winter, with the discrepancy between the two datasets becoming more accentuated as time continues away from the agreement at the time of temperature initialization in February 2005. The difference and continued drift in modelled temperatures is attributed to the incomplete parameterization of near-surface heat transfer processes being accentuated over time, as outlined above. In addition to the absolute values of the temperature variation, the timing of the onset of periods of warming and cooling is critical to the interpretation of model performance and identification of missing processes. In 2005 the 0.7 m temperature began to rapidly increase on day 486 (120) while the modelled temperature did not show similar rapid increase until day 574 (208), 88 days later, on the day that the snow pack fully ablated (Figure 7.13). Similarly in 2006 the warming trend in measured temperatures began on day 862 (131) (before data logger failure prevented further data collection) while the warming of modelled temperatures did not begin until day 929 (198) corresponding to the exposure of the ice surface. 1.7 m deep ice temperatures exhibited rapid temperature warming on day 486 (120, 2005) at the same time as 0.7 m (earlier than would have been expected if ice heat transfer were via conduction alone), suggesting some form of rapid heat transfer mechanism downwards from the ice surface under snow cover conditions, probably in the form of melt percolation and refreezing through tension cracks opened during the winter allowing rapid transit of the first spring melt to reach the ice surface. Modelled 1.7 m temperature increase however, began 5 days later than the modelled temperature rise at 0.7 m in 2006, reflecting the time required in the model for conduction of heat downwards to the deeper ice layer. The initiation of autumn cooling (under snow free conditions) occurred concurrently in both the modelled and measured temperature time series.

It is clear from comparisons of measured and modelled near-surface ice temperature time series that warming of near-surface thermistors occurs at Tsanfleuron under snow cover conditions, a process not replicated in the “tsanf” model. The reduced ice warming period as a consequence of the missing under snow ice surface warming processes may somewhat explain the discrepancy between modelled and measured ice temperatures.

Figure 7.17: Comparison of modelled and measured ice temperature time series over the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2007.

Analysis of selected individual measured and modelled ice temperature profiles (Figure 7.17) further highlights the inadequacies of the representation of the near ice surface heat transfer processes via conduction alone in the “tsanf” model. Measured and modelled ice temperature profiles on day 80 (2005) show good correspondence soon after initialisation of the temperature profile, from this accurate initialisation modelled and measured profiles begin to diverge. Day 193 (July) 2005 exhibits approximately isothermal measured ice temperatures at or near melting point just before complete removal of the winter snow pack (see Figure 3.15 a) indicating elimination of the “winter cold wave” was initiated under snow cover conditions. Modelled temperatures however, were considerably colder than measured ($-2.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to $-0.04\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the ice surface respectively) as ice warming in the model began once the snow pack was removed. The modelled temperature profile displayed temperatures of below melting point to a depth of $\sim 20\text{ m}$ below the ice surface, considerably deeper than the measured penetration depth of the “winter cold wave” at BH04-01 of 13.24 m (see Section 4.1.2.2). Both day 272 (September) 2005 and day 230 (August) 2006 exhibit similar patterns of measured and modelled

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

ice temperatures. In both cases in the middle to late ablation season, modelled ice temperatures display evidence of warming from the surface (but surface temperatures remain below those measured by thermistors, $-0.38\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to $-0.12\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 272 (2005) and $-1.94\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to $-0.10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on day 230 (2006) respectively), with remnants of the previous winter's cold wave manifest as temperature minima of -1.20 and $-3.43\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at depth below the surface respectively. At a height of 40 m above the bed the measured cold ice temperatures are not replicated by the model, neither are the positive borehole temperatures at the bottom of the adjacent BH05-16. Whatever englacial or subglacial processes are causing the observed deviations from melting point, are not incorporated into the model, it is suggested that the thermistor temperature at 40 m above the bed may be a consequence a cold air temperature being logged in the borehole (Section 4.1.2.2), while the positive temperatures in the vicinity of the bed were possibly an artefact of the drainage of warm drilling water. Though it seems more likely basal heat sources were due to the inflow of slightly warmer water from up-glacier propagating up the borehole or from the subglacial karst system, in response to remote changes in the hydrology in the karst system or via air flow between the karst system and the glacier bed. Days 340 (2005) and 100 (2006) show similar patterns of modelled and measured temperature variation. Temperature profiles on day 340 (2005) suggests ice temperature cooling from the surface downwards, quicker in the model than in reality, resulting in surface ice temperatures of $-6.90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-3.17\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively. It is suggested on the basis of the modelled temperature profile on day 272 (2005) that the winter cooling began from an initially too cold autumn ice temperature profile, accentuating the problems of heat transfer processes not included in the model which may in the case of day 340 serve to reduce the rate of winter cooling (for example via percolation and refreezing of melt generated during peak $\text{SW}\downarrow$ periods during otherwise energy loss environments). The day 100 (2006) (at a time just prior to the initiation of the first surface derived melt) temperature profile represents a similar scenario whereby too great a winter cooling was predicted by the model or the correct amount of cooling but beginning from too cold an autumn profile, the effects of which continue to be felt at the end of the winter and into the following ablation season resulting in the deeper penetration depth of the winter cold wave in the second modelled summer.

Figure 7.18: Comparison of selected modelled and measured ice temperature profiles (with the top 20 m ice temperatures expanded as an inset in each plot).

7.6.3 Discussion

Analysis of modelled ice temperatures and surface ablation as outlined above indicate parameterisations of the heat transfer processes at the ice surface and within the near-surface ice incorporated into the “tsanf” model are oversimplified. Further evidence for the necessary incorporation of water flow and the associated heat transfer through the snow pack, at the ice surface and into the macro-porous near-surface ice are outlined as follows: Glacier surface temperature (Figure 7.19) consistently reaches melting point under deep snow conditions (Figure

3.15 a) daily from day 500 (134, 2005) and day 842 (111, 2006) when percolation of melt-water through the snow pack starts and a melt generated heat flux begins to develop.

Figure 7.19: Modelled glacier surface temperature for the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2006.

The timing of the first augmentations of the measured and modelled glacier ice heat fluxes (Figure 7.20) do not correspond. Modelled ice surface heat fluxes were very low ($0 \pm 1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) during the winter when snow covered, beginning to fluctuate greatly between $\sim \pm 80$ and 100 W m^{-2} between day 574 (208, 2005) and 663 (297, 2005) when the glacier surface was snow free. In 2006 the modelled ice surface heat flux began to increase on day 931 (200, 2006), 63 days after the observed increase in measured ice surface heat flux on day 868 (137, 2006) (Figure 7.20). The rapid increase in measured flux on day 868 (137, 2006) represents the time at which the melt-water heat flux (not included in the “tsanf” model) first reached the ice surface, the flux subsequently quickly decreased over a few days as the ice surface in the vicinity of the HPF01 increased in temperature and the flow of heat then became undetectable by the thermopile sensor. As stated above the snow surface was at melting point on day 842 (111, 2006), the measured ice surface heat flux began to increase on day 868 (Figure 7.20) implying the snow pack at the North site took 23 days to become isothermal at 0°C . The 63 day gap between the measured heat flux increase and the modelled increase represents a period of warming experienced by the near-surface ice, over which time no ice warming occurred in the model, which may partially explain why ice temperatures modelled by the “tsanf” model were too cold.

Figure 7.20: Modelled and measured ice surface heat flux for the 2 year period of meteorological data collection, between February 2005 and February 2006.

7.6.4 Investigation of the effects of slush flows over ice surface ablation

As detailed in Section 5.7.3 slush flows have been observed on Tsanfleuron and are identified as potentially contributing to the different recorded across glacier ablation rates (Table A3). To assess the potential impacts of such processes on the ice surface ablation, the “tsanf” model was run with the snow depth instantaneously reduced to 0 m on days 175 (2005), 177 (2006) and 186 (2006) corresponding to the times when snow pack and meteorological conditions were thought to have been optimum for slush flow occurrence (Section 5.7.3). Modelling results displayed in Figure 7.21 suggest that had a slush flow occurred on day 175 (2005) and 2.02 m of snow was removed, the ice surface would have been exposed 34 days earlier than under the no slush flow scenario, resulting in an additional 2.08 m of ice surface lowering. A slush flow removing 1.92 m of snow on day 177 (2006) was predicted to result in 1.52 m of addition ice surface lowering, while a slush flow removing 1.06 m of snow on day 186 (2006) was predicted to ablate an additional 0.84 m of glacier ice. If as suggested in Section 5.7.3, slush flows occurred at the South site (BH04-06) and not at the North (BH04-01) and Central (BH05-07) sites as a consequence of hydrological differences, “tsanf” model predictions for ice ablation suggest that the process of slush flow snow pack removal and the associated additional ice surface ablation are sufficient to account for the greater glacier ice surface lowering recorded at the South site (BH04-06) (see Table A3, Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3).

Figure 7.21: Modelled snow depth and ice surface elevation under slush flow snow pack removal scenarios.

Summary

- Ice surface ablation was overestimated by the “tsanf” model.
- Partitioning of energy at the glacier ice surface between that used for surface warming and melt, and that transferred to depth is incorrectly represented in the model resulting in overestimated surface ablation and underestimated ice temperatures.
- A Tsanfleuron derived ice thermal conductivity value was used in the model, suggesting energy transfer via conduction is of the correct magnitude and thus additional important ice heat transfer mechanisms appear to have been omitted, probably in the form of water percolation into the ice at the micro- and macro-scale.
- Modelled ice temperature time series and profiles are notably colder than measured values.
- Measured ice temperature warming begins soon after the modelled glacier surface temperature reaches 0 °C and melt is generated. Modelled ice temperatures are much slower to respond, beginning to rise once the snow pack had fully ablated.
- In 2006 it took 26 days for the snow pack to become isothermal, following which the melt water heat flux reached the ice surface 63 days before the complete ablation of the winter snow pack.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

- Water driven heat transfer through the snow pack was not included in the model and is identified as a key process in the early summer warming of the ice surface.
- In the absence of warming under remnant winter snow cover conditions in the “tsanf” model, the duration of ice warming is reduced, consequently ice temperatures are underestimated.
- The modelled winter cold wave is not fully eliminated in either 2005 or 2006, due to insufficient heat transport downwards from the ice surface.
- Parameterisations of geothermal, frictional and strain heating were included in the model but are not visible in the temperature profiles once the ice temperature is at melting point. No calculation of basally derived melting was made, however, 214 mm a⁻¹ of melt was attributed to strain heating throughout the ice column.
- Positive temperatures at the base of the borehole, not represented in the model are considered to be the result of water flows at the glacier bed from up glacier and due to water and / or air flows between the glacier sole and the karst system beneath, not incorporated in the model.
- Modelling reconstructions of the impact of slush flows suggests such events have the capacity to explain differential across glacier ice surface ablation as observed at Tsanfleuron.

7.7 Modelling snow and ice temperature change under global warming best estimates

Possible future changes in seasonal snow pack evolution, ice ablation and snow pack and glacier temperatures are of importance in the wider context of alpine cryospheric response to global warming and are of specific economic importance at Tsanfleuron, where the resort of Les Diablerets is highly dependent upon the glacier for a substantial part of its income through tourism based on winter sports. The two principal parameters controlling the snow pack and glacier mass balance and temperatures, influenced by climate change predictions are air temperature and precipitation (Beniston *et al.*, 2003). Various studies have made estimates for future climate change in Switzerland, (Marinucci *et al.*, 1995, Beniston *et al.*, 1996, Rotach *et al.*,

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

1997, Maisch, 1998 and Beniston *et al.*, 2003), predicting air temperature increases of up to 3 °C by 2050 and increased winter and decreased summer precipitation. As part of the PRUDENCE (Prediction of Regional scenarios and Uncertainties for Determining European Climate change risks and Effects) project Frei (2004, in Salzmann, 2006) predicts summer temperature increases of 0.9 to 3.4 °C, winter temperature increases of 1.4 to 4.7 °C, summer precipitation decreases of 7 to 30 % and winter precipitation increases of 0 – 20 % for southern Switzerland by the year 2050. Over a slightly longer period, global average temperature increases of between 1.1 to 6.4 °C and a best estimate of 1.8 to 4.0 °C are predicted by the IPCC (2007) by the year 2100. While regional climate modelling of areas of the Alps suggests air temperature increases of between 4.5 and 5 °C and summer precipitation increases by 10 to 15 % (but with the snowfall fraction of that summer precipitation decreasing by about half of its current level by 2100) (S. Kotlarski, Pers.comm)⁸.

Ignoring the above stated deficiencies and assuming the “tsanf” model (Essery, unpublished) to reasonably represent snow and ice temperatures, snow accumulation and snow and ice ablation, investigations into the influence global warming will have on Glacier de Tsanfleuron were made by running the “tsanf” model a number of times with the temperature driving data augmented to various levels within the range 1 to 5 °C (following predictions by Kotlarski) and with the winter snowfall precipitation data increased by up to 20 % (following Frei (2004, in Salzmann, 2006)).

7.7.1 Increasing air temperature scenarios

Air temperature rises associated with global warming are predicted to increase ice ablation (Figure 7.22). Augmentations of 1 to 5 °C are predicted to result in sequentially greater ice ablation in the first summer of modelling, a 1 °C air temperature rise increases surface lowering from the no change scenario by 0.35 m, a 2 °C temperature increase elevates surface lowering by 0.79 m and so on until a 5 °C air temperature rise will result in 2.33 m of extra ice ablation. In the second summer the influence of air temperature augmentation has similar effects on surface lowering with a 1°C temperature increase resulting in the position of the ice surface lowering to 0.84 m below the no change scenario and 5.17 m lower under the 5 °C temperature increase. In addition to increasing the depth of ice lowering, the timing of the initiation of ice ablation becomes successively earlier under higher air temperatures, peaking at 17 days earlier under a 5 °C temperature increase in both years. Predictions suggest air temperature increase will have no notable effect on the magnitude and timing of peaks in the snow depth record (Figure 7.22),

⁸ Dr Sven Kotlarski, Max-Planck-Institut für meteorologie, Hamburg.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

however, rising air temperatures are shown to increase the rate of snow ablation, specifically in the second half of the snow ablation period in the first winter and in the first half of the snow ablation period of the second winter. The main influence of air temperature warming over the snow depth will manifest itself in the date upon which the snow pack is fully removed, exposing the ice surface. In the first modelling year a 1 °C temperature increase will result in the ice surface being exposed 3 days earlier than under the no change scenario, a 2 °C increase will lead to exposure 6 days earlier, 3 °C, 10 days earlier, 4 °C, 14 days earlier and 18 days earlier under a 5 °C augmentation. In the second summer similar results were obtained with ice surface exposure 3 days earlier under a 1 °C increase, through to a 16 day earlier exposure under a 5 °C air temperature warming. The impact of such an earlier exposure will be felt in terms of the increased time available for ice surface ablation (see Section 5.3) and economically by cutting nearly 3 weeks off the time for which the glacier surface is skiable and thus winter sports revenue can be generated.

Predictions suggest ice temperatures will respond positively to air temperature warming, the influence of which increases throughout the two year study period, away from the time of model initialisation (Figure 7.22). The net effect of air temperature augmentation will be to increase ice temperatures, by up to 0.35 °C under a 1 °C air temperature rise by the end of the two year modelling period, by 0.58 °C under a 2 °C increase and up to 1.34 °C under a 5 °C air temperature rise. The timing of winter cooling initiation is predicted to remain unchanged, however, the initiation of the 0.7 m ice warming will be brought forward as a direct consequence of the earlier exposure of the ice surface as outlined above. The anticipated influence of global warming on the snow temperature time series is for the most part simply manifest as a sequential snow temperature increase of ~ 0.2 °C for each 1 °C air temperature increase. The effect of such an increase is that the snow pack will become isothermal earlier, thus generating melt which percolates to the ice surface sooner, ~ 16 to 18 days earlier under a 5 °C temperature increase compared to the no change scenario.

Figure 7.22: Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various air temperature warming scenarios.

7.7.2 Increasing solid (winter) precipitation scenarios

Having assessed the impact of air temperature increase over ice ablation, snow accumulation and ablation, snow and ice temperatures, the influence of solid precipitation increase in the range 0 to 20 % (Frei 2004, in Salzmann, 2006) is considered. After increasing the solid precipitation, predictions suggest the amount of ice surface lowering will decrease, with ablation beginning sequentially later for larger increases of precipitation (Figure 7.23). In the first modelled ablation season a 5 % increase in precipitation decreases the ice surface lowering by 0.11 m, each additional 5 % precipitation increase decreases surface lowering by a further 0.11 m to a maximum of a 0.44 m lowering reduction under a 20 % precipitation rise. In the second modelled ablation season similar results are anticipated, with the ice surface lowering reduced by 0.30 m by each 5 % precipitation increase, to a maximum of 1.23 m under a 20 % increase. The initiation date for ice ablation will also be affected by the predicted precipitation increases, delayed by 2 days for each 5 % augmentation. The reduced surface lowering and later start to the ice ablation season under conditions of precipitation increase are explained by the increased mass of snow to be ablated prior to ice surface lowering and a larger impact of summer snowfalls, which reduce ice ablation for a slightly longer period than under the no change scenario.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

The predicted key impact of solid precipitation increase is reflected in the snow depth time series (Figure 7.23), with deeper maximum snow depths and greater mass added during each period of precipitation. In addition it is anticipated that the exposure of the ice surface following snow ablation will be delayed by the increased SWE to be melted. Sequentially higher snow depth maxima will occur under sequentially larger augmentations of solid precipitation. Peak snow depths in the first modelled winter will increase by 0.22 m under a 20 % precipitation increase to a maximum of 3.78 m. In the second winter, predictions suggest a maximum snow depth increase of 0.83 m leading to a peak snow depth of 4.90 m. As a direct consequence of the additional mass which will be stored in the snow pack, ablation will take longer than under the no change scenario, though it is predicted to occur at the same rate. It is anticipated from the model runs that the ice surface will be exposed 3 days later at the end of the first winter's snow ablation and 8 days later under second winter's snow pack ablation under the maximum 20 % precipitation scenario. Predictions suggest the influence of summer snowfalls may be somewhat increased by the precipitation augmentation, especially in the case of the second summer where the duration of cover of the summer snowfall increases by up to 6 days.

The modelled effects of solid precipitation increase on the 0.7 m ice temperature appear limited (Figure 7.23). Although peak summer temperatures show no change, winter temperatures are predicted to rise by as much as 0.52 °C in response to an increased insulation effect of the greater snow mass, which in turn is expected to lead to a slight decrease in the amount of energy transfer from deep within the glacier to replenish energy lost at the ice surface. The modelled effect of precipitation augmentation over the 0.2 m snow temperature will be felt primarily in the early winter (Figure 7.22), where snow temperatures are suggested to increase by ~ 0.5 °C as a direct result of increased insulation from the cold atmospheric boundary layer air. The precipitation increase will also delay the evolution of the snow pack towards isothermal status by ~ 8 days as a larger mass of cold snow will require warming to 0 °C by the percolating melt water heat flux.

Figure 7.23: Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various increasing solid precipitation scenarios.

7.7.3 Simultaneous increasing air temperature and solid (winter) precipitation scenarios

It is generally accepted that global warming and precipitation augmentation will occur simultaneously (though there is debate as to by exactly how much). The predicted effects of combined air temperature and precipitation increase are less detrimental to the health of the glacier than through air temperature rise alone (Figure 7.24). Under the probable future climate change scenario of a 5 °C temperature warming and a 20 % solid precipitation increase, the ice surface lowering at the end of the first modelled ablation season is predicted to be 1.97 m greater than the no change scenario and 4.46 m greater at the end of the second modelled ablation season. With lower precipitation increases (at the same 5 °C temperature increase) the ablation is greater as less SWE need be ablated at the beginning of the ablation season before the ice is exposed, summer snowfalls have a smaller impact. The proposed 5 °C, 20 % precipitation increase scenario drives maximum snow depths to higher values than the no change scenario, 3.67 m maximum depth in the first modelled winter and 4.71 m in the second (Figure 7.24). It is anticipated however, that these higher snow depths will ablate more quickly than under the no change scenario as a result of the augmented air temperatures, consequentially the ice surface will be exposed 13 days earlier at the end of the first winter and 10 days at the end of the second.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

0.7 m ice temperatures are expected to experience an increase as a result of the predicted 5 °C, 20 % precipitation increase climate change scenario. The greatest ice temperature augmentations will be as high as 1.52 °C in winter, while summer maxima are predicted to increase by between 0.19 and 1.07 °C. The predicted summer maxima increases are attributed to higher heat conduction through the ice surface under warmer air temperatures, while increases in winter temperatures may additionally be influenced by the increased insulation properties of the deeper snow. Similar to the 0.7 m ice temperatures, the 0.2 m snow temperatures also exhibit a predicted rise under the 5 °C, 20 % precipitation increase scenario (Figure 7.24). The modelled 0.2 m snow temperature increases from the no change scenario are predicted to be greatest in early winter reflecting the dependence of the initial snow temperature at the time of deposition on the air temperatures in the “tsanf” model. The effect of the warmer early winter snow temperatures will be felt throughout the whole winter with temperatures 1.15 °C warmer than if no air temperature and precipitation increase had occurred. Warmer snow temperatures help explain the model prediction of the snow pack becoming isothermal 10 days earlier than under the no change scenario, as less heating would be required from the surface conduction flux in the “tsanf” model.

Figure 7.24: Ice surface ablation, snow depth, 0.7 m deep ice temperature and 0.2 m snow temperature under various increasing air temperature and solid precipitation scenarios.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

It is concluded that under the modelled climate change scenario of a 5 °C air temperature and a 20 % solid precipitation increase that despite more mass being added to Tsanfleuron, the snow pack will warm and ablate more quickly. The near-surface ice will receive greater energy input and thus warm to melting point quicker, generating greater ice surface ablation. From a glaciological perspective this warming (depending on its depth of penetration) may be sufficient to warm much of the cold near-surface ice at BH04-06 (see Section 4.1.2) to melting point. From an economic perspective the global warming scenario predictions will decrease the period for which the glacier is skiable by up to 2 weeks (with real financial implications for a glacier visited by thousands of pass – paying skiers per day), also the predicted rise in ice surface lowering will increase the frequency with which draglift A frames located on the ice will need to be repositioned as they melt out of the ice surface.

Summary

- A 5 °C increase in global air temperatures is predicted to result in increased ice surface ablation, faster snow pack ablation in early summer and warmer snow and ice temperatures.
- A 20 % increase in solid precipitation is predicted to result in decreased ice surface ablation, increased snow depth, slightly slower snow pack ablation and a small increase in snow and ice temperature, most noticeable in the early winter.
- The combined effect of the 5 °C, 20 % precipitation increase scenario will likely be; 2.0 to 2.4 m of additional ice surface lowering each ablation season, an increase in maximum snow depth in the region of 0.20 to 0.70 m each winter, exposure of the ice surface 10 to 13 days earlier each summer, a 0.2 to 1.5 °C rise in near-surface ice temperatures (at a depth of ~ 0.7 m) and a 1.2 °C increase in the 0.2 m snow temperature, allied to which, the snow pack would become isothermal 10 days earlier than under the present no change scenario.
- Economic costs of changes on Tsanfleuron under the 5°C, 20% precipitation increase climate change scenario will be experienced in terms of a reduction of the ski season by up to 2 weeks (with real financial implications for a glacier visited by thousands of pass – paying skiers per day) and the need to more frequently reposition drag lift A frames located on the ice, as ice surface ablation increases.

7.8 Chapter summary

- The non measured meteorological parameters of $SW\downarrow$, $SW\uparrow$, $LW\downarrow$, $LW\uparrow$, Q_{LE} and Q_H have been reconstructed from measured parameters allowing quantification of the glacier surface energy balance.
- Seasonally varying $SW\downarrow$ dominates the surface energy balance for much of the year, during the winter $LW\uparrow$ becomes the largest flux, while Q_S and Q_{LE} in general add energy to the glacier surface but at values a lot smaller than the SW and LW fluxes.
- A 1 D numerical model was used to model the surface energy balance, snow pack evolution, ice ablation and snow and ice temperatures.
- Changes in the direction of heat conduction in the near-surface ice closely follow changes in the direction of the glacier surface energy flux. Positive summer energy fluxes drive ice warming and melt, while negative winter fluxes result in ice cooling.
- Snow pack accumulation and ablation is predicted well by the “tsanf” model.
- Modelling investigations suggest slush flows are capable of enabling enhanced ice surface lowering of the magnitudes observed at the South site relative to the North and Central sites.
- Modelled snow temperature profiles were colder than the measured values due to insufficient modelled heat transfer from the snow surface.
- Water transfer through the snow pack was not included in the model and has subsequently been identified as an important heat transfer mechanism in the early summer warming of the of the Tsanfleuron snow pack, in terms of refreezing and latent heat release and via heat advection.
- Analysis of modelled and measured heat fluxes at the ice surface indicates elimination of the winter cold wave begins at Tsanfleuron under the winter snow cover, via snow pack melt-water heat transfer processes not incorporated into the model, as soon as the snow pack becomes isothermal.

CHAPTER 7: MODELLING

- Modelled ice temperatures are underestimated, attributed to a shorter warming period (as ice warming only begins in the model once the snow pack has fully ablated) and due to missing processes of heat transfer down through the ice, primarily via liquid water flow.
- The “tsanf” model significantly overestimates ice surface ablation as a consequence of incorrect partitioning of energy at the ice surface between that which warms and ablates the surface and that which is transferred deeper into the ice.
- Modelling investigations as to the impact of global warming at Tsanfleuron suggest that under air temperature and solid precipitation increases the glacier will experience deeper winter snow packs, faster snow and ice ablation, earlier ice surface exposure, warmer snow and ice temperatures and greater ice surface ablation. These effects will have economic impacts on the Glacier 3000 winter sports operation on the glacier.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

8.1 Introduction

What did this thesis set out to achieve?

This study set out to measure glacier snow pack and ice temperatures, quantify the associated physical and thermal snow and ice properties and to investigate the influence of these characteristics on the glacier energy balance in supra-, en- and subglacial environments.

In order to address these aims, seven distinct thesis objectives were formulated, specifically this investigation attempted to:

1. Conduct accurate temperature measurements continuously within snow pack and ice boreholes to the glacier bed, over a number of annual cycles at several locations in an across-glacier transect at a continuous temporal resolution of two hours or better. Spatial resolution of temperature measurements had to be sufficiently high to characterise internal snow pack processes as well as near-surface and deeper englacial temperature fluctuations.
2. Measure temperature profiles throughout the ice depth and compare the profiles with theoretical pressure melting point temperatures previously used to characterise ice temperature in temperate glacier flow models.
3. Measure electrical conductivity and water pressure near to temperature measurements at the glacier bed to assist in the interpretation of basal temperature records.
4. Determine the spatial variability of snow depth over the ice surface and the physical and thermal properties of the snow pack, using repeat snow depth surveying techniques and snow pit analysis.
5. Determine glacier ice density and thermal conductivity using temperature measurements and ice cores recovered from Glacier de Tsanfleuron by Tison and Hubbard (2000).

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

6. Deploy basic automated meteorological instrumentation at one or more locations on the glacier surface to collect continual meteorological data throughout two annual cycles. Develop and apply a snow and ice temperature model predicting surface energy balance, snow pack growth and decay, ice ablation and snow and ice temperature profiles. Compare predicted and measured snow depths, ablation rates and temperature profiles and further run the model to assess glacier response to future climate change scenarios.
7. Deploy eddy correlation and four-component radiation sensors for short attended periods to measure at high frequency the turbulent heat fluxes and all four components of the radiation balance over snow and ice surfaces. Compare measured turbulent heat fluxes with those determined using the bulk aerodynamic methods applied to basic meteorological data.

How well were the thesis objectives met?

In general all thesis objectives were met. Snow and ice temperatures were accurately recorded, snow depth spatial variability was investigated, physical and thermal snow and ice properties were determined, water pressure and electrical conductivity measurements were made at the glacier bed to aid in thermal process interpretation, while glaciometeorological data were collected using both basic and eddy correlation and four component radiation measurement techniques. Additionally (as a means of integrating the various thesis findings and evaluating thermally important glacial processes), a glacier energy flux model was developed which replicated snow and ice temperatures, accumulation and ablation. This model was applied to generally accepted future climate change scenarios to assess the possible impacts to Glacier de Tsanfleuron, specifically:

1. Temperature measurements were made to an accuracy of $\pm 0.04^{\circ}\text{C}$ in three boreholes, in an across glacier transect, at an approximate altitude of 2260 m a.s.l. instrumented throughout the ice depth using 108 thermistors over two annual cycles. Data was collected at a two hour resolution for the majority of the study period, at times this decreased to three hour at the South site where limitations were imposed by the available data logger storage. The only real deficiencies in the temperature data collection arose due to data logger malfunction resulting in missing data and the insufficient deployment height of thermistors in the snowpack at the end of the winter to fully characterise the temperatures of the upper snowpack layers. In the lower snow pack the 0.20 m thermistor spacing was sufficient to characterise the snow pack processes, while in the near-surface ice, a tighter thermistor spacing (0.50 m to an initial

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

depth of 20 m at time of deployment) would have, with hindsight been more appropriate for monitoring fluctuating temperatures, considering the ablation season melt out of the upper thermistors.

2. Comparison between measured temperatures and the theoretical ice pressure melting point temperatures was achieved for all three boreholes in Figures 4.13 to 4.19 (using dissolved solute concentration values from Hubbard *et al.*, 2003). These comparisons facilitated identification of the presence of liquid water and/or air where temperatures were warmer than melting point and cold ice where temperatures below.
3. Electrical conductivity and water pressure sensors were deployed at the base of a number of boreholes terminating at the glacier bed. Unfortunately (due to the belated realisation of the benefit of data from such sensors for subglacial process characterisation) only the Central site saw EC and water pressure sensors deployed in the same borehole as the thermistors. As a consequence, interpretations and inferences made using the EC and water pressure data (where available) at the North and South sites were presented with the caveat that connections to the subglacial hydrological system may have differed slightly to those experienced in the boreholes housing the thermistor strings. EC sensors constructed from 230 V light bulb fittings were cheap, simple to manufacture and calibrate and provided accurate results when initially deployed, however, many of the probes malfunctioned when exposed to the high pressures encountered in down borehole deployment. The in-house manufactured water pressure sensors and the self logging TAFARAG sensors displayed no operational problems in the subglacial environment, however, borehole re-drilling problems prevented the recovery of one of the self logging sensors (and consequential completed data loss) at the North site.
4. Spatial variability of snow depth across the glacier was accurately measured by means of a number of snow depth transects conducted using a graduated avalanche probe (accuracy ± 1 cm). Transects conducted across glacier passing through the three borehole locations at a 10 m spacing and down glacier in an 'X' shape following piste routes (at ~ 30 m spacing) in both January 2006 and January 2007 allowed, from the evaluation of 479 depth readings, the conclusion to be drawn that point snow depth measurements recorded automatically at the North site were representative for the whole glacier. Snow pit analysis at each of the three

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

thermistor sites during January 2006, April 2006 and January 2007 facilitated measurement of the stratigraphic and physical properties of the snow pack, when used in comparison with temperature time series thermal properties were derived. An initially unforeseen large detrimental thermal effect of snow pit excavation was observed in the snow and uppermost ice thermistor time series as a consequence of digging pits too close to thermistors, at times exposing them to cold ambient air temperatures.

5. Ice density was determined from measurements conducted on sections of the Tsanfleuron cores (Tison and Hubbard, 2000) to be close to published values of ice pure density and within the range of values generally accepted for glacier ice. However, no account was made of any relaxation and associated density change in the cores resulting from pressure changes once recovered from the glacier and stored for 6 years. Ice thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity were successfully determined using the amplitude of temperature variation attenuation method in conjunction with the ice core derived ice density.
6. A suite of basic meteorological instruments were deployed at the North site in February 2005, from which data was recovered as intended (with only minor omissions) until the end of the project in February 2007. During August 2006 an additional glaciometeorological station was deployed at the South site. Following the righting of the initial sensor assembly in July 2005 (following the mast toppling over) and refinement of the sensor mounting structure, both meteorological stations operated successfully for the remaining period of their deployment in an inhospitable environment with only one of the SR50 UDG sensors exhibiting any form of sensor degradation. The favourable operation of the meteorological instrumentation allowed successful data collection for just less than two calendar years.

A snow and ice temperature model (tsanf), based on many simplifying assumptions was developed and driven using the basic meteorological data collected over the glacier surface. The model was run as intended to predict the glacier surface energy balance (Figure 7.12), snow and ice temperatures, accumulation and ablation and further run to predict the implications of commonly accepted climate change scenarios. Comparisons between modelled and measured surface energy balance, snow pack accumulation and ablation, suggested these parameters were accurately predicted by the model, however, snow temperatures and near ice surface temperatures specifically were poorly predicted, while

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

modelled ice surface ablation was significantly overestimated. Specific model deficiencies, leading to the incorrect snow and ice temperature predictions, requiring further development include; the failure to account for percolation and refreezing of liquid water in the snow pack and at the ice surface by the tsanf model. Additionally surface melt was poorly predicted due to failure of the model to fully characterise the drawdown of energy into the ice (the full limitations of the Snow and Ice model sub routines are outlined on pages 371 and 376 respectively). The significant overestimation of the ice surface ablation was attributed to the incorrect partitioning of energy at the ice surface between that which warms and ablates the surface and that which is transferred deeper into the ice. It is questionable as to whether or not a less computationally demanding, simple degree day model may have produced similar or better ice ablation results.

In light of the acknowledged deficiencies of the tsanf model, predictions as to the response of Glacier de Tsanfleuron under climate change scenarios have a high degree of uncertainty attached to them. It was however possible to run the model and predict that under a 5 °C temperature increase and a 20 % precipitation increase scenario, Tsanfleuron is likely to experience increased ice ablation and a reduction in the duration of seasonal snow cover.

7. Eddy correlation and four component radiation instrumentation was deployed on the glacier on three occasions in August 2005, August 2006 and January / February 2007. Sensor malfunction (in extremely wet conditions) and power supply problems prevented any usable data being recovered from the August 2005 deployment, though quality, high frequency sensible and latent heat flux and individual radiation component data were successfully collected during the second and third deployments. Comparisons between the turbulent heat flux values measured using the eddy correlation instruments and those generated by the aerodynamic determination method (driven by the basic meteorological data) were not possible as, only a limited amount of measured turbulent flux data was available. All of this measured turbulent flux data was used to optimise the values for the exchange coefficients required in the aerodynamic method. To have compared the measured data with that calculated using exchange coefficients derived for the same data set would have been appropriate.

8.2 Key thesis findings and implications

Detailed summaries of each discussion theme have been presented throughout the interpretation (Chapters 5 and 6) along with chapter summaries (Sections 5.8 and 6.5). The key thesis findings and conclusions are presented below

- The net surface energy budget of Glacier de Tsanfleuron was, at least, an order of magnitude greater than the basal energy budget. Radiation dominated the surface energy balance, with seasonal and diurnal cycles in the intensity of $SW\downarrow$ exerting a large influence over the other radiation fluxes. In contrast to many other mountain glaciers shading did not significantly influence the $SW\downarrow$ radiation as there are no significant topographic features to the East and South. Net radiation values ranged from 897 W m^{-2} in summer to -172 W m^{-2} in winter, with a mean annual value of -3 W m^{-2} .
- Sensible and latent heat fluxes predominantly added energy to the glacier surface; however, their relative magnitudes were small in comparison with the dominant radiation fluxes (typically 0 to 60 W m^{-2} for sensible heat and 0 to 10 W m^{-2} for latent heat).
- Snow temperatures, ranging between ~ -22 and $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, were coldest near the snow surface and warmest near the ice surface. Temperatures near the top of the snow pack exhibited diurnal and longer duration temperature fluctuation, while temperatures stabilized and gradually warmed with depth following significant early winter surface cooling.
- Snow densities ranged between 177 and 499 kg m^{-3} .
- Snow pack thermal conductivity varied between 0.19 and $1.78 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and associated thermal diffusivity varied between 0.22 and $1.91 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$. As a result of this low thermal conductivity, the snow pack insulated the ice surface in winter considerably reducing heat loss.
- Anthropogenic disturbance of the snow pack by snow pit excavation resulted in cooling of snow layers and the near-surface ice during mid winter (low air temperatures) and sped up the warming of the snow pack to isothermal conditions in spring (mainly through providing preferential pathways for melt to reach the snow pack base).

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

- Ice surface ablation was not uniform across the glacier surface at the three study sites of similar altitude. Instead, ablation was notably higher at the South site than at the North and Central sites. Between 1.61 m and 2.40 m of ice in 2005 and 1.29 m of ice in 2006 were ablated at the South site, compared with 0.63 m and 0.90 m of ice surface lowering at the North site and > 0.98 m and 0.42 m of lowering at the Central site. These differences were attributed to differences in ice surface morphology, permeability and the operation of slush flows at the South site. The glacier surface ice at the North and Central sites was permeable while a surface concavity and compressional flow prevented surface crevassing at the South site.
- The winter cold wave penetrated deeper at the North than at the South site, attributed to the differences in temperature gradients below ~ 8 m depth. Penetration occurred to depths of 13.2 and 15.1 m at the North site during the 2004/05 and 2005/06 winters respectively. At the South site the cold wave penetrated to a depth of 10.0 m in the 2004/05 winter (prior to the cessation of the data record in February) and to 12.7 m in the 2005/06 winter. At the Central site the cold wave penetrated 10.5 m in the 2005/06 winter prior to the cessation of the data record. These yielded an average value for the penetration of the winter cold wave at ~ 2760 m a.s.l. of 13.7 m.
- Initiation of warming and elimination of the winter cold wave occurred under snow cover conditions through the advection of heat to the ice surface via the percolation of melt, refreezing at the ice surface and at depth within macro-porous water pathways in the near-surface ice. Percolation through the snow (and to a lesser extent through permeable near-surface ice) and latent heat release on refreezing was identified in the numerical modelling as a key process. The absence of such processes in the “tsanf” model resulted in modelled ice temperatures being notably colder than measured values.
- Crevasses acted simultaneously as both heat sources and heat sinks to the near-surface ice, with the direction of heat exchange controlled by depth below the surface. The instrumented crevasse at the Central site acted as a heat source to a depth of 3 m below the ice surface, and as a heat sink from 4 m depth to the maximum depth of instrumentation at 6 m (though the crevasse would probably continue as a heat sink to its base at an unknown depth). The observed absence of ponded water in all Tsanfleuron crevasses implies local englacial

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

conduit development, draining the crevasses. These would provide pathways of heat advection deep into the glacier.

- The coldest recorded ice temperatures of ~ -4.5 °C occurred at the ice surface in response to winter cooling. Large sections of englacial ice in the three instrumented boreholes were as theory suggests, at local melting point. By the end of the ablation season, melting point temperatures were restored at the North and upper section of the Central site, bringing the glacier to a 'temperate' condition here. However, the winter cold wave was not eliminated at the South site. Extensive perennial cold ice, to a minimum of -0.99 °C was recorded below the influence of the seasonal thermally active near-surface ice layer at the South and at depth at the Central site. Basal temperatures of >0 °C at the North and South sites were interpreted in terms of warm air and / or water found in association with basal heat sources.
- Under the strict definition of a temperate glacier, Glacier de Tsanfleuron cannot be classed as 'temperate', due to the existence of the perennial cold ice at the South site between the heights of ~ 25 and 56 m above the bed and at the Central site below ~ 35 m above the bed. Tsanfleuron thus, required reclassification as a polythermal glacier.
- Water flow from the subglacial karst to the glacier bed (most likely in response to a higher elevation influx of water into the aquifer), resulted in a large positive basal thermal disturbance (~ 3.5 °C) recorded in BH04-06 during early summer 2006. Water stored in the cave system over-winter was considered to have been warmed by geothermal heating in the aquifer. The basal temperatures in BH04-06 also exhibited evidence of cave breathing (the flow of air between subglacial caves and the glacier bed) with an associated energy transfer. Such a mechanism is believed to control background temperatures in the subglacial cavity of $\sim +0.5$ °C and diurnal, and smaller amplitude longer duration, heat supply events.
- The density of the Tsanfleuron glacier ice measured from ice cores was 894 kg m⁻³.
- Thermal conductivity of the Tsanfleuron glacier ice was 1.96 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹. Thermal diffusivity was calculated to be 1.05×10^{-6} m² s⁻¹.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

- A surface energy balance model was developed which, based on basic meteorological variables recorded over the glacier surface, allowed calculation of the four individual radiation components and turbulent sensible and latent heat fluxes over the full period of data collection. SW_{\downarrow} was found to dominate the surface energy balance for much of the year.
- Investigations of the impact of global warming on Tsanfleuron indicate that increasing air temperatures alone will result in increased ice surface ablation, faster snow pack ablation in early summer, and warmer snow and ice temperatures. Increased precipitation associated with global warming scenarios has the reverse effect-decreasing ice surface lowering, and increasing maximum snow depths, though small temperature increases were predicted. The combined effect of a 5 °C and 20 % precipitation increase was modelled to be a 2.0 to 2.4 m increase in ice ablation each year, an increase in maximum snow depth of 0.20 to 0.70 m each winter, exposure of the ice surface 10 to 13 days earlier each summer, a 0.2 to 1.5 °C increase in near-surface ice temperatures and a 1.2 °C increase in the 0.2 m snow temperature.

Implications

The ice temperature findings in this thesis replicate the findings of Paterson (1971 and 1972) and Harrison (1972 and 1975) who found ice temperature distribution near the glacier surface to be directly related to surface air temperature and energy transfers, mediated by snow pack and ice physical properties. However, results of this investigation suggest the presence of perennial cold ice, specifically between ~0.5 m below the surface and ~25 m above the bed at the South site and below ~35 m above the bed at the Central site. This differs from the results reported by Paterson (1971 and 1972) and Harrison (1972 and 1975) in as much as Tsanfleuron can no longer be classed as a temperate glacier and thus, must be reclassified as polythermal.

There is no reason to assume that at any given time, the temperature profile of a ‘temperate’ glacier should exhibit melting temperatures throughout. The ice composing the seasonal thermally active layer was only entirely at melting point at certain glacier locations for a few weeks, and not at all at other sites. Indeed, the condition of melting point temperatures throughout may be a rare occurrence, which can only manifest itself for a limited period of time towards the end of the ablation season. The implication of this finding in terms of modelling ‘temperate’ glacier flow is that the temperature-dependent ice rheology parameterization is for all but a short period at the end of summer, too soft.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

The linear melting point depression with depth relation adopted by many researchers may be inappropriate.

The flow law parameter A increases exponentially with temperature up to a maximum of 0 °C (Figure 1.1). The presence of colder ice below melting point (specifically near the bed, where deformation induced strain is greatest (Figure 4.27) i.e. towards the base of BH05-07) will consequently increase ice stiffness. The identification of colder ice will also impact ice crystallography, as ice crystal growth is a function of temperature and strain deformation. Thus, different ice crystal size and textures may have evolved at the South site from those observed in the cores collected by Tison and Hubbard (2000) in the vicinity of the North site.

Ice water content has been identified as a rheologically important property (Lliboutry, 1976). Hubbard *et al.* (2003) reconstructed the liquid water content of Glacier de Tsanfleuron from the bulk vein water concentration within the ice (the volume of water per unit volume of ice) following:

$$W_V = F \frac{Mb_i}{\theta_t} \quad (8.2.1)$$

where:

W_V = Bulk vein water concentration,

F = Constant determined from the slope of a bivariate plot of freezing point versus concentration ($K m^3 g^{-1}$),

Mb_i = Bulk ionic concentration,

θ_t = Temperature depression of the ice below its pressure melting point.

In the absence of profiles of temperature variation with depth, Hubbard *et al.* (2003) assumed θ_t to be spatially uniform, supported by borehole temperature measurements in Blue Glacier, USA (Harrison, 1975). This study has revealed this assumption to be an inappropriate oversimplification at Tsanfleuron and, as such, ice water contents may require recalculation in light of the measured temperature profiles (specifically the identification of regions of colder ice). Similarly, since there is a strong linear correlation between water content and effective strain rate (Duval, 1977), ice softness and thus glacier flow may require reassessment.

The identification of heat supply at the glacier sole from connections to the subglacial karst system, via both water and air flows, has implications for the generation and supply of water at the glacier bed and the seasonal evolution of the subglacial drainage system. At present, little is known about subglacial drainage configurations over such a macro-porous bed, and previous investigations of the seasonal evolution of subglacial drainage have largely been conducted over relatively impermeable

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

beds. The implication of high basal heat supply through the winter months is that melt generation can occur all year, and this may act to induce winter sliding and to limit winter close-up of the drainage system, a phenomenon which requires further investigation at Tsanfleuron.

The predicted snow and ice temperature and ablation changes under a 5 °C and 20 % precipitation increase global warming scenario have real economic implications for the Glacier 3000 ski operation on Tsanfleuron, where the glacier plays a key economic role in the local economy. Modelling predictions suggest an earlier end to the ski season by up to 2 weeks each year and imply the need for more frequent repositioning of drag lift frames (drilled into the ice) under increased surface ablation. For the ski operations on the glacier to remain economically viable there will be an increasing need for investment in artificial snow generation. Similarly, snow management techniques warrant investigation, for example piste grooming and how this can be used to increase the length of the skiable period on key pistes.

From a glaciological perspective the predicted increase in ice temperatures shouldn't significantly increase the rate of glacier flow, as temperature increases will be felt most strongly near the ice surface, where deformation rates are lowest. Towards the bed (where deformation rates are higher and consequently the potential exists for the greatest increase in deformation), temperatures are (with the exception of BH05-07) already at melting point (Section 6.4). Thus no further increase at these locations may occur. Similarly the increased ablation and consequential supply of water to the bed is unlikely to cause a significant increase of basal sliding as such a water supply will have a much smaller impact at Tsanfleuron than would be the case at other glaciers with an impermeable bed.

The wider significance of this work

Results, conclusions and inferences drawn from this thesis are significant to many areas of glaciological and snow science research on other valley glaciers, ice caps and to the larger scale ice sheets (Greenland and Antarctica). Though specific values and some processes may be applicable only to small scale alpine glaciers in a similar setting to Tsanfleuron (specifically the exposure to full shortwave radiation in the absence of shading topography and the basal thermal energy regime which may be unique to Tsanfleuron or applicable only to a limited suite of glaciers with a similar subglacial karstic drainage connection), much of the snow pack hydrological and thermal process understanding and near-surface ice thermal interactions may be applicable over a range of spatial scales to other ice masses.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

Of greatest glaciological significance is the successful collection of a high resolution snow and ice temperature profile data set, quantifying the previously assumed (but unmeasured) thermal regime of the glacier. Importantly these measurements indicate that the extensively researched (e.g. Fairchild *et al.*, 1993; 1994; 1999a; 1999b; Tison and Hubbard, 2000; Hubbard *et al.*, 2000a; Hubbard, 2002; Grust, 2004) and modelled (e.g. Hubbard *et al.*, 2003; Chandler, 2005; Chandler *et al.*, 2006) Glacier de Tsanfleuron is not temperate, but contains perennial cold ice and thus displays a polythermal temperature regime. Such a finding is not simply a change of nomenclature; this represents a significant reclassification as it materially impacts on the modelling of ice dynamics and ultimately glacier response to climate change. Such is the importance of this finding, allied to the temperature dependence of ice softness in Glen (1955)'s Flow law and the sensitivity of such ice masses to global warming that, there appears now to be a need to reassess the thermal regime of other 'temperate' glaciers, specifically those which are the subject of flow modelling upon which climate change response is based. A precedent has been set by this study, implying the possible existence of cold ice in other so called 'temperate' glaciers, future investigations need to determine the 3D variation of temperature in other glaciers, extending the 2D across glacier sampling technique applied in this investigation. It is suggested that GPR radar transects conducted during late summer may provide an efficient means of identifying areas of colder ice warranting detailed thermal investigation.

Components of the new Tsanfleuron data set and the discovery of perennial cold ice are already being integrated into current ice flow modelling⁹ and GPR radar interpretation¹⁰ work. These data highlight the need for continued research (as pioneered for polythermal ice sheets by Payne *et al.*, (2000) and initiated for temperate ice research by Hubbard *et al.* (2003)) focusing on improving the way 'temperate' ice flow is modelled, specifically accounting for both spatial heterogeneity and temporal evolution of ice temperatures (and thus ice softness and deformation) at a range of scales from the diurnal through to annual scale and beyond, to predict glacier response to climate change.

Prior to this investigation little or no evidence of temperatures recorded in boreholes connected to an air or water filled subglacial cavity had been reported. Temperatures in air filled cavities had been reported to be ~ 0.5°C (Vivian, 1980), background air temperatures measured in this investigation closely support this finding. Additionally there was no recorded evidence of temperatures measured in boreholes connected to macro-porously drained karstic bedrock (previously only inferences were

⁹ Dr David Chandler, Centre for Glaciology, University of Wales, Aberystwyth.

¹⁰ Prof. Tavi Murray, School of Environment and Society, Swansea University.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

made as to the effects of air and water flows). Ford *et al.*, (1976) proposed air flow towards the bed of the Columbia ice field from observations of air flow in Castleguard cave, though no evidence was presented to support this theory. This thesis for the first time provides compelling evidence to support this proposal, quantifying the thermal effect of such air flow on thermistors in a subglacial cavity with an inferred connection to the karst system. Similarly results from this study also for the first time suggest periodic water fluxes from the karst system to the subglacial drainage system (synchronous with the timing of the “spring event”, supported by EC and water pressure data) result in significant increases in subglacial cavity temperature, by as much as $\sim 3.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The discovery and measurement of the thermal effects of these energy fluxes driven by air and water flows between the glacier bed and the bedrock presented in this thesis is of importance to the understanding of glacier/karst interactions, highlighting a need for further subglacial investigation in such environments.

Accounts of the thermal influence of crevasses to date had been ambiguous, suggesting crevasses may act as either heat sources or heat sinks, with little or no explanation of the factors controlling the direction of energy flux to and from the adjacent ice. For the first time this thesis accurately measured the thermal influence of crevasses to the near-surface ice in a ‘temperate’ glacier and has shown that in such scenarios, small crevasses (~ 1 m wide) act as both heat sources and sinks to the surrounding ice. The direction of heat transfer being controlled by depth below the surface. Little or no seasonality was observed in the direction of energy transfer, with the crevasse acting as heat sink at depth, for whole period due to ponding of cold air and as a heat source near the surface. Such findings may be of specific relevance to the study of thermal interactions on highly crevassed surge type glaciers.

The wider significance of this thesis is not limited to glaciological research, a number of important processes have identified which are of significance to snow science and snowpack modelling investigations on other ice masses. Specifically the development of the tsanf model in this investigation highlighted (by its lack of consideration of, in conjunction with snow pit investigations and snow thermistor time series data), the importance of melt water percolation through the snow pack and refreezing, forming superimposed ice (evidenced at the South site) as a key energy (and to a lesser extent mass) transfer process within the snow pack. Evidence for, and process understanding of, water percolation, refreezing within the snow pack, at the ice surface and in macro-porous pathways within permeable glacier ice and the associated latent heat release at Tsanfleuron, is

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

directly applicable to studies on other ice masses including the Greenland ice sheet were similar processes are observed (Parry *et al.*, 2007; Pers.comm.¹¹).

Energy transfer within the snow pack to the ice surface has been identified in this study as initiating the elimination of the “winter cold wave”. Elimination of winter cold wave has also been observed in this investigation to be more rapid through ice with macro-porous water flow pathways, underlain by warm ice at melting point (at the North and Central sites on Tsanfleuron) than topographically controlled impermeable ice with perennial cold ice below (identified at the South site). To date very few or no reports to the author’s knowledge have been made regarding differences in the elimination time of winter cold wave being influenced by ice surface morphology and permeability. The discovery that near-surface glacier ice warming occurs prior to ice surface exposure (via latent heat release on refreezing of melt and limited percolation of melt into the ice surface, at a range of scales), requires further investigation to determine the extent to which these processes operate at the ice sheet scale.

Glacier surface morphology in addition to snow pack and ice permeability has also been identified as important in controlling ice ablation, with possible application to studies on the Greenland and other ice sheets. Results presented above, pertaining to the slush flow hypothesis as a means of rapidly removing snow, facilitating ice ablation earlier in the season under the correct conditions is of notable interest to those conducting snow pack analysis on the Greenland Ice sheet as ground truthing for part of the European Space Agency’s (ESA) CryoSat mission (due for relaunch in 2009) (Pers.comm)¹².

A number of significant methodological observations, relevant to similar future field investigations were also made during this study, specifically:

1. Simple, accurate, durable and inexpensive temperature sensors for glaciological applications can be made using Fenwal UNICURVE 192-502 LET-A01 thermistors as outlined in Section 2.3.3.

¹¹ & ¹² Dr. Pete Nienow, School of Geosciences, University of Edinburgh.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

2. EC probes constructed using 230 V light bulb fittings (Hubbard and Glasser, 2007) have proven insignificantly robust for en- and subglacial deployment. It is apparent that their future use should be limited to supra- and proglacial applications.
3. Problems encountered in the recovery of sensors for the glacier bed leads the author to advise against the use of self logging sensors in subglacial environments. The use of surface controlled sensors (with regular data transfer to surface based storage media) is preferable for future borehole investigations.
4. Eddy correlation instruments when deployed in cold environments, have considerably larger power supply requirements than when deployed in more hospitable environments. It is recommended that 7.2 Ah, 12V batteries charged with 2.88 W solar panels used in everyday sensor applications be replaced by 90 Ah, 12V batteries, charged by 64 W panels for ice surface deployment. Additionally the CSAT3 sonic anemometer fails to operate in heavy rain, the manufacturer can provide rain shields to alleviate this problem.

8.3 Evaluation of methods of investigation

8.3.1 **Temperature measurement in hot water drilled boreholes and the snow pack**

The Fenwal Uni-Curve thermistors were robust, inexpensive and performed satisfactorily, showing very few signs of degradation or calibration drift. The main weakness in the temperature measurement were the susceptibility of the AM16x32 multiplexers to relay damage and the CR10X loggers to final storage data loss and corruption under the influence of static charge buildup associated with early summer thunderstorms. With hindsight the loggers, enclosures and the steel mounting poles could have been earthed directly to the glacier bed in an adjacent borehole using an un-insulated, weighted copper wire, which may have safely discharged the static. Alternatively, data logger telecommunications via either satellite telemetry or CS-GSM modules communicating with the data loggers remotely from the UK via a Swiss mobile phone network could have reduced the data loss problem by means of daily data recovery and would have indicated when problems occurred, requiring repair, dramatically reducing the amount of missing data in early summer.

Initial delays and problems during drilling in April 2004 were in part the result of an old drill (subsequently replaced) and difficulties arising from the availability of liquid water. In future,

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

drilling programs would benefit from summer scheduling. Where unavoidable winter drilling should use a two way valve (with flow regulation) attached to the drilling hose to split water for heating the water butt making snow melting to generate drilling water considerably more efficient by eliminating the need to stop drilling to heat the water each time slush formed in the water butt.

A problem was encountered as a result of the boreholes remaining open or partially open. Open holes transferred basally derived energy fluxes up through the ice mass, being registered by thermistors sequentially above the bed. In the absence of the borehole, the flux would have been focused only at the glacier bed with minimal transfer upwards via conduction (such as that which occurred in BH04-06, visible in Figures 4.10, 6.3 and 6.7). To reduce this problem, future thermistors would be deployed at the base of multiple blind (englacially terminating) boreholes drilled in the same area, each to the depth of the individual requirement for thermistor installation. The effect of this would be to stop energy transfer upwards through sections of open borehole below the height of thermistor deployment. The need to suspend thermistors from the surface would be eliminated, allowing excess cable to be deployed in the hole, reducing any stretching effects on the cables due to ice deformation.

8.3.2 Snow pack investigations

The 0.2 m thermistor spacing within the snow pack allowed identification of internal snow pack processes (warming at the base; reduction in amplitude of temperature fluctuations with decreasing influence of the atmospheric processes; penetration of the wetting front down through the snow pack and the evolution to isothermal conditions). The penetration and elimination of the winter cold wave was adequately represented by near-surface ice thermistors, allowing detailed investigation of energy transfer processes. However, the snow pack thermistor temperature measurements were limited by insufficient thermistor height in winter (to a maximum height of 3 m above the ice surface) as well as missing data. With hindsight the mounting of thermistors on poles in the snow pack should have occurred to a height of 4.5 m above the ice surface to fully characterize the upper layers of the snow during late winter and the initiation of melt generation and percolation in spring.

Snow pit survey techniques allowed repeatable snow density and snow temperature measurements, validating thermistor time series. Though these surveys were successful, the excavation of only two pits at each site in a particular winter was limiting: ideally snow pits would have been dug more frequently. Specifically, an additional pit dug during the snow pack ablation period, towards the end

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

of June would have been useful for evaluation of water and energy transfer and determination of the presence (or absence) of conditions favoring slush flows at the South site. The belated realization that the excavation of data loggers and snow pits during winter field visits resulted in considerable thermal disturbance of the snow depth and near-surface ice, would in future investigations lead to data loggers being mounted and snow pits conducted a good distance (>20 m) from the boreholes and the snow pack thermistor strings and a change in procedure to ensure that no snow pits were left open overnight (when the greatest cooling occurs).

The importance of snow cover in controlling annual ice surface ablation rates came to be appreciated only as other aspects of the work were completed. Thus, with hindsight a second SR50 UDG would have been installed at the South site in February 2005 at the same time as that deployed at the North site. This would have allowed full comparison of the accumulation and ablation of the snow pack (and ice surface lowering in summer) and provided evidence relating to the slush flows proposed to operate at the South site (Section 5.7).

8.3.3 AWS data collection over the glacier surface

The basic AWS deployed on the glacier in February 2005 comprised of a robust suite of sensors which operated successfully for the duration of the study period. Early problems of mounting pole stability were eliminated following the drilling of the mounting pole into the glacier surface in August 2005. Further problems arose when lower sensors became buried prior to field visits in winter to raise sensors up the mounting pole. Cables also pulled out of the data logger terminals when spare cables, looped below the logger enclosure, became enclosed in ice and were pulled downwards under the weight of settling snow. The SR50 appeared to suffer gradual sensor degradation over the later part of the period of data collection, generating increasingly noisy data. Replacement or deployment of a second SR50 (on a separate mounting pole) at the North site may have helped remove some of the uncertainty in the position of the glacier surface (which had at times to be reconstructed, as outlined in Section 7.2).

Though the NR Lite net radiation measurements were for the most part successful, the sensor suffered some degradation from autumn 2006 onwards and was prone to erroneous readings during winter when snow settled on its upper face. In an ideal situation, radiation measurements would have been conducted using a four component CNR1 radiometer deployed on a long boom, >7.5 m away from the other instruments at the North site, remaining snow free thanks to the incorporated

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

heater. However, sensor availability and power requirements unfortunately prevented this deployment.

The eddy correlation instrumentation provided an accurate method of turbulent flux measurement when the sensors were working. However, the CSAT3 sonic anemometers failed to work in rain, a frustrating weakness of the sensor design which could not have been foreseen.

8.3.4 Water pressure and electrical conductivity

Water pressure and electrical conductivity were not parameters initially intended to have been monitored in this investigation. The pressure and EC sensors were deployed at the bed in August 2005 in light of the intriguing temperature variations observed at the base of BH04-06 at the South site. Ideally the pressure, EC, and temperature sensors should have been installed in the same borehole (as was the case at BH05-07). However, re-drilling of BH04-06 was not possible (due to the multiple thermistor cables in the hole) so water pressure and EC sensors were deployed in adjacent boreholes and interpretations conducted under the caveat that the sensors may not have connected with the same subglacial cavity.

8.3.5 Energy balance and glacier temperature modelling

Modelling using the MicroMet pre-processing algorithms (Liston and Elder, 2006a) facilitated successful gap filling in meteorological time series. Components of the MicroMet model in conjunction with the tsanf surface energy balance model (Essery, unpublished) allowed reconstruction of the non measured individual radiation components, turbulent heat fluxes and solid precipitation, and determination of the glacier surface energy budget for the whole period of data collection, which would have been impossible from the meteorological data alone. Incorporating snow and ice temperature modules allowed reproduction of the general trends of snow and ice temperature variation but at too low temperatures in both cases as a result of omitted processes, in particular penetrating and refreezing melt-water, similar to Suter *et al.* (2001). In addition to determining snow and ice temperatures, the glacier temperature and mass balance modelling provided a valuable means of validating the feasibility of the slush flow hypothesis and of assessing the potential impacts of climate change over snow and ice temperatures and glacier mass balance.

8.4 Recommendations for future work

In light of the results generated by this study, a number of factors warrant further investigation:

8.4.1 **Temperature measurement**

Further investigation of the thermal structure of Glacier de Tsanfleuron would be desirable in light of the identification of regions of perennial cold ice below the depths of influence of the winter cold wave. Deployment of thermistor strings in boreholes along the central glacier flow line would expand the 2D knowledge of temperature variation outlined in this study and could be used to determine a 3D understanding of the ice temperature fluctuation, and variations thereof, of Tsanfleuron. Of specific interest would be the altitudinal temperature variation and potentially the origins of the perennial cold ice observed in this study. A 50 MHz GPR survey in the accumulation area, up-glacier of the South site, would assist in the identification of source regions of cold ice. This should be followed by a drilling program and instrumentation with thermistor strings. Future thermistor strings would involve a tighter spacing of englacial thermistors (~5 m maximum separation) to detail thermal stratigraphy and locate englacial heat sources and sinks more accurately.

Data interpretation from new boreholes would benefit from a detailed borehole video survey prior to instrument deployment, e.g. to assist in interpreting the basal contact and identifying the presence of englacial connections. Where englacial connections to the borehole are observed, repeat EC borehole profiling (e.g. Gordon *et al.*, 2001) would aid in interpretation of the pattern of water flow between the conduit and the multiply-connected borehole. This would aid in investigations of the heat supply effects of such water fluxes and allow targeted thermistor deployment at the point of water and heat inflow.

In addition to borehole thermistor deployment the thermal influence of crevasses may be deserving of further investigation, in particular a detailed temperature characterization of the full depth of larger crevasses located near the snout. Allied to thermistor deployment in larger crevasses, profile measurements of wind speed and direction within those crevasses would allow evaluation of the hypothesized cold air drainage mechanism and the heat source and sink properties of the crevasses.

A final area for further temperature measurements are the sink-holes on the exposed limestone former glacier bed (Figure 6.9 a and b). A valuable insight into cave breathing could be gained from deployment of thermistor strings and small anemometers (as suggested for crevasse deployment)

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

within these more accessible holes. Similarly, exploration of the caves on the exposed bedrock surface in the forefield, would allow investigation of the directions and temperature of air flows within the caves, and the temperature of karstic subglacial drainage.

8.4.2 Snow pit investigations

The generation and percolation of water through the snow pack (and its interaction with spatially-variable ice surface permeability) have been noted to play a key role in water transfer into the glacier, with implications for the local englacial temperature, subglacial water pressure, and the proglacial hydrograph (Campbell *et al.*, 2006). However, there remain relatively few field observations of the thermal effects of such meltwater transfer. Future snow pack investigations should focus on this requirement. A campaign of snow pit excavation during June to assess snow pack temperature, density, stratigraphy and water content during the ablation season, specifically at the South site would be beneficial to understanding the snow pack water and energy transfer processes. Such a study would also assist in investigating the hypothesized relationship between slush flows and underlying surface ice permeability.

8.4.3 AWS data collection over the glacier surface

Establishment of new instrumented boreholes along the central glacier flow line would benefit greatly from the simultaneous deployment of basic meteorological stations at each drill site. Areas of specific interest warranting deployment are near the snout and high in the accumulation area, facilitating investigation of the influence of altitude over surface energy balance and possibly the influence of surface energy balance on the formation of cold ice in the upper reaches of the glacier. Allied to basic meteorological station deployment, periodic along-glacier deployment of eddy correlation and four-component radiation sensors would allow assessment of the altitudinal variation of turbulent and individual radiation fluxes.

Further investigation of the variability in across glacier winter snow pack ablation, through simultaneous SR50 time series at the North and South sites, coupled with liquid precipitation data collection during June and July (when heavy thunderstorms have the potential to saturate the snow pack), could allow validation or falsification of the slush flow ablation hypothesis.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

8.4.4 Water pressure and electrical conductivity

Detailed investigation of the subglacial drainage of Tsanfleuron is required, specifically the interaction between the subglacial karst aquifer and the glacier bed. The installation of a borehole array, with each hole containing water pressure and EC sensors and single thermistors (possibly with all three sensors built into one instrument, to ensure deployment at exactly the same depth) is proposed at the glacier bed at the South site to try to characterize fully the energy flows and the subglacial connection to the karst drainage system.

Additionally, dye tracing from the bottom of boreholes (e.g. Fountain, 1992) to the proglacial discharge stream and to streams emerging further afield from the karst may prove valuable in determining the routing of subglacial drainage. Where such subglacial drainage occurs through karst passages, knowledge of the drainage pathways would allow identification of connected vadose conduits for deployment of EC sensors and thermistors to monitor the thermal and solute content variations of the evacuated subglacial drainage. Dye recovery and transit time analysis would also provide an insight into possible storage within the karst aquifer, allowing inferences to be made as to warming of the waters and solute acquisition during storage.

8.4.5 Numerical modelling

Full integration of the measured temperature profiles (and the seasonal and spatial variation thereof) into the Tsanfleuron glacier numerical flow model, replacing the current assumption of universally temperate ice (e.g. Hubbard *et al.* 2003), is required. Further beneficial extensions of this model include coupling to the “tsanf” surface energy balance model and the snow and ice temperature modules (which themselves require further development, see below) to predict the rheological influence of temperature variation and the spatial variation.

The snow and ice temperature modules in the “tsanf” model require the incorporation of several additional heat transfer processes to improve the model’s representation of temperatures at Tsanfleuron:

- Water percolation through the snow pack and the associated heat advection and latent heat release on refreezing.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS

- Water percolation through ice at both the granular scale through intercrystalline voids at triple grain boundaries and at the macro-scale through cracks and crevasses.
- Englacial melt generation and the associated water transfer from zones of melting and subsequent refreezing on contact with regions of colder ice.
- Subglacial heat sources, in this case basal meltwater and the karst aquifer.

Further suggestions for model extensions include the effects of ice surface aspect on radiation receipt and ablation, and the influence of ice surface morphology and permeability on englacial heat transfer by meltwater.

Following improvement of the process representation within the model, the next step would involve application of the 1D model to different locations on the glacier, specifically to account for the temperature and ablation differences between the three drill sites (having initialized the model with observed temperature profiles). Subject to additional thermistor strings and meteorological stations being deployed in an along flow line configuration, further development would involve expansion of the model to 3D incorporating lateral heat and mass transfers. Such an expansion would allow investigation of the influence of elevation over the surface energy balance, glacier temperatures, accumulation and ablation.

Appendix

<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Calibration Parameter B*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Calibration Parameter B*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Calibration Parameter B*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Calibration Parameter B*</i>
10.0A	1625.22883	10.0B	1638.52288	10.0C	1626.97695	10.0D	1622.75357
10.2A	1626.07178	10.2B	1631.82451	10.2C	1635.06185	10.2D	1627.83892
10.4A	1627.00383	10.4B	1629.73369	10.4C	1631.34228	10.4D	1624.00090
10.6A	1641.61195	10.6B	1627.52335	10.6C	1635.64967	10.6D	1619.35126
10.8A	1628.89291	10.8B	1634.90150	10.8C	1633.67150	10.8D	1624.14840
11.0A	1630.82416	11.0B	1626.34070	11.0C	1626.79775	11.0D	1619.68459
11.2A	1634.70548	11.2B	1632.17268	11.2C	1629.51012	11.2D	1625.64633
11.4A	1628.74081	11.4B	1635.63186	11.4C	1629.00027	11.4D	1623.38424
11.6A	1632.71708	11.6B	1630.16282	11.6C	1633.38614	11.6D	1630.12510
11.8A	1639.53556	11.8B	1626.75295	11.8C	1626.37656	11.8D	1622.53816
12.0A	1630.65438	12.0B	1629.57273	12.0C	1631.11004	12.0D	1622.36002
13.0A	1632.56538	13.0B	1635.40923	13.0C	1634.14402	13.0D	1616.36272
14.0A	1640.33453	14.0B	1645.66721	14.0C	1639.04707	15.0D	1606.99552
15.0A	1646.86032	15.0B	1638.29181	15.0C	1637.23377	11.8E	1619.38612
16.0A	1636.86905	16.0B	1636.69110	16.0C	1636.70890	A	1623.27106
18.0A	1637.87402	18.0B	1643.09196	18.0C	1640.07713	B	1621.93903
22.0A	1647.34611	22.0B	1639.71315	22.0C	1642.36544	C	1619.86955
26.0A	1636.06811	26.0B	1641.32818	26.0C	1640.90242	D	1628.16229
30.0A	1636.74449	30.0B	1641.66515	30.0C	1631.93164	E	1617.41267
50.0A	1638.86940	50.0B	1637.18040	50.0C	1636.94022	F	1627.84769
70.0A	1658.68386	70.0B	1640.14815	70.0C	1630.35053	G	1616.60660
90.0A	1635.01731	90.0B	1631.66378	90.0C	1634.87477	H	1624.72614
110.0A	1628.71396	110.0B	1628.23068	110.0C	1636.03251	I	1633.10142
110.0D	1638.89605	110.0E	1637.84735	110.0F	1622.01383	J	1622.21754
						K	1625.10692
						L	1622.08503
						M	1624.92453
						N	1620.37865
						O	1630.33409
						P	1619.23740
						R	1628.38042
						S	1624.64313
						T	1626.53062
						U	1625.98966
						V	1621.92374

Table A1: Calibration constant, B^* , for use in Blatter (1998) temperature calculation, determined from distilled water and distilled water ice cube calibration.

APPENDIX

<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Correction Factor A*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Correction Factor A*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Correction Factor A*</i>	<i>Sensor</i>	<i>Correction Factor A*</i>
10.0A	0.049	10.0B	0.055	10.0C	0.057	10.0D	0.004
10.2A	0.059	10.2B	0.053	10.2C	0.061	10.2D	-0.015
10.4A	0.062	10.4B	0.050	10.4C	0.049	10.4D	-0.006
10.6A	-0.084	10.6B	0.055	10.6C	0.031	10.6D	-0.004
10.8A	0.051	10.8B	0.058	10.8C	0.049	10.8D	-0.060
11.0A	0.056	11.0B	0.066	11.0C	0.070	11.0D	0.032
11.2A	0.045	11.2B	0.058	11.2C	0.036	11.2D	-0.063
11.4A	0.064	11.4B	0.053	11.4C	0.060	11.4D	0.035
11.6A	0.030	11.6B	0.044	11.6C	0.053	11.6D	-0.072
11.8A	0.020	11.8B	0.049	11.8C	0.033	11.8D	0.028
12.0A	0.037	12.0B	0.031	12.0C	0.009	12.0D	-0.052
13.0A	0.010	13.0B	0.035	13.0C	0.010	130.0D	0.016
14.0A	-0.002	14.0B	-0.055	14.0C	-0.047	150.0D	0.016
15.0A	-0.030	15.0B	0.016	15.0C	-0.042	11.8E	-0.153
16.0A	-0.037	16.0B	-0.045	16.0C	-0.035	A	-0.025
18.0A	-0.030	18.0B	-0.051	18.0C	-0.040	B	0.027
22.0A	-0.120	22.0B	-0.025	22.0C	-0.030	C	0.060
26.0A	-0.005	26.0B	-0.047	26.0C	-0.010	D	-0.041
30.0A	-0.015	30.0B	-0.073	30.0C	0.011	E	0.078
50.0A	-0.065	50.0B	0.053	50.0C	-0.017	F	-0.036
70.0A	-0.348	70.0B	-0.073	70.0C	0.033	G	0.081
90.0A	-0.022	90.0B	-0.028	90.0C	-0.020	H	-0.027
110.0A	0.024	110.0B	-0.022	110.0C	-0.110	I	0.005
110.0D	-0.118	110.0E	-0.114	110.0F	0.013	J	0.002
						K	0.028
						L	0.035
						M	0.010
						N	0.093
						O	-0.034
						P	0.101
						R	-0.096
						S	0.036
						T	-0.046
						U	0.024
						V	0.017

Table A2: Correction factor, A^* , for correction of intermediate calibrated temperature, determined empirically from snow calibration of thermistors.

APPENDIX

	<i>Summer ice surface ablation (m)</i>		
	<u>2004</u>	<u>2005</u>	<u>2006</u>
BH04-01	2.46	0.63	0.90
BH04-06	≥ 1.05 and $\leq 1.84^*$	≥ 1.61 and ≤ 2.40	1.29
BH05-07	N/A	0.98 [^]	0.42 [^]

Table A3: Glacier surface annual ablation at borehole locations during the summers of 2004, 2005 and 2006. Values marked with (*) denoted estimated values, the BH04-06 summer 2004 value had to be estimated using the BH04-01 snow depth at the time of thermistor installation in May 2004 as drilling occurred through the snow pack and no pit was dug to accurately locate the ice surface (however, changes in drilling speed correspond to the assumed snow depth). Values marked with (^) denote incomplete ablation periods, the BH05-07 summer 2005 value indicates the ablation from the time of drilling on day 225, no measurement of early summer ablation prior to hole drilling was made, similarly the BH05-07 summer 2006 value only covers the period up to day 233 as measurements in January 2007 were inconclusive as to the amount of ablation in the period between day 233 and the initiation of the winter snow pack at BH05-07.

APPENDIX

(a)

<i>BH04-01</i>			
		<i>Date of thermistor deployment:</i>	<i>Day 133 (2004)</i>
		<i>Ice thickness at time of deployment:</i>	<i>131.43 m</i>
Thermistor	Deployment height above glacier bed (m)	Depth below surface at time of deployment (m)	Melt out date
110.0a	41.23	90.20	n/a
90.0a	53.23	78.20	n/a
70.0a	73.23	58.20	n/a
50.0a	93.23	38.20	n/a
30.0a	113.23	18.20	n/a
26.0a	117.23	14.20	n/a
22.0a	121.23	10.20	n/a
18.0a	125.23	6.20	n/a
16.0a	127.23	4.20	n/a
16.0c	127.23	4.20	n/a
15.0a	128.23	3.20	Day 209 (2005)
14.0a	129.23	2.20	Day 320 (2004)
13.0a	130.23	1.20	Before day 263 (2004)
12.0a	131.23	0.20	Before day 263 (2004)

(b)

<i>BH05-16</i>			
		<i>Date of thermistor deployment:</i>	<i>Day 263 (2005)</i>
		<i>Ice thickness at time of deployment:</i>	<i>128.50 m</i>
Thermistor	Deployment height above glacier bed (m)	Depth below surface at time of deployment (m)	Melt out date
150.0d	1.00	127.50	n/a
130.0d	8.50	120.00	n/a
110.0e	28.50	100.00	n/a
110.0f	38.50	90.00	n/a
90.0b	48.50	80.00	n/a

(c)

<i>BH04-06</i>			
		<i>Date of thermistor deployment:</i>	<i>Day 133 (2004)</i>
		<i>Ice thickness at time of deployment:</i>	<i>60.40 m</i>
Thermistor	Deployment height above glacier bed (m)	Depth below surface at time of deployment (m)	Melt out date
70.0b	0.00	60.40	n/a
50.0b	24.00	36.40	n/a
30.0b	44.00	16.40	n/a
26.0b	48.00	12.40	n/a
22.0b	52.00	8.40	n/a
18.0b	56.00	4.40	267 (2006)
16.0b	58.00	2.40	230 (2005)
15.0b	59.00	1.40	294 (2004)
14.0b	60.00	0.40	Before 263 (2004)

Table A4: Borehole thermistor deployment dates, locations with in the boreholes and melt out dates of near-surface thermistors in holes (a) BH04-01 (b) BH05-16 (adjacent to BH04-01) and (c) BH04-06.

APPENDIX

(a)

<i>Crevasse</i>	<i>Date of thermistor deployment: Day 225 (2005)</i>
Thermistor	Depth of deployment below glacier surface (m)
U	1.00
V	2.00
11.2d	3.00
11.4d	4.00
11.8d	6.00

(b)

<i>BH05-07</i>	<i>Date of thermistor deployment: Day 225 (2005)</i>		<i>Ice thickness at time of deployment: 98.5 m</i>
Thermistor	Deployment height above glacier bed (m)	Depth below surface at time of deployment (m)	Melt out date
110.0d	0.00	98.50	n/a
110.0c	3.50	95.00	n/a
110.0b	8.50	90.00	n/a
90.0c	18.50	80.00	n/a
70.0c	38.50	60.00	n/a
50.0c	58.50	40.00	n/a
30.0c	78.50	20.00	n/a
26.0c	82.50	16.00	n/a
22.0c	84.50	14.00	n/a
18.0c	86.50	12.00	n/a
15.0c	88.50	10.00	n/a
14.0c	90.50	8.00	n/a
12.0d	91.50	7.00	n/a
11.0d	92.50	6.00	n/a
10.8d	93.50	5.00	n/a
10.6d	94.50	4.00	n/a
10.4d	95.50	3.00	n/a
10.2d	96.50	2.00	n/a
10.0d	97.50	1.00	210 (2006)

Table A5: Borehole and crevasse thermistor deployment dates, locations within the borehole and crevasse and melt out dates of near-surface thermistors in (a) a crevasse adjacent to BH05-07 and (b) BH05-07.

APPENDIX

	<i>Thermistor</i>	<i>Data from which transient effects removed</i>	<i>Nature of removed effects</i>	<i>Field evidence supporting removal</i>
BH04-01	14.0a	Day 264 - 294 (2004)	Time series characteristic of air temperatures with nocturnal minima of -1.53 °C and maxima of 2.57 °C during daylight hours.	On day 263 BH04-01 was air filled to an unknown depth, while 14.0a was partially frozen into borehole wall at a depth of 85 cm below the surface.
	15.0a	Day 272 – 305 (2005)	Time series characteristic of air temperatures with nocturnal cooling cycles to a minima of -1 °C.	On day 270, 15.0a was 11 cm below the surface and the top of BH04-01 open (though no measurement of to what depth).
	16.0a	Day 289 – 305 (2005)	Cooling periods correspond to near-surface diurnal air temperature minima as recorded by 15.0a.	As for 15.0a.
BH04-06	15.0b	Day 248 – 293 (2004)	Positive temperatures of up to 0.44 °C indicative of liquid water in the borehole.	On day 270 BH04-06 was open at the surface and water full to a depth of ~50 cm, 15.0b was 35 cm below the ice surface in the water.
BH05-07	10.0d	Day 245 – 308 (2005)	Time series characteristic of air temperatures with nocturnal minima of -2.5 °C and positive temperatures during daylight hours.	BH05-07 drained following drilling and was open and air filled to an unknown depth on day 231.
	10.2d	Day 214 – 321 (2006)	Time series characteristic of air temperatures with positive temperatures during daylight hours reaching maxima of 2.85 °C and minima as low as -9.5 °C during November, likely a consequence of ponding of cold atmospheric air in an open borehole.	No direct observations of BH05-07 at the glacier surface as the glacier was snow covered for the duration of the summer 2006 field visit.
	10.4d	Day 214 – 321 (2006)		

Table A6: Periods of data from which non ice temperature transient effects were removed from the near-surface thermistors of all three boreholes prior to presentation of ice temperatures and supporting evidence for removal.

References

- Abels G. (1893) Beobachtungen der taglichen Periode der Temperatur in Schnee und Bestimmung des Wärmeleitungsvermögens des Schnees al Funktion seiner Dichtigkeit. *Kaiserliche Akademie der Wissenschaften Reportorium fur Meteorologie*, **16**, 1 – 53.
- Adhkiary S., Nakawo M., Seko K. and Shakya B. (2000) Dust influence on the melting processes of glacier ice: experimental results from Lirung Glacier, Nepal Himalayas. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication*, **264**, 43 – 52.
- Adhkiary S., Seko K., Nakawo M., Ageta Y. and Miyazaki N. (1996) The nature of ablation and aggregation on the dusted snow surface. *Extended abstracts of International Conference on Ecohydrology of Mountain Areas*, 24 – 28 March. ICIMOD, Kathmandu, Nepal, 293 – 295.
- Adhkiary S., Seko K., Nakawo M., Ageta Y. and Miyazaki N. (1997) Effect of surface dust on snow melt. *Bulletin of Glacier Research*, **15**, 58 – 92.
- Adhkiary S., Yamaguchi Y. and Ogawa K. (2002) Estimation of snow ablation under a dust layer covering a wide range of albedo. *Hydrological Processes*, **16**, 2853 – 2865.
- Ahlmann H.W. (1935) Contribution to the physics of glaciers. *Geographical Journal*, **86** (2), 97 – 113.
- Albert M.R. (2002) Effects of snow and firn ventilation on sublimation rates. *Annals of Glaciology*, **35**, 52 – 56.
- Albert M.R. and Hawley R.L. (2000) Seasonal differences in surface energy exchange and accumulation at Summit, Greenland. *Annals of Glaciology*, **31**, 387 – 390.
- Alton Wade F. (1947) Sub-surface temperature measuring equipment. *Journal of Glaciology*, **1** (2), 73 – 74.
- Ambach W. (1963) Untersuchungen zum Energieumsatz in der Ablations – zone des gronlandischen Inlandeises. *Medd. Gromland*. **174** (4), 311pp.
- Ambach W. (1986) Nomographs for the determination of melt water from snow ad ice surfaces. *Berichte des Naturwissenschaftlich – Medizinischen Vereins in Innsbruck*. **73**, 7 -15.
- Ambach W. (1979) Zum Wärmehaushalt des grönländischen Inlandeises: vergleichende Studie im Akkumulations und Ablationsgebiet. *Polarforschung*, **49** (1), 44 – 54.
- Ambach W. and Hoinkes H.C. (1963) The heat balance of an alpine snow field. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No. 61*, 24 – 36.
- Andrews T. (1886) Observations on pure ice and snow. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, **40**, 544 – 549
- Aristarain A.J., Pinglot J.F. and Pourchet M. (1987) Accumulation and temperature measurements on the James Ross Island Ice cap, Antarctic Peninsula, Antarctica. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (115), 357 – 362.
- Arnold N. S., Willis I. C., Sharp M. J., Richards K. S. and Lawson W. J. (1996) A distributed surface energy balance model for a small valley glacier. I. Development and testing for Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Valais, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **42** (140), 77 – 89.
- Atkinson T.C., Smart P.L. and Wigley T.M.L (1983) Climate and natural radon levels in Castlegaurd Cave, Columbia Icefields, Alberta, Canada. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **15** (4), 487 – 502.

REFERENCES

- Bader H. (1950) The significance of air bubbles in glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **1** (8), 443 – 51.
- Bader H.P. and Weilenmann P. (1992) Modelling temperature distribution, energy and mass flow in a (phase changing) snow pack. I Model and case studies. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, **20** (2), 157 – 181.
- Baker R.W. and Gerberich W.W. (1979) The effect of crystal size and dispersed solid inclusions on the activation energy for creep of ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **24** (90), 179 – 194.
- Barnes P. and Tabor D. (1966) Plastic flow and pressure melting in the deformation of ice 1. *Nature*, **210** (5039), 878 – 883.
- Barnes P., Tabor D. and Walker J.C.F. (1971) Friction and creep of polycrystalline ice. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A*, **324** (1557), 127 – 55.
- Beck A.E. and Balling N. (1988) Determination of virgin rock temperatures. In *Handbook of terrestrial heat flow density determination*. Haenel R., Rybach L. and Stegna L. (eds). Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, Netherlands. P. 87 – 124.
- Beniston M., Fox D.G., Adhikary S., Andressen R., Guisan A., Holten J., Innes J., Maitima J., Price M. and Tessier L. (1996) The impacts of climate change on mountain regions. *Second Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)*, Chapter 5, Cambridge University Press, pp 191 – 213.
- Beniston M., Keller F. and Goyette S. (2003) Snow pack in the Swiss Alps under changing climatic conditions: an empirical approach for climate impact studies. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, **74**, 91 – 31.
- Benjumea B., Macheret Y.Y., Navarro F.J. and Teixido T. (2003) Estimation of water content in a temperate glacier from radar and seismic sounding data. *Annals of Glaciology*, **37**, 317 – 324.
- Benn D.I. and Evans D.J.A. (1998) *Glaciers and Glaciation*. Arnold, London.
- Bergen J.D. (1970) A possible relation between grain size, density and light attenuation in natural snow cover. *Journal of Glaciology*, **9** (55), 154 – 156.
- Berner W., Stauffer B. and Oeschger H. (1977) Dynamic glacier flow model and the production of internal melt water. *Zeitschrift für Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **13** (1/2), 209 – 217.
- Bertoldi G., Tamanini D., Zanotti F. and Rigon R. (2004) GEOTOP: a hydrological balance model. Technical description and programs guide. University of Trento (Italy) E – Prints. [http://eprints.biblio.unitn.it/archive/00000551/\[04/04/2004\]](http://eprints.biblio.unitn.it/archive/00000551/[04/04/2004])
- Bindschadler R., Harrison W.D., Raymond C.F. and Gantet C. (1976) Thermal regime of a surge type glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 251 – 259.
- Blackwell D.D. and Spafford R.E. (1987) Experimental methods in continental heat flow. In *Geophysics part B, field measurements*. Sammis C.G. and Henyey T.L. (eds). Academic Press Inc., Orlando, Methods of Experimental Physics, 24, 189 – 226.
- Blackwell D.D. and Steele J.L. (1989) Thermal conductivity of sedimentary rock: measurement and significance. In *Thermal history of sedimentary basins: methods and case histories*. Naeser N.D. and McCullough T.H. (eds). Springer – Verlag, New York. P. 13 – 36.
- Blatter H. (1987) On the thermal regime of an arctic valley glacier, Axel Heiberg Island, N.W.T. Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **334** (114), 200 – 211.
- Blatter H. (1998) Calibration of Fenwal thermistors. Geographisches Institut, Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule, Zürich, Switzerland.
- Blatter H. and Haeberli W. (1984) Modelling temperature distribution in alpine glaciers. *Annals of Glaciology*, **5**, 18 – 22.

REFERENCES

- Bøggild C.E. Oerter H. and Tukiainen T. (1996) Increased ablation of Wisconsin ice in eastern North Greenland: observations and modelling. *Annals of Glaciology*, **23**, 144 – 148.
- Bøggild C.E., Reeh N. and Oerter H. (1994) Modelling ablation and mass balance sensitivity to climate change of Storstrømmen, North East Greenland. *Global and Planetary Change*, **9**, 79 – 90.
- Bohren C.F. and Barkstrom B.R. (1972) Theory of the optical properties of snow. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **79** (30), 4527 – 4535.
- Bosch G., Kirnbauer R. and Gutknecht D. (1991) Distributed snow melt simulations in an alpine catchment: I Model evaluation on the basis of snow cover patterns. *Water Resources Research*, **27** (12), 3171 – 3179.
- Boulton G.S. (1972) The role of thermal regime in glacial sedimentation. *Institute of British Geographers, Special Publication No. 4*, pp. 1 – 18.
- Boulton G.S. (1974) Processes and patterns of glacial erosion. *In Coates D.R. ed. Glacial geomorphology*. Binghamton, NY, State University of New York, 41 – 87.
- Bowden F.P. and Hughes T.P. (1939) The mechanism of sliding on ice and snow. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series A*, **172** (949), 280 – 298.
- Box G.E.P. and Jenkins G.M. (1976) *Time series analysis, forecasting and control*. Holden – Day, 575 pp.
- Box J.E. and Steffen K. (2001) Sublimation on the Greenland ice sheet from automated weather station observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **106**, 33965 – 33981.
- Braithwaite R. J. (1981). On glacier energy balance, ablation and air temperature. *Journal of Glaciology*, **27**(97), 381-391.
- Braithwaite R.J. (1995a) Aerodynamic stability and turbulent sensible heat flux over a melting ice surface, the Greenland Ice Sheet. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41** (139), 562 – 571.
- Braithwaite R.J. (1995b) Positive degree-day factors for ablation on the Greenland ice sheet studied by energy – balance modelling. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41** (137), 153 – 160.
- Braithwaite R.J. and Olesen O.B. (1989) Ice ablation in West Greenland in relation to air temperature and global radiation. *Zeitschrift für Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **20**, 1 – 8.
- Braithwaite R.J. and Olesen O.B. (1990) A simple energy balance model to calculate ice ablation at the margin of the Greenland ice sheet. *Journal of Glaciology*, **36** (123), 222 – 228.
- Braithwaite R.J. and Zhang Yu (2000) Sensitivity of mass balance of five Swiss glaciers to temperature changes assessed by tuning a degree – day model. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (152), 7 – 14.
- Braithwaite R.J. Konzelmann T., Marty C. and Olesen O.B. (1998) Reconnaissance study of energy balance in North Greenland, 1993 – 1994. *Journal of Glaciology*, **44** (147), 239 – 247.
- Brandt R.E. and Warren S.G. (1993) Solar heating and temperature profiles in Antarctic snow and ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **39** (13), 99 – 110.
- Brock B.W. (2004) An analysis of short term albedo variations at Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Geografiska Annaler*, **86** (A), 53 – 65.
- Brock B.W. and Arnold N.S. (2000) A spreadsheet-based (Microsoft Excel) point surface energy balance model for glacier and snow melt studies. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **25**, 649 – 658.

REFERENCES

- Brock B.W., Willis I.C. and Sharp M.J. (2000b) Measurement and parameterization of albedo variations at Haut Glacier d' Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (155), 675 – 688.
- Brock B.W., Willis I.C., Sharp M.J. and Arnold N.S. (2000a) Modelling seasonal and spatial variations in the surface energy balance of Haut Glacier d' Arolla, Switzerland. *Annals of Glaciology*, **31**, 53 – 62.
- Brown G.H., Sharp M.J., Tranter M., Gurnell A.M. and Nienow P.N. (1994) The impact of post mixing chemical reactions on the major ion chemistry of bulk melt waters draining the Haut Glacier d' Arolla, Valais, Switzerland. *Hydrological Processes*, **8**, 465 – 480.
- Brun E., Martin E., Simon V., Gendre C. and Coleou C. (1989). "An energy and mass model of snow cover suitable for operational avalanche forecasting." *Journal of Glaciology*, **35** (121): 333 - 342.
- Buck A.L. (1981) New equations for computing vapour pressure and enhancement factor. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **20**, 1527 – 1532.
- Budd W.F. and Jacka T.H. (1989) A review of ice rheology for ice sheet modelling. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, **16** (2), 107 – 144.
- Budd W.F. and Radok U. (1971) Glaciers and other large ice masses. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, **34**, 1 – 70.
- Burke (1981) Electronics 2nd edition, in "Using thermistor temperature sensors with Campbell scientific dataloggers" Technical note 15 – 95AS (1995). Campbell Scientific Inc., Loughborough.
- Burridge D.M. and Gadd A.J. (1974) The Meteorological Office operational 10 level numerical weather prediction model (December 1974). *U.K. Met. Office. Technical Notes 12 and 48*, 57pp.
- Butkovich T.R. and Landauer J.K. (1958) The flow law for ice. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No. 47*, 318 – 327.
- Calanaca P. and Heuberger R. (1990) Energy balance. In Glacial climate research in the Tianshan. Ohmura A., Lang H., Blimer F. and Grubner D. (eds). *Zurcher Geographische Schriften 38*. Geographisches Institut, ETH: Zurich, Switzerland: 1810.
- Calles B. and Calles U.M. (1990) Temperature correction of electrical conductivity values. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **15**, 673 – 678.
- Cameron R.L. and Bull C.B. (1962) The thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity of glacial ice at Wilkes Station, Antarctica. *Maury Memorial Symposium, Antarctic Research Reports*, **7**, 178 – 184.
- Campbell F.M.A., Nienow P.W. and Purves R.S. (2006) Role of the supraglacial snow pack in mediating melt water delivery to the glacier system as inferred from dye tracer investigations. *Hydrological Processes*, **20**, 969 – 985.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002c) *CS547 Conductivity and Temperature Probe and A547 Interface user guide*. Campbell Scientific Inc.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (1989) *KH2O Krypton Hygrometer User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (1995) *MP100A Temperature and Relative Humidity Probe User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (1998a) *NR-Lite Net Radiometer User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (1998b) *HFP01 Heat Flux Plate User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.

REFERENCES

- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2000) *CR10X Measurement and Control Module Instruction Manual*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2001) *Voltage Measurement Accuracy, Self-Calibration and Radiometric Measurements. White Paper 3*. Campbell Scientific INC, Logan, Utah.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002a) *Wind Monitors (05103/05103LM & 05106) (including optional Wind Tracker) User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2002b) *CSAT3 Three Dimensional Sonic Anemometer User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2003a) *SR50 Sonic Ranging Sensor User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Campbell Scientific Inc. (2003b) *CNR1 Net Radiometer User Guide*. Campbell Scientific Ltd, Leicestershire.
- Carroll J.J. (1982) Long-term means and short term variability of the surface energy balance components at the South Pole. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **87** (C6), 4277 – 4286.
- Carslaw H.S. and Jaeger J.C. (1959) *Conduction of Heat in Solids*. Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Cathles L.M., IV, Cathles L.M., III and Albert M.R. (2007) A physically based method for correcting temperature profile measurements made using thermocouples. *Journal of Glaciology*, **53**, 181, 298 – 304.
- Chandler D.M. (2005) Measuring and modelling glacier sliding, *Ph.D. thesis*, University of Wales, Aberystwyth, U.K.
- Chandler D.M., Hubbard A.L, Hubbard B.P. and Nienow P.W. (2006) A Monte Carlo error analysis for basal sliding velocity calculations. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **111** (F04005), 1 – 13.
- Cherry J.E., Tremblay B.L., Dery S.J. and Stieglitz M. (2005) Reconstructing solid precipitation from snow depth measurements and a land surface model. *Water Resources Research*, **41** (W09401), 1 – 15.
- Clarke G.K., Nitsan U. and Paterson W.S.B. (1977) Strain heating and creep instabilities in glaciers and ice sheets. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*. **15** (2), 235 – 247.
- Clarke G.K.C. and Jarvis G.T. (1974) Thermal effects of crevassing on Steele glacier, Yukon Territory, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **13** (68), 243 - 254.
- Clarke G.K.C. and Jarvis G.T. (1976) Post surge temperatures in Steele glacier, Yukon Territory, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 261 – 268.
- Clarke G.K.C., Fisher D.A. and Waddington E.D. (1987) Wind pumping: a potentially significant heat source in ice sheets. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication 170* (Symposium at Vancouver 1987 – The Physical Basis of Ice Sheet Modelling), 169 – 180.
- Clarke G.K.C., Nitsan U. and Paterson W.S.B. (1977) Strain heating and creep instability in glaciers and ice sheets. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*. **15** (2), 235 – 247.
- Clarke M.J. and Seppala M. (1988) Slush flows in a subarctic environment, Kilpisjarvi, Finish Lapland. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **20** (1), 97 – 105.
- Classen D.F. (1977) Temperature profiles for the Barnes Ice Cap surge zone. *Journal of Glaciology*, **18**, 391 – 405.
- Cline D.W. (1997) Snow surface energy exchanges and snowmelt at a continental, mid latitude Alpine site. *Water Resources Research*, **33** (4), 689 – 701.

REFERENCES

- Clow G.D., Saltus R.W. and Waddington E.D. (1996) A high precision borehole temperature logging system used at GISP2, Greenland, and Taylor Dome, Antarctica. *Journal of Glaciology*, **42** (142), 576 – 584.
- Cohen D. (1999) Rheology of basal ice at Engabreen, Norway. *PhD thesis*, University of Minnesota.
- Cohen D. (2000) Rheology of ice at the bed of Engabreen, Norway. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (155), 611 – 621.
- Cohen D., Hooke R.LeB., Iverson N.R. and Kohler J. (2000) Sliding of ice past an obstacle at Engabreen, Norway. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (155), 599 – 610.
- Colbeck S.C. (1979) Grain clusters in wet snow. *Journal of Colloid Interface Science*, **72** (3), 371 – 384.
- Colbeck S.C. (1993) The vapour diffusion coefficient for snow. *Water Resources Research*, **29** (1), 109 – 115.
- Colbeck S.C. and Evans R.J. (1973) A flow law for temperate glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **12** (64), 71 – 86.
- Collins D.N. (1977) Hydrology of an alpine glacier as indicated by the geochemical composition of melt water. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **13** (1/2), 219 – 239.
- Collins D.N. (1979) Quantitative determination of the subglacial hydrology of two alpine glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **23** (89), 347 – 362.
- Collins D.N. (1981) Seasonal variation of solute concentration in melt waters draining from an alpine glacier. *Annals of Glaciology*, **1**, 11 -16.
- Collins D.N. (1983) Solute yield from a glacierized high mountain basin, in Webb B.W. (ed) Symposium on Dissolved Loads of Rivers and Surface Water Quantity / Quality Relationship (Proceedings of the Hamburg Symposium, 15 – 17 August 1983), *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No.141*, pp 41 – 50.
- Conway H. and Benedict R. (1994) Infiltration of water into snow. *Water Resources Research*, **30** (3), 641 – 649.
- Conway H. and Raymond C.F. (1993) Snow stability during rain. *Journal of Glaciology*, **39** (133), 635 – 642.
- Copland L., Harbor J. and Sharp M. (1997b) Borehole video observations of englacial and basal ice conditions in a temperate valley glacier. *Annals of Glaciology*, **24**, 277 – 282.
- Copland L., Harbor J., Gordon S. and Sharp M. (1997a) The use of borehole video in investigating the hydrology of a temperate glacier. *Hydrological Processes*, **11**, 211 -224.
- Copland L., Harbor J., Minner M. and Sharp M. (1997c) The use of borehole inclinometry in determining basal sliding and internal deformation at Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Annals of Glaciology*, **24**, 331 – 337.
- Cove J. (2006) Ski Resorts depressed by snowfall. BBC News Online, Published 19/01/2007 <http://news.bbc.co.uk/go/pr/fr/-/1/hi/world/europe/6277331.stm> [accessed 12/05/07].
- Curry J.A., Schramm J.L. and Ebert E.E. (1995) Sea ice albedo climate feedback mechanism. *Journal of Climate*, **8** (2) 240 – 247.
- Cutler P.M. and Munro D.S. (1996) Visible and near infrared reflectivity during the ablation period on Peyto Glacier, Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **42** (141), 333 – 340.
- Dahl – Jensen D. and Gundestrup N.S. (1987) Constitutive properties of ice at Dye 3, Greenland. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No.170*

REFERENCES

- (Symposium at Vancouver 1987 – The Physical Basis of Ice sheet Modelling), 31 – 43.
- Dahl-Jensen D., Gundestrup N., Gogineni P. and Miller H. (2003) Basal melt at North GRIP modelled from borehole, ice core and radio-echo sounder observations. *Annals of Glaciology*, **37**, 207 – 212.
- De la Casiniere A.C. (1974) Heat exchange over a melting snow surface. *Journal of Glaciology*. **13** (67), 55 – 72.
- De Quervain M.R. (1956) Zur Waermeleitung von Schnee. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication* **39** (General Assembly of Rome 1954 – Snow and Ice), Vol **4**, 26 – 32.
- Denby B. (1999) Second order modelling of turbulence in katabatic flows. *Boundary Layer Meteorology*. **92**, 67 – 100.
- Denby B. and Greuell W. (2000) The use of bulk and profile methods for determining surface heat fluxes in the presence of glacier winds. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (154), 445 – 452.
- Denby B. and Smeets C.J.P.P. (2000) Derivation of turbulent flux profiles and roughness lengths from katabatic flow dynamics. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **39**, 1601-1612.
- Dozier J. (1980) A clear sky spectral solar radiation model for snow covered mountainous terrain. *Water Resources Research*, **16** (4), 709 – 718.
- Duval P. and LeGac H. (1980). “Does the permanent creep rate of polycrystalline ice increase with crystal size?” *Journal of Glaciology*. **25**, 151 – 157.
- Duval P. (1973). “Plasticite: Fluage de la glace Polycristalline pour les faibles contraintes. C.R. Hebd. *Seances Acad. Sci., Ser. A*, **277**, 703 – 706.
- Duval P. (1977) The role of the water content on the creep of polycrystalline ice. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication* No.**118** (Symposium at Grenoble, 1975 – Isotopes and impurities in Snow and Ice), 29 – 33.
- Duynkeke P.G. and van den Broeke R. (1994) Surface energy balance and katabatic flow over glacier and tundra during GIMEX-91, *Global and Planetary Change*, **9** (1-2), 17 – 28.
- Dyrgerov M. and Meier M.F. (2005) Glaciers and the Changing Earth System: A 2004 Snapshot. *Occasional Paper* **58**, Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, 118 pp.
- Echelmeyer K. and Zhongxiang W. (1987) Direct observation of basal sliding and deformation of basal drift at sub-freezing temperatures. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33**, 83 – 98.
- Echelmeyer K., Harrison W.D., Clarke T.S. and Benson C. (1992) Surficial glaciology of Jakobshavns Tsjbrae, West Greenland: Part II. Ablation, accumulation and temperature. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38**, 169 – 181.
- Elder K., Dozier J. and Michaelson J. (1991) Snow accumulation and distribution in an alpine watershed. *Water Resources Research*, **27**, 1541 – 1552.
- Engelhardt H. (1978) Water in glaciers: Observations and theory of the behaviour of water levels in boreholes. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie* **14**, 35 – 60.
- Engelhardt H., Humphrey N. and Kamb B. (1990a) Borehole geophysical observations on Ice Stream B, Antarctica. *Antarctic Journal U.S.*, **25**, 80 – 82.
- Engelhardt H., Humphrey N., Kamb B. and Fahnestock M. (1990b) Physical conditions at the base of a fast moving Antarctic ice stream. *Science*, **248**, 57 – 59.

REFERENCES

- Englhardt H. (2004) Ice temperature and geothermal flux at Siple Dome, West Antarctica, from borehole measurements. *Journal of Glaciology*, **50** (169), 251 – 256.
- Escher – Vetter H. (1985) Energy balance calculations for the ablation period 1982 at Vernagtferner, Oetztal Alps. *Annals of Glaciology*, **6**, 158 – 160.
- Escher – Vetter H. (2000) Modelling melt water production with a distributed energy balance method and runoff using a linear reservoir approach – results from Vernagtferner, Oetztal Alps, for the ablation seasons 1992 to 1995, *Zeitschrift für Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **36**, 119 – 150.
- Essery R. (2005) Snow modelling in JULES: a report for CLASSIC. University of Wales Aberystwyth.
- Fairchild I.J., Bradby L. and Spiro B. (1993) Reactive carbonate in glacial systems: a preliminary synthesis of its creation, dissolution and reincarnation. In Deynoux M., Miller J.M.G, Domack E.W., Eyles N., Fairchild I.J. and Young G.M. eds. *Earth's glacial record – IGCP Project 260*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 176 – 192.
- Fairchild I.J., Bradby L., Sharp M.J. and Tison J.-L. (1994) Hydrochemistry of carbonate terrains in alpine glacial settings. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **19** (1), 33 – 55.
- Fairchild I.J., Killawee J.A., Hubbard B. and Dreybrodt W. (1999a) Interactions of calcareous suspended sediment with glacial meltwater a field test of dissolution behaviour. *Chemical Geology*, **155** (3-4), 243 – 263.
- Fairchild I.J., Killawee J.A., Sharp M.J., Spiro B., Hubbard B., Lorrain R.D. and Tison J.-L. (1999b) Solute generation and transfer from a chemically reactive alpine glacial – proglacial system. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **24**, 1189 – 1211.
- Faust B.S. (1947) An unusual phenomenon. *National Speleological Society (NSS) Bulletin*, **9**, 52 – 54.
- Favier V., Wagnon P., Chazarin J.P., Maisincho L. and Coudrain A. (2004) One year measurements of surface heat budget on the ablation zone of Antizana Glacier 15, Ecuadorian Andes. *Journal of Geophysical Research – Atmospheres*, **109**, (D18), Article number D18105.
- Fenn C.R. (1987) Electrical Conductivity. In *Glacio-fluvial Sediment Transfer*. Gurnell A.M. and Clarke M.J. (eds). Wiley and Sons. pp 377 – 414.
- Fetterer F. and Untersteiner N. (1998) Observations of melt ponds on Arctic sea ice. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **103** (C11), 24,821 – 24,835.
- Fischer U.H. and Clarke G.K.C. (2001) Review of subglacial hydro-mechanical coupling: Trapridge Glacier, Yukon Territory, Canada. *Quaternary International*, **81** (1), 29 – 43.
- Fish A. M. and Zaretsky Y.K. (1997) Ice strength as a function of hydrostatic pressure and temperature. *Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory Report* **97 – 6**.
- Fisher D.A. and Koerner R.M. (1986) On the special rheological properties of ancient micro particle – laden Northern Hemisphere ice as derived from borehole and core measurements. *Journal of Glaciology*, **32** (112), 501 – 510.
- Fitzharris B.B. Stewart D. and Harrison W. (1980) Contribution of snowmelt to the October 1978 flood of the Pomahaka and Fraser Rivers, Otago. *Journal of Hydrology (NZ)*, **19** (2), 84 – 93.
- Fohn P.M.B. (1973) Short term snow melt and ablation derived from heat and mass balance measurements. *Journal of Glaciology*, **12** (65), 275 – 289.

REFERENCES

- Ford D.C. (1971) Alpine karst in the Mount Castlegaurd – Columbia Icefield area, Canadian Rocky Mountains. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **3** (3), 239 – 252.
- Ford D.C., Harmon R.S., Schwarcz H.P., Wigley T.M.L. and Thompson P. (1976) Geohydrologic and thermometric observations of the Columbia Ice field, Alberta and British Columbia, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 219 – 230.
- Fountain A.G. (1994) Borehole water level variations and implications for the subglacial hydraulics of South Cascade Glacier. Washington State U.S.A. *Journal of Glaciology*, **40**, 239 – 304.
- Fountain A.G. (1989) The storage of water in, and hydrological characteristics of, the firn of South Cascade Glacier, Washington State, U.S.A. *Annals of Glaciology*, **13**, 69 – 75.
- Fountain A.G. (1992) Subglacial water-flow inferred from stream measurements at South Cascade Glacier, Washington, USA. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (128), 51 – 64.
- Fountain A.G. (1994) Borehole water level variations and implications for the subglacial hydraulics of South Cascade Glacier, Washington State, U.S.A. *Journal of Glaciology*, **40**, 293 – 304.
- Fountain A.G. (1996) Effect of snow and firn hydrology on the physical and chemical characteristics of glacial runoff. *Hydrological Processes*, **10**, 509 – 521.
- Fountain A.G. and Vecchia A. (1999) How many stakes are required to measure the mass balance of a glacier? *Geografiska Annaler*, **81** (A), 4, 563 – 573.
- Fountain A.G. and Walder J.S. (1998) Water flow through temperate glaciers. *Reviews of Geophysics*, **36** (3), 299 – 328.
- Fountain A.G., Schlichting R.B., Jansson P. and Jacobel R.W. (2005a) Observations of englacial water passages: a fracture dominated system. *Annals of Glaciology*, **40**, 25 – 30.
- Fountain A.G., Schlichting R.B., Jansson P. and Jacobel R.W. (2005b) Fractures as the main pathways of water flow in temperate glaciers. *Nature*, **433** (7026), 618 – 621.
- Freitas C.R., Litteljohn R.N., Clarkson T.S. and Kristament I.S. (1982) Cave climate: Assessment of air flow and ventilation. *Journal of Climatology*, **2**, 383 – 397.
- Fukazawa H., Sugiyama K. and Mae S. (1998) Acid ions at triple junctions of Antarctic ice observed by Raman scattering. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **25** (15), 2845 – 2848).
- Gagnon R.E. and Gammon P.H. (1995) Triaxial experiments on iceberg and glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41**, (139), 538 – 540.
- Gao X.Q., Jacka T.H. and Souchez R.A. (1988) Rheological contrast between Pleistocene and Holocene ice in Barnes Ice Cap, Baffin Island. N.W.T. Canada: a new interpretation. *Journal of Glaciology*, **34** (118), 364 – 365 (letter).
- Garnier B. J. and Ohmura A. (1970) The evaluation of surface variations in solar radiation income. *Solar Energy*, **13**, 21 – 34.
- Garrat J.R. (1992) *The atmospheric boundary layer*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Geiger R. (1966) *The climate near the ground*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge Massachusetts.
- Gerdel R.W. (1954) The transmission of water through snow. *Transactions of the American Geophysical Union*, **35** (3), 475 – 485.
- Gerland S., Liston G.E., Winther J.G., Ørbæk J.B. and Ivanov B.V. (2000) Attenuation of solar radiation in Arctic snow: field observations and modelling. *Annals of Glaciology*, **31**, 364 – 368.

REFERENCES

- Gerland S., Winther J-G., Orbaek J.B., Liston G.E., Oritsland N.A., Blanco A. and Ivanov B. (1999) Physical and optical properties of snow covering Arctic tundra on Svalbard. *Hydrological Processes*, **13**, 2331 – 2343.
- Giddings J.C. and La Chapelle E. (1961) Diffusion theory applied to radiant energy distribution and albedo of snow. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **66** (1), 181 – 189.
- Gillet F. (1975) Steam, Hot water and Electrical thermal drills for temperate glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **14** (70), 171 – 179.
- Glen J.W. (1955) The creep of polycrystalline ice. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A*. **228** (1175), 519 – 583.
- Glen J.W. (1958) The flow law of ice: a discussion of the assumptions made in glacier theory, their experimental foundation and consequences. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No.47*, (Symposium at Chamonix 1958 – Physics of the Movement of the Ice), 171 – 183.
- Glen J.W. (1974) The Physics of ice. *Cold Regions Science and Engineering Monograph 11-c2a* (CRREL) 79 pp.
- Glen J.W. (1975) The Mechanics of ice. *Cold Regions Science and Engineering Monograph 11-c2b* (CRREL) 44 pp.
- Goodman D.J, King G.C.P, Millar D.H.M. and Robin G de Q. (1979) Pressure melting effects in basal ice of temperate glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **23** (89), 259 – 271.
- Gordon S., Sharp M., Hubbard B., Willis I., Smart C., Copland L., Harbor, J. and Ketterling B. (2001). Borehole drainage and its implications for the investigation of glacier hydrology: Experiences from Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Hydrological Processes*, **15** (5), 797 – 813.
- Gow A.J. (1963) Results in the 309 m borehole at Byrd Station, Antarctica. *Journal of Glaciology*, **4** (36), 771 – 784.
- Gow A.J. (1969) On the rates of growth of grains and crystals in south polar firn. *Journal of Glaciology*, **8** (53), 241 – 252.
- Grainger M.E., Lister H. (1966) Wind speed, stability and eddy viscosity over melting ice surfaces. *Journal of Glaciology*, **6** (43), 101 – 127.
- Gregory J.M. and Oerlemans J. (1998) Simulated future sea level rise due to glacier melt based on regionally and seasonally resolved temperature changes. *Nature*, **391**, 474 – 476.
- Greuell W. and Konzelmann T. (1994) Numerical modelling of the energy balance and the englacial temperature of the Greenland Ice Sheet. Calculations from the ETH – Camp location (West Greenland, 1155 m a.s.l.). *Global and Planetary Change*, **9**, 91 – 114.
- Greuell W. and Oerlemans J. (1986) Sensitivity studies with a mass balance model including temperature profile calculations inside the glacier. *Zeitschrift Fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **22** (2), 101 – 124.
- Greuell W. and Smeets P. (2001) Variations with elevation in the surface energy balance on the Pastereze (Austria). *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **106** (D23), 31,717 – 31,727.
- Greuell W., Knap W. and Smeets P. (1997) Elevational changes in meteorological variables along a mid latitude glacier during summer. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **106**, 25,941 – 25,954.
- Grust K. (2004) The hydrology and dynamics of a glacier on limestone. *PhD thesis*, University of Glasgow.

REFERENCES

- Gudmundsson G.H., Bauder A., Luthi M., Fischer U.H. and Funk M. (1999) Estimating rates of basal motion and ice deformation from continuous tilt measurements. *Annals of Glaciology*, **28**, 247 – 252.
- Haeberli W. (1976). "Eistemperaturen in den Alpen." *Zeitschrift für Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie* **11**, 203 - 220.
- Haeberli W. (2005) Mountain glaciers in global climate-related observing systems. in *Global Change and Mountain Regions, an overview of current knowledge*. eds, Huber U.M., Bugmann H. K. M. and Reasoner M.A., Springer, Dordrecht, Netherlands.
- Haeberli W. and Funk M. (1991) Borehole temperatures at the Colle Gnifetti core drilling site (Monte Rosa, Swiss Alps). *Journal of Glaciology*, **37** (125), 37 – 46.
- Haeberli W. and Holzle M. (1995) Application of inventory data for estimating characteristics of and regional climate-change on mountain glaciers: A pilot study from the European Alps. *Annals of Glaciology*, **21**, 206 – 212.
- Haeberli W., Hoelzle M. and Zemp M. (2007) Glacier Mass Balance Bulletin, Bulletin No. **9** (2004 – 2005). WGMS, Zurich, Switzerland.
- Haeberli W., Rellstab W. and Harrison W.D. (1984) Geothermal effects of 18 Ka BP ice conditions in the Swiss Plateau. *Annals of Glaciology*, **5**, 56 – 59.
- Halberstam I. and Schieldge J.P. (1981) Anomalous behaviour of the atmospheric surface layer over a melting snow pack. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **20**, 255 – 265.
- Hallet B., Lorrain R. and Souchez R.A. (1978) The composition of basal ice from a glacier sliding over limestones. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, **89** (2), 314 – 320.
- Hansen B.L. and Landauer J.K. (1958) Some results of ice cap drill hole measurements, *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No.47*, 313 – 317.
- Hantz D. and Lliboutry L. (1983) Water ways, ice permeability at depth and water pressures at Glacier d'Argentiere, French Alps. *Journal of Glaciology*, **29**, 227 – 239.
- Harding R.J. (1986) Exchanges of energy and mass associated with a melting snow pack. *International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication No.155*, 3 – 15.
- Harding R.J. and Lloyd C.R. (1998) Fluxes of energy and water from three high latitude tundra sites in Svalbard during snowmelt and snow free periods. *Nordic Hydrology*, **29** (4/5), 267 – 284.
- Harper J.T. and Humphrey N.F. (1995) Borehole video analysis of a temperate glacier's englacial and subglacial structure: implications for glacier flow models. *Geology*, **23**, 901 – 904.
- Harper J.T., Humphrey N.F, Pfeffer W.T., Huzurbazar S.V., Bahr D.B., Welch B.C. (2001) Spatial variability in the flow of a valley glacier: deformation of a large array of boreholes. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **106** (B5), 8547 – 8562.
- Harper J.T., Humphrey N.F. and Pfeffer W.T. (1998) Three-dimensional deformation measured in an Alaskan glacier. *Science*, **281**, 1340 – 1342.
- Harris C., Haeberli W., Muhll D.V. and King L. (2001) Permafrost monitoring in the high mountains of Europe: the PACE project and its global context. *Permafrost and Periglacial Processes*. **12**, 3 – 11.
- Harris C., Muhll D.V., Isaksen K., Haeberli W., Sollid J.L., King L., Holmund P., Dramis F., Guglielmin M. and Palacios D. (2003) Warming permafrost in European mountains. *Global and Planetary Change*. **39**, 215 – 225.
- Harrison W.D. (1975) Temperature measurements in a temperate glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **14** (70), 23 – 30.

REFERENCES

- Harrison W.D. (1972) Temperature of a temperate glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **11** (61), 15 – 29.
- Harrison W.D. and Raymond C.F. (1976) Impurities and their distribution in temperate glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 173 – 181.
- Harrison W.D., Echelmeyer K.A. and Larsen C.F. (1998) Measurement of temperature in a margin of Ice Stream B, Antarctica: implications for margin migration and lateral drag. *Journal of Glaciology*, **44** (148), 615 – 624.
- Hastenrath S. (1978) Heat budget measurements on the Quelccaya Ice cap, Peruvian Andes. *Journal of Glaciology*, **20** (82), 85 – 97.
- Hay J.E. and Fitzharris B.B. (1988b) The synoptic climatology of ablation on a New Zealand glacier. *Journal of Climatology*, **8**, 201 – 215.
- Hay J.E. and Fitzharris B.B. (1988a) A comparison of the energy balance and bulk aerodynamic approaches for estimating glacier melt. *Journal of Glaciology*, **34** (117), 145 – 153.
- Hestnes E. (1985) A contribution to the prediction of slush avalanches. *Annals of Glaciology*, **6**, 1 – 4.
- Hicks B.B. and Martin H.C. (1972) Atmospheric turbulent fluxes over snow. *Boundary layer Meteorology*, **2**, 496 – 502.
- Higashi A. (1967) Ice crystal growth in a temperate glacier in Alaska. *Physics of Snow and Ice*. Oura H. (ed), 1 (1). Institute of Low Temperature Science, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, 409 – 430.
- Hinzman L.D., Goering D.J. and Kane D.L. (1998) A distributed thermal model for calculation soil temperature profiles and depth of thaw in permafrost regions. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **103** (D22), 28,975 – 28,991.
- Hjelstrom S.A. (1889) Sur la conductibilité de la neige. *Øfversigt af Kongl. Vetenskaps – Akademiens Forhandlingar*, **46**, 669 – 675.
- Hock R. (1999) A distributed temperature –index ice- and snow-melt model including potential direct solar radiation. *Journal of Glaciology*, **45**, 101 – 111.
- Hock R. (2003) Temperature index melt modelling in mountain areas. *Journal of Hydrology*, **282** (1-4), 104 – 115.
- Hock R. and Holmgren B. (1996) Some aspects of energy balance and ablation of Storglaciären, Northern Sweden. *Geografiska Annaler*, **78A** (2-3), 121 – 131.
- Hock R. and Holmgren B. (2005) A distributed energy balance model for complex topography and its application to Storglaciären, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (172), 25 – 36.
- Hock R. and Hooke R le B. (1993) Evolution of the internal drainage system in the lower part of the ablation area of Storglaciären, Sweden. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, **105**, 537 – 546.
- Hock R. and Noetzli C. (1997) Areal melt and discharge modelling of Storglaciären, Sweden. *Annals of Glaciology*, **24**, 211 – 216.
- Hodge S.M. (1976) Direct measurement of basal water pressures: a pilot study. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 205 – 218.
- Hogg I.G.G., Paren J.G. and Timmis R.J. (1982) Summer heat and ice balances on Hodges glacier, South Georgia, Falkland Islands dependencies. *Journal of Glaciology*, **28** (99), 221 – 238.
- Hoinkes H.C (1968) Glacier variation and weather. *Journal of Glaciology*, **7** (49), 3 – 19.
- Holdsworth G. and Bull C. (1970) The flow of cold ice: investigations on Meserve Glacier, Antarctica. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No. 86* (Symposium at Hanover, 1968 – Antarctic Glaciological Exploration (ISAGE)) 204 – 216.

REFERENCES

- Honeywell. (1998) Honeywell Sensing and Control – Thermal – Products – Industrial – Uni. [online]. Available from <http://content.honeywell.com/sensing/hss/thermal/product/industrial/uni.asp> [Accessed 13/10/2003].
- Hooke R le B. and Hudleston P.J. (1980) Ice fabrics in vertical flow plane, Barnes ice cap, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **25** (92), 195 – 214.
- Hooke R le B. (1973) Structure and flow in the margin of the Barnes ice cap, Baffin Island, N.W.T. Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **17** (75), 49 – 59.
- Hooke R le B. (1976) Near surface temperatures in the superimposed ice zone and lower part of the soaked zone of polar ice sheets. (Abstract) *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 302 – 304.
- Hooke R le B. (1981) Flow of polycrystalline ice in glaciers: comparison of theoretical predictions, laboratory data and field measurements. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*. **19** (4), 664 – 672.
- Hooke R le B., Calla P., Holmlund P., Nilsson M. and Stroeven A. (1989) A 3 year record of seasonal variations in surface velocity. Storglaciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **35**, 235 – 247.
- Hooke R le B., Miller S.B. and Kohler J. (1988) Character of the englacial and subglacial drainage system in the upper part of the ablation area of Storglaciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **34** (117), 228 – 231.
- Hooke R. le B. (1977) Basal temperatures in Polar Ice Sheets: A Qualitative Review. *Quaternary Research*, **7**, 1 – 13.
- Hooke R. le B. (1998). *Principles of Glacier Mechanics*. Prentice Hall, New Jersey, USA.
- Hooke R. le B., Dahlin B.H. and Kauper M.T. (1972) Creep of ice containing dispersed fine sand. *Journal of Glaciology*, **11**, 327 – 336.
- Hooke R. LeB. (1978). Temperature measurements on the Barnes Ice Cap, Baffin Island, Canada and on Sukkertoppen Iskappe, Greenland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **20** (83), 441 – 443.
- Hooke R. LeB. and Hanson B. (1986) Borehole deformation experiments, Barnes Ice Cap, Canada. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, **12** (3), 261 – 276.
- Hooke R. LeB. Pohjola V.A., Jansson P. and Kohler J. (1992) Intra-seasonal changes in deformation profiles revealed by borehole studies, Sorglaciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (130), 348 – 358.
- Hooke R. LeB., Alexander C.E. and Gustafson R.J. (1980) Temperature profiles in the Barnes Ice Cap, Baffin Island, Canada and heat flux from subglacial terrain. *Canadian Journal of Earth Science*, **17**, 1174 – 1188.
- Hooke R. LeB., Holmlund P. and Iverson N.R. (1987) Extrusion flow demonstrated by borehole deformation measurements over a riegel, Sorglaciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (113), 72- 78.
- Howat I.M., Joughin I., Tulaczyk S. and Gogineni S. (2005) Rapid retreat and acceleration of Helheim Glacier, East Greenland. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **32**, L22502, doi:10.1029/2005GL024737.
- Hubbard B. (2002) Direct measurement of basal motion at a hard-bedded temperate glacier: Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **48**, 1 – 8.
- Hubbard B. and Glasser N. (2005) *Field Techniques in Glaciology and Glacial Geomorphology*, Wiley, Chichester, England.
- Hubbard B. and Hubbard A. (1998) Bedrock surface roughness and the distribution of subglacially precipitated carbonate deposits: implications for formation at Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **23**, 261 – 270.

REFERENCES

- Hubbard B. and Sharp M. (1995) Basal ice facies and their formation in the western Alps. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **27** (4), 301 – 310.
- Hubbard B., Bayley O., Chandler D., Hubbard A., Murray T., Freeman H., Kulesa B., Rippin D., Mader H., and West J. (2006) Development of a spatially distributed ice flow model: Tsanfleuron Glacier, Switzerland. *Ice, News bulletin of the International Glaciological Society*, **1**, p 7.
- Hubbard B., Sharp M.J., Willis I.C., Nielsen M.K. and Smart C.C. (1995) Borehole water-level variations and structure of the subglacial hydrological system of Haut Glacier d'Arolla, Valais, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41**, 572 – 583.
- Hubbard B., Siegert M.J. and McCarroll D. (2000b) Spectral roughness of glaciated bedrock geomorphic surfaces: implications for glacier sliding. *Journal of Geophysical Research*. **105**(B9), 21,295 – 21,303.
- Hubbard B., Tison J.-L., Janssens L. and Spiro B. (2000a) Ice-core evidence of the thickness and character of clear facies basal ice: Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (152), 140 – 150.
- Hubbard B.P. and Nienow P. (1997) Alpine subglacial Hydrology. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, **16**, 939 – 955.
- Hubbard B.P., Hubbard A., Mader H.M., Tison J-L., Grust K. and Nienow P. (2003) Spatial variability in the water content and rheology of temperate glaciers: Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. *Annals of glaciology*, **37**, 1 – 6.
- Hubleby R.C. (1957) An analysis of the surface energy during the ablation season on Lemon Creek Glacier, Alaska. *Transactions of the American Geophysical Union*. **38** (1), 68 – 85.
- Hughes T.P. and Seligman G. (1939) The temperature melt water movement and density increase in the neve or an alpine glacier. *Monthly notices of the Royal Astronomical Society. Geophysical Supplement*, **4** (8), p. 632.
- Humphrey N. (1991) Estimating ice temperatures from short records in thermally disturbed boreholes. *Journal of Glaciology*, **37** (127), 414 – 419.
- Huybrechts P., Payne A.J. and the EISMINT Intercomparisson Group. (1996) The EISMINT benchmarks for testing ice sheet models. *Annals of Glaciology*, **23**, 1 – 12.
- Icefield Tools Corporation. 2005. [online] How it works MI-3 Digital Borehole Survey tools. Icefield Tools Corporation, Yukon, Canada. Available at www.icefieldtools.com [Accessed 20/10/2005].
- Iken A. (1972) Measurements of water pressure in moulins as part of a movement study of the White Glacier, Axel Heiberg Island, North West Territories, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **11**, 53 – 58.
- Iken A. and Bindschadler R.A. (1986) Combined measurements of the water pressure and surface velocity of Findelengletscher, Switzerland, conclusions about drainage system and sliding mechanism. *Journal of Glaciology*, **32** (110), 101 – 119.
- Iken A., Echelmeyer K., Harrison W. and Funk M. (1993) Mechanisms of fast flow in Jakobshavns Isbrae, West Greenland: Part 1. Measurements of Temperature and water level in deep boreholes. *Journal of Glaciology*, **39** (131), 15 – 25.
- Ingersoll L. R., O. J. Zobel, and Ingersoll. A. C. (1954). *Heat Conduction with Engineering, Geological and Other Applications*. McGraw-Hill. New York.
- IPCC (1990) *Climate change: The IPCC Scientific Assessment. Report of Working Group I of the IPCC* (J.T. Houghton, G.J. Jenkins and J.J. Ephraums (eds)). Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- IPCC (2007): Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the*

REFERENCES

- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Solomon, S., D. Qin, M. Manning, Z. Chen, M. Marquis, K.B. Averyt, M. Tignor and H.L. Miller (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.
- Isaksen K., Muhl D.V., Gubler H., Kohl T. and Sollid J.L. (2000) Ground surface temperature reconstruction based on data from a deep borehole in permafrost at Janssonhaugen, Svalbard. *Annals of Glaciology*, **31**, 287 – 294.
- Iverson N.R., Hanson B., Hooke R le B. and Jansson P. (1995) Flow mechanism of glaciers on soft beds. *Science*, **267**, 80 – 81.
- Iziomon M.G., Mayer H. and Matzarakis A. (2003) Downward atmospheric long wave irradiance under clear sky and cloudy skies: measurement and parameterization. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, **65**, 1107 – 1116.
- Jacka T.H. and Li J. (1994) The steady state crystal size of deforming ice. *Annals of Glaciology*, **20**, 13 – 18.
- Jacka T.H., Donoghue S., Li J., Budd W.F. and Anderson R.M. (2003) Laboratory studies of the flow rates of debris laden ice. *Annals of Glaciology*, **37**, 108 – 112.
- Jahn A. (1967) Some features of mass movement on Spitsbergen slopes. *Geografiska Annaler*, **49A**, 213 – 225.
- Janssens I. and Huybrechts P. (2000) The treatment of melt water retention in mass balance parameterisations of the Greenland Ice Sheet. *Annals of Glaciology*, **31**, 133 – 140.
- Jansson P. (1995) Water pressure and basal sliding on Stornglaciaren, Northern Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41**, 232 – 241.
- Jarvis G.T. and Clarke G.K.C. (1975) The thermal regime of Trapridge glacier and its relevance to glacier surging. *Journal of Glaciology*, **14** (71), 235 – 250.
- Jenssen D. and Radok U. (1963) Heat conduction in thinning ice sheets. *Journal of Glaciology*, **4** (34), 387 – 397.
- Johannesson T., Sigurosson O., Laumann T. and Kennet M. (1993) Degree day glacier mass balance modelling with applications to glaciers in Iceland and Norway. Reykjavik, Orkustofnun. *Nordic Hydrological Program Report 33*.
- Johannesson, T. Sigurdsson O. Laumann T. and Kennett. M. (1995) Degree-day mass balance modelling with applications to glaciers in Iceland, Norway and Greenland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41**, 345-358.
- Jolliffe I.T. and Stephenson D.B. (2003) *Forecast verification: a practitioner's guide in atmospheric science*. John Wiley and sons, 240 pp.
- Jones S.J. and Glen J.W. (1968) The mechanical properties of single crystals of ice at low temperatures. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No. 79*, 326 – 340.
- Jones S.J. and Glen J.W. (1969) The effect of dissolved impurities on the mechanical properties of ice crystals. *Philosophy Magazine*, **19** (157), 13 – 24.
- Jordan R. (1991) A one dimensional temperature model for a snow cover. *Special Report 91 – 16. U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory*, Hanover, New Hampshire.
- Joughin I., Abdalati W. and Fahnestock M. (2004) Large fluctuations in speed on Greenland's Jakobshavn Isbrae glacier. *Nature*, **423**, 608 – 610.
- Kamb B. (1987) Glacier surge mechanism based on linked cavity configuration of the basal water conduit system. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **92** (B9), 9083 – 9100.
- Kamb B. and Engelhardt H. (1987) Waves of accelerated motion in a glacier approaching surge: the mini surges of Variegated Glacier, Alaska, U.S.A. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (113), 27 – 46.

REFERENCES

- Kamb B., Raymond C.F., Harrison W.D., Engelhardt H., Echelmeyer K.A., Humphrey N., Brugman M.M. and Pfeffer T. (1985) Glacier surge mechanisms: 1982 – 83 surge of Variegated Glacier, Alaska. *Science*, **227**, 469 – 479.
- Keller T., Pielmeier C., Rixen C., Gadiant F., Goustaafsson D. and Stahli M. (2004) Impact of artificial snow and ski – slope grooming on snow pack properties and soil thermal regime in a sub alpine ski area. *Annals of Glaciology*, **38**, 314 – 318.
- Klok E.J. and Oerlemans J. (2002): Model study of the spatial distribution of the energy and mass balance of Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **48** (163), 505 – 518.
- Klok E.J, Greuell W. and Oerlemans J. (2003) Temporal and spatial variation of the surface albedo of Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland, as derived from 12 Landsat images. *Journal of Glaciology*, **49** (167) 491 – 503.
- Klok E.J., Nolan M. and Van den Broeke M.R. (2005) Analysis of meteorological data and the surface energy balance of McCall Glacier, Alaska, USA. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (174), 451 – 461.
- Koenig U. and Abegg B. (1997) Impacts of climate change on winter tourism in the Swiss Alps. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, **5** (1), 46 – 58.
- Kondo J. and Yamazawa H. (1986) Measurement of snow surface emissivity. *Boundary layer meteorology*, **34** (4), 415 – 416.
- Konya K., Mataumoto T. and Naruse R. (2004) Surface heat balance and spatially distributed ablation modelling at Koryto Glacier, Kamchatka peninsular, Russia. *Geografiska Annaler*, **86** A, 337 – 348.
- Konzelmann T. and Braithwaite R.J. (1995) Variations of ablation, albedo and energy balance at the margin of the Greenland ice sheet, Kronprins Christian Land, eastern north Greenland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **41** (137), 174 – 182.
- Kuhn M. (1970) On the computation of heat transfer coefficients from energy balance gradients on a glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **22** (87), 263 – 272.
- Kuhn M. (1981) Die Reaktion der Schneegrenze auf Kilmaschwankungen. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **16** (2), 241 – 254.
- Kuhn M. (1987) Micro meteorological conditions for snow melt. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (113), 24 – 24.
- Kulesa B. (2000) Geophysical borehole investigations of subglacial drainage conditions at Haut Glacier d'Arolla, Switzerland. *PhD Thesis*, University of Wales, Aberystwyth, UK.
- Kulesa B., Murray T. and Rippin D. (2006) Active seismoelectric exploration of glaciers. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **33** (L07503), doi: 1029/2006GL025758.
- Kuon L.G. and Jonas J.J. (1973) Effect of strain rate and temperature on the microstructure of polycrystalline ice. In Whalley E., Jones S.J. and Gold L.W. (eds) *Physics and Chemistry of ice*. Royal Society of Canada, Ottawa.
- Kyle H.L., Ardanuy P.E. and Hurley E.J. (1985) The status of the Nimbus-7 Earth – Radiation – Budget data set. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, **66**, 1378 – 1388.
- La Chapelle E.R. (1959) Annual mass and energy balance on the blue glacier. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **64** (4), 443 – 449.
- La Chapelle E.R. (1992), *Field Guide to Snow Crystals*. International Glaciological Society, Cambridge.
- Landauer J.K. (1957) Creep of snow under combined stress. *Snow Ice and permafrost Research Establishment, Corps of Engineers, U.S. Army, Research Report*, **33**.
- Lang H., Schadler B. and Davidson G. (1979) Hydrological investigations on the Ewigschneefeld – Gr. Aletschglescher: ablation, melt water infiltration, water table

REFERENCES

- in the firn, heat balance. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **15** (2), 209 – 218.
- Lange M.A. (1985) Measurements of thermal parameters in Antarctic snow and firn. *Annals of Glaciology*, **6**, 100 – 104.
- Lange M.A. and Ahrens T.J. (1983) The dynamic tensile strength of ice and ice silicate mixtures. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **88** (B2), 1197 – 1208.
- Langham E.J. (1974a) Phase equilibria of Veins in Polycrystalline Ice. *Canadian Journal of Earth Science*, **11**, 1280 – 1287.
- Langham E.J. (1974b) The occurrence and movement of liquid water in the snow pack . In *Advanced Concepts and Techniques in the Study of Snow and Ice Resources*. Santeford H.S. and Smith J.L. (eds) Washington, D.C., National Academy of Sciences, 67 – 75.
- Langham E.J. (1981) Physics and properties of snow cover. In *Handbook of Snow*, Gray D.M. and Male D.H. (eds) Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Laumann T. and Reeh N. (1993) Sensitivity to climate change of the mass balance of glaciers in southern Norway. *Journal of Glaciology*, **39** (133), 656 – 665.
- Lemmens M., Lorrain R. and Haren J. (1983) Isotopic composition of ice and subglacially precipitated calcite in an Alpine area. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **18** (2), 151 – 29.
- Li J. and Jacka T.H. (1999) Crystal growth rates in firn and shallow ice at high accumulation sites. *Annals of Glaciology*, **29**, 169 -175.
- List R.J. (1968) *Smithsonian Meteorological Tables*. 6th Revised Edition. The Smithsonian Institute, Washington D.C.
- Liston G.E. (1995) Local advection of momentum, heat and moisture, during the melt of patchy snow covers. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **34**, 1705 – 1715.
- Liston G.E. and Elder K. (2006a) A meteorological distribution system for high resolution terrestrial modelling (MicroMet). *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, **7**, 217 – 234.
- Liston G.E. and Elder K. (2006b) A distributed snow-evolution modelling system (SnowModel). *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, **7** (6), 1259 – 1276.
- Liston G.E., Winther J.G. Bruland O., Elvehoy H. and Sand K. (1999) Below surface ice melt on the coastal Antarctic Ice sheet. *Journal of Glaciology*, **45**, 273 – 385.
- Lliboutry L. (1983). Modifications to the theory of interglacial waterways for the case of subglacial ones. *Journal of Glaciology*, **29** (102), 216 – 226.
- Lliboutry L. (1976) Physical processes in temperate glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 151 – 158.
- Lliboutry L. (1996) Temperate ice permeability, stability of water veins and percolation of internal melt water. *Journal of Glaciology*, **42**, 201 – 211.
- Lliboutry L. (2002) Velocities, strain rates, stresses, crevassing and faulting on Glacier de Saint – Sorlin, French Alps, 1957 – 76. *Journal of Glaciology*, **48** (160), 125 – 141.
- Lliboutry L. (1971) Permeability, brine content and temperature of temperate ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **10** (58), 15 – 29.
- Lliboutry L. and Duval P. (1985) Various isotropic and anisotropic ices found in glaciers and polar ice caps and their corresponding rheologies. *Annales Geographicae* **3** (2), 207 – 224.
- Lloyd C.R., Harding R.J., Friberg T. and Aurela M. (2001) Surface fluxes of heat and water vapour from sites in the European Arctic. *Theoretical Applied Climatology*, **70**, 19 – 33.

REFERENCES

- Loewe F. (1966) The temperature of the Sukkertoppen ice cap. *Journal of Glaciology*, **6** (43), 179 (letter).
- Luce C.H. and Tarboton D.G. (2001) A modified force – restore approach to modelling snow surface heat fluxes. Paper presented at 69th Annual Meeting of the Western Snow Conference, 2001.
- Luthi M.P. and Funk M. (2001) Modelling heat flow in a cold, high altitude glacier: interpretation of measurements from Colle Gnifetti, Swiss Alps. *Journal of Glaciology*, **47** (157), 314 – 324.
- Luthje M., Pedersen L.T., Reeh N. and Greuell W. (2006) Modelling the evolution of supraglacial lakes on the West Greenland ice sheet margin. *Journal of Glaciology*, **52**, **179**, 608 – 618.
- Mader H.M. (1992a) Observations of the water vein system in polycrystalline ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (130), 333 – 347.
- Mader H.M. (1992b) The thermal behavior of the water vein system in polycrystalline ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (130), 359 – 374.
- Mair D., Willis I.C., Fischer U.H., Hubbard B., Nienow P. and Hubbard A. (2003) Hydrological controls on patterns of surface, internal and basal motion during three “spring events”: Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **167**, 555 – 567.
- Mair D., Nienow P., Willis I.C. and Sharp M. (2001) Spatial patterns of Glacier motion during a high velocity event: Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **47**, (156), 9 – 20.
- Mair D., Sharp M. and Willis I.C. (2002a) Evidence for basal cavity opening from analysis of surface uplift during a high-velocity event: Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **48** (161), 208 – 216.
- Mair D., Nienow P., Sharp M., Wohlleben T. and Willis I. (2002b) Influence of subglacial drainage system evolution on glacier surface motion: Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **107** (B8), 10.1029/2001JB000514.
- Maisch M. (1998) *Die Gletscher der Schweizer Alpen*. Vdf Publishers, Zurich, 387 pp.
- Makinson K. (2003) Future hot water drilling on Rutford Ice Stream 2004/05. *FRISP Report No. 14*.
- Male D.H. (1980) The seasonal snow cover. In Colbeck S.C. (ed) *Dynamics of snow and ice masses*. Academic Press, New York, pp 305 – 396.
- Male D.H. and Granger R.J. (1981) Snow surface energy exchange. *Water Resources Research*, **17** (3), 609 – 627.
- Male D.H. and Gray D.M. (1981) Snowcover ablation and runoff. In: Gray, D.M. and Male, D.H., Editors, 1981. *Handbook of Snow*, Pergamon Press, Toronto, Ontario.
- Marie R. (1977) Les karsts haut-alpin de Plate du Haut – Giffre et de Suisse Occidentale. *Revue de géographie alpine*. **65**, 403 – 425.
- Marinucci M.R., Giorgi F., Beniston M., Wild M., Tschuck P. and Bernasconi A. (1995) High resolution simulations of January and July climate over the Western Alpine region with a nested regional modelling system. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, **51**, 119 – 138.
- Marks D. and Dozier J. (1992) Climate and energy exchange at the snow surface in the alpine region of the Sierra Nevada 2. Snow cover energy balance. *Water Resources Research*. **28** (11), 3043 – 3054.
- Marmo B.A., Blackford J.R. and Jeffree C.E. (2005) Ice friction, wear features and their dependence on sliding velocity and temperature. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (174), 391 – 398.

REFERENCES

- Marsh P. and Woo M. (1984) Wetting front advance and freezing of melt water within a snow cover 1. Observations in the Canadian Arctic. *Water Resources Research*, **20**, 1853 – 1864.
- Martin P.J. and Sanderson T.J.O. (1980) Morphology and dynamics of ice rises. *Journal of Glaciology*, **25** (91), 33 – 45.
- Martin S. (1975) Wind regimes and heat exchange on Glacier de Saint – Sorlin. *Journal of Glaciology*, **17**, 70), 91 – 105.
- Mathews W. H. (1964) Water pressure under a glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **5**, 235 – 240.
- Mattson L.E. and Gardner J.S. (1989) Energy exchanges and ablation rates on the debris covered Rakhoit Glacier, Pakistan. *Zeitschrift für Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*. **25** (1), 17 – 32.
- McClung D. and Schaerer P. (1993) *The Avalanche Handbook*. Seattle, The Mountaineers.
- Meier M.F., Tangborn W.V., Mayo L.R. and Post A. (1971) Combined ice and water balances of Gulkana and Wolverine Glaciers, Alaska and South Cascade Glacier, Washington, 1965 and 1966 hydrologic years. *US Geological Survey Professional Paper*, **715** – A, 23p.
- Mellor M. (1977) Engineering properties of snow. *Journal of Glaciology*, **19** (81), 15 – 66.
- Mellor M. and Smith J.H. (1967) Creep of ice and snow, in *Physics of snow and ice: Proceedings of International Conference on Low Temperature Science 1966*, **1** (2), 843 – 845. Institute of Low Temperature Science, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan, 1967.
- Mellor M. and Testa R. (1969) Effect of temperature on the creep of ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **8** (52), 131 – 145.
- Meteosuisse.ch (2006) (translated from German) Aktuelles zum Wettergeschehen. Published 05/07/2006, http://www.meteosuisse.ch/web/en/weather/weather_news.htm [Accessed 21/05/07].
- Mihalcea C., Mayer C., Diolaiuti G., Lambrecht A., Smiraglia C. and Tartari G. (2006) Ice ablation and meteorological conditions on the debris covered area of Baltoro glacier, Karakoram, Pakistan. *Annals of Glaciology*, **43**, 292 – 300.
- Miller M.M. (1954) Glaciotermal Studies on the Taku Glacier Southeastern Alaska. *Publication no 39 de l'Association Internationale d' Hydrologie*, IUGG (Assemblée general de Rome, tome IV), Extrait pp 309 – 327.
- Mittaz C. Hoelzle M. and Haeberli W. (2000) First results and interpretation of energy – flux measurements over Alpine permafrost. *Annals of Glaciology*. **31**, 275 – 280.
- Moore R.D. and Owens I.F. (1984) Controls on advective snowmelt in a maritime alpine basin. *Journal of Climatology and Applied Meteorology*, **23**, 135 – 142.
- Morassuti M.P. and LeDrew E.F. (1996) Albedo and depth of melt ponds on sea ice. *International Journal of Climatology*, **16** (7), 817 – 838.
- Morris E.M., Bader H.P. and Weilenmann P. (1997) Modelling temperature variations in polar snow using Daisy. *Journal of Glaciology*, **43** (143), 180 – 191.
- Motoyama H., Kobayashi D. and Kojima K. (1986) Effect of melting at the snow – ground interface on the runoff during winter. *Japanese Journal of Limnology*, **47**, 165 – 176.
- Muller F. and Keeler C.M. (1969) Errors in short term ablation measurements on melting ice surfaces. *Journal of Glaciology*, **8** (52), 91 – 105.
- Muller F. (1976) On the thermal regimen of a high Arctic valley glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16** (74), 119 – 133.

REFERENCES

- Mulvaney R., Wolff E.W. and Oates K. (1988) Sulphuric acid at grain boundaries in Antarctic ice. *Nature*, **331**, 247 – 249.
- Munro D.S. (1989) Surface roughness and bulk heat transfer on a glacier: comparison with eddy correlation. *Journal of Glaciology*, **35** (121), 343 – 348.
- Munro D.S. (1990) Comparison of melt energy computations and ablatometer measurements on melting snow and ice. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **22** (2), 153 – 162.
- Munro D.S. (1991) A surface energy exchange model of glacier melt and net mass balance. *International Journal of Climatology*, **11** (6), 689 – 700.
- Munro D.S. and Young G.J. (1982) An operational net shortwave radiation model for glacier basins. *Water Resources Research*. **18** (2), 220 – 230.
- Munro D.S. and Davies J.A. (1977) An experimental study of the glacier boundary layer over melting ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **18** (80), 425 – 436.
- Murakami S. and Maeno N. (1989) [Thermal conductivity of snow and snow / metal mixtures.] *Low Temperature Science, Series A*, **48**, 13 – 25. [In Japanese with English summary].
- Murray T. and Clarke G.K.C. (1995) Black box modelling of the subglacial water system. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **100**, 10231 – 10245.
- Murray T., Kulesa B., West J., Rippin D., Endres T.J., Mader H., Hubbard B., and Bayley O. (2006) Constraining ice water contents using radar velocity and attenuation measurements. *Ice, News bulletin of the International Glaciological Society*, **1**, p 8.
- Murray T., Smart G.W., Fry M., Gamble N.H. and Crabtree M.D. (2000) Englacial water distribution in a temperate glacier from surface and borehole radar velocity analysis. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (154), 389 – 398.
- Nakamura T. and Jones S.J. (1970) Softening effect of dissolved hydrogen chloride in ice crystals. *Scr. Metall.* **4** (2), 123 – 126.
- Nakamura T. and Jones S.J. (1973) Mechanical properties of impure ice crystals. In Whalley E., Jones S.J. and Gold L.W. (eds) *Physics and Chemistry of ice*. Ottawa, Ontario, Royal Society of Canada, 365 – 369.
- Nakicenovic, N. and Swart, R., (Eds.) 2000. Emissions Scenarios. 2000, *Special Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* Cambridge University Press, UK. pp. 570.
- Nayar H.S., Lenel F.V. and Ansell G.S. (1971) Creep of dispersions of ultra – fine amorphous silica. *Journal of Applied Physics*, **42** (10) 3786 – 3789.
- Nelson F.E., Hinkel K.M., Shiklomanov N.I., Mueller G.R., Miller L.L. and Walker D.K. (1998) Active layer thickness in north central Alaska: Systematic sampling, scale and spatial autocorrelation. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **103** (D22), 28,963 – 28,973.
- news.search.ch. (2005) (translated from French) Les Diablerets: phase urgente terminee. News.search.ch, Published 26/06/2005, <http://news.search.ch/inland/2005-06-26/les-diablerets-phase-urgente-terminee.fr.html> [accessed 15/05/07].
- Nyberg R. (1989) Observations of slush flows and geomorphological effects in the Swedish mountain area. *Geografiska Annaler*, **71A**, (3-4), 185 – 198.
- Nye J.F. (1953) The flow law of ice from measurements in glacier tunnels, laboratory experiments, and the Jungfraufirn borehole experiment. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A*, **219** (1139), 477 – 489.
- Nye J.F. (1973) Water at the bed of a glacier. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No.95* (Symposium at Cambridge 1969 – Hydrology of glaciers), 189 – 194.

REFERENCES

- Nye J.F. and Frank F.C. (1973) Hydrology of the intergranular veins in a temperate glacier. Union Geodesique et Geophysique Internationale, Association Internationale d'Hydrologie Scientifique. Commission de Neiges et Glaces. Symposium on the Hydrology of Glaciers, Cambridge, 7 – 13 September, 1969, p.157 – 161.
- Obleitner F. (1994). Climatological features of glacier and valley winds at the Hintereisferner (O'tztal Alps Austria), *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, **49**, 225– 239.
- Oerlamans J. and Klok E.J.L. (2004) Effect of summer snowfall on glacier mass balance. *Annals of Glaciology*, **38**, 97 – 100.
- Oerlemans J. (1992) Climate sensitivity of glaciers in southern Norway: application of an energy balance model to Nigardsbreen, Hellstugubreen and Alftobreen. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (129), 223 – 232.
- Oerlemans J. (2000) Analysis of a 3 year meteorological record from the ablation zone of Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland: energy and mass balance. *Journal of Glaciology*, **46**, 571 – 579.
- Oerlemans J. (1993) A model for the surface balance of ice masses: Part 1. Alpine glaciers. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **27 / 28**, 63 – 83.
- Oerlemans J. and Fortuin P.F. (1992) Sensitivity of glaciers and small ice caps to greenhouse warming. *Science*, **258** (5079), 115 – 117.
- Oerlemans J. and Grisogono B. (2002) Glacier winds and parameterization of the related surface heat fluxes. *Tellus Series A*, **54** (5), 440 – 452.
- Oerlemans J. and Klok E.J.L. (2002) Energy balance of a glacier surface: Analysis of automatic weather station data from the Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland. *Arctic, Antarctic and Alpine Research*, **34**, 477 – 485.
- Oerlemans J. and Knap W.H. (1998). A 1 year record of global radiation and albedo in the ablation zone of Morteratschgletscher, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **44** (147), 231 – 238.
- Oerlemans J. unpublished “The microclimate of glaciers – I”.
- Oerlemans J. unpublished “The microclimate of glaciers – II”.
- Oerlemans J., Bjornsson H., Kuhn M., Obleitner F., Plasson F., Smeets C.J.P.P., Vugts H.F. and De Wolde J. (1999) Glacio-meteorological investigations on Vatnajokull, Iceland, Summer 1996: An overview. *Boundary Layer Meteorology*, **92** (1), 3 – 26.
- Oerter H. and Moser H. (1982) Water storage and drainage within the firm of a temperate glacier (Vernagferner, Oetztal Alps, Austria). International Association of Hydrological Sciences Publication 138 (Symposium at Exeter 1982 – Hydrological Aspects of Alpine and High Mountain Areas), 71 – 81.
- Oerter H., Baker D., Moser H. and Reinwrath O. (1981) Glacial hydrological investigations at the Vernagferner glacier as a basis for a discharge model. *Nordic Hydrology*, **12** (4 – 5), 335 – 348.
- Oeschger H., Schotterer U., Stauffer B., Haeberli W. and Rothlisberger H. (1978). First results from Alpine core drilling projects. *Zeitschrift fur Gletscherkunde und Glazialgeologie*, **13**, 193 – 208.
- Ohmura A. (1980) Climate and energy balance on Arctic tundra, Axel Heiberg Island, Canadian Arctic Archipelago, spring and summer 1969, 1970 and 1972. *PhD thesis*. Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich.
- Ohmura A. (1981) Climate and Energy Balance on Arctic Tundra, Axel Heiberg Island, Canadian Arctic Archipelago. *Zürcher Geographische Schriften*, No.3, Fachvereine Verlag, Zurich, 448 p.

REFERENCES

- Ohmura A. (1984) Comparative energy balance study for Arctic tundra, sea surface, glaciers and boreal forests. *Geographical Journal*, **8** (3), 221 – 228.
- Ohmura A. (2004) Cryosphere during the twentieth century, in; The State of the Planet: Frontiers and Challenges in Geophysics. eds, Sparks R. S. J. and Hawkesworth C. J. *Geophysical Monograph* **150**, International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics, Boulder, CO and American Geophysical Union, Washington, DC, 239 – 257.
- Oke T.R. (1987) *Boundary Layer Climates*. Routledge. London New York, Second edition. 435 p.
- Onesti L.J. (1985) Meteorological conditions that initiate slush flows in the Central Brooks Range, Alaska. *Annals of Glaciology*, **6**, 23 – 25.
- Ostin R. and Anderson S. (1991) Frost growth parameters in a forced air stream. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, **34** (4-5), 1009 – 1017.
- Palosuo E. (1987) A study of snow and ice temperatures on Vestfonna, Svalbard, 1956, 1957 and 1958. *Geografiska Annaler*, **69 A** (3 – 4), 431 – 437.
- Parry V., Nienow P., Mair D., Scott J., Hubbard B., Steffen K. and Wingham D. (2007) Investigations of meltwater refreezing and density variations in the snowpack and firn within the percolation zone of the Greenland ice sheet. *Annals of Glaciology*, **46**, 61 – 68.
- Paterson W.S.B. (1994) *The Physics of Glaciers*. Third ed. Butterworth Heinmann. Oxford.
- Paterson W.S.B. (1968) A temperature profile through the Meighen Ice cap, Arctic Canada. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No. 79*, 440 – 449.
- Paterson W.S.B. (1971) Temperature measurements in the Athabasca glacier, Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **10** (60), 339 – 349.
- Paterson W.S.B. (1972) Temperature distribution in the upper layers of the ablation area of Athabasca Glacier, Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **11**(61), 31 – 41.
- Paterson W.S.B. (1977) Secondary and tertiary creep of glacier ice as measured by borehole closure rates. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*, **15** (1), 47 – 55.
- Paterson W.S.B. and Savage J.C. (1963) Measurements on Athabasca glacier relating to the flow law of ice. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **68** (15), 4537 – 4543.
- Payne A.J. (1999) Thermo mechanical model of ice flow in West Antarctica. *Climate Dynamics*, **15**, 115 – 125.
- Payne A.J. and Baldwin D.J. (2000) Analysis of ice flow instabilities identified in the EISMINT intercomparison exercise. *Annals of Glaciology*, **30**, 204 – 219.
- Payne A.J. and Donglemans P.W. (1997) Self organisation in the thermomechanical flow of ice sheets. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **102**, (B6), 12,219 – 12,233.
- Payne, A. J., P. Huybrechts, Abe-Ouchi A., Calov R., Fastook J.L., Greve R., Marshall S.J., Marsiat I., Ritz C., Tarasov L. and Thomassen M.P.A. (2000). "Results from the EISMINT model intercomparison: the effects of thermo mechanical coupling." *Journal of Glaciology*, **46** (153): 227 – 234.
- Pellicciotti F., Brock B., Strasser U., Burlando P., Funk M. and Corripio J. (2005) An enhanced temperature-index glacier melt model including the shortwave radiation balance: development and testing for Haut Glacier d’Arolla, Switzerland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (175), 573 – 587.
- Perovich D.K., Tucker W.B. and Ligett K.A. (2002) Aerial observations of the evolution of ice surface conditions during summer. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **107** (C10), 8048, 10.1029/2000JC000449.
- Perutz M.F. (1950) Direct measurement of the velocity distribution in a vertical profile through a glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **1** (7), 382 – 383.

REFERENCES

- Petrovich D.K. (2007) Light reflection and transmission by a temperate snow cover. *Journal of Glaciology*, **53**, 118, 201 – 210.
- Pettersson R., Jansson P. and Holmund P. (2003) Cold surface layer thinning on Storgläciaren, Sweden, observed by repeat ground penetrating radar surveys. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **108 (F1)**, 6004, doi:10.1029/2003JF000024.
- Pettersson R., Jansson P., Huwald H. and Blatter H. (2007) Spatial pattern and stability of the cold surface layer of Storgläciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **53** (180), 99 – 109.
- Pfeffer W.T. and Humphrey N.F. (1996) Determination of timing and location of water movement and ice layer formation by temperature measurements in subfreezing snow. *Journal of Glaciology*, **42** (141), 292 – 304.
- Philips M., Broccard A., Margreth S. and Thalparpan P. (2002) Stability of an artificially modified scree slope in alpine permafrost. In *Interdisciplinary Mountain Research*. Bottarin R. and Tappeiner U. (eds) Europäische Akademie, Bozen, Fachbereich Alpine Umwelt. Blackwell - Verlag.
- Pings C.J. (1963) Heat flux distribution near a crevasse. *Journal of Glaciology*, **3** (34), 461 – 465.
- Plummer W.T. (1969) Infrasonic resonances in natural underground cavities. *The Journal of the Acoustic Society of America*, **46** (5), 1074 – 1080.
- Pluss C. and Mazzoni R. (1994) The role of turbulent heat fluxes in the energy balance of high alpine snow cover. *Nordic Hydrology*. **25** (1/2), 25 – 38.
- Poggi A. (1977) Heat balance in the ablation area of Ampere Glacier (Kerguelen Islands). *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **16**, 48 – 55.
- Pohjola V.A. and Hedfors J. (2003) Studying the effects of strain heating on glacial flow within outlet glaciers from Heimefrontfjella Range, Dronning Maud Land, Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, **37**, 134 – 142.
- Pohjola V.A. (1994) TV – Video observations of englacial voids in Storgläciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **40**, 231 – 240.
- Potts W.T.W., Oates K., Wolff E.W. and Mulvaney R. (1992) The distributions of impurities in Antarctic ice. *Scanning Microscopy*, **6** (1), 295 – 299.
- Prensky S. (1992) Temperature measurements in boreholes: An overview of Engineering and Scientific applications. *The Log Analyst*, **33** (3), 313 – 333.
- Price A.G. (1986) Modelling of snowmelt rates in a deciduous forest. In Seasonal Snow covers: Physics, Chemistry, Hydrology Symposium, Les Arcs France, 13 – 25 July 1986, Jones HG, Orville-Thomas WJ (eds). *NATO ASI Series C, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, **211**, 151 – 165.
- Price A.G. and Dunne T. (1976) Energy balance computations of snowmelt in a Sub arctic area. *Water Resources Research*. **12** (4), 686 – 694.
- Price P.B., Nagornov O.V., Bay R., Chirkin D., He Y., Miocinovic P., Richards A., Woschnagg K., Koci B. and Zagorodnov V. (2002) Temperature profile for glacial ice at the South Pole: implications for life in a nearby subglacial lake. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, **99** (12), 7844 – 7847.
- Profansky H.A. and Dutton J.A. (1984) *Atmospheric turbulence: models and methods for engineering applications*. New York, John Wiley.
- Prowse T.D. and Owens I.F. (1982) Energy balance over melting snow, Craieburn Range, New Zealand. *Journal of Hydrology (NZ)*, **21** (2), 133 – 147.
- Rabus B.T. and Echelmeyer K.A. (2002) Increase of 10 m ice temperature: climate warming or glacier thinning? *Journal of Glaciology*, **48** (161), 279 – 286.

REFERENCES

- Rao U.M. and Jessop A.M. (1975) A comparison of the thermal characteristics of shields. *Canadian Journal of Earth Science*, **12**, 347 – 360.
- Rapp A. (1960) Recent development of mountain slopes in Karkevagge and surroundings, Northern Scandinavia. *Geografiska Annaler*, **42**, 71 – 200.
- Raraty L.E. and Tabor D. (1958) The adhesion and strength properties of ice. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series A*, **245**, 184 – 201.
- Raymond C.F. (1971) Flow in a transverse section of Athabasca glacier, Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **10** (58), 55 – 84.
- Raymond C.F. (1976) Some thermal effects of bubbles in temperate glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **16**, 159 – 171.
- Raymond C.F. and Harrison W.D. (1975) Some observations on the behavior of the liquid and gas phases in temperate glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **14** (71), 213 – 233.
- Reeh N. (1991) Parameterisation of melt water and surface temperature on the Greenland Ice Sheet. *Polarforschung*, **5913**, 113 – 128.
- Reijmer C. and Oerlemans J. (2002) Temporal and spatial variability of the surface energy balance in Dronning Maud Land, East Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research – Atmospheres*, **107** (D24). Article number 4759.
- Reijmer C., Greuell W. and Oerlemans J. (1999) The annual cycle of meteorological variables and the surface energy balance on Berkner Island, Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, **29**, 49 – 54.
- Renaud A. (1949) A contribution to the study of the glacier grain. *Journal of Glaciology*, **1** (6), 320 – 324.
- Rignot E. and Kanagaratnam P. (2006) Changes in the velocity structure of the Greenland Ice Sheet. *Science*, **311**, 986 – 990.
- Rignot E., Casassa G., Gogineni S., Kanagaratnam P., Krabil W., Pritchard H., Rivera A., Thomas R., Turner J. and Vaugan D. (2005) Recent ice losses from the Flemming and other glaciers, Wordie Bay, West Antarctic Peninsula. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **32** (7), 1 – 4.
- Rignot E., Casassa G., Gogineni S., Krabil W., Rivera A. and Thomas R. (2004) Accelerated ice discharge from the Antarctic Peninsular following the collapse of Larsen B ice shelf. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **31** (18), L18401, doi:10.1029/2004GL020697.
- Rist M.A. and Murrell S.A.F. (1994) Ice triaxial deformation and fracture. *Journal of Glaciology*, **40** (135), 305 – 318.
- Robin G de Q. (1955) Ice movement and temperature distribution in glaciers and ice sheets. *Journal of Glaciology*, **2**, 523 – 532.
- Robin G de Q. (1969) Initiation of glacier surges. *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, **6**, 919 – 928.
- Robin G. de Q. (1958) Glaciology III. Seismic shooting and related investigations. *Norwegian – British – Swedish Antarctic Expedition, 1949 – 52. Scientific Results*, **4**, A, B, C.
- Rohrer M. (1989) Determination of the transition air temperature from snow to rain and intensity of precipitation. *Instruments and observing methods. Geneva, World Meteorological Organization. Technical Report* **48**, 475 – 482.
- Rotach M., Wild M., Tschuch P., Beniston M. and Marinucci M.R. (1997) A double CO₂ experiment over the Alpine region with a nested GCM-LAM modelling approach. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, **57**, 209 – 227.
- Rothlisberger H. (1972) Water pressure in intra- and subglacial channels. *Journal of Glaciology*, **11** (62), 177 – 203.

REFERENCES

- Rothlisberger K. and Lang H. (1987) Glacial Hydrology. In *Glacio-fluvial Sediment Transfer: an alpine perspective*. Gurnell A.M and Clarke M.J (eds). Wiley: Chichester.
- Russell – Head D.S. and Budd W.F. (1979) Ice – sheet flow properties derived from borehole shear measurements combined with ice – core studies. *Journal of Glaciology*, **24** (90), 117 – 130.
- Salzmann N. (2006) The use of results from regional climate models for large scale permafrost modelling in complex high mountain topography. *PhD Thesis*, University of Zurich.
- Sanderson T.J.O. (1978) Thermal stresses near the surface of a glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **20** (83), 257 – 283.
- Sass J.H., Lachenbruch A.H., Munroe R.J., Greenr G.W. and Moses T.H. (1979) Heat flow in the Western United States. *Journal of Geophysical Research*. **76**, 6376 – 6413.
- Sass J.H., Nielsen B.L., Wollenberg H.A. and Munroe R.J. (1972) Heat flow and surface radioactivity at two sites in south Greenland. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **77** (32), 6435 – 6444.
- Savage J.C. and Paterson W.S.B. (1963) Borehole measurements in the Athabasca glacier. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **68** (15), 4521 – 4536.
- Savage J.C. and Paterson W.S.B. (1965) Additional borehole measurements in the Athabasca Glacier. *Journal of Geophysical Research*. **70** (14), 3511 – 3513.
- Scambos T., Bohlander J., Shuman C. and Skvarca P. (2004) Glacier acceleration and thinning after ice shelf collapse in the Larsen B embayment, Antarctica. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **31**, L18401, doi:10.1029/2004GL020670.
- Schneider T. (1999) Water movement in the firm of Storglaciaren, Sweden. *Journal of Glaciology*, **45** (150), 268 – 294.
- Schwerdtfeger P. (1963) Theoretical derivation of the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of snow. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No. 61*. General Assembly of Berkeley, 1963 – Snow and Ice. 75 – 81.
- Schytt V. (1964) Scientific rules of the Swedish Glaciological expedition to Nordaustlandet, Spitsbergen, 1957 and 1958. *Geografiska Annaler*, **46** (3), 243 – 281.
- Schytt V. (1968) Some comments on glacier surges in Eastern Svalbard. *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, **6** (4 (2)), 867 – 873.
- Schytt V. (1958) The inner structure of the ice shelf at Maudheim as shown by core drilling. Norwegian- British-Swedish Antarctic Expedition, 1949 – 52. *Scientific Results 4, Glaciology 2*. *Norsk Polarinstittut*, Oslo, 115 – 151.
- Sclatter J.G., Jaupart C. and Galson D. (1980) The heat flow through oceanic and continental crust and heat loss of the earth. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*, **18** (1), 269 – 311.
- Semadeni-Davies A., Marechal D., Bruland O., Kodama Y. and Sand K. (2004) Estimating latent heat over a melting arctic snow cover. *Nordic Hydrology*, **35** (3), 175 – 190.
- Serreze M.C. and Bradley R.S. (1987) Radiation and cloud observations on a High Arctic plateau ice cap. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (114), 162 – 168.
- Sharp M. (1991) Hydrological inferences from melt water quality data: the unfulfilled potential. Proceedings of the British Hydrological Society, Third National Hydrological Symposium, Southampton, 16 – 18 September, 5.1 – 5.8.

REFERENCES

- Sharp M.J., Gemmell J.C. and Tison J.-L. (1989) Structure and stability of the former subglacial drainage system of Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, **14**, 119 – 134.
- Sharp M.J., Tison J.-L. and Fierens G. (1990) Geochemistry of subglacial calcites: implications for the hydrology of the basal water film. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **22** (2), 141 – 152.
- Sharp M.J., Willis I.C., Hubbard B., Nielsen M., Brown G.H., Tranter M. and Smart C.C. (1993) Water storage, drainage evolution and water quality in alpine glacial environments. *Interim Report on NERC Grant No. GR3/8114*.
- Sharp R.P. (1951) Thermal regimen of firn on upper Seward glacier, Yukon territory, Canada. *Journal of Glaciology*, **1** (9), 476 – 487.
- Sharp R.P. (1952) Melt water behavior in firn on the upper Seward Glacier, St. Elias Mountains, Canada. Union Geodesique et Geophysique Internationale. Association Internationale d'Hydrologie Scientifique. Assemblee generale de Bruxelles, 1951, Tom 1. pp. 246 – 253.
- Sharp R.P. (1953) Deformation of borehole in Malaspina Glacier, Alaska. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, **64** (1), 97 – 100.
- Shepherd A., Wingham D. and Rignot E. (2004) Warm ocean is eroding West Antarctic Ice Sheet. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **31** (23), 1 – 4.
- Shoji H. and Langway C.C. (1987) Flow parameters of the Dye 3, Greenland, deep ice core. *Annals of Glaciology*, **10**, 146 – 150.
- Shreve R.L. and Sharp R.P. (1970) Internal deformation and thermal anomalies in lower Blue glacier, Mount Olympus, Washington, U.S.A. *Journal of Glaciology*, **9** (55), 65 – 86.
- Shumskiy P.A. (1960) Density of glacier ice. *Journal of Glaciology*, **3** (27), 568 – 573.
- Smart C.C. (1992) Temperature compensation of electrical conductivity in glacial melt waters. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (128), 9 – 12.
- Smart C.C. (1996) Statistical evaluation of glacier boreholes as indicators of basal drainage systems. *Hydrological Processes*, **10**, 599 – 613.
- Smart C.C. (1983) The hydrology of the Castlegaurd karst, Columbia Ice fields, Alberta Canada. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **15** (4), 471 – 486.
- Smart C.C. and Ford D.C. (1983) The Castlegaurd karst, main ranges, Canadian Rocky Mountains. *Journal of Hydrology*, **61**, 193 – 197.
- Smart C.C. and Ketterling D.B. (1997) A low cost electrical conductivity profiler for glacier boreholes. *Journal of Glaciology*, **43** (144), 365 – 369.
- Smart C.C., Owens I.F., Lawson W. and Morris A.L. (2000) Exceptional ablation arising from rainfall-induced slush flows: Brewster Glacier, New Zealand. *Hydrological Processes*, **14**, 1045 – 1052.
- Smeets C., Duynkerke P.G., Vugts H.F. (1998) Turbulent characteristics of the stable boundary layer over a mid latitude glacier. Part 1: A combination of katabatic and large scale forcing. *Boundary Layer Meteorology*, **87**, 117 – 145.
- Smith S. and Burgess M. (2002) Scherrerville Permafrost temperature database. *Geological Survey of Canada, Natural Resources Canada, Contribution to CAPS2 and Global Geocryological Database*.
- Song M., Baker I. and Cole D.M. (2005) The effects of particles on dynamic recrystallization and fabric development of granular ice during creep. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (174), 377 – 382.
- Song M., Cole D.M. and Baker I. (2004) Initial experiments on the effects of particles at grain boundaries on the anelasticity and creep behavior of granular ice. *Annals of Glaciology*, **39**, 397 – 401.

REFERENCES

- Song M., Cole D.M. and Baker I. (2005b) Creep of granular ice with and without dispersed particles. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51** (173), 210 – 218.
- Sostmann H.E. and Metz P.D. (1992) Fundamentals of Thermometry Part VI: Thermistor thermometers. *The Isotech Journal of Thermometry*, **3** (2), 66 – 84.
- Souchez R.A. and Lemmens M. (1985) Subglacial carbonate deposition: an isotopic study of a present day case. *Paeleogeography, Paeleoclimatology and Paeleoecology*, **51** (1 – 4), 357 – 364.
- Souchez R.A. and Lemmens M.M. (1987) Solutes. In *Glacio-fluvial Sediment Transfer*. Gurnell A.M. and Clark M.J. (eds). Wiley and Sons. pp 285 – 303.
- Steffen K. and Box J. (2001) Surface climatology of the Greenland ice sheet: Greenland climate network 1995 – 1999. *Journal of Geophysical Research – Atmospheres*, **106** (D24), 33,951 – 33,964.
- Steffen K., Box j. and Abdalati W. (1996) Greenland climate network: GC-Net. *CRREL*, pp. 98 – 103. Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, Hanover.
- Steinemann S. (1954) Results of preliminary experiments on plasticity of ice crystals. *Journal of Glaciology*, **2**, 404 – 412.
- Steinemann S. (1958a) Resultats experimentaux sur la dynamique de la glace et leur correlation avec le movement et la peterographie des glaciers. *International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication No. 47*, 184 – 198.
- Steinemann S. (1958b) Thermodynamics and mechanics of ice at the melting point. Union Geodesique et Geophysique Internationale. Association Internationale d'Hydrologie Scientifique. Symposiym de Chamonix, 16 – 24 September, 1958, pp 254 – 265.
- Steinhart I.S. and Hart S.R. (1968) Calibration curves for thermistors. *Deep Sea Research*, **15**, 497 – 503.
- Stenborg T. (1973) Some view points on the internal drainage of glaciers. In *Hydrology of Glaciers, International Association of Scientific Hydrology Publication*, **95**, 117 – 129.
- Stone D.B, Clarke G.K.C. and Blake E.W. (1993) Subglacial measurement of turbidity and electrical conductivity. *Journal of Glaciology*, **39** (132), 415 – 420.
- Stone D.B. and Clarke G.K.C. (1996) In situ measurements of basal water quality and pressure as an indicator of the character of subglacial drainage systems. *Hydrological Processes*, **10** (4), 615 – 628.
- Strasser U., Corripio J., Pellicciotti F., Burlando P., Brock B. and Funk M. (2004) Spatial and temporal variability of meteorological variables at Haut Glacier d'Arolla (Switzerland) during the ablation season 2001: Measurements and simulations. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **109**, Article number D03103.
- Streten N.A and Wendler G. (1968) The mid summer heat balance of an Alaskan maritime Glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **7** (51), 431 – 440.
- Sturm M. and Holmgren J. (1993) Rain – Induced water percolation in snow as detected using heat flux transducers. *Water Resources Research*, **29** (7), 2323 – 2334.
- Sturm M. and Johnson J.B. (1987) Measurements of the thermal conductivity of depth hoar. *Eos Trans. AGU*, **68** (44), 1271.
- Sturm M. and Johnson J.B. (1992) Thermal conductivity measurements of depth hoar. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **97** (B2), 2129 – 2139.
- Sturm M., Holmgren J., Konig M. and Morris K. (1997). The thermal conductivity of seasonal snow. *Journal of Glaciology*, **43** (143), 26 – 41.
- Suter S., Laternser M., Haeberli W., Frauenfelder R. and Hoelzle M. (2001) Cold firn and ice of high altitude glaciers in the Alps: measurements and distribution modelling. *Journal of Glaciology*, **47** (156), 85 – 96.

REFERENCES

- Sverdrup H.U. (1935) The temperature of firn on Isachen's Plateau and general conclusions regarding the temperature of the glaciers on West Spitsbergen. *Geografiska Annaler*, **17** (1-2), p.71.
- Sverdrup H.U. (1936) The eddy covariance of the air over a smooth snow field – Results of the Norwegian – Swedish Spitzbergen Expedition in 1934. *Geofys. Publication* No. **11** (7), 1 – 69.
- Swinzow, G.K. (1962) Investigation of the shear zones in the ice sheet margin, Thule area, Greenland, *Journal of Glaciology*, **43** (32), 215 – 229.
- Swissinfo. (2006a) Sunshine replaces snow in the Alps. Swissinfo.org, Published 27/12/2006, <http://www.swissinfo.org/eng/swissinfo.html?siteSect=105&sid=7384899> [accessed 12/05/07].
- Swissinfo. (2006b) Hopes of a snowy winter ski season melt away. Swissinfo.org, Published 04/12/2006, <http://www.swissinfo.org/eng/swissinfo.html?siteSect=105&sid=7316986> [accessed 12/05/07].
- Takeuchi. Naruse R. and Skvarca P. (1996) Annual air temperature measurement and ablation estimate at Moreno Glacier, Patagonia. *Bulletin of Glaciological Research*, **14**, 23 – 28.
- Tangborn W.V., Mayo L.R., Scully D.R. and Krimmel R.M. (1977) Combined ice and water balances of Maclure Glacier, California, South Cascade Glacier, Washington and Wolverine and Gulkana glaciers Alaska, 1967 hydrologic year. *US Geological Survey Professional Paper*, **715** – B, 20p.
- Taras B., Sturm M. and Liston G.E. (2002) Snow ground interface temperatures in the Kuparuk River Basin, Arctic Alaska: Measurements and model. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, **3** (4), 377 – 394.
- Taylor J.R. (1997) *An introduction to error analysis: The study of uncertainties in physical measurements*. University Science books. Sausalito. 327pp.
- Thermometrics Inc. (2004) NTC Thermistors [online]. Available from <http://www.thermometrics.com/assets/images/ntcnotes.pdf> [Accessed 21/01/04].
- Thomas R. H., Abdalati W., Frederick E., Krabill W. B., Manizade S. and Steffen K. (2003) Investigation of surface melting and dynamic thinning on Jakobshavn Isbrae glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **49**, 231 – 239.
- Thomas R., Rignot E., Casassa G., Kanagaratnam P., Acuna C., Akins T., Brecher H., Frederick E., Gogineni P., Krabill W., Manizade S., Ramamoorthy H., Rivera A., Russell R., Sonntag J., Swift R., Yungel J. and Zwally J. (2004) Accelerated sea-level rise from West Antarctica. *Science*, **306** (5694), 255 – 258.
- Thorsteinsson T., Waddington E.D., Taylor K.C., Alley R.B. and Blankenship D.D. (1999) Strain enhancement at Dye 3, Greenland. *Journal of Glaciology*, **45** (150), 338 – 344.
- Thwaites R.J., Wilson J.L. and McCray A. (1984) Relationship between borehole closure and crystal fabrics in Antarctic ice core from Cape Folger. *Journal of Glaciology*, **30** (105), 171 – 179.
- Tison J.-L. and Lorrain R.D. (1987) A mechanical and basal ice layer formation involving major ice fabric changes. *Journal of Glaciology*, **33** (113), 47 – 50.
- Tison J.-L. and Hubbard B. (2000) Ice crystallographic evolution at a temperate glacier: Glacier de Tsanfleuron, Switzerland. In Maltman A.J., Hubbard B. and Hambrey M.J. (eds). *Deformation of Glacial Materials*. Geological Society, London, *Special Publications*, **176**, 23 – 38.
- Tranter M., Sharp M.J., Brown G.H., Willis I.C., Hubbard B., Neilsen M.K., Smart C.C., Gordon S., Tulley M. and Lamb H.R. (1997) Variability in the chemical composition of insitu subglacial melt waters. *Hydrological Processes*, **11**, 59 – 77.

REFERENCES

- University of Swansea, Glaciology. Online. Effect of the Spatial Variability of Physical Parameters on the Rheology of Temperate glaciers and their response to Climate Change. <http://ralph.swan.ac.uk/glaciology/projects/tsan/spring2004.html> [accessed 03/04/06].
- Untersteiner N. (1961) On the mass and heat budget of Arctic Sea ice. *Arch. Meteorol. Geophys. Bioklimatol. Series A*, **12** (2), 151 – 182.
- Vallon M., Petit J.R. and Fabre B. (1976) Study of an ice core to the bedrock in the accumulation zone of an alpine glacier. *Journal of Glaciology*, **17** (75), 13 – 28.
- Van de Wal R.S.W., Oerlemans J. and Van der Hage J.C. (1992) A study of ablation variations on the tongue of Hintereisferner, Austrian Alps. *Journal of Glaciology*, **38** (130), 319 – 324.
- Van de Wal R.S.W., Mulvaney R., Isaksson E., Moore J.C., Pinglot J.F., Pohjola V. and Thomassen M.P.A. (2002) Reconstruction of the historical temperature trend from measurements in a medium length borehole on the Lomonosovfonna Plateau, Svalbard. *Annals of Glaciology*, **35**, 371 – 378.
- Van den Broeke M. (1996) Characteristics of the lower ablation zone of the West Greenland ice sheet for energy balance modelling. *Annals of Glaciology*, **23**, 160 – 166.
- Van den Broeke M., Reijmer C., Van As D., De Wal R.V. and Oerlemans J. (2005) Seasonal cycles of Antarctic surface energy balance from automatic weather stations. *Annals of Glaciology*, **41**, 131 – 139.
- Van der Avoird E. and Duynkerke P.G. (1999) Turbulence in a katabatic flow. Does it resemble turbulence in stable boundary layers over flat surfaces? *Boundary Layer Meteorology*, **92**, 39 – 66.
- Van der Veen C.J. (1999) *Fundamentals of Glacier Dynamics*. Rotterdam, A.A.Balkema.
- Van Dusen M.S. (1929) Thermal conductivity of non metallic solids. In Washburn E.W., West C.J., Dorsey N.E., Bichowsky F.R. and Ring M.D., (eds) *International critical tables of numerical data, physics, chemistry and technology*. Vol **4**, New York, McGraw – Hill, 216 – 217.
- Van Ommen T.D., Morgan V.I., Jacka T.H., Woon S. and Elcheikh A. (1999) Near surface temperatures in the Dome Summit South (Law Dome, East Antarctica) borehole. *Annals of Glaciology*, **29**, 141 – 144.
- Vincent C. and Vallon M. (1997) Meteorological controls on glacier mass balance: empirical relations suggested by measurements on glacier de Sarennes, France. *Journal of Glaciology*, **43** (143), 131 – 137.
- Vivian R. (1980) The nature of the ice – rock interface: the results of investigation on 20, 000 m² of the rock bed of temperate glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **25** (92), 267 – 277.
- Vivian R. and Bocquet G. (1973) Subglacial cavitation phenomena under the Glacier d' Argentiere, Mont Blanc, France. *Journal of Glaciology*, **12** (66), 439 – 451.
- Wager A.C. and Jamieson A.W. (1977) Energy exchange at a glacier surface: an alternative to aerodynamic methods of measurement. *Journal of Glaciology*, **18** (78), 47 – 55.
- Walcek C.J. (1994) Cloud cover and its relationship to relative humidity during a spring mid latitude cyclone. *Monthly Weather Reviews*, **122**, 1021 – 1035.
- Walder J.S. and Fowler A. (1994) Channelized subglacial drainage over a deformable bed. *Journal of Glaciology*, **40** (134), 3 – 15.
- Wallen C.C. (1948) Glacio-meteorological investigations on the Karsa glacier in Swedish Lapland, 1942 – 1948. *Geografiska Annaler, Arg.* **30**, HT. 3 – 4, 451 – 672.

REFERENCES

- Warren S.G. (1982) Optical properties of snow. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space Physics*, **20** (1), 67 – 89.
- Warren S.G. and Wiscombe W.J. (1980) A model for spectral albedo of snow II: Snow containing atmospheric aerosols. *Journal of Atmospheric Science*, **37** (12), 2734 – 2745.
- Washburn A.L. (1979) *Geocryology. A survey of Periglacial Processes and Environments*. London. Arnold, 406 pp.
- Webb E.K. (1965) Aerial microclimate. *American Meteorological Society Agricultural Meteorological Monograph*, **6** (28), 27 – 58.
- Weertman J. (1957) On the sliding of glaciers. *Journal of Glaciology*, **3** (21), 33 – 38.
- Weertman J. (1961) Mechanism for the formation of inner moraines found near the edge of cold ice caps and ice sheets. *Journal of Glaciology*, **3**, 965 – 978.
- Weertman J. (1972) General theory of water flow at the base of a glacier or ice sheet. *Reviews of Geophysics and Space physics*, **10** (1), 287 – 333.
- Weertman J. (1973) Creep of ice. In *Physics and Chemistry of Ice*. E. Whalley, S.J. Jones and L.W. Gold, pp. 320-337.
- Weller G. (1968) The annual heat energy transfer above and inside Antarctic blue ice. Union de Geodesie et Geophysique Internationale. Association Internationale d'Hydrologie Scientifique. Assemblee general de Berne, 25 Sept – 7 Oct. 1967. [Comission des Neiges et Glaces]. Rapports et discussions. P 417 – 28.
- Wendler G. and Streten N.A. (1969) A short term heat balance study on a Coast Range glacier. *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, **77** (6), 68 – 77.
- Wendler G. and Weller G. (1974) A heat balance study on McCall glacier, Brooks Range, Alaska: a contribution to the international hydrological decade. *Journal of Glaciology*, **13** (67), 13 – 26.
- West J.L., Rippin D.M., Murray T., Mader H.M. and Hubbard B. (in press) Dielectric Permittivity Measurements on Ice Cores: Implications for Interpretation of Radar to Yield Glacial Unfrozen Water Content. *Journal of Environmental and Engineering Geophysics*.
- Wigley T.M.L. (1967) Non steady flow through a porous medium and cave breathing. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **72**, 3199 – 3205.
- Wildberger A. (1981) Zur Hydrogeologie des karstes im Rawil-Gebiet. *Beitrage zur Geologie der Schweiz – Hydrogeologie*, **27**, 275 pp.
- Williams G.P. (1971) Predicting the data of lake ice break up. *Water Resources Research*, **7** (1), 323 – 333.
- Williams M. (2006) Snow hydrology (GEOG 4321): Energy Balance. University of Colorado.
- Williams M.W., Cline D., Hartmann M. and Bardsley T. (1999) Data for snowmelt model development, calibration and verification at an alpine site, Colorado Front Range. *Water Resources Research*, **35**, 10, 3205 – 3209.
- Willis I.C., Arnold N.S. and Brock B.W. (2002) Effect of snow pack removal on energy balance, melt and runoff in a small Supraglacial catchment. *Hydrological Processes*, **16**, 2721 – 2749.
- Willis I.C., Mair D., Hubbard B., Nienow P., Fischer U.H. and Hubbard A. (2003) Seasonal variations in ice deformation and basal motion across the tongue of Haut Glacier d' Arolla, Switzerland. *Annals of Glaciology*, **36**, 157 – 167.
- Wiscombe W.J. and Warren S.G. (1980) A model for spectral albedo of snow I: Pure snow. *Journal of Atmospheric Science*, **37** (12), 2712 – 2733.
- Wolff E.W. and Mulvaney R. (1988) The location of impurities in Antarctic ice. *Annals of Glaciology*, **11**, 194 – 197.

REFERENCES

- Woo M.K. and Fitzharris B.B. (1992) Reconstruction of mass balance variations for Franz Josef Glacier, New Zealand, 1913 – 1989. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, **24** (4), 281 – 290.
- Yen Y. C. (1962) Effective thermal conductivity of ventilated snow. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **67** (3), 1091 – 1098.
- Yen Y.C. (1965) Effective thermal conductivity and water vapour diffusivity of naturally compacted snow. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, **70** (8), 1821 – 1825.
- Yen Y.C. (1995) Sensible heat flux measurements near a cold surface. *CRREL Report* **95** – 22.
- Yuen D.A, Saari M.R. and Schubert G. (1986) Explosive growth of shear heating instabilities in the down slope creep of ice sheets. *Journal of Glaciology*, **32** (112), 259 – 268.
- Zagorodnov V., Nagornov O. and Thompson L.G. (2006) Influence of air temperature on a glacier's active layer temperature. *Annals of Glaciology*. **43**, 285 – 291.
- Zanotti F., Endrizzi S., Bertoldi G. and Rigon R. (2004) The GEOTOP snow module. *Hydrological Processes*, **18**, 3667 – 3679.
- Zemp M., Frauenfelder R., Haeberli W. and Hoelzle M. (2005) Worldwide glacier mass balance measurements: general trends and first results of the extraordinary year 2003 in Central Europe. in XIII Glaciological Symposium, Shrinkage of the Glacosphere: Facts and Analyses, St Petersburg, Russia. Data of Glaciological Studies, Moscow, Russia. pp. 3 -12.
- Zhongyuan B. and Xinzhi Y. (1985) Energy exchange and its influence factors on mountain glaciers in west China. *Annals of Glaciology*, **6**, 154 – 157.
- Zwally H.J., Giovinetto M.B., Li J., Cornejo H.G., Beckley M.A., Brenner A.C., Saba J.L. and Yi D. (2006) Mass changes of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets and shelves and contributions to sea level rise: 1992 – 2002. *Journal of Glaciology*, **51**, 509 – 527.